

**12th International Conference on
Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries**

COMPIT' 13

Cortona, 15-17 April 2013

Edited by Volker Bertram

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12th International Conference on Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries, Cortona, 15-17 April 2013, Hamburg, Technische Universität Hamburg-Harburg, 2013, ISBN 978-3-89220-663-7

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Schriftenreihe Schiffbau
Schwarzenbergstraße 95c
D-21073 Hamburg
<http://www.tuhh.de/vss>

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Advanced Simulations for Offshore Industry Applications

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Abstract

An overview of simulations for assorted advanced engineering analyses in the offshore industry is given, focussing on the benefits for the business processes of the customers. The analyzed structures include fixed and floating offshore platforms, related ships such as supply vessels, and selected equipment. The analysis looks at the main operational problems such as ensuring low environmental impact, high availability and compliance with regulations, as well as promoting innovative designs and procedures. The role of assorted advanced simulations (structure, noise & vibration, fluid dynamics, aerodynamics, installation simulations, etc) in this context is illustrated by case studies taken predominantly from the experience of GL Group with a strong focus on industry projects and recent research projects.

1. Introduction

Traditionally, design and operation of ships and offshore structures have been based on experience. This is still true to some extent, but increasingly we rely on “virtual experience” from dedicated simulations. Scope and depth of these simulations guiding our decisions have developed very dynamically over the past decade. In previous publications, we have focussed on the technical aspects of simulations, *Bertram and Couser (2007)*, *Bertram (2009a,b)*, *Peric and Bertram (2011)*. In the present paper, we want to focus instead on the benefits of simulations from the customer’s point of view. The “customer” may be the designer, builder or operator of an offshore installation, or any subcontractor, i.e. any business unit outsourcing services based on the special competence of simulation experts. From a customer perspective, simulations serve to support business processes through

- Ensuring low environmental impact
- Ensuring high availability / utilisation
- Promoting innovative designs and procedures
- Ensuring compliance

These items are discussed in the following sections in the context of offshore installations and their supporting fleet of ships for installation, maintenance and supply.

2. Ensuring low environmental impact

Accidents like the “Exxon Valdez” and the “Deepwater Horizon” have had profound impact on the offshore industry. This does not only concern direct liability claims, but also indirect business impact due to impaired image with other stakeholders, most notably customers. Safety, also environmental safety, concerns both design and operation.

Designs should be sufficiently strong to avoid problems in usual operation, including rare events. International and national regulations as well as classification society rules are taken as guidelines for what has to be assumed as worst-case scenario, e.g. “the highest wave to be expected in this region within 100 years”. The specification of such worst-case scenarios and associated probabilities gains in importance within the context of risk-based design, but will not be discussed further here. Industry practice is that the simulation expert follows user specifications or common practice. In most cases, the largest uncertainty in the structural assessment comes through the assumed loads. Detailed structural analyses therefore require generally dedicated other simulations to prescribe load distributions (varying in space and time):

- Long-term spectral distributions of wave loads, based on linear seakeeping methods, for fatigue analyses, e.g. discussed in *Bertram (2011)*, *Bertram and Gualeni (2011)*. For many seakeeping issues, linear analyses (assuming small wave height) are appropriate and frequently applied due to their efficiency. Linear approaches are very fast and allow thus the investigation of many parameters (frequency, wave direction, ship speed, etc.). They may also be used for most mooring applications, estimates for second-order drift forces, and for multi-body analyses in moderate waves.
- Extreme wave scenarios, including freak waves, require free-surface RANSE (Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations) simulations, Fig.1, e.g. *El Moctar et al. (2007)*. Such free-surface RANSE simulations are generally employed for cases with strongly nonlinear geometries of waves and object. The computations require usually parallel computer hardware and CFD (computational fluid dynamics) experts. Combining intelligently linear frequency-domain methods with nonlinear time-domain simulations allows exploiting the respective strengths of each approach. For example, the linear analysis identifies the most critical parameter combination for a ship response. The subsequent RANSE simulation determines motions, loads and free surface (green water on deck).
- Impact loads, using free-surface RANSE solvers. Impact loads appear for slamming and sloshing analyses, Fig.2, Fig.3, *Bertram et al. (2003)*, *Peric et al. (2007)*, *Morch et al. (2009)*. The approach has been extensively validated. Mostly, these simulations assume weak fluid-structure interaction, i.e. the fluid dynamic simulation specifies the loads for the structural finite-element analyses (FEA), but the deformation is not considered for the CFD simulation. However, strong fluid-structure interaction considering also the effect of the structural response on the fluid dynamics is feasible, *Oberhagemann et al. (2008)*, *El Moctar et al. (2011)*. Applications include springing and whipping for ships, and sloshing for tanks with very flexible membranes.

Fig.1: Simulation of platform in extreme waves

Fig.2: Sloshing simulation

Fig.3: Simulation of offshore free-fall lifeboat, *Morch et al. (2009)*

- As a special case, ice loads may be considered. Here, simulations of offshore structures in brash ice consider e.g. the loads for dynamic positioning of drill ships, *Wang and Derradji-Aouat (2011)*. LS-DYNA, a finite-element code usually used for ship-ship collision analyses can be applied for these simulations. *Vroegrijk (2011)* employs the commercial CFD code StarCCM+ with the Discrete Element Method (DEM) option to model brash ice flows around an obstacle. But more frequently dedicated software is used, Fig.4, e.g. *Puntigliano (2003)*, *Liu et al. (2010)*, *Lubbad and Løset (2011)*.

Fig.4: Numerical ice breaking, *Puntigliano (2003)* (left) and *Lubbad and Løset (2011)* (right)

Strength analyses have reached a mature state and are widely applied in the design of offshore structures to ensure sufficiently strong designs. Finite-element analyses (FEA) for global strength within the elastic material domain are widely applied to ships, offshore structures, and subsystems (e.g. gearboxes, engines, cranes, risers, pipelines, etc.). Particularly for offshore platforms and FPSOs, frequently more sophisticated analyses are performed, such as fatigue analyses or collision analyses, Fig.5. Collision analyses play a major role in (passive) safety against oil spills. Based on extensive experience with such simulations, Germanischer Lloyd provided as first classification society a standard for evaluation and approval of alternative solutions for design and construction of tankers, *Zhang et al. (2004)*. Today, collision analyses are regularly performed for ships with class notation “COLL” and for offshore wind farms where authorities require proof of collision friendliness.

Fig.5: Collision analysis using nonlinear finite-element methods

Also, operational guidelines may be based on simulations. This concerns in particular accident response procedures. Progress in simulation techniques and computer hardware have led to a multitude of applications that were previously not possible at all or approximated by more expensive and/or less accurate model tests, e.g.:

- Towing of damaged structures
 After an accident, damaged ships or offshore structures often must be towed to repair sites. Typically, the initial accident will impair the strength of the structure, but may also affect residual freeboard and stability. This must be considered for the towing. CFD simulations for towed systems manoeuvring in waves represent the state-of-the-art approach for the hydrodynamic issues, Fig.6. FEA simulations determine stress distributions in damaged structures, considering the actual hull structure condition including corrosion.
- Oil spills
 Multi-phase flows, i.e. flows with several fluids of differing density and viscosity, can be simulated by all major commercial CFD codes. For oil spills, oil and water are considered, sometimes also air (when waves or sloshing plays a role). *Vasconcellos and Alho (2012)* give a typical application for an oil spill in an FPSO, Fig.7.

Fig.6: Tug-tow system in waves

Fig.7: Oil spill simulation, *Vasconcellos and Alho (2012)*

Fig.8: Mesh for offshore superstructure and CFD simulated flow around it, *Peric and Bertram (2011)*

Fig.9: Gas dispersion in closed working areas after (potential) leak

Fig.10: Temperature distribution in supersonic gas leak

- **Gas dispersion**
Aerodynamic flows around offshore structures can be computed in great detail, Fig.8, with or without added smoke or gas. From a simulation point of view, gas dispersion is very similar to fluid dispersion. The same techniques and software can be applied, albeit with different density and viscosity. In addition, for gas (including smoke) dispersion, thermal processes and thermal buoyancy play usually a significant role and must be reflected in the simulation model. Such simulations may concern external flows, typically near crew quarters or helidecks, or internal flows in closed working or living areas, Fig.9. They may also cover extreme temperatures or speeds, including supersonic, explosive leaks, Fig.10.
- **Disposal /cleaning operations**
Multi-phase flow simulations have been used for decision support in cleaning offshore structures, in regular operation or in preparation for disposal, Fig.11. Simulations identify for example stagnant flow regions in tanks or the effectiveness of cleaning procedures.

Fig.11: Simulation of stagnant or low-velocity regions in tank (sediment accumulation)

3. Ensuring high availability

Offshore structures usually have much higher down-time costs than cargo ships. Consequently, much higher focus is placed on ensuring high availability of these structures. High availability is mainly achieved through three levers, “design for availability” (system robustness), “monitoring for availability” (condition based maintenance to avoid downtime), and fast “trouble-shooting”. The role of simulations in this context will be discussed in the following:

- **Design for availability**
Failure mode and effect analyses (FMEA) or related formal risk assessment techniques are widely applied to offshore systems and subsystems. A “system” in this sense is not just the technical object, but includes also operational procedures. Operational guidelines for risk mitigation contribute significantly to ensure high availability. A typical example are specifications for operational limits (sea states) for installation, maintenance and operation, both of offshore installations (platforms, FPSOs, etc), and offshore supply vessels. Such operational limits are determined based e.g. on seakeeping simulations. The appropriate simulation tools depend on required accuracy, geometry of the object (slender monohull, catamaran, large dis-

placement structure, hydrodynamically transparent jack-up structure, etc) and speed through water, *Bertram and Gualeni (2011)*. Increasingly, viscous CFD simulations, which can also simulate breaking waves, are employed partially or fully in these analyses. For a jack-up installation ship, Fig.12, we computed the forces in waves just before touch-down of the jack-up legs. The simulations were performed using AQWA, a commercial Green function method seakeeping code. However, AQWA requires force coefficients for viscous force components. These can be specified using experience or semi-empirical formulae (where applicable), or (as in our case) using RANSE simulations in pre-processing once, before a wide parameter space is analysed using the fast potential-flow seakeeping code. Such a hybrid approach combines thus accuracy with time and cost efficiency.

Fig.12: Jack-up platform in waves during touch-down; hybrid computation with AQWA and STAR CCM+

Fig.12: CFD simulations give load histories for fatigue strength analyses on bilge keels

Another typical application concerns fatigue strength. Here FEA simulations, with load spectra that may be tailored to local regions, determine fatigue life of structures with considerable safety margins to account for unavoidable random variations in structural fatigue. For example, in one project the focus was on the fatigue strength of bilge keels for an FPSO. The flows which induce the fatigue loads featured massive vortex generation, Fig.12, and were not properly captured at model scale. Hence the complete ship including bilge keels was modelled and simulated in waves using a free-surface RANSE code. The load histories were then used in finite-element analyses for fatigue strength assessment, guiding the redesign of the bilge keels.

The assessment of critical structural details during the design stage allows early, thus cost-effective, re-design. Similar analyses are highly recommended for deployed offshore structures if original design life is planned to be exceeded.

- Monitoring for availability

In some applications, accepting degradation and planned replacement of system elements is more economic than designing for complete avoidance of replacements. This concerns machinery (e.g. filters) as well as structures, where corrosion is often accepted as “unavoidable”. In these cases, condition based maintenance scheme monitor the condition of system elements with the aim of having timely replacement and no unscheduled down-time.

Condition assessment schemes for steel hulls of ships and offshore structures are not new. However, more recently initiatives have started to combine hull condition monitoring systems and structural FEA models, maximizing the data model re-use, thus reducing response time and costs for users, *Wilken et al. (2011)*. Within this approach, the global strength of partially corroded structures can be assessed by FEA, determining much more accurately the residual strength of a structure with locally heterogeneous corrosion. These results are the basis for risk based inspection schemes for offshore structures, equipment or FPSOs, *Stadie-Frohboes et al. (2008)*.

- Trouble-shooting

For cylindrical structures, the vortex-induced vibrations can be investigated using simple, semi-empirical formulae. For complex systems like ships or FPSOs, there are many degrees of freedoms for local and global vibrations and these may be excited by vortex shedding at many local structures, typically at appendages or hull openings. The traditional trial-and-error approach to localise the source of vortex-induced vibrations may today be replaced by a more time and cost efficient search guided by CFD and vibration analyses, *Menzel et al. (2008)*. In one project, the problematic vibrations had a distinct frequency that ruled out engine, propeller or sea waves as exciting source. Unsteady RANSE simulations gave then the vortex formation and associated pressure time histories at all appendages, Fig.13. The frequency of the pressure fluctuations at the outer propeller shaft matched the frequency of the vibrations measured onboard. The stern part was modified adding streamlined fairings between the propeller shafts and the underside of the hull, Fig.14. This resulted in a much smoother flow in this region, eliminating the vibrations completely.

Fig.13: CFD simulation for vortex induced vibrations at appendages

Fig.14: Redesign of problematic appendage

4. Enabling innovative designs and procedures

The offshore industry has been (by necessity) much more innovative than the shipbuilding industry. Often, considerable benefits can be reaped by being “the first”, the first to master larger drilling depth,

the first to master arctic exploration, etc. Innovation unlocks new riches, but also involves the risk of venturing into technologically unknown territory. Whenever we leave our “comfort zone” of experience moving to new designs or procedures, simulations give us most valuable insight and “virtual experience”, ensuring not only that envisioned concepts are feasible, but also efficient and safe. This approach applies to installations, individual equipment or procedures alike as illustrated by the following examples:

- System design

Simulations play a role in accelerating progress in systems design. For example, CFD has been applied for type approval of innovative ballast water management systems, *Zorn et al. (2012)*. If treatment is based on chemical approaches, rapid and effective mixing of the chemical component with the ballast water is vital to achieve a homogeneous concentration of the biocide. Simulations can be a valuable tool for type approval of new systems. In one case, FutureShip simulated the mixing of chlorine and ballast water in pipes during ballasting. The CFD simulations were used to determine the required pipe length of the mixing zone to ensure homogeneous mixing. Simulations showed that mixing was inefficient in the initial design. Very simple and cost-effective modifications of the inlet geometry increased the turbulence level significantly, resulting in a much shorter pipe length for complete mixing. Fig.15 shows computed streamlines and chlorine concentration in the mixing pipe resulting from one such simulation. The authorities accepted the simulations as engineering proof for type approval.

Fig.15: Pipe flow investigating turbulent mixing of two fluids

Fig.16: Flow analysis for OSV hull optimization

Fig.17: Virtual seakeeping comparison of two OPV designs, *Harries et al. (2012)*

- Global platform / hull design

Simulations play a role in accelerating global platform / hull design. For example, modern design practice employs CFD and formal optimisation to derive optimum hull shapes, *Abt and Harries (2008)*, *Hochkirch und Bertram (2012)*. Similar applications are known for offshore

platforms and appendages. Parametric shape variation, advanced optimisation models and large parallel computer hardware have given significant design improvements in many projects in our experience. OSV (offshore supply vessels) are good candidates for formal hull optimisation, but fuel efficiency, stability, and seakeeping must be reflected in the optimisation model to find good trade-offs, Fig.16, Fig.17, *Harries et al. (2012)*.

- Operational procedures

Simulations play also a role in innovative operational procedures. For example, discrete event simulations (DES) can be used to instigate different scenarios in the installation of offshore structures. Offshore wind farms require installation of many, many wind turbines. DES allows detailed insight and quantitative planning for the installation of such offshore wind farms (or similar applications), Fig.18, *Steinhauer (2011)*: Different alternative procedures of the installation process can be modelled and evaluated. Parameters of the installation process can be varied, e.g. the type of the installation vessel including its attributes or the strategies for supply or assembly. Constraints (like weather and sea state) can be considered in the simulation model. By evaluating different alternative scenarios, the total installation process can be optimized with respect to shortest installation times and highest robustness of the schedule.

Fig.18: Simulation of offshore wind farm installation, *Steinhauer (2011)*

5. Ensuring compliance

The offshore industry, in particular the oil & gas sector, is under tight scrutiny by authorities and pressure groups alike. High-profile accidents invariably lead to additional regulations. Simulations play here a vital role, particularly in the design and approval phase. By now, simulations are widely accepted by national authorities as “engineering proof” of compliance.

Typical analyses performed to obtain approval for installation concern:

- Formal risk assessment

Formal risk assessment procedures, based on FMEA (failure mode and effect analysis) or similar approaches, have been established in the offshore industry much longer than in ship-building and ship operation. Risk assessment procedures combine typically probabilistic frameworks with dedicated simulations, especially for the “effect” part of an FMEA. Examples are collision analyses, damage stability analyses and evacuation analyses. Germanischer Lloyd has developed an integrated methodology, combining fire simulations, evacuation simulation and Event Tree Analysis for risk assessment, *Petersen and Voelker (2003)*.

- Occupational health and safety
International regulations (e.g. ILO (International Labour Organisation)), industrial agreements and company guidelines address various aspects of occupational health and safety. The ILO Maritime Labour Convention of 2006 is expected to become obligatory by 2013, but has already noticeable impact on many building specifications. One of the most important changes of the Convention addresses noise and vibrations levels in crew accommodation and work spaces. Three-dimensional finite-element analyses are the standard choice for maritime vibration analyses today, Fig.19.

For structure-borne noise, the standard FEA approach is impossible due to excessive computational requirements. However, since information is required only averaged over a frequency band, we can use a far more efficient approach based on statistical energy analysis (SEA). Validation with full-scale measurements shows that the accuracy of this approach is sufficient for the frequency range between 80 Hz and 4000 Hz, *Wilken et al. (2004)*. Offshore applications concern living and working spaces of crews, both on ships and offshore platforms, Fig.20.

Fig.19: Vibration analysis for an OSV

Fig.20: Structure-borne noise analysis for jack-up structure in transit

- Fires
For fire simulations, zone models and CFD tools are employed in practice. Zone models are suitable for examining more complex, time-dependent scenarios involving multiple compartments and levels, Fig.21, but numerical stability can be a problem for scenarios involving multi-level ship domains, HVAC systems and for post-flashover conditions. CFD models can yield detailed information about temperatures, heat fluxes, and species concentrations, Fig.22. However, the time penalty of this approach still makes CFD unfeasible for long periods of real time or for large computational domains. Nevertheless, applications have graduated to more complex industry applications for maritime structures, *Bertram et al. (2004)*.

Fig.21: Zonal fire simulation for cabin and corridor

Fig.22: CFD simulation for fire

- Evacuation simulation

Simulations become complex if human behaviour must be included automatically, as in the case of traffic flow simulations, Fig.23. State-of-the-art are simulations that couple discrete event simulations (DES) with simple expert systems for the decision strategies of each simulated human in the evacuation. Germanischer Lloyd and TraffGo have developed the software AENEAS for this purpose, *Petersen et al. (2003)*. Within AENEAS, the ship or offshore habitat is represented by a simplified grid of different cell types (accessible floor, doors, stairs, obstacles/walls), Fig.24. Humans are represented by simple expert systems, so-called intelligent agents. Once the model has been set up, the simulations are very fast, allowing typically 500 simulations within one hour, to gain a broad basis for statistical evaluation.

Fig.23: Evacuation analysis

Fig.24: Grid for AENEAS

More advanced simulation combine damage scenarios (flooding, fire) with evacuation and possibly risk assessment, e.g. *Petersen and Voelker (2003)*, *Pawling et al. (2012)*.

6. Conclusions

Simulations are, as shown, a powerful and versatile tool. The technological progress is rapid, both for hardware and software. Simulations for numerous applications now often aid decisions, sometimes 'just' for qualitative ranking of solutions, sometimes for quantitative 'optimization' of advanced engineering solutions. Continued validation feedback serves to improve simulation tools as well as it serves to build confidence.

However, advanced simulation software alone is not enough. The key to success is finding the right balance between level of detail and resources (time, man-power). This modelling requires expertise and experience. Only the symbiosis of software, hardware and experts unlocks the true value that advanced engineering services can offer.

Acknowledgement

Many colleagues at GL Group have supported this paper with their special expertise, supplying text and/or figures, namely (in alphabetical order) Bettar El Moctar, Karsten Hochkirch, Axel Köhlmoos, Holger Mumm, Jan Oberhagemann, Daniel Povel, Stefan Semrau, Gundula Stadie-Frohbös, Tobias Zorn. In addition, Dirk Steinhauer (Flensburger Shipyard) supplied figures.

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Use of Current Computer Simulation Technologies in the Development of Ship Control Systems

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Abstract

Recent automation achievements in the Russian shipbuilding apart, the situation with underwater vehicles can hardly be considered satisfactory. We believe the vessels still have the features to be improved by the implementation of advanced automated control systems. Some of the problems at hand can be solved within the main trends of ship control automation development. Among those is the production of virtual full-scale simulators for the development and debugging of onboard control systems as far as their algorithm packages and software are concerned. As far back as 1980s, basic principles of scaled-down control process simulation were developed. Then, the task was set to establish a facility for the development of unified underwater vehicle models and flexible software to be used not only for real-time parameter updates, but also for model modifications, for the comparative analysis of structural configurations and control algorithms, and the improvement feasibility expertise. The basis laid down by the Trapeznikov Institute of Control Sciences provided a selection of software tools to solve the above tasks. Central Design Bureau for Marine Engineering Rubin made use of the research simulator to work with individual issues of control over underwater vehicles. With the tools, full-scale workbenches and research simulators can be made to analyse and develop control algorithms for underwater vehicles operated in various regimes including emergencies, and for operator training. The report describes a practical case of using the research simulator to solve the above tasks: the production of a research simulator to examine and debug the algorithms to control hovering underwater vehicles.

1. Introduction

With the emergence of computers, the development and implementation of automated modelling for processes, dynamic calculations and control system synthesis have become one of the most significant challenges encountered by researchers. The systems for automation of dynamic calculations and modelling were first discussed practically at the same time when digital computers were introduced, which allowed to present solutions for various tasks in the shape of algorithms, with the answers conveniently output in a descriptive form. But a single task solved with a computer is not a solid reason to talk of automation in dynamic calculations.

For the automation, the most important characteristic is the availability of software tools, which allow collecting individual modules solving a smaller task into a single system for a task of a higher complexity level. Another important feature of modern dynamic process modelling systems is the most realistic exterior simulation of the object and environment where processes take place. In training applications, even sounds and vestibular effects are simulated to provide comprehensive representation of the surroundings. 3D representation and software tools that can reproduce the external situation from various viewpoints also play an important role.

Systems which have the above features are termed Virtual Dynamic Systems (VDS). They exist as software modules and only the computer operation makes them simulate effects on human senses similar to those that might be experienced by a person in reality; with that, virtual dynamic systems can also provide visual information about ongoing processes. VDS production encounters numerous problems. The production of VDS for various applications depends on three main factors, which also cause the difference in both the system functionalities and the service level. These factors are:

- Hardware
- Operating environment
- Object domain

In recent decades, the hardware has developed rapidly. The performance increased by almost an order every two years. The achievements in up-to-date operational systems, program languages and object-oriented software were as great.

Rather than in individual task-solving algorithms, the challenges of automation for dynamic computations are encountered with the interface convenient for a researcher to solve the task. It is VDS that actually ensure direct interference into the modelling process and update the problems to the researcher's desire, with the overall task-solving structure retained.

Modelling facilities available with large companies are basically made on the hardware / software principle and comprise a complicated system of computers, display devices and other components. They are connected into a local network, meant for individual objects and difficult to update. Moreover, they are usually meant to model and evaluate individual subsystems while most of modern underwater vehicles are objects with a complicated structure and it is crucial to study and evaluate their functioning as a whole and not on a by-system approach.

The unavailability of full-scale VDS, which could ensure an instant check of control laws inbuilt into the objects, and display their behaviour, often, causes incidents and non-standard situations during full-scale trials or in operation.

In research simulator production, turning from software / hardware principles to VDS, which allows modelling the behaviour of all sophisticated underwater vehicle systems in their interaction, a simple and visually comprehensive interface is of primary importance. It is even more so, as the research simulators shall be widely used not only for the development of structurally complicated underwater vehicle models, but also for the assessment of the behaviour and status of these models by various researches. The information shall be displayed by a virtual system in a most comprehensive manner, while control over systems and parameter setting shall be as close as possible to the operator actions in controlling the actual object.

In standard and non-standard situations, a virtual system shall display the object's status and environment, and highlight critical parameters. For example, for manoeuvring an underwater vehicle, the virtual model might be used to check whether the input parameters and the manoeuvre program are correct, and how the control system is capable to control the forces and moments occurring during the manoeuvre. Currently, it is not done in full scope, because the data obtained from models are output in a format suitable for the control system developer, but unsuitable for people who commission and operate the underwater vehicle. An expert, relying on his experience when controlling a simulated vehicle might anticipate a non-standard situation even if all the system parameters are within the limits.

Traditional ways to produce a VDS for an individual object are labour and cost intensive, and involve numerous highly qualified staff. It is reasonable to turn from software / hardware approach to the use of specialized tool environments, which enable even the developers and not only IT specialists to model the behaviour of all systems in their interaction in a sophisticated military or special engineering models, and do real-time re-adjustment.

Studies at the Trapeznikov Institute of Control Sciences between 2000 and 2010 permitted to solve some of theoretical problems connected with computer-aided dynamic system calculations, and validate the hierarchical structure of automation tools for dynamic analysis and control systems calculations. Procedures and algorithms were put forward to study stability parameters, to model objects and improve their parameters, etc.

The theoretical work made the basis in the development of various software packages for the control systems' analysis and synthesis. The latest, Research of Dynamic Systems (RDS), *Dorri and Roshchin (2008a,b)*, has exceeded similar well-known Russian and international products in many characteristics. In its properties, it is very close to VDS. The functionalities of the package are: generation of visual hierarchical block diagrams for control systems; use of standard blocks (from libraries) and blocks with automatically compiled models; coordination of multilevel interaction between the blocks and between the blocks and the system, etc. Based on the package, a desktop research simulator was produced for Rubin.

A major difference between training stations and the desktop research simulator produced by the Institute of Control Sciences for Rubin to fine-tune control tasks for modern propulsion systems on underwater vehicles is that the latter can be used for personal operator training and to validate control tasks at developing companies. The simulator does not require complicated equipment, or a special place. Operational experience with the simulator, obtained by Rubin while practising underwater vehicle control tasks and writing control instructions, proved its efficiency in the development and evaluation of control algorithms for underwater vehicles in special motion modes.

Application software similar to RDS includes:

- Software packages for simulation and synthesis of control systems (PC-MATLAB, Lab-View, MVTU)
- Supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) systems
- Mathematical packages (MathCAD Plus 6.0, Maple V R3)
- Computer-aided engineering systems for manufacturing processes

2. Computer-Aided Modelling Applicability

Competitive high-end machinery cannot emerge without the extensive use of test and trial equipment. Moreover, some problems have not found their solutions yet because the available facilities cannot ensure proper situation modelling.

Currently, computer-aided modelling is productively used in:

- Producing training simulators and object prototypes (aircraft, submarines, ships, etc.)
- Simulating conditions to enhance the operator's efficiency (this is of special importance for underwater vehicles where the external situation can be roughly simulated)
- Fine-tuning automatic control algorithms for products undergoing construction or retrofit
- Detailing model and its control system characteristics with consideration to full-scale trial results

The feasibility to detail the characteristics of the model is of special interest.

Modern methods of identification, recognition and filtering with consideration to the laws of physics describing transitional processes in the model ensure pretty close approximation between the object's and model's parameters. Figs.1 and 2 show how motion parameters of the underwater vehicle changing depth can almost be matched by adjusting the characteristics of the model. The results were obtained at the desktop research simulator produced with the use of the RDS software tool for Rubin.

The validity of the results obtained from the model and their correlation with field results is of crucial importance in making decisions at all life stages of objects under control.

Fig. 1: Motion parameters of the underwater vehicle while changing depth (Eta is simulated depth; a_H is depth recorded at field tests)

Fig. 2: Underwater vehicle motion parameters with simulated parameters updated

3. Example of Using RDS

3.1 Production of Efficient Algorithms for Safe Control of a Manoeuvring Underwater Vehicle

Research simulators made with RDS were used to make effective control algorithms for various applications, specifically, for modelling underwater vehicle subsystems. For example, to maintain an underwater vehicle's activity in a critical situation, there is a demand to provide efficient vehicle hovering, since if the power or propulsion fails it could fatally compromise the vehicle endurance. This might be an alternative to the surfacing of the underwater vehicle or its grounding, which cannot always be done.

Below, there is a description of a research simulator fragment to develop safe control algorithms for a hovering underwater vehicle.

The hovering control system block diagram is compiled with the RDS tool environment. The animation is done in the RDS in-built vector graphic editor, which is easy to handle: a developer should just draw a picture with a detail and align its coordinates (value, rotation angle, colour or visibility) with one of the coordinates in the system. The animation feature enables visual presentation of ongoing processes placing the RDS software alongside SCADA systems. We can actually talk about virtual models of controlled objects. To improve the parameters, there are special blocks and the interface which caters for several standard algorithms (enumeration, coordinate-wise descent, etc.) to find the best parameter values for the control system. Fig.3 shows how easy it is to make the customized blocks.

Fig. 3: Subtractive model to control the hovering system

The subtractive model view with Eulerian approximation is given in Fig.3, where step means calculation step size. The model is coded in C++, converted automatically into a required dll file and used in the research desk operation. This is very convenient, as a researcher is not required to have a high qualification in programming. He only has to know the subject and calculation algorithm.

The software package is capable of simulating systems represented as a set of interconnected modules. Each module can contain the calculation program that determines the interaction with other modules of the system and response to the user's actions. Groups of functionally related blocks can be united in composite blocks (subsystems) that may contain their own routine in addition to routines residing inside the subsystem of blocks.

An important RDS feature is the availability of visible and invisible layers and their configurations. The placement of blocks and links for different applications at different levels ensures streamlining of the diagram, thus making it easy to work with, as the diagram part not currently in use can be concealed at invisible levels.

Fig.4 shows screen shots of a research simulator made for the Rubin design bureau to study and compile manoeuvring programs for an underwater vehicle. Main control elements of the vehicle are shown: the control planes, tanks and propeller. There is a functionality in the research system to set control inputs, and to simulate control plane jamming and other incidents.

Fig. 4: Elements of the research system for the development of motion control algorithms for underwater vehicles

Fig.5: Heel and trim indicators and the sea bottom representation

Working as a model-generating server, a graphic station visualises the underwater vehicle motion in a 3D space with the representation method, which uses the state vector received via the LAN (local area network) from models in real time. The graphic station also receives signals from the vehicle control

systems. The modelling subsystem is developed for 3D visualization of the vehicle motion underwater. The visualization is computationally intensive and involves numerous data display technologies like complicated texture configuration, dynamic topographical generations, viewpoint changeover, etc. To meet the subsystem requirements, OpenGL software is used.

In the subsystems which simulate the underwater vehicle motion, OpenGL is used to produce templates to select geometrical dimensions, as well as colours and other characteristics of the underwater vehicle's spatial motion. They allow the data to be updated and refined interactively with the results visually displayed on the monitor screen. Fig.6 shows visualization examples of the surroundings and devices displaying the spatial position of the underwater vehicle. The devices rendering the spatial position of the underwater vehicle are similar to those used in aviation.

Fig.6: Sea bottom representation device. General view

3.2 Depth Control for a Hovering Underwater Vehicle

Underwater vehicles (research vehicles both manned and unmanned) are usually controlled with horizontal planes and/or ballast water with the use of the hovering tank. At usual - very low – speeds, ballasting is the main control method, normally controlled with regard to the signals of the mismatch between the vehicle's depth and vertical speed. The vehicle's own residual buoyancy depends on two factors:

- Pressure hull volume, which changes with the change of the vehicle's diving depth
- Vertical variations of sea water density

Pressure hull volume change is normally pre-defined and can be set. Vertical variations of sea water density can be found by calculations with the use of current hydrological data on sea water parameters like temperature, salinity (electrical conduction) and pressure (depth). Instrumentation collecting hydrological data onboard the underwater vehicle provides the option to input into the control equipment an additional control signal, which responds to the water density change to improve the vertical motion control. Thus the use of the information on sea water density provides more reliable and controllable underwater vehicle manoeuvring. The research system was used to model underwater vehicle behaviour to produce algorithms to control hovering.

Fig. 7: Fragments of the research system to develop control algorithms for a hovering underwater vehicle

Several factors affect the underwater vehicle control stability. These are external and internal disturbances like changes in the vehicle's weight and buoyancy during horizontal sailing and manoeuvring, as well as control efficiency of the planes and hovering tank. Most prominent are:

- Mismatch between the buoyancy and the moment of buoyancy forces
- Wave effects: force and moment
- Partial buoyancy reduction due to the pressure hull compression at depth
- Change in sea water density depending on depth (layering)
- Low efficiency of the planes in changing depth in the control algorithm
- Insufficient volume of the hovering tank or low pump capacity

Let us consider a hovering submerged underwater vehicle with zero residual buoyancy. Then, there will be the following correlation between the weight and volume displacement of the vehicle:

$$P_n = D_n = \gamma \mathcal{V}_n, \quad (1)$$

where γ is the density of water.

As, due to various reasons, values V and γ change, the equation $P_n = D_n$, can be offset to any side. For $D_n = \gamma \mathcal{V}_n > P_n$, the underwater vehicle will be positively buoyant, for $D_n < P_n$ negatively buoyant. The equation can be broken by the following causes:

A. Increase of water density because of pressure

Water density γ increases with depth. It can be assumed that with every 10 m of depth water density increases upon 0.005%, or by 0.00005 t/m.

B. Change of water density because of temperature

Water density changes with the change of water temperature. When water temperature drops to a limit, water density increases, and then begins to decrease. With the increase of water salinity the maximum density temperature limit decreases. Approximately, in the range

between 20° and 10°, the weight of fresh water increases by 0.015% for 1°. With further temperature drop from 10° to 4°, it decreases by 0.005% for 1°.

C. Change of buoyancy because of to salinity change

When the trimmed submerged underwater vehicle in water with density γ gets into a water layer with density γ_1 , it will naturally change its buoyancy. Buoyancy change can be quite significant in this case. It may make it impossible for the underwater vehicle to dive below the layer without extra ballast taken onboard (if $\gamma_1 > \gamma$), or the vehicle will dive abruptly (if $\gamma_1 < \gamma$). Table 1 gives water temperature and salinity distribution with depth, east of Hogland Island in summer.

Table 1: Water temperature and salinity distribution with depth

Sea Depth	Temperature	Salinity
0 m	13.8°C	0.698 ‰
20 m	13.2°C	0.700 ‰
30 m	8.2°C	0.709 ‰
65 m	2.3°C	0.743 ‰
100 m	4.2°C	1.023 ‰
210 m	4.7°C	1.189 ‰

D. Change of buoyancy due to hull compression under water pressure at a greater depth

When the underwater vehicle submerges to a greater depth, the hull is subjected to water pressure from all sides, which increases with dive depth. Increasing water pressure reduces the volume V_h , thus the vehicle's buoyancy. The dependence of the residual buoyancy on the pressure hull compression is usually found by hull deformation calculations and can later be checked by submerging the underwater vehicle at various depths using a crane (crane capacity permitting) while measuring the vehicle's weight at every level.

Automatic hovering control shall set the succession of operations with the hovering tank, as well as the time of their beginning and end. For an underwater vehicle to change over to hovering, the following preliminary actions shall be done: pressure in the hovering tank shall differ from ambient seawater pressure in the range $\pm\Delta p$, where Δp is pressure drop in the air line (preparation with air), and water shall be taken into the hovering tank to medium G level (preparation with water). Before the hovering tank is pressurised, the pressure is equalized with the ambient to $\pm\Delta p$; thereafter, the underwater vehicle is trimmed with regard to buoyancy and moment with maximum possible accuracy, and the actual diving depth is coordinated with the set hovering depth. The pipelines are prepared and the pump is started. When the vehicle speed is slowed down, the hovering mode is enabled automatically. Water and air flow equations, which describe the dynamics of the processes in the hovering tank (as in Fig.7), are as given below:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dg}{dt} = A \\ \frac{dG}{dt} = B, \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

G is water weight, g air weight. A and B are, respectively, air and water flow.

$$A = \begin{cases} g_1 & \text{if } (p - p_h) < -\Delta p \\ g_2 & \text{if } > \Delta p \\ 0 & \text{if } -\Delta p < (p - p_h) < \Delta p \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

g_1 and g_2 are valve capacities, p_h the pressure depending on depth.

The amount of air by weight at any time point is found with Mendeleev-Clapeyron equation.

$$g = \frac{pV_A}{RT}, \quad (4)$$

p , V_A are air pressure and volume in the hovering tank. Differentiating the equation and taking V_T as the tank volume and γ for specific water weight $V_A = V_T - G/\gamma$, we will have the equations describing the process of preparation with air for the hovering tank, with valve operation considered and water level changing:

$$\frac{dg}{dt} = -\frac{p}{RT\gamma} \frac{dG}{dt} + \frac{V_T}{RT} \frac{dp}{dt} - \frac{G}{RT\gamma} \frac{dp}{dt} \quad (5)$$

The approximated equation, which describes the process of preparation with water, depends on characteristics of pipelines and pumps:

$$\frac{dG}{dt} = c_1 M - c_1 (p - p_h), \quad (6)$$

where c is used for coefficients depending on characteristics of pipelines and pumps, and value of M is 0 or ± 1 , which corresponds to the non-operating pump, or its suction or discharge.

4. Mathematical Model of Underwater Vehicle Motion

The motion of the underwater vehicle is described with the system of differential equations as below:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rho V (1 + k_{22}) \ddot{\eta} + c_y(90) \frac{\rho}{2} V^{2/3} \dot{\eta} |\dot{\eta}| + f(\eta) = P \\ J_z (1 + k_{66}) \ddot{\psi} + m_z(90) \frac{\rho}{2} V^{4/3} \dot{\psi} |\dot{\psi}| + \rho g V h \psi = Pl, \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

where $V(\eta)$ – displacement in depth function,

V_0 – displacement at the initial height,

$\rho(\eta)$ – sea water density in depth function,

ρ_0 – sea water density at the initial depth,

η – diving depth of the underwater vehicle (its centre of gravity),

l – hovering tank arm,

k_{22} and k_{66} – respective generalized coefficients of associated masses of the vehicle hull in the vertical motion and while rotating around the transverse axis going through the CoG in free floating,

J_z – moment of inertia in rotation around the transverse axis,

g – gravitational acceleration,

ψ – underwater vehicle trim,

h – underwater vehicle initial metacentric height,

$c_y(90)$ and $m_z(90)$ – respective hull drag coefficients in the vertical motion and while rotating around the transverse axis.

The mathematical problem of hovering control is formulated as below: The underwater vehicle shall be brought from $\eta(0) = \eta_0$ into $\eta(T) = \eta_1$ with the following restrictions observed:

$$\left| \dot{\hat{\eta}} \right| = \hat{\eta}, \quad \left| \dot{\hat{\psi}} \right| \leq \hat{\psi}, \quad P = \int_0^T (k + \left| \dot{\hat{P}} \right|) dt \leq P_0 \quad (8)$$

With that, buoyancy P is controlled in accordance with the equation:

$$\dot{\hat{P}} = \begin{cases} \hat{P} \operatorname{sign} \sigma \operatorname{npu} |\sigma| > \sigma_0 \\ 0 \operatorname{sign} \sigma \operatorname{npu} |\sigma| \leq \sigma_0, \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where \hat{P} – efficiency of intake / discharge in the hovering tank,

σ – the control signal,

\wedge symbol is used for a filtered value of a respective coordinate.

Control algorithm synthesis is done as below. First, the vehicle is controlled to come to point $\hat{\eta}$. For this, by introducing variables $\dot{\eta} = \dot{V}_y = z$ and using similarity transformations relative to control $\dot{\hat{P}}$, an equation system was made to control the vehicle's vertical speed with the signal controlling intake / discharge of the water ballast in the hovering tank:

$$\dot{\hat{P}} = \begin{cases} \dot{V}_y = z \\ z = -2a_1 z V_y \operatorname{sign} V_y + c_1 V_y + m \dot{\hat{P}} \sigma, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{where } a_1 = \frac{c_1(90)}{2V^{1/3}(1+k_{22})}, \quad m = \frac{1}{\rho V(1+k_{22})}, \quad c_1 = \frac{c^\eta}{\rho V(1+k_{22})}, \quad c^\eta = \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta} \right|_{\eta=\eta_0},$$

V_y, \dot{V}_y – vehicle's vertical speed and its first derivative.

Then, surfacing speed is automatically stabilized. With that, value P is restricted with $|P| \leq P_0$,

$$\text{where } P_0 = \frac{\hat{\psi} g V h}{l}.$$

At the same time, to compensate for the buoyancy dependence on the above factors, which influence the vehicle position while hovering, control over the additional compensating tank is enabled based

on algorithm $\sigma = -k_1 \dot{\hat{\eta}} + f(\eta) - P$ or in the remote operation mode. Maintaining the underwater vehicle to bring it to the set depth $\eta = \eta_1$ is done with the hovering tank fulfilling $\Delta\eta = \Delta\eta^*$, where

$\Delta\eta^*$ diving depth increment with η changing from $\eta = \hat{\eta}$ to $\eta = 0$. So, the structure of the control algorithm for the hovering tank is defined by the pump capacity controlling signal:

$$\sigma = f(\eta_1) - P - k_1 \dot{\hat{\eta}}_1 - k_2 \dot{\hat{\eta}} \quad (11)$$

The above algorithms are implemented in the research system to develop control algorithms for a hovering craft with the use of research of dynamic systems. Full-scale trials proved that the above algorithms were selected correctly.

5. Conclusions

Computer simulation technologies shall be widely used at all stages of an underwater vehicle's life cycle. The production of specific research simulators requires special tool environments and facilities facilitating their use and upgrading.

The use of current technologies in the computer simulation will provide the functionality to verify and check control algorithms for the control system onboard the underwater vehicle, collect more data on the operation of the actuators and the force action on the vehicle, and validate the mathematical model of the dynamics.

The use of computer technologies including extensive database and simulation of various processes can make a virtual dynamic model of operators' activities and of the crew as a whole. Then, of extreme importance is proper representation of actual processes in the underwater vehicle motion control, and this is only possible when comparative analysis is done for full-scale and model motion parameters, and model results are juxtaposed to actual processes taking place during trials. This will enable one to assess the mathematical models of underwater vehicle dynamics and operation of its equipment.

Factors critical for the stability of the underwater vehicle control depending on its diving depth were studied. The comparative analysis of the factors which have their effect on the hovering underwater vehicle behaviour demonstrated that their stability depends on the correlation between two gradients, change of buoyancy with depth depending on the hull compression, and change of buoyancy with depth depending on the variations in sea water density.

Algorithms to control the hovering underwater vehicle have been validated based on computer simulation of the vehicle's vertical manoeuvring with controlled ballasting of the hovering tank. This proved that the use of water density data in the vertical manoeuvre control considerably improves the control quality and ensures faster manoeuvring.

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The True Nature of Ship Concept Design – And What it Means for the Future Development of CASD

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Abstract

This paper considers the nature of the concept design phase for such “Physically Large and Complex” (PL&C) systems and focuses on what has been defined as the “Requirement Elucidation” task. This demands from the concept designer a different approach to that taken in the rest of the design process. From this several potential approaches to exploit emergent computer based methods, seen as enhancing the concept designer’s ability, are examined before a clear recommendation is made regarding any future investment in such “concept design” tools.

1. Introduction

It is often acknowledged that the initial (or concept) design phase is the most critical design phase, because by the end of this phase most of the cost is incorporated in the design despite little of the design effort having been expended. However, the real issue in using computers to improve the concept phase is that this usage has been misdirected at greater verisimilitude (almost for its own sake) rather than being driven by an understanding of the real nature and objective of the concept phase. Once the real nature of the concept phase of ship design is appreciated one may ask whether computer tools currently used are appropriate and how designers should influence the production of future advanced tools for use in concept design.

While a lot has been written on ship concept design, there are divergent views on its nature – in part due to the different types of ship design processes and the different perspectives of those involved in what is understood to be concept design. These different types of ship design and the associated designer perspectives are considered further in this paper after a brief outline of the recent history of the use of computer based tools in the design of ships.

The general use of computers in ship design has been reviewed by *Nowacki (2009, 2010)*, one of the pioneers in computer aided ship design (CASD). He charts the origins of both computer aided design (CAD), *Ross (1960)* and CASD. Much of that early work was focussed on hull form definition, which we almost take for granted today. However, one can also see the origins of CAD applied to detailed design – now part of large Integrated Product Model (IPM) systems and even Integrated Product Data Environment (IPDM) tools sets, such as TRIBON and FORAN – and of early stage design CASD systems, such as PARAMARINE and ASSET. These two application areas are quite distinct and my paper clearly will focus on the latter. However it is worth looking at *Nowacki’s* inclusive overview. He reviews the achievements to date in two areas: in design methodology (i.e. the search for economic efficiency, safety and risk, rationality, optimality and versatility) and in computer technology (i.e. issues of integration, communication, longevity, man-machine integration, process control and life-cycle support). This then leads to some interesting perspectives on the future where he lists over twenty recommendations under two main headings of design methodology (here split into economy and safety, systems approach, parametric design and design as learning) and Product Data Technology (consisting of products and processes, standards, technological changes, organisational changes and societal changes). He sees that “ship design has become more systematic, more rational and analytical, and more transparent in its justification”. However with regard to computers in ship design “caution is still due against blind dependence on calculated data. In CASD we must continue to seek the proper balance between man and machine,” *Nowacki (2009)*.

When the developments in early stage CASD are considered, *Nowacki’s* perspective is largely from a commercial ship application area, with its overriding economic driver. When this is compared with the naval ship environment, the differences are most marked in early ship design. The mercantile

approach starts with a market oriented requirement exploration by a prospective ship owner (sometimes with an in-house team, but more often using a design consultancy). This outline study and emergent requirement set is offered to the shipbuilding industry, who normally only have just six weeks to respond with a single solution, including a build cost and delivery time, to which the selected shipyard is then contractually committed. This means the shipyard has to produce quick and “commercially safe”, and hence conservative, proposals based very much on their own previous built solutions. Thus concept ship design in the commercial world is heavily constrained. Consequently design innovation is limited as it commences with a clear overriding specific performance based ship requirement set and clear measure of merit (MOM) on which “to turn the handle” – usually that of achieving a required freight rate. The naval ship concept design approach is different, particularly in the major navies such as the US Navy and the Royal Navy, where the process (and CASD developments) have been written about extensively, *Gale (2003)*, *Andrews (2010)*. The highly political nature of the process is captured by *Benford’s (1979)* biting description: “Multi disciplinary, multi million dollar Navy design extravaganza where every decision must be analysed, traded off, massaged and documented to the point that the basic design issues are often lost in the process.” The vast sums involved in the acknowledged complexity of concurrently developing and integrating a mobile system of systems with major weapon and sensor sub-systems is caught by *Graham’s (1982)* claim: “It is understandable that today’s warships are the most complex, diverse and highly integrated of any engineering system“. Consequently, the early design process is particularly protracted, given the search for innovation to solve what can be seen as the squaring of the circle of (impossible) needs with the initial procurement cost squeeze resulting from tax payers’ dislike of an exorbitant defence “insurance premium”. This then results in a concept phase which is distinctly different to that for merchant vessels. This paper largely explores the naval case as both an extreme and, it is believed, a likely indicator of the manner in which all major ship acquisition will be undertaken in the future, especially given recent moves in merchant ship design for first-principles and risk-based approaches, *Papanikalaou (2009)*.

2. Descriptions of Concept Ship Design

In order to address the true nature of concept ship design it is necessary to not only look at how the ship concept phase has been considered by various authors and practitioners, but also to look at the early stages of other design practice and particularly that appropriate to the design of physically large and complex (PL&C) systems. *Andrews (2012a)* summarised the nature of ship design in general which can be seen as pertinent in considering views of concept design, which can be then measured against these “ship specific” characteristics:

- a. the diversity of ship types, which has been spelt out in terms of design complexity and usage, *Andrews (2010)*, while acknowledging there are clearly other taxonomies (such as types of hull configuration and differing propulsion systems, to name but two obvious approaches);
- b. the many issues that all ships have to address (e.g. severe environments, high endurance and self sufficiency, integrating many diverse and interdependent sub-systems), together with the generally bespoke nature of ship design, which makes that design environment more like that of civil engineering than that typical of other (much smaller) vehicles;
- c. the difficulty, particularly for multirole service vessels, of requirement identification or elucidation (see *Andrews (2011)* and next section);
- d. the multitude of performance issues, alongside the main economic or operational function, that the design must address, including those (loosely) grouped under the term “style” (see *Brown and Andrews (1980)* and *Andrews (2012b)*);
- e. the professional conflict the naval architect has in being both the hull engineer and the ship’s overall architect, since he is the principal ship designer yet is part of a wider design team, where in recent years the design leadership might well have been subsumed by a generic systems engineer or project manager, who may not be a naval architect.

Rawson and Tupper (1976) not only see ship design as the *raison d’être* of naval architecture but in their penultimate chapter they both outline “preliminary (design) studies” (concentrating on space

allocation, main dimensions, displacement, form parameters, weather deck and machinery layout) and scope the whole warship design process (see Fig. 1 where *Rawson and Tupper's* overview is compared with a detailed process just for the concept phase). They call these preliminary studies “feasibility studies” to distinguish them from the subsequent “design studies”. This is not the first instance of nomenclature confusion and there is a need to clarify terms, which will be done once other versions have been considered. Rawson and Tupper also invoke the design spiral, which can be seen to just represent the iterations of a sizing routine (or simple synthesis program/spread sheet) in achieving a balanced design study or option, or alternatively is used as a description of the whole ship design process. The issue of the validity of the design spiral has been addressed by *Andrews et al. (2012)*. An essentially US Navy perspective on concept design is provided by *Gale (2003)*. Gale lists some detailed outputs from typical combatant concept studies and shows how they lead on to the much greater definition required in the subsequent phases of design but in the end Gale’s exposition is largely process focused.

Watson (1998) gives examples of merchant and warship design spirals which (questionably) show not just ship design starting with operational/naval staff requirements but also implies there is no feedback from concept design insights to revise those initial requirements. This is quite contrary to item (c) listed above. While Watson details both methods and data appropriate to concept design, his book can be seen to be largely addressing the phases beyond concept.

a. “Concept Design” in Overall Ship Design Process, *Rawson and Tupper (1976)*

Notional Concept Design Process

b. Example of the concept design process, *Brown and Thomas (1998)*

Fig.1: Extreme representations of the concept design process

If descriptions of ship design like Gale’s and Watson’s are considered, it can be seen that they largely address design management issues (in the former case) or specific technical steps (in the latter). Thus the wider objectives of ship design are largely ignored, despite the fact that it is the latter that truly

drive the initial concept phase and, hence, provide the underpinning understanding for the overall design decisions through-out the rest of the design. This follow on aspect of “true concept design” reflects a vision of the “system of systems” nature of PL&C systems and echoes the conflict identified in item (e) above. It is this wider vision of the role of ship concept design that this paper seeks to foster amongst ship designers. The managerial based approach seeks to manage ship design essentially through the Work Breakdown Structure, *Bose (2003)*, and uses approaches, such as Design Structure Matrix, *Eppinger and Browning (2012)*, to efficiently organise the sequence of design activities, once the team effort becomes significant, together with Systems Engineering, as an overarching “philosophy” applied across the wider military acquisition domain, *Calvano et al. (2000)*. With regard to the latter, *Andrews (2012c)* argues that the Systems Architecture variation, *Maier (1996)*, originating in complex software design projects, might be more relevant to the design of PL&C systems. This is, in part, due to the strong emphasis in systems architecture on the concept phase (and the concept designer), which Maier sees as absolutely key to the coherence of the downstream process, especially in the final design acceptance.

If the wider compass of design is considered for a sense of the uniqueness of the concept phase, then it is worth consulting key publications on design practice encompassing general design, architectural design and engineering design as well as the design of PL&C systems, typified by complex ship design. Several early books on design actually have concept or conceptual in their titles. Thus *French (1971)* “Engineering design: the conceptual stage” where he states the conceptual is the phase that makes the greatest demands on the designer and “takes the statement of the problem and generates broad solutions to it”. However his first diagram of the process shows this phase following on from not just “need” but also “analysis of the problem” and “statement of problem”, albeit with a feedback from “conceptual design” to analysis. Whereas *Pugh and Smith (1976)* in talking of CAD, see the conceptual stage as being “or should be concerned with synthesis”, which leads to *Alger and Hayes (1964)* “Creative Synthesis in Design”, where they provide several comparative statements of the design process. From these they conclude that, while it is “important to define and understand the design process”, the exact words adopted to do so are of “little importance in themselves”. This is useful advice against being too hung up on the variations in the terminology for describing the overall design process phases, even if the initial/early/concept phase is clearly the first design phase.

Given this level of uncertainty in the general descriptions, what this paper seeks to do is to at least explain the distinction, for PL&C systems, of what is the underlying motivation behind the concept phase, as it is this that makes it noticeably different from the subsequent phases of design. The reason why this is not generally appreciated is because descriptions of design in general, including the design of most engineering artefacts, sees the concept phase as coming after the problem definition, see Fig. 2.3 in *Dym and Little (2000)*, or even the response to a worked up specification. The latter seems to echo commercial ship practice with the ship owner’s call for shipbuilders’ bids.

A closer analogy to the engineering design of PL&C systems than that invoked for mass produced engineering products is probably found in architectural design, although there the architect’s motivation is often overlaid with cultural, psychological and artistic issues seldom indulged in engineering design. Importantly in bespoke buildings, human usage of the building figures highly and *Broadbent (1988)* has sought to bring the new human sciences into architectural design practice, which had been (and largely remains) a highly subjective and artistically inspired practice. The recognition that the design of such PL&C systems is characterised by also being a “wicked problem” helps significantly to clarify why the general engineering design process description, including the general perception of the underlying nature of the concept phase, is wrong for complex ship design.

The concept of the “wicked problem”, first coined by *Rittel and Webber (1973)* for urban planning and large scale architecture, was then suggested as appropriate to complex ship design, since “identifying what is the nature of the problem is the main problem, and that attempting to do so without recourse to potential material solutions verges on making a difficult operation impossible” certainly rings true for naval ship acquisition, *Andrews (2003)*. Before the next section explores the implication of this for the concept phase of the design of PL&C systems, it is sensible to further clarify that not all

ship design is the same, even in the specific instance of complex (bespoke) ship design. Furthermore, the concept design phase, as practiced for the most complex of vessels, is itself in several stages (or overlapping sub-phases). Within each of these stages are a series of operational steps whose order should not be prescribed since the order in which they are employed should be responsive to the particular imperatives of a given new design project.

It is important to distinguish between the types of ship design that are commonly undertaken, before outlining the description of the concept phase relevant to the level of design upon which this paper is focused, namely that appropriate to PL&C systems. While one can think of different design processes that have been adopted, the most useful discriminator is that associated with the distinctly varying levels of novelty that can exist in ship design practice. This is summarised in Table 1 with examples of increasing design novelty. Most ships are designed on a relatively straight-forward evolutionary basis, often drawing on a successful design, already built by the bidding shipyard, to reduce the risk to acquisition cost and technical reliability. However, most discussion of design methodology tends to address the exciting novel cases, as can be seen from historical presentations to learned societies of specific ship designs considered innovative, *Andrews (2010)*. In addition it could be argued that advances in design practice and tools are primarily driven by the perceived needs of such novelty.

Table 1: Types of ship design in terms of design novelty

Type	Example
second (stretched) batch	RN Batch 2 Type 22 frigate and Batch 3 Type 42 destroyer
simple type ship	Most commercial vessels and many naval auxiliary vessels
evolutionary design	Family of designs, such as VT corvettes or OCL container ships
simple (numerical) synthesis	UCL student designs
architectural synthesis	UCL (DRC) design studies (see below)
radical configuration	SWATH, Trimaran
radical technology	US Navy Surface Effect Ship of 1970s

Before considering the fundamental motivation behind the initial or concept phase of ship design, it is finally considered sensible to spell out the overall concept process, which has been applied to a major new naval ship design (i.e. the third and fourth design types in Table 1). This can be done in terms of three initial overlapping design stages, comprehensively presented in the paper on the preliminary design of warships, *Andrews (1994)*. The following outlines each stage in a little more detail.

2.1 Concept Exploration

This initial design stage can be said to comprise a wide-ranging exploration, which starts with the initiation of investigations for a new ship design. It should be an extensive consideration of all possible options and, typically, include the option of modernising existing ships, modifying existing designs and exploring the full range of, for example:

- (i) packaging of the primary function (e.g. aircraft, weapons or sensors for a combatant; cargo/passengers for naval auxiliaries or, even, merchant ships);
- (ii) capability of the ship to deliver the functions (e.g. speed, endurance, standards);
- (iii) technology options to achieve the functions and capability (e.g. existing technologies, enhanced materials and systems, enhanced technological/configurational options, reduced technology levels).

These explorations may well be cursory or may show the need to further pursue more than one distinct option some of which may require research programmes, to de-risk key technologies, or revisiting (not for the last time) the initial operational concept.

2.2 Concept Studies

Assuming only one or two options are to be taken forward, the wide ranging but cursory nature of the initial exploratory stage is unlikely to have investigated, in any depth, the perceived design drivers and the impact of various choices on function, capability and technology. This next stage depends on the type of vessel (e.g. combatant, amphibious vessel) and degree of novelty (e.g. conventional mono-hull, unconventional configuration), as well as a range of issues from varying payload demands, through the impact of speed and endurance to style issues; such as those associated with design life, signatures, survivability and complement standards. All these issues normally merit investigation before the design is too fixed. They can also significantly influence the downstream design but, more importantly, they need to be debated with the requirements owner, since their impact on the ship's performance and affordability should be part of that dialogue, before the form and style of the solution (and importantly the requirement) are too precisely fixed.

2.3 Concept Design

This final stage, prior to approval to commit to a more substantial design effort (i.e. in UK MoD terms, prior to Initial Gate decision), is primarily focused on the design (and costing) information necessary to ensure the approval to proceed is based on sufficient information and that the process, beyond that approval, can then proceed coherently. Typically, this stage in naval ship design is dominated by cost capability trade-off studies and the interaction with any associated operational analysis. It can be appreciated that to enter into this last stage of the concept phase, with inadequate exploration of the solution space or of the style and performance issues, is unwise as any submission to proceed is then likely to be vulnerable to probing by approval authorities as to the impact of such issues. This just emphasises the inherently "political" nature of naval ship acquisition at the front end of the process and why it is often protracted and seen to be unsuccessful and apparently costly, in comparison with the process for even the most sophisticated merchant vessel. However it is still nothing like as expensive as the development processes for major aircraft programmes, given these include the production of several full-scale prototypes and design of the specific tooling facilities required for a large production run. Rather than investing in such extensive preproduction development for very limited numbers of large vessels, there are issues in the case of major naval programmes that are seen to need exploring. The latter issues often being more related to the environment in which such design and acquisition is undertaken than the direct drivers of a given ship design. This is a complex world well addressed in US Navy organisational papers, e.g. *Tibbitts and Keane (1995)*, and for the UK by *Andrews (1993)* and its associated lengthy published discussion.

Fig. 2 gives an example of ship design process representation. This is an up-dated version of the process flow model, incorporating the architectural element in initial design synthesis, given in *Andrews (1998)*. This sequence shows the major choices that a ship designer or design organisation, but not a CAD toolset, has to make in order to proceed to the later phases of the design. Those phases have been summarised as ever more detailed design iterations, in the last three steps of Fig. 2. This is a top-level representation and, while designer decisions ("Selection") have to be made before their related steps in the process, sometimes the sequence of the steps may be different when specific aspects drive a particular design. (Each step is spelt out in some detail in the Appendix.)

The decision-making steps in Fig. 2, prior to each computational and configurational design activity, are themselves design activities, which the designer makes, hopefully, in a conscious manner. Emphasising the selection choices that have been made (consciously or unconsciously) distinguishes this diagram from most representations of the design process, which just specify the direct design activities, such as synthesis and exploration of features. Amongst the designer choices is the selection of the "style" of the design solution and selection of the synthesis model (or often just a sizing model). Such choices are often not questioned by the designers or, worse, not even by their design organisation and end customer. Yet they are likely to have major impact on the eventual solution. Other decision points shown in Fig. 2, such as the basis for decision-making on an initial synthesis output, criteria for acceptance of the design, and evaluation (against a selected set of criteria of acceptability),

might be considered by the design organisation. However, all too often, they are laid down by the customer or an acceptance agency, or just adopted from previous practice. Such acquiescence was understandable before computers enabled a more scientific approach to both analysis and synthesis. However, this is an unacceptable stance today, given *Nowacki's (2009)* justifiable emphasis on rationality in the development of ship design practice. It is important that the facility of option exploration through computation is also tied to graphically modelling the design, if innovative options are to be investigated more comprehensively in early design, *McDonald et al. (2012)*.

Fig. 2: Representation of the overall ship design process emphasising key decisions

Having spelt out the main steps in a major new ship concept design process, we focus on the specific technical step in the Fig. 2 representation of the overall ship design process. This step was expanded in *Andrews (1986)* as “The Warship Initial Sizing Process” and is often referred to as a numerical synthesis. Such iterative sequences have significant caveats underlying their adoption. This was reinforced at *Andrews (1998)* where that figure (reproduced at Fig. 3) was stated to be one step (the seventh) in the decision-making representation of the overall ship design process. However the main

reason for reproducing this diagram is to re-emphasise the typical range of caveats associated with any synthesis sequence. The complete figure shows, in some detail, typical Assumptions and Sources behind any such numerically based synthesis.

Fig. 3: Numeric ship synthesis with associated assumptions and sources, *Andrews (1998)*

Given the initial stages of the design of PL&C systems constitute the most vital phase in the design process, this section concludes with a summary of a recent architecturally or graphically descriptive example of a set of preliminary ship design studies. These studies adopted the design approach outlined in *Andrews (1998)*, which as the Design Building Block (DBB) approach was subsequently incorporated, via the SURFCON module, into the PARAMARINE CASD system.

2.4 The UK Mothership studies

The UCL design research team used PARAMARINE to produce a series of novel mothership concepts. These concepts had different means of deploying relatively small naval combatants, which resulted in several distinct ship configurations to meet the same operational concept of a fast “mothership” to carry small combatants. It was intended to transport the combatants over long distances so they could then be deployed in a littoral environment, avoiding the need to provide large and costly ocean going combatants. Each of the “mothership” configurations addressed a different deployment and recovery method, namely, well dock; heavy lift; crane; stern ramp; and stern gantry. The origin

and management of this set of studies was comprehensively described by *Andrews and Pawling (2004)* and so, for the purposes of this exposition, what is relevant is whether such a range of concept designs could be investigated, to such a level of design fidelity, without an architecturally driven design approach. The range of design solutions produced can be appreciated from the 3D representations in Fig. 4 of the seven vessel types conceived. Summary characteristics of each technically balanced design are detailed in the 2004 paper. Each new ship concept was driven not just by the carriage and deployment of the small combatants but also, in most instances, by the extensive water ballasting arrangements required and the considerable bunkering for the stowage of fuel, necessary to propel the vessel at speed some 10,000 nm. The architecturally based synthesis gave a higher degree of confidence in the realism of each of the distinct solution types, compared to an approach using just a conventional numerical synthesis. In particular, the integrated representation of ship architecture with the usual technical/numerical aspects of naval architecture mitigated errors in the modelling. This was particularly relevant to the interface between the spatial and numerical representations, which in any subsequent design development might otherwise have been shown to be sufficient erroneous to render a configuration unworkable.

Fig. 4: Set of Mothership ship options, *Andrews and Pawling (2004)*

The physical complexity of combining the architectural and engineering science in initial design required the facility of computer graphics, alongside analytical modules for the designer to adequately explore configurationally diverse potential solutions. This demonstration effectively unified the art of spatially based inventiveness with the necessary engineering sciences to achieve a range of novel and balanced design concepts.

3. Requirements Elucidation makes the Concept Phase Different

Andrews (2003) concluded that the practice of first investigating in considerable depth and in non-material specific terms the requirements for a major naval programme was

- a) not appropriate for major warships; and
- b) bad systems engineering practice

corroborated by the views of systems engineering theorist *John (2002)*. Requirements engineering's emphasis on abstraction is clearly counter-intuitive to designers of engineering physical systems (such as ships). This abstraction presents operational users, trying to spell out what they want, with immense cognitive difficulties, because they have to identify appropriate capabilities to do future tasks, by clearly drawing on their experience of operating current real ships and systems, yet are expected to spell out such capabilities without ostensibly picturing potential physical solutions. *Andrews*

(2003) argued that this is a false and highly inefficient approach, which further extends the front end decision making for such politically sensitive programmes in a wasteful manner.

Like the design of large complex buildings, the design of naval ships is characterised by the “wicked” nature of the design process, *Rittel and Webber (1973)*, where “formulation of a ‘wicked’ problem is the problem. ...setting up and constraining the solution space... is more essential than the remaining steps of searching for a solution.” This explains why the formulation of requirements is inherently difficult, but also why this is intimately interwoven with the search for and exploration of solutions. Sorting out what a multi-functional, largely autonomous vehicle, containing a hundred or more highly trained personnel, might need to do in an uncertain future can only be explored in terms of possible design options. If furthermore cost, time and risk have to be taken into account (see the version of the “Vee” diagram by *Elliott and Deasley (2007)*), in moderating any needs expression by the achievable and affordable, then the case for solution exploration, not just informing the requirements owner but also ensuring the designer as an equal partner in the dialogue, seems patently obvious. This dialogue is precisely what is meant by requirements elucidation.

At the initial (concept) phase of ship design, there are five highly interrelated aspects that characterise this fundamentally different part of the process of designing such PL&C system as naval vessels:

1. The process is characterised as a wicked problem. Unlike the downstream process, which is of a highly convergent nature and seen to be “peeling off the layers of an onion” to reveal more technical detail to gain design assurance and then sufficient detail to manufacture the eventual ship, this phase consists of working out what is really wanted and what can be afforded. It is characterised by starting with one or several blank sheets of paper and producing design concepts to gain the insights on performance, cost, time and risk, as suggested by the first bubble of Elliot and Deasley’s Vee diagram.
2. This is a key phase where major decisions are made. Design has been characterised as decision making in its entirety. But, as shown by the overall ship design process (Fig. 2), the crucial decisions are made at the very front of the process and (as highlighted by the assumptions and sources examples in Fig. 3) many of these are often not appreciated by the two key players in the initial design phase – the requirement owner (usually the naval staff) and the concept designer. This lack of awareness can prematurely narrow down the options for consideration and constrain the task of tackling the, essentially, wicked problem.
3. In coming to the conclusion of this largely divergent and exploratory phase in order to proceed into “engineering design proper”, decisions have to be made as to which one or possibly two outline design concepts, balanced to the limited extent appropriate to inform the decisions, is to be taken forward. Classically, this is a “trade-off” process, where distinctly different options with inevitably different attributes and levels of uncertainty have to be assessed. There are tools available to assist in decision-making but there is a risk in using them blindly, if the process has not been recognised as “wicked” and full of (potentially) unappreciated constraints. So there is the need to ensure that a comprehensive and challenging design process has been conducted. This has to be done before trade-off studies are undertaken and is essential to inform any quantitative trade-off process. Numerical trade-off studies should be undertaken to provide enlightenment rather than being the sole basis of decision-making.
4. Part of the nature of this wicked, decision-making and complex trade-off process is that choices have inevitably been made as to the “style” of the various design concepts investigated. Thus the next crucial aspect is identification of style. This brings to the fore many issues of importance to the ship operator. These were either hard to recognise in the traditionally narrow (numerical) concept exploration, or not considered addressable by the traditional naval architectural (largely stability and powering) input to concept design studies. In what has been argued to be a paradigm shift, due to advances in computer graphics, *Andrews (2003,2006a)*, ‘softer’ design concerns, especially those dealing with the human factors aspects of PL&C systems, can now be more readily addressed in ship concept studies.
5. The final aspect is that of requirement elucidation, which brings together much of the first four considerations but strongly emphasises that this first phase of design is not about a

blinkered rush into the subsequent design phases but, rather, is a process of elucidating what is required. Furthermore, requirements elucidation can only be done properly by an open and un-constrained dialogue between the naval staff and the concept ship designer, where each helps the other in the decision-making necessary to cope with the wicked nature of the process. That the process must be done in a manner using the design skills of the ship designer should be all too obvious and that the ship concept designers have the obligation to encompass style issues, which are beyond their naval architectural comfort zone (see *Andrews (2006)*), is a significant consequence of the paradigm shift. This then leads on to a clear statement as to what must characterise the output produced by concept design tools, if they are to assist the ship designer in properly undertaking requirements elucidation in the complex acquisition environment for PL&C vessels:

- Believable solutions, i.e. solutions which are technically balanced and sufficiently descriptive;
- Coherent solutions, i.e. the dialogue with the customer and other stakeholders should be more than merely a focus on numerical measures of performance and cost, by including a comprehensive visual representation (noting that the SURFCON module provides considerably more than an artist's impression of the outside of the ship);
- Open methods, i.e. not a 'black box' or a rigid/mechanistic decision system, so that the description is responsive to those issues that matter to the customer, or are capable of being elucidated by the designer from dialogue with customer/user teams;
- Revelatory insights, in particular identifying likely design drivers, early in the design process, to aid design exploration in initial design and the subsequent "working up" of the design's feasibility through to the build description;
- A creative approach, not just as a "clear box" but actually encouraging exploration "outside the envelope", including radical solutions, and a wide design and requirement exploration to push the requirement elucidation boundaries.

4. The Implications for CASD

Having clearly stated that the initial concept phase of the design of PL&C systems is different from the downstream process, in its aims and its practice, it is now appropriate to conclude by looking at the various emergent methods and tools that have been proposed to "improve" initial ship design. This should draw on the understanding of the true nature of initial concept design, as outlined above. Thus each approach to improving the ship concept process should be interrogated to see if it provides the necessary insight into requirements elucidation, as the essential driver for the Concept Phase, rather than just increased verisimilitude for its own sake.

The first approach adopted has been to use computer techniques to provide rapid generation of many options. This can be achieved by simple algorithms of the sort implied by Fig. 3, with simple performance checks (e.g. stability and powering) to achieve "balanced solutions" and then interrogating a large number of incremental variations, *Vasudevan (2007)*. It can even be extended to different hull types, *McDonald (2010)*. The question to ask is does the large number of options assist in requirement elucidation, to which the answer must be: only if such an approach provides insight into those issues that matter in making the difficult requirement choices. Those choices are usually more about the particular functions the new concept is intended to perform than necessarily those revealed by refinements and variants on 'a simple balance of weight, space, stability and powering'.

Optimisation has a relatively long history in ship design, *Mandel and Leopold (1966)*, *Keane et al. (1991)*, *Parsons and Scott (2003)*) and can be seen both to be focused on specific techniques, such as Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), *Mandel and Leopold (1966)*, neural networks *Clausen et al. (2001)*, genetic algorithms *Vasudevan (2008)*), and approaches to deal with the results of optimisation, such as multi-criteria decision making (MCDM), *Sen (2006)*, and Pareto fronts, *McDonald (2009)*. The latter approaches reflect the problem that the optimisation is rarely governed by a single overriding aspect. The real problem is how to properly decide just what criteria are truly important and if (as is all too likely) there are several disparate quantities, such as initial cost and through-life

cost, economic and operational performance, robustness and adaptability. Then arriving at measures of merit with believable weighting factors becomes seriously problematic. Once the design is largely determined (i.e. at the end of the concept phase) this may be clearer but in the initial stages of the concept phase such “optimisation” is questionable. If the concept phase is about elucidation then part of this has to be the determination of what is important and this should then inform any MCDM or weighting decisions – not the other way around. Furthermore to undertake a set of multi-criteria optimisations ahead of requirements elucidation is to fall into the same error as requirement engineering and its ilk. That is to say using the wide concept exploration of potential design options to elucidate not just the requirements that are practical (in regards to affordability, risk and performance) and also reveal the relative balance of design drivers (from concept studies) that will best meet the emerging requirements set, which then can inform any optimisation criteria and weightings.

Van Oers and Stapersma (2006) argued that with more effective analytical tools, particularly in the “hard engineering” disciplines of naval architecture (hydrodynamics and structural response), less reliance should be paid in concept phase on “rules of thumb” for concept sizing and balance (see Sources in Fig. 3). Rather “first principles” should be adopted as far as possible. This would mean when going into the feasibility phase that a lot of the initial uncertainty regarding the viability of the chosen solution would be reduced and furthermore the basis of decision-making would have a surer foundation. Some of this is already happening. It is perfectly possible in early concept studies to select an appropriate hull form and with simple damage extent criteria, *Sarchin and Goldberg (1962)*, position main watertight bulkheads so that “at the press of a button” a range of damage GZ curves can be produced. This would seem to mean the concept designer should no longer rely on a simple $GM_{\text{achieved}} > GM_{\text{required}}$ criterion in driving the ship’s beam. In passing, such apparent verisimilitude is actually pointless if the assessment of KG is no better than choosing a percentage of the hull depth. One of the advantages in adopting an architecturally driven concept design approach such as the UCL Design Building Block approach, *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*, is that a better basis for KG estimation could be obtained, but only if the proper investment in an architecturally driven design study is made (see “worked” example in *Andrews and Pawling (2008)*).

However, overly investing in first principles in the concept phase also misses the point of what the concept phase is about. If the concept phase is to elucidate the “wicked” requirements and not just produce a “better” solution to pre-determined (“engineered”) requirements, then it needs to be questioned whether investing in better and more “first principles” in the concept phase necessarily provides the most effective support to the elucidation dialogue? An old adage says “reduce to a minimum the amount of design effort in concept”: to keep down time and cost pre-feasibility. This is quite sensible, but not if the motivation is to save design costs (which are of minor design expenditure for a few concept designers). If instead the objective is that the designer does not lose sight of the main aim, which of course is to elucidate what is wanted and achievable/affordable, then the option of not extending the relatively minor resources on the concept design team is likely to be massively outweighed by the downstream consequences of exiting the concept phase prematurely.

The approach to preliminary or initial design that I have propounded for several decades has been the architectural or DBB approach to ship synthesis. This best assists the requirement elucidation process in the concept phase in that, while like “first principles” it does complicate the design effort in concept, it does so in direct pursuit of elucidation. Because it gives the other partner in the requirement elucidation dialogue – the naval operator – a better feel for the multifarious design options, showing him the interior architecture of a potential vessel (not just the topside and hull form), it also opens up a much wider range of issues that now can be technically addressed. In contrast to “first principles”, which gets into more detail about what interests the naval architect, the architectural approach opens up consideration of issues such as features of the ship’s configuration that might make the ship more effective for fighting, surviving attack, carrying out evolutions, such as storing, maintenance and role changing, all of which are likely to be of prime concern to the operator. Such wider aspects involve assessing the personnel’s effectiveness onboard and require an architecturally driven design approach if their impact on the design and achievement of the emergent requirements is to be investigated.

Just as the computer has made optimisation and the application of first principles more possible in ship concept design, simulation tools are also coming on stream to investigate, even in concept, issues such as human factors, *Andrews et al. (2008)*, fire fighting, *Pawling et al. (2012)*, air weapon handling, *Owen and Oakley (2003)*, design for production, *Andrews et al. (2005)*. It could be argued that these topics are more important in the requirements elucidation process than further refinement of well-established naval architectural aspects, precisely because they can be major cost and performance drivers in interacting directly with the (still) emerging requirements. Furthermore such simulation tools go hand in hand with an architecturally based model of innovative ship concepts.

So if we look to how the development of computer aided ship design (CASD) in concept ought to be driven, this should be by meeting the true needs of the concept designer. Thus developments that both foster insight and creativity, rather than just provide faster and more detailed numeric analysis, would better achieve the aims of requirement elucidation. That is to tackle the “wicked nature” of the concept phase for the design of PL&C systems, typified by the multi-functional naval vessel.

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Appendix: Description of the steps in the ship design process (Figure 2)

- a. Perceived need – This should emerge from the customer’s consideration of the market drivers or, in the case of naval vessels, from a threat analysis, the need to get a new sensor or weapon to sea in a new class of vessels or just the replacement of a class of ships that are reaching their end of life. This need is best approached (given the wicked nature of requirement elucidation) in broad terms: thus ‘a new general combatant/fleet escort’ or ‘a replacement amphibious landing (dock) ship’.
- b. Outline of initial requirements – This should also be very broad in that beyond the basic capability ‘everything should be negotiable’. Aspects, such as cost and time, are still important, but even these should be in the equation as the individual vessel size or style might yet be better met in a manner yet to emerge from the requirements elucidation dialogue.
- c. Selection of the style of the emergent ship design – This is the first design choice. Given the exploration stage should consider a range of technological solutions, each of these may have specific styles associated with their particular technology (e.g. commercial design standards for a utility helicopter carrier (HMS OCEAN), low underwater signature for an ASW frigate (Type 23)). But also there are generic style choices, such as being robust, highly adaptable, high sustainability or low manning, which should be considered for specific concepts. While adopting such style issues is inherent in commencing any design study it is important that this is done consciously since each one has implications for the eventual design outcome and therefore ought to be investigated before that style aspect is incorporated or rejected.
- d. Selection of major equipments and operational sub-systems – Given an indication for a given solution type on the Concept Exploration solution space (such as a fast trimaran frigate or a utility carrier) and its appropriate performance (e.g. fleet speed, sustained endurance, maintenance standard), it is necessary to postulate from a likely ship size the likely power plant. It is also necessary to identify the likely major combat equipment or sub-systems. (Selection of standard items such as medium calibre guns or PDMS but less so if a concurrently developing major combat element, such as the PAAMS for the Type 45 Destroyer or the Towed array for the Type 23, where options may be explored. This could be just the size and split of weapon silos but more likely this would be the subject of trade off studies later in concept.
- e. Selection of Whole Ship Performance Characteristics – For a naval combatant these may actually have more effect on the whole ship solution than the combat system choices. Thus classical hull form drivers of stability, resistance and seakeeping, which could be seen as emerging from the style choices above or more directly. As performance characteristics or laid down standards, like complementing ‘rules’ are likely to be major size and (ship) cost drivers. So again these should be open to revision – probably informed by the Concept Studies stage.
- f. Selection of synthesis model – Despite the fact that this is a crucial decision, it is often made by default. Individual design organisations have their own synthesis tools and associated data-bases. These can inhibit the scope of the Concept Exploration, if for example a trimaran design cannot then be considered. As was amply demonstrated for the classical numerical synthesis sequence, *Andrews (1986)*, there are inherent assumptions and data/rules in any approach. The real issue is that these are rarely questioned and their limitations can compromise subsequent baseline design definitions and the trade-off studies refining them and the requirements elucidation dialogue – especially if the modelling tool is a ‘black box’.
- g. Selection of the basis for Decision Making in Initial Synthesis – This should be a conscious choice before the (selected) synthesis modelling tool or approach is used. Again this is often made by default choice of the synthesis tool. Thus classical numeric sizing will balance an option in weight & displacement and volume required & volume available, while subject to crude checks of stability and powering. Often the metric sought is then (an equally) crude initial (weight based) costing – or at best RFR for merchant ships. Whether this is the right basis for decision-making is questionable - particularly as the main design drivers may yet to emerge (e.g. underwater noise signature, amphibious force offloading, air wing sortie rate). The more sophisticated architecturally driven synthesis realised by the UCL Design Building Block (DBB) approach opens up the synthesis and enables a Simulation Based Design prac-

tice, where the 3-D configuration can be investigated for human factors aspects or other simulations (such as Design for Production, Design for Support and Design for Survivability). This can then ensure that the balanced synthesis reflects more than a crude initial cost and simple stability and power checks.

- h. Synthesis of Ship Gross Size and Architecture – With the initial choices consciously made the baseline and subsequent concept studies, and then the Concept Design options can be produced. Provided an architectural definition has been included in this many of the style issues and the requirement elucidation (providing the basis for the dialogue with the requirements owner or customer) can be investigated.
- i. Exploration of Impact of Style, Major Equipment and Performance Characteristics – Although style is seen to be the most crucial exploration, without an architecturally centred synthesis it is questionable that many style aspects can be explored at this stage. Rather most exploration tends to be focused, in the Concept Design trade off stage on ‘payload’ and powering. If, as well as style issues, different solution types such as SWATH and Trimaran configurations are to be properly considered in this exploration the an architecturally based approach should be employed.
- j. Selection of Criteria for Acceptance of Emerging Design – This is really setting up the basis for the Concept Design stage trade off studies and sensibly informed by the Concept Studies of what might be the crucial style choices. This should not just be dependant on the perceived overall project needs but also which of the technological (and packing/capability) alternatives have been revealed as relevant and significant to be pursued in more depth in the trade-off exercise, when agreement to proceed to the next project phase needs to be robust for high level approval.
- k. Analysis of Size and Form Characteristics – If just a simple numerical synthesis has been undertaken in the Concept Studies stage then only default hull form parameters are likely to have been assumed. Before the Baseline Design for each of the (few) selected option from the wide Concept Exploration solution space from which Concept Studies have been performed, then it is necessary to conduct an investigation of the main hull dimensions and principal form parameters (typically for a monohull this includes C_p , C_m , B/T, L/D and superstructure percentage). This is called a parametric survey at UCL, which is different to US Navy practice where the same term denotes a trade-off of hull sizing. If a proper architecturally based synthesis is performed it is likely that the parametric survey will already have been informed by the internal compartmental disposition so that overall hull sizing and shaping will merge from realistic hull form options. If not then hull form dimension and parameters will be wrongly selected and this will only be revealed later in the design development. If unconventional configurations, including multihulls, are being properly considered and then taken forward the likelihood of an unrealistic parameter selection will be even greater, weakening the conclusions from trade-off studies.
- l. Architectural and Engineering Synthesis and Analysis – This step reflects the need in a given project to undertake (as part of Concept Design prior to finalising any comprehensive trade off of requirements, style, configuration etc.) specific detailed engineering design and preliminary analysis. Such more detailed first principles design work is not undertaken comprehensively in the Concept Phase – this being the task of the early iterations of the selected Concept Design solution in the next (and subsequent) phase of design (i.e. Feasibility or Embodiment Design). However it may well be for a given project that in the concept phase that a certain aspect needs to be investigated in more depth. (An example of this being done, was that conducted by the author in the early 1990s in the concept phase of what became the RFA WAVE Class Tankers (AO). This AO was the first RFA fleet tanker required to be doubled hulled. It was therefore necessary to undertake detailed damage stability analysis of all the ships’ likely operating conditions. This would not normally be required pre-feasibility and reinforces the adage that ‘the minimum detailed engineering is undertaken in the concept phase’, however sometimes the ‘minimum’ is comprehensive in a specific aspect (namely extensive damage stability here)). The inclusion of the ‘architectural element’ in this step’s title is deliberate as once any detailed engineering synthesis and analysis is undertaken, it must be

with reference to the internal architectural arrangement or, once again, conclusions drawn will be found to be inadequate or even misleading once Feasibility is underway.

- m. Evaluation of the design to meet the Criteria of Acceptability – This evaluation occurs both in the trade-off exercise from which the final Concept Design is selected and essentially to the subsequent design development of that design. Clearly it is necessary to have a basis for evaluation to make that selection and to spell out the criteria for acceptability. These criteria will be quite high level for the Concept Phase and of ever greater detail once downstream. Given that the task of Concept is Requirement Elucidation, it is important that the evaluation is consistent with the evolving refinement of the requirement that emerges from the dialogue with the selected Concept Design. That design provides the start point for the Feasibility Phase with the matching requirement statement providing the specification (along with associated standards and style statements) that can be used for the main design development.
- n. The remaining three steps in Fig. 2 indicate the rest of the design process, once the Concept Phase has been correctly conducted, and is a process of ever greater detailing of the design through the various design phases to achieve sufficient definition for building, setting to work and through life performance. Given these phases constitute the vast bulk of the time and design resources this can seem a little glib. However the point of this current exposition is to emphasise that all subsequent design is based on both the emergent concept design and the matching requirements, such that the initial process as requirements elucidation is quite different in intent and hence process. That far too many major (naval) ship designs revisit much of the concept and requirement effort is clearly indicative that the Concept Phase is too often inadequately undertaken. This is not least because all too often it is seen as the first part of the rest of the design and not the ship design half of Requirements Elucidation.

Automatic Tuning of Metamodels for Optimization

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Abstract

The use of surrogate models is considered a valid alternative to the massive recourse to complex and expensive CFD solvers in design optimization. Many different interpolation and approximation techniques are available in literature, each with its own advantages and drawbacks. Among them, Kriging is gaining credibility due to its flexibility and ease in implementation and training, but also for the theoretical background. However, some crucial parameters need to be assumed, and the final result depends on these choices. In this paper, some guidelines and techniques for the identification of the base elements of a Kriging interpolator are suggested and partly explored.

1. Introduction

The general credibility of the final result of an optimization process is strongly based on the mathematical model adopted in computing the objective function. For this reason, one of the first and more important phases in formulating an optimization problem is the selection of tools. When the physics involved in the problem do not allow a simple mathematical model, we are forced to apply some other simplification techniques in order to solve the optimization problem in a reasonable time. This is particularly evident when many computations of the objective function are needed in order to assess the robustness of the solution with respect to some stochastic parameters, as in *He et al. (2012)*.

To this aim, different approaches are available. One possibility comes from the combined use of different solvers, with different fidelity, so that a reduced-order model formulation is adopted for the problem. The optimization is mainly performed by applying the low-fidelity solver, fast but less reliable, and the high-fidelity solver (slow but trustable) is used few times in order to redirect the search. The original framework, proposed in *Alexandrov and Lewis (2001)*, for which a solid consistency condition between the original and reduced-order model is provided, was applied to ship design optimization in *Peri et al. (2006)* and extended to global optimization in *Peri et al. (2012)*.

Another possibility is the use of a surrogate model (metamodel) of the objective function. A surrogate model is an interpolation/approximation model, providing an estimate of the objective function value on previously unexplored regions. The cost of a single prediction is meaningful if compared with every CFD solver, since it is based on simple algebraic relationships. Complete reviews are presented in *Giunta et al. (2003)* and in *Peri (2009)*.

Determining a reliable surrogate model for a limited number of training points, i.e. the points in which the objective function is known, is not easy and straightforward. In fact, for the same training set different interpolation models can be derived, with different shapes and features, Fig. 1.

Fig.1: Two different interpolators for an assigned training set: both solutions are acceptable since the error in the prediction at the training point is null.

Among the possible choices, the Kriging metamodel is a good option basically for two reasons: first, under some hypothesis, it is demonstrated that Kriging is the best linear unbiased estimator, i.e. the model provides the lowest possible mean squared error of the estimate. Second, determining the parameters of the metamodel is rather simple and fast, once some basic assumptions have been made. However, some free parameters remain in the general formulation and these influence the final solution. In order to identify the basic elements for tuning the metamodel, the next chapter provides some basics about Kriging. After that, the methodology for the selection of the most appropriate parameters will be given, together with some numerical experiments. Finally, some conclusions and perspectives will be drawn.

2. Basics about Kriging

The original formulation of Kriging is provided in *Matheron (1965)*, obtained as a further interpretation of a previous paper by Krige dated 1951. Matheron baptized the method “Kriging” because the basic elements were detected by Krige. Since then, a number of different formulations have been developed: We refer here to the formulation known as “Ordinary Kriging”, see also *Cressie (1990)*.

The general idea is to treat the training set as observation from a random (or stochastic) process

$$\{Z(s) : s \in D\}; D \subset \mathfrak{R}^d$$

at some known locations $\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \dots, \mathbf{s}_n$ (the training set). We are also assuming

$$Z(s) = \mu + \delta(s); s \in D$$

$\delta(s)$ is a stochastic process with zero mean and known covariance function

$$C(s, u) \equiv \text{cov}\{Z(s), Z(u)\}; s, u \in D$$

We want to derive a homogeneous linear predictor

$$\hat{Z}(s) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i Z(s_i)$$

also satisfying the condition

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = 1$$

Defining the matrix and the vectors

$$\Gamma = \begin{vmatrix} C(s_1, s_1) & C(s_1, s_2) & \cdots & C(s_1, s_n) & 1 \\ C(s_2, s_1) & C(s_2, s_2) & \cdots & C(s_2, s_n) & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ C(s_n, s_1) & C(s_n, s_2) & \cdots & C(s_n, s_n) & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 0 \end{vmatrix}; \quad \Lambda = \begin{vmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ \lambda_2 \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_n \\ \omega \end{vmatrix}; \quad M = \begin{vmatrix} C(s_1, V) \\ C(s_2, V) \\ \vdots \\ C(s_n, V) \\ 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

V is the general position at which the prediction is to be computed. The ordinary Kriging system of equations can be expressed as:

$$\Gamma \Lambda = M$$

As a consequence, the Γ matrix needs to be inverted once and for all, and the Kriging prediction in the general point V can be simply obtained by a matrix-vector operation. Dimensions of the Γ matrix are determined by the number of points in the training set, independently by the space dimension. The variance of the prediction can be obtained by the simple relation

$$\sigma^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i C(s_i, V) + \omega - C(V, V)$$

Journal and Huijbregts (1978) demonstrate how a non-singular covariance matrix ensures the existence and uniqueness of the solution to the ordinary Kriging system of equations, and also that the ordinary Kriging variances are always positive. It is now clear that the only unknown part of the ordinary Kriging system is the covariance operator. In *Matheron (1964)* the concept of semi-variogram is adopted. The semi-variogram is defined, in discrete form, as

$$\gamma(h) = \sum_{i=1}^{n(h)} \frac{(Z(s+h) - Z(s))^2}{n(h)}$$

where h is the distance between two samples and $n(h)$ is the number of samples at the distance h . The semi-variogram is commonly interpolated by an algebraic function in order to define the spatial correlation between the points. Unfortunately, the semi-variogram depends on the computational point, and rarely a clear tendency is identifiable. The use of the semi-variogram implies the base hypothesis that data should be stationary, i.e. their correlation depends only on the distance. This hypothesis is not verified by very simple algebraic functions. In practice, if we want to apply Kriging we need to assume a semi-variogram, but this will be not completely representative of the real spatial correlation between the data. As a consequence, some of the theoretical qualities of Kriging are lost.

In literature, many different options are reported. The most popular ones involve an exponential operator. In this paper, two different exponential semi-variograms will be adopted:

$$\gamma_1(h) = e^{\left(-\alpha \frac{h}{h_{\max}}\right)}; \quad \gamma_2(h) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{\left(-\alpha \frac{h}{h_{\max}}\right)}}$$

A third semi-variogram obtained by a spline curve will be also investigated. In this case, the number of parameters is free. The extreme points of the spline have been constrained: the spline must pass through the origin and the end asymptotically, with horizontal asymptote of free value. Another constraint forces the spline to be strictly positive. We will refer to this semi-variogram as

$$\gamma_3 = \text{spln}(x_s, n_s)$$

x_s is the vector of n_s control points of the spline.

3. Adaptive Kriging

If we wish to adapt the Kriging metamodel to the current training set, we need two ingredients: some parameters to be modified and some criteria to be optimized in order to improve the quality of the prediction. In *Simpson et al. (2001)*, γ_1 is adopted, and a single parameter for each design variable is tuned considering the definition of the variogram, similarly to what proposed also in *Zhao et al (2011)*. Using this approach, the variogram is again the same for all the elements, and the spatial variability is averaged on the entire space, without introducing any further element related to any possible local change of the variogram. In this paper, we will consider local variations of the variogram function, in order to better assess the variogram on the local variations of the objective functions. To do that, we will describe first the free parameters available for the Kriging metamodel and then the criteria to be considered in order to measure the quality of the prediction.

3.1 Tuning Parameters in Kriging

From the expression of γ_1 and γ_2 , we can see how one free parameter α is included. The selection of α strongly influences the solution at every region different than the training points. In fact, Kriging is an interpolation model, providing the exact value of the objective function at the training points, but the

shape of the semi-variogram influences the behavior in the region between two training points, as illustrated in Fig. 1. In the case of γ_2 , the number of unknowns could be even higher.

Another key point of the classical implementation of Kriging is the stationary of the semi-variogram. With this hypothesis, we exclude any directional dominance for the influence of a point on the surrounding region. In order to include this possibility, we can act on the norm adopted for the computation of the semi-variogram, changing the way in which the distance h is defined. This option can be realized in many ways: here we are substituting the classical

$$h = \|x\| = \ell^2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|^2} \Rightarrow \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i |x_i|^2 + \vartheta_i |x_i|^3}$$

With this new metric, we are stretching the semi-variogram in different ways along the different directions, and also along the positive and negative direction of the same axis. The iso-contours of the h function are no longer spherical; they are now elliptical with a shift of the focus in order not to be symmetrical. This introduces $2 \cdot n + 1$ additional free parameters, one for the exponential and $2 \cdot n$ for the new expression of the distance. β_i and ϑ_i should be selected carefully, to avoid a negative value for the argument of the square root. This is ensured by limiting ϑ_i to a fraction of β_i . If $|x_i|$ is limited to 1, the norm is strictly positive for $\vartheta_i \leq \beta_i$ and the curve has no change of curvature for $\vartheta_i \leq 0.5\beta_i$.

We can finally assume that the semi-variogram is different for each training point. As a consequence, if N is the number of training points, the total number of unknowns is $N(2 \cdot n + 1)$ if γ_1 or γ_2 are adopted, $N(2 \cdot n + n_s)$ if we are using γ_3 . A training set of 25 points in \mathfrak{R}^2 with four spline points results in 200 parameters to be identified. The large number of parameters gives the idea that the identification of a configuration able to meet all the criteria is possible; on the other hand it puts some concern observing the complexity of the problem in hands.

3.2 Optimizing Criteria in Kriging

As Kriging is an interpolation model, it provides an exact solution at the training set: as a consequence, we have not a quantity to be minimized if we do not change something in the usage of the training set.

One technique typically adopted for the evaluation of the quality of the prediction is to measure the error on each training point when that point is excluded by the training set (Leave-One-Out – LOO). It is typically referred to as “cross validation”. One of the training points is excluded from the training set, and Kriging is computed leaving this point out of the training set. The metamodel is not guaranteed to pass through the excluded point, and the prediction will be different on it. Computing the error obtained by leaving out each training point, and summing up all the errors, we obtain a cumulative error in the prediction ε_{LOO} . This can be interpreted as a measure of the inadequateness of the covariance operator with respect to the true fitting function. A change in the parameters of the semi-variogram may lead to a smaller ε_{LOO} , possibly to 0. In the meantime, we have also to consider that Kriging provides an exact prediction at the training points, so that also the variance is zero at each known point. As a consequence, a second criterion could be introduced, summing up all the variances and obtaining μ_{LOO} accordingly.

A second option can be obtained splitting the training set in two parts, as commonly performed for the neural network training. We are dividing the full set of available simulations in two distinct set of points, one called “training” and the other called “validation”. The quantity to be minimized is the error on the validation set, not used in order to derive the Kriging model. We will refer to this procedure in the following as T&V. In some sense, LOO a particular case of T&V, where a single validation point is adopted and all the options are checked. Same criteria can be derived, namely ε_{TV} and μ_{TV} . Number and position of the validation points is a further unknown of the problem. In this paper, priority is given to the equally-spaced distribution of the training points, while the validation

points will be the remaining ones. The first training point is selected as the closer to the center of the current distribution of training point. For each training successive point, we are sequentially selecting the point minimizing the quantity

$$q = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \|x_i - x\| \right) \frac{\min(\|x_i - x\|)_{i \in n_t}}{\max(\|x_i - x\|)_{i \in n_t}}$$

By maximizing q , we are requesting a point with great distance from the other previously selected training point, with some emphasis on the minimum and maximum distance from them. Using this strategy, the extreme points (here the corners) are always selected as training points, avoiding extrapolations in the field. Examples are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Selection of five validation points over a regular (left) and irregular (right) set of samplings

4. Optimization Algorithm and Problem Formulation

In order to minimize ϵ_{LOO} or ϵ_{TV} , a Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm has been adopted. The algorithm, proposed in *Kennedy and Eberhart (1995)*, was implemented in the variant proposed in *Campana et al. (2009)*, where the random parameters are excluded from the formulation and a local search method is applied once the maximum dimension of the swarm and its speed is strongly reduced. In this case, a Conjugate-Gradient method (Polak-Ribiere formulation, *Nocedal and Wright (1999)*) is applied once the dimension and speed of the swarm are fading.

Regarding the optimization problem formulation, we have 36 different options coming from the different possible combinations. Furthermore, we have to select the number of spline points when the semi-variogram γ_3 is adopted and the number of validation points when LOO is applied. Evidently, a full exploration of all possible options may result in a too confuse presentation of results. Therefore, in this paper only a subset of the different problem formulations will be presented, trying to stress the most relevant aspects.

Lastly, some words about the constraints of the optimization problem. Due to the great instability of the problem, we need to put some box constraints on the variables. In order not to consider special techniques for managing the constraints, a change of variables is adopted:

$$\tilde{x} = x_{\min} + (x_{\max} - x_{\min}) \cdot \left(0.5 + \frac{\text{atan}(x)}{\pi} \right)$$

The optimization problem is solved using x , but the computation is performed using \tilde{x} . This is equivalent to the consideration of box constraints: the inverse tangent is limited in between $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, and then \tilde{x} is limited in between $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ while x is unlimited. This approach introduces a stretch in the objective function, potentially increasing the complexity of the optimization problem: on the other hand, we can easily manage the bound constraints and all the considered configurations will be feasible, avoiding recourse to special techniques or penalty functions.

5. Numerical Experiments

In order to reduce the number of possible formulation of the optimization problem, a limited number of tests on the different components will be performed. Although the cross effect of the different ingredients is probably not supporting the linear superimposition of effects, we have some preliminary indication about the effect of each choice.

5.1. Effect of Modification on Distance Metric

The effects of the different space deformation techniques are shown Fig. 3, with the error in the prediction as a function of the abscissa. Kriging is used to fit a simple parabola $y=x^2$, where x varies from -1 to 1. For each graph, the effect associated with the selection of a different variogram is shown. Lastly, a summary of the best situation for each selection of the variogram is shown in Fig. 3 (bottom right). The effect of the cubic terms is positive for all the different variograms, providing the lowest ϵ_{TV} in all the different cases. Tests are produced using the T&V approach for a 1D parabola, with five training point and two validation points.

Fig. 3: Square of error of estimate of function ($y=x^2$) for different variograms (γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_3) and different space deformations (no space deformation, quadratics term, quadratics term plus cubic terms, here indicated as 1, 2 and 3, respectively) as a function of x [-1:1]: from top to bottom, left to right, γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_3 . On bottom right, the best estimate, all obtained by using both second and third order terms for the different variograms.

Among the variograms, inverse exponential appears to be the best choice for this algebraic function. The behavior of the error is highly noisy, but this is probably associated with the really low value of the error (lower than 10^{-9}). From these tests on, we will exclude in further consideration other different space deformation, using both quadratic and cubic terms.

This first simple test is also useful to stress how different the computation of the error performed “a posteriori” on a large sample is from the computation of the error on a small training set. By tuning the parameters we minimize the error on the known part of the interval in which the function is defined, and nothing is known in the region between two training points. By changing the shape of the

variogram and deforming the space we can simply hope that the good fitting qualities obtained are also able to mimic the real behavior of the objective function in a wider region of the space. But the elements available to force this situation are fairly weak. In fact, if we look at the results in Fig. 4, we can observe how the combination providing the best fit on the training set is variogram 3 with the full space deformation. However, the best results for the “a posteriori” evaluation are provided by variogram 2. As a consequence, we are not completely aware of the risk of discharging a better configuration of parameters, because the criterion for the evaluation of the quality of the prediction is not fully adequate. Indeed, the differences between the final results and their quality support the conclusions that the approach is able to provide a better prediction with good global qualities.

Fig. 4: Error reduction on the training set connected with the use of a different variograms. Number of iterations is reported on the horizontal axis, and it has been normalized for convenience (1 indicating the last iteration).

5.2. Effect of Number of Spline Points on Variogram γ_3

For a preliminary check of the effect of different choices in the number of spline points for the variogram γ_3 , a classical 2D algebraic function adopted commonly in the optimization algorithm testing has been used, namely the “6 humps camel back”:

$$f = \left(4 - 2.1x^2 + \frac{x^4}{3} \right) x^2 + xy + (-4 + 4y^2) y^2$$

81 points were distributed uniformly (Cartesian grid 9x9) in the interval $x \in [-1.5, 1.5]$, $y \in [-1, 1]$. Nine points were adopted for validation. The remaining 72 points were used as training set. The T&V approach was applied: further comparisons with the results produced by LOO will be considered in the future.

Fig. 5: Effect of the number of spline points on the final result of the Kriging metamodel optimization
Dependence of the residual (left) and dependence on the global error (right)

Fig. 5 shows the residual on the validation points ε_{TV} and the global error on the true function for the optimal configuration as a function of the number of spline points. ε_{TV} is the objective function for the optimization problem here resolved for the tuning of the Kriging parameters, so that differences in the final results are a compromise between the adaptability of the spline variogram and the complexity of the optimization problem: in fact, the number of design variables increases while spline points are added, and also the space dimensions and complexity of the optimization problem increase accordingly. From Fig. 5, five and six spline points appear to be the best possible compromise between precision and complexity. Fig. 5 (right) stresses the incomplete coupling between the residuals and the global error of the true function. Anyway, the best of the global error coincides with the best of the residuals, so that the overall criteria of minimizing the residuals appear to be efficient.

5.3. Differences between LOO and T&V Approaches

In order to observe the differences between the two different approaches (LOO and T&V), the “6 humps camel back” function was adopted, but with a reduced training of 25 points only. Five validation points were selected for T&V.

From a first analysis of the computational aspects, T&V requires the determination of a single Kriging system in order to compute the prediction error on the validation points. Conversely, LOO requires the determination of N different Kriging systems, one for each training point, in order to compute the cumulative error. Each Kriging system implies the inversion of a $(N-1) \times (N-1)$ matrix: for this reason, LOO is computationally more expensive than T&V.

LOO computes the error associated with N different Kriging configurations, but all the N training points are used in the end: as a consequence, the error is computed by using a different configuration of the training points, while T&V optimizes the coefficient for a single Kriging system. In this sense, T&V is more consistent than LOO. On the other hand, LOO uses a larger training set, since no validation set is required. Another interesting aspect for T&V is the evaluation of variance on the validation points. Since we have information of the validation set, variance should be zero on the validation points. This quality is not preserved by T&V, since no guarantee is provided about the variance to vanish at the validation points as soon as some further conditions are enforced in the optimization problem. For this reason, some dedicated comparisons are needed in order to better qualify the results provided by the two approaches.

Results are reported in Table I. Here the summary of the results of some numerical experiments is reported. Results are presented for a single algebraic function; evidently a larger number of functions should be analyzed in order to draw more general conclusions: this first set of numerical experiments represents the starting point for a wider analysis to be performed.

Table I: Convergence and global error analysis for different variograms and techniques. Fitting error indicates the error computed at the validation points, global error is computed on a large number of points (a Cartesian grid of 101x101 points). Fitting error with variance does not include the term related with variance, in order to be comparable.

T&V				
Without variance		With variance		
Variogram	Fitting error	Global Error	Fitting error	Global error
γ_1	1.28938409E-04	0.205895111	5.28740473E-02	0.515460908
γ_2	1.65338668E-06	0.488002270	8.19981750E-02	0.270399034
γ_3	2.49037186E-07	0.443554938	1.88480451E-01	0.496517211
LOO				
γ_1	0.176805630	0.301389039		
γ_2	1.36263130E-04	3.34578681		
γ_3	0.229663536	0.337563127		

The three different variograms were tested on the two different approaches. For the T&V approach, the option of minimizing both ε_{TV} and μ_{TV} is also reported. This option is not considered for the LOO approach since in the final Kriging model the variance is zero at all the known points, with all the training points reintroduced.

A feature clearly shown in the results is the absence of a complete adherence between fitting error and global error. In other words, the configuration providing the smaller value of the fitting error does not provide the best value of the global error. This situation puts some shadows on the general approach. However, the configuration obtained after the parameter optimization provides still a large improvement with respect to the initial configuration, where a single variogram is adopted for all the points.

Fig. 6: Best and worst case as from Table I. T&V method (left), γ_1 , with variance; LOO method (right), γ_2 . True function (solid); interpolation by Kriging (dashed). Right picture is 3D in order to show the noisy behavior.

Variogram γ_2 represents the less stable option regarding the correlation between fitting error and global error, and this is particularly evident in the case of the LOO approach: we obtain a really small fitting error and a relatively large global error at the same time. γ_2 appears to be the variogram that takes more advantages by using the variance of the validation point as further criteria to be minimized, while γ_1 and γ_3 do not improve results obtained by simply minimizing the fitting error.

The poor fitting qualities of γ_2 are attributed to the noisy behavior. Some further conditions to avoid this situation can be added in order to regularize the solution: this will represent one of the elements of further studies.

5.4. Implications on Adaptive Training Set Generation

Peri (2009) presented a strategy for the determination of the optimal position of training points. Starting from an assigned DOE, the combined use of two different metamodels and the evaluation of the uncertainty associated to the two different estimates were used in order to determine regions of the design space still poorly explored by the training set: a new training point is suggested to be added onto each if those regions. The comparison between a static determination of the training set and the self-learning approach showed the latter to be superior. Similar results were also reported in *Zhao et al. (2011)*. Kriging provides itself a local variance of the fitting function, so that its usage in order to determine the location of new training points appears to be straightforward. Unfortunately, in the classical Kriging implementation sometime the estimated variance simply provides a quantity related to the measure of the distance between the current location and the closest point of the training set. This is connected with the assumption of a constant variogram for the entire design space. Conversely, once the variogram changes with space position, the variance is no more mimicking the distance from the training set, and it can be used in order to detect the correct place for the new training point.

Fig. 7: Variance provided by Kriging for uniform variogram (left) and optimized variogram (right)

Fig. 7 shows the case of a 2D parabola. Here, the variance provided by Kriging is strictly related to the distance of the computational point from the closest training point. All the maxima are equal, so that no preference is given for the nine positions evidenced. This is not a general behavior, but this occurrence is negative in the perspective of adopting the variance in the self-learning procedure. Furthermore, this behavior cannot be detected a priori, since it depends on the unknown objective function. Fig. 7 (right) shows the variance provided by the Kriging metamodel after adaptation: A clear location with high variance is evidenced. Further numerical experiments will clarify if this situation is positive or not in order to improve the training set by implementing a sequential addition of the training points as in *Peri (2009)*. Here a single example is reported, for a simple 1D problem. The algebraic function adopted is:

$$y = \sin\left(x + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) - \cos\left(x + \frac{\pi}{3}\right) + \sin\left(x + \frac{\pi}{3}\right)$$

defined in the interval $x \in [-1.5, 1.5]$. The initial design of experiment (DOE) was composed by five equally spaced points. Five more points were added by checking the location where the variance provided by Kriging had a maximum. For this first test, the LOO approach was adopted, since it guarantees zero variance at the training points.

Fig. 8: Results obtained by using the self-learning approach to define sequentially the training set. Global error as a function of the points added to the original DOE (left). Evolution of the function reconstruction as a new point is added to the original DOE (top left to bottom right on right).

Results are shown in Fig. 8. On the left part, the evolution of the global error as a function of the points added to the original DOE is shown. Different methods are applied in order to select the new point to add. As an ideal reference point, the location of maximum difference between the real fitting function and the Kriging interpolation is adopted. This is not commonly applicable, since it requires the knowledge of the function, but it is here reported as an extreme situation. Other two curves are representing the use of a second metamodel (Inverse Distance Weighted – IDW according to *Peri (2009)*) and the variance provided by Kriging as indicators. Finally, the global error provided by the DOE with ten points is reported, in order to check if there is some advantage in the application of the

self-learning strategy. Under this perspective, Kriging variance appears to be preferable to the use of a second metamodel for the identification of the point to be added to the training set. All the indicators are able to provide a final value of the global error lower than the one obtained by applying an equally-spaced DOE with the same final number of training points.

Fig. 8 (right) shows the evolution of the fit provided by Kriging. Dashed lines represent the true algebraic function, dots the positions of the training points. From top to bottom, left to right, we can observe the effect of the addition of a further training point. The selection method is, in this case, the Kriging variance.

6. Conclusions

Preliminary results for the optimal selection of Kriging parameters have been shown. Different methodologies and approaches have been presented, indicating some first guidelines for a more detailed analysis. Encouraging results have been obtained, even if a more extensive analysis is needed in order to better understand limits and possibilities of the suggested methodologies.

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Cooperative Autonomous Robotic Towing System – Exploitation of Autonomous Marine Vehicles in Emergency Towing Procedures

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Abstract

The CART (Cooperative Autonomous Robotic Towing system) Project proposes a new concept for salvage operations of distressed ships at sea based on the development of robotized unmanned marine platforms able to (semi-)automatically execute the high-risk operation of linking the emergency towing system of distressed ships to towing vessels. The CART device will be able to improve operations for safeguarding the environment, helping to reduce maritime oil pollution and risk for human lives. This paper describes the overall project concept, focusing on the developed robotic prototype and its experimental evaluation in real case scenarios.

1. Introduction

Oil spills in coastal areas (involving immediate and long-term effects on fragile marine ecosystems, fishing, tourism and recreation) cause environmental and socio-economic damages that often exceed first estimates. The costs of oil spills depend on different factors: type of oil, amount spilled and rate of spillage, physical, biological and economic characteristics of the spill location, weather and sea conditions, time of the year, and effectiveness of clean up, *White and Molloy (2003)*. The location of a spill affects the costs of an incident since it determines the requirements of clean-up response and the degree of damage to the environment and economic resources. Oil spills, if they remain at sea long enough, will dissipate through natural processes. Spills close to coastlines require costly clean-up operations. For example, the Amoco Cadiz accident (1978) reported a cost of \$282 million for a 220000 t spill. For spills of heavy, non-volatile oils, costs dramatically increase. For example, for the Nakhodka (1997), although involving a relatively small amount of oil (estimated 17500 to 20000 t), the compensation was settled at \$219 million.

The number of large oil spills (> 700 t) has decreased significantly during the last 40 years. The spills are mostly due to accidents such as collisions and groundings, *ITOPF (2009)*. In this context, Emergency Towing Systems can improve the efficiency of salvage operations and contribute to reducing the risk of ship grounding and thus oil spills. *IMO (2003)* gives an accurate cost-benefit analysis of Emergency Towing Systems (ETS), providing a clear view of the desirability of ETS for the different classes of ships, their installation and maintenance costs with respect to the avoidable risk and the amount of insurance premiums.

The main goal of ETS is to facilitate the physical connection between the towing vessel and the distressed ship. Classical operational procedures involve the supply of a thin rope, called “live-line”, connected to a more robust rope or chain, which actually tows the distressed vessel. Currently, the main ways of supplying the live-line are:

- line-throwing gun: a bullet, connected to the live-line is shot from the tug to the distressed ship, where it is recovered by the crew. Then the live-line is connected to the actual towing line, Fig.1;
- pick-up buoy: the crew of the distressed ship fix the live-line, or directly the messenger line, to a pick-up buoy, launched at sea before abandoning the ship, Fig.2.

Fig. 1: Line-throwing gun recovery procedure

Fig. 2: Pick-up buoy recovery procedure

On arrival to the site, the tug has to recover the pick-up buoy and its connected live-line, messenger and towing line, and then proceed to the towing operations.

Existing Emergency Towing Systems usually consist of a system for fast deployment and a pick-up buoy equipped with an emergency light and, in some cases, with an EPIRB (distress radio beacon) system for the transmission of position information. A close range between the tug and the ship is required – this is not always possible and often very dangerous. Moreover, when a line-throwing gun is used, the crew has to remain aboard the distressed vessel, which may be also dangerous.

The primary goal of the CART (Cooperative Autonomous Robotic Towing system) project is to develop a new safety-oriented concept and technology for salvage operations of distressed vessels at sea. The proposed concept relies on robotized unmanned marine vehicles able to (semi-)automatically execute the high-risk operation of linking the emergency towing system of distressed ship and tug.

2. Project concept

The CART concept is based on the idea of using advanced cooperative robotics technology for unmanned marine vehicles to improve the safety and feasibility of salvage operations. This can be done by

- combining the use of a pickup buoy named B-ART, robotized and able to manoeuvre in order to keep a safe position during the operations, deployed at sea from the distressed ship with a human operator aboard the tug, or
- with an unmanned semi-submersible vehicle (USSV), named ART, remotely controlled or supervised (according to its degree of autonomy), performing the recovery task, in the case of cooperative robotic operations.

The main objective of the CART project is the validation of a new robotics-based concept of intervention for the linking of the emergency towing system of distressed ships to tugs and salvage vessels of any type. The main objectives of the CART project are:

1. to validate the CART concept;
2. to perform application-driven research for cooperative marine robotic systems and guidance and control of small vessels in rough sea;
3. to transfer technology and know-how to industry.

For the purpose of the project development, three main case studies are considered for the CART concept application.

The first case study considers a conventional operating scenario where a tug needs to tow a barge,

ship, hull (parts), or any other floating object to a new destination. The towages can be quite long, between continents and crossing oceans. Therefore the towing system may face also severe weather conditions, which put high loads on tug, towed object and towing gear. During these operations a tug, equipped with a small crew (usually 5-6 people), is connected by a cable to the unmanned towed object. Tugs performing sea towages are usually required to have a long steel wire as a main towing line. Usually tugs have 500 – 900 m steel wire, as long and heavy wire form U-shape curve between a tug and a towed object, absorbing shocks by stretching it underwater due to own weight and water resistance. In order to operate such a long and heavy steel wire, tugs have towing winches installed on the aft deck. The other end of the main towing line is connected to the towed object. Good practice requires installation of emergency wire on a towed object, which is a polypropylene wire attached with cords to a side of a towed object (or packed onboard of a towed object) with one end freely floating in water and connected with a messenger rope to a pick-up buoy (also in water). In case the main towing line is broken, the tug has to come close to the towed object, find the pick-up buoy, get it out of the water, get the emergency towing line onboard and fasten it to the tug. The emergency towline has a lower breaking load and shock absorbing capabilities. However, it may help keeping the towed object in a safe position preventing it from drifting (which may result in grounding or another accident) or possibly to even continue towage. If the towing line breaks the main problem is recovering the floating buoy, often in harsh operational conditions. In rough seas or poor visibility (night, fog, rain, snow) it is difficult to find and pick the buoy up. Moreover, since the buoy is very small with respect to the tug, they could drift at different speed, and due to the combined effects of waves and wind, the buoy may displace under the towed object. In rough seas, it could be very/too dangerous to approach the towed object with the tug for recovering the emergency buoy.

The second case study considers a conventional operating scenario where a tug needs to tow a ship out of a harbour, e.g. a burning tanker in an oil terminal. State-of-the-art procedures foresee the deployment of a rope at sea by tankers during harbour operations. For fire aboard or any other accident requiring the emergency towing of the vessel outside the harbour for safety reasons, the tug has to recover that rope to connect the emergency towing line. Although the execution of this task could be supported by the use of fire-fighting equipment aboard the tug, it still requires the approach of the firing area with high danger for the human beings involved in the operations.

The third case study considers a scenario in which a ship in distress is rescued by another ship. Examples can be provided by naval vessels, where for protecting classified information the intervention of third-parties should be avoided, and by situations in which, in presence of risk of imminent environmental contamination, e.g. oil spills, tugs are only available at some days of navigation while other ships are in the area. In these very specific situations, ship-to-ship towing, where both vessels (towed and towing ship) are assumed to have crew aboard, able to deploy B-ART/ART systems, can be considered. In this scenario, a cooperative approach for recovering the towing line is considered. From the operational point of view, after the deployment of the two robotic vehicles, the vessel released by the distressed ship should behave as BART in the first scenario, i.e. moving away from the ship itself to reach a user defined position, while the rescue ART vehicle should manoeuvre (automatically or human piloted) in order to recover the B-ART Emergency Towing System.

3. Operative procedures

In the CART concept, the B-ART vehicle (i.e. the robotized platform deployed from the distressed ship) has the task of navigating to a reasonable distance from the ship in order to reach a safe and visible position where it can be easily recovered, Fig.3. The ART vehicle, launched from the support tug, has the task to autonomously move towards the buoy and "capture" it through a proper tying manoeuvre, Fig.4, allowing the recovery of the emergency line.

Fig. 3: B-ART vehicle moving away from distress ship

Fig.4: ART vehicle tying B-ART platform

3.1. Manual operating mode

Manual operating mode allows the human operator to drive the robotic platform applying different thrust force and torque commands to the vehicle. From experimental trials, a varying steering behavior, function of the surge speed of the vehicle, was evaluated. At zero or very low speed ($0 \div 5\%$ of the surge thrust force) a fast turning rate is obtained for very low torque command values ($1 \div 5\%$). As the surge speed increase, higher torque is required in order to steer the vehicle. This effect is mainly due to two factors: (1) the water flow tends to maintain the vehicle on the actual orientation at higher speeds; (2) the rope, attached to rear shackle, generates a "sail" effect which counteracts the steering torque. This "sail" effect can be increased further by the presence of sea currents. Still, observations of the sea trial results and impressions of the human operator piloting the vehicle indicate a very maneuverable vehicle. Fig. 5 shows an example of manual mode piloting.

(a) Vehicle motion

(b) Thrust force and torque commands

Fig. 5: Manual mode piloting

3.2. Automatic operating mode

The automatic operating mode allows the human operator to set a desired orientation that the vehicle will reach and maintain. Such an "autopilot" mode improves the motion capability allowing the vehicle to move along desired courses. This simplifies the maneuvers to be carried out in order the fulfill the operation task, especially in harsh and hostile sea conditions, where wind and current affect the motion of the vehicle and reduced visibility complicates the actions to be undertaken.

In order to speed-up the development and testing phases of the automatic operations, a simple

Proportional-Derivative (PD) control scheme was applied. The torque reference signal generated by the controller has the following form:

$$\tau = k_p (\psi^* - \psi) - k_d \dot{\psi}$$

ψ is the actual heading, ψ^* the desired orientation; k_p a tunable parameter for the proportional action, and k_d another settable value multiplying the time derivative of the heading. The tuning phase of the parameters was experimentally carried out, obtaining a good (empirically evaluated on the basis of the precision and response time of the control action) performance of the automatic regulator. The set value for the two parameters are $k_p = 0.03$ and $k_d = 0.01$.

The introduction of an integral compensation term in the torque generation law, i.e. an additional parameter multiplying the value of the sum of the orientation error during time, was evaluated. The introduction of such an integral term induced oscillations in the controller response and therefore the integral term was discarded. Fig.6 shows experimental results of the automatic heading control mode.

Fig.6: Automatic operating mode trial

3.3. Remote control operating mode

The remote control operating mode provides the highest level of operation autonomy of the CART system. Two guidance tasks are implemented for this working mode, depending on the actual vehicle: a line-following procedure for the B-ART vehicle, to move away from the distressed ship, and a circle-following behavior for the ART vehicle, for automatically capturing the robotized buoy.

3.3.1 Line-following procedure

Given a reference line, defined by the human operator choosing a suitable point (x^*, y^*) and

orientation ψ^* , the line-following procedure computes the cross-track distance d between the vehicle and the target line with: $d = (x^* - x)\sin(\psi^*) - (y^* - y)\cos(\psi^*)$, where the point (x,y) denotes the actual position of the vehicle.

On the basis of the distance error dynamics, expressed by the equation: $\dot{d} = u \sin(\psi - \psi^*)$, (d is the cross-track distance, u the surge speed of the vehicle and ψ the vehicle's orientation), a suitable guidance law obtained via Lyapunov method is designed obtaining: $\psi_r = \psi^* + \arcsin(-\gamma d)$. Here γ is a tunable parameter that sets the response behavior of the guidance system. Such a heading reference ψ_r is proven to asymptotically reduce the cross-track error to zero for any surge speed $u > 0$.

A result of the execution of a line-following example is shown in Fig.7. Fig.7(a) shows the convergence to and the maintenance of the motion over the red reference line; Fig.7(b) shows the computed heading reference (in red) and the actual heading (blue) converging to the target orientation.

Fig.7: Line-following experiment

3.3.2 Circle-following procedure

During circle-following operations, a target reference circle with a predefined radius is generated around a desired position. For the circle-following task, a particular case of the generic path-following approach, the design of a virtual target based guidance system is developed following *Bibuli et al. (2009)*. The along-track and cross track errors, namely s_l and y_l , are computed as follows:

$$s_l = -(x^* - x)\cos(\psi^*) - (y^* - y)\sin(\psi^*)$$

$$y_l = (x^* - x)\sin(\psi^*) - (y^* - y)\cos(\psi^*)$$

The point (x,y) is the actual position of the vehicle. (x^*,y^*) and ψ^* respectively denote the position and orientation of a virtual target that moves on the reference circle.

On the basis of the dynamic system of the kinematic error expressed by:

$$\dot{s}_l = -\dot{s}(1 - c_c y_l) + u \cos \beta$$

$$\dot{y}_l = -c_c \dot{s} s_l + u \sin \beta$$

\dot{s} is the speed of the virtual target along the reference path, c_c the local curvature of the path (equal to the inverse of the radius, for the circle-following case), $\beta = \psi - \psi^*$. The zeroing of the kinematic error, i.e. the convergence to and the following of the reference circle, is achieved through the implementation of two guidance laws: (1) one which regulates the evolution of the virtual target motion over the path, and (2) one computing the orientation that the vehicle has to assume in order to converge to the circle. The virtual target and orientation laws have the following expressions:

$$\dot{s}_r = u \cos \beta + k_s s_1$$

$$\psi_r = -\psi_a \tanh(k_y y_1)$$

k_s and k_y are tunable parameters, and ψ_a the maximum angle of attack, with respect to the local path tangent that the vehicle can assume to converge to the path.

Fig.8 shows the motion of the vehicle during a circle-following experiment; the vehicle was required to converge to and follow the red circle. The blue line highlights the behavior of the vehicle. The following of the circle is not very precise, with deviations in the order of meters from the desired position over the path, due to the above mentioned effects induced by cable and flow. Anyway, the task of turning around a target point, with the aim of capturing a floated object, is fully achieved.

Fig.8: Circle-following experiment

4. Vehicle prototype development

The vehicle frame consists of a horizontal trapezoidal double-T structure with top and bottom rings for housing electronics and battery canisters, respectively, two front and two rear rings for housing actuators, and one rear shackle for connecting the emergency towing line. The frame, built in stainless steel, is 900 mm long and 750 mm wide, and weighs 8.3 t. The brushless motor Maxon EC 4 pole 22 120W 311537 – 36V with Maxon Gearhead GP 22 HP was selected as thrust module for the CART vehicle. The power is supplied by Panasonic NCR-18650 Li-ion batteries, arranged in a cylindrical shape canister, arranged in three layers separated by intermediate flanges. The computing and I/O boards, a PCM-3362 PC/104-Plus Single Board Computer and a DMM- 32DX-AT PC/104-format data acquisition board respectively, are housed in a custom cylinder, also containing DC/DC converters, motor controllers, temperature and hall effect sensors for current measurements. The physical sub-systems are integrated by mounting thruster modules, electronics and batteries cylinders, buoyancy onto the main steel frame, Fig.9.

The thruster modules (each consisting of motor, propeller and nozzle) are mounted on the transversal elements, two on the front and two on the rear. Thruster modules on the front part are mounted closer to the main longitudinal axes, while rear modules are mounted at a reasonable distance. This mounting configuration is chosen in order to minimize interaction between front and rear thruster flows.

The buoyancy, constituted by expanded PVC, is mounted on a custom rail on the top of the vehicle, above the electronics' cylinder. It houses the radio antenna, visual signaling light and a waterproof box containing AHRS and GPS devices. Thanks to the custom rail, the horizontal mounting of the buoyant element can be changed, setting up the buoyancy position for balancing the vehicle, thus finding the optimal trim.

During missions, the vehicle is operated with a rope used for achieve capture operations. The employed rope is a Dyneema 10 mm - 4 t breaking load. The rope is tied to the vehicle by means of the shackle mounted on the rear part of the frame.

Fig.9: View of the assembled CART vehicle

Fig.10: Rope capture hook detail

For the project purpose of capturing a rope through proper maneuvers of the vehicle, a simple hooking mechanism was designed and mounted on the top part of the vehicle, above the buoyancy element, Fig.10. As shown in Fig.11, a hook lock rod is free to rotate around a pin. When the rope moves toward the lock rod, its motion opens the lock allowing the rope to enter inside the hook. Once the rod is free from the rope, the lock rod is closed by gravity action. The forward motion of the vehicle maintains the rope on the rear part of the hook, so that even if the lock accidentally opens, the rope will almost certainly remain inside the hook.

Fig.11: Rope capture hook mechanism

The overall software architecture of the CART system is composed by three different elements:

- the control software: executed on the vehicle computing architecture;
- the console software: executed on the remote piloting console;
- the human-machine interface software: executed on a remote computer, basically mimicking the functionalities of the piloting console and mainly used for debugging and testing phases.

The overall software architecture is organized as shown in Fig.12, where the control software, managing the functionalities of the vehicle, is linked to the remote operator station. The latter one is consists of the piloting console which is directly connected to the communication link on one side, and combined with the Human-Machine Interface (HMI) on the other side.

Fig.12: Overall software architecture

5. Experimental evaluation

Sea trials for real-case operating scenarios were carried out in Murter (Croatia) in October 2012 and Tallinn (Estonia) in November 2012. The performance of the CART framework was tested in single-vehicle trials, in order to verify the reliability and capabilities during operations, and in multi-vehicle trials testing the cooperative procedures to achieve the project goals.

5.1 Single-vehicle tests

Trials in restricted water were carried out inside the tug parking area of the port located outside the urban area of Tallinn. These trials focused on the procedure to capture and recovery a floating buoy deployed near a vessel.

The CART vehicle, remote control station, communication system and all the auxiliary equipment were set up on a tug provided by the Project partner PKL. The target buoy to be recovered was deployed by another tug. In particular, the vehicle was prepared, deployed and recovered from the tug stern main deck accessing the water from the stern gunwale, while the remote control station consisted of the control console, the laptop running the human-machine interface, and the wireless radio link were placed inside the command deck.

Because of the reduced field of view, given by the area of work, presence of the tug, space offered by the command deck, combined with the parallax effect given by long distance between the remote station and the vehicle (order of 50 - 100 m), it was decided, for the buoy capture tests, to operate the vehicle in the automatic working mode, i.e. commanding the reference orientations that the vehicle has to assume to accomplish the goal task.

Two buoy capture tests were executed. In the first one, the buoy was deployed close to the hull of a tug (simulating the distressed vessel). The task was to command the vehicle to navigate as close as possible along the hull of the tug and then turn around the buoy, in order to tie the CART vehicle rope around the buoy then dragging it away from the dummy "distressed ship". In particular, after turning around the buoy, the vehicle has to catch its own rope, by means of the hook system, in order to close the rope loop around the buoy when the CART vehicle is recovered by human operators. The sequence of the approach maneuvers to turn around the buoy is shown in Fig.13, showing the position of the vehicle close to the vessel hull, in order to move around and capture the vehicle. The motion of the vehicle during the first capture test is shown in Fig.14. Note the approach to the buoy position and the loop maneuver for the capture operation.

In the second experiment, the CART vehicle is commanded to execute a half-loop around the buoy, driving it directly towards the buoy's rope in order to capture it by means of the top-mounted hook system. Also in this case, the vehicle was operated in automatic working mode, commanding the desired orientations to achieve the task.

Fig.13: CART vehicle approaching the buoy during first capture experiment

Fig.14: Vehicle motion during first capture experiment

Fig.15 shows the sequence of the successful buoy's rope capture, while Fig.16 shows the approach to, turn around and towing of the buoy executed by the CART vehicle. Detailed pictures of the vehicle towing back the buoy to the tug and the particular of the rope captured by the top-mounted hook are shown in Fig. 17.

Trials in open sea, 3-4 km outside the tug port, were also carried out. In order to test the prototype vehicle in real operative conditions, the trial was executed during sunset time (around 16:00 pm) in sea condition with waves characterized by a width of about 1 - 1.5 m and a length of about 2 m, evaluation obtained by empirical observation. The sea trial was not focused only on the evaluation of navigation and capture capabilities of the CART vehicle, but also on the reliability of deployment and recovery operations of the robotic platform from the operating tug.

Fig.15: Buoy's rope capture during second capture experiment

Fig.16: Vehicle motion during second capture experiment

(a) CART vehicle towing the buoy

(b) The buoy's rope captured with the hook

Fig.17: Rope's capture details

The buoy was deployed downwind with respect to the tug, in order to let it float away from the tug itself, reaching a reasonable operating distance. The buoy is captured as in the port area experiments, heading the CART vehicle towards the buoy's rope, catching the latter one with the hook system. The operation is complicated by the low visibility and the motion uncertainties given by the wind, sea currents and waves affecting the operating area.

In order to achieve the buoy capture task, the vehicle is pushed towards on one side of the buoy and then commanded to turn around the buoy in order to cross the rope linked to the buoy. As already proven during port area tests, the rope is captured by the hook system. Once the rope is locked in the hook, the vehicle is driven back to the tug, helped by human operators pulling the vehicle's rope. The complete sequence of the buoy capture is shown in Fig.18.

Fig.18: Buoy capture sequence during open sea operation

5.2 Multi-vehicle framework tests

A two-phase test framework was set up emulating the behavior of the robotized platform. In a first phase, a path-following experiment along a straight line reference was carried out collecting motion data sets; in the second phase, the data set was used to feed the target position of the vehicle for the circular path-following, thus emulating the motion of the first vehicle that should be tied by the second one. The line-following data were synchronized with the execution of the circle-following task by means of the comparison of the time-stamps associated to all the telemetry data. In such a way, the remote control system of the vehicle, executing the circle-following task, tracked a reference circle

that appeared to move along a straight line. Fig.19 shows the result of the experiment, where the yellow vehicle turns around the red target vehicle moving on a straight line path.

Fig.19: Cooperative capture maneuver with coordinated line and circle following

6. Conclusion

This work has presented the design and development of a robotic platform to be exploited in the framework of the EU Project CART, focused on the introduction of unmanned marine vehicles in the procedures for ship towing in emergency situations. The results of the single-vehicle capabilities and performances have been reported, proving the validity of the design and development carried out. A preliminary multi-vehicle architecture development and test were carried out, proving the effectiveness of the concept.

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Lean ECO-Assistant Production for Trim Optimisation

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This paper describes the trim optimization tool ECO-Assistant and the project to streamline its production. The ECO-Assistant is an easy-to-use stand-alone software tool that delivers the optimum trim angle for a specific ship based on the operational parameters of speed, displacement and optionally water depth. The key ingredient of the ECO-Assistant is the comprehensive database of ship specific resistance data based on computational fluid dynamics (CFD). In order to satisfy the demand of ECO-Assistants a lean production process has been developed and implemented at FutureShip to transform the individual manufacturing approach for each project into a scalable lean work flow. The implemented process starts with standardised quotation and data collection procedures where relevant project and ship specific information is entered and administered in a global data model. An efficient and semi-automated CFD process was developed that allows the engineers to set up, run and monitor the simulations with well defined quality metrics. Post-processing and checking of results is also integrated into the production process, as well as importing results into the ECO-Assistant software tool for the customer and finalising the product. Through this lean project a scalable production process built around state-of-the-art CFD simulations has been implemented. Quality and throughput are increased while lead time and production resources are reduced.

1. Introduction

Increasing fuel prices and legislation concerning CO₂ emissions (respectively energy efficiency) have made the fuel efficiency of ships a key topic in our industry. While new designs offer much larger potential gains in energy efficiency, there are many refit and operational measures which may increase fuel efficiency in existing ships, and some of these offer attractively short payback times. We refer to *Bulhaug et al. (2009)*, *OCIMF (2011)* and *Bertram (2011)* for overviews of such measures. All these standard references for ship energy efficiency consider trim optimisation, which is a very cost-effective lever for increased energy efficiency for most ship types.

The influence of trim on fuel consumption has been known for quite some time. However, there is no single trim for a vessel that is optimum for all speeds, displacements and water depths, leave alone an optimum single-value for all ships. Finding the optimum trim for a ship is thus a non-trivial task. There are several commercial trim optimisation tools on the market to help with this task, which vary in price, user friendliness, fundamental approach and thus performance. We describe here our ECO-Assistant software tool and the considerations involved in reducing delivery time and production costs. Since the earlier presentation in *Hansen and Freund (2010)*, the tool has evolved in scope and quality of the fundamental hydrodynamic database. But the aim of the ECO-Assistant still is to help the crew to sail a vessel at optimum trim for a given operating condition (i.e. combination of speed and displacement).

Unlike most other trim assistance tools, the ECO-Assistant does not use logged operational data to calculate the optimum trim. Instead, it utilises a comprehensive database of ship specific resistance data for different operating conditions to compute the optimum trim. The ECO-Assistant can be seen as a product consisting of two parts:

1. A comprehensive database of ship specific data for the different operating conditions.
2. A user interface which makes the optimum trim information available to the crew onboard the vessel in a simple format.

Compared to trim assistance tools based on logged operational data, the ECO-Assistant does not require interfacing with the onboard systems or sensors to monitor operational parameters. The ECO-Assistant can be installed on any computer on the vessel, which makes the installation by very nature much more cost effective than sensor-based trim optimization tools.

The tool solely relies on the database input and the operational parameters entered by the crew. Of the operational parameters affecting optimum trim, the ECO-Assistant considers speed, displacement and optionally water depth. Other factors, such as seaway, are seen as secondary for the trim optimisation problem and therefore not considered. The ECO-Assistant provides information for the most fuel efficient sailing condition. Practical constraints such as bending moment and stability are checked by other software tools according to the crew's best practice. To support efficient cross-referencing, the ECO-Assistant can be integrated into a vessel's loading computer and cargo planning system.

The benefits of such trim optimisation were so convincing that FutureShip started to face production bottlenecks within one year of launching the product. The short-term solution was "borrowing" manpower from other departments of GL Group, raising the ceiling for permissible overtime and acquiring additional computational resources. However, it became rapidly clear that a more fundamental solution was desirable as the demand was likely to grow further rather for years to come before a saturation of the market would lead to gradual decline in demand. Thus the idea for a lean production for ECO-Assistant was born.

2. The way to lean production

The challenge was to transform a manufacturing-type engineering service where every customer project was different and where new methods and processes were developed and tested within each project into a lean production process, where production and process development would be separated. In order to cope with the rapidly rising demand, a scalable process was required that no longer depended on unique knowledge and experience of different experts.

In order to kick-start this transformation a reorganisation project was conducted in the third quarter of 2011. To have professional assistance and best practice examples available, FutureShip decided to work with a professional lean process consulting firm. Porsche Consulting was chosen because of their competence in transferring lean principles from a production environment into an engineering environment as well as from the automotive industry into other branches and from large organisations into small highly flexible organisations. First proof of their expertise in this specific area could be seen during the assistance and consulting of the America's Cup challenger United Internet Team Germany in 2007 and 2008.

The reorganisation project consisted of three phases, *NN (2011)*:

1. Analysis phase

Interviews, workshops and trainings were conducting during the first phase. The company and business models were analysed so that the project boundaries and detailed scope could be defined. "Lean" principles were taught to enable the project team to record the current process and organisation structure. As a result, critical process steps and key areas for improvements with associated potential for improvement were identified.

2. Concept phase

In workshops, tasks were prioritised and the new target process was developed as shown in Fig.1. Standards, methods and tools were defined for each process step. A reporting system and the organizational structure resulting from the new process were laid out and an implementation plan with quality gates was developed. "A quality gate is a special milestone in a software project. Quality Gates are located before a phase that is strongly dependent on the outcome of a previous phase," [Wikipedia].

3. Piloting and implementation planning phase

In workshops and trainings the new target process and the implementation plan were communicated and one process standard was developed as a pilot implementation. The final results of the reorganisation project were presented to the steering group and implementation of the target process in 2012 was decided.

Fig. 1: Representation of target process with quality gates

3. The lean production process

The new process was implemented in the year 2012. The new process foresees specialised project engineers which take responsibility for the specific project work flow at its full scope. This provides a clear separation between project work with released standards and development and testing of new features.

New features are only released into production process after thorough validation and testing. Key steps in the production process are described in the following:

1. Collect initial data

Data required for the ECO-Assistant (or more specifically for the computation of the hydrodynamic database) is collected from clients by the project manager with a “List of Documents” describing requirements. The list ensures that required data is collected once avoiding disruption in the production process for reasons of incomplete data. Data is entered by the project manager directly in a global data model via a user-friendly interface, Fig. 2. This makes it easy to identify missing data and check data quality. It also ensures a consistent data management avoiding double data keeping. One global data model is used for the whole process including shipping information for the final product (which is delivered as a CD-ROM).

Fig. 2: User interface for data input

2. Define simulation range

Once data is entered the simulation range can be defined easily within the interface, Fig. 3. With standard graphical output, the simulation range is discussed and agreed upon with the customer.

Fig. 3: User interface for definition of simulation range

3. Create hull geometry

- For CFD simulations, a geometry model is needed. Often the customer does not have the required 3D surface model. In this case, the hull geometry has to be remodelled. A process has been developed which allows working with external service suppliers as well as internal resources. This includes a specification for suppliers of deliverables and a standardized process of checking the delivered geometry for accuracy and usability for CFD analyses. For in-house modelling, a standardized process for efficient remodelling was set up. This process supports flexible importing of structural design drawings and a correction for distorted drawings (due to printing and scanning). Structural design drawings contain 2D geometry information for frames and the centre-plane curve, Fig.4 (left). This 2D geometry information is combined with sparse user input to generate automatically a 3D hull surface, Fig.4 (right).

Fig. 4: Frames and centre-plane curve from construction drawings (left); lofted hull surface (right)

Various checks are performed, before the geometry is passed on for further processing:

- The hull geometry is checked for fairness and accuracy.
- The hull description is checked for surface quality required for meshing.
- Hydrostatics is checked against known data for the ship.

4. Generate CFD grid

Prior to meshing, grid sections (“patches”) are defined on the hull surface. The actual grid generation follows a quality assessed procedure and is fully automated. The grid is locally refined near the free surface (intersection of water and air where the waves form) and in regions with expected high flow gradients. Depending on the CFD tool used different meshing routines are available in the process. We employed HEXPRESS and our automated in-house grid generation software based on SnappyHexMesh. Local refinement information for each patch, as well as vessel particulars (principal dimensions, drafts aft and fore, speeds, trim values) are taken from the global data model. Fig.5 shows an example of the result of this process.

Fig. 5: CFD mesh for a container ship

5. Run CFD computations

With the generated grid and information from the global data model in place, the CFD simulations can be started. Different CFD tools can be used in the process. Originally, an in-house wave resistance code (based on Rankine panels) was used, later enhanced by selective RANSE (Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations) simulations, *Hansen and Freund (2010)*. Today, the simulations are completely based on RANSE solvers and numerical propulsion tests with a body-force propeller model. So far, we have employed the following RANSE solvers: ISIS-CFD and our in-house RANSE solver based on OpenFOAM. The simulations are performed for full-scale Reynolds numbers, i.e. the flow conditions of the ship rather than those in a model basin. Full-scale simulations enhance the accuracy of the CFD model significantly in certain critical conditions, as discussed in *Hochkirch and Mallol (2013)*. The associated computational power is furnished by parallelized HPC (high-performance computing). A standardized set-up supports monitoring the large number of parallelized simulations. Fig.6 shows automatically generated and updated convergence plots. Sophisticated convergence criteria stop simulations at the appropriate time to ensure consistent accuracy and economic computing times.

a) Convergence

STA	PERC	CO?	DATE	150Fx	300Fx	150Sinkage	150TrimRad	CONVERGENCE	CASEPATH
FIN	74%	CON	04:23:25	-8.628e+04	-8.598e+04	-7.922e-02	1.055e-03	(CC Cn)	CC CC calcs/geo1/T_09_40/gIIsis/gp1/v_08_50/cp1/TR_07/isis
FIN	100%	NCO	11:48:40	-8.836e+04	-8.803e+04	-7.126e-02	-4.404e-03	(Cn Cn)	CC CC calcs/geo1/T_09_40/gIIsis/gp1/v_08_50/cp1/TR_09/isis
RUN	67%	NCO	16:29:33	-8.945e+04	-8.896e+04	-7.702e-02	-9.879e-03	(nn nn)	CC CC calcs/geo1/T_09_40/gIIsis/gp1/v_08_50/cp1/TR_11/isis
FIN	100%	NCO	10:04:12	-9.327e+04	-9.302e+04	-9.788e-02	-1.537e-02	(Cn Cn)	CC CC calcs/geo1/T_09_40/gIIsis/gp1/v_08_50/cp1/TR_13/isis
RUN	83%	NCO	16:29:35	-1.172e+05	-1.169e+05	-2.265e-01	1.784e-02	(Cn Cn)	CC CC calcs/geo1/T_09_40/gIIsis/gp1/v_10_00/cp1/TR_01/isis
RUN	77%	NCO	16:29:39	-1.168e+05	-1.164e+05	-1.743e-01	1.244e-02	(Cn Cn)	CC CC calcs/geo1/T_09_40/gIIsis/gp1/v_10_00/cp1/TR_03/isis

b) Summary of simulation jobs

Fig. 6: Interface for simulation monitoring

Fig. 7: Automatically generated views for checking the simulations

6. Check results

After the simulations, results are checked against various criteria. Fig.7 shows some typical post-processing results. CFD results are validated against towing tank and sea trials data whenever possible. Project managers enter validation data into the global data model at the outset of the project. Thus at this stage, instant comparison is possible. The results are also compared for plausibility against similar ships in our database.

7. Final integration into the ECO-Assistant software tool

The checked and approved data is incorporated in the ECO-Assistant tool. The discrete simulation data sets are connected by a multi-dimensional response surface. This allows continuous display of results and consistent interpolation for arbitrary input values within the simulated range, Fig.8.

Fig. 8: Multi-dimensional fit of simulation data; calculated (red) and interpolated (green) points

8. Completion of ECO-Assistant

The ECO-Assistant has a graphical user interface (GUI) that uses the centre-plane curve to show schematically the investigated ship with simplified superstructure. The interface is kept simple with a minimum of user input: speed, drafts aft and fore, and optional extra ballast. The tool then displays optimum trim, regions of good trim values (in green), regions of satisfactory trim (in yellow) and regions of poor trim (in red). In addition, the savings in required power and tons of fuel and CO₂ per day as compared to the initial trim are displayed. Fig.9 shows the user interface of the ECO-Assistant for a sample ship.

9. Delivery of ECO-Assistant

The ECO-Assistant is burned on CD-ROM and an associated hardware dongle (key) produced automatically. The completed product is then shipped to the customer.

Fig. 9: GUI of finished ECO-Assistant

4. Lean organisation structure to support lean production

To support the lean production process, several mechanisms were implemented in the support organization. The project coordination and management are important as up to 12 ECO-Assistants can be produced in parallel. From the global data model, status reports can be generated by the engineers for project control. These reports are condensed into an aggregated status list for the production manager to support multi-project management.

If changes to the planned production process or schedule become necessary a decision request form is integrated into the status report set-up to facilitate value oriented escalation. A committee structure of two levels was established for production process control and decision requests ruling.

Key performance indicators (KPIs) for customer satisfaction, production cost, delivery reliability, processing time and lead time were established to monitor the process. KPIs are essential for measuring the process performance and utilising the established continuous improvement process

5. Conclusions

The streamlined and highly automated process was implemented within one year, in parallel to the regular business. By late 2012, processing time from order to delivery had been reduced on average by 27%. The target reduction by 43% is expected to be achieved by mid-2013 driven by a continuous improvement process. The lean process with quality gates reduces loops and uncertainty significantly so that delivery reliability and quality have been increased.

Key ingredients for the lean process were the separation of production and development with controlled implementation of tool/process upgrades and standardisation of tasks. A clear definition of responsibilities and effective utilisation of key competencies has shown to be important. The

reorganisation project to kick-start lean production was important in enabling and accelerating the process transformation project.

Acknowledgements

We sincerely thank our project partner Porsche Consulting GmbH for the contribution towards lean production, especially Oliver Kayser, Stefan Tabatabai, Michael Leyh and Martin Vu for their commitment to this project. We also thank our colleagues at FutureShip GmbH for their support, in particular Volker Bertram and Daniel Schmode.

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On the Importance of Full-Scale CFD Simulations for Ships

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Abstract

This paper shows that differences between model-scale flows and full-scale flows can have significant effects. In various projects, we observe that ranking of design candidates in optimization or operational conditions in trim optimization may change for model-scale and full-scale computations. The changes between model scale and full scale concern primarily the relatively different boundary layer, but also wave breaking, in particular behind transom sterns. For simulation-based design projects, full-scale analyses are thus advisable. For formal optimization, constraints in time and computational resources make a selection of chosen approach more complicated. Hybrid computing schemes, reusing CFD (computational fluid dynamics) knowledge and meta-modelling are seen as techniques to pave the way towards using full-scale CFD also as standard option in optimization.

1. Introduction

Energy efficiency has become the dominant topic for ship operators ever since in 2008 the fuel prices started to explode. As propulsion accounts for 60-90% (depending on ship type and speed) of the energy consumption of ships, the limelight is on measures to reduce fuel consumption. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is widely seen as a key technology in this respect. CFD denotes techniques solving fluid dynamics equations numerically, usually involving significant computational effort. See *Bertram (2011)* and *Molland et al. (2011)* for an introduction to CFD for ship and propeller flows.

More colloquially, CFD for resistance and propulsion analyses is sometimes referred to as the “numerical model basin” or the “numerical towing tank”. While these expressions are popular with the general public, the term “numerical sea trials” would be more appropriate, as CFD nowadays often simulates the flow around ships at full-scale Reynolds numbers. High-fidelity CFD refers to RANSE (Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations) solvers which employ fine grids and advanced turbulence models. As high-fidelity CFD requires considerable computational effort and specialised user skills, the industry is looking often for cheaper and simpler alternatives. The most common questions are then:

- Can’t we use potential flow codes (which are found in many ship design offices)?
- Can’t we use existing model tests?

The debate over model tests versus CFD is old and often more emotional than rational. The law of the instrument or Maslow’s hammer has been aptly formulated by *Maslow (1966)*: “I suppose it is tempting, if the only tool you have is a hammer, to treat everything as if it were a nail.” Fortunately, we have now a variety of tools at our disposal. In fact, we have experience in all three tools under discussion for ship hull assessment and improvement: model tests, potential-flow codes (based on panel methods), and high-fidelity CFD for full-scale simulations. We are thus in a position to discuss above questions based on professional experience.

2. Scale effects

For a long time, naval architects had to rely almost exclusively on model tests for insight into ship hydrodynamics. The traditional resistance decomposition into viscous parts and wave parts has shaped our concepts of resistance and propulsion for generations. The advent of numerical ship hydrodynamics initially enforced this, as free-surface potential-flow codes addressed wave resistance without capturing viscosity. With the progress in CFD and a series of dedicated validation workshops and research projects after the year 2000, we have now a more differentiated view on scale effects among

ship hydrodynamics experts. However, few ship designers are aware of these specialised publications. We therefore recall the main scale effects here:

- **Boundary layer**
The boundary layer is relatively thinner in full-scale flows than in model test conditions. The wake fraction is therefore larger in model tests than in full scale. Propulsion improving devices operate (at least partially) in the boundary layer, which results in different behaviour of such devices between model scale and full scale.
- **Flow separation and vortex formation**
Flow separation is generally delayed in full scale and vortices encounter higher damping. Thus ship wakes in the propeller plane are significantly changed. Vortices from bilge or struts are much weaker and vanish sometimes altogether in full-scale simulations, e.g. *Visonneau et al. (2006)*.
- **Wave breaking**
The decomposition of a ship resistance into wave resistance, frictional resistance and viscous pressure resistance is artificial. In reality, wave making and viscous flows interact. Changes in the viscous flow field lead to changes in the wave pattern. Especially in the aftbody, this interaction can be significant. *Mizine et al. (2009)* give an example, where the modification of the pressure field results in a local suction of the free-surface leading to local wave breaking, which dramatically increases the resistance.

Visonneau et al. (2006) come to the conclusion that a “[...] complete analysis of the scale effects on free-surface and of the structure of the viscous stern flow reveals that these scale effects are not negligible and depend strongly on the stern geometries.”

3. Engineering assessment of hulls and appendages

Generally, we can assess services in terms of time, quality (in the case of hydrodynamic prediction this means accuracy) and cost. For numerical ship hydrodynamics, this is discussed in more detail in *Bertram (2011)*. Academia tends to focus exclusively on accuracy, but in practical design projects there is no benefit in finding a better hull shape after the ship has been built. Tight constraints on time and budget force us to make concessions on accuracy, for example neglecting some aspects of scale effects.

The main tools for ship hull design and optimization are discussed in the following sub-chapters. The focus lies here on a global understanding for ship designers and operators. We will not go into details of variations of techniques. For a more profound discussion, we refer to the given references.

3.1. Rankine panel methods

Fully non-linear wave resistance codes based on Rankine panels have been extensively used in ship design since the 1990s, *Bertram (2011)*. Well-known codes used in commercial applications include SHIPFLOW-XPAN, SHALLO, RAPID, SWIFT, and FSWAVE/VSAERO. We employ FS-Flow, e.g. *Hochkirch and Bertram (2012)*, which is a comparable in-house development of FutureShip. The state of the art is well documented in two PhD theses, *Raven (1996)* and *Janson (1996)*. Despite occasional contrary claims, all ‘fully non-linear’ wave resistance codes have similar capabilities and similar shortcomings. Pros and cons of Rankine panel methods are:

- ☺ The codes capture global wave patterns and predict dynamic trim and sinkage well in most cases.
- ☺ The codes are very fast. Processes for grid generation and computation have been fully automated and computational times may be less than a minute for one speed and one geometry on a regular single-processor computer.

- ⊗ The codes reach limits of applicability for flows with breaking waves, semi-planing or planing boats, and extreme non-linearity. Typical critical cases are emerging bulbous bows and immersing transom sterns with the associated complex wave breaking.
- ⊗ Viscous effects (such as a recirculation zone at the stern or wave-boundary layer interaction) cannot be modelled correctly.

The automation and the short computational times have fostered wide-spread acceptance in ship design and with some time delay also in ship hull optimization. See *Hochkirch and Bertram (2012)* for various examples. Also simulations for trim optimization were initially based exclusively on Rankine panel methods, *Hansen and Freund (2010)*.

3.2. Free-surface RANSE methods

Our high-fidelity CFD applications shown here are based on FINETM/Marine, which can be seen as representative of leading-edge CFD marine software. FINETM/Marine is a CFD product of NUMECA International. This software suite is dedicated to marine applications and integrates:

- Full-hexahedral unstructured mesh generator HEXPRESSTM, Fig.1
- Free-surface RANSE solver ISIS-CFD, *Duvigneau et al. (2002,2003)*: Turbulent flow is simulated by solving the incompressible unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations (RANS). The solver is based on the finite volume method to build the spatial discretization of the transport equations. The face-based method is generalized to two-dimensional, rotationally symmetric, or three-dimensional unstructured meshes for which non-overlapping control volumes are bounded by an arbitrary number of constitutive faces. The velocity field is obtained from the momentum conservation equations and the pressure field is extracted from the mass conservation constraint, or continuity equation, transformed into a pressure equation. In the case of turbulent flows, additional transport equations for modelled variables are discretized and solved using the same principles. Several turbulence models ranging from one-equation model to Reynolds stress transport model are implemented in ISIS-CFD. Free-surface flow is simulated with an interface capturing approach. Both non-miscible flow phases (air and water) are modelled through the use of a conservation equation for a volume fraction of phase. The free-surface location corresponds to the isosurface with volume fraction $\alpha = 0.5$. To avoid any smearing of the interface, the volume fraction transport equations are discretized with a specific discretization scheme which ensures the accuracy and sharpness of the interface. More details are given in *Queutey and Visonneau (2007)*.
- Dedicated flow visualizer CFView, Fig.2

Fig.1: Mesh generation with HEXPRESSTM

Fig.2: Flow visualization with CFView

FINE™/Marine has been validated against model tests for a variety of test cases, e.g. *Mizine et al. (2009)*. The performance of the code has been also demonstrated in computations at model and full scale for a fully appended hull configuration including free-surface, ducted propeller, brackets and rudder, *Visonneau et al. (2006)*. The computations agree well with full-scale measurements (within the EU project EFFORT). This indicates that CFD tools may be used with confidence to predict full-scale conditions in ship design.

Various CFD codes can capture full-scale viscous flows with free surfaces. However, good quantitative predictions require advanced techniques as offered by FINE™/Marine and sufficient grid resolution. Pros and cons of free-surface RANSE methods are:

- ☺ The codes capture global and local wave patterns including complex breaking waves.
- ☺ The codes are capable of capturing viscous effects at full scale.
- ☹ The computational times are significant, even on parallel processor architectures.
- ☹ Quality of results differs significantly between various CFD service suppliers. It is difficult for the general public to identify competent and less competent suppliers.

Free-surface RANSE codes are the standard choice in designing propulsion improving devices and ship aftbodies, i.e. cases where viscosity effects dominate. Application in ship design are much more widespread than in optimization where the high computational effort requires a combination of massive computing power and smart optimization strategies.

3.3. Model basin tests

The basic idea of model testing is to experiment with a smaller model to extract information that can be scaled (transformed) to the real ship. Ship models in professional tests are 4-12 m in length and may weigh up to a ton. Manufacturing these models is a time-consuming task and requires expert knowledge. Professional model tests give high accuracy for bare-hull model tests, but full-scale predictions between various model basins show much larger scatter. Part of the problem is that model tests violate several similarity laws, foremost Reynolds similarity which governs viscous flow effects. Appendages generally make scaling more difficult, because they are strongly affected by viscosity effects such as differences in boundary layers and vortex formation. Techniques such as tuft tests and paint streak tests give (limited) insight into local flow details.

- ☺ Widely known in the industry and de facto standard for power predictions.
- ☺ Industry standards exist for most procedures through ITTC (International Towing Tank Conference) as international expert body. Therefore all larger model basins listed by ITTC offer comparable quality in services.
- ☹ Scaling laws are violated by necessity.
- ☹ Model tests are time-consuming and expensive.
- ☹ Parallel operation is not possible.

In summary, model tests suffer from scale effects like panel methods and are slow and expensive as RANSE simulations, albeit without the hope of parallel operation which makes RANSE simulations increasingly feasible also for wide-spread design investigations and optimization projects. Model tests are hardly suitable for appendages such as propulsion improving devices due to scale effects.

For trim optimization, model tests are also hardly suitable. Trim optimization for most ship types require sufficiently fine coverage of a range of speeds, drafts and trim angles to be accurate. Certain intermediate draft and trim conditions will feature discontinuities, when bulbous bows emerge and transom stern immerse. The associated breaking wave patterns show larger scale effects than “benevolent” loading conditions such as the design draft and trim.

4. Case studies

4.1. Trim optimization

Military Sealift Command (MSC) operates a large fleet of diverse vessels, primarily to support the US Navy. As trim significantly affects fuel consumption, MSC initiated a study to evaluate how fuel consumption dependence on trim can be best assessed. Full-scale sea trials with one ship identified substantial savings to be made by choosing the best trim. However, the associated effort of such sea trials is high, making the approach uneconomical. Therefore FutureShip was tasked to evaluate trim dependence by traditional model testing and CFD simulations. The model tests were performed at the Hamburg Ship Model Basin (HSVA). The CFD simulations used FINETM/Marine.

The analyses focused on calm-water powering performance, specifically on changes of the delivered power (P_D) requirement. CFD simulations were performed both for full scale and for model scale (1:25.67). The study showed that generally all three methods (i.e. full-scale measurements, model tests, and CFD) agreed well with each other concerning the trends in power requirement with respect to trim. As full-scale data were available only for a few sailing conditions, most comparisons focused on CFD and model test results. The ranking derived from CFD simulation at model scale agreed very well with model tests, Fig.3 (left). However, for certain conditions, the model basin extrapolations to full scale deviated significantly from the CFD prediction, Fig.3 (right).

Fig.3: Change in total resistance R_T with trim for one speed and draft; model scale (left) and full scale (right);

HSVA = model tests / model test extrapolation; CFD = computations with FINETM/Marine

4.2. Hull optimization

For a new build project of a 2300 TEU container ship, a ship owner and a ship yard agreed on a formal hull optimization to improve fuel efficiency of the new design across an operational profile of service conditions. The parametric design for the optimization had 65 free form parameters. The ship owner specified nine operational conditions (combinations of draft and speed), with an associated weight reflecting the estimated time the vessel would sail in each condition. Constraints were imposed on displacement, stability, and several hard points (deck for container stowage, aftbody for engine, forebody for bow thruster, etc.)

1. A concept exploration model was set up based on a wave resistance calculation. Displacement constraints were relaxed allowing 4% deviation for wider design exploration. More than 6000 variants were thus investigated covering the design space with a quasi random sequence (SOBOL algorithm). This concept exploration served as discussion basis for the next stage with more constrained specifications. The pre-optimization study revealed already significant potential for hull improvement, Fig.4.

Fig.4: Wave pattern and hull pressures for one operational case computed by potential-flow based pre-study; baseline design (bottom) and best design of pre-study (top)

2. The most promising design candidate from the pre-study was selected for an optimization restart focusing on the aft body flow and the wake characteristics, using a RANSE solver and performing numerical propulsion tests. This proper optimization loop considered more than 3000 aftbody variants, considering resistance and wake as indicators for least power and fuel consumption, however, it must be considered, that the full scale wake significantly differs from the model scale prediction, Fig.5. The wave pattern shows significant improvement, Fig.6.

Fig.5: Nominal wake for one operational condition; model scale (left) and full scale (right)

Fig.6: Wave pattern for one operational condition; baseline (bottom) and optimized design (top)

The optimized hull design had approximately 8% lower required power P_D compared to the baseline design. In addition, the stability was improved adding 14 cm to the KM value at scantling draft.

4.3. Appendage improvement

Appendages contribute above proportion to fuel consumption of ships. The rise in fuel costs has led to a renaissance in interest in propulsion improving devices (PIDs). These are generally appendages in the aftbody of the ship, in the (upstream or downstream) vicinity of the propeller. As such, PIDs are strongly affected by scale effects. An OCIMF (Oil Companies International Marine Forum) report on energy efficiency measures for large tankers sums up, *NN (2011)*: “Opinions on propulsion improving devices scatter widely, from negative effects (increasing fuel consumption) to more than 10% improvement. Full scale CFD simulation [during design] [...] may reduce the present uncertainty.” *Zorn et al. (2010)* compare the effect of a propulsion improving device both in model and in full scale, and both on resistance and propulsion, Fig.7. The investigation is typical for the lowest level of hydrodynamic design involving PIDs, namely just the comparison of two variants (with and without a given nozzle geometry and arrangement). Such an investigation should always be performed at full scale and including the propeller in the computational model.

Fig.7: Numerical propulsion test for tanker with nozzle; streaklines (wall shear stress streamlines) for

model scale (left) and full scale (right); *Zorn et al. (2010)*
Similar analyses have been used to improve “negative” appendages, i.e. recesses in ship hulls, such as bow thrusters, Fig.8.

Fig.8: Bow thruster analyses using full-scale RANSE

Yu (2011) investigates a twisted rudder. After the classical investigation of two geometries (twisted and not twisted), he couples the FRIENDSHIP Framework to the CFD solver to reduce the rudder drag by 12% (for given rudder lift force) which corresponds roughly to 1% fuel savings. Fig.9 shows an application for an optimization of headbox and twisted rudder for a twin-skeg vessel. As the rudders of twin-skeg vessels are much closer to the free surface, their impact on the wave pattern is not negligible and fine tuned optimization is required to achieve best fuel efficiency.

Fig.9: Twisted rudder behind propeller in CFD optimization study

Such formal optimization studies reflect the current state of the art in industry. However, only few projects provide sufficient time and budget to spend similar attention and resources on appendages as on the main hull. We expect this to change, as response time for such analyses will decrease with time and attention to appendages is likely to increase with fuel prices.

5. Techniques to open the door for wider full-scale CFD applications

Various techniques contribute to making formal optimization projects based on full-scale CFD applicable feasible also for industry projects:

- Progress in “brute-force” computing power
Computer performance has increased with time. Recent predictions indicate an accelerated growth rather than a slowing down of this trend, *Couser et al. (2011)*. There is not only exponential growth in the computing power per se, but also – more importantly – in computing power per dollar.
- Parallel computing
Domain parallelization is a standard technique in RANSE solvers. Current parallelization practice can be extended to achieve further progress in response time. Besides extending domain parallelization to more cores (where the added gain decreases with number of cores), RANSE simulations can also be parallelized in time, *Ferziger and Peric (2010)*. In addition, evolutionary optimization strategies such as multi-objective genetic algorithm (MOGAs) compute several variants in parallel. However, progress in parallelization is deemed to be the least contributing factor in advancing full-scale optimization for ships.
- Restart from related case
RANSE computations are always iterative. Much computational time can be saved if the computation starts from a good approximation of the flow to be solved. Many RANSE solvers offer the possibility to start from an arbitrary approximation, initially intended to interrupt a RANSE computation and restart it at a later time. During an optimization, there are many variations which are close to each other, e.g. similar shapes for same speed in hull optimization or similar load conditions (draft and trim) in trim optimization. While the first computations take much time, subsequent computations employing the existing approximations of the flow field are much faster.
- Meta-modelling
Meta-models (or surrogate models) employs approximation techniques (Kriging, neural nets, response surfaces, etc.) to reduce the number of expensive CFD evaluations in optimization projects, e.g. *Peri (2009)*, *Peri and Diez (2013)*, *Couser et al. (2011)*.

6. Conclusions

Design constraints, especially in available time in design projects, force us to use simpler approaches. In each case, a balance between available resources and required accuracy has to be found. Progress in algorithms and computing hardware shift this balance towards better and more accurate models. Simpler methods such as panel methods or model-scale investigations have their usefulness, as demonstrated in many projects. However, our experience confirms the observation of *Duvinneau et al. (2002,2003)*: “[...] the information given by the model scale computations is useful for the full-scale problem, but only in terms of trend. When the fitness of the shape optimized at model scale is evaluated at full scale, it can be seen that about three-quarters of the improvement is obtained compared with the optimization at full scale.” Thus we get trends, we get even significant improvement, when using model-scale analyses, but we may also miss out on significant further improvement.

Advances in available brute-force computing power, parallel computing, re-use of knowledge from other computations (restart and meta-modelling) will eventually open to path to wide-spread application of full-scale computations. This is a natural evolution which has started already and we expect that full-scale CFD analyses also for optimization projects will become standard within the next decade.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful for the assistance of Volker Bertram and Daniel Schmode (FutureShip) for this paper.

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The Impact of Design Tools: Looking for Insights with a Network Theoretic Approach

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Abstract

The choice of design tools fundamentally predicates the information used to make design decisions, and thus to some degree affects what the outcome will look like, regardless of process or organization. This paper will introduce a network theory based framework that can resolve the fundamental relationships within design tools, producing lead indicators on the potential outcomes of larger design structures. To illustrate the framework, a network model of a classic marine design tool will be used. Background and contrast with existing design structure analysis methods will be presented. Future research on expanding the framework to include other design structures will also be discussed.

1. Introduction

Experts in the defense acquisition community have said that the acquisition process should be structured around the following three questions, in order:

1. What to buy?
2. How to buy it?
3. Who to buy it from?

The first question is inherently product focused, the second process focused and the third organization focused. Given this rational state of affairs, it is no wonder that design research has also focused primarily on product, process or organization. However, even in an ideal world, the complexity of acquired systems seems to result in an equally, if not more, complex acquisition program. Unfortunately, “This situation is not new. Throughout history, inventions and new technology have often gotten ahead of their scientific underpinnings and engineering knowledge, but the result has always been increased risk and accidents until science and engineering caught up”, *Leveson (2011)*. Optimizing an acquisition program's structure is merely an academic exercise unless methods exist to understand how the structure functions in the first place, a view shared by those trying to improve the ship design process, *Cooper et al. (2011)*. This research is not advocating a better acquisition structure (process, product or organization together), but the development of a framework to increase the understanding of any such structure, ideal or not. This framework will serve as a lead indicator, used prior to beginning and during an acquisition program, to determine impacts of the structure on program outcomes.

Development of this framework has been divided into two stages, the first of which will be discussed in this paper. The first stage addresses the role of engineering models (or design tools) in acquisition. A design organization is built around a design process, whose purpose is to create a product. Or a design process is adapted to an existing organization, which then creates the product. Either way, a focus on the engineering models which create information for design decisions is missing. At least part of an engineering model exists prior to the formation of a process or organization, and long before the finished product emerges. For instance, if a ship is to be designed then a set of variables and the existence of relationships between them is known to exist simply by the existence of ship design models. If requirements are known, then there is generally a good idea of which models will be used. This paper demonstrates that the structure of engineering models alone provides information through network analysis that can be useful for the engineer in a new way. A network representation of these models, and other known or guessed relationships, can inform an engineer about design drivers, constraints, conflicts and general structure without performing a single design calculation,

and without having to deeply study each model.

A static network has been constructed from a ship design tool and then analyzed to gain insight that could be found from its structure alone. This reveals several characteristics which impact the information generated by the tool. This demonstrated the feasibility of a network representation of an engineering model. This initial static network was then analyzed with the addition of peripheral arcs. Core arcs are those whose typical relationships and functional evaluations are known (the base network), while peripheral arcs are those whose relationships or existence is unknown, simulating uncertainty in the model. By creating or manipulating arcs in the periphery, the impact of change to the network was observed and measured using standard network theory metrics. This paper will discuss the formulation, analysis, manipulation and results from the ship design tool network as outlined above. Relevant background material and network theory mathematics will also be introduced. An introduction to the second stage of the ongoing research will conclude the paper.

2. Related Research

The idea of analyzing the structure of design products, processes, and organizations is not a new one, and network science is a field that dates at least as far back as the 1930's. Several of the more relevant studies in these two separate fields are presented below to provide a basis to understand on-going research that merges the two. In his PhD thesis, *Maurer (2007)* notes “[a] methodology focusing on the consideration of structures in product development seems to be promising as an approach for enhancing the possibilities of the analysis, control, and optimization of complex design”. There are many such methodologies already proposed in the literature, so the purpose of the following sections is to clarify that the focus of this paper is not a version of any of them, a point which is often confused.

2.1. Design Space Exploration

The primary purpose of design space exploration is to correlate valued inputs to valued outputs. When studying design tools, design space exploration is concerned with correlating the outputted feasible region created by these tools to inputs, without necessarily understanding the “how” of the link between the two. This is evident from the use of Pareto fronts, meta-models, response surfaces, etc. These results are lag indicators, meaning that they are generated post process. An appropriate analogy is the marionette. Design space exploration correlates the movements of the puppet with the position of the control bar, while the strings between puppet and control bar are left unresolved. The research discussed in this paper considers the structure of these strings, which fundamentally determines what the puppet can and cannot do before the show begins. The discussed research is not focused on lag indicators, but using fundamental structure to generate pre-process or lead indicators. Design space exploration may be used as part of the future research during a case study to verify or validate the lead indicators produced, but the fundamental framework being developed is inherently pre-process or lead indicator focused.

2.2. Design Structure Matrix Methods

A popular commonality between network theory and the design world are the Design Structure Matrix (DSM) methods pioneered by Steward, published starting in the 1980's, *Steward (1981,1991,1993)*. The DSM in its simplest form is actually the adjacency matrix of a network, and many of the operations performed on DSMs such as clustering have network equivalents as well, *Browning (2001)*. The recognition that networks are the foundation of DSMs has only recently been emphasized in the literature with Eppinger and Browning's most recent definition, “The DSM is a network modeling tool used to represent the elements comprising a system and their interactions, thereby highlighting the system's architecture (or designed structure)”, *Eppinger and Browning (2012)*. Older works define four main types of DSMs: system architecture, engineering organization, scheduling and parameter-based. A survey of the literature reveals that DSM research focuses almost exclusively on the first three types. Recent work has been done on integrating these different types of

DSMs into a larger structure through some variation of “domain mapping”, yielding the new Multi-Domain Architecture DSMs, *Bartolomei (2007)*, *Maurer (2007)*, *Eppinger and Browning (2012)*.

A pure DSM usually relates the elements of one domain to itself. The evolution of Multi-Domain DSMs (MDMs) allows for the representation of links between different domains, but work in this area is still tied to a matrix representation and matrix mathematics. DSM researchers have tried to incorporate more information into a visual matrix structure; the result is matrices that may not be amenable to mathematical analysis because multiple pieces of information reside within a cell, *Kreimeyer et al. (2008)*, *Yassine et al. (2003)*. To address this issue, Kreimeyer et al. proposed a modification to the MDM, resulting in the addition of two more domains. Due to the exponential growth in the size of the matrix, common sense suggests there is a limit to the amount of information that can be readably presented or interpreted using a DSM in this fashion. Kreimeyer et al. also identified this shortcoming, but experimental results on interpreting DSMs are mixed, *Keller et al. (2006)*. In terms of populating the nodes and arcs of a network, the experience of ship designers leans towards a network representation, *Cooper et al. (2011)*.

DSM methods can be considered a design specific mathematical subset of existing network theory, but have not sufficiently addressed the internal structure of engineering models in affecting the outcome of product development. More importantly, DSM methods do not include true heterogeneous structures or the techniques to analyze them. The research discussed in this paper is novel not only in this respect, but also contends that such heterogeneous structures are more effective for modeling the disparate elements of an acquisition program.

2.3. Change Propagation

Change propagation data from large design activities has been studied extensively using network methods. Pasqual and de Weck analyzed the relationships in an organization between people, design teams and design artifacts to metricize those that absorb change, multiply change, carry change, are receptive to change, resist change etc., *Pasqual (2010)*, *Pasqual and de Weck (2011)*. Change propagation research demonstrates the application of networks to new fields, and provides examples for deriving custom metrics. However, it is essentially product or organization focused and is not predictive. “...It is unclear (and not within the scope of this paper) whether sufficient data would have been available to reveal any actionable trends in real time”, *Pasqual and De Weck (2011)*. The discussed research uses some similar methods but on a totally different topic. Where change propagation research analyzes static product or organization networks after design completion, the discussed research analyzes static networks to understand how model structure affects designs to generate lead indicators.

2.4. Ship Design

The idea of representing a ship design through networks is not new. In many cases the representation of the design is in the form of constraints or variable interactions, which are shown as networks, though networks are not mentioned explicitly, *Brown (1986)*, *Brown (1993)*, *Watson (1962)*, *Watson and Gilfillan (1977)*. There are cases where networks are mentioned directly, but more often than not the use of the term network is used in association with design activities, in some way relating or contrasting with the design spiral, *Laverghetta and Brown (1999)*, *Cooper et al. (2011)*. Cooper et al. describe a large Navy effort to capture the ship design process, primarily using the commercial software Plexus. They started their effort using DSMs, but found network representations easier to populate. Similar in nature to Cooper et al.’s work is the Design Building Block (DBB) approach introduced at IMDC in 1997 and championed in many other works by *Andrews (2006)*. It is an academic vision of an ideal preliminary ship design process. Andrews’ illustration of the approach can be interpreted as a directed network (though he does not use the term) of design activities. In summary, beyond the occasional graphical representation of a network or a lead in to DSM methods, network concepts in ship design have not been developed further until recently.

Justin Gillespie proved the applicability of networks to ship design layout problems in his thesis and other works by adapting the extensive constraint library of the Intelligent Ship Arrangements (ISA) software program into a network representation. ISA is a ship general arrangement tool that produces rational space allocation and arrangements for designer review. ISA's extensive constraint library was derived from standard arrangements design practice. Gillespie's work explicitly demonstrated how a network approach to product layout yields innovative results not seen using other methods. He used computationally simple network mathematics to generate significant designer insight in a way ISA was not enabled to do, and generated rational layouts in a fraction of the time, *Gillespie et al. (2010, 2011)*, *Gillespie and Singer (2011)*, *Gillespie (2012)*. Gillespie's research did not replace the full functionality of ISA, but showed how network structure could provide different solution mechanisms to the same problem. Gillespie's work serves as the inspiration and partial basis of this research. His research took the need for a rational approach to arrangements elucidated by Brown in 1993 and codified with ISA back to the fundamental "mesh" concepts that Brown used to describe ship design in general, *Brown (1993)*, *Parsons et al. (2008)*. Gillespie used networks to create designs, and he baselined against an existing design tool (ISA). In the process of doing so, he discovered designer intent implicit within ISA. This discovery demonstrates that tool structure can have an effect on the outcome of product development, and network theory can identify it. The current research capitalizes on this discovery, and will develop a framework to analyze ship design models for that very purpose. The proposed research diverges from Gillespie's in that he was focusing on product structure (creating designs) rather than model structure (creating information). Of greater significance, the current research builds on static networks to create a framework that integrates models (first stage), processes and organizations in the time domain via temporal networks (second stage).

3. Engineering Model Network Formulation

For the purposes of this research, an engineering model is any tool or method that an engineer might use to create, manipulate or analyze a design. With this definition, a physics-based model, an empirical model, and a black-box piece of software all equally qualify. At the earliest stages, an engineer might have a simple regression model to determine basic parameter ranges. This model might have a list of variables, requirements, functions etc. DSM methods would typically represent each of these in a separate matrix, meaning a separate network, like the homogeneous networks of *Bartolomei (2007)* and *Maurer (2007)*. However, designers do not think about these things separately and decoupling them results in a loss of information. As a result, this research uses a single network with multiple node types, based on a hypothesis that variables do not directly influence one another, they must have context, usually provided by a mathematical function. For example, length alone has no bearing on longitudinal strength, it is its relation to depth that is commonly used in early design. The L/D ratio is a function through which length and depth relate. Again, when formulating a network an engineer might conclude that length influences beam for powering reasons, but that influence is routed through the L/Bratio, a function which provides context. Functions and variables are well defined within the engineering model, but levels of context above them, i.e. disciplines, may very well be at the discretion of the designer. Disciplines, providing context to functions, provide one example of how a designer's style can be analytically incorporated into a design structure.

This insight leads towards a specific network structure, a multipartite network. In this network structure, nodes of the same type can have no arcs between them, they can only relate by passing through nodes of another type. Though this particular way of representing variables and functions is believed to be unique to this work, and the idea of thinking about design in a multipartite fashion was conceived independently, it was discovered to have been mentioned by DSM researchers in another context. "That means that one domain of interest is linked to itself or another via a third domain. Tasks in a process, for example, are not linked directly, but one task generates a piece of information that serves as input for the next task. This example can be extended to almost any problem in engineering design; usually, whenever one looks more closely into the nature of a certain relationship, such as a bi-/multipartite relation is found", *Kreimeyer et al. (2008)*.

A multipartite structure can be projected into a homogeneous network (like those of the DSM world),

called a one mode projection. It is not possible using only the information available in the one mode projection to recreate the full network. The reason that Multi-Domain Matrices of the DSM world have such complicated transition rules is that they essentially start from a one mode projection and then attempt to add context to build up a larger structure. As DSM researchers have attempted to correctly map these different homogeneous domains to one another, the resulting matrix representations have been increasingly cumbersome and complicated. Taking the opposite approach, the discussed research starts with all the a priori nodes and context available, and encodes them within a multipartite network from the start. This property is a key element of the current research. If necessary, multipartite networks can be easily simplified to homogeneous DSMs, but homogeneous DSMs cannot be used independently, or easily, to construct the corresponding multipartite network. Fig.1 demonstrates this visually, with a multipartite network on the left and its associated one mode projections on the right.

Fig.1: Multipartite Network (left) and associated one-mode projections (right)

3.1 Network Theory Basics

Network theory and graph theory are essentially the same, with mathematicians typically preferring graph theory terminology and the social sciences preferring the network equivalents. In this work, a network is defined as a finite set of n elements called nodes and a set of m lines that connect pairs of nodes. If a line has a direction it is referred to as an arc, if it is directionless, or bidirectional, it is referred to as an edge. Typically, a network containing edges contains no arcs, and vice versa. A network containing only arcs is called a directed graph, digraph for short, or a directed network. This research makes extensive use of directed networks, and unless otherwise noted a directed network is henceforth assumed.

3.1.1 The Adjacency Matrix

The adjacency matrix, A , is an $n \times n$ matrix representing the m arcs in the network. Entry a_{ij} of the adjacency matrix represents the arc running from node i to node j . This notation is not consistent across the literature. The notation adopted here is consistent with very common DSM literature but inverted from the main network references this research draws upon *Gillespie (2012)*, *Newman (2010)*. In this work, it is preferable to say i influences j , rather than j is influenced by i because it is more natural to the naval designer. Mathematically there is no difference; converting between notations requires merely the transpose of the adjacency matrix. In an undirected network, the adjacency matrix is symmetric as each edge is bidirectional thus $a_{ij} = a_{ji}$. In an unweighted network, i.e. each arc is of equal importance, the existence of an arc from i to j is denoted by a $\mathbf{1}$ in

the adjacency matrix. This brings into question the value of entries along the diagonal a_{ii} . Some types of networks allow for a self edge or arc. This research currently does not require the existence of self arcs so entries along the diagonal equal zero. In DSM visualizations, the diagonal elements are often presented with no value, but are shaded in.

3.1.2 Centrality

A measure of centrality quantifies the importance of a node, edge or arc in a network. The most basic is degree centrality. The degree of a node is the total number of edges or arcs connected to it. A directed network requires more specificity, where *in-degree* is the total number of arcs directed at the node, and out-degree is the total number of arcs the node is directing. These metrics can be calculated by summing over the columns or rows of the adjacency matrix respectively, yielding vectors \vec{k}_{in} and \vec{k}_{out} containing an entry for each node. In terms of an engineering model, if a node is a variable then the degree is the total number of calculations that variable may be involved in. Out-degree would be the calculations the variable might input to, whereas in-degree would be the calculations that might directly change the variable itself.

Degree centrality evaluates nodes as if they exist in isolation, or can be decoupled somehow from the network. Though informative, a lot of information contained in the network is not represented using only degree centrality. In naval design, considering only degree centrality might show the direct importance of one aspect of design, but neglects the indirect influences that cause cascading changes. Park and Newman developed a relatively new measure to American college football, referred to herein as the “Park Ranking” shown in Eq.(1), which takes into account the relationship of each node to every other node, *Park and Newman (2005)*. This is one creative way of addressing the limitations of degree centrality. The idea is that a node’s ranking is increased from each node it directly influences (out-degree), and a discounted increase for each node that the influenced node influences and so on. At the same time, a node receives a decrease in rank for each node that influences it (in-degree), and a discounted decrease for each node that influences the influencing node and so on. Though the application is new, the Park Ranking is actually a generalization of Katz centrality as shown in Eq.(1), where \vec{w} and \vec{l} are the win (influencing) and loss (influenced) ranking vectors, respectively. The parameter α is the discount factor, and is adjustable, depending on the weighting desired for indirect wins/losses. However, α is limited to $\alpha < \lambda_{max}^{-1}$ if the result is to converge, where λ_{max} is the largest eigenvalue of A . In cases where the exact final eigenvalues are not fully known, i.e. halfway through a season, a reasonable bound for α can be derived from an equivalent randomly generated network. This yields the expression for α shown in Eq.(2). The full derivation can be found in Park and Newman’s work, though their notation is different, requiring an opposite placement of the matrix transposition, *Park and Newman (2005)*.

Park Ranking:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{w} &= \vec{k}_{out} + \alpha A \vec{w} \quad \therefore \quad \vec{w} = (I - \alpha A)^{-1} \vec{k}_{out} \\ \vec{l} &= \vec{k}_{in} + \alpha A^T \vec{l} \quad \therefore \quad \vec{l} = (I - \alpha A^T)^{-1} \vec{k}_{in} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Park Ranking} = \vec{w} - \vec{l} \quad (1)$$

Random Network α Approximation:

$$\alpha = \frac{(2k)}{(k^2) - (k)} \quad (2)$$

3.1.3 Betweenness

Another common measure of centrality is betweenness centrality. Degree centrality and Katz centrality are measures of a node’s direct and indirect impacts on a network from the standpoint that

flow from the network is either emanating from, or terminating at the node being evaluated. Consider these egotistical measures of centrality. Betweenness centrality is a measure of a node's impact on flow between other nodes in the network, hence betweenness. In naval design models, betweenness is one way of representing how important a node is for transferring information between other aspects which are not directly connected. As an example, engine rpm is only connected to speed by acting through gear ratios in most naval vessels, showing the importance of gear ratios in the selection of a prime mover. An engineering model which yields no betweenness for gear ratios might be assuming a directly connected two-stroke diesel. This is an example of how network theory can show the bias in a model. A frigate designer would want to follow up on that. Betweenness can be calculated by quantifying the number of geodesic paths (shortest paths) between all other nodes in the network that pass through the node of interest. Newman's general definition of betweenness centrality is shown in Eq.(3), *Newman (2010)*. In Eq.(3), x_i is the betweenness score of node i , s and t are the index values for all other nodes in the network, n_{st}^i is the number of geodesic paths from s to t that pass through i , and g_{st} is the total number of geodesic paths between s and t . Though nodes are used as the example, betweenness can also be calculated for edges or arcs. This property can be used to help divide networks into logical groupings of nodes, which will be discussed in future publications. There are a few variations on how to calculate betweenness which may change the magnitude of the metric, but not the ranking of nodes relative to one another. The betweenness values shown in this work are computed by the software Pajek, *Nooy et al. (2005)*, and normalized over the lowest nonzero result. In this case, normalizing emphasizes that betweenness centrality is important as a comparison across nodes, not as an individual attribute.

$$x_i = \sum_{st} \frac{n_{st}^i}{g_{st}}$$

Betweenness Centrality:

(3)

4. Watson & Gilfillan Ship Design Equation Network

An abbreviated version of the classic Watson & Gilfillan ship design method was selected to conduct this study, *Watson and Gilfillan (1977)*. Elements of the Watson & Gilfillan method are used in NA 470, the first of two senior level marine design courses taught at the University of Michigan. A small and coherent set of formulae or presumed functions were constructed from the paper, either as printed or derived from printed charts. Terms involving cost were not available from Watson & Gilfillan, and were taken from the NA 470 cost model. The three node types of the network are variables, functions and disciplines. A subset of relationships between variables, their defining functions and the disciplines involved are shown in Table 1, with the complete list located in the appendix. The left column of Table 1 is a list of variables, the center column shows the function that defines each respective variable, and the third column the discipline a function is judged to belong to.

Table 1: Subset of the Watson & Gilfillan Network Relationships

Variable	Functional Input	Discipline
L		
B	F(L)	Powering
T	F(D)	Rules/Safety Freeboard
D	F(B,L)	Stability/Seakeeping & Structures
Delta	f(Cb,L,B,T,s)	Ship Type
Cb	f(L,V)	Powering & Ship Type
Total Cost	f(L,Cb,Ws,MCR)	Ship Type

There are a total of 51 nodes in this network: 28 variables, 17 functions and 6 disciplines. The function-to-variable relationships are well defined in the source paper. The discipline groupings are the judgment of the author, with guidance from the organization of the source paper. Analytically capturing designer judgment is a key benefit of the multipartite network structure. Since there are

three different node types being represented, the network is tripartite. Once the relationships between nodes were assigned, each node was given a number. An arc list, containing the ordered pairs of nodes for each arc was then constructed from the node numbers. With software (it can be done by hand) this arc list was used to create the adjacency matrix. In this case, the arc list was input directly into the freeware network analysis software Pajek for visualization and basic metric calculation. The Watson & Gilfillan ship design network as visualized by Pajek is shown in Fig.3.

4.1 Centrality Results

For brevity, a subset of the results will be presented and discussed, as shown in Table 2. Even with abbreviated results there is some insight, an example of which can be found by studying the results for length (L). It can be concluded that length is a primary design driver for two reasons. First, it has the highest Park Rank of any node (functions and disciplines included) in the network. This means that the direct and indirect influence of length over other nodes in the network, minus the amount to which length itself is influenced, is far greater than any other node. Secondly, closer examination reveals that length itself is not influenced at all, its in-degree and thus “loss” term for the Park Rank are zero. By contrast, the out-degree is eight, the highest of any node in the network. In terms of design, this means that a change in length will have more and farther reaching impacts on other parts of the design than any other change, whereas changes anywhere else will have no direct or indirect impact on length. If an optimization problem were to be formulated using this network, length could serve as an independent variable. What cannot be concluded from these metrics is the magnitude of impact a change in length will have on other nodes, only that an impact exists. Recalling that betweenness centrality is a measure of a node’s impact on flow between other nodes in the network, it becomes obvious that without non-zero in and out-degree centrality the betweenness score for a node will be zero, as is the case for length. This reinforces the concept that length is an independent variable, though with more nuance. Length is not required for coupling between other nodes, though its removal from the network can still isolate flow to nodes solely dependent on length. An example is beam (B), defined by the function $f(L)$, which in turn is solely dependent on length.

There are multiple ways in which a design can be “driven”, such as that shown by length or the opposite, by constraining a design. By Park Rank, the most influenced variable in the network was Total Cost, node 28. It has no influence over other variables with an out-degree of zero, and thus a betweenness of zero. If there were constraints on cost, the network indicates the design could be highly sensitive. In practice, this has proven to be exactly the case. The NA 470 Weights I spreadsheet uses the same basic Watson & Gilfillan model. When students formulate their principal ship parameters using the Weights I spreadsheet there are no cost inputs (i.e. zero out-degree and betweenness). It is only when those parameters have stabilized that cost is checked. If their cost value is deemed too high, they must restart the entire process or fudge the cost number. The network indicates the addition of a function that relates cost back to length within the Weights I tool might alleviate the risk of this occurrence. Though anecdotal, this example provides justification for continued research.

The previous two examples of structural insight were generated using the tripartite network formulation, and focus primarily on variables. Looking beyond variables, Park Rank results show that the weights discipline is the most influenced node of the entire network. By contrast, the structural and stability/seakeeping disciplines were not as influenced as several functions, and even variables. This indicates that the model is focused heavily on the weight related aspects of design rather than structural, a potential shortcoming. This was in fact a complaint noted in *Watson and Gilfillan (1977)*. Comparative analysis across different node types should be undertaken carefully, as there are complex interactions taking place. However, standard parameter-based DSM methods would not have been able to characterize any of these cross node type interactions because by definition they define homogeneous networks. This is important, because to accurately model a complete design evolution as part of an acquisition program multiple node types must be considered as part of the total network.

Table 2: Subset of the Watson & Gilfillan Network Centrality Results

Node Number	Node	Park Rank	Out-Degree	In-Degree	Normalized Betweenness
1	L	30.64	8	0	0
2	B	12.18	4	1	24.75
8	l1	2.92	1	0	0
9	h1	2.92	1	0	0
10	l2	2.92	1	0	0
11	h2	2.92	1	0	0
14	Cb	12.70	6	1	32.75
29	F(L)	8.32	2	1	1.00
36	f(L,B,T,D,l1,h1,l2,h2)	-7.76	2	8	57.00
46	Powering	-17.69	0	6	0
47	Weights	-23.19	0	5	0
48	Ship Type	-20.25	0	5	0
49	Stability/Seakeeping	-4.63	0	2	0
50	Rules/Safety	-2.25	0	1	0
51	Structures	-2.50	0	1	0

4.2 Network Perturbation Results

The Watson & Gilfillan ship design method is for use in the early stages of design when very little information is available, and low fidelity results are adequate. As such, there is still a great deal of uncertainty in both the inputs to the model and the resulting outputs. As has been described in literature regarding Set-Based Design (SBD), and is common knowledge to practicing designers, an inaccurate assumption or mistake in early stage design can be quite costly to remedy later on, *Singer et al. (2009)*, *McKenney et al. (2012)*. Network analysis can help identify areas where a false (or missing) basic assumption could cause the most devastating impacts later on. The impact of a missing assumption can be simulated by adding an arc to the network and observing the overall change to the network's structure. In the case of the Watson & Gilfillan unweighted directed network, there are 1073 possible arcs that can be added to the network. It is a simple matter (on the order of seconds) to step through each possible arc one at a time and recalculate the centrality results presented in the previous section.

It is potentially useful to the engineer to think about the general stability of the network structure via risk. Risk in this case can be defined as the likelihood that a change will occur along with the magnitude of that change. A simple way to measure the magnitude of change is to number the nodes by Park Ranking, and then measure the deviation between the initial numbering and the numbering created after the addition of a single arc. One visual representation of this risk is a histogram, as shown in Fig.2. The abscissas of the plots in Fig.2 show the deviation from the initial numbering for design variables, while the ordinate shows the total number of times that deviation occurred after each of the 1073 new arcs were added separately. If the plot peaks at zero deviation with a sharp drop off, it is unlikely a deviation will occur, and if one does occur it is likely to be small. This means low risk, i.e. a generally stable network structure. The mean deviation alone, also noted in Fig.2, does not provide a good estimate of network stability.

The most significant result of this analysis is that length (L), already identified as the most influential node in the base network, faces zero risk in losing this distinction with the addition of any single arc to the network. Showing the same trend are other variables classically perceived to be the principal dimensions of a vessel, given that the mode for deviation in all cases is zero with a sharp drop off. The bottom right plot in Fig.2 shows the additive result for all nodes in the network, once again

indicating low risk. Ongoing research is concerned with evaluating the risk from the addition and deletion of multiple arcs and nodes in the network. Computation time increases geometrically with the number of simultaneous changes being evaluated.

Fig. 2: Network Perturbation Results

5. Conclusion

The case study involving a classic ship design model verified that:

- A network representation of a ship design model is feasible.
- A multipartite network formulation can accurately reflect a ship design model.
- Analysis of a simple ship design model network can correctly identify what naval architects intuitively understand about the model, correctly identifying design drivers, constraints and other features of model structure.

In detail, length was identified as the driving independent variable of the model, having more and farther reaching impact than any other. Cost is the most influenced variable, indicating that it could be the most constraining element of the design. The analysis also easily indicated that cost has no direct or indirect impact on any other element of the design, meaning that the model does not consider it when determining other variable values. The network showed that weight considerations dominated the formulation, in contrast with other disciplines which were seemingly neglected such as structures.

Lastly, simple perturbation analysis showed that regardless of any single missing assumption, the principal dimensions generated by use of the Watson & Gilfillan ship design method are not prone to a change in influence. These results were achieved using information present in the model, independent of product, process or organization. Designer style was incorporated by including disciplines, which provided context to functions. The calculation and interpretation of the results is both fast (order of seconds and minutes) and of broader potential application than similar methods. These results provide appropriate justification for further research into the subject. If analyzing the network structure of a simple ship design model verifies intuition, then analyzing network structures where no intuition is present, such as with very complex or new models, could prove highly valuable. The successful test of the multipartite formulation also validates its basis for extension to the large temporal networks to be developed in the second stage of research. The value of the multipartite approach is that it is easily extensible to model the larger multi-domain structures, an area where other methods struggle in the static case, and do not exist in the temporal one.

The case study shown in this paper, though promising, was intentionally limited to show only the

feasibility of a network representation of an engineering model. Standard, yet unquantifiable, designer intuition was verified rather than reproducible experimental results. This research hypothesizes that a network theoretic framework can predict impacts of model structure on resulting designs. An appropriate case study is needed to numerically verify this hypothesis. Construction, simulation and analysis on this larger static case study will complete the first stage of research. After completion of stage one, the main body of the future work (stage two) will be concerned with extending it to the time domain emphasizing the integration of process and organization to create an acquisition program network. Methods to construct the network to accurately represent the function of an acquisition network will be studied.

Appendix

Fig.3: Watson and Gilfillan Network

Table 3: Watson & Gilfillan Network Relationships

Node	Functional Input	Discipline
L		
B	F(L)	Powering
T	F(D)	Rules/Safety Freeboard
D	F(B,L)	Stability/Seakeeping & Structures
V		
Ct		
s		
l1		
h1		
l2		
h2		
RPM		
Delta	f(Cb,L,B,T,s)	Ship Type
Cb	f(L,V)	Powering & Ship Type
LCB	f(Cb)	Powering & Stability/Seakeeping
S	f(Cb,L,B,T)	Powering
E	f(L,B,T,D,l1,h1,l2,h2)	Weights
Cb'	f(T,D,Cb)	Weights
K		
Ws7	f(E,K)	Weights
Ws	f(Ws7,Cb')	Weights
Pe	f(V,Ct,S)	Powering
Eta		
MCR	f(Pe,Eta)	Powering
Wme	f(RPM,MCR)	Weights
Structural Cost	f(L,Cb,Ws)	Ship Type
Machinery Cost	f(MCR)	Ship Type
Total Cost	f(L,Cb,Ws,MCR)	Ship Type

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A Mid-Term Outlook on Computer Aided Ship Design

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Abstract

This paper sketches an image of the near future of Computer Aided Ship Design (CASD). First a number of technical CA-related individual subjects are discussed, such as advances in virtual and tactile modelling methods of the ship hull, and the organisation of heterogeneous software components into one (virtual) CAD system. Other subjects are of more general nature, such as a plea for the return of empirical methods in ship design, making use of present tools for data representation and processing, and a reflection on the model of ship design methodology. Finally, three possible future scenarios are elaborated, which reflect general trends in programming and the daily use of computers, and their impact on CASD.

1. Introduction

In this paper an outlook is given on Computer Aided Ship Design (CASD). I restrict myself to the mid-term - say the next decade - because a longer period cannot be foreseen. The basis for the outlook is threefold: (1) our experience with software development and contributions to research projects, (2) some notions from literature and (3) personal observations and projections. Addressed will be five, more or less disconnected subjects:

1. Design and representation of ship shape; this includes the external shape (hull) and the internal shape (bulkheads, decks and compartments).
2. Collaborative ship design.
3. A plea for the revival of empirical prediction methods in ship design.
4. Future scenarios.
5. The model of the ship design process.

A general conclusion at the end of this paper was omitted. Instead each section ends with a conclusion of the particular section subject.

2. The shape of things to come

One of the things that makes our sector unique is the design and representation of the hullform of a ship, where so many technical and aesthetical aspects are related to. Although much has already been said about this subject, some new developments can be noticed. These will be the subject of this first section, first on the virtual representation and secondly on tactile objects.

2.1 How can we hang on to a dream?

There is a bug within the heart of our industry, which is not an accidental software fault, but a deliberate and collective surrender to an inapt modelling method: NURBS surfaces for ship hull modelling. I was professionally educated with pencil and paper, and remember very well the excitement when the first experiments with parametric bivariate B-splines showed a hullform-like surface on the screen of my Apricot 8086 computer. Around 1983. In many places in the world, similar work was done and the same conclusions were drawn. Rapidly the B-spline surface, and a little later NURBS, became the de facto standard for ship hull modelling. However, when applied in practice quite some disadvantages showed up. The strange contradiction is that in private communication with practical ship designers those drawbacks have been commonly recognized and shared, but publications on the issue are scarce. For example, in COMPIT a paper was devoted to this subject, albeit ten years ago, *Koelman (2003)*. A recent overview paper on CASD, *Sharma et al. (2012)*, drew the same conclusion: NURBS are not particularly suitable for ship hull form design. Although Sharma et al. proposed an alternative, it was not well elaborated. *Koelman and Veelo (2013)*

have made some further analyses and suggestions, with a number of alternatives sketched, falling into two categories: approximating methods and interpolating methods. Approximating methods continue to use the same paradigm as traditional NURBS surfaces, in which the surface shape is derived from distinct control points positioned in the vicinity of the surface. Solutions include:

- T-splines, see e.g. *Sederberg et al. (2003)* for a general background and *Sederberg and Sederberg (2010)* for an application aimed at ship design. T-splines overcome the rectangularity limitation of NURBS. However other drawbacks continue to exist (such as the indirect control by means of the vertices, or the fact that no variations in knot spacing across faces and T-joints are allowed).
- NURBS with extraordinary points, *Cashman et al. (2009)*. This is another generalization of NURBS, supporting higher (but odd) degree surfaces.
- Subdivision surfaces, *Nasri (1987)*. Methods for direct evaluation of shape and curvature exist, *Stam (1998)*, as well as solutions against impurities around extraordinary points, *Peters (2000)*. Subdivision surfaces have been commercially available in MCAD systems for half a decade, *Cashman (2012)*.
- Manifold surfaces. This is another approach to modelling free form surfaces of arbitrary topology based on the concept of overlapping charts, *Grimm and Hughes (1995)*. The method was further elaborated in many more publications, resulting in very high quality surfaces well suited for various kinds of numerical analysis.
- To stick with NURBS surfaces, while trying to overcome the fundamental problems with user-interface wizardry. For example: n -sided holes can be filled with n smaller NURBS patches, *Piegl and Tiller (1999)*.

With an interpolating method, on the other hand, a coherent network of curves is constructed and maintained, on which surfaces are interpolated which fill the holes between the curves. Some solutions include:

- To apply a wireframe network, where the holes are ‘filled in’ with surface patches, as e.g. obtained by transfinite interpolation. Such a solution was proposed e.g. in *Michelsen (1995)*. Furthermore, work on the smoothness of such a network and the continuity of derivatives along the edges and at the corners of the surface patches is reported in *Ye and Nowacki (1996)*, *Nowacki et al. (1997)*, *Westgaard and Nowacki (2001)*.
- To extend the wireframe from the previous method with a *solid model* in order to ensure topological consistency. This solution was first proposed in *Jensen et al. (1991)*, while the first application in ship hull modelling was *Koelman (1997)*, where it was baptized *hybrid method*. This method contains three constituents: a) a B-rep solid model, b) methods for curve fairing and c) methods for interpolation of n -sided surface patches.

Finally, the question is whether we will see the NURBS paradigm replaced by a better solution. With the academics of *Sharma et al. (2012)* now convinced there might be a momentum for change. However, there is another factor in play, which is the data exchange practice. Being conceptually simple, the NURBS method has gained wide support in Product Data Transfer (PDT) standards, notably in DXF and IGES. Support for the sketched alternatives is often not readily at hand in such standards. Solutions can be found in converting the alternative native representations into one of the formats supported by the standard, but the shift to more advanced ship hull representations would certainly be stimulated if the popular PDT standards were extended.

2.2 This year’s model

These days it is hard to read serious newspapers without being flooded by articles on 3D printing (a.k.a. rapid prototyping, layered manufacturing or other fashionable terms). Those with a backlog will find a good summary in *NN (2012a)*, www.economist.com/node/21552892. Although reflections on the impact of 3D printing on the structure of the global industry or on the distribution of labour over

the world are fascinating, we shall restrict ourselves to its meaning for ship design. For this purpose, I experimented with the Ultimaker 3D printer, www.ultimaker.com, a low-cost Do It Yourself (DIY) printer, which builds up the model layer by layer with molten polymer material. The technology is called Fusion Deposit Modelling (FDM). A movie of this printer in action, producing a cargo vessel demi-model, can be found on <http://youtu.be/L91vZ8iQQ50>. An example Ultimaker print of a ship hull is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Ultimaker print of aft hull of an IWW vessel, with propeller tunnels

My experiments led to these conclusions:

- A 3D print of the hull provides a distinct view of the hull shape. Strangely, even people with experience and background of reading lines plans or rendered views see things differently with a 3D print. But especially for other stakeholders in the design process, a tactile model, no matter how small, gives natural insight into the shape.
- The accuracy of the printer (within 1/5 mm) is more than sufficient to transfer the (subjective) notion of shape. On the downside, the shrinkage strain in the polymer causes a slight deformation. This is hardly noticed, but e.g. in an assembly it can be annoying. Fig.2 shows a model that was printed in two parts, port (PS) and starboard (SB), and glued together. Here the shrinkage strain causes a fissure between the parts. Fig.3 shows the same launch, now printed with Selective Laser Sintering (SLS). This technology is too expensive for DIY, but offers much higher quality.
- DIY printing is cheap on investment and material. The downside is that the prints require some fine tuning and may sometimes fail. In the first Ultimaker models, we experienced failure rates of tens of percents. However, with the latest 2013 modifications, this appears to be much improved.
- Computer representations have to fulfill specific requirements to be suitable for 3D printing. Notably, the printing software requires the representation to be a solid model; so the idea that lines drawings or collection of unconnected surfaces can be used as basis for a 3D print is a bit naive.
- With this FDM layered manufacturing, a print requires a flat base layer of sufficient size. For example, it is not possible to print an Eiffel Tower model upside down, because due to the lack of a base layer the object will turn over. Thus complex artefacts have to be segmented into parts which can be built from a flat base layer. The parts must be glued together afterwards. For

example the internal ship model of Fig. 4 was segmented with a provisional subdivision algorithm, printed in four parts, which were finally assembled manually. The optimal subdivision strategy for such an object is still an open issue.

Fig.2: Ultimaker print of motor launch, printed in two parts (SB and PS)

Fig.3: SLS print of motor launch, printed in two parts (hull and deck)

Fig.4: Ultimaker print of an internal ship arrangement, printed in four parts

Given the enormous attention in the media and the significant resources that are now being put in the development of 3D printing technologies (a Google search of ‘3D printing’ and ‘investment’ gives 3.040.000 hits), we may expect that new technologies will emerge that will make 3D printing much more user-friendly and accessible, just as in the early 1980s the PC hardware grew from a hobby machine to a professional product in only a few years. Given the price difference between DIY and high-quality machines, the most likely model is with a cheap DIY on your desk, for the rapid result, and a print shop in your town for high-quality prints. And finally the big question: will the designs of our ships benefit from 3D printing? I guess that we will not design better products per se; however, the communication in the design and manufacturing process will improve, leading to a better understanding.

3. Let’s get together

Our sector has seen a dispersion of activities over the past decades. There have been times when ship designs were mostly produced by the design team of a shipyard, which could oversee all design aspects, and performed most of the design activities in-house. Nowadays, activities are distributed over multiple individuals or small groups, possibly scattered over the world, and working with different design software and analysis tools. This fact asks for software tools where people can work collaboratively, and geographically dispersed, on the design of a ship. Aimed at the engineering and production phases of the ship such collaborative tools are quite established. So, in this section we will only concentrate on design. The first thing to do is to sketch the requirements for collaborative CASD.

3.1 Just what I always wanted

Li et al. (2005) make a useful distinction between horizontal and hierarchical collaborative CAD. In horizontal collaboration, persons from the same discipline are co-designing in parallel or in a serial

way. In the hierarchical mode, teams of different disciplines are involved. Examples of the latter are the collaborations with specialists in hydrodynamics, construction costs estimations, seakeeping, structural strength and production. Horizontal collaboration can further be subdivided into visualization-based systems and co-design systems. In the first category, the emphasis is on a fast distribution of the visual design amongst the peer designers. However, our focus is on co-design systems. According to *Fuh and Li (2005)* such systems can be classified into three types:

- Communication server + modelling client (thin server + strong client). Here, the clients are equipped with full CAD functionality, while the server plays mainly a communication role.
- Modelling server + visualized-based manipulation client (strong server + thin client). Here, the main modelling activities are carried out on the server.
- Application or service sharing (peer-to-peer), where the different CAD systems have more or less the same ‘weight’, and share some of each other’s facilities by means of an API (application programming interface).

In distributed CASD environments we do not see a tendency towards a centralized model, where most design activities are carried out on a single platform, either with a strong or with a thin server. On the contrary, as motivated above, many design groups work with a variety of tools, each for a specific task and each operating quite independently. However, the different systems need to collaborate and without restructuring many software tools - which is considered rather unrealistic - the third model can show a way out: on a peer-to-peer basis, with systems ‘peeking’ into each others data and methods. In the next sub-section this model will be worked out.

3.2 Bits and pieces

The idea of a software tool as ad hoc combination of components was investigated in the Dutch Innovero project, *de Koningh et al. (2011)*. Experimental software implementations consist of:

- An internal ship hull modelling tool, based on a binary space partitioning (BSP) method. This tool was recently equipped with APIs in order to facilitate peer-to-peer communications.
- A provisional XML dictionary. After long deliberations the consortium decided not to aim at a top-down designed dictionary, but to let it organically grow from the communication requirements, just as with natural language dictionaries, similar to the approach of *Whitfield et al. (2011)*.
- Two general CAD systems. Two, because two project partners use different CAD systems; the Eagle system (<http://macrovision.ie>) and Rhinoceros (www.rhino3d.com). Despite different functionalities in Eagle and Rhinoceros, with both CAD systems a similar confederation of software systems was achieved, enabling transfer of the internal geometry from the BSP-based program to the CAD system and vice versa, Fig.5.
- Communication of the XML content over TCP/IP (transmission control protocol/internet protocol) on an ad-hoc basis.

Fig.5: Rhino model (left) transferred to the BSP-based CASD tool (right)

A proof-of-concept project was the generation of two-dimensional design drawings in a general-purpose CAD system based on information as available in other connected design tools. The background for this work is that on one hand the design geometry and topology is available in specific ship design tools, while on the other hand two-dimensional overview drawings are important to provide global design lay-out information. These drawings are distributed to other persons downstream in the design and production process. For that purpose, such drawings (typically a general arrangement plan or a tank capacity plan) should also be visually appealing, and preferably formatted in the house-style of a specific shipyard or design office. The aim of this project is the automatic generation of such 2D drawing, albeit in an easily configurable way. This project was in collaboration with Conoship International, performed with the Eagle general-purpose CAD system. With the Eagle language the different ship elements were requested from the BSP-based design tool, processed, and equipped with the desired attributes. Although at the moment of writing the project is not finalized, there are strong indications that its goal can indeed be achieved without the assignment of significant resources. Fig.6 shows an automatically generated double-bottom view visualized in Eagle.

Fig.6: Top view on tank top of double bottom in Eagle

In conclusion, a system consisting of relatively light-weight application programs or CAD applications, communicating over a relatively simple peer-to-peer communication infrastructure can provide a very attractive and flexible solution. And this approach offers also a way out of over-engineered monolithical software packages which have the danger to combine complexity with inflexibility.

4. The empiricists strike back

The advance of the computer has opened up new possibilities for the ship designer and brought many handy tools, such as CFD (computational fluid dynamics), advanced optimization algorithms and product model sharing. However, with the emphasis on these new possibilities an elder class of tools, the empirical prediction methods, is being neglected. In particular for concept studies and the early design stage, such methods have proven to be extremely useful. Take for instance resistance prediction methods such as from Savitsky and Holtrop & Mennen, or steel weight approximations by Schneekluth or Westers. Unfortunately, these methods have not been updated for modern designs or construction methods. The most recent Holtrop & Mennen publication is from 1984, and the steel weight approximations date back to the early 1960s. This is peculiar, not only because the need for such methods is compelling, but also because these days empirical methods could be built with today's possibilities, such as:

- Massive statistical analyses, such as regression models with a large degree of freedom, or response surface models.
- Collecting empirical material used to be tedious, for example doing model experiments. However, numerical experiments based on FEA (finite element analysis) or CFD could generate "numerical series".
- In 'those' days a prime requirement was to communicate the method in a condensed way, by using equations with only a few coefficients or graphs. But nowadays things are much easier. Large amounts of numerical data can easily be distributed and just as easy being read into a computer program or a spreadsheet.
- The increased processing power brings additional features within reach. For example by extending the prediction method with confidence limits. In this fashion a probabilistic steel

weight method might be possible, where not only the steel weight is predicted, but also its probability distribution.

In this respect, the occasional publication with a fully elaborated empirical method is a delight, e.g. *Bertram and Mesbahi (2004)* or the compact overview of empirical prediction methods for catamarans in *Haase et al. (2013)*. And notably *Hekkenberg (2013)*, which will have a sequel in a Joint Industry Project in the Netherlands, aimed at the construction of empirical prediction methods for inland waterway vessels. I hope that this work will be an inspiration to other scholars to work in this area. And remember: eternal fame will be yours. For what is the reason we are still familiar with the names of e.g. Puchstein or Lap?

5. Scenarios on the use and advancement of computers and their impact on CASD

We all are aware that the future is difficult to predict. There are so many disrupting mechanisms and unknowns that simple extrapolations are most likely to fail. Moreover, predictions may be self-fulfilling or self-destroying. For this reason some fortunetellers from major companies find it more appropriate not to present a deterministic prediction, but to sketch different lines of likely scenarios. Restricted to the topics of COMPIT, I would like to postulate three mid-term scenarios - say for the next decade - on the use and advancement of computers, and their impact on CASD:

- **Fragmentation, symbolized by the collapse of MS-Windows.** Time was that Microsoft (MS) ruled the world. However, in the technology battle of today its role seems to be over; for example a briefing on future platforms, *NN (2012b)*, reports in depth on Apple, Amazon, Google and Facebook, but spends only a single word on MS. Although as such the downturn of MS might be a relief for many, the annoying undertone is that no prevailing platform will arise that can mature to mainstream. As such, the lack of a clear winner is not a big disadvantage, it might even be healthy for innovation. But consequences might be that PDT and collaborative design will become tedious. The same might happen on our CASD terrain. For example, as we saw in section 2.1, there are several candidates for the succession of today's prevailing hull form representation method, which holds the risk of fragmentation.
- **The standstill era.** In the Netherlands the 18th century is known as the 'wig age', the 'pruikentijd'. This is generally considered to have been a standstill era, where the country still floated on its successes of the Dutch glorious Golden Age, however, with little innovation. The same might hold for the future of computing: overwhelmed by the magic of the computing and connectivity power the strive for innovation is lost for the moment. Or to condense this scenario in a rethorical question: Do you think that our common desktop tools, such as spreadsheets, word processors and databases have significantly improved since 1986? I don't. Admittedly, we have gained e-mail and Internet, but for the rest my office productivity was higher in 1990 than it is now.
- **A bright young world.** In this scenario the focus lies not so much on computer programs, but more on methodological advancement; the development of methods that assist the ship designer in the daily practice, but also at a deeper level help to make our industry more competitive and more pleasant. Obviously, the results will become available as computer applications, however, with more attention to the methodological user-friendliness than to appearance and user-interface wizardry. This kind of user-friendliness also stimulates a common ground for interoperability technologies.

The advantage of scenarios is that we do not have to choose. It is likely that a mixture will become reality. Obviously, everybody will favour the third scenario. But please see that such a choice is not without engagement. This scenario can only become reality if we actively contribute to it and stimulate others to do so, too. And in that way make my other two prophecies self-destructing.

6. Winding down

In the section on ship hull form design we have noticed a manifestation of cognitive dissonance: the phenomenon that people tend to adapt their system of values to a certain theory, although empirical evidence or indications do not support that theory. Such discrepancies occur also in other fields, take the common model of the ship design process. Brought back to its basics, ship design consists of two parts: choices and evaluations. Design choices comprise e.g. main dimensions, displacement, layout of tanks and spaces, propulsion concept and structural concept. Evaluations can include computations in the field of speed and power, stability, cargo capacity, tank capacity, endurance and structural strength. The sequence of choose and analyse is re-iterated until all design requirements are met (or it can be concluded that they cannot be met at all). This method is commonly depicted as a design spiral, which is attributed to *Evans (1959)*. However, this spiral suggests a fixed sequence of activities, which in reality only seldom occurs. Also the distinct design stages (initial design, embodiment design, contract design, detailed design) may in practice overlap to some extent. Recently we have seen a tendency to omit the sequence notion from the spiral, *Nowacki (2009)*, *Harries et al. (2011)*. We are left then with the model of the toolbox, from which the ship designer can pick his tools as the situation requires. My favorite graphic for such a model is depicted in Fig.7, *Koelman (1999)*, not that the alternatives are worse, but because it is readily at hand on my desk. Is this methodology thing relevant for the daily ship design practice? No. But a misfit gives novices an incorrect notion of their profession and their activities, and for no reason.

Fig.7: Toolbox metaphor of the ship design process

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Innovative Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics for Wave Impact Simulation on Ships and Platforms

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Abstract

The explicit dynamic Finite Element (FE) modules of the Virtual Performance Solution TM (VPS) software package with an embedded and fully coupled, innovative Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) modules and selected industrial applications are discussed. For a given problem, the mechanical response of the structural components involved is evaluated with the FE part of the package while the SPH part is used to solve the non-linear hydrodynamics of the violent flow. The interaction between the structure and the fluid is addressed using a robust contact algorithm. Recent innovations in the SPH solver are discussed in detail. Regularization algorithms to improve the particle distribution, both at the start of, and throughout, the simulation, highlight that such features help to ensure accurate interpolation of relevant fluid properties. A pressure correction method is also discussed. Periodic boundaries are used to reduce the size of the computational domain and a moving floor technique is applied to generate regular and irregular waves efficiently. This paper features the use of this coupled FE-SPH approach within VPS to analyze the structural response in large waves of fast ships, boats and yachts as well as off-shore platforms, including those for wind turbine structures. Also considered are the entry of life boats into the sea and the effect of a huge wave representative of a devastating tsunami on rigid, moveable and deformable on-shore structures. Finally, techniques that can reduce the computational demands of these kinds of simulations, such as Multi-Model coupling and GPU exploitation, are discussed.*

1. Introduction

Major technological challenges arise when designing fixed or moving structures that will be able to withstand loads coming from large impacting waves or slamming events. Such structures include on-shore and off-shore platforms, commercial and military ships as well as large ocean going ferries and yachts. Virtual prototyping (VP) using advanced numerical simulation techniques has become an indispensable tool to meet such challenges, *El Khaldi and McGuckin (2012)*. This paper presents one such VP tool which is built around an explicit Finite Element (FE) software package with an embedded and fully coupled Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) solver. In most cases the FE part of the solver is used to evaluate the mechanical response of all structures involved, whereas the SPH method is used to solve the non-linear hydrodynamics of the flow. Coupling is achieved through robust contact algorithms and allows the interaction of the fluid and structure to be modeled. Many of the earlier shortcomings or limitations of the SPH method have been overcome by introduction of improvements to the basic SPH algorithm such as the pressure correction terms in the formulation and particle regularization algorithms introduced below. Periodic boundary conditions and the introduction of non-uniform particle distributions provide further significant increases in computational efficiency.

The usage of the coupled FE-SPH approach will be demonstrated for the response of ships and floating off-shore platforms in large waves, as well as for water entry of life boats. The effect of a huge wave representative of a devastating tsunami on rigid, moveable and deformable on-shore structures will also be presented. High-performance computing (HPC) technology including the use of GPUs and Multi-Model Coupling (MMC) are also used to reduce the computational demands.

2. A Brief Overview of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics

An overview of the ‘standard’ (Weakly Compressible) Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (WC-SPH) method and the optional coupling with Finite Elements will be presented in this section. The special features that have recently been introduced into SPH to provide more accurate pressure results and that allow for reduction of the computational efforts are discussed in the following section.

2.1. The standard SPH method

The SPH method is an interpolation method in which each ‘‘particle’’ describes a fixed amount of material in a Lagrangian reference frame. Despite its appearance as a collection of points, the SPH method provides an approximate solution to the continuum mechanics equations of fluids and solid materials. Since the method requires no mesh, SPH facilitates the simple handling of the motion and topology changes of material surfaces. As shown in figure 1, the evaluation of relevant field variables such as density and velocity, at the location of a selected particle is conducted by interpolation over all neighbor particles in a region of influence. The size of the sphere (or circle in 2D) of this region is defined by a smoothing length, h . Importantly, spatial derivatives of unknown field variables may be evaluated using the known derivative of the smoothing kernel.

Fig.1: Two-dimensional representation of the region of influences of particle ‘i’

Unless mentioned otherwise, the SPH method discussed here is basically similar to that of *Monaghan (1992, 1994)*. Therein, the continuity equation provides the derivative of the density for particle i :

$$\frac{d\rho_i}{dt} = \sum_j m_j (\bar{v}_i - \bar{v}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where the sum extends over all neighbor particles j , each with a mass of m_j . \bar{v}_i and \bar{v}_j are the velocities of the i^{th} and j^{th} particles, respectively, and W is the smoothing kernel evaluated at the distance between the i^{th} and j^{th} particles. Optionally, renormalization of the density field may be performed, *Colagrossi and Landrini (2003)*. The updated velocity may be obtained from the momentum equation:

$$\frac{d\bar{v}_i}{dt} = -\sum_j m_j \left(\frac{p_i}{\rho_i^2} + \frac{p_j}{\rho_j^2} + \Pi_{ij} \right) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where p_i and p_j represent the particle pressures. The artificial viscosity is defined as:

$$\Pi_{ij} = \frac{2}{\rho_i + \rho_j} \left(-\alpha \frac{c_i + c_j}{2} \mu_{ij} + \beta \mu_{ij}^2 \right), \quad (3)$$

with c_i and c_j being the local sound speed, and with

$$\mu_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(h_i + h_j) \frac{(\bar{v}_i - \bar{v}_j) \cdot (\bar{r}_i - \bar{r}_j)}{|\bar{r}_i - \bar{r}_j|^2 + \epsilon^2 h^2} \quad \text{when } (\bar{v}_i - \bar{v}_j) \cdot (\bar{r}_i - \bar{r}_j) < 0 \quad (4)$$

And zero otherwise; h_i and h_j are the smoothing lengths. The $\varepsilon^2 h^2$ term in the denominator is included to avoid divergence in case particles collide. The parameters α and β determine the strength of the artificial viscosity required to suppress numerical shocks. These artificial viscosity parameters should be set as low as possible to avoid the flow becoming too viscous. To mitigate the effect of particle clumping together during flow simulations, the anti-crossing option (XSPH), *Monaghan (1994)*, may be employed as follows:

$$\frac{d\vec{r}_i}{dt} = \vec{v}_i + \eta \sum_j m_j \frac{(\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j)}{\frac{1}{2}(\rho_i + \rho_j)} W_{ij} \quad (5)$$

For a non-zero η parameter, equation (5) is used to update the particle positions, whereas the strains remain based on the uncorrected displacements.

A cubic spline kernel is used for the smoothing kernel and is given by:

$$W(|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|, h) = \begin{cases} \frac{N}{h^D} \left[\frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}{h} \right)^3 - \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}{h} \right)^2 + 1 \right], & 0 \leq \frac{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}{h} < 1 \\ \frac{1}{4} \frac{N}{h^D} \left[2 - \left(\frac{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}{h} \right) \right]^3, & 1 \leq \frac{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}{h} < 2 \\ 0, & 2 \leq \frac{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}{h} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where the smoothing length, h , is proportional to the particle radius, D is the dimensionality of the simulation (1, 2 or 3) and N is a normalization constant. The flow is assumed to be nearly incompressible implying that the pressure field is obtained from an equation of state (EOS) model. A polynomial EOS may be used for water, but it is convenient to use an alternative, the Murnaghan (also known as the Tait) model, whose EOS is given by:

$$p = {}^0p \left[\left(\frac{\rho}{{}^0\rho} \right)^\gamma - 1 \right] \quad (7)$$

where 0p is the reference pressure, ${}^0\rho$ the reference density and γ is a user-defined parameter, which is commonly 7.0. A cut-off pressure may be included as a simple approximation to cavitation.

Particles are assumed to interact mutually only if they are sufficiently close to each other. This is established by a nearest neighbor (NN) search feature that is not repeated each computational cycle for efficiency reasons. Second-order accurate leap-frog time stepping is used for the explicit time integration of the above rate equations. The numerical time step is set at a fraction (usually about 0.8) of the well-known Courant (or CFL) criterion based on the current size and sound speed of all particles and finite elements present in the model. The accurate location of the free surface can be determined at specific fixed 'gauge' locations in the SPH domain by an algorithm that searches for significant density changes in the direction of the gravity acceleration vector from the gauge point.

2.2. Contact Treatment

Interaction between particles, representing a fluid, and finite elements, representing moving or deformable structures, may be modeled by one of the sliding interface contact algorithms available in VPS (of which the explicit part dedicated to crashworthiness is also known as PAM-CRASH). Such algorithms prevent penetration between selected structures, with sliding allowed in most cases. The sliding interfaces employed are based on the well-known penalty formulation, where geometrical interpenetrations between so-called slave nodes and matching master faces are penalized by counteracting forces that are essentially proportional to the penetration depth. The contact algorithm automatically detects when a particle (slave) penetrates any segments (master) representing the outer

surface of the finite element model of the structure. The contact thickness indicates the distance away from a contact face where physical contact is established. For SPH particles as slaves, the contact thickness should be representative of the particle spacing. This type of contact has been validated by simulating the vertical motion of floating bodies. It has been found that the neutrally buoyant position and buoyancy forces are accurately predicted when the thickness defined for the contact is one half the particle spacing and the artificial viscosity coefficients are taken significantly smaller than the values normally applied for shocks, *Cartwright (2012)*. The contact thickness and the relative strength of the repulsive forces are defined by the user. The coupled FE-SPH method has been applied to a range of applications including sloshing, *Meywerk et al. (1999)*, the opening of a heart valve, *Haack (2000)*, bird strike and the impact of aeronautical structures on water, *Climent et al. (2006)*. This FE-SPH coupling via contact is also used to define rigid boundary conditions to limit the flow domain. A tied contact may be used when sliding can be ignored, such as when an artificial interface between particles and volumetric elements is used to represent a contiguous volume of water.

3. SPH Innovations

Despite obvious advantages of SPH to simulate fluid flow involving free surfaces or interaction with a structure or other fluids, the method has not gained general acceptance in the maritime industry. Some reasons for this are the generation of irregular particle distributions ('clumping'), the occurrence of scatter in computed pressures, and limitations in defining non-uniform particle distributions.

3.1. Pressure correction

One of the outstanding problems of the WC-SPH solution as discussed above is the rather large variation in pressure, both in time and space. *Molteni and Colagrossi (2009)* introduced the option they referred to as a mass diffusion option which provides a significant reduction of these pressure variations. There is however, no apparent physical or numerical justification for why there should be something like mass diffusion in a domain filled with a single liquid only. This formulation was later extended with a viscous term and the resulting δ -SPH scheme, *Antuono et al. (2009, 2010)*, has been demonstrated to provide superior pressure results. A slightly different formulation, using a pressure correction based on a finite difference approximation to the incompressibility constraint for nearly incompressible flow yields, *Groenenboom (2009)*:

$$\frac{\rho^{n+1} - \rho^n}{\Delta t} = \sum_j m_j \cdot (\bar{u}_i^n - \bar{u}_j^n) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} - 2 \cdot \xi \sum_j \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} \frac{(P_i^n - P_j^n) \cdot \vec{r}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} \cdot \Delta t}{(r_{ij}^2 + \epsilon \cdot h^2)} \quad (8)$$

in which the superscript refers to the time step, $\vec{r}_{ij} = \vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j$ and Δt is the time step.

Eq.(8) may be shown, *Groenenboom (2011)*, to be equivalent to the first-order approximation to the Riemann problem for fluid flow (Rusanov flux), *Ferrari et al. (2016)*, where the free parameter is set to 0.5. The pressure correction provides a significantly smoother pressure distribution than the reference SPH simulation but without observable effects on the free surface location and velocities. The total fluid volume (or average density) is also not modified.

3.2. Particle regularization algorithms

The 'clumping' of particles is a primary cause for some of the inaccuracies of the original SPH method. Particle regularization algorithms (PRA) are designed to reduce the occurrence of this clumping by redistributing the particles at regular intervals throughout the analysis. Such an algorithm is expected to mitigate numerical effects such as the irregular pressure distribution for the standard SPH. Since the tension instability is related to the presence of irregular particle distributions, it is expected that a suitable PRA may alleviate the problems due to this instability. A good redistribution algorithm should ensure that:

1. The method should yield a more regular particle distribution within a few calculation steps.

2. The effect of the correction of a locally ‘poor’ distribution should remain local.
3. The method should be numerically stable and not require excessive amounts of CPU.
4. The exterior surface should remain close to the original one.
5. The updated mass, velocity, density and other properties should be defined optimally.
6. The modifications in the total mass, momentum and energy should remain very small.
7. The modifications of the properties should be close to zero for initially smooth distributions.

If particles are defined to be in a different position than that obtained by direct integration of the individual particle kinematics, they no longer represent the same amount of material and a correction is required. This correction has not been considered by *Yu and Turk (2010)* nor is it accounted for in the usual particle displacement correction methods (XSPH).

When the first-order series expansion of any spatial function, f , around the updated position \vec{R}_i for SPH is made, the following expression is obtained:

$$f(\vec{R}_i) = f_i - \sum_j \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} f_j \nabla(W_{ij}) \cdot (\vec{R}_i - \vec{r}_i) \quad (9)$$

f may be a scalar function such as density, internal energy or pressure, but can also be a component of a vector (i.e. velocity) or tensor (i.e. stress). As is well known from the standard SPH, the right hand side of equation (9) is not guaranteed to vanish when f represents a uniform field. For that reason, it is better to subtract the value of f for the i^{th} particle. This yields:

$$f(\vec{R}_i) = f_i - \sum_j \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} (f_j - f_i) \nabla(W_{ij}) \cdot (\vec{R}_i - \vec{r}_i) \quad (10)$$

Using this relationship, the contribution from higher orders i.e. the product of the squared change in displacement with the Laplacian of the smoothing kernel, may be assumed to be negligible.

The particle positions are redefined in the above approach and hence the individual particle mass may no longer be assumed to remain constant. An initial attempt to redefine the particle mass based on an SPH representation of the inverse volume did not produce accurate results. This is due to the fact that the particle mass is a function of density and volume and both of these quantities are interpolated based on Eq.(10). Both the density and smoothing length h are interpolated directly from Eq. (10) and the volume is proportional to h^d , where d is the dimension of the problem.

To account for this relationship between mass, density and volume, the following method was used to evaluate the updated mass:

$$M_i = \rho_i V_i (1 + \Delta \rho_i / \rho_i) (1 + \Delta V_i / V_i) = m_i (1 + \Delta \rho_i / \rho_i) (1 + (\Delta h_i / h_i)^D) \quad (11)$$

V is the particle volume and Δ represents the change in a quantity. .

Various regularization algorithms have been investigated and although an optimal algorithm has yet to be developed, the current implementation demonstrates significantly improved accuracy for SPH flow simulations. Furthermore, it is now feasible to replace the artificial viscosity by a model for the (laminar) fluid viscosity and with such a model, in conjunction with the pressure correction, simulate wave propagation and water entry phenomena with improved accuracy, *Groenenboom and Cartwright (2013)*.

3.3. Moving Floor Technique

Most waves in this paper are considered to be deep water waves for which the water motion at a depth beyond the limit of about half a wavelength has become small enough to be neglected. Second-order Stokes’ waves are assumed. To reduce computer resources, the domain depth will be chosen to be less than this limit. In that case, the domain floor can no longer be assumed to remain at rest but will be

assigned the displacement field corresponding to the analytical approximation for the undisturbed waves. Another reason to assign the undisturbed wave motion to the floor is to counteract any losses in the wave amplitude usually observed when a wave series traverses an extended domain of sufficient depth but represented by a computationally acceptable number of particles. With this ‘moving floor’ approach, excellent wave propagation results have been obtained for linear waves, *Cartwright et al. (2004)*. Similar displacement conditions are assigned to all other walls enclosing the domain. In case the waves are disturbed by floating or dropped objects, the location of the boundaries needs to be chosen sufficiently far away from the objects that the reflection of any wave disturbance can safely be ignored. For consistency with the finite element concepts of VPS, the boundaries have been defined in a Lagrangian frame of reference. A similar approach has recently been applied to create irregular waves, *Aristodemo and Groenenboom (2012)*.

3.4. Moving Domains and Periodic Boundaries

In many cases, particles located outside a region of interest are not expected to be relevant for at least part of the simulation time. To take advantage of this, an ‘active moving box’ has been developed. None of the particles outside of the box are processed during the particle interaction computation and hence do not contribute to the CPU load.

Another method of reducing the CPU load for flow simulations is that of ‘periodic boundaries’. This feature allows particles leaving a user-defined rectangular domain to be entered at the other end with the same velocity and is useful for a variety of flow studies. It has recently been extended to allow opposing boundaries to be translated according to the motion of a user-defined node. With this extension, the particle domain can follow the motion of a moving structure such as a ship or a ditching aircraft, without needing to introduce additional velocities for the particles themselves.

3.5. Damping of SPH particles

An important issue for simulation of free surface waves and the interaction with floating objects in open seas is that computational models have to be confined by definition of artificial boundaries. Depending on the type of boundary condition and the distance from the region of interest waves may reflect off these boundaries and influence the results. The option of a ‘damping zone’ has recently been introduced to eliminate the problems arising from reflections at the boundaries. Using this feature, the user may define regions in space having a smooth transition from no damping to full damping. If the transition is smooth enough, the size of the reflected waves is negligible.

3.6. Pressure initialization and recovery

Another feature that helps to reduce the CPU effort when chasing more accurate results is that of a ‘hydrostatic equilibrium condition’. Adding the hydrostatic pressure to the material pressure from the start of the simulation avoids the need to conduct an initialization-simulation to obtain hydrostatic pressure equilibrium dynamically.

A ‘gauge’ feature provides a mechanism to monitor the pressures and, in relevant situations, the free surface level. A ‘pressure gauge’ may be considered as the computational equivalent to physical pressure gauge in an experiment, *Siemann and Groenenboom (2013)*. They may be positioned anywhere within an SPH domain without influencing the results. Due to the averaging conducted over nearby particles, the pressures obtained suffer less from the oscillations observed for individual particles. A ‘level gauge’ is used to monitor the free surface location.

4. Performance Related Issues

The SPH method has a reputation of being expensive in terms of CPU effort. This is not always the case, particularly when it is compared to more traditional types of CFD analysis where the geometry or topology of the free surface is complex and rapidly changing. The SPH solver within VPS has been

optimized by implementing a CPU-effective NN search and is available on both SMP and DMP architectures allowing for effective execution on a cluster of processors.

The MMC mentioned earlier is strategy that can reduce the CPU and execution time on clusters. MMC is beneficial when model components requiring a very fine mesh interact with more coarsely meshed components because it enables two independent, but interacting FE or SPH models, to be run as a single model, *Greve and Vlachoutsis (2007)*. MMC allocates different CPUs to each of the two models, running them independently. The two distinct models are typically linked numerically by either a defined tied interface (which stipulates how the models are joined) or by a defined contact interface (which describes how they physically interact). Internally, it exploits a sub-cycling technique to allow each model to run using its own time-step while simultaneously accounting for any interactions between the two models via the interface. The application of MMC for combined FE-SPH models has been discussed by *Groenenboom et al. (2010)*.

Recently, a GPU version of VPS including SPH has been created, *Kamoulakos et al. (2012)*. In terms of granularity, the computations related to the SPH are extremely well adapted for the GPU. Due to the absence of explicit “connectivity”, the calculations for a given particle at one given moment are independent of the calculations of the other particles around it. In the FE method by way of contrast, the actual Finite Elements do interact using the pre-defined and fixed connectivity of their nodal variables. The resulting “summation” process of the FE method disrupts the GPU efficiency. In SPH, the interaction between particles occurs between a particular particle and those particles within a given neighborhood size linked to the smoothing length of the particles. However, there is a significant amount of calculation which is carried out after the determination of this neighborhood and this suits a mixture of GPU and CPU. A new executable of VPS, dubbed ‘version GPU’, recodes (for the GPU) some of the most computationally demanding pieces of code where much of the total computing time is normally spent. The remainder of the calculation is still done in the CPU. Calculations were carried out initially on only one processor (a CPU or a GPU) and then on several processors according to the DMP model. While the precise performance gain will be model dependent, the results obtained to date are encouraging. They suggest a speedup of about three when compared to the equivalent DMP run with only CPUs, *Vlachoutsis (2011)*. The evaluation is proceeding and further improvements are expected. The results of the calculation of “version GPU” were initially compared with the results of “version CPU” to ensure that the calculations were correct.

5. Ships Moving In Waves

Before trying to simulate ships moving in waves, it had to be proven that undisturbed waves could be simulated employing the moving floor concept of Section 3.3. As discussed by *Groenenboom and Cartwright (2009)*, this has been tested for second-order deep water waves in a two-dimensional section in which both the wave length and domain length was set to 294 m. The model had a depth of 24 m, filled with particles on an initial spacing of 0.5 m. Contours of the pressure for 16m high waves are shown in Fig.2. Also shown in this figure are a few particle paths that display the combination of circular motion with the Stokes’ drift in the direction of wave propagation. Although not shown, the velocity distribution within the wave correlates well with the theoretical distribution.

Fig. 2: Pressure contour and selected particle trajectories for the 16 m high 294 m long wave

For a similar test case of a regular wave of 4.0 m height and 73.5 m length, the computed vertical velocities of a selected particle in the domain are compared to the analytical result in Fig.3. Even for this case with higher wave steepness, there is excellent agreement between simulation and the

analytical solution. These results demonstrate that the wave dynamics generated using the moving floor technique is correct within the domain of interest and hence suitable for the study of the response of floating objects. Having generated a non-diminishing regular wave, it was then possible to drive a ship through the waves to observe the ship response. Fig.4 illustrates the response of a generic frigate in seas of 3 m high waves with a 110 m wavelength.

Fig. 3: Time histories of the vertical velocity of a selected particle compared to the second-order analytical solution. For clarity the initialization phase is deleted in this figure.

Fig. 4: Generic frigate with typical responses and wave-making tendencies when traversing waves generated by the moving floor boundary conditions. Upper images show the vessel beginning to move; lower images show top and side views for vessel at 30+ knots.

Most numerical studies of ships in waves are conducted assuming the hull to be rigid. However, *Groenenboom et al. (2010)* demonstrated that it is possible to simulate the motion of the flexible hull of a generic frigate in waves using the coupled FE-SPH approach. This study demonstrated that the flexibility of the frigate model does influence the kinematics of the vessel response. For 8m high waves it was also predicted that green water will occur.

6. Lifeboat Water Entry

Free-fall lifeboats are used as an escape mechanism for offshore platforms and large ocean vessels. Modern lifeboats can hold as many as 40 people and are designed to withstand the g-forces from their impact on the ocean surface from a height of up to 32 m. *Groenenboom (2008)* investigated the pressure distribution and acceleration on the lifeboat as it entered the water. In the simulations involved, the lifeboat was modelled as a rigid body of shell elements and had a mass of 14.85 t (including occupants). The water was modelled as SPH particles in the region where violent flow was anticipated, and solid elements elsewhere. Immediately above the impact region of the water, a volume of SPH particles representing air was included to capture the cushioning effect of air. The air is omitted from the figures here for clarity. Fig.5 shows the lifeboat penetrating the free surface, and creating spray and splash on the surface. Fig.6 compares experimental data and simulations for this lifeboat. The global shape of the acceleration curve agrees well with the test. More results are shown in *Groenenboom (2008)*. An unpublished ‘blind’ industrial validation study has demonstrated that the match between the numerical and experimental acceleration of a lifeboat model is good enough for the simulation technique as described here to be used as an industrial tool.

Fig.5: Free-fall lifeboat as it penetrates the water surface

Fig. 6: Accelerations of the simulation and model tests

7. Floating Off-shore Platform in Waves

This example investigated the dynamic response of a floating (moored) offshore platform subject to strong wave action, Fig.7. The platform was modeled using finite elements and was 105 m long, 65 m wide, and had draft of 16.5 m with a mass of 27.7 t. The water domain was 1460 m x 244 m x 55 m and employed approximately 2.4 million SPH particles. The main body of the platform was modeled as a rigid body with appropriate mass, centre of gravity and moments of inertia defined. The anchor cables were modeled using flexible 1-dimensional (1D) finite elements.

Fig. 7: Offshore platform responds to waves (with mooring lines beneath the moving floor)

Fig. 8: Particle distribution and velocities for a wave approaching a TLP support of a wind turbine

The use of periodic boundary conditions applied to the SPH particles allowed the computational domain to be limited to 4 wavelengths in the direction of wave travel. The waves were generated by applying the moving floor technique. The dynamic response of the above platform was presented by *Croaker et al. (2011)* for the case of the platform operating at a depth of 310 m under the influence of waves with a wavelength of 365 m and wave height of 20 m. An extension of this approach also considered the motion-induced stresses in the structural members of the cranes located on the operations deck of the platform.

As the stable time step for these 1D elements was much smaller than for the SPH particles, employing MMC (Section 4) greatly reduced the computation time of this simulation. This reduction exceeded 25 when MMC was used in the model containing both flexible anchor cables and flexible cranes.

A recently-commenced study is using SPH to assess the hydrodynamic forces due to extreme waves acting on the Tension-Leg Platform (TLP) support for a floating wind turbine, *Adam et al. (2012)*. Fig.8 shows a preliminary result of the velocities in the approaching wave. The resulting accelerations of the wind turbine may be used to determine the forces and kinematics of the structure.

8. Tsunami Flooding

With their huge destructive power, tsunamis can devastate vast regions of a coastline and generate catastrophic damage to both infrastructure and buildings, *Lukkunaprasit et al. (2010)*. A tsunami consists of a series of water waves generated by the (often earthquake-induced) displacement of a huge volume of water. Special coastal defenses are used to protect coastal communities from such threats. However, the 2011 Tōhoku earthquake has highlighted that even the most sophisticated of these defenses, such as the massive Kamaishi bay breakwater, *Tanimoto and Goda (1992)*, are insufficient to prevent catastrophic flooding of anything in the path of the tsunami. To better design coastal protection, it is now evident that an improved understanding is needed of not only the tsunami dynamics but also of the associated flooding phenomena. This enhanced insight can be achieved economically and effectively using advanced software tools such as VPS. A feasibility project was carried out to illustrate how a VPS based solution can reproduce the physical features of the wave slamming and the building flooding, *Kamoulakos et al. (2012)*. The building was modeled as rigid as previous projects had already demonstrated the capability of accounting for deformable structures interacting dynamically with water masses. This typical test configuration and the applied tsunami load case are shown in Fig.9. Figs.10 and 11 show the waves slamming onto the structure and the building flooding, respectively.

Fig. 9: Tsunami Demonstration case #1

Fig. 10: Wave slamming and initial flood

Fig. 11: Building flooding

In an additional industrial test case, a tank for liquefied natural gas (LNG), Fig.12, was selected. Some items of debris, in this case automobiles, were placed in front of the structure to demonstrate the capacity of the model to handle (what are effectively) projectiles in addition to wave slamming and subsequent flooding. Initially, the LNG tank and all debris were modeled as rigid structures. The results at two stages of the slamming simulations are shown in Fig.13. Fig.14 shows the eventual flooding after the water mass has passed the protective dyke. At this point in the simulation any potential intrusion of water into the structure can be assessed.

Fig. 12: Demonstration case #2

Fig.13: Tsunami slamming simulation; initial stage (left) and later stage (right)

Fig. 14: Tsunami eventual flooding simulation

An additional analysis was conducted in which the LNG tank was modeled as a deformable structure comprised of shell elements. Using an elasto-plastic material model for the LNG tank, a complex collapse path was observed, started by the inward buckling of the dome as shown in Fig.15. The inclusion of the deformable structure makes the time-step drop considerably, resulting in a ten-fold increase in solution time. As mentioned earlier in this paper, utilizing the MMC feature, or the exploitation of the GPU version of the code, will help ameliorate this increase for future studies.

Fig. 15: Plastic yielding of tank under wave slamming after 1 s

9. Summary and Conclusion

Discussed herein are the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method and the coupling approach to the Finite Element solution within VPS to simulate violent flow phenomena and related fluid-structure interaction. Innovative features within the SPH solution allow for more accurate and more efficient fluid flow simulations. Issues about numerical efficiency have also been addressed, in particular the proposed improvements with the Multi-Model Coupling and the recently developed GPU version of VPS. Industrial examples such as ships moving in waves, wave impact on off-shore platforms, water entry of lifeboats, and the flooding and structural integrity of a building that is being inundated by a tsunami, have been discussed.

It may be concluded that the coupled FE-SPH approach within an existing industrial grade explicit FE program such as VPS can provide the essential numerical support and engineering insight to design structures that are capable of resisting loads due to contact with violent flow.

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e-Navigation Starts with e-VoyagePlanning

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Abstract

Considering the balancing of data/information flow needed in NextGen Navigation (e-Navigation) and decision support already in the VoyagePlanning phase. The navigational world is getting more and more complex. And the need for intelligent solutions to handle the workflow processes both onboard, to ship-ship and shore-ship collaboration, are in high demand. This includes all tasks; from the information collection in the voyage planning and optimization process, to reporting regimes and berth to berth safe navigation based on up to date and real time situation awareness. Not only to get more data out to the mariners whom are taking navigational and other operational decisions, but to enhance cooperation or “co-navigation” happening between other ships, and shore side support – from VTS and SAR, to dedicated routing service, presented as Intelligent Integrated Information. One of the main hazard to (e)-Navigation is the availability of good data that is presented and compiled in an “unintelligent” way. The same goes for the workflow for the operators: the process from Planning, Optimizing and Reporting, to berth to berth navigation is only as good as the weakest link of all the marine operators: be it the VTS or SAR operator, Pilot, Captain or the Lookout. And with no integrated tools to handle this workflow, the risk for misunderstanding, fatigue and human errors is very much present. This paper presents three central challenges and potentials in the voyage towards eNavigation: (1) More optimized and safer navigation based upon closer ship-ship and ship-shore collaboration, (2) a concept for voyage planning, optimization, collaboration and reporting processes, (3) The impact of e-Navigation on Polar Navigation. The paper presents the current status from different test beds, as well as IMO and industry alignment, to ensure that the harmonization and enhancement set forward in the e-Navigation visions are being realized. Stressing the need for good solutions that take into account intelligent information exchange between all marine stakeholders, from the onboard navigators, shore side VTS and SAR operators and the ship operators.

1. Introduction

As the shipping world is truly moving into the “Digital Ship”, international organizations and industry do a joint effort to ensure that the safety and security of both the seafarers and society are maintained and improved.

Saying that “e-Navigation starts with e-VoyagePlanning”, one have to look at what information vision IMO has for the Marine Community. The proposed solutions were drafted in IMO NAV 58, annex 4 and 5. Some of the system requirements concerned user-friendliness, automation and graphical integrations, and some functional requirements where information and reporting management, VTS service portfolio, Search and Rescue, and route and voyage plan exchange.

A key consideration is how this information is collected and presented to the marine operators; be it onboard for the mariner, or shore side for a marine VTS/SAR coordinator or manager. Also considerations work to be done to data compilation and compression, and the “postman”; communications.

The work to prepare and execute a voyage plan, is described on high level in IMO Res. A893; “Guidelines for Voyage Planning”. Starting with the appraisal, collection of relevant information, updating of charts (be it paper or digital official ENC), publications, and ship particulars are key. Going into planning process, manual or digital tools are available to collect and plan use of navigational aids, weather, and port information etc. Coming into actual execution, the process of navigation begin with maneuvering and ship handling; where one react to changing elements and situations, including COLREG and severe weather, ice and all other conditions that cannot be mitigated in the risk analyzing done in the Passage planning process. Finally for verifying; aids to

monitor the process like radar, ECDIS, and most important; lookout need to be used.

The Voyage Plan is sometimes referred to as the “tactic”, as it is done usually days or hours ahead of starting the voyage. The process of “e-Navigation” could probably be referred to as “wheel” or a circle; a continuous process of managing nautical information, preparing voyage and passage plans, maneuvering and navigation, optimizing especially in Transocean passages, reporting and voyage analyzing. Looking into the offshore industry; the process is the same, the only difference is that the ports are at sea; complicating the operations further (but mitigated i.e. with use of dynamic position systems).

The process should all collect in the all important voyage plan being available on the bridge. Taking into account more information being available – the risk of “information overflow” is becoming more present. The aviation industry has taken this into account, where Jeppesen has been in the lead to replace the traditional aviation charts with digital means. While in the marine industry; paper charts and publications are still to be maintained in a painstaking process. How do we ensure that the transformation to the digital information age in marine, thus e-Navigation, is happening as effective and user-friendly as possible?

Fig.1: Guidelines for voyage planning - process

2. IMO E-Navigation Development

For IMO, the visions of e-Navigation are developing into a reality. Even if the current ECDIS is under rigid performance standards, it is considered a key waypoint towards the realization, as part of the “INS” (Integrated Navigational System).

Some of the proposed e-Navigation solutions address potential for integration, graphical display, exchange of “Marine Service Portfolio” information (such as SAR and VTS), route segment exchange between ships (intended route), and collaboration on voyage plans (for authorized parties) for seaside and shore side operators. For the ship operators, the return of investment lies in safer and more efficient operations, and for the global society greener and safer ship operations with reduced risk of accidents – as well as increased transport efficiency.

The “BLAST” (Bringing Land and Sea together” project newly ended. The projects objective was:

- A harmonized model for data across land-sea, together with a prototype for land/sea interoperability between multiple sectors.
- Improved solutions for North Sea Navigation, including improved ENC harmonization, maritime data collection system, 3d port model, Digital Mariners Guide, and Harmonization of Nautical Information. Marine Traffic Harmonization and Climate Changes in Coastal Zones, as well as the operating ship reporting system “SafeSeaNet”.

Fig. 2: Results from BLAST

The need for a common “language” on information exchange has been solved with the development of the International Hydrographic Organization (IHO) “S100 GI registry” – which in contrast to the current “S57” format is an “open” registry. Meaning that organizations may submit new or improved standards, and is open for the industry to develop, adopt and improve solutions in the registry. This concept is being maintained by cross-organizational work between i.e. IHO, IALA, CIRM and so on – where industry members such as Jeppesen has leading positions and expertise.

Some of the potential for such solutions has already been proven: in 2011 the “EfficienSea” project was closed with a practical demonstrator on VTS and Ship collaboration chaired by the Danish Maritime Authority. In April 2012, as part of the “Marine Electronic Highway” project, a joint sea trial on real time information exchange of MSI (Maritime Safety Information), METOC and Notice to Mariners (NTM) was carried out in the Singapore straight. Systems involved were a Jeppesen eNav prototype based on a Navigational Kernel (Jeppesen SDK) and Kongsberg Norcontrol VTS – “C-Scope system.

Fig. 3: Singapore sea trials on “S100”

The sea trials were performed on request from IMO, chaired by Norwegian Coastal Administration and with close support from the Singapore MPA. The process was later replicated under an IMO workshop. It proved that AIS could be one potential carrier for “real time” short range navigational information from i.e. a VTS. In combination with efficient data compilation for NTM (Notice to Mariners) over minimum “internet” access such as WiMax – “S100” can work as a common framework for information exchange (Portrayal and data structure). Based on the project, the “S100” was adopted by IMO as a framework for e-Navigation data exchange.

Currently the joint EU funded project “MonaLisa2” is being established with the industry as vital contributors. The first waypoint for the project will to be establish of a common route (and potential voyage plan) format, and infrastructure to handle such exchange and collaboration between marine stakeholders. It also aligns with the IMO proposed e-Nav solutions for “exchange of route segment between ships and VTS”, and “voyage plan exchange and collaboration for authorized parties”. Questions has been raised, especially on “voyage plan exchange and collaboration” – however this is already being done between ship and specialized weather routing services – such as the Jeppesen Vessel Voyage Optimization Service (VVOS). The Monalisa project will look into how more services and expertise can be made available through common platforms for the onboard navigators and shore side operators (marine coordinators/ship operators) to ensure effective collaboration with safer and more efficient marine traffic handling. The objective for the project is to go from “surface based operations” to “voyage based operations”. Potential partners are SAAB, Jeppesen, SAM, Kongsberg, Furuno with others.

3. Industry Alignment

Jeppesen is one of the companies that already are aligning with the need for improved routing and information exchange; on automatic routing the “SeaRoutes” database is available in selected ECDIS/ECS systems with Jeppesen Chart databases, as well as the legacy “OceanView”. The onboard database is based on industrial recommended routes, and is updated weekly together with digital NTM's. For the end user, it reduce time for route planning from hours to seconds, freeing more time available to do quality assurance of the voyage plan. Also additional data such as Tides and Currents, SAR and GMDSS areas, and other information needed for improved voyage planning (Value Added Data) are available in the Jeppesen official ENC (Primar) and derived chart databases. To further support the need for improved voyage planning and operational support, the “eVoyagePlanner” program is currently being developed. Being another example how technology may help addressing all the aspects that are being involved in the voyage planning process.

As the ECDIS mandate is coming into effect for the IMO mandated fleet, more ship-owners and on-board operators are coming more familiar how technology can help them both to reduce cost and maintenance compared to traditional paper charts management, and improved safety. In parallel, development is being done to help support the transition. Jeppesen’s “Nautical Manager” and Chartco’s “Passage Planner” are just some of the solutions becoming available to minimize manual work for digital chart ordering and maintenance with highly automatic processes. Last year’s partnership between these two companies highlights the industrial efforts to ensure effective and cost effective transition.

For the navigational officer, effective distribution and loading of official ENCs and other marine information such as Weather forecasts raise issues due to general communication and performance restrictions. Jeppesen has achieved distribution of Official ENCs, weather forecast and other marine information in a “CM93/3 SENC” format – with a ratio approximately 1:9 compared to the “raw” S-57 and GRID formats. The data however, are in its nature official. But risk in loading into the systems and cost for communication are highly reduced. And probably improvements on the “S100” standard will further mitigate the risk and optimize the transition to the “Digital Ship”.

Fig. 4: Industrial alignment in the e-Navigation infrastructure

4. E-Navigation and Polar Navigation

In parallel with IMO e-Navigation, the IMO Polar Code is going from a vision to reality as the Polar Regions are being opened for commercial shipping. Questions are raised about the challenges and possible solutions for navigation safety in the areas.

Potential for both improved natural/fossil resource extraction, considerably shorten the Europe – East Asia route, as well as avoiding high security threat areas such as the Indian Ocean are just some of the incentives making shipping and oil and gas operators aware of the potential now opening up. However, marine operations in Polar Regions are facing considerable challenges. Remote areas, communication, icing of vessels, technology development, and access to information and so on, are just some of the issues that need to be addressed. As not only cargo shipping, but also tourist cruises are increasing in numbers.

5. Polar Code Status

In parallel with the work done on e-Navigation, mandates and regulations are being developed to ensure protection of both human life and environment in the regions under the Polar Code. Today IMO has issued the “Guidelines for vessels operating in polar waters” (2009) as an important mile stone towards a mandatory code.

This code cover the full range of design, construction, equipment, operational, training, search and rescue and environmental protection matters relevant to ships operating in the inhospitable waters surrounding the two poles.

The obvious challenge is ice coverage in general; a traditional ship with “V-shape” bow will be stuck in the ice attacking it from head on. Today this is solved in ice covered areas such as the Baltic Sea, northern Russia and so on with the support from specialized Ice breaker services. Some ship-operators, such as Knutsen OAS, has contracted specialized LNG carrier vessels to be able to sail the North East Passage route (LNG/C “Ribera del Duero” – classed DNV ICE-1A (up to 0.8 m ice thickness). However, they still will need help from ice breakers in some of the areas. A more direct approach is i.e. the “Norilskiy Nicke” working in Siberian waters, sailing traditional “bow first” in open waters, but with a special designed rear, going “aft first” up to 1.5 m thick ice.

Another well-known problem sailing in Polar Regions is the icing of the vessels, reducing the stability due to higher center of gravity (CG) For vessels risking this, dynamic stability calculation and mitigation with use of i.e. deck steam are important, as well as solutions for calculating risk of icing.

If an accident happens, both Search and Rescue, evacuation of personnel, as well as environmental impacts are great challenges. Pr. Today the IMO “Guidelines for voyage planning for passenger vessels operating in remote areas”, has escort/”tandem” sailing as one of the considerations. Also use of dedicated ice navigators is recommended. Another long term impact is a potential oil spill; as the oil will be trapped inside the ice, oil recovery is practical impossible – and may have greater environmental impact than ever seen before in very vulnerable environments. Norway and Russia have been cooperating to mitigate these potentials, with the “Barents Watch” program. The “Barents Ship Reporting System”, coming in effect 1. Of June 2013 are one of the results impacting the marine operations in the Arctic as one potential solution to improve Vessel Traffic Services (VTS) in the region.

Taking into account navigational issues – hydrographic surveys and charting is in its nature extremely challenging in these areas, and need special charts. ENC coverage to be used in the “ECDIS” is improving especially due to Norwegian and Russian collaboration, however is still a challenge due to projection issues and quality of data. Organizations like BSH and The Arctic and Antarctic Institute, are distributing special charts and ice coverage predictions, and navigational data providers such as Jeppesen ensures that the data is available in as efficient means as possible – such as through the “dkart IceNavigator”. The Norwegian “Hurtigruten” is one of the pioneers in Arctic/Antarctic tourist cruising. Their vessels doing polar tourist cruises use solutions such as official ENC charts and decision support tool “OceanView” software both from Jeppesen, in combination with a portable survey solution mounted on a tender boat when sailing in unsurveyed areas. Also specialized radars are being developed to ensure better situational awareness sailing in ice covered areas.

For areas surveyed, another issue arise with regards to Aids to Navigation (AtoN) – buoys are well known to drift, and taking into account the heavy forces drifting ice represent and maintenance for short range shore side systems, such solutions are practical impossible. Under the “e-Navigation” development, solutions such as “Virtual Aids to Navigation” and “specialized route exchange and advisory” are only some of the possible solutions that may arise.

Fig. 5: IceNavigator using official ENC and updated Ice information overlay

If e-Navigation is going to be used as a potential solution for polar navigation, communication has to be improved. In an IMO eNavigation workshop in Haugesund, Norway, results from a sea trial of VSAT coverage done aboard MV “Hurtigruten Fram” in September – coordinated by Norwegian Coastal Administration, showed large variations on coverage even within the “A3” area.

Fig. 6: Results from VSAT coverage sailing from Spitsbergen to Greenland and Iceland Sept. 2012

Today most SOLAS vessels are under GMDSS “A3” regulations to ensure communication especially for distress situations. For vessels sailing in Polar Regions the GMDSS “A4” regulations will apply. Today this is mostly covered by HF (High frequency – short wave) voice radio carriage, but is subject to effects such as frequency shift throughout the day, atmospheric disturbance and voice/language issues in general. The Iridium system is another available option, but not covering A4 carrier requirements. From the Norwegian hosted workshop, it became clear that both efficient compilations of navigational data, as well as improved communication infrastructure are critical to ensure e-Navigation in the regions.

6. The Way Forward

As much work are being done in IMO and supporting organizations such as IHO and IALA, with support from the industry, it is clear that navigation in general will change from reaction to changing elements, to better preparation, planning and mitigation of risks. Work is being done to ensure a shared minimum framework in the “S100”. It is clear that e-Navigation improve voyage based operations through better voyage planning. Seafarers will still need to be able to react to changing conditions, but probably technology can help in the processes of risk management and planning both for seagoing and shore side personnel. Information need to be available as early as possible.

Polar navigation represent a new frontier, and will maybe be the ultimate test of e-Navigation solutions for information exchange such as weather and ice forecast, recommended routes, maritime service information and so on.

The industry has already available solutions for efficient data handling, information exchange and management - mitigating risk of system failure or loss of data, and ensuring situation planning and awareness for all marine stakeholders. Be it for the ship side navigators or shore side operators and managers.

Probably the largest challenge lies in communication infrastructure (the “postman”) – where joint

industrial effort in combination with international collaboration are underway. Taking all these considerations into account is a huge task. Marine traffic are increasing, and demand for safer and more efficient operations put the whole marine industry under pressure; from the onboard navigators and shore side marine VTS/SAR coordinators, to the Fleet Managers and Authorities.

Simple standards to exchange the knowledge and information between all stakeholders are a necessity and has always been done some way or the other. The change is that e-Navigation will require extended situational awareness. And situational awareness starts with proficient planning and preparation. That's why "e-Navigation starts with e-VoyagePlanning".

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A CAD Development Strategy for the Next Years

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Abstract

This paper suggests a new strategy to develop CAD applications taking into account some of the most interesting proposals which have recently appeared in the technology development arena. Programming languages, operating systems, user devices, software architecture, user interfaces and user experience are among the elements which are considered for a new development framework. This strategy considers the organizational and architectural aspects of the CAD application together with the development framework. The architectural and organizational aspects are based on the programmed design concept, which can be implemented by means of a three-level software architecture. These levels are the conceptual level based on a declarative language, the mathematical level based on the geometric formulation of the product model and the visual level based on the polyhedral representation of the model as required by the graphic card. The development framework which has been considered is Windows 8. This operating system offers three development environments, one for web applications (HTML5 + CSS3 + JavaScript), and other for native applications (C/C++) and of course yet another for .NET applications (C#, VB, F#, etc.). The user interface and user experience for non-web application is described with XAML (a well known declarative XML language) and the 3D API for games and design applications is DirectX. Additionally, Windows 8 facilitates the use of hybrid solutions, in which native and managed code can interoperate easily. Some of the most remarkable advantages of this strategy are the possibility of targeting both desktop and touch screen devices with the same development framework, the usage of several programming paradigms to apply the most appropriate language to each domain and the multilevel segmentation of developers and designers to facilitate the implementation of an open network of collaborators.

1. Introduction

This paper describes a combination of push-pull technology innovations in the CAD development process to create a new category of applications. Push innovation is the process of incorporating new product concepts to develop truly unique product offerings. On the other hand, pull innovation consist of playing the role of early adopters to integrate innovative solutions which have been developed by third parties.

The push innovation considered in this paper is the programmed design concept, *Rodríguez and Fernández-Jambrina (2012)*. Programmed design is an evolution of parametric design, being its objective to create parametric designs tools. Programmed design provides a methodology to extract the design knowledge from a design experience to store and reuse it many times.

Programmed design must be supported by a comprehensive product model in order to face the modeling of any type of ship. Additionally, the product model has to be created by means of a design language. The main purpose of the language is to publish the modeling algorithms of the CAD application in the designer knowledge domain to let the designer create parametric model scripts.

The pull innovation which is being considered in this paper is the adoption of Windows 8 as a development framework. Windows 8 comes with a new development model to create a new kind of application called Windows 8 Style, which provides a first-class user experience with multi-touch and sensors, being very sensitive in terms of user interface responsiveness. Additionally, Windows 8 still allows developing traditional desktop applications. To cope with these two environments, Windows 8 provides two fundamental stacks of technologies, one for Windows 8 style applications and one for desktop applications, that can be used side-by-side.

Consequently, Windows 8 is the first operating system that tries to get the best of both worlds by providing a mix of the two UI paradigms. The well-known desktop applications are best suited for content-creating scenarios (such as designing CAD product models) whereas Windows 8 style apps are best at consuming content. These type of applications can be very useful when exploiting the aforementioned CAD product models far from the design office, for example, replacing the use of paper drawings by using smart (and sometimes ruggedized) devices. The next paragraphs are devoted to explain these innovations more in detail.

2. Programmed design

2.1. Concept

Programmed design is a proposal to provide advanced users with a CAD environment in which they can incorporate their knowledge in the application by themselves. Consequently, the programmed design functionality is a component to be built on top of an existing CAD application, where the CAD application provides the algorithms used to create the product model elements. To reach this goal, programmed design incorporates a design language to allow the advanced user to write modeling scripts. The CAD application plays the role of provider (of the modeling algorithms) and the design language publishes these algorithms in the designer knowledge domain.

2.2. Design language

A suitable language for supporting modeling tasks performed by a CAD user without programming skills must comply with some requirements. As the language has to be read by the design application, it plays the role of interpreter of the language.

As the CAD user is not supposed to have special skills to write complex algorithms, his objective would be to specify what the program should accomplish, rather than describing how to go about accomplishing it. Additionally, the language should be specifically oriented to the ship design modeling domain. Consequently, the design language should be a declarative interpreted domain specific language with some control sentences such as loops and conditional branches to facilitate executing repetitive tasks and automation of processes.

A declarative language script consists of a sequence of declarations with the objective of building product model elements. Each of these sentences creates a geometric construction which can be either a product model component or an auxiliary entity to be used later to build a more complex component of the product model. These declarative sentences can be considered “constructors” of primitives (auxiliary elements) or components (constitutive product model elements).

Hence, a design language script is a set of constructors which can be combined with control sentences to create loops, branches and procedures. The outcome of executing this script should be a complete ship product model or a part of it.

2.2.1. Types and constructors

The design language has to provide a complete set of element types in order to be able of creating any primitive or component which may be required to build the product model.

According to these language premises, each type contains a set of constructors, each of them implementing a specific algorithm or method to create an element of such type. Each constructor must be identified by a unique name and has associated a list of arguments which collects all the input data required by the algorithm. Each element of the list of arguments is a primitive of the product model. The result of executing the constructor is a new primitive or a new component of the product model.

In order to create a primitive or a component of a concrete type with a specific constructor, all of the primitives required by the list of arguments must be created previously. This can lead to very heavy scripts. To avoid this problem the language must provide the option of specifying anonymous constructors. An anonymous constructor creates on the fly an element of the required type within the list of arguments of another constructor, in order to be consumed immediately and for this reason no name is required.

Then the syntax of a constructor invocation is: *TYPE elemID ConstructorID (primID1, . . . , primIDn);*

An anonymous constructor contains only the constructor identification with the list of arguments, as the type is inferred from the context:

ConstructorID (primID1, . . . , primIDn)

Using an anonymous constructor consists in substituting a primitive identification in the list of arguments of another constructor with the anonymous constructor invocation:

TYPE elemID ConstructorID1(primID1,primID2, . . . , primIDn);

↓

TYPE elemID ConstructorID1(primID1, ConstructorID2(p1, . . . , pn), . . . , primIDn);

Anonymous constructors can be nested ad infinitum.

3.3.2. Control sentences

The designer must have the possibility of writing loops and conditional jumps to implement more advanced procedures. The following schemas are required:

Conditional branching: *if (B1); . . . ;else if (B2); . . . ;else; . . . ;end if;*

Conditional loop: *while(B); . . . ;end while;*

In the above expressions, B, B1 and B2 are identifications of Boolean elements or anonymous constructors of such type of primitive.

List scanning loop: *for(listID, listIndex, listElement); . . . ; end for;*

In order to take full advantage of the list scanning loop, the language has to include a list type for each type of primitive (float list, points list, curves list, etc.) and some list of lists types (list of lists of floats, etc.).

Element mutator: *set elemID ConstructorID (primID1, . . . , primIDn);*

The mutator syntax is required for modifying existing elements by means of any of its constructors.

In order to organize, encapsulate and reuse design language scripts, the language must provide the possibility of writing procedures and user constructors:

Procedure encapsulation: *proc procID(inputID1, . . . , inputIDn); . . . ;end proc(outputID1, . . . , outputIDm);*

Procedure invocation: *call proc((inputID1, . . . , inputIDn), (outputID1, . . . , outputIDm));*

User constructor definition: *cons TYPE ConstructorID(TYPE1 primID1, . . . , TYPE n primIDn); . . . ;ret retID;*

User constructor invocation: *TYPE elemID ConstructorID(primID1, . . . , primIDn);*

A complete language specification is out of scope of this paper, but in order to explore the programmed design concept the authors have developed a program for demonstration purposes. This prototype implements some geometric constructors for hull form design. In the next paragraph a simplified case of use of programmed design is shown, which has been created with the demonstration program just to illustrate this paper.

2.3. Example

The first example illustrates a script for the creation of a fore profile curve from the given x and z coordinates.

<code>lf <i>xp</i> .(50,59,55,65,70);</code>	Create a list of floats (lf type) named <i>xp</i> with the default constructor
<code>lf <i>zp</i> .(0,4,10,17.5,20);</code>	Create a list of floats (lf type) named <i>zp</i> with the default constructor
<code>lp2 <i>lprof</i> .lf (<i>xp</i>, <i>zp</i>);</code>	Create a list of 2D points (lp2 type) named <i>lprof</i> with the .lf constructor from two list of floats (one for the u coordinates and the other for the v coordinates)
<code>c2 <i>c2prof</i> .(<i>lprof</i>);</code>	Create a 2D curve named <i>c2prof</i> with the default constructor from a list of 2D points
<code>c <i>prof</i> .xz(0, <i>c2prof</i>);</code>	Create a 3D curve named <i>prof</i> with the .xz constructor from y coordinate and a 2D curve (if y is omitted default value is 0)

The following picture illustrates the first example with some syntactic simplifications easily admitted by the language, including the use of anonymous constructors.

Fig.1: Fore profile curve definition (simplified)

The construction of the curve can be enhanced by considering the tangencies at each point of the curve. Another constructor for the 2D curve is required for this new definition. The following script shows only the modifications from the previous one.

<code>ltc2 <i>tprof</i> .(0,90,90,30, .n);</code>	Create a 2D curve tangencies list named <i>tprof</i> with the default constructor from a list of 2D tangencies (angles). A free tangency is indicated with the tangency constructor <i>.n</i>
<code>c2 <i>c2prof</i> .pt(<i>lprof</i>, <i>tprof</i>);</code>	Create a 2D curve named <i>c2prof</i> with the .pt constructor from a list of 2D points and a list of 2D tangencies
<code>c <i>prof</i> .xz(0, <i>c2prof</i>);</code>	Create a 3D curve named <i>prof</i> with the .xz constructor from y coordinate and a 2D curve (if y is omitted default value is 0)

Fig. 2 illustrates the new version of the curve with the same syntactic simplifications.

Fig.2: Fore profile curve definition (enhanced)

To illustrate the use of loops, the next example shows the construction of several frames from a simplified offset. The offset is defined by means of list of (lists of) floats.

lf <i>x</i> .(0, 20, 40);	List of floats (lf) for frame abscissas named <i>x</i>
lf <i>z</i> .(0,4,10,17.5,20);	List of floats (lf) for waterline heights named <i>z</i>
mf <i>y</i> .(.(0,10,17.5,20,20), .(0,7.5,16,19.5,19.5), .(0,4.5,9.5,15,15));	List of lists of floats for frame half breadths, named <i>y</i> . There is one list of half breadths for each frame (3 lists = length of <i>x</i> list), with the half breadths for each height (5 half breadths = length of <i>z</i> list).
ltc2 <i>tframes</i> .(0, .n, .n, 90, 90);	List of 2D curve tangencies named <i>tframes</i> , for the frames
for <i>x</i> <i>i</i> <i>xc</i> ;	Init loop through list <i>x</i> using index <i>i</i> =(0, 1, 2) and the list value at <i>i</i> named <i>xc</i> =(0, 20, 40)
c <i>fr</i> < <i>i</i> > .yz(<i>xc</i> , .pt(.lf(.lis <i>y</i> <i>i</i> , <i>z</i>), <i>tframes</i>));	Create a 3D curve named <i>fr</i> < <i>i</i> > =(fr0, fr1, fr2) with the .yz constructor from x coordinate and a 2D curve
end for;	End loop

Fig.3: Frames created with a loop from offset lists

Before creating a patch with the previous curves, a patch tangency is required for the fore end. The creation of this curve from the fore profile is illustrated in the following example.

<code>ltc2 tprof .(0,90,90,30, .n);</code>	Create a list of 2D tangencies named <i>tprof</i> with the default constructor using a list of angles. A free tangency is indicated with the tangency constructor <i>.n</i>
<code>c2 c2prof .pt(lprof, tprof);</code>	Create a 2D curve named <i>c2prof</i> with the <i>.pt</i> constructor from a list of 2D points and a list of 2D tangencies
<code>c prof .xz(0, c2prof);</code>	Create a 3D curve named <i>prof</i> with the <i>.xz</i> constructor from y coordinate and a 2D curve (if y is omitted default value is 0)
<code>pla pi .xy(50 0, 20);</code>	Create a plane named <i>pi</i> which intersection with XY plane passes through XY point (50, 0) forming 20° with X axis
<code>c tfore .pxz(pi, c2prof);</code>	Create a 3D curve contained in the plane <i>pi</i> and which projection in the XZ plane is <i>c2prof</i>

Both curves, the fore profile and the fore end tangency, are created with the same geometry in order to make waterline endings perpendicular to the centre plane. Fig. 4 illustrates the example with the simplified notation.

Fig.4: Fore end tangency curve

Then, the fore body can be created using a list of curves in order to gather all of the input data required by the patch constructor.

Fig.5: Fore body creation

Fig.6: Fore end construction with the tangency curve

The script shown in Fig.7 generates a product model (or a part of it) with the geometric representation of the ship hull forms. At this point the script can be considered as a conceptual representation of the product model as it contains all the information required to generate it. One of the major advantages of programmed design is that it comes with the geometric parameterization out of the box. Any of the values used within the script to generate the product model can be converted automatically in a parameter to produce variations of the model. To illustrate this feature, in the following example the complete script is encapsulated within a user constructor which exposes only one parameter to produce model variations. For this example, the bulb nose abscissa has been selected as a parameter.

```
const pat .bulb(f len);
  if x 0 20 40;
  if z 0 4 10 17.5 20;
  mf y ( 0 10/17.5 20 20, 0 7.5 16 19.5 19.5, 0 4.5 9.5 15 15);

  if xp 50 len 55 65 70;
  if zp 0 4 10 17.5 20;

  lc lfr .ini;
  ltc2 tfr 0 .n .n 90 90;

  for x i xc;
    set lfr .add(.yz(xc, .pt(.lf(.lis y i, z), tfr)));
  end for;

  ltc2 tprof 0 90 90 30 .n;
  set lfr .add(.xz(0, .pt(.lf xp zp, tprof)));
  c tbody .pxz(-xy(50 0, 20), .pt(.lf xp zp, tprof));

  pat body .ti(1 tbody, .rev lfr);

ret body;
```

Fig.7: User constructor defining the patch with all the input data as internal values and exposing the abscissa of the nose of the bulb as a single parameter or external value

2.4. Programmed design architecture

The different types of algorithms and services which are implemented by the product model can be organized into three levels of abstraction. The most abstract level is devoted to implement the design language, the organization of the model, the topology and any other kind of relational or organizational aspect of the product model. The following level provides a mathematical formulation for each of the entities created by the product model. Finally, the model has to interact with the graphic card, which requires a visual representation of the model based on faceted or polyhedral surfaces and polylines. This visual model is created from the mathematical formulation by means of some algorithms which require the selection of certain precision parameters.

Fig.8: Product model variations produced with a list of abscissas and a loop over it to generate one patch for each abscissa of the bulb nose

These three levels can be identified as the conceptual level, the mathematical level and the visual level and they can be interpreted as a cause–effect chain or a three stage projection process. The concept is implemented or described mathematically and these mathematical entities are visualized or represented in the machine. Ideally, the whole definition of the product model should be performed at the conceptual level while the whole product model exploitation would take place at the visual level.

2.5. Use cases

Programmed design can be considered as a tool for creating design tools or as a method to store and reuse design experiences. For a single or sporadic design, programmed design may not be the preferred tool because the user interface based on a design language is not the most adequate for the occasional designer. To fill this gap, the scripts developed with programmed design could be wrapped within advanced user interface widgets to facilitate their usage by less experienced designers.

Another scenario where programmed design provides some advantages is CAD-PLM integration. With programmed design CAD apps, the PLM can manage the product model by controlling scripting files instead of product model files. CAD-PLM integration can be easily implemented at the conceptual level.

Finally, another way to improve the use of programmed design is to reverse the normal flow from conceptual level to mathematical level. Hence, this functionality would provide the possibility of transferring a mathematical model to a conceptual model. This process could require the selection of the types of entities and constructors which are required to generate the mathematical model being imported, but it should be automated as much as possible in order to take full advantage of the process. This improvement would allow the application to incorporate external designs with the same capabilities as native or proprietary designs and consequently create programmed designs with external information in a very easy way.

3. Development Framework

3.1 Windows 8

Windows 8 comes with two fundamental stacks of technologies that can be used side-by-side, one for Windows 8 style applications, which is adequate for touch screen devices and other for the “traditional” desktop applications, *Novák et al. (2012)*. While Windows 8 has put a lot of importance on the user interacting with the computer through the use of touch gestures, the Windows 8 user interface is referred to as touch-first and not as touch-only. Fig. 9 shows both stacks of technologies, showing their different layers. Web application layers have been omitted to simplify the figure.

Fig. 9: Windows 8 stacks of technologies for desktop and Windows 8 style applications, adapted to CAD applications development

The advantage of this new framework is that both architectures can share the same business layers (the business layer can be located within the language layer of the Fig.8) while their differences can be isolated in the UI and API layers. The UI layer of both types of application can be based on the same declarative UI language, XAML. Microsoft provides several implementations of XAML. WPF is the XAML implementation for desktop applications while there is a new implementation for Windows 8 style applications called Windows 8 XAML. Other implementations are the different versions of Silverlight.

The API layer for native desktop applications is the traditional Win32 API, while managed desktop applications use the .NET framework API which is built on top of the previous one. Windows 8 style applications have one single API layer, Windows Runtime, which can be accessed from C++, C#, Visual Basic, and JavaScript.

3.2. Language layer

For the past couple of decades, object-oriented programming has dominated the CAD application development industry due to its ability to hide complexity and provide structure and intuition. Object-oriented programming encourages code reuse and provides specialization through inheritance, which can help to deal with complexity. The most widespread development language in this context is C++. This language is extremely popular and therefore lots of support is available. But C++ has a more difficult learning curve than modern object oriented languages like java and C#. The C++ language is very demanding about how code is formatted and the most powerful features, such as templates, have a very complex syntax. In C++ GUI, threads and networking are not standardized, requiring the use of non-standard third-party libraries. Memory management in C++ is quite a complex feature compared

to java and C#, which frees developers from manually allocation and freeing the memory occupied by objects.

Taking into account all these facts, C# can be considered a serious alternative to C++. In the comparison between C# and C++, it is usually accepted that C++ provides better program performance while C# provides better programmer productivity. The CAD applications require intensive use of graphic operations, where the C++ performance can be decisive. To counteract this advantage, the C# JIT (just in time) compiler has incorporated lots of optimizations and really the differences in performance for a CAD application could be relevant only the first time the program is executed and this can be assumed as the last deployment step. Just focusing on the development process issues (productivity, code readability, code free of errors, memory leaks, ease of maintenance, etc.) C# has many advantages.

One point in favor of C++ is that the cloud is promoting native applications because they reduce battery consumption with respect to managed applications. This is very important when applications are executed in smart devices. Maybe this is the reason why Windows 8 gives to C++ such a relevant role in its development architecture. But using C++ or C# should not be an issue in Windows 8, because in this platform both languages can coexist without too much effort if a clear frontier between them is well established. In desktop applications this interface is built with technologies such as platform invocation (P/Invoke) and COM interoperability. For Windows 8 style applications there is a smarter solution in which native and managed code can interoperate easily because each programming language is capable of consuming Windows Runtime objects. In order to utilize a component in any other language, its functionality can be exposed creating a reusable Windows Runtime object that can be utilized in Windows 8 applications independently of the consuming programming language. An application built on this basis is called a “hybrid solution”.

C++ and C# are both object oriented languages. While object-oriented programming may work well for modeling some concepts, it has a tough time encoding algorithms and abstract concepts because not all kinds of complexity submit willingly to the mechanisms of encapsulated shared state and virtual methods. In the context of object-oriented programming, the solution comes in the form of general reusable solutions called design patterns, which formalize best practices and help to describe abstractions in terms of objects and their relationships, *Smith (2012)*.

While design patterns are helpful, they are simply a compensation for object-oriented programming inability to simply express certain concepts. In addition, they are a burden for the programmer by forcing the creation of boilerplate code in order to define the contract and relationships between objects. When reaching this complexity, the alternative to object-oriented programming is functional programming. Functional programming is a paradigm originating from ideas older than the first computers. Its history goes as far back as the 1930s, when Alonzo Church and Stephen C. Kleene introduced a theory called lambda calculus as part of their investigation of the foundations of mathematics. Even though it did not fulfill their original expectations, the theory is still used in some branches of logic and has evolved into a useful theory of computation, *Petricek and Skeert (2012)*.

Functional programming is a style of programming that emphasizes the evaluation of expressions, rather than execution of commands. The expressions in these languages are formed by using functions to combine basic values. Functional languages are expressive, accomplishing great feats using short, succinct, and readable code. All of this is possible because functional languages provide richer ways for expressing abstractions. Developers can hide how the code executes and specify only the desired results. The code that specifies how to achieve the results is written only once.

As a result, many mainstream languages now include some functional features. In the .NET world, generics in C# 2.0 were heavily influenced by functional languages. One of the most fundamental features of functional languages is the ability to create function values on the fly, without declaring them in advance. This is exactly what C# 2.0 enables to do using anonymous methods, and C# 3.0

makes it even easier with lambda expressions. The whole LINQ project is rooted in functional programming. Also C++ 11 brings a number of new tools for functional-style programming. While the mainstream languages are playing catch-up, truly functional languages have been receiving more attention too. The most significant example of this is F#. F# is a functional programming language for the .NET Framework. It combines the succinct, expressive, and compositional style of functional programming with the runtime, libraries, interoperability, and object model of .NET.

Programming paradigms are not exclusive. The C# language is primarily object-oriented, but in the 3.0 version it supports several functional features. On the other side, F# is primarily a functional language, but it fully supports the .NET object model. The great thing about combining paradigms is that developers can choose the approach that best suits their problem. Functional programs on .NET still use object-oriented design as a methodology for structuring applications and components.

Thanks to functional programming, many of the standard object-oriented design patterns are easy to use because some of them correspond to language features in F# or C# 3.0. Also, some of the design patterns are not needed when the code is implemented under the functional paradigm. The biggest impact of functional programming is at the level where the algorithms and behavior of the application are encoded. Thanks to the combination of a declarative style, succinct syntax, and type inference, functional languages help to express concisely algorithms in a readable way. Another important feature of functional programming is the immutability of data structures (values instead of variables) which leads to concurrency friendly application design. Using a declarative programming style, parallelism can be easily introduced into existing code.

In the context of CAD applications development, functional programming offers significant productivity gains in important application areas such as the implementation of complex algorithms. Additionally, F# supports yet another programming paradigm, the language-oriented programming, *Syme et al. (2012)*. Language-oriented programming facilitates the manipulation and representation of languages using a variety of concrete and abstract representations and it is based on three advanced features of F# programming: F# computation expressions (also called workflows), F# reflection, and F# quotations. This paradigm is very useful to implement the programmed design concept.

3.3. UI & API layers

When the Windows Presentation Foundation (WPF) graphical subsystem was introduced in the .NET Framework the UI development paradigm was totally changed, from imperative programming to declarative programming. In order to describe UI elements, WPF uses the eXtensible Application Markup Language (XAML), an XML language. WPF also leverages the hardware capabilities of graphics processing units (GPUs). Additionally, Silverlight (the Microsoft's rich Internet application framework) also uses XAML to define the user interface, *Novák et al. (2012)*.

In Windows 8, the core of the XAML-based WPF and Silverlight technologies has become a part of the operating system, rewritten in native code. The UI of C++, C#, and Visual Basic applications can be defined in XAML. The same XAML produces the exact same UI in every language, without constraints or barriers. Because of the uniform UI technology and the same APIs providing access to the operating system services, application models are the same for C++, C#, and Visual Basic. XAML not only defines the UI, but can also declare its dynamic behavior using a minimal amount of code. XAML connect the UI with the business layer of an application. Following are some important features of XAML, *Novák et al. (2012)*:

- XAML is designed and tailored to allow creating rich, powerful desktop or Internet applications and to produce a superior user experience. In addition to providing simple UI elements (such as text boxes, buttons, lists, combo boxes, images, and so on), it also provides the freedom to create content with animation and media elements, such as video and audio. In contrast to the traditional UI approach with rectangular UI elements, XAML enables to change the entire face of an application.

- XAML provides a very flexible layout system that makes it easy to create layouts which can be automatically adapted to a number of factors, such as available screen size, number of items displayed, size of the displayed elements, and magnification.
- Styles and templates are features that contribute to a smooth cooperation between developers and designers. Developers implement the logic of the application, so that they never set the visual properties of the UI directly. Instead, they signal programmatically that the state of the UI is changed. Designers create the visuals of the UI, taking into account the possible states of the UI.
- With XAML data-binding, information coming from the database and the application's logic can be declaratively bound to the UI elements. Data binding works in cooperation with styles, templates, layouts, and even animations.
- XAML UI incorporates vector graphics. Vector graphics use math to render the contents, rather than pixels. The components are composed of curves and lines, and not of dots. This means that, with different resolutions, the UI remains visually pleasing. Scaling up and scaling down can be performed easily without the loss of quality. XAML-based UIs always show crisp and perfect fonts and drawings.

Fig. 10: Expression Blend (XAML visual edition)

XAML approach promotes true separation of concerns. Since XAML is its own file type, it is by necessity separated from the code that executes. While there is still a code behind file that accompanies it, good XAML together with solid application architecture can almost eliminate the need for code behind. In order to encourage better architecture and less code behind, XAML provides support for application features such as data binding and commands.

Expression Blend is the graphic design tool of choice for XAML based applications, *Cochran (2012)*. Blend is a vector graphic design tool which translates the design on the screen to the expressive text of XAML, bringing true separation of concerns to visual application development. It is mainly a design tool which can be used by designers and developers to share the product creation process. In

summary, Blend is a visual design tool that generates XAML, increases drastically the productivity, provides rapid prototyping, and greatly simplifies visual tasks.

With respect to the 3D API, it must be noted that everything in Windows 8 is optimized for and built around DirectX, from the developer platforms to the OS and to hardware design. This way, DirectX must be used to achieve the highest performance rendering in Windows 8, but DirectX APIs are available only in C++ and they are not defined as Windows Runtime types. In order to use DirectX from C#, the DirectX calls must be wrapped. For Windows 8 style applications, these calls can be wrapped in a separate Windows Runtime type library written in C++. Then, these Windows Runtime objects can be included and consumed from C#. For desktop applications the wrapper must be based on the interoperability tools already mentioned.

Fortunately, there is a great initiative in the form of an open source project called SharpDX, which has been created by Alexandre Mutel. The following paragraph is extracted from SharpDX web site, *Mutel (2010)*:

“SharpDX is an open-source project delivering the full DirectX API under the .Net platform, allowing the development of high performance game, 2D and 3D graphics rendering as well as real-time sound application. SharpDX is built with a custom tool called SharpGen able to generate automatically a .Net API directly from the DirectX SDK headers, thus allowing a tight mapping with the native API while taking advantages of the great strength of the .Net ecosystem. SharpDX is providing the latest DirectX and Multimedia API to .Net with true AnyCpu assemblies, running on .Net and Mono. SharpDX provides also a high level Graphics API called the Toolkit. SharpDX is ready for next generation DirectX 11.1 API, Windows 8 and Windows Phone 8 Platform. SharpDX is the fastest managed DirectX implementation.”

4. Conclusions

This paper is a proposal containing several technical innovations to develop a new generation of CAD applications. The main objective is to incorporate some of the following competitive advantages in the new product:

- Desktop and touch screen applications developed with the same framework and sharing most of the software layers will allow to extend the CAD functionality to smart devices.
- The possibility to use several programming paradigms allows a better segmentation of developers, advanced users and UI designers, providing a very productive separation of concerns which facilitates the implementation of an open network of collaborators:
 - Object oriented programming for developers coding service layers
 - Functional programming for engineers and scientist writing complex algorithms, languages and semantics
 - XAML visual design for UI designers
 - Programmed design for advanced users creating model scripts to store and reuse knowledge and to facilitate PLM integration

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CFD Prediction of Wind and Current Loads on a Complex Semi-Submersible Geometry

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Abstract

This paper presents steady RANS simulations results of the wind and current loads acting on a semi-submersible oil platform, using OpenFOAM 2.0. Flow angles range from 0 to 360 degrees. The current and wind analyses are treated separately. The current analysis is performed in a uniform flow. In the wind analysis, the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) is captured. The computational mesh is generated in snappyHexMesh including several levels of detail. Viscous layers are not modelled. The computed results are compared to wind tunnel measurements.

1. Introduction

Environmental loads acting on floating offshore units play an important role in the assessment of stability and in the design of anchoring systems. Traditional methods of determining wind and current loads have been to conduct model tests in a wind tunnel or to rely on empirical methods based on the compilation of experimental results. In recent years, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has become increasingly popular and has proved to be more cost effective and flexible than traditional approaches. Before CFD can be used on its own with appropriate confidence, a better understanding of the possibilities, limitations and sensitivity of CFD results to various parameters is required.

The present paper assesses the wind and current loads on the Åsgard B platform by means of full scale CFD simulations. Åsgard B is a Statoil operated semi-submersible offshore oil platform moored in the Norwegian sea at about 300 meters depth. The numerical results are compared to wind tunnel measurements performed at FORCE Technology, *Smidemann (2012)*. The two main challenges that are addressed in this paper are the complexity of deck structure meshing and an accurate model of the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL).

In most studies about current loads, *Vaz et al. (2009)*, *Ottens et al. (2009)*, and wind loads, *Furnes (1998)*, *Zhang et al. (2010)*, the geometry of the platform is simplified. This simplification has the advantages of reducing the mesh size, the mesh generation and computation times, as well as improving the mesh quality. However, the accuracy of the results is reduced with increasing simplification level. *Koop et al. (2010)* observed a 20 % decrease in wind loads due to geometrical simplifications and concluded that they should be done with great care. In the present study, only very small features were removed from the CAD model of the platform. This choice resulted in a complex geometrical model with a very large number of surfaces. An automatic meshing process had to be implemented in order to avoid large mesh generation time.

The above water section of the platform is located in the lower part of the ABL where large vertical velocity gradients occur. As the major contribution to the wind load is reported to come from the platform columns, *Furnes (1998)*, *Lee and Low (1993)*, it is important to have a proper representation of the wind close to the ground. In offshore environment, the vertical wind profile is often estimated by the power law:

$$U(z) = U_{ref} \left(\frac{z}{z_{ref}} \right)^{\alpha} \quad (1)$$

U is the horizontal flow velocity, z is the elevation above mean sea level, U_{ref} is the magnitude of U at the reference height z_{ref} and α is a dimensionless parameter which depends on the terrain roughness. In

DNV (2010), a value of $\alpha = 0.12$ is recommended for open seas with waves. Furnes (1998) and Koop et al. (2012) reported difficulties to maintain this inlet profile through the computational domain and observed that the wind loads are highly dependent on the velocity profile at the model location. This difficulty has been extensively studied in Computational Wind Engineering. Richards and Hoxey (1993) and Blocken et al. (2007) recommend using a logarithmic velocity profile together with an appropriate set of boundary conditions in order to obtain a horizontally homogeneous wind profile when modelling the ABL. However, it is seldom that their recommendations are applied in CFD simulations of wind load on offshore structures. In this study, a logarithmic wind profile is designed to fit experimental data from wind tunnel tests and recommendations from Richards and Hoxey (1993) and Blocken et al. (2007) are applied.

2. Definitions and dimensionless parameters

The platform's coordinate system orientation and the flow direction ψ are defined in Fig.1. The origin is located at mean sea level and at mid distance from the platform's columns in longitudinal and lateral directions. Note that this coordinate system is not coherent with the ABL model coordinate system (used e.g. in Eq.(1)), in which the x-direction is aligned with the flow direction and pointing downstream, and the z-direction is pointing up.

Fig. 1: Platform's coordinate system and definition of flow direction H represents the helideck.

The forces and moments coefficients estimated on the platform are defined by

$$C_{Fx} = \frac{F_x}{\frac{1}{2} U_{ref}^2 A_F}, \quad C_{Fy} = \frac{F_y}{\frac{1}{2} U_{ref}^2 A_S} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{Mx} = \frac{M_x}{\frac{1}{2} U_{ref}^2 A_S L_{ref}}, \quad C_{My} = \frac{M_y}{\frac{1}{2} U_{ref}^2 A_F L_{ref}} \quad (4)$$

F_x and F_y are the forces on the structure in x- and y- direction and M_x and M_y are the moments on the structure in x- and y- direction around the center of the platform. A_F and A_S are the projected front and side areas. U_{ref} the free stream velocity and L_{ref} is the length over-all of the platform's hull. The coefficients are expressed in the platform's coordinate system.

The Reynolds number is defined as

$$Re = \frac{U_{ref} L_{ref}}{\nu} \quad (2)$$

ν is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid. For the studies performed in ABL flow, the free stream velocity is given at $z_{ref} = 10$ meters above the mean sea level. Table 1 presents the Reynolds numbers of the various dataset.

Table 1: Reynolds numbers of the various dataset.

	Current coefficients	Wind coefficients
Wind tunnel tests	$3.3 \cdot 10^5$	$2.0 \cdot 10^5$
CFD simulations	$2.3 \cdot 10^8$	$2.2 \cdot 10^8$

3. Wind tunnel tests

Wind tunnel tests were performed at FORCE Technology with a 1:250 scale model of the platform, *Smidemann (2012)*. An overall view of the model is presented in Fig.2. The current loads have been determined for the underwater section of the platform in uniform flow conditions. The wind loads have been determined for the above water section of the platform in an ABL flow corresponding to a power law profile with $\alpha = 0.13$, see Eq.(1). Measurements of the wind profile at the model location are presented in Fig.3. The angle between the incoming wind direction and the model varied from 0° to 360° with 10° increments.

Fig. 2: Wind tunnel model (left) and CFD model (right). The CFD model is split in four partitions corresponding to four levels of details.

Fig. 3: Atmospheric Boundary Layer: velocity (left) and turbulent kinetic energy (right) profiles. Left: Comparison of inlet velocity profile with wind tunnel measurements and target power law profile. Left and right: Comparison of the inlet and outlet profiles for the undisturbed flow.

4. CFD simulations

The CFD simulations were performed at full scale with the OpenFOAM 2.0 software. Considering low Froude regime, the free surface effects may be neglected and the problem can be split into underwater loads and above water loads. Based on this splitting process, simulations were performed in the air phase only for wind loads and in the water phase only for current loads.

4.1. Domain and boundary conditions

Table 2 shows the main dimensions of the computational domains, which are shaped as boxes. On the platform surface, a wall function is applied on a non-slip smooth wall. The domain's side walls are considered as free-slip walls. At the outlet, a constant static pressure is specified and a zero normal gradient condition is imposed for all quantities.

Table 2: Dimension of domains

	Current simulations	Wind simulations
Domain size (x, y, z)	(10, 6, 2)*L _{ref}	(8, 6, 3)*L _{ref}

4.1.1. Current simulations

For the current simulations, uniform velocity and turbulence profiles are imposed at the inlet. Indeed, up to the depth of interest in this study, the current velocity profile can be assumed to be uniform, *Faltinsen (1993)*. The top boundary, which corresponds to the mean sea level, is considered as a free-slip wall assuming that there is no influence from the free surface on the flow. A sensitivity study was performed on the inlet turbulence intensity. It was found that in any case, the turbulence intensity decreases to less than 1% before reaching the model location. No solution was found in order to maintain the turbulence intensity level up to the model location in the case of a uniform flow.

4.1.2. Wind simulations

For the wind simulations, the vertical wind and turbulence profiles prescribed at the inlet boundary are the ones suggested by *Richards and Hoxey (1993)*:

$$U(z) = \frac{u_*}{\kappa} \ln \left(\frac{z + z_0}{z_0} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$k(z) = \frac{u_*^2}{\sqrt{C_\mu}} \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon(z) = \frac{u_*^3}{\kappa(z + z_0)} \quad (7)$$

k is the turbulent kinetic energy, ε the turbulent dissipation rate, u_* the friction velocity, C_μ a model constant of the standard k - ε model, κ the von Karman's constant (0.4187) and z_0 the surface roughness length. The values $u_* = 1.78$ m/s and $z_0 = 0.0021$ m were obtained from a fit of wind tunnel measurements, Fig.3. Those inlet conditions were implemented in a home made library which was used in the wind simulations. A constant shear stress in the streamwise direction is imposed at the top of the domain in order to maintain the flow at higher z -levels by imposing a constant velocity equal to $U(z=z_{\text{top}})$. The lower boundary, located at mean sea level, is treated as a rough wall and a wall function is applied. In order to avoid development of the ABL on this wall, there must be a first order matching between the ABL profile and the wall function velocity profile in the centre point z_p of the wall adjacent cell, *Blocken et al. (2007)*:

$$U(z_p) = \frac{u_*}{\kappa} \ln \left(\frac{z_p + z_0}{z_0} \right) = \frac{u_*}{\kappa} \ln \left(\frac{E z_p^+}{1 + C_s k_s^+} \right) \quad (8)$$

k_s is the equivalent sand grain roughness height, z_p^+ and k_s^+ are non-dimensional variables, respectively defined as $z_p^+ = z u_* / \nu$ and $k_s^+ = k_s u_* / \nu$, and $E = 9.793$. With the simplifications that $z_p \gg z_0$ and that in fully rough regime $C_s k_s^+ \gg 1$, the value of C_s has to be equal to

$$C_s = \frac{E z_0}{k_s} \approx \frac{E z_0}{z_p} \quad (9)$$

The equality between z_p and k_s allows to maximize the mesh resolution at the wall while keeping a wall adjacent cell center higher than the roughness height in order for the flow to be physical.

By using those boundary conditions, the inlet profiles, the ground shear stress and the turbulence model are in equilibrium and horizontal homogeneity is achieved for the undisturbed flow. Fig.3 presents the U and k profiles at the inlet and at the outlet of the domain. Variation of less than 1% and 3% are observed for the velocity and turbulence profiles, respectively.

4.2. Geometry and mesh

A block-structured hexahedral grid generated with the blockMesh utility is used as background mesh. For the current simulations, the background mesh is isotropic and uniform. For the wind simulations, the background mesh has a vertical gradient in the whole domain and local refinement in x- and y-directions around the platform location, Fig.4. The wall adjacent cell has a height of 1.3 m and an expansion ratio of 1.12 is applied. The combination of the different refinements leads to isotropic cells at the platform's deck level.

Fig. 4: Computational domain and background mesh for the wind simulations

For each flow angle, the flow direction is kept constant while the platform geometry is introduced with the appropriate orientation in the domain using the snappyHexMesh utility. The CAD model, shown in Fig.2, is split in four partitions corresponding to four levels of details. Features which could not be captured by the smallest cells ($L_{ref}/1000$) are removed from the model. A suitable refinement approach is defined for each partition in snappyHexMesh. This meshing strategy prevents the need of working individually with each surface of the CAD model. As the pressure component of the force is expected to be highly dominant, *Furnes (1998)*, viscous layers are not inserted in the mesh. Additional refinement boxes are placed around the platform in order to capture the near-wake effects.

The computational meshes contain about 5.6 million cells for the current simulations and 13 million cells for the wind simulations. Some details of the final wind simulation mesh are presented in Fig.5. The mesh generation time is decreased to less than one hour on a 32-cores 2.2 GHz computer by scripting the full meshing process and using the parallel capability of the snappyHexMesh utility.

4.3. Numerical setup

The potential flow solution of the problem is used as initial condition. The Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations are then solved iteratively with the steady-state solver simpleFoam for

incompressible turbulent flow. For the current simulations, a second order upwind method is used for the spatial discretization. For the wind simulations, first and second order upwind methods are successively used. The applied turbulence models are the $k-\omega$ SST for current simulations and the standard $k-\epsilon$ for wind simulations. However, for the turbulent kinetic energy dissipation rate ϵ to fulfil its conservation equation with the above mentioned inlet profiles, the turbulence model constant σ_ϵ is set to a value of 1.22, *Richards and Hoxey (1993)*. Residuals for the pressure, velocity and turbulence parameters are monitored.

Fig. 5: Surface mesh detail for the wind simulations

Fig.6: Typical convergence of residuals (left) and forces (right) for a wind simulation.

Although flow unsteadiness is expected in the wind tunnel tests, the main interest for design is the average loads. Comparisons between averaged unsteady loads and steady loads at some flow angles, *Ottens et al. (2009)*, showed that good agreement can be reached. The simulations were carried out seeking a steady-state regime, but the complex flow behaviour makes the convergence task extremely hard to achieve. A typical convergence behaviour for wind loads simulation is presented in Fig.6. The peak at 1000 iterations is due to a restart of the computation with the higher order scheme. As the residuals depend on the initial solution (i.e. the potential solution), a convergence of only two orders

is reached but the forces quickly reach a steady state value. After convergence, the loads oscillate around constant values and the mean coefficients for the last 300 iterations were calculated for force and moment prediction.

5. Analysis of results

The experimental and numerical results are compared for the longitudinal force C_{Fx} , the lateral force C_{Fy} , the roll moment C_{Mx} and the pitch moment C_{My} in Fig.7 for the current loads and in Fig.8 for wind loads.

The following observations can be made from the comparison of the current loads:

- The experimental measurements show that for a current direction of 0° and 180° the downstream columns are in the wake of the upstream columns, resulting in longitudinal loads C_{Fx} smaller than for the contiguous current directions. The transverse loads C_{Fy} presents a similar behaviour for current directions of 90° and 270° . This behaviour is properly captured by the CFD for C_{Fx} , resulting in an excellent agreement between the numerical and experimental results. It is not captured for C_{Fy} which however present an overall good match for other flow directions.
- Regarding the moment coefficients C_{Mx} and C_{My} , it is apparent that the general features of the measured moment components are resolved by the CFD simulations. However, the CFD simulations estimate a maximum roll moment C_{Mx} that is higher than the wind tunnel measurements. For the pitch moment C_{My} , some scatter appears between the results obtained numerically and experimentally but the trend is captured.

Fig.7: Current loads: Numerical simulations and wind tunnel measurements

The following observations can be made from the comparison of the wind loads:

- Taking into consideration the previously mentioned discrepancy in wind profile definition, the agreement is generally very good between the numerical results and the experimental values over the whole range of the wind angle.
- The numerical simulations capture the same trends as the wind tunnel measurements.
- At the peak values, the magnitude of the coefficients is systematically overestimated by $\sim 10\%$ for the force coefficients C_{Fx} and C_{Fy} and $\sim 20\%$ for the moment coefficients C_{Mx} and C_{My} .

Fig.8: Wind loads: Numerical simulations and wind tunnel measurements

There are a number of possible explanations of the deviations between numerical and experimental results. However, it is expected that the main error source are the different scales, the viscous effects for the current loads and the different wind profiles for the wind loads.

Experimental tests were performed at model scale while CFD simulations were performed at full scale, yielding different Reynolds numbers. It is reasonable to believe that scale effects will occur in wind tunnel tests and hence introduce errors when converting to full scale. Simulations at model scale are required in order to understand the connection between model scale and full scale loads.

The pressure part of the load is known to be dominant for blunt bodies. The viscous effects were therefore neglected in the CFD simulations. While the above water section of the platform is actually composed of blunt bodies, the pontoons and columns in the submerged section present rounded shape. The separation points in the current computations may therefore be affected by the wall shear stress. Simulations including viscous layers should be performed in order to show the impact of the viscous contribution on the loads. However, viscous layer generation at full scale requires a much higher mesh resolution near solid walls and is still a challenge, *Ottens et al. (2009)*.

The wind loads are highly sensitive to the inlet profile. In the CFD simulations, a fit of the experimental wind profile was used as inlet profile. The fit present some discrepancies relative to the measure-

ments close to the ground. Those discrepancies can affect the wind loads. Wind tunnel tests in a uniform flow should be performed in order to validate the CFD model independently from the ABL inlet profile.

It is also very likely that the flow during the model tests was unsteady. However, CFD simulations were performed assuming a steady-state regime. Averaging of oscillating steady-state results may not lead to results equivalent to averaged transient loads for all flow directions. It should be investigated whether the steady-state values are equal to the averaged unsteady values.

6. Conclusion

The current and wind loads on the Åsgard B semi-submersible oil platform were computed by means of full scale steady-state CFD simulations using the OpenFOAM 2.0 software. The objectives were to obtain a good quality mesh for a complex geometry and to model the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) with high accuracy. The quality of the predictions is assessed by comparing the numerical results with experimental results obtained from wind tunnel measurements on a 1:250 scale model.

An automated meshing approach for complex geometry was implemented and successfully used in this study. The geometry split into partitions with various levels of details eased the application of appropriate refinement on each surface. The parallel capability of snappyHexMesh was used to reduce mesh generation time to less than one hour. Viscous layers were not generated. The very dense mesh resolution required near solid walls at full scale is still a challenge. However, viscous loads may be an important part of the current loads and further simulations including viscous layer modelling should be performed.

For the wind simulations in an ABL flow, the *Richards and Hoxey (1993)* vertical wind profiles were used as inlet profiles and showed horizontal homogeneity, providing good control on the incident flow. The experimental wind profile does not match the theoretical profiles, and the impact of this variation on the loads can be large. Further investigation on wind loads in uniform flow is recommended to validate the CFD model independently from the inlet profile.

In general, the numerical predictions compare reasonably well with the experimental results. In addition to the points previously mentioned, scale effects and unsteadiness of the flow may also be at the origin of discrepancies and would require further investigation.

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Simulation-Based Design Approach for Safer RoPax Vessels

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Abstract

Several major accidents during the last years encouraged the public discussion about passenger ship safety. On the other hand, R&D activities created a set of new safety concepts and design methods with good potential to enhance passenger ship safety to a higher level. This paper will give an overview on latest developments of simulation based design methods and tools, enabling the application of new safety concepts for RoPax vessels. Special focus will be drawn on a newly developed dynamic stability assessment criterion derived from sea keeping simulations and statistical evaluations, mitigating the risk of large amplitude rolling. Another topic will address a new approach for damage stability calculations, allowing evaluation of advanced hull subdivision concepts to increase survivability beyond SOLAS requirements. Furthermore the application of FEM based calculation methods in early ship design to evaluate the impact of collision resistant side structures on a RoPax layout will be discussed.

1. Insufficient Stability Event Index (ISEI)

The Insufficient Stability Event Index (ISEI) is an additional stability criterion to evaluate the dynamic stability of an intact vessel in waves. It evaluates a wide range of possible operating conditions for a specific loading condition. The index directly evaluates the ship responses in waves which are obtained from numerical simulations. During every simulation the actual condition of the ship is judged as safe or unsafe by applying the *Blume (1987)* criterion or the maximum roll angle, whichever of these two criteria is more conservative. Within the simulation, special care is taken to gather also all effects of parametric rolling.

Fig. 1: Ship with large roll amplitude

It is strictly recommended to sail ships with a GM solid (GM without correction for free surfaces of partially filled tanks like the flume roll stabilizing tank) above the limiting ISEI curve, even if the damage and intact stability regulations according SOLAS require less GM. If the present GM solid is below the limiting ISEI curve but still above the intact and damage stability regulations, it is strongly recommended to use anti-rolling devices like roll stabilizing tanks or fin stabilizers. For FSG ships the ISEI curve is displayed in the stability booklet together with the GM-required curves as shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2: Typical GM-Required and ISEI curves

2. Computational Procedure

2.1 E4-Rolls

The numerical simulation of ship motions known as E4-Rolls simulates the motion of ships in the time domain in all six degrees of freedom in irregular short crested sea ways. For four motions (heave, pitch, sway and yaw), response amplitude operators (RAO) are used, which are calculated linearly by means of strip theory. The surge motion is simulated assuming a hydrostatic pressure distribution under the water surface for the determination of the surge-inducing wave forces. The roll motion is simulated taking into account the non-linearity of the lever arm curve as well as the dynamic changes of the lever arms in waves. Details regarding the mathematical model are published e.g. in *Söding (1987a,b)*. Recent comparisons of model test and simulation results show a very good agreement especially for phenomena dominated by roll excitation due to stability alterations in waves, which also includes resonance conditions like parametric rolling. Usually the simulation results are somewhat conservative.

Fig. 3: Comparison of E4-Rolls simulation and tank testing

2.2 Blume Criterion

The stability criterion according to *Blume (1987)* evaluates the stability based on the still-water GZ-curve. Whenever the ship does not capsize during a simulation, the area E_R under the still-water righting lever arm curve between the maximum roll angle ϕ_{max} during the simulation and the point of vanishing stability is calculated, Fig.4. If the vessel capsizes during the simulation the area E_R is set to zero for this particular simulation. The mean E_R of all simulations in the same condition and the standard deviation σ of E_R are determined subsequently. A ship is regarded as save if the following equation is satisfied:

$$\bar{E}_R - 3\sigma \geq 0$$

Fig. 4: Residual area under the lever arm curve for the determination of the Blume-Criterion

2.3 Calculation of the Index Value

The index is determined by systematic and stepwise variation of characteristic wave period, the significant wave height, the encounter angle between the ship and the mean wave direction and the ship speed. For each combination, numerical simulations are performed which are used to determine whether the vessel is safe ($C_{fail} = 0$) or un-safe ($C_{fail} = 1$) in the given situation. The actual value of C_{fail} is determined either by the Blume-criterion or the maximum roll angle as explained above. Consequently, all un-safe situations contribute to the index. Each contribution is weighted with the probability of occurrence of the present combination. This probability of occurrence is calculated from the probability contributions for the sea state δP_{sea} , the encounter direction δP_{μ} and the ship speed δP_v . The probability distribution for the sea state is obtained from *Söding (2001)*, using the North Atlantic Ocean as reference area. The probability for the encounter direction is assumed to be equally distributed. The probability for the ship speed is modeled by a linear probability density function. Concluding, the ISEI is determined by:

$$ISEI = \sum_{head, beam, following} \left[\sum_{T_1} \sum_{H_{1/3}, \mu = \mu_{min}}^{\mu_{max}} \sum_{v_s = v_{min}}^{v_{max}} \delta P_{sea}(H_{1/3}, T_1) \cdot \delta P_{\mu}(\mu) \cdot \delta P_v(v_s | H_{1/3}, T_1, \mu) \cdot C_{fail}(H_{1/3}, T_1, \mu, v_s) \right]$$

2.4 Limiting Values

Limiting values for the ISEI have been found by analyzing various accidents which occurred during the past decades. Details of this work can be found in *Krüger et al. (2008)*. Based on the findings made during these accident investigations, ISEI values below 0.001 are considered to be sufficiently safe. The limiting curve in Fig.2 represents stability values for which the index lies at this limit.

3. Advanced Ship Hull Subdivision Concepts

If an accident occurs and the ship hull is penetrated due to collision or grounding, sea water will flow into the damaged and (through progressive flooding) all connected compartments. The remaining undamaged compartments have to provide sufficient buoyancy to keep the ship upright and afloat, allowing reaching the next harbor or at least allowing evacuating the ship's crew and passengers in a safe manner and sufficient time. The rules and regulations for damage stability conditions are defined for RoPax vessels in the SOLAS 2009 and for European waters in the Euro-SOLAS. Based on the Monte Carlo method, a new method to calculate damage stability was developed.

3.1 Basics of Monte Carlo-Simulation

Fig. 5: Statistical process: Probability distribution of the side penetration depth ($I/L=J=0.2$) acc. SOLAS 95, B1 and form simulation

Every statistical process may be described by a probability distribution. This probability distribution is typically determined by observation of events taking place in real life. As an example, Fig.5 may be taken. The graph shows the probability of the depth of a side penetration with a dimensionless length of 0.2 according SOLAS 95, B1. Using this probability distribution, e.g. the probability for penetrating a longitudinal bulkhead located at $B/5$ may be determined. Fig.5 shows that the probability for a penetration depth up to $0.2 B$ is approximately 0.63; i.e. 63% of all possible damages will not penetrate a longitudinal bulkhead located at $B/5$, because their depth is less than $B/5$. Consequently, 37% of all damages would penetrate the longitudinal bulkhead. The maximum probability is 1, corresponding to the maximum penetration depth. The minimum probability is 0, corresponding to the minimum penetration depth. By using the probability distribution for every transversal location of a longitudinal wall the probability of damage can be calculated. Thus, the probability distribution is assigning the probability to a certain event.

The principle of the Monte Carlo Simulation works is that a probability $P(x)$ is selected and, by applying the probability distribution, the corresponding event is determined. For selecting $P(x)$, a random generator is used, calculating uniformly distributed numbers in the interval $[0,1]$. Applying these random numbers as probabilities and determining the corresponding event by using the probability distribution, a population of events is generated. For a sufficiently high number of events taken into consideration, this population reflects the statistical distribution of the events that originally created the probability distribution.

The graph for “extent simulation” in Fig.5 was calculated by randomly creating 20.000 events with different penetration depths on discrete positions and determining the probability of bulkhead penetration by counting the yes / no events. Fig.5 clearly shows that the result is the same as given from SOLAS, except of the upper and lower extremes. To evaluate the accuracy of the procedure, depending on the number of events taken into account, the confidence interval can be calculated.

By this procedure the creation of explicit damage events (damage cuboid) needed for a damage stability calculation can be performed by a fully automated simulation, based on uniformly distributed random numbers and given probability distributions for position and size of damage. Each damage block causes a set of damaged rooms. The probability of damage for a given room set is determined by counting the number of damages and dividing this number by the number of all damages. The generation of damages works like this:

- Determining a damage cuboid by random generator based on given probability distributions
- Determining the damaged room sets
- Summation of the damages of the rooms of this set
- The probability of damage of a room set is then calculated by dividing the number of damages of this set by the total number of damages

This procedure, first mentioned and tested by Tellkamp in the EC research project NEREUS, turns out to be very simple and efficient in the daily work compared to the usual, manual definition of damage cases:

- As the probability of damage is determined by simple counting damages also very complex sets of adjacent compartments are automatically covered. This makes the evaluation of damage cases very clear.
- As the probability of damage relies on the binary evaluation of yes / no cases (damaged / not damaged) also for very complex geometries a distinct result is calculated (different to e.g. the use of the explanatory notes of SOLAS)
- As all probabilities of damage are calculated individually, the results of a damage calculation may be sorted according their probability. Thus, areas of possible improvements can be identified very easily.
- As the simulation is fully automated the number of damage combinations is nearly unlimited compared to the manual procedure. Thus, the critical value of the maximum possible index of survivability can be calculated. This is important for approval issues.

After generation of all damages a list of damages room sets and related damage probabilities is provided. For these the probability of survival has to be calculated to determine the index of survivability. Pre-condition for the use of this method is just, that the distribution of probability for location and size of damage is given. Furthermore, an algorithm is needed for determination of the damaged rooms by a given damage cuboid.

3.2 Application of the Monte Carlo method to the design of a RoPax vessel

The new method for calculation of damage stability was applied to investigate the further potential for further optimizing the safety of a modern RoPax design, Table 1, Figs.6 and 7.

Table 1: Main data of RoPax design

L_{oA}	199.90 m	Lane Meters	3158 m
L_{pp}	188.79 m	Trailer Capacity	210
Breadth Moulded	30.80 m	Car Capacity	161
Depth Moulded to Upper Deck	15.95 m	Pax in Cabins	420
Draught (Design)	6.50 m	Pax max.	542
Speed	25.00 kn	Crew	58

Fig. 6: Modern RoPax design

Fig. 7: Midship section

As a first step, the damage stability index of the given design was calculated to define a baseline. Applying the new Monte Carlo method, the achieved damage stability index was calculated to 0.779. The required damage stability index defined by SOLAS 95, B1 was 0.721. Thus, the given design is rated to be safe according to the SOLAS rules.

As mentioned before, the Monte Carlo method allows sorting the results according to their probability for easy identification of areas for possible improvements. For the given RoPax design, quite naturally, the very big and long lower hold was identified as the main driver of the damage stability index. As the lower hold is an important area to create income, its geometry should be untouched. Therefore the rooms and compartments around the lower hold were considered as potential areas to improve the damage stability performance further. The Monte Carlo method was applied on several new ideas for the arrangement of rooms and compartmentation around the lower hold, like e.g. triple hull, double hull above main deck, dividing the subdivision length of the double hull, etc. Finally, the most promising solution was identified to be kinds of pontoon deck, created by closing the areas between the existing web frames below the main deck, see the area marked in pink in Fig.8.

Fig. 8: Pontoon deck below main deck

If the lower hold is damaged and flooded, the pontoon deck acts like a kind of life belt, keeping the ship floating upright and stable. The damage stability index for this solution was calculated to be 0.834, compared to 0.779 for the initial design and 0.721 as required index by SOLAS 95, B1. This means an improvement of the damage stability performance of 6% against the initial design and 13% against the required index.

As the ship is rated safe according to rules and regulations when the calculated damage stability index is above the threshold of the required index, a further study was performed to evaluate whether the geometry of the lower hold could be improved for transportation of more trailers while still fulfilling all requirements from rules. A further lane was introduced to the lower hold, marked in yellow in Fig.9.

Fig. 9: Additional lane in lower hold

Consequently, the breadth of the double hull between tank top and main deck had to be reduced and the ramp connecting tank top and main deck had to be shifted outwards, all together being counter-productive for damage stability. Nevertheless, the newly introduced pontoon deck provides such an amount of additional safety that the drawbacks of the wider lower hold can be compensated. The achieved damage stability index was 0.745 compared to 0.721 as required. Thus the ship is still rated as safe, while being able to carry 3 more trailers in the lower hold. A rough estimation on additional investment for the pontoon deck versus the additional income from the trailers shows that an investment would pay off in less than three years.

4. Collision Resistant Ship Side Structures

If damage (e.g. by collision or grounding) cannot be avoided, the size of the penetration to the hull should be kept as small as possible. Within the German funded research project ELKOS a number of solutions to improve the collision resistance of the double hull on the ship sides were investigated.

4.1 Evaluation of Calculation Method by Large-Scale Tests

Explicit FEM methodology was applied to perform the crash simulations. To evaluate the results and adjust the calculation parameters to typical ship side structure crash behavior, a number of large-scale tests were performed at TU Hamburg-Harburg. The test facility arrangement is shown in Fig.10. On a stiff foundation built by two very large double T bars the test specimen (scale 1:3) can be placed. A complex clamping system fixes the specimen on the foundation, allowing adjustment of rotational and transversal boundary conditions of the side structure to realistic values. This is important to ensure realistic side structure behavior. Above this structure, a wide cross beam, connected to the foundation by four constrained joint translational motors, is placed. In the middle of the span of this cross beam different bulbous bow structures can be installed, directed to the middle of the side structure specimens placed on the foundation. When the four translational motors start pulling the

cross beam in direction to the foundation, the bulbous bow is pulled through the side structure, simulating a crash situation.

Fig. 10: Arrangement of test facilities

Fig. 11: Full equipped test arrangement

Fig. 12: Clamping

During the tests, all kinds of deformations, stresses, strains and forces were measured, allowing later evaluation of the FEM calculation procedures. To study the influence of the stiffness of side structure and bulbous bow on the crash behavior, a systematic approach was selected: Before testing the “real situation” with elastic bow and double hull, tests with elastic side structure and completely stiff bulbous bow (filled with concrete) and test with completely stiff side structure (80 mm steel plate on concrete) were performed. Thus, the typical parameter of the single components could be determined before combining them to a complex system.

After that, various side structure designs were tested. Starting with a conventional side structure, built from transversal webframes, plates and stiffeners of typical dimensions and spacing, thickness of plates, size of stiffeners and webframe spacing were varied systematically. It turned out that especially the webframe spacing had a major influence to the collision resistance of the side structure. All tests were also calculated by FEM. Figs.13 and 14 show the very good agreement between test and calculation, especially with regard to collision energy consumption.

Fig. 13: Collision force per distance

Fig. 14: Collision energy per distance

4.2 Improving Crash Worthiness of Side Structures

To improve the collision resistance furthermore, new ideas for side structure designs were investigated. A so-called X-core structure, developed by the University of Rostock, gave very promising results. Here, the side structure stiffening is built up from corrugated plate structures, Fig. 15.

Fig. 15: X-core side structure (test specimen scale)

Fig. 16: Kinetic energy consumption of different side structures

The corrugated structures are able to take very large collision energies, as they will buckle and deform heavily before cracking. Drawbacks of this structure are the complicated maintainability of the high number of closed and narrow cells. Fig.16 shows the calculated collision resistance over time for a number of different structures. The X-core side structure is able to consume 70% more energy than the conventional, “non crash worthy” side structure.

Thus, building up the side structure in a crash worthy way gives a high potential for geometrical improvement of the lower hold on RoPax ferries. Within the German national funded project ELKOS a methodology to include the results of crash calculations in the damage stability calculations is being developed. The idea is to adapt the probability distribution used for the damage stability calculation as described above with the results created from FEM crash calculations.

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Maritime Unmanned Navigation through Intelligence in Networks: The MUNIN project

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Abstract

This paper introduces the MUNIN project attempting to put a 200 m bulk carrier under autonomous control. The paper gives an overview of the project and presents some of the key research questions dealing with the human intervention possibilities. As a fallback option the unmanned ship is monitored by a shore control center which has the ability to take direct control if necessary. A challenge for the unmanned ship is the interaction with other manned ships.

1. Introduction

This paper will give a short overview of a recently started EU 7th Framework program named MUNIN (Maritime Unmanned Navigation through Intelligence in Networks) with a special focus on human interaction possibilities. The project started in September 2012 and will conclude in August 2015 with demonstrating the feasibility of the concept in setting a simulated 200 meter long dry cargo vessel under autonomous control, monitored by a shore control center.

As technology evolves more things, that previously were complex and needed human supervision, become trivial and automatized. No one misses the elevator conductors that in the beginning of the twentieth century harnessed the electrical power and made a small wooden case elevate vertically up inside buildings. Today, after a week in Copenhagen, riding the unmanned Metro becomes yesterday's news. It is actually just a more complex elevator? Is it safe? These are questions you ask yourself sitting up front in the first car, where the driver used to be.

1.1. Why would anyone want to build an unmanned ship?

Within the military domain development and use of unmanned autonomous or remote controlled vehicles has been going on for many years. The reason is of course to minimize risks for own personal in e.g. mine sweeping or reconnaissance operations. And we are all aware of current use of unmanned air vehicles. In the civilian domain, unmanned and remote controlled underwater vehicles, for instance, has been used for many years in risky operations on great depths. Also unmanned ships have and are being investigated. For a presentation of previous projects see e.g. *Bertram (2008)*, *Caccia (2006)*, *Caccia et al. (2008)*, *Manley (2008)*. Recently the ACCeSS project, *Tam et al. (2011)*, started working on an Autonomous Surface Vessel (ASV) platform.

There can be many reasons for this interest, also in the civilian domain:

- **Cost reduction**
The quest for cost reduction in transportation systems could be one driving factor. With no crew onboard the running coast for the ship could possibly be reduced. Even considering that some kind of monitoring crews will be needed in remote centers the cost might be reduced, but only if technology can provide a sufficiently safe system.
- **Safety**
Strive for increased safety could strangely enough be another driver when it comes to motivation for building automatic ships. This is due to the fact that many studies report a

huge majority of accidents in transportation systems are caused by “human error”. (65-96 %; e.g. *Sanquist, 1992; Blanding, 1987; Rothblum, n.d.*) Removing the human from the direct control of the ship could prevent some kinds of accidents. "The big benefit of having a driverless system is the safety - the element of human error is taken out completely," said Copenhagen unmanned Metro chief executive Piero Marotta already in 2009. (*Fischer, 2011*). On the other hand we know little about mixing manned and unmanned systems, as unmanned ships will still be interacting with manned ships. Even if we defer the unmanned ships to restricted corridors, they will eventually cross ordinary shipping routes, if nowhere else, when they approach port. In cases of remote control we still have a human element in control, although remotely. And in the remote control we have the same situation as with a manned bridge or engine control room, only worse: because the limitations of sensor capability and bandwidth will reduce the amount of information available on the remote bridge. So the validity of this argument is yet unclear, but will be answered within MUNIN.

- Sustainability in transportation

Pressure to reduce atmospheric emissions due to climate impact is a recent, highly relevant factor as fuel consumption per travelled mile is greatly reduced by lower speed (so-called slow steaming). Recently the term “ultra slow steaming” has been used for voyages in the very low speeds taking advantage of favorable currents and winds, building on the knowledge of the old windjammers, e.g. www.ultraslowships.com. In the 1930s the ship owner Gustav Eriksson cheaply acquired most of the remaining large steel sailing ships he could find. These ships were at that time considered too old and uneconomical to use for trading. They needed large crews and were dependant of weather and wind and therefore slow and costly, as salary had to be paid whether the wind was blowing or not. However, Eriksson had an idea. He manned the ships with a majority of paying apprentices (as in those days deck officers had to practice on a sailing ship in order to acquire their master certificates). He then sailed the ships from Europe to Australia in ballast (~5 months) during the northern hemisphere autumn. He arrived just in time for the harvest of the grain crops and then sailed back another ~5 months and arrived in Europe just in time for last summer’s grain to be finished and the prizes was up, *Newby (1956)*. This way he could make benefit from the long trips, using the ships as storage houses while waiting for the prizes to rise. However if this concept were to be copied by today’s shipping companies the salary cost as well as the social impact of really long sea voyages would be a problem where autonomous vessels could provide a solution.

2. The MUNIN project

The objective of the MUNIN project is to demonstrate the feasibility of putting a Handymax bulker (~200 m) under autonomous command and sail it through a number of different scenarios in a simulator environment, Fig.1. The project includes autonomous navigation, autonomous engine control, shore based remote control with necessary communication links, small object detection capabilities which also would allow the unmanned ship to participate in search and rescue operations. The project will also investigate the legal implications of autonomous shipping.

Fig. 1: A Handymax bulker of the type shown will be used in the project. The modern standard ship will be equipped with an unmanned bridge and an unmanned engine room

The Fraunhofer Centre for Maritime Logistics and Services (CML) in Hamburg coordinates the project in cooperation with MARINTEK in Trondheim. Academic partners are Chalmers University in Gothenburg (human interaction through the shore control center), University of Applied Science Wismar (simulation platform), and University College Cork (legal implications). Industrial partners are Aptomar (stabilized camera platform), Marorka and MarineSoft Entwicklungs- und Logistikgesellschaft (both on engine control systems and simulations).

Fig. 2: Illustration of the MUNIN project

Fig. 3: MUNIN validation system, consisting of three simulators (bridge, engine and VTS), where the VTS is enhanced to include also functions to handle unmanned ships. The onboard sensor suite will be enhanced (partly shaded) as needed and special onboard and shore control systems will be developed. The system will make use of standard voice communication (VC) as well as of AIS and satellite communication to communicate between shore, ship and other parties.

The project is summarized in Fig.2. To the left we see the unmanned ship under autonomous control. Voyage plans, weather routing and other track parameters are stored and kept updated in the ship's computer system. The system is constantly monitoring its surroundings using radar, AIS and infrared sensors. In that sense an unmanned ship might be more vigilant than a manned ship affected by fatigue and the shortcomings of a human lookout. The ship avoids collisions according to the International Regulations for Avoiding Collisions at Sea (COLREGS). Automatic systems are also constantly monitoring the wellbeing of the onboard engine systems. All parameters are communicated in real-time to a Shore Control Center (SCC) which monitors the unmanned and autonomous ship. This is the entity that is in "constant control" of the ship as defined in the SOLAS convention. The communication between the ship and the SCC is done by "available means," meaning that close to shore high bandwidth systems like e.g. 3/4G GSM and WIMAX can be used, were as further out in the oceans satellite links will have to be used. At any point in time the SCC has the ability to take direct control of the ship using a remote bridge. Depending on the bandwidth of the communication links, the data input to the remote bridge will vary in quality, but should always hold a minimum standard. As the ship approaches the port, a pilot and a port crew will climb onto the ship at sea, just as pilots do today, and guide the ship into confined waters of archipelagos or ports. In these areas the ship might also be controlled on short range by pilots, tug boats, or mooring masters using a hand held remote control unit.

The MUNIN project intends to simulate the final demonstration as project budgets as well as the legal situation prevents us from doing it with a real ship. In this demonstration the ship will be simulated by the FH Wismar's simulator center in Warnemünde (Germany) and with the SCC at Chalmers University in Gothenburg (Sweden), Fig.3.

2.1. Autonomous and unmanned ships

An autonomous ship is navigating and making evasive maneuvers based on an automated software system. The system and the ship are under constant monitoring by a Shore Control Center (SCC). An autonomous ship does not have to be unmanned but can contain maintenance or service crews, while the bridge and/or the engine control room is unmanned.

An unmanned ship is a ship with no humans onboard. An unmanned ship does not have to be autonomous; it can be under autonomous control but it can also be under remote control from a SCC, or from other places (e.g. a pilot or tug boat, or a mooring supervisor).

3. Technical challenges

The technical challenges for autonomous and unmanned ships are great. Although automatic systems are used everywhere today, critical systems normally have instant access to maintenance and repair. In cases, like aviation, where functionality of e.g. engines have to be guaranteed, the running intervals are relatively short, maximum 10-20 h. A huge challenge for unmanned ships is to keep systems running for days and weeks without access to maintenance or repair, although one might see a business opportunity for off-shore repair vessels stationed at sea if unmanned ships were to become frequent. But even so opportunities for problems are abundant. Let us just look at one example.

In December 2011 the Norwegian Color line ferry "Superspeed" with 450 persons onboard on her way from Hirtshals in Denmark to Kristiansand in Norway ran into an unusually high wave which crushed one of the windscreens on her bridge wing and soaked the steering control panel which resulted in that the safety system shut down the main engine, *Olsbu (2011)*. After 40 minutes, the engine crew managed to start the engine with limited effect and the ship could continue its voyage with reduced speed and escorted by a tug boat. Luckily the engine room was manned and the engineers manage to disconnect the automatic safety systems and get the engine running again, Fig.4.

Superspeed fikk motorstopp

Fig. 4: Newspaper clipping from Kristiansand paper Faedelandvennen, 3.12.2011. Headline reads: “Superspeed got engine stop”

For an unmanned ship such a situation would have posed a serious challenge. Not in the sense that there would be any difficulty in designing a technical system that could cope with an extreme wave crushing windows at the bridge, but in designing a technical system that can cope with all possible unexpected events. And let us say it right up front: It will not be possible. We have to calculate with events that will bring systems down. The issue is instead how do we design a fail-to-safe system that allows a graceful degradation into a safe mode that gives a reasonable assurance against a catastrophic outcome for people and environment?

4. Human intervention possibilities

One of the great challenges for an unmanned system is interaction with other manned systems. An unmanned ship must respond to other manned ships in the vicinity. If the unmanned ship is called over VHF radio the shore control center will have to be there and answer the call. The unmanned ship must also be able to communicate its intentions using technical means, e.g. the Automatic Identification System (AIS). The International Maritime Organization is in its “e-navigation” concept, *IMO (2013)*, working on new ways of collecting, integrating, exchanging, analyzing and presenting data onboard and ashore. One of these new proposals is called “intended routes”, which would allow ships to show their intended routes for a period of time ahead of their present position. Such a service should be of great value for manned ships interacting with unmanned ships. Of course this does not mean that unmanned ships should not follow the rules of the road which will be programmed into their autonomous system, however the displayed intentions would serve as a confirmation of its intentions, and could for instance include the unmanned ship’s interpretation of the present visibility (restricted, or good – following which, two different kinds of rules of the road apply).

When something fails onboard the unmanned ship automatic failure analysis will be done and the SCC is notified. If no automatic repair, redundant system or workaround is found, the ship will send a request for help to SCC. Dependant on the quality of the current communication link the SCC will have access to most of the systems onboard. Should the SCC fail in solving any critical systems, or should the link to the SCC be unavailable the ship will start to go into so called “fail-to-safe mode”. Safe mode is a software system term meaning that the system will shut down advanced parts, only using simple robust parts that hopefully work. The ultimate safe mode for the unmanned ship is shutting down its engines, closing watertight doors and hanging out all 12 shackles of anchor chain and start to drift, waiting to be picked up by a tug boat or hocking on to a continental shelf.

We can never achieve a system that is 100 % failure proof. The question should instead be: can we design a system that is safer than the manned systems we have today?

Important to design the overall system is to facilitate to keep the human operator in the loop. Otherwise it will be difficult for the operator at the SCC to grasp the situation if he or she is suddenly thrown into a situation that needs immediate action. For instance, if a sensor detects a problem on board the unmanned ship, and the on board intelligence solves the situation in some way; it is of crucial importance that the system also informs the SCC about its actions and the new status. Low degree of activation and human-out-of-the loop-syndrome is a huge problem in automatic systems (e.g. Williams (2006); Endsley and Jones (2012), Wickens et al. (2013), especially since it is probable that the SCC will serve several unmanned ships. It might be necessary to make new routines where the personnel of the SCC spend time manually driving the unmanned ships in periods according to a rolling schedule to make sure that system knowledge is kept up.

5. Security issues

We need to mention the issue of willfully malicious attack on the unmanned ship. Most commonly these days are pirate attacks. They seem to be of two types: e.g. along the coast of the Horn of Africa pirates attack and capture ships to take the crew hostage, and the use the hostage to press money out of, ship owners, families or nations. In western Africa (Nigerian Bay) pirates seem to be more interested in capturing the ship and sell the cargo, ICC (2013) Pirates are a problem that has to be taken seriously when designing unmanned ships. Different physical protections can make it hard for pirates to enter, and once entered, gaining access to the interior of the ship. But because no humans are onboard the risk of taking hostage is gone. As long as communication link is open SCC can exercise some control and maybe order “emergency stop” shutting down all systems and dropping anchor and in a very worst case the SCC could sink the ship by remote control. But it is hard to prevent pirates using tug boats to take control of the ship, once the propeller has been stopped by ropes or chains.

One might also spend a minute or two figuring over the scenario narrated in another entertainment motion picture, where a terrorist hack his way into the central computer system of a large cruise liner and took complete control over it. If the SCC can remotely control the ship, so could any other hacker that has cracked, or obtained the codes and protections of the remote links. System security needs to be high on the design list of any unmanned ship designer.

Acknowledgement

MUNIN is funded by the EU’s 7th Framework Program under the Grant Agreement Number 314286.

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A Comprehensive Performance Management Solution

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Abstract

As of today vessels have and will in future have even more possibilities to affect the ship's overall energy balance. These possibilities are enabled for example with diesel electric configurations, waste heat recovery units, trim variations, operational profiles, alternative fuels and hull cleaning schedules. Unfortunately all this flexibility comes with certain problems as the system complexity grows beyond human understanding. Finding and especially operating constantly at the optimum point is significantly more challenging with all these variables. Even if one or two specific areas can be efficiently optimized by for example a dedicated chief engineer, the full potential of comprehensive optimization is often left unused. This paper takes an insight into a holistic performance management and optimization solution developed by ABB for any type of vessel. It not only takes in account energy efficiency but also the availability and safety of the vessel and fleet. ABB's long experience working and providing for land based industry, such as power plants, pulp factories and paper mills, has produced expertise and a comprehensive optimization and monitoring framework for overall energy efficiency of basically any process. ABB's Advisory Systems is the marine application of this already proven technology. The presented solution gives clear decision support both to the users onboard and also for the management ashore.

1. Introduction

To improve your operations you need to change the current way of working to more optimum. To be able to change the correct areas in your operations you need to fully understand your current performance. To understand the operations in a whole you need to know and measure the key elements from each and every vessel in the fleet. This type of behaviour forms an iterative benchmarking process which is often referred to as the “denim cycle”: Plan – Do – Check – Act, *Ignatius (2008)*. The performance management solution studied in this paper consists of several products which are intended from the beginning to follow this benchmarking scheme.

Fig. 1: Benchmarking process with ABB's Advisory Systems

As a whole, this product portfolio is called ABB’s Advisory Systems, Fig.1. It consists of onboard modules for energy monitoring, optimization, decision support and office tools for fleet wide data analysis. All the modules are divided to two product lines based on their functionality; EMMA for energy and OCTOPUS for motions, Fig.2.

Fig. 2: Two product lines of ABB’s Advisory Systems

EMMA is a complete energy monitoring and optimization tool and aims to look the vessel as a whole instead of providing separate decision support tools for different problem areas. Several modules are offered for various monitoring or optimization tasks and the correct ones are selected together with the customer for the vessel in question. OCTOPUS is a comprehensive vessel response monitoring and forecasting tool providing decision support tools for example to heavy weather conditions. Basically any vessel motion or seakeeping parameter can be accurately predicted using a combination of ship model, statistical information collected from the vessel and the weather forecast.

2. Relationship to SEEMP

MEPC (Marine Environment Protection Committee) describes SEEMP (Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan) as a four step cycle of planning – implementation – monitoring – self-evaluation and Improvement, *MEPC (2009)*. In combination with the presented energy manager and possibly with the help of Energy Coaching services the shipping company can implement a full SEEMP which has been mandatory since of 1st of January 2013, *MEPC (2011)*.

Fig. 3: SEEMP process

This paper will follow the procedure described in the SEEMP guidelines describing how the energy manager application and ABB's Energy Coaching services can help you fulfil this mandatory requirement, taking full advantage of the available measures starting from the beginning of SEEMP.

3. Planning

First of all, the SEEMP required the ship and company specific measurements to be decided, *MEPC (2009)*. EMMA has a good set of proposed Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) including EEOI (Energy Efficiency Operational Indicator, MEPC 2009/2) and with the expertise of ABB's Energy Coaches even more can be selected to fit the operations in question.

Naturally the measures taken towards better energy efficiency need to be addressed as well. Depending a bit on the vessel type, for example the following measures can be selected to the implementation as a turn-key delivery. SEEMP suggests several measures thriving towards best practices for example to problems such:

- Optimum trim
- Hull & propeller condition maintenance
- Energy management
- Waste heat recovery
- Propulsion system
- Speed management/planning

There are several measures in addition to the proposed ones. One of the most obvious is hardware retrofitting for higher efficiency. Such is the deployment of Variable Frequency Drives (VFDs) can be used to get direct savings and very fast return-of-investment.

The next step is a voluntary goal setting for the selected measures. MEPC states that the goal may take any form, fitting well with the various KPIs that ABB's solution presents. Depending on the operational profile a suitable target setting is done either qualitatively or quantitatively.

All the findings from the planning are documented to a ship specific SEEMP paper which the shipping company can include in the SMS (Safety Management System) and have onboard the vessel as the regulation states, (MEPC 2009).

3.1 Optimum Trim & Speed

EMMA is based on the principle of easy optimization for even the most complex onboard processes. This principle requires smart algorithms and state-of-the-art user experience design. Combined Trim and Speed optimization is a very good example of such as we see from Fig.4 which visualized the dynamic trim decision support. Basically showing the current dynamic trim, the optimum and maybe some savings potential with some trend is enough. The operator can see from ten feet distance what the overall status is.

The algorithm used is basing on a statistical model of real, full scale, measurements instead of CFD or towing tank tests. This type of approach will find the optimum trim and speed for any given operating condition. The model uses data collected from several sources onboard, such as IAS (Integrated Automation System), navigation system, weather forecast and ABB attitude sensors that measure the ship movements in roll and pitch direction. Typically after installing the system onboard the measurements are recorded for 1-2 month time to ensure that the parameters of the optimization model gain enough statistical significance. If the draft, speed and trim don't vary enough during the measurement period, additional trim sweep tests can be performed with the help of ABB's Energy Coach.

Fig. 4: Example of EMMA dynamic trim optimization screen

The optimization model is based on state-of-the-art machine learning methods, and real-time sensor fusion algorithms, *Nelles (2000)*, *Ljung (1999)*, *Bishop (2006)*. The model can be included with prior information about the vessel's propeller's properties, and the known relationships between certain key variables that affect the vessel's resistance and propulsion power loss. The simplest example of inclusion prior information to the model is the widely used speed-power relationship. It is known that the vessel's propulsion power in ideal operating conditions is approximately proportional to the third power of the vessel's speed through water. Thus, one can include this known relationship in the model in order to reduce the number of free parameters that need to be learnt from the data. Once enough data are gathered, the optimization model learns the dependencies between the measured variables by using a self-learning algorithm developed by ABB.

Speed (or RPM) advice is given to execute the planned voyage with the most optimum speed. Traditionally masters tend to build up buffer time by executing the first half of the voyage very fast, and when they start to see that they reach the required ETA, they slow down. There are several reasons behind this, but maybe most importantly, the captains are missing a trustworthy decision support tool providing them with information of accurate ETA, since the relation between speed and RPM is not constant. EMMA can calculate the vessel's real speed very accurately using the combination of ship model, statistical data and weather forecast. This way the end user can be provided with an even speed profile recommendation from day one of the voyage.

Customer studies show that the combined savings potential of trim and speed optimization is up to seven percent of the propulsion power. About half of this potential comes from the dynamic trim and half from the minimized energy losses of fluctuating speed.

3.2 Hull & propeller condition maintenance

While the optimization model is built for power plant, trim and speed optimization, there are a number of other purposes the model can readily be used. This is because the model gives very accurate prediction of the propulsion power taking into account the operating conditions, such as wind, sea state, speed, currents, etc. Therefore, the model gives a benchmark for the propulsion system performance and the hull condition. Interesting side product of the normalized measurement is the hull maintenance planning aid.

The typical problem in interpreting full scale speed-power measurements is clearly visible in Fig.5. The transparent surface indicates the raw measurements for an approximately two week long measurement period, as received from the automation and navigation systems. This raw measurement

set has approximately 112000 measurements. The coloured surface represent the measurement set once the obviously erroneous and low speed values are removed and the data is normalized for weather and floating positions effects using the EMMA method. When fitting to a curve the raw measurements have 0.706 as the coefficient of determination. The filtered and normalized values have 0.992 which is a remarkable improvement.

Fig. 5: Speed-Power curve as raw measurements and filtered & normalized (except trim)

Calculating these normalized figures over time shows the hydrodynamic performance of the vessel. The effect of hull & propeller condition is evident from these figures and the shipping company can use this data in correctly timing the hull cleanings or even dry dockings.

3.3 Energy Management & Waste Heat Recovery

Bit similar to the Trim optimization the Power Plant optimization uses a physical model (including for example Specific Fuel Oil Consumption curves) adjusted with statistical data of the real life measurements. This combination gives a definite advantage to a plain power plant physical modelling since any energy producer will not be the same for its life cycle.

Fig. 6: Example of EMMA power plant optimization user interface

Decision Support for the user is given in a simple way, observing the power plant as a whole. This is very important especially with more complex configurations. The example in Fig.6 is from a large container vessel with two main engines, two shaft generator/motors, four auxiliary engines and a large 20 MW Waste Heat Recovery (WHR) unit.

Optimizing such power plant requires extensive knowledge and the number of possible combinations grow beyond possible real-time human interpretation. EMMA user interface (UI) clearly indicates the overall status as seen in Fig.6. Each energy producer is listed and the UI indicates with colour codes the running status, current and optimum load and the advice for the user. The power plant optimizer is implemented onto the ABB Energy Manager (ABB, 2010) platform that is designed for process industry and smart-grid type of applications. The technology has proven to be very efficient in process optimization in numerous applications.

The optimizer allows the user to determine can change the required spinning reserve, as well as the operation limits for each power producer. Moreover, the user can exclude some power produces from the optimization model in real-time. The model is also able to take into account the maintenance cycles of the power producers. The optimization model can easily be equipped with possibly available forecast of the becoming power demand, which allows the system to use the MPC (Model Predictive Control) philosophy, *Camacho and Bordón (2004)*. MPC is based on the idea that the optimization algorithm uses the existing model of the system, and the forecasts of the future inputs to simulate forward the consequences of the actions taken now. In a nonlinear dynamical system with constrained outputs and controls this typically improves the optimization results significantly. For example, if the power demand is forecasted to grow only for, say, fifteen minutes, and the currently running diesel generators can easily fulfill the demand, it is not profitable to start another diesel engine, even though the steady-state consumption by starting that engine and stopping the current one would be smaller. In Fig.7 only main engine 1 is running, with the current load of 18 MW and the advice is to load the engine with 2 additional MWs.

Fig. 7: Example of EMMA power plant optimization – user interface detail

3.4 Propulsion System

For vessels equipped with two or more Azipod® propulsion units, ABB offers the azipod dynamic optimization (ADO) tool for the towing angle of the Azipods. This is also a problem of dynamic nature, and requires constant measurements of the real conditions. The system doesn't require any user interference and is totally automatic, providing constantly the most optimum thrust for the vessel.

3.5 Hardware Retrofitting

Until recently, energy efficiency in auxiliary systems was not taken into account during the design process or construction of marine vessels. Therefore, systems on existing ships are not energy efficient and have not been fully optimized for minimizing overall fuel consumption. The onboard ship systems most suitable for improving energy efficiency are systems with large pumps and fans, which are not required to run continuously and at full capacity. When applicable, electric motors could be fitted with Variable Frequency Drives (VFD) to operate pumps and fans more efficiently in partial loads during slower sailing speeds or with reduced ventilation requirements. The electric power consumption of a pump is related to the pump volumetric flow according to affinity laws. As an example, a reduction of the pump speed with 10% will save 27% of the consumed power.

Pumps and Fans onboard vessels are often a vital application. If these are not working the vessel is not sailing. A common fact for pump applications is that they are very often over-dimensioned to the need. This is simply because the design criterion is set to meet the extreme conditions the vessel may operate in, as an example the sea water temperature for dimensioning is generally set above normal operating conditions. Although it is required for a ship to be able to operate in extreme cases and environments, every-day operations rarely come close to such conditions.

By far the most commonly used flow control in pump applications is throttle control and by-pass loops to control the temperature. As a consequence pumps are running at 100% loads continuously, even though the requirement would be actually about 40% in average. In vessels built between years 1988 to 2008 and still sailing, approximate 2% of the main sea water cooling systems have VFD control. By modifying these systems, which is a fairly simply thing to do, there is a substantial amount of reduced emissions and costs to achieve. Relatively small changes can have a major impact on consumption and thus emissions.

3.6. Motion monitoring and forecasting

In heavy weather conditions, the OCTOPUS tool provides extremely valuable decision support advice for the operating crew. Whilst the complete advisory system is optimizing energy consumption, OCTOPUS is calculating and warning about any sea keeping attribute, such as rolling, slamming probability or parametric roll. OCTOPUS offers a simple user interface, Fig.7, advising the users on safe speeds, headings and operating windows. Originally developed as a tool for safe and economic navigation onboard container vessels, the product has since evolved to a complete vessel motion monitoring and forecasting system offering tools for example to advice on DP capability, helideck or crane operational windows, offshore loading/discharging scenarios, speed losses due to weather, etc.

3.7 Sloshing prevention

The sloshing advisory function is an advanced extension within OCTOPUS. It provides warning for risk of sloshing in LNG-tanks; the crew is exactly informed how to stay within the set limits and avoid risk for sloshing and possible consequential damage. ABB works together with GTT in sloshing prevention. GTT specializes in designing and licensing the construction of cryogenic LNG storage tanks for the shipbuilding industry. The risk for sloshing is calculated by combining the motion measurements or forecasts from OCTOPUS with GTT's model tests results for determination of sloshing criteria. The master of the vessel has a clear display on the bridge how to operate the vessel in a way that the risk for sloshing is minimized.

3.8 DP Capability Forecasting

For vessels equipped with a Dynamic Positioning system, OCTOPUS has a DP Capability function available. The DP Capability functionality gives offshore vessels the possibility to make optimum use of a safe time window for their weather-sensitive operations. A forecast is given if the vessel is capable of maintaining her position and heading in changing environmental and weather conditions, hours and days ahead. This leads to maximized workability and more productive hours during operations where the DP system is used. The calculations are based on the thruster properties, in combination with measured environmental conditions and on weather forecasts, which are an integrated part of OCTOPUS.

4. Implementation

MEPC guidelines state that the selected measures for energy management have to be implemented, by defining tasks and assigning them to qualified personnel (MEPC 2009). As mentioned, ABB can implement a project as a complete turn-key delivery, thus minimizing the shipping company's risk and involvement in the possible installations and modifications. Naturally tasks to use and follow the measures are assigned to the personnel operating vessel.

Depending on the selected measures, installation of some sensors might be required. For example dynamic trim optimization requires attitude sensors and propeller shaft torque measurement. Power plant optimization requires power measurements and as accurate fuel flow meters as possible. If such do not exist, and are required, ABB can package all required hardware in the same turn-key project. Some examples of typical sensors required in SEEMP are described in the following chapters.

4.1 Torductor – Shaft torque meter

Torductor is a proven product for shaft torque measurement for any size of a propeller shaft. With already more than 100 marine applications, and much more on shore industry, it has shown remarkable accuracy and service/calibration free life cycle. The technology used bases on measurements of the magnetic characteristics of the shaft, which changes in a uniform way when the shaft is under torque. Being contactless improves error-free operation and the technology does not set any criteria on the mist in the measurement area as the laser based technologies do. Installation of Torductor can be done without dry dock.

4.2 CoriolisMaster – Mass flow meter

ABB portfolio includes a mass flow meter operating on the Coriolis principle. It can measure very accurately mass flow, volume flow, density, temperature and concentration without moving parts guaranteeing no wear and no maintenance.

4.3 Attitude sensors

For accurate dynamic trim measurements ABB uses military grade attitude sensors. Depending on the size of the vessel, two to three sensors are installed to measure the attitude. In addition to static trim and list, the sensors provide information about the dynamic behavior of the vessel, such as roll, heel and pitch, hull deformations, etc.

4.4 Draft radars

The typically used draft sensors onboard the vessel provide accurate readings while in port and more or less in a static floating position. Whilst on way, these pressure based sensors don't work that accurately. This is especially important for vessels of which operation profile shows a lot of variation in displacement. For this reason a trim optimization solution is typically equipped with microwave draft radars. These radars are installed on the bridge wings, measuring down towards the water surface. Combining this with the attitude sensor information an extremely accurate information of floating position is obtained, for static and dynamic condition.

5. Monitoring

SEEMP guidelines state that the onboard monitoring should quantitative, be assisted by shore personnel, it should be consistent and continuous and it should involve the crew as little as possible, *MEPC (2009)*. ABB's Advisory Systems handles the monitoring automatically on two levels; onboard the vessel with automatic monitoring tools and for the office personnel with a cloud based fleet management tool. Please see details of these two distinct systems in the following chapters.

5.1 Onboard monitoring tool

EMMA includes a fully automatic tool for onboard Key Performance Indicator (KPI) calculation, display and recording purposes. The user interface is heavily implemented on the "ten-feet-screen" ideology, which simply means that the overall status is visible from a distance without having to go to the details. Fig.8 shows an example of the main dashboard.

Fig. 8: Example of EMMA Onboard Tracker main dashboard

The UI in this example is divided in four segments presenting different type of KPIs:

- Upper left: Cost of operation
- Upper right: Energy production/consumption
- Lower left: Navigational aspect, in this case consumption per nautical mile
- Lower right: Overall optimization status

The large dials are visible from a long distance. If all the segments are lit up, the vessel is performing well in the specific area with the current surrounding environmental conditions. The more segments are missing the more improvement should be possible.

These KPIs are not compared against fixed targets. All the calculations and limits are dynamic, basing on the statistical model, giving realistic targets for the operating crew. Thus for example a vessel operating in heavy weather will not have all dials empty, if they operate well in that condition. The essential idea is that each variable shown as a trend or a number is always given a reference that takes into account the operating conditions affecting the variable. In performance evaluation systems the fundamental issue is to provide the user with information of the current state of the system, we well as a reference which evaluates the performance with respect to the operating conditions. It is very typical in marine applications that the performance of some equipment varies significantly more with respect to the operating conditions than with respect to the poor operation. For example, on deep sea the greatest variation in the vessel's propulsion power comes from the vessel's speed as well as wind, weather and waves. These operating conditions need to be taken into account when evaluating the performance. This issue is solved by employing the ABB self-learning model to provide adaptive dynamic targets for each power producer. The model can learn the dependencies between a consumer and the operating conditions automatically during the operation without any human effort. Once the model can predict the consumer behaviour to the extent that is considered necessary, the model starts to provide the adaptive dynamic KPI value for the consumer. By normalizing the effect of operating conditions from the consumer measurements the performance degradation due to equipment wear or poor operation can be spotted easily.

5.2 Fleet Management tool

All the data collected and calculated onboard is automatically transferred to EMMA Fleet Control, which is a modern business intelligence data discovery tool. EMMA Fleet Control is build to a high cyber security Azure Cloud service by Microsoft. This enables secure data access at any locations for the ship owner. This centralized database of EMMA is used to form baseline & ranking of the fleet performance. This benchmarking data is replicated back to the vessels so that the fleet wide performance is visible for the onboard users without a broadband connection. See Fig.9 for data transfer principles.

Fig. 9: EMMA data transfer principles

All collected and calculated figures are available for access in graphical and numerical way. One key driver of EMMA Fleet Control is predefined views for certain data. If the user, for example, wants to view speed profiles, the graph type is automatically a line graph. Weekly fuel oil consumption is visualized with bar charts, fleets position on an interactive map (Fig. 10) and speed-power curve as a scatter chart with curve fitting. The user may toggle the numerical figures on/off and also choose to export the report to PDF-document or Excel Spreadsheet.

Fig. 9: Example of EMMA Fleet Control view

6. Self-evaluation and Improvement

As in any benchmarking process, the MEPC describes the last step of SEEMP as the step which “should produce meaningful feedback for the coming first stage, i.e. planning stage, of the next improvement cycle.” All the measures documented in the SEEMP together with ABB are documented and quantitatively recorded using the onboard and office tools. It actually is even advisable that all the possible measures are not included in the first implementation of SEEMP. Having the EMMA system implemented for couple of months provides excellent information of the vessels current status and additional measures can be chosen more wisely with this baseline.

Also understanding the way EMMA operates reveals an interesting fact: With the adaptive model even more improvement can be achieved to the already selected energy management measure such as power plant optimization. In such case only the new goals are set for the next iterative cycle.

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Efficient Use of 3D Tools at Early Design Stages

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Abstract

The design, production and operation of ships need to be understood as an overall business from the beginning, when the major decisions are made. Many of these decisions are based on estimates or data from previous projects. The more accurate these estimates are, the better results are obtained. If 3D ship model can be created cost efficiently at early design stages, simple but accurate enough, benefits will be collected downstream. However, there are two important drawbacks that need to be overcome. The first one is the fact that the design team devoted to initial and basic design do not usually prefer 3D CAD tools and choose to use 2D drawings. The second one is that this stage is very agile and fast, introducing many changes and modifications. This paper describes how it is possible to use a 3D CAD tool at early design stages, in order to improve the overall design process. SENER has provided FORAN, a shipbuilding CAD/CAM system, with the necessary capabilities to ensure its efficient use at early design stages. Some remarkable capabilities are based on the total integration between all ship design stages and disciplines, the use of topology and tools to facilitate seamless transition to the detail design stage. Benefits are an easy evaluation of design alternatives, management of modifications, full control of the integrity of the information and quality, all in a collaborative design environment.

1. Introduction

Concept and basic design of ships are widely based in 2D tools. Only in long-term naval projects the use of a 3D approach is common at this stage, because it is critical to avoid errors that will be very costly at further stages. The challenge is the propagation of the 3D approach at early design stages to any vessel, taking in consideration the advantages that can be reached at the end of the design process. This paper shows the advantages of this approach, and describes the design process from concept design through basic and detail design in 3D, based on the application of FORAN, a shipbuilding-oriented CAD (Computer Aided Design) tool developed by SENER.

Fig. 1: Computer generated image of a vessel being developed in FORAN

2. Challenges of Early 3D Design

The debate about the advantages of using an early 3D model in shipbuilding started many years ago. In the beginning, it was rather philosophical, because the tools in the market were not good enough to ensure a successful 3D model approach at early design stages. That is why most ship designers still work in 2D at this stage. Only by adding important and innovative new capabilities was it possible to allow easy generation of 3D models.

With all stakeholders still debating advantages and disadvantages of 2D or 3D approaches, what is clear is that paper documents tend to disappear. We can see it in many industries, in many fields, which makes us think that we are on the right track.

Concept and basic design stages are very constrained in time. If a design team had all the time it could build a 3D model with any tool. But time is short, and the demand for information quality increases. The 3D approach ensures quality avoiding errors and inconsistencies inherent to the 2D approach. Regarding time, 3D tools need to be designed for simplicity and automation. Reducing the number of clicks, modules and commands is crucial. Then, generating an early 3D model accurate but quick enough to be competitive with the 2D approach is possible. Later on, the re-use of information with a seamless transition to the detail design pays off. Better weight estimation and the exact positioning of main equipment are other important advantages.

3. FORAN Philosophy

Key aspects of FORAN enabling this approach are described in this chapter:

- **Database:** FORAN is built on a relational database which ensures data consistency during the whole design process
- **Topology:** Introducing quick changes that can be propagated through the model with a single click is possible thanks to the topological approach of FORAN. This is specifically relevant in early design, when important changes are introduced into the project and important decisions need to be made having as much reliable information as possible
- **Integration:** All disciplines in FORAN are totally integrated in a single environment. The early 3D model of the structure is generated with the same tool that for detail design. The re-use of information is crucial, substantially reducing the effort in detail design.

The proposed solution is based on a 3D ship product model, e.g. Fig.2, in which the geometry and the attributes of the elements of the ship are stored. The model is built as an essential part of the engineering work, can be visualized at all stages and can be exploited to obtain information for material procurement and for production. The main characteristics of the ship product model are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Building an early 3D model in FORAN allows improving the design process of the ship and studying different design alternatives in shorter times, which reduces both delivery schedule and cost.

The use of a topological model instead of a geometrical model facilitates the model definition, allows the quick study of different design alternatives and simplifies modifications. The main advantage of the topological definition, where geometrical data are not stored but calculated on-line, is that changes in the main hull surfaces are automatically incorporated in the modified elements, just by reprocessing them. The topological definition allows powerful copy commands making the definition far more efficient than working only with geometry. Another benefit of the topological model is the size of information stored in the database, which is much less than for geometrical models.

Fig. 2: The interior of the ship is made visible by use of a clip plane in FORAN FVIEWER

The key aspect of the design process is the definition of a single ship 3D model, accessible for several designers working concurrently and used in all stages of the design. While the project is progressing, the level of detail is increasing and the different parts of the model are subdivided by a progressive top-down definition. The solution delivered by FORAN includes tools that facilitate the direct transition from basic to detail design, by means of simple operations that include block splitting, assignment of parts to blocks and completion of the model with attributes for the manufacturing phase.

4. Basic Design Process

The basic design process in FORAN begins with the form definition, hydrostatic calculations, definition of volumes, characterization of intact and damage stability conditions and other naval architectural concepts. Later on, it is necessary to define the material catalogues describing plates and profiles to be used in the design. Once the hull forms, decks, bulkheads and other surfaces are created, the hull structure module is used to create the major openings in all surfaces, the scantling of the main surfaces for plates and profiles as well as the main structural elements (floors, web frames, girders, stringers, etc.). The definition is usually based in frame and longitudinal systems which allows a full recalculation of the model in case of changes in the spacing between elements.

In early stages, plates and profiles are created as objects representing zones of a surface with common scantling properties. Therefore, the size of the objects is not consistent with production aspects, which are considered in later stages of the design. Other properties like continuity and watertightness attributes of surfaces or parts of them can be defined at any time.

The sequence of the model definition in FORAN is highly flexible, allowing creation of both plates and profiles at any time. However, designers normally follow the same rules as when working in 2D;

they start with the definition of the continuous elements because this will allow the automatic splitting of the non-continuous elements.

The assembly break down to unit or block is optional at this stage, and the level of detail of the 3D model is the one required by classification drawings, with respect to the type of parts included (brackets, face bars, clips, collars, etc.) as well as to other characteristics (profile end cuts, scallops, notches, etc).

Fig. 3: General Arrangement of a ship in FORAN

4.1 Surface definition and Naval Architecture calculations

Ship moulded surfaces models include the external hull shell, decks, bulkheads, appendages and superstructures. In FORAN, the geometrical representation for all the surfaces is a collection of trimmed NURBS patches, Bezier patches, ruled surfaces and implicit surfaces (planes, cylinders, spheres and cones). The surfaces can be imported from files using different generic formats, such as IGES and the AP-216 STEP format.

FORAN has two complementary tools for surface definition. The traditional tool permits the definition of the hull surface, either conventional or special forms (such as non-symmetrical ones, multi-hulls or offshore platforms). This tool includes advanced fitting and fairing options and allows several transformations of hull forms (based on block coefficient, longitudinal position of the centre of buoyancy, etc) and other operations like lengthening or shortening of a ship.

FORAN has incorporated recently an additional tool based in the latest-generation of mechanical design that can be used for improving hull forms.

The intensive use of topology allows the automatic recalculation of all elements when a modification is performed in upper level concepts (hull and decks surfaces or material standards). This type of topological definition saves a lot of time in basic design, where modifications are frequent.

Once the surfaces have been defined, it is possible to analyse the hydrostatic and stability calculations. For these purposes, SENER has developed the new FBASIC module that groups the former modules in a single solution.

Fig.4: Realistic visualization of the general arrangement using FORAN FDESIGN

4.2 Volume definition

The next step in the basic design definition is to define the compartment arrangement. This is based on the definition of spaces. Each space is represented by its 3D model. The new FGA (FORAN General Arrangement) module is dedicated to define and manage the compartment arrangement of a project. A 3D model of the spaces is generated taking as reference the surfaces of the ship as well as auxiliary planes. It is also possible the definition of spaces from 2D drawing in a specific definition environment. Compartment arrangement defined on FGA will be available in FBASIC for hydrostatic and stability calculations.

4.3 Hull Structure Basic Design

4.3.1 Shell and decks definition

The 3D curved surfaces context allows the definition of plates, profiles and holes. Work division is supported by using surface and zone concepts, which allow the multi-user access to any surface. A general zone may be used to contain the entities common to several zones. The following type of profiles can be defined:

- Shell and deck longitudinal
- Frames and deck beams
- General profiles

Profile definition is mainly based on topological references to already existing structural elements, as well as to auxiliary concepts used in the early design stage (longitudinal spacing, frame system, other profiles, etc). The user can assign different attributes such as material, scantling and web and thickness orientation. These basic attributes can be completed by adding constructive attributes (parametric web, flange end cuts, etc) at any time of the design process. The profiles can be split into profile parts later, when the transition from basic to detail design is performed. Profiles crossing other profiles will automatically generate the necessary cut-outs and scallops.

All types of profiles including flat, curved and twisted are represented as solids. Web, flange and the corresponding end cuts are displayed with a user configurable degree of accuracy.

Due to the intensive use of topology, the definition of the shell and deck plating can start in early design, even with a preliminary definition of the hull and decks. The basic concepts are:

- **Butts:** Lines lying on a surface used as aft and fore limits for the plates. Butts can have any shape or be located in transverse planes at any abscissa.
- **Seams:** Lines lying on a surface used as lower and upper limits for plates, with any geometric shape. Seams are usually defined by means of a set of points on the surface and some additional rules to define the layout.
- **Plates:** Zones of the surface defined by aft and fore butts, and lower and upper seams, with attributes such as gross material, thickness and, optionally, bevelling/edge preparation, construction margins and shrinkage factors. Plates can also be the result of breaking down an existing plate in two smaller plates.

Flat and curved plates are represented as solids (including thickness) and the information for plate pre-development is automatically generated allowing an early material take-off list.

4.3.2 Internal structure definition

The internal structure context is based on the same topological and visualization environment as for the curved surfaces, but applied to a section lying on a plane. This environment provides a set of advanced functions for easy definition and modification of plates (flat, flanged and corrugated), straight and curved stiffeners, holes, face bars, standard plates, on and off plane brackets, collars and others.

Fig. 5: 3D model of one naval vessel block created for this paper

It is possible to have several sections in memory making easy operations, like copy or multiple editions of elements in different sections. The work division is made by using section, structural element and zone concepts, which allows multi-user access to any section. As an example, Fig.5 shows a basic design patrol vessel created using the FHULL structure module in FORAN.

The main features are:

- Predefined best-practice support through the use of structural element concept, defining default constructive values and parameters for plates, profiles and face bars
- Automatic part splitting, using the crossing/not crossing structural element attribute
- High productivity tools, like one-click plate definition, reduction to the minimum of the auxiliary geometry and join and split functions for plates and profiles
- XML based topological definition language for the definition of plates, profiles and face bars
- Profile and face bars definition using standard profile cross-sections, parametric cut-outs and parametric web and flange end cuts
- Automatic cut-outs insertion for both plates and profiles
- Standard or free shape holes definition and automatic application to the affected plates
- Split, multi-edit and multi-copy commands for both plates and profiles in the same or in different sections and structural elements

4.4 Main equipment positioning

Once the structure has been defined over the hull forms, it is the time for outfitting and electrical disciplines. The key action is to place all the main equipment, such as main engine, reduction gear and propeller shaft. Other equipment, such as electrical equipment (generators and transformers) and or outfitting equipment (e.g. ballast-water systems) can also be positioned for initial stability calculations.

4.5 Generation of output from the 3D Model

The next paragraphs describe the tangible output derived from an early hull structure 3D model like drawings, reports and models to be used in the analysis and calculation tools.

4.5.1 Classification drawings for approval

Although the approach described in this paper is rather general, any improvement in the process of basic design must consider the fact that the main output during the hull structure basic design stage is the set of classification drawings for approval. These include:

- Shell and deck drawings (different views, including expansion)
- Typical planar sections
- Other detail drawings

The drawing generation in FORAN is managed by a single module, which covers the output drawings of all design disciplines (general, hull structure, outfitting, electrical and accommodation). The drawing generation is completely user configurable, as the final aspect of the drawings depends on the user requirements. Drawings are generated directly from the 3D product model, and the 2D entities that represent the product model are linked to the 3D elements. They are always updated with the latest version of the product model. A symbolic representation for modelled elements is possible and different visualization methods are available.

The drawing generation module includes also a function to reprocess the drawing after changes in the model, at the same time keeping any manual modifications introduced by the user in the drawing.

There are also options for automatic dimensioning and labelling by means of user-configurable formats and templates representing different attributes of the selected elements (identification, scantling, profile cross sections, end-cuts and others). These entities are also linked to the product model elements. The drawings generated are compatible with most standard drawing formats.

Fig. 6: Detail of the aft area of the ship

4.5.2 Other outputs

One of the advantages inherent to integrated 3D applications is the easy data extraction as the whole product model is stored on a single source of information. With FORAN, different types of reports that can be generated are configurable and can be exported to most standard formats like Excel, HTML and ASCII.

Fixed content reports like steel order (plates and profiles) and configurable bill of materials can be obtained based on user-specified query conditions. Report content depends on the degree of definition of the project. Among others, the following reports can be obtained in FORAN:

- Weight and centre of gravity
- Painted areas
- Material takes off lists
- Bill of materials
- Welding lengths

5. Link with FEM tools

One of the most relevant aspects during the basic engineering of a ship is the structural analysis by finite element methods (FEM), which allow improving and validating the feasibility of the design. In practice, it is a laborious task that requires the preparation of a suitable model for calculation, meshing, the application of loads and constraints, processing, post-processing and analysis of the results.

Most finite element tools include standard formats for the direct import of 3D CAD models, but fail when these models come from the shipbuilding industry due to the complexity of the ship models. The effort required in the manual simplification of the model is such that it is more efficient to repeat the model with a calculation-oriented approach, which slows down the analysis process dramatically.

The use of a ship model already created in a 3D CAD for FEM analysis would optimise the design performance in the early stages. For this, there must be an efficient link between both tools so that a simplified ship model adapted to each type of calculation can be exported directly from CAD. SENER's approach to this problem combines its broad experience in CAD/CAM (computer aided manufacturing) shipbuilding tools with innovative solutions to obtain the expected results: a link that allows exporting a simplified ship model, leveraging its topological characteristics. Functional algorithms in FORAN allow the creation of an intelligent model, simplifying, filtering and deleting unnecessary data to guarantee the quality of the model transferred.

Among other functionalities, the user can decide in FORAN:

- Whether the plates are translated as surfaces by the neutral axis or the moulded line
- The automatic assignment of colours to every material and profile scantling
- Whether the profiles will be translated as surfaces or as curves
- The minimum area to discard the transfer of holes and brackets

Fig. 7: 2D FEM model produced using FORAN FEM link

All structure entities will be subject to an idealization process aiming to simplify the 3D model by using the following criteria:

- For plates, notches, scallops, fillets and chamfers are removed from the outer contour.
- For profiles (either via surfaces or curves), notches, scallops, macro-holes, end-cuts and profile extensions are removed.
- Surfaces created as plate or profiles are extended topologically to the moulded line/neutral axis of the surface used in its definition. This simplification is applied on every intersection line with other surfaces used in the plate or profile definition.
- Plates are split in different surfaces using the profile layout and any other marking line.
- Corrugated and flanged plates are split in planar faces.
- Surfaces sewing; surfaces created by a previous split are joined on the join line.
- Profiles sewing: If the profile is translated as a surface, flange and web is sewn. Translated profile web surface is sewn to its underlying plate surface, too.
- Plate limits are extended to the surfaces used in its definition.

6. Transition to Detail Design

The key point for any software aiming to provide a complete solution for ship design and manufacturing is the smooth transition between the design stages, avoiding rework and delays. A logical continuation of the basic design, FORAN provides tools for subdividing and joining plates and profiles, and also features additional attributes for detail design such as bevelling, construction margins and shrinkage factors, and defining parts that are not relevant during the basic design stages.

The way from the initial to the basic and the detailed design is also the way from the conceptual and abstract to the concrete and producible. Large conceptual parts useful to analyze for instance weight and structural behaviour must be converted in producible parts reusing all the information provided in the conceptual stages and detailing when necessary.

Fig. 8: Detail of a 3D model of a structure

The split concept is foundation in this transition. For example, large longitudinal layouts are split into producible profile parts inheriting layout attributes and with the appropriated split properties according to end-cuts, margins, etc. The split concept is applied to any kind of part, from bulkhead profiles to curved hull plates.

The level of detail not only concerns geometry but also attributes. Part attributes irrelevant in conceptual stages become critical in detailed design. In order to provide a smooth transition, tools to modify, check and copy attributes of large groups of pieces are provided.

The block subdivision is perhaps one of the most critical points in ship design regarding the transition between design stages. Although split and refinement tools can be used for block subdivision, some specific tools are provided in order to perform automatic recalculation of parts when the block butts are modified. Assignment of parts to units can be done at any time by means of a powerful graphical selection tool.

Finally, in this stage it is the right time to complete the detail design by defining those parts which are not relevant for the basic design stage.

Fig. 9: FEM analysis in the warship mid block studied

7. Benefits in Area of Improvements

The benefits of this approach are:

- Shorter evaluation of different design alternatives due to the high level of topology that allows an automatic recalculation in case of upper level modifications.
- The generation of a 3D model at early design stages allows taking decisions based on more detailed information rather than estimates, e.g. for materials and weights (including welds and coating).
- Less risk of inconsistencies compared to the 2D approach in which every view is independent and has no relation to the others. The 3D approach combines the implicit intelligence associated to the model by means of certain attributes (continuity, watertightness) with the graphical checking performed by the user leading to better designs.
- Easier link with analysis and calculation tools based on a single 3D model. The 3D model lends itself much easier to FEM model generation and other calculations. Most of these calculations are made during basic design.
- The quick positioning of the most relevant equipment helps in setting the most important spaces of the ship. It also improves the estimates for weights and centres of gravity.

- Due to the incremental development of the model as the design evolves, there is a seamless transition to detail design based on the re-use of data which reduces the design time and simplifies the overall process.
- More accurate design due to the use of a 3D tool
- Easier coordination among disciplines as hull structure and various disciplines of outfitting are represented in the same underlying product model. This has obvious advantages in terms of interference or collision checks and leads to a better outfitting design regarding the general arrangement definition and critical compartments layout.
- Having the 3D model at early design stages allows Virtual Reality exploration. This is an important advantage for marketing activities or to control the design process in a very intuitive way.

Fig. 10: Virtual reality navigation using 3D glasses around a ship 3D model in FORAN FVIEWER

Some areas of improvements are:

- The simpler the generation of the 3D model is, the more benefits are obtained. There are things to improve in reducing and simplifying the generation of the model.
- The solution needs to be flexible and easy to use. The people involved in concept and basic design usually work with 2D tools, which are very easy to use. They expect a similarly easy 3D tool.

8. Conclusions

FORAN improves design quality, provides higher precision and reduces the risk of inconsistencies.

The rapid evaluation of several design alternatives and the early estimation of materials, weights, welding and painting are additional advantages, as is the efficient link with finite element analysis tools. Finally, it also facilitates the outfitting definition (general layout and layout of critical compartments) and improves the coordination between disciplines. In conclusion, the key points are the simple transition to detail design and the reuse of information.

This substantial change in the development of the basic design stage is expected to become the routine way of working in the future, particularly when the continuation with the detail design is considered and/or outfitting design is part of the scope of work.

It is well known that most of the costs of a ship are compromised during the initial design stages. The proposed solution delivers tangible benefits as it optimizes the process by reducing the time dedicated to design and consequently cost.

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Towards the Estimation of Directional Wave Spectra from Measured Glider Responses

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Abstract

Technological developments have allowed the transformation of ocean observations from platform based capabilities to networks of sensor nodes. Nodes are autonomous robotic platforms, named underwater gliders, designed for real-time observation of the ocean. Expanding the observational capabilities of gliders is a technological demand. It is envisioned that information about the on-site directional wave spectra could be obtained from glider response measurements at the sea surface. The objective of this paper is twofold: (1) it reviews present underwater glider technology and applications; (2) it summarizes the research developed to derive the directional wave spectra from the platform.

1. Introduction

Gliders are unpropelled and autonomous underwater robots that make use of their hydrodynamic shape and buoyancy changes to induce net horizontal motions in the water column, *Stommel (1989)*, Fig.1. Gliders presently found in the market share common structural properties, *Eriksen et al. (2001)*, *Sherman et al. (2001)*, *Webb et al. (2001)*. These robots are characterized by a winged body of torpedo shape with a weight between 50 and 100 Kg and a total length between 1.5 and 2 m. Wings are usually small with a wingspan of 1 m. The pressurized hull hosts the electronic for navigation and communication, the battery packages and a buoyancy engine. The latter differentiates gliders from other autonomous underwater vehicles. The buoyancy engine is constituted by a piston or, alternatively, a pumping system that modifies the buoyancy of the vehicle. At surface, gliders fill an internal piston with seawater to change buoyancy from positive to negative, Fig.2. A dive with a pitch of around 26° results from this buoyancy change. Pitch modifications are obtained by slight displacements of the internal battery package while heading is controlled by small fins. Alternatively, some gliders modify the heading by changing the roll angle by means of battery displacements. The lift generated by the wings induces a net horizontal displacement during diving. Gliding ratios of present glider technology are about 2:1 (2 m of horizontal displacement for each meter dived in the vertical water column) and horizontal speeds are order of 0.4 m/s. The water in the piston is ejected when the platform reaches a pre-determined depth. The robot gets a positive buoyancy to start the ascending portion of the overall undulatory motion. This cycle is repeated during a period of time ranging from 3 to 8 h. Then, the platform surfaces to reposition and to proceed with data transmission. A satellite link is established between the platform and the laboratory during each surfacing, to download the collected data and upload new mission commands. The time at surface is programmable and it usually ranges from a few minutes up to an hour depending on the amount of information to be transmitted. This working procedure requires low power consumption, awarding gliders with long endurance at sea (up to several months).

Fig.1: Glider fleet of CMRE

Gliders are becoming a popular platform in observational oceanography due to their long endurance, autonomy and maneuverability at sea. Traditional applications include sustained monitoring of the oceanographic conditions in marine areas, *Heslop et al. (2012)*. For this use, gliders are commanded to perform certain oceanic transects on a regular basis to assess the spatio-temporal variability of marine regions. Determination of the spatial representation of the data gathered by oceanographic moorings is another application of glider platforms, *Wallace (2009)*. In this case, gliders provide information about the spatial variability in the surroundings of a moored buoy. Other studies combined the in situ information gathered from gliders with the data obtained from remote sensing to improve the oceanographic characterization of coastal regions, *Alvarez and Mourre (2012a)*, *Alvarez et al. (2013)*. Besides the traditional uses, glider technology is bringing new paradigms to observational oceanography; networking and adaptive sampling are among them. The former refers to the observations gathered by teams of cooperative and spatially distributed underwater gliders. Ocean sampling with networked autonomous sensors was introduced by *Curtin et al. (1993)* twenty years ago. Since then, significant effort has been directed to achieve the operational implementation of Autonomous Ocean Sampling Networks (AOSN). A remarkable contribution was provided by the AOSN-II field program performed in Monterey Bay, California, from mid-July to early September 2003 (*Ramp et al., 2009*). Posterior studies further investigated different aspects to control networks of gliders. Control methods for fleet formation to detect and track ocean features were proposed by *Fiorelli et al. (2006)*. A Glider Coordinated Control System (GCCS) for planning to steer a fleet of underwater gliders to a set of coordinated trajectories was developed by *Paley et al. (2008)*. *Zang and Leonard (2010)* developed optimal strategies for mission design, addressing both the coordinated motion control and the cooperative sensing of a noisy scalar field. Studies have also optimized network topologies to achieve a performance gain over naïve collective behavior. *Alvarez et al. (2007)* used a genetic algorithm to find optimal gliders trajectories to get together an unevenly distributed network of floats, the best quality of the sampled field. The quality of the oceanographic field (objective function to minimize) was measured in terms of the mean formal error obtained from an optimum interpolation scheme. Genetic algorithms were also employed by *Heaney et al. (2007)* to optimize sampling strategies of fleets of gliders based on the estimated performance of ocean predictions when glider data is assimilated into ocean models. Similarly, *Alvarez and Mourre (2012b)* and *Mourre and Alvarez (2012)* used simulated annealing and pattern search as the optimization engines. These approaches have been experimentally implemented in the framework of a military exercise (*Osler et al., 2012*).

Fig.2: A cycle of a glider yo-yo motion

Adaptive sampling concerns the modification of sampling strategies of a glider or network of gliders to the evolution of the environment. Adaptivity of the network topology requires a continuous feedback of information between the gliders and a data processing unit. The core of this unit is a data fusion engine that produces a physically sounded analysis of the marine environment, based on the information received from the in situ network and remote sensors. The analysis establishes the hierarchy of near future sampling strategies that is communicated to the gliders through above water communication. *Mourre and Alvarez (2012)* implemented an adaptive sampling scheme with a glider in an operational characterization of a marine region, Fig.3.

Presently, temperature and salinity are the ocean variables most commonly gathered from glider platforms. However, it is envisioned that these platforms could provide information about a wider range of environmental parameters. Sea state condition is among them. This could be achieved by expanding glider sensing capabilities to include an accelerometer package to determine the platform motions when excited by ocean waves, *Pereira and Sukhatme (2010)*. Determination of the response of a glider platform to regular waves when surfaced is a requirement to infer sea state conditions from the platform motions. On-site directional wave spectra could then be estimated on the basis of these glider response measurements at the sea surface. Specifically, linear spectral analysis can be used to set up the equations which relate the measured glider responses with the wave energy spectrum through complex valued transfer functions, *Nielsen (2006)*. The latter must be numerical or experimentally determined. This contribution summarizes the procedure followed for the numerical determination of the transfer functions of a glider excited by regular waves.

Fig.3: Adaptive sampling from a) August 20 to August 22, b) August 22 to August 24 and c) August 24 to August 26, 2010 off shore La Spezia (Italy). Black lines are commanded mission while red lines are real tracks. Color scale in °C represents the temperature uncertainty of a two days model forecast when the glider data was assimilated in the ocean prediction model. Initial uncertainty was slightly above to 2 °C. Figures show the impact of glider data to reduce forecast uncertainty.

2. Wave responses of an underwater glider at sea surface

A free-floating glider is assumed at the sea surface. The glider interacts with a regular wave field consisting of a prescribed incident wave system plus outgoing waves associated with the radiation and scattering. Considering small unsteady motions relative to the wavelength and relevant scales of the glider, the free surface and glider boundary conditions can be linearized around their mean positions. A time-harmonic dependence in the oscillatory motions is also assumed. The following system of equations holds for small motions of the different degrees of freedom, *Newman (1977)*:

$$(M_{ij} + A_{ij})\ddot{\eta}_j + B_{ij}\dot{\eta}_j + C_{ij}\eta_j = F_i e^{i\omega t} \quad (1)$$

η_i , $i=1..3$ represent the amplitudes of translation displacements in the x , y and z directions (surge, sway and heave, respectively) while η_i , $i=4..6$ are the amplitudes of rotational displacements about the same axis (roll, pitch and yaw, respectively). These displacements are represented on a right handed Cartesian coordinate system, fixed with respect to the mean position of the body and with the origin in the plane of the undisturbed free surface. The terms M_{ij} , A_{ij} , B_{ij} and C_{ij} are the mass-inertia matrix of the glider, the matrix of added mass coefficients, the damping coefficient matrix and the hydrostatic restoring terms, respectively. Finally, F_i represent the complex amplitude of the exciting force in the i -th direction. Coefficients in matrices M_{ij} and C_{ij} can be computed knowing the shape

and internal mass distribution of the floating glider, whereas, matrices A_{ij} and B_{ij} represent the bulk effect of pressure forces exerted by the fluid on the glider. Their coefficients are estimated considering that the fluid is homogeneous, inviscid and incompressible and the fluid motion is irrotational. Under these conditions, the flow velocity can be defined in terms of a velocity potential satisfying the Laplace equation:

$$\Phi(x, y, z, t) = \text{Re}(\phi(x, y, z)e^{i\omega t}) \quad (2)$$

The time independent velocity potential can be decomposed as:

$$\phi(x, y, z) = i\omega \sum_{j=1}^6 \eta_j \phi_j(x, y, z) + A(\phi_I + \phi_S) \quad (3)$$

ϕ_j is the time independent velocity potential corresponding to each mode of oscillation of the glider with unit amplitude, $\phi_I = i \frac{g}{\omega} e^{Kz} e^{-iK(x \cos(\beta) + y \sin(\beta)) + i\omega t}$ is the velocity potential of the incident wave with unit amplitude A , wave-number $K = \omega^2/g$ (g is the acceleration of gravity and β is the angle of incidence), and ϕ_S is the scattered potential. The complex spatial part of the velocity potentials must satisfy, *Newman (1977)*:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 \phi_{j,S} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_{j,S}}{\partial z} - K \phi_{j,S} &= 0 \text{ for } z = 0, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_{j,S}}{\partial z} &\rightarrow 0 \text{ as } z \rightarrow -\infty, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial n} (\phi_I + \phi_S) &= 0 \text{ on body surface,} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial n} \phi_j &= n_j \quad j = 1 \dots 6 \text{ on body surface, and} \\ \sqrt{R} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial R} - iK \right\} \phi_{j,S} &\rightarrow 0 \text{ when } R \rightarrow \infty, z \leq 0, \text{ and } R = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$(n_1, n_2, n_3) = (n_x, n_y, n_z)$ are the components of a unit vector normal to the body surface (outward of the fluid) and $(n_4, n_5, n_6) = (x, y, z) \times (n_x, n_y, n_z)$. The boundary value problem is solved by using Green's theorem to derive integral equations for the different velocity potentials on the glider boundary. The integral equation satisfied by the radiation velocity potentials ϕ_j on the glider boundary is

$$2\pi\phi_j(\bar{x}) + \iint_S \phi_j(\bar{\xi}) \frac{\partial G(\bar{x}; \bar{\xi})}{\partial n_\xi} dS = \iint_S n_j G(\bar{x}; \bar{\xi}) dS, \quad (5)$$

S denotes the body wetted surface at calm water and $G(x; \xi)$ is the Green function:

$$\begin{aligned} G(x, y, z; \xi, \theta, \varsigma) &= \frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{r'} + 2K(P.V.) \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{k-K} e^{k(z+\varsigma)} J_0(kR) dk - 2\pi i K e^{K(z+\varsigma)} J_0(KR), \\ r &= \sqrt{(x-\xi)^2 + (y-\theta)^2 + (z-\varsigma)^2}, \\ r' &= \sqrt{(x-\xi)^2 + (y-\theta)^2 + (z+\varsigma)^2}, \text{ and} \\ R &= \sqrt{(x-\xi)^2 + (y-\theta)^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The coefficients of matrix A_{ij} and B_{ij} are then given by:

$$A_{ij} - \frac{i}{\omega} B_{ij} = \rho \iint_S n_i \phi_j dS, \quad (7)$$

ρ is the density of the fluid. The scattered field is considered negligible due to the long wave lengths relative to the scale of the body and thus the exciting forces (defined by the forces exerted on the glider by the incident and scattered field) are given by their Froude-Krylov approximation:

$$F_i = -i\omega\rho \iint_S n_i \phi_i dS, \quad (8)$$

Eq.(1) is written in the frequency domain like:

$$[-\omega^2(M_{ij} + A_{ij}) + i\omega B_{ij} + C_{ij}] \hat{\eta}_j = F_i; \quad \eta_j = \hat{\eta}_j e^{i\omega t}, \quad (9)$$

Fig.4: Semi-submerged glider configuration and definition of sea directions

The solutions of the system of equations are the transfer functions for the responses and the response amplitude operator (RAO) is the magnitude of the transfer function. Transfer functions represent a linear approximation of the frequency response of the glider motion in regular waves.

The hull of a Slocum glider, *Webb et al. (2001)*, was segmented into 838 panels to compute the corresponding transfer functions in regular waves, Fig.4. A pitch of 10° was measured during the communication phase when the platform is at the sea surface. Notice that only the submerged portion of the hull has been considered in the computations. Wings have been modeled by plates of 0.002 m thickness. Fig.5 shows the RAOs of heave and pitch and associated phases computed for different wave periods and sea directions. Results show the existence of a resonance marked in the diagrams by a local maximum in the RAO and an abrupt change in response phase. In fact, analytical approximations predict the existence of resonance phenomena at periods of 1.05 and 5.46 s for the case under study. The former period is related to the natural frequency of the vehicle (corresponding period of 1.32 s). RAOs decrease for small wave periods while go to 1 in the case of heave and zero for pitch. Thus, for periods longer than 10 s the glider follows the wave surface. Note that a negligible pitch is induced in the platform by long wavelengths. RAOs are insensitive to sea direction while corresponding phases show a dependence on this parameter for short waves. This is understood in terms of the long wavelengths compared to the glider size.

3. Conclusion

Results indicate that the small-body approximation is appropriate to describe heave and pitch responses of a glider for wave periods longer than 10 s. Resonances are expected below this time period. In the present case, a resonant peak was found at 5 s. A second resonance peak would correspond to the natural period of the platform, $T=1.3$ s. Note that resonance periods depend on the hydrostatic restoring terms of the glider. The stern of Slocum gliders is an open hull and buoyancy is provided by inflating a blade. This could require a more accurate determination of the heave restoring term than determined in this report which considered the glider hull as a unit without open portions.

Summarizing, it is expected gliders will follow the wave surface for wave periods longer than 10 s. This simplifies the determination of directional spectra for long wave periods. A more detailed study (probably experimental) is required to refine present results for shorter wave periods.

Fig.5: RAOs and corresponding phases for heave (a and b) and pitch (c and d) for sea directions of 0° (o), 91° (+) and 182° (*). T is the period in seconds and phases are in radians.

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A Combination of Morphing Technique and Cartesian Grid Method for Rapid Generation of Objects and their Performances

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Abstract

Morphing is a geometric interpolation technique which can produce a great number of 'intermediate' forms instantaneously. In addition, the morphing method can be easily and directly used in mesh-based performance assessment programs such as CFD. This paper discusses an application of Cartesian grid method to a commercial CFD program, Fluent, instead of attempting to use a grid which conforms to the boundary. The use of Cartesian grid method allows high quality grid generation of complex geometries produced through morphing technique. Examples of 2D grid generation were studied in this work, but the underlying ideas are clearly extendable to 3D problems as well. It has been found that the combination of morphing technique and Cartesian grid method has great potential as a powerful tool for the optimisation process of product design.

1. Introduction

Computers have now been firmly established as the essential tool in most industries with their abilities to store and access a huge amount of information relatively cheaply and their speed and accuracy in information and numerical processing. They allow very complex engineering models to be created and studied and enormous amount of work can be done automatically or with minimum human intervention.

Maritime industries are no exception and computers have penetrated every aspect of design, construction and operation of marine systems and structures. Ship hull design, for example, received much research attention since the early days of computer applications. It is easily understandable why the hull form design has been one of the many preoccupations of naval architects. Once upon a time it was treated more as an art than engineering skill. Then some visionaries set about making this task of creating efficient and effective hull forms easier and more scientific through a systemic study of hull forms. *Taylor (1915)* went one step beyond that and tried to devise a method of representing the hull forms through mathematical formulations. *Lackenby (1950)* attempted to give more 'handles' to designers by formalising methods of creating a new hull form by transforming an existing one. These mathematical methods have been important groundwork for computer-based ship designs, and *Lackenby's* methods are still used in modern hull design applications.

With more widespread use of digital computers, many mathematical methods were developed to define the surface of the hull forms numerically or mathematically. This task was more difficult because of the very nature and diversity of hull forms, which can be described in single phrase as 'free forms'. It is not just ship hulls which had free forms, of course. One of the major breakthroughs occurred when *Bézier (1968)* introduced a technique of generating a free form curve for designing automobile bodies while working as an engineer at the car manufacturer Renault. After *de Boor (1971)* and *Cox (1972)* independently developed a numerical algorithm for B-spline, *Riesenfeld (1972)* applied the technique to ship form definition. Such curve generation techniques have been used for representing wire-frame models by specifying each of the physical objects or by connecting object's surface vertices with spatial curves, usually parametrically orthogonal to each other. This modelling method was found eminently suited for visualisation of 3D models, and it has been used widely and successfully for representing hull forms especially in CAD software.

After further work on the curves, Non-Uniform Rational B-Spline, normally called NURBS was introduced, and it has become very popular for geometric modelling. NURBS can offer great flexibility and precision with weighted control points, and they have been used to represent hull forms by many researchers. However, most of the researches have focused on accurate representation rather

than rapidity or efficiency of generation. This type of method, therefore, cannot be easily adopted for automatic optimisation process which typically requires many alternative designs to be provided on demand.

With rapid increase in speed and capability of computing facility, development of various performance evaluation tools such as CFD (computational fluid dynamics), FEA (finite element analysis) and various simulation programs have been accelerated in ship design. Full-scale testing of ships is almost out of the question at the design stage, and even scale model tests of ships for design assessment for optimisation purpose are not so simple or easy to perform. Consequently the number of hull forms that can be studied with experiments is limited. It is, therefore, hardly surprising that the use of computational tools for evaluating performance has mushroomed and, in many instances, is accepted to be nearly as good as, or occasionally better than, the physical model tests. There can be no doubt that performance analysis using a CFD program is time-saving and inexpensive compared to a model test. However, a preparation process for CFD also requires hugely time-consuming work, and it could be difficult to generate a good mesh if CFD operators are not sufficiently well-trained or experienced in meshing process.

Combined with the difficulties in generating viable designs, the difficulties in representing them with meshes suitable for use in such analysis programs have now become the new bottlenecks of computer-based optimisation, Fig.1. In an effort to overcome these problems, this paper presents a combination of a rapid form generation method based on morphing technique and a high quality and speed grid generation based on Cartesian grid.

Fig. 1: Bottlenecks of computer-based optimisation

2. Morphing

The word morphing originates from the word metamorphosis which means a transformation of an insect or an amphibian from an immature form or a larva to an adult form in distinct stages. Morphing, in the context of graphical manipulation, is usually defined as a geometric interpolation technique that transforms an object into another through a seamless transition. Recently, morphing techniques have been developed and applied very successfully in various areas, particularly in the field of computer graphics. Commercial advertisements, animations and films using morphing are often seen in today's media. Although little attention has been given to the application of morphing for product design so far, it is possible that the method holds significant potential for rapid generation of shape modelling, *Chen and Parent (1989), Terzides (1989), Hsiao and Liu (2002) and Kang and Lee (2010, 2012)*.

The linear morphing is defined by:

$$M(t) = (1-t) \bullet R_0 + t \bullet R_1, \quad t \in [0,1] \quad (1)$$

where t is the morphing parameter, $M(t)$ is the generated model and R_0 and R_1 denote the first and second parent models respectively. The model at $t = 0$ is equivalent to the first parent model (i.e.

$M(0) = R_0$), and the model at $t = 1$ is equivalent to the second parent model ($M(1) = R_1$). When t is close to zero, the generated model $M(t)$ is close to the source model R_0 ; conversely, when t is close to one, the generated model $M(t)$ is close to the target model R_1 .

2.1. Curve morphing

Curve morphing is a geometric interpolation carried out between two curves. These curves can be either 2D polyhedral models or 3D polygonal curves. A polygonal curve is a set of line segments $p_0p_1, p_1p_2, \dots, p_{n-1}p_n$, where p_i ($i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$) is a vertex and each segment $p_i p_{i+1}$ is an edge that represents a curve. Some objects can be defined purely as curves (e.g. cross sections outline of an airfoil) or a group of curves (e.g. a mesh representing a surface). Thus curve morphing can be directly to curve designs, or applied to definition of boundaries of surface meshes. In this paper, two airfoil models are randomly selected to show an example of the curve morphing. The first parent model is Gottingen 796 airfoil (Goe796), and the second one is NACA 64(3)-218 airfoil (Naca643218).

One of the most important and difficult problems of the curve morphing is to establish a correspondence between the vertices of the parent objects. However, the two original airfoil models have different number of nodes representing the shapes; for example, the first model, Goe796 has 42 and the second one, Naca643218 has 51 nodes respectively. In addition, the order of data both models are different. The nodes of Goe796 model start from leading edge to the trailing edge through the upper part for the upper part of airfoil, and the nodes starts again from leading edge to the trailing edge through the lower part for the lower part of the airfoil respectively. On the other hand, the nodes of Naca643218 start from the trailing edge of the airfoil, through the upper part to the leading edge and trough lower part back to the starting node. Thus, the vertices of both models should be established to be an identical mesh structure.

In order to establish a correspondence, the order and the number of data for both models should be identical. For this task, the data order of Goe796 was made to be the same as the Naca643218's, and each model was made to have 200 nodes by using cubic spline to be same number of data. Through morphing, numerous intermediate models can be generated instantaneously. Fig.2 illustrates some of these newly generated airfoils (b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j) from the Goe796 (a) and Naca643218 (k) airfoils. The results of morphing for the interpolation parameter t at the intervals of 0.1 are shown in this figure.

Fig. 2: Original models and newly generated models: (a) first parent model ($t = 0$); (b) $t = 0.1$; (c) $t = 0.2$; (d) $t = 0.3$; (e) $t = 0.4$; (f) $t = 0.5$; (g) $t = 0.6$; (h) $t = 0.7$; (i) $t = 0.8$; (j) $t = 0.9$; (k) second parent model ($t = 1$)

2.2. Surface morphing

Most of the objects found in the real world are 3D shapes. One of the methods of representing these objects is through defining their surface, and a triangular mesh is used to model 3D surfaces in this paper. Correspondence between the vertices of parent models is again one of the most important problems in surface morphing process. In this paper, two methods are introduced in order to solve the correspondence problem on 3D surface. One method is based on merging, and another is on regularising the meshes. A common goal of these two methods is to create identically structured meshes.

2.2.1. Merging

Merging method has been mostly used for establishing correspondence between vertices of the models as a first step in a 3D morphing process. This method can keep the original vertices of the parent meshes, and the redefined meshes through the merging method will inherit the original mesh characteristics. Fig.3 shows the outline procedure of the merging method of preparing the hull form meshes prior to morphing. The first task for the merging method is mapping the two original meshes of the hull forms onto a 2D parameter plane in order to make it easier to handle the meshes. The next step is merging the projected meshes into a single mesh. When this 2D mesh is mapped back onto the original parent 3D surfaces, they will have an identical mesh structure and the correspondence between the two meshes is automatically assured. Fig.4 shows examples of intermediate hull forms generated through morphing based on the merging method.

Fig. 3: Algorithm used for the hull form morphing: (a) Original 3D meshes; (b) Projecting 3D meshes on 2D plane; (c) Merging two 2D meshes; (d) Remapping 2D mesh to each original 3D surface, Kang and Lee (2012)

Fig. 4: Hull form morphing using the merged method

2.2.2. Regularising

Regularising method is usually mentioned in connection with mesh quality in order to obtain better numerical results rather than for correspondence problem. Nevertheless, when the parent models are regularised to identically structured meshes, the vertices of the two models will correspond to each other. Even when more than two parent models are used, the regularising method provides a single common mesh structure unlike the merging method. Thus this method is suitable for multi-parent morphing. The multi-parent morphing method will be discussed in more detail later in this paper.

Fig.5 shows the procedure of regularising meshes for bulbous bow of a ship for example. The first task of regularisation is mapping the 3D surface mesh onto a 2D plane in order to handle mesh elements easily, as in the merging method described above. Since a regular triangular mesh can be easily created by repeatedly bisecting each edge of a triangular shape, a convenient set of three points are selected from the mesh nodes on the boundary curves of the surface. Fig.6 illustrates examples of intermediate bulbous bow forms generated using the regularising method.

Fig. 5: Procedure of re-meshing for bulbous bow; (a) Original 3D mesh; (b) Mapping 3D points onto 2D plane; (c) Regularisation on 2D plane; (d) Remapping from 2D to 3D

Fig. 6: Original bulbous bows and newly generated models: (a) first parent model ($t = 0$); (b) $t = 0.25$; (c) $t = 0.5$; (d) $t = 0.75$; (e) second parent model ($t = 1$)

2.3. Other supporting techniques

The normal morphing technique is based on interpolation between two models, and it is obvious that the 'morphed' forms will inherit the geometric characteristics of both of the parent forms. This results in more or less predictable intermediate forms which may be an advantage in some one but a shortcoming in another. In order to overcome this predictability and to allow the designer more freedom to control the forms, this paper introduces several supporting techniques for the morphing technique. They are multi-parent morphing, warping and extrapolating methods.

2.3.1. Multi-parent morphing

Multi-parent morphing uses more than two models for the parent models. The multi-parent morphing is defined as:

$$M(t_0, t_1, \dots, t_n) = t_0 \cdot R_0 + t_1 \cdot R_1 + t_2 \cdot R_2 + \dots + t_n \cdot R_n, \quad t_n \in [0,1] \quad (2)$$

t_n : weight factor (or, morphing parameter) for parent models, $t_0 + t_1 + t_2 + \dots + t_n = 1$

R_n : parent models

Depending on the combination of the weighing factors, shapes of many different characteristics can be generated through this method. Fig.7 shows some of the forms generated through the three-parent morphing (Gottingen 796 (a), NACA 64(3)-218 (b), Eppler E858 propeller (c) airfoils).

Fig. 7: Some models generated through multi-parent morphing of three parent models: (a) $(t_0, t_1, t_2) = (1, 0, 0)$; (b) $(0, 1, 0)$; (c) $(0, 0, 1)$; (d) $(0.5, 0.25, 0.25)$; (e) $(0.25, 0.5, 0.25)$; (f) $(0.25, 0.5, 0.25)$; (g) $(0.34, 0.33, 0.33)$

2.3.2. Warping

Warping can deform a single model naturally into another model. This technique would be useful when there is only one parent model available and it is necessary to generate the candidates for the second parent. Of course, the model generated through the technique can also be used as a design alternative itself. Warping can be achieved by applying Laplacian differential coordinates, and the coordinates represent a point s_i by using a set of differential $L(s_i)$ between s_i and the average of its neighbours s_j :

$$s_i = L(s_i) + \sum w_{ij} s_j \quad (3)$$

w_{ij} is the weighting factor for point s_j with $\sum w_{ij} = 1$, L the Laplacian operator. Fig.8 shows two bulbous bows (a and c) generated extremely through warping from an original bulbous bow model (b).

Fig.8: Newly generated bulbous bows (a, c) from original bulbous bow (b) through warping

2.3.3. Extrapolating

Extrapolating technique produces new forms beyond parent models, so it is a potentially more creative process. The algorithm of extrapolating can be also conducted by Eqs.(1) and (2) used in morphing; however, the parameter t can go beyond the bounds of from 0 to 1, such as 1.3, 0.5 and 1.2. Fig.9 shows some of the models generated from two-parent extrapolating technique.

Fig. 9: Original airfoil models and some models generated through extrapolating: (a) $t = -0.66$; (b) first parent model ($t = 0$); (c) second parent model ($t = 1$); (d) $t = 1.29$;

3. Cartesian grid

The governing equation of CFD is partial differential equations, and in order to analyse fluid flows, therefore, flow domains need to be split into smaller subdomains such as triangles or quadrilaterals in 2D and tetrahedra and hexahedra in 3D. There are many different computational mesh types, but the choice of the proper mesh is very important.

Cartesian grids consist of rectangular (or cubic in 3D) cells which are aligned to the axes of the coordinate system. As shown in Fig.10(a), Cartesian grids result in the same discretisation for most grid cells. Thus, the grid method has grids of better quality with high orthogonality, low skewness and aspect ratio compared to boundary-fitted grid (b). In addition, the Cartesian grid has high flexibility on geometry shape since it is possible to put a grid around any shape, no matter how complicated. Moreover, Cartesian grid can handle the resolution more easily compared to body-fitted grid by using hanging nodes which can split a face or a cell of mesh. With the possibility of fully automatic process, the method of generating Cartesian grid is relatively quick.

On the other hand, body-fitted grid has difficulty in generating a ‘good’ mesh for a complicate shape. The boundaries of flow field would have to differ according to the shape of an object in order to obtain better mesh qualities with respect to orthogonality, skewness and aspect ratio. Multi-block grids are another way for the body-fitted grid method to have high-quality mesh, and this can handle a tricky portion of the geometry relatively easily. However, the subdivision task will necessitate manual manipulations which can result in more opportunity for human error. These problems of body-fitted grids, therefore, are not well suited for automatic mesh preparation process in most cases.

Fig.10: Examples of Cartesian grid (a) and body-fitted grid (b)

4. Application of a combination method to CFD (Fluent)

Typically, there are three methods of solving a system of partial differential equations, i.e. finite-difference, finite-element and finite-volume methods. The CFD program Fluent uses the finite-volume approach to discretisation, so this paper focuses on this approach. A finite-volume method calculates the values of the conserved variables over the grid cell (or volume) surrounding each node point on a mesh as shown in Fig.11(a). It is said that the finite volume method is easier to implement for unstructured meshes and is more stable.

Fig.11: An example of Cartesian grid based on finite-volume method (a), and hanging node adaptation for Fluent (b)

Fig.12: Comparison between Cartesian grid (left) and body-fitted grid (right) of NACA 0012 airfoil

Fig. 13: Generated Cartesian grids based on intermediate models formed through morphing technique (a) first parent model ($t=0$); (b) $t=0.25$; (c) $t=0.5$; (d) $t=0.75$; (e) second parent model ($t=1$)

As mentioned in Section 3, most of the Cartesian grid cells have regular and identical discretisation. However, it is inevitable that irregular-shaped grid cells such as a triangle, a quadrilateral, and a pentagon occur on the physical boundaries of an object. There is no problem for Fluent to read triangular or quadrilateral shape cells. Unfortunately, however, a pentagonal mesh element cannot be read in Fluent, and thus the pentagonal element must be divided into 3 quadrilateral and 1 triangular elements by inserting hanging nodes as shown in Fig.11(b). Through this process it is possible to produce Cartesian grids for the Fluent, and Fig.12 illustrates a comparison between a Cartesian grid (a) and a body-fitted grid. The model of both objects is NACA 0012 airfoil. Fig.13. shows examples of generated Cartesian grid based on intermediate models formed through morphing technique. The first parent model (correspond to $t = 0$) and the second model ($t = 1$) models are NACA 0012 and NACA 0024 airfoils respectively.

5. Conclusion

A combination of morphing technique and Cartesian grid method has been explored for rapid generation of objects and their mesh representations. Morphing technique has been found to be very useful in producing numerous feasible models, and with the several supporting techniques such as multi-parent morphing, warping and extrapolating methods, the morphing technique has more powerful potential as a design tool.

Cartesian grid method offers high flexibility on geometries. No matter how complicated, a grid can be generated around any object. In addition, the absence of multi-block grid allows the meshes to be generated quickly and automatically. These properties of Cartesian grid method are very useful in producing meshes for CFD from design alternatives generated through morphing technique. Thus, it can be said that the morphing method and Cartesian grid method are a perfect match for automatic or semi-automatic optimisation process in design.

In this paper, examples of 2D grid generation were studied, but the underlying ideas are clearly extendable to 3D problems as well.

Acknowledgements

Part of this research has been carried out with the support of the research programme 'Improved ship design and operation, by operational data aggregation, key performance indices and numerical optimization (ImproVEDO)' headed by SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture, and funded by Rolls-Royce Marine and the Norwegian Research Council.

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Analysis of Economic and Environmental Performance of Retrofits using Simulation

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Abstract

Increasingly ship operators are under pressure to respond to demanding environmental regulations, e.g. ballast water treatment. Often these problems must be solved by some retrofitting activity, like installation of a treatment unit. As most applicable technologies are quite new, a decision is difficult to make. The whole life-cycle must be considered, not just initial investment and operating cost. This requires a detailed analysis of the retrofitting process. Our approach uses production simulation to determine actual exchanges with the environment and resulting overall cost. The method shall enable stakeholders of retrofitting projects to take an informed decision among implementation alternatives and strategies. It also provides another perspective to judge the feasibility of greening technologies, in particular from an environmental view.

1. Introduction

Environmental operating conditions and effects of marine vessels are currently in the focus of regulating authorities, since the contribution of marine traffic to pollution and other negative impacts on marine life has - at least in some geographical regions - reached levels that have spurred various regulatory activities. Typical examples are topics such as ballast water treatment (BWT) to avoid spreading of marine species to other habitats, or the avoidance of air pollution at sea and coastal regions resulting from engine exhausts.

For many of these issues, counteractions have been or are being devised. In many cases, several options exist for how to address the target issue. For example, pollution caused by exhaust from engines may be reduced by either reducing the exhaust volume as such as a result of improved efficiency and less fuel consumption, or by removing the most problematic polluting substances (like SO_x or NO_x) from the exhaust fumes. To reduce the total amount of pollutants at least two general philosophies exist: either the level is reduced by cleaning/filtering/neutralizing the exhaust gas or by switching to a completely different type of fuel (e.g. LNG). For the any of these options multiple implementation solutions exist. As can be seen from the exhaust example, some measures may at the same time be combined with a reduction of operating cost. This leads to a complex decision problem for owners and makes it a complex task for consulting entities to provide optimal advice.

As already indicated, there is a strong economic impact related to this topic. While regulations, when ratified and enforced leave no general choice other than implementing a compliant solution, there are also often situations in which the economic conditions are the driving factor. The cost of fuel is again a good example. These kinds of motivations tend to be more complex and sensitive, as there is often more room for variation. It is therefore important to combine economic and environmental aspects when trying to analyse solutions in order to support the decision making process. However, this is leading us to fundamental questions concerning the definition of the environmental and cost impact resulting from the environmental balance of a product's life cycle. The methodology of 'Life Cycle Assessment' (LCA) has been developed to aid in the appraisal of these issues.

2. LCA analysis

Life Cycle Assessment is a methodology applied to evaluate the overall environmental balance of a product or service. A key element of this method is a qualitative and quantitative analysis of products'

and/or processes' (services) effects in terms of consumed resources and emitted or disposed substances, energy or radiation (e.g. noise). This analysis is applied to the whole life cycle of a product or performance period of a process under investigation. Covering the whole life cycle is often referred to as the "cradle-to-grave" approach, Fig.1.

More recently, the methodology has developed to include among its appraisal boundary, the so-called three pillars of sustainability: people, planet, profit, *Guinée (2011)*. The planet aspect, meaning the environmental facet of the study, was the initial trigger in the formation of the methodology; however, it has advanced to include additional and more complex impacts. Similarly, the methodology also encompasses a way to account for the 'profit' pillar; the Life Cycle Costing (LCC) addition strives to include and assess economic factors, along with environmental impacts, throughout the complete life of a product or a service, with the aim of increasing even more the holistic approach of the practice, *Rebitzer and Hunkeler (2003)*.

As mentioned above, the standardised LCA method is a process model assessment, which includes a detailed inventory of resource inputs and environmental outputs (i.e. input and output flows), while additionally computing mass and energy balances, and evaluating potential environmental harm. The method, throughout its 'holistic' approach, is capable of serving as an evaluating tool, in order to improve environmental quality and sustainability.

Elementary flows are defined as per ISO as "material or energy entering the system being studied that has been drawn from the environment without previous human transformation, or material or energy leaving the system being studied that is released into the environment without subsequent human transformation", *ISO (2006)*. This last refers to flows that enter the technosphere (i.e. the system being assessed) from nature, such as resource flows (e.g. iron ore); and flows that leave the technosphere system to nature as emissions, whether they are directed to air, water or soil.

In recent years, the LCA methodology has been applied commonly for two purposes: one using elementary flows and potential environmental impacts in order to account for the history of a product, or a system; and the other which studies the future environmental consequences of a product or a system, versus an alternative.

In either of the two purposes, LCA allows decision makers to study the entire product system instead of focusing on a single process, hence avoiding the potential underestimation of environmental impacts. More specifically, LCA data can identify the transfer of ecological impacts from one environment to the other; for example, eliminating air emissions by creating a wastewater effluent instead. Similarly, it can pinpoint potential impacts shifting from one life cycle stage to another; for example, from use and reuse of the product to the raw material acquisition phase, *SAIC (2006)*. An additional benefit resides in the capability of quantifying environmental releases to air, water and land in relation to each life cycle stage; and that this information can also be tied up to other factors, such as costs and performance data for a relevant product or process.

LCA has grown from a methodology thought and applied strictly to potential environmentally harmful processes, to a tool applied and used to improve product design, while additionally used to enforce product regulations. The use of the methodology has also extended to various types of industry, finding widespread use, and it is included even among novel management practices, *Rebitzer (2005)*. Because of its ideal application as a design tool, LCA is usually carried out before a product is built or a process is established. It is used among other things to provide additional information during design, which can be used to investigate alternatives and to enable sound reasoning for decisions to be made. The fact that the product is most likely still under design means that LCA has to be performed using a model that reflects the expected properties of the product. Therefore, the LCA has to be based on models reflecting all essential product or process characteristics.

Unfortunately, the methodology requires intensive data gathering, which could prove expensive and time consuming. Additionally, compiling all material and energy balances for each relevant process is

impractical; therefore, the methodology calls for proper boundary setting, in order to assess complete systems. Both, boundary setting and data gathering can influence results certainty, by erroneous adjustment on the first, and lack of availability on the second, for example; both of these issues should be kept in mind by the LCA practitioner in order to avoid erroneous results.

Some of the key challenges when performing an LCA are:

- Capturing the life cycle involves the consideration of a large number of variables that may have an influence. Particularly for one-of-a-kind type products like most maritime vessels the construction period is a resource intense phase that has entirely different characteristics compared to the vessels in-service operations. Decommissioning is also considerably different e.g. from common recycling procedures. Similarly, repair and retrofitting activities involve another set of unique processes.
- Forecasting the performance of the product poses a challenge to identify the key performance factors and drivers. For a typical ship the operational profile mix must be captured and reflected. In this process various assumptions need to be made which typically leads to the definition of multiple scenarios to be evaluated.
- Managing the complexity of the problem is a key factor as well. It is important to introduce reasonable simplifications in an LCA model to control the number of input parameters.
- Determining the relevance of various details is needed when trying to establish a model that involves simplification in order to select the most important factors.

Fig. 1: Product life cycle phases, from *FhG (2012)*

3. Ship Life-Cycle

The life cycle of a ship is characterized by four main phases: planning/ordering, construction, operation/maintenance, and decommissioning/scraping, *Fet (1998)*. These phases have substantially different economic and environmental profiles; for example, within shipping, the life cycle concept is often understood as the period from when the ship is contracted to when it is sold. Therefore, when starting to investigate this in more detail, the operation phase turns out to be potentially quite complex. A ship may operate on different trading routes, for example; it may also change ownership, and be in need of regular inspection, maintenance and - due to the long life span - will additionally undergo modifications, retrofits, etc. Moreover, the assessment of its economic life is often focused on its trading profit, *Fet (1998)*, Fig.2.

Fig. 2: Life cycle of a ship, from *Ship* (2012)

Furthermore, and mostly during the operational phase, the vessel will produce emissions, generate wastes, and discharge various effluents, which will incur in the contribution of greenhouse effects, acidification, eutrophication, and other environmental impacts, *Fet and Sjørgård (1998)*. In the other hand, while contributing at a minor scale, shipyard processes included in the building phase, and scrapping operations, i.e. the end-of-life phase, could also incur in relevant environmental and cost impacts, and therefore should also be included in the assessed vessel's life span.

It is of importance to gather all available information regarding main construction or repair materials (e.g. ship erection modules, engine blocks, shipboard systems, piping, etc.), as well as energy consumption inputs, throughout the different life cycle phases of the specified vessel, in order to list them as available data inputs for the LCA modelling. The following is a list of minimum expected input information for modelling purposes, as adapted from, *Blanco-Davis and Zhou (2012)*:

- It is beneficial if one is able to choose a specific case vessel scenario (e.g. an existing ship or system in order to model after). If one is able to narrow the broadness of a sample, detailed data can be gathered, which will simplify and provide for a more detailed assessment.
- Gathering of as much general information from the case vessel as possible, in order to complete an operational profile is essential. This will also allow for assumptions and educated guesses when information is not available. The following elements, while not compulsory, could assist for performing more detailed assessments: annual voyages (light/heavy), operational schedule (sea/harbour), bunker price, fuel consumption, cargo volume, etc.
- Modular material composition is also essential for a complete assessment; as well as any type of energy consumption, including water, compressed air, fuel, etc. Disclosed information may not include all details, specifically material composition and weight information; manufacturers and actual on-board applications may possibly be the best source of information available.
- Information such as purchase, installation and operational costs of the shipboard systems (or retrofit option to be assessed) are very important for comparative assertions between an array of competing or different alternatives. This information allows putting into perspective systems' environmental balances versus economical scores.

- Information regarding transportation and manufacture processes is also beneficial for complete cradle-to-grave assessments. While this information is really difficult to come across to, manufacturing plant and/or shipyard location and purchasing information may allow completing better case assumptions.

Lastly, please note that data related to labour rates, machinery use, and flow (material and energy) costs if available, can be used to comprise a Life Cycle Costing (LCC) assessment, to be performed parallel to the LCA. If this kind of information is not readily available, relevant information to be recorded as mentioned above includes capital and operational expenses, in order to perform a cost-benefit analysis at a later stage, linking environmental scores to these results.

With the specified model created as mentioned above, the user will have a baseline scenario of the environmental impacts produced by the most ‘normal’ operation of the vessel in question; therefore, using elementary flows and environmental impacts in order to account for the history of the ship, and additionally to extrapolate to potential future impacts. Any alternation in the most common behaviour of the operational profile (e.g. change to low-sulphur fuel) can now be assessed versus the baseline scenario. Secondly, the user can also now compare the baseline scenario with an applied retrofit or maintenance application, in which current and future environmental consequences of each system can be appraised. This in turn offers the simulation end-user extended control over system inputs, and the flexibility to adjust them through various operational profiles, allowing to foresee different applicable alternatives, and aiding in the decision making process of these.

4. From Production Simulation to LCA

Simulation of planned production processes of a ship is used by several shipyards today, and may become a general and relevant part of production preparation planning activities. Therefore it seems logical to try to transfer this technique to retrofit projects. Since these projects are characterised by short planning periods and highly dynamic decision making processes, a powerful validation method like simulation has a promising potential for decision support.

To support LCA analysis through simulation, additional capabilities are needed in the software systems employed. The production simulation system being suggested here has previously been used for shipbuilding production, as described in *Koch (2011)*.

Fig. 3 shows the overall composition of the developed LCA tool suite. Based on existing tools for performing LCA and for executing shipyard production simulation, new functions have been added to implement the required functionality for the retrofitting assessment scenario.

Fig. 3: System architecture

Production simulation is intended to provide better insight into complex production work flows. It uses a model of the production facilities, resources and workloads; possibly combined with a more or less detailed planned schedule, in order to validate the intended production process execution, the execution sequence and dependencies, and the schedule adherence and resource utilization or demand. The actual input and output varies depending on the available information and the questions posed. For example, given a drafted schedule, a simulation may be used to generate its own sequence of events by allowing jobs to start based only on non-schedule related constraints (e.g. availability of

material and resources). Relaxing resource constraints would lead to results providing details about the maximum resource demands, while observing other production constraints. Other applications include identification of process bottlenecks, inefficient resource utilization, or investigating ‘what-if’ scenarios which may be based on a modified production environment, or a modified schedule, etc.

Production simulation includes tracking of a wide range of performance data for all entities included in the simulation model. For example, for a machine the periods of active use can be recorded together with the type of work being done. For purposes of LCA, the idea for the approach described here is to use these capabilities to generate and track similar data for those properties that are needed to perform a detailed LCA, most notably the consumed and emitted flows.

Furthermore, due to the application area in focus, production simulation methods have to be applied to retrofitting activities. Retrofitting can be characterised as a combination of activities similar to the production of new product components and those typically found in repair. Many repair activities differ substantially from production activities: they mostly occur on-site (thus being somewhat similar to on-board outfitting tasks), and they also include various kinds of “destructive” or removal-type operations like waste disposal, cleaning, removal of damaged/old parts or equipment, performing replacements or removing and reinstalling items for refurbishment.

For the work described in this paper, an initial activity has been to identify what needed to be added or changed for a production simulation system, to be able to apply it to retrofitting activities and whether this could be accomplished in a feasible way.

The main differences in requirements can be summarized as:

- Repair work is usually completely controlled and managed by schedule. This is mainly due to the fact that typical maintenance activities are service oriented, i.e. they often do not follow the typical pattern found in production tasks, where a bill of material is used as input to produce some interim or final product, which is then used in follow-on tasks that depend on the availability of such interim products. Repair tasks in contrast do have logical constraints, but most time there is no relevant material flow between them.
- Retrofitting and modifications can constitute a mix of repair and production tasks. There is often a limited number of part/assembly oriented production tasks.
- Support for task types that are often neglected in production simulations like cleaning, ventilation, installation and removal of access paths, temporary setup of support structures and waste removal and disposal. Some task types need more detailed consideration like painting and surface treatment than is typically applied in new-building production scenarios, for example.
- To provide the desired information for LCA, tracking of LCA flow data is needed. This requires a considerable number of flow parameters for all machinery and facilities being used. The LCA flow data encompasses any kind of relevant flow of substances, energy or radiation consumed by or emitted from any active component being involved in a process. Table I and Table II show a set of sample properties that are applicable to common shipyard production activities, and that are additionally of general interest for LCA analysis.

Table I: Sample LCA Consumption Parameters

Parameter	Quantity
Power , Electrical (Alternating, 3-phase)	Energy
Power , Electrical (Alternating, 2-phase)	Energy
Power , Electrical (Direct Current)	Energy
Gas, Natural Gas	Mass

Parameter	Quantity
Gas, Pressurized Air	Mass
Gas, Acetylene	Mass
Gas, Hydrogen	Mass
Gas, Carbon Dioxide	Mass

Table II: Sample LCA Emission Parameters

Parameter	Quantity
Water Vapour	Mass
Gas, Carbon Dioxide	Mass
Gas, Ozone	Mass
Gas, Sulphur Dioxide	Mass
Gas, Nitrogen Oxides	Mass
Gas, Chlorine	Mass
Gas, Carbon Monoxide	Mass
Gas, Fluorine	Mass

LCA flows are handled as user-configurable attributes that are linked to production equipment, see Table I and Table II. All flows can be specified as rates (i.e. consumption per hour) or as levels of emission (e.g. noise, vibration). To configure the system, cross tables are used to assign parameters to equipment types. Once this configuration is complete, the user of the system can define specific consumption or emission rates for any of the applicable parameters, while also defining the details of a specific production equipment item. During simulation, these rates will be used to calculate actual prorated and accumulated values. The configuration can be done by using a simple spread sheet workbook as input, and can thus be easily modified and adjusted as shown in Fig. 4.

Input	AirConditioningEquipment	BeadlingMachine	Burner	CleaningEquipment	CuttingRobot	FrameBendingMachine	PaintingEquipment	PaintingRobot	PanelLine	Planer
Consumption, Power, Electrical (AC, 3-phase)	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
Consumption, Power, Electrical (AC, 2-phase)	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x
Consumption, Power, Electrical (DC)			x	x						
Consumption, Gas, Natural Gas										
Consumption, Gas, Pressurized Air	x	x		x			x	x	x	
Consumption, Gas, Acetylene			x							x
Consumption, Gas, Hydrogen			x							x
Consumption, Gas, Carbon Dioxide			x							x
Consumption, Gas, Oxygen			x							x
Consumption, Gas, Nitrogen			x	x						x
Consumption, Gas, Helium			x							x
Consumption, Gas, Argon			x							x
Consumption, Fluid, Gasoil	x									

Fig. 4: Equipment/LCA flow cross table

Once LCA flow data is defined, the simulation system can provide tracking data for any of these parameters. In this context, it is also important to note that the underlying system is capable of describing and maintaining multiple states for any given piece of equipment. The simplest (and default) case would be an ON and an OFF state, which corresponds to all flows pertaining to that machine to be zero or the defined maximum rate. However, frequently used machines do operate in one of several active states. By being able to define flow rates for every state separately, per-task operating conditions will be reflected in the tracked data. Furthermore, it is possible to specify any equipment parameter either as a constant value, a stochastic distribution, tabular data (from which actual data points will be interpolated), or functions that may be defined based on other model parameters.

Fig. 5: Sample plasma burner process LCA model, generated with *GaBi (2012)*

Tracked data for any of these process parameters can then be interfaced to corresponding LCA models, ‘dragging’ specific consumption and emission values from the applied simulation into the LCA. These rates or values are then linked to specified model flows, allowing the LCA software to track all material, energy, and emission inputs and outputs, and allowing it to later analyse, summarise and distribute the results to various environmental impact categories. Fig. 5 shows a simplified LCA model of a typical shipyard process, which is represented as a flow diagram comprised of processes and flows. The basic processes are defined as to include linked results from the simulation.

5. LCA enabled simulation

To perform a simulation of a retrofitting project, a simulation model has to be established. Fig. 6 shows the required input and work flow to prepare, execute and evaluate for a simulation.

Some parts of this model are fairly static, while others need to be defined for each individual project. To prepare for retrofit simulations, the following initial setup steps are needed:

- Configuration of the LCA flows for all resources involved. This follows the principle as described in Section 4.
- Establishing a model of the shipyard and its facilities. This is a one-time activity, which will only require small scale modifications in due course when shipyard installations are upgraded or reconfigured. The model includes definition of facilities and equipment available for production, retrofitting or repair activities, and will be defined including their LCA flow parameters. Fig. 7 depicts an example layout of a shipyard with buildings and facilities shown in an aerial view on top of a map backdrop. The correct geographical arrangement allows precise definition of transport paths, for cases where the transport activities need to be included in the simulation.

- Definition of LCA flow data is essential for being able to use simulation results in a life cycle assessment activity. Gathering detailed data of this kind can be challenging. First logical sources of information are equipment data sheets, which will often provide at least fundamental data like power consumption. Fortunately, various additional information sources exist - like the *ecoinvent* database, *Frischknecht (2005)*. These LCA-oriented databases provide fairly complete data sets about flows pertaining to a broad range of industrial processes. The information can be directly transferred into the simulation model; in fact, a future development of the system may include direct online access to such data. As part of our development project a direct connection to the ERLCA-DB (Eco-REFITec LCA-Database) is being developed in parallel, *Fercu (2012)*. Fig. 8 shows an example of an equipment definition that includes some LCA flow rates.

Fig. 6: Simulation work flow

Fig. 7: Shipyards model in a geographic view

Fig. 8: Sample facility flow rate definition

Once the shipyard model has been created, individual retrofitting projects can be prepared for simulation. For each project the following actions need to be carried out:

- Modification/addition of equipment that is temporarily used for purposes of the project, e.g. rented equipment.
- Definition of the intended retrofit schedule: it may be imported from an existing scheduling or planning system like MS Project, or it may be created in the scheduling definition component of the system. As part of the schedule definition, some details are required to specify the work content of the individual tasks. For retrofitting activities this is usually straightforward, since this information is directly available for the project specification or offer description documents. Fig. 9 shows an example of an *activity description* that incorporates details about the task to be simulated – in this case a painting specification.

Fig. 9: Sample schedule definition

- Applicable shift definitions: used to model the availability of resources. Shift schedule definitions are applicable to selected work places and work stations or resource pools to operate in an area or group of facilities.
- Definition of all required material resources: in case of the installation of new components, the replacement of existing components or addition/modification of the ship structure, the corresponding bill of material needs to be imported or defined. This can be used to control the effects of the supply chain, e.g. by specified expected availability, probability of delays, etc. If this is not in focus, instant availability can be assumed instead.
- Setting of simulation parameters: to carry out the actual simulation run, a scenario needs to be defined, enumerating all model components to be included, the stimuli being used to initiate the simulation, and any further controlling parameters. Such parameters typically include data such as the simulated start date, and whether various resource limits shall be applied. The selection of the model entities available aid in the configuration and control the simulation goals.
- Execution of simulation: this is obviously the key step to calculate results. The model will be loaded and the simulation carried out by starting the simulation engine. The actual execution times depend on the complexity of the problem being investigated. For typical retrofitting cases, this has shown to be negligible. All results are stored in a database for further evaluation.
- Preparation of reports, analysis of results: evaluation can be carried out instantly. Any tracked parameter (including those related to LCA flows) can be selected and visualised or tabulated in various ways.
- Transfer of flow data into the Ship LCA software: once the simulation results have been reviewed, all LCA flow data can be transferred to the ship LCA tool.

6. Sample cases

The system is being applied to several use cases to evaluate the best option for carrying the intended work. Some samples include:

- Application of a new paint system to the underwater hull surface to reduce resistance and consequentially fuel consumption.
- Comparative study of innovative abrasive processes being used for cleaning the underwater hull surface.
- Installation of a ballast water treatment system. This includes comparison of the retrofitting requirements of the different systems being offered.
- Installation of an exhaust SO_x scrubber system.

Fig. 10: Sample operating data and LCA flow results

Fig. 10 shows some sample results from the simulation being carried out for the paint system case, including a high pressure water blasting process being applied during the cleaning. The sampled data include overall power consumption, as well as fresh water consumption, which is one of the “hidden” factors for this case.

7. Conclusions

A novel application of simulation to the area of retrofitting has been herein proposed. At the same time, features to generate simulation results that can be directly fed into a life cycle assessment task have been introduced. An important feature is that the simulation will be carried out for a specific shipyard setup and an individual retrofitting schedule, such that all influencing factors will be considered. This is very helpful when trying to decide ahead a planned project. This last applies to eco-innovative projects such as the installation of ballast water treatment systems, exhaust scrubbing systems, or propulsion energy reduction techniques, in which many details will depend on the actual ship, the shipyard, and/or the system being chosen, and will ultimately drive the decision.

Input to the system is straightforward, as it is completely based on the available schedule and job specification data. LCA flow rate data input is one of the more demanding activities; however, these are shown to be supported by utilising existing LCA databases.

LCA model generation and appraisal, allows for the computing of historical and forecasted potential environmental impacts, with the possibility of also linking these results to economic factors. This in turn offers decision makers a *holistic* evaluation of a specific option or model (e.g. a specific case ship), or of an array of different alternatives (e.g. different ballast water treatment systems).

A common concern with simulation projects is the effort to establish a validated model, with sufficient level of detail. It has been demonstrated that with a well-adjusted suite of tools, this issue can be very well mitigated. Furthermore, in the retrofitting domain the required shipyard model is of reduced complexity compared to new-building projects, and it only needs to be set up once for a shipyard. Minor modifications are added on demand, like for rental equipment that is temporarily used. The reduced model generation effort paves the way towards comparative studies and hypothetical what-if analyses, which ultimately expand decision space.

Output from the system includes information about production data (utilisation, schedule, resources and cost), as well as LCA flow data that can be used directly in the long-term product LCA, to assess feasibility of a planned retrofitting measure.

Acknowledgements

Work described in this paper has been supported with funding from the 7th Framework Programme of the European Commission under Grant Agreement FP7-SST-2010-RTD-1, CP-266268. The authors also wish to thank the partners of the Eco-REFITec Project, (Eco innovative refitting technologies and processes for shipbuilding industry promoted by European Repair Shipyards) for their input and support.

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An On-board Expert System for Damage Control Decision Support

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Abstract

A survey of the use of advanced applications to improve shipboard security and to assist crew members in the effective handling of dangerous events and accidents is given. A knowledge-based decision support system (DSS) integrated within a Damage Control System (DCS) is described. The DCS project resulted from a collaborative effort between Apphia and Avio for the development of innovative damage control systems for navies. The DSS uses a hybrid design and runtime knowledge model to assist damage control operators supporting damage identification, action scheduling and system re-configuration. A firefighting scenario as illustrative application and an evaluation of benefits in terms of times reduction for limiting the damage are reported.

1. Introduction

Aboard most ships, the safety is still a mostly manual and manpower-intensive function and more automatic and effective systems are thus required to assist the crew in taking corrective actions, *Runnerstrom (2003)*. Technologies such as video processing and visualization, expert systems, platform management, simulators, and human-system interfaces can be integrated into a more complex architecture for shipboard safety control. In the navy context, the experience of the damage control (DC) officer on-board a navy ship is crucial in the management of DC situations. Immediate damage containment and long-term consequences may conflict. Quick decisions have to be made often under stressful conditions, based on incomplete information, for complex technical systems, *Bertram (2000)*. Thus, a Damage Control System (DCS) can assure the timely and informed application of men and equipment in scenarios such as fire or flooding, violation of the ship closure state, threats to essential equipment, ventilation close down, and atomic/biological/chemical issues. DCSs are also relevant for emergency training and damage instructor assistance purposes, *Bulitko and Wilkins (1999)*, *Peters et al. (2004)*.

The field of expert and decision support systems can provide a relevant contribution to design more performing DCSs. However, the study of expert systems and DSS in navy contexts has mostly focused on the design process whereas a very limited number of contributions have addressed the implementation of integrated systems to ensure the safety and operational stability of modern ships. For a brief history on Damage Control and Decision Support Systems see *Calabrese et al. (2012)*, *Ostuni et al. (2012)*.

A knowledge-based decision support system (DSS) is described in this paper; it is integrated within the DCS designed for the operating needs of a national navy. Starting from the analysis of the typical damage control process the identification of a model of knowledge acquisition and reuse in damage management scenarios has been executed. The tool provides a graphical information-retrieval and equipment-control dashboard that gives damage crew the ability to handle various types of damage control situations.

2. Overview of the innovative DCS

The Damage Control System project was a collaborative effort between Apphia s.r.l., www.apphia.it, and Avio SpA, www.aviogroup.com, for the development of innovative damage control systems for navies. Apphia is an Italian engineering company specializing in research and development in many areas of intervention, such control systems and automation, innovative manufacturing and engineering

analysis. In particular Apphia has extensive experience in the design and implementation of advanced automation and simulation in the shipbuilding industry and collaborates with Avio in this field. Avio is a world leader in the design, development and manufacturing of aerospace propulsion components and systems for both for civil and military aircraft and it operates in the marine industry for the provision of control, automation and propulsion systems and components.

The DCS is a supervisor system embedded in the Integrated Platform Management System (IPMS), developed by Avio Spa, which is a distributed hardware architecture used for real-time monitoring of the ship propulsion, mechanical, electrical, auxiliary and damage control systems. Monitored components include gearboxes, pitch propellers, power generation sets, power distribution switchboards, electrical distribution centers, fire pumps, systems for heating, ventilation, air conditioning, chilled water, and so forth.

The IPMS controls all the onboard equipment, excluding weapons/sensors (for military ships) and the ship’s communication and navigation equipment. The general IPMS architecture comprises Multi-Function Consoles (MFCs) and Remote Terminal Units (RTUs). MFCs are mostly laptops and workstations providing the human-machine interface for the operators at various shipboard locations whereas RTUs are used for data acquisition and control and they are connected to sensors and actuators (e.g. FDS – fire detection sensors, pumps, fans). The IPMS is endowed with a runtime application allowing monitoring the whole ship from each MFC.

Fig.1 shows the architecture of the IPMS and the basic interface of the DCS. Whereas the IPMS represents the hardware backbone for damage control operations, the DCS is the software platform configured within the IPMS with functions such as monitoring of ship subsystems, longitudinal, planar and isometric views, Tiled Layered Graphics (TLGs) approach (for automatic de-cluttering and display of complex information), casualty management, support to manage emergency states, event log and report, and compartment monitoring.

Fig.1: IPMS hardware architecture and main DCS interface

These functionalities are integrated into four modules:

- (1) Damage Control Management System (DCMS) which enables to automatically acquire all the relevant ship safety and other data needed to handle damages, display data to the operator in an optimized way, handle alarms, and rapidly share/communicate the information between the different MFCs, *Mancarella et al. (2011)*;

- (2) On Board Stability Software (OBSS) to obtain and visualize ship stability data and calculate the stability parameters, *Calabrese et al. (2012)*;
- (3) Closed Circuit TV (CCTV) which activates cameras to monitor real-time the compartments of the ship;
- (4) Decision Support System (DSS), to assist the damage control officer in case of critical events by indicating the most suitable procedures to handle the specific situation.

Fig.2: Components of the DCS

Starting from a main window and navigating within the system by means of guided paths and hyperlinks the operator can access each function of the four modules using an unique organized interactive interface.

For developing the DSS, we first studied the decision/action process of the damage control operator onboard. We have then identified the information flows at the basis of decisions as actions and developed the four core components of the DSS, *Bonczek et al. (1981)*, i.e. the knowledge system (sources of data and information), the language system (input format), the presentation system (interface and layout) and the problem processing system (software engine). Outputs of our work are reported in the next section.

3. DSS: analysis and features

The damage control officer (DCO) is usually supported by a damage control assistant (DCA) and a team in charge of maintaining situational awareness and taking actions to prevent injury to personnel, damage to ship systems, or loss of the ship as well. The DSS has a direct impact on the decision making process and actions of these actors. A generic decision making flow includes the recognition of the problem, the listing of objectives, the perception of environment and constraints, the listing of options, the decision analysis and the action plan, *Arbel and Tong (1982)*. In the damage control perspective, these steps are specifically translated in a flow.

Fig.3: Decision and action flow of damage control operator

The operator takes critical decisions related with what to do, what to do first, how to undertake actions, and in which order undertake actions throughout five steps, Fig.3. Through the damage control platform the operator is able to acquire situational awareness of damage (step one) and identify where the damage is located and which is its extent (step two). Next, the operator can start a set of preliminary actions aimed to contain and control the effects of damage (step three) and activate the damage control systems and crew to eliminate the causes of emergency and prevent further issues (step four).

Finally, the operator reconfigures the navy and control systems after that the problem has been completely solved (step five).

Four major requirements to drive the design of the DSS have been identified:

- (1) monitor all damage control status and operations at any time and from each control position onboard;
- (2) support damage control operations by acquiring all ship's security relevant data;
- (3) allow efficient presentations of information to the damage control operator;
- (4) provide decision aids, actions, procedural checklists and alarms when handling emergency situations.

A DSS is a special system for decision support which is able to recommend actions based on specialized problem-solving expertise stored as facts, rules, procedures, or in similar structures. We first designed the knowledge model underlying the system. Basic knowledge to support the decisions and actions of the damage control crew derives from two main sources:

- (1) design time knowledge sources, which include the ship and damage control data available at the design of the system; and
- (2) run time knowledge, including damage control data received "in process" through the damage control equipment.

Design time knowledge was obtained from the ship structure and engineering data (e.g. ship layout and dimensions of compartments), navy/ship rules (e.g. operating and security management procedures) and damage control officer (e.g. engineering expertise, design suggestions, insights). Run-time knowledge is implemented in the system through damage system information (e.g. fire and flooding sensors connected with the RTUs) and shared communications among the damage control operators onboard (e.g. separated actions which have to be consolidated into a unique damage checklist).

Knowledge sources are integrated within the *kill card*, i.e. an information and operation support dashboard which groups logically all the information related to the ship equipment and security systems, provides predefined automatic control sequences to respond to specific casualty conditions, and allows the operator to rapidly (knowing and) executing the correct actions at the moment.

Fig.4: Model of the knowledge-based DSS for shipboard damage control

Since a damage generally originates in one specific compartment of the ship (and then it can propagate to other compartments), each compartment is associated to a dedicated kill card. The kill card is

the main element of the user interface and it allows a dynamic situational awareness of damage, damage localization and extent, preliminary counteractions, damage control systems and crew activation and reconfiguration. The DSS suggests therefore to the damage control operator what to do, what to do first, how to undertake actions, and in which order undertake actions in the different emergency situations which may happen onboard. DSS model is shown in Fig.4.

Two main components have been developed for the kill card function: the editor and the viewer. The editor allows to create a new card (with a preview function), modify or delete an existing card from the kill card database if/when basic requirements related to ship structure, rules and operating procedures should change (i.e. the design time knowledge sources). The viewer allows opening and visualizing an existing kill card generated through the editor. In order to retrieve a card, the operator has three options:

- (1) use a plan or isometric view of the ship to click on the description of a compartment;
- (2) choose a card from a purposeful kill card area by using a database tree structure (which describes the whole ship);
- (3) use a search function based on compartment names.

The damage control operator can also share the action list, i.e. score when response actions (e.g. in case of fire) have been started and/or completed and share this information to every MFC onboard. Finally, it is possible to reset changes by using a clear function and control the dynamic buttons of devices through a device window.

Fig.5: Kill card structure

The general format of a kill card (the “template”) is an empty format structured in text fields and buttons (for operating various devices) and it includes three sections or areas:

- (1) compartment identification area, showing critical information such as ship general data and compartment location;
- (2) summary area, with information related to ship and compartment sensors;

- (3) detail area, including several tables with information related to danger hazards, compartment views and video clips, firefighting installations, actions, ventilation control and status of devices.

The basic structure and content of a kill card template can be modified through a purposeful configurator. The editor, viewer and configurator components are operationalized by a software application available in every MFC of the ship, allowing damage control operators to be always in possession of the information pertinent to the emergency situation managed at the moment. The kill card “uses” the design information (such as compartments layout and dimensions, ship security management procedures, and damage control officer insights) and run time knowledge (like system status, status of actuators and shared information on actions taken by different operators), to provide expert assistance to the damage control crew, Fig.6.

Fig.6: Kill card example.

We implemented the DSS as a Microsoft Windows Environment developed in Visual Studio 2008 and using at least Windows XP as operating system. We used C# as programming language as it presents the power of C++ and the slickness of Visual Basic. Besides, the language supports the introduction of XML comments which can turn into documentation. The comments are placed into XML format and can then be used as documentation which can include example code, parameters, and references to other topics.

All the information contained in every kill card and all the changes made on them are stored in a database using a XML file whose name corresponds to the ship compartment name (e.g. wardroom, engine room).

The damage control operator can visualize actions from a predefined list and “check off”, Fig.7, when these actions have been successfully completed. The system also allows to link kill cards of different compartments when the effects of damage propagate into different ship rooms. In this way, it is possible to use the sensors and devices available in more compartments, identify priority areas, execute shared actions, and so forth.

All the information are logged in manner to create a repository in which the management of a particular damage scenario is recorded with the indication on what were the actions executed to solve it. This

functionality generates an expert system because after a damage event it is possible to turn into the kill card of a compartment and, using the configurator, to change the configuration of actions to be executed using the knowledge of previous events. This functionality is provided to each operator onboard, after authorization of DCO, and using a user-friendly system. This update is executed by one operator on one MFC and the system will automatically execute the update on all other MFCs using a method of security and assuring the uniformity of all information in all MFCs. The next section shows an example of use in presence of an event of fire and in which modality the system can provide its support to damage control operations.

5. Example of use: Fire event

An illustrative scenario in which a fire emergency onboard requires rapid actions to avoid serious injuries to personnel or damages to vital ship systems is here described. In this case, the damage control crew is involved in the following sequence of steps:

- (1) acquire awareness about a fire happened onboard;
- (2) identify where fire is located and which is its extent;
- (3) start a set of preliminary actions aimed to contain and control the effects of fire;
- (4) activate damage control systems and crew to eliminate causes of fire and prevent further damages;
- (5) reconfigure and restore the ship and damage control systems after fire.

The five steps are supported by the integrated functionalities allowed by the IPMS and the DCS of the ship. In particular, the DSS developed has a direct impact on steps 3 and 4. In the first step, the sensors installed in the compartment concerned with the fire transmit an alarm or warning message which is visible in the summary area of the kill card interface. The operator can thus immediately become aware of the emergency. In the second step, the system allows the operator to visualize which compartment is concerned and which is the seriousness of damage. Devices and sensors acquire quantitative measures (e.g. temperature, pressure, CO₂ level, etc.) which are sent to the system for real-time damage evaluation. After that, the operator can start a set of preliminary actions (step 3) aimed to contain and control the effects of fire. At this purpose, the operator can access the kill card database to retrieve the specific kill card of the compartment concerned with the fire. In fact, the list of actions suggested by the DSS (on the basis of the knowledge model underlying the system) will be indicated into the kill card to solve the problem.

An example of action list in case of fire is the following, Fig.7:

- (1) close ventilation;
- (2) preserve watertight integrity;
- (3) maintain vital systems;
- (4) isolate, prevent, extinguish, combat and remove the effects of fire;
- (5) facilitate the care of personnel casualties; and
- (6) make rapid repairs to the ship's structure and equipment.

The operator can then activate the damage control systems and crew (step 4) to prevent further damage and limit current issues.

For example, the operator can monitor the status of devices and control remotely pumps and fans which are present at the fire scene. Then, it is possible to execute the secondary action plan with the purpose to completely extinguish the fire. Each information and the indication of check off on an action executed by one operator on a particular MFC are automatically shared by the system. So all operators in each console onboard know what is happening in each time instant. Information sharing, which before was based on exchange of documents, physical meetings and phone calls, is now supported into DSS by the direct communication among the Multi-Function Consoles (MFCs) on board.

Fig.7: Kill card windows in presence of fire

When the alarm status is over, the operator can then reconfigure and restore the ship and damage control systems. Through the remote control functionalities of the DSS, the sensors and devices, as well as all the action lists turned on can be reset and made ready in case of a new emergency. The fire-fighting case, along with other damage management scenarios, was created to test the behavior of the crew and the system through the damage management process.

For validation of the DSS, we used indeed a combination of technical, empirical and subjective methods, *Adelman (1992)*, *Borenstein (1998)*, *Papamichail and French (2005)*. We have also measured the benefits allowed by the DSS in terms of awareness time, action time, crew need and action costs. The use of kill cards connected with sensors and cameras allows to reduce situational awareness time to few seconds (and less than 1 min) needed by the operator to visualize the automatic warning message on the screen. The damage action time can be decreased from 45 to about 15 min, as the operator can now immediately start a set of corrective actions directly from the remote terminal unit and there is no need to be physically present at the damage site. Navigability of the tool is supported by the use of hyperlinks and function navigation trees. The system allows some multimedia features with audio and video signals directly coming from ship compartments. Finally, the system also supports interoperability as the IPMS, the modules of the DCS and the DSS are fully integrated and can be customized based on user needs and requirements.

6. Conclusion

We have presented a knowledge based DSS to help the operator onboard into the decision making process and sequence of actions required to the damage control in case of emergency. The system uses design time and run time knowledge sources and it allows the operator to have complete information about the ship condition, i.e. the knowledge of the current condition in event of damage in all ship areas by dedicated displays. By the navigability of the system, multimedia tools, the interoperability with other DCS applications, it is possible to execute all operations for damage monitoring and control having a more effective information sharing.

The log of all information allows to verify the history of the various events and to improve the action plan verifying the used procedure and the related time of execution, avoiding the possibility to repeat actions not necessary or to modify the sequence of actions. In this sense, the DSS represents an expert system configurable directly by the final users, i.e. the operators onboard, using an user-friendly interface and without the necessity to modify the software, can update in any moment the information on the base of the best knowledge of the ship system.

The rapid identification of the emergency and the corrective actions to be executed to prevent and limit the damage provide a reduction of response time and costs and improve the ship management. The use of the application developed could be enlarged to other contexts in which the monitoring of risky events is crucial (e.g. building sites, other energy production sites).

New improvements are in progress for the extension of the DSS application for training purposes, and in particular for on-the-job training of damage crew members. The onboard training system of the ship could be indeed used to simulate events in normal ship operation as well as in degraded conditions using the same interface. The adoption of enhanced reality and 3D technologies could represent a second area of development to obtain always faster and more effective actions.

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An Integrated Approach to Style Definition in Early Stage Design

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Abstract

The general arrangement of a ship significantly impacts overall characteristics, but research into and use of modern computer methods in developing and exploring general arrangements in preliminary ship design has lagged behind other fields such as hydrodynamics. A collaborative project between three institutions aims to develop new approaches for exploring this key aspect of ship design at an early stage. An outline approach to this problem has been developed which makes use of the concept of “style” as a mechanism for storing and applying information and making design decisions.

1. Introduction

Many papers have been published on preliminary ship design, however generally they are either describing a specific ship design or talking in general about different ways in which ships may be designed. With notable exceptions, *Andrews (1981,1986,2003)*, *Nick and Parsons 2007*, *van Oers 2011*), ship architecture has been rarely highlighted in such papers. The question of how ship architecture is defined as part of the evolution of a new ship design needs to be researched if we are to move forward in creating new, novel, more complex vessels. There is a growing awareness of both the importance and practicality of developing methods to effectively utilise ubiquitous desktop computers and computer-aided design tools in arrangement design. This is reflected by the inclusion of a dedicated “Design for Layout” state-of-the-Aat report in *Andrews et al. (2012)*, whereas in *Basu (1997)* layout was just a sub-section to a broader state-of-the-art report.

2. NICOP Preliminary Ship Design General Arrangements Project

The University College London (UCL), Delft University of Technology (TU Delft) and the University of Michigan (UofM) are currently engaged in collaborative research into Preliminary Ship Design General Arrangements. This joint five year project is sponsored by the US Navy Office of Naval Research and involves academics, PhD students and post-doctoral researchers. The project has two broad aims; to investigate and improve methods for generating general arrangements in preliminary ship design, and to develop and demonstrate collaborative working between widely separated institutions using e-collaboration tools. Work so far in pursuit of the first aim has concentrated on gaining an understanding of previous research in this area, and the development of a potential approach to using the three institutions design methods together. In support of the second aim, the project partners have made extensive use of HD video conferencing and on-line content sharing and collaboration tools to aid the ongoing discussion and ideation in this area of research.

3. Architectural Approaches in Concept Ship Design

An early description of a 'Functional Arrangement Design' was due to *Barry (1961)*, describing both large passenger ship conversions to troop ships and on cruiser gun disposition, while providing insights relevant to current ship design practice. Barry proposed the juxtaposition of drafting tables, so that those designers working up the upper decks and superstructure could better interface with the outboard profile designer, while those responsible for the lower deck arrangements interfaced with the inboard profile design. This emphasized the importance of the general arrangement in the design development. With the move to computerisation of the ship design process, manual general

arrangement procedures were still adopted and the computer used to present compartment attributes and to manage the auditing process, *Carlson and Cebulski (1974), Holmes (1981)*.

General Arrangement design has continued to be a constrained process, with decisions which constrain the downstream architectural design being made at the preliminary or concept stage, where there is an apparently unavoidable and insufficient consideration of the consequences of the constraints being imposed on the layout. These constraints inhibit the possibility of radical re-arrangement of the architecture of the ship.

3.1. The Importance of Architecture and Arrangements in Preliminary Ship Design

Brown (1987) emphasized how, for a frigate and similar combatant vessels, the key to the internal layout is the design of the upper or weatherdeck disposition of weapons, helicopter arrangements, radars, communications, bridge, boats, seamanship features, machinery uptakes and downtakes, and the access over the deck and into the ship and superstructure. Fig. 1 shows *Andrews' (2003)* updated version of *Brown's* frigate configuration.

Fig. 1: Frigate layout considerations, updated by *Andrews (2003)* from *Brown (1987)*

Levander (2003) described how the physical description of a passenger, cruise or ferry ship can only be produced by commencing with the arrangement of the public spaces and cabins. Similarly the configuration of certain large naval vessels, such as aircraft carriers and amphibious warfare vessels, are driven by the arrangement of a limited set of spaces, such as the hangar and flight deck or the well dock and vehicles decks. *Honnor and Andrews (1981)* in describing the *Invincible* class aircraft carriers revealed the primary spatial interactions that drove the design as being the vertical relationships between spaces in the hull (stores, machinery, accommodation) and the aviation facilities on the upper decks (hangar and flight deck).

In the case of displacement-borne multi-hulled configurations the architectural design is highly significant. Their initial sizing is not constrained by the relatively narrow range of parameters typical of monohulls. Instead their hullform configuration can add additional arrangement possibilities, relationships and constraints that must be considered, both in terms of overall configuration and internal arrangement, discussed in more detail by *Andrews (2003)*.

3.2. Style in Preliminary Ship Design

“Style” was explicitly incorporated as a characteristic of a ship design by *Brown and Andrews (1981)* as the fifth “S” in their “S⁵”, the others being Speed, Seakeeping, Stability, and Strength. However the exact nature of style, as a type of information or design characteristic, that set it apart from other domains such as speed or structural strength, was not so clear. We have engaged in lengthy discussions on this subject and a tentative definition has emerged. We propose that the design issues

generally grouped under style, see e.g. *Andrews (2012a)*, are conceptually different not because they are unsuited to mathematical analysis (the same was once true of seakeeping or vibration analysis, but simulation techniques are increasingly being applied in these areas, *Fach and Bertram (2009)*) but because style is a cross-cutting concept, where one decision explicitly influences a wide range of solution areas. Stylistic information also has the key property of being able to accommodate uncertainty, containing both “hard” knowledge (such as structural standards) and “soft” knowledge (guidance on layout) that can be conceptually connected or grouped. In addition, style may also reflect the weighting factors chosen for multiple criteria when selecting the “best” design from a larger set, e.g. in an optimisation study.

An example of style would be survivability in naval ships. A decision on the level of survivability can influence a wide range of overall and detailed design features, such as the choice of signatures and defensive systems (to prevent a hit) the number and spacing of bulkheads (to resist weapon effects and flooding), arrangement of compartments (to protect vital spaces and aid in recovering) and structural details (to resist shock). This particular example also illustrates another feature of style as cross-cutting: it may better reflect the type of decisions required in preliminary ship design. It could be argued, however, that the difference between style and the other elements of “S⁵” is a matter of degree – i.e. all areas of ship design interact to some degree – and this is an area for further investigation in the methodological element of the joint research.

A further feature of style is that, if it can influence multiple areas of design, then it must itself represent the “grouping” of multiple sources of information in some way. Developing an ontology and taxonomy for style is seen to offer potential advantages to the practice of concept design, as it could allow for more efficient storage, retrieval and application of potentially disparate pieces of information or decisions. It is further proposed that this could be combined with the semi-automatic layout generation methods developed by two of the partners (University of Michigan and TU Delft) to allow the exploration of the impact of stylistic decisions in preliminary ship design.

Referring to the examples of ship architecture given above, it is considered that these can be seen as highly stylistic, in that decisions such as the number of masts on a frigate, or whether to have an enclosed hangar on an aircraft carrier are highly cross-cutting, with direct and indirect impacts on a wide range of overall and detail design features.

Style and computer-aided approaches that enable methods responsive to style related issues are seen to have potential at two levels. Firstly, the development of semi-automatic methods of generating sufficiently detailed designs based on a crude layout would allow the designer to focus on the overall style of the arrangement, which is seen to be very significant. Secondly, a style taxonomy could be used as a method for describing and storing the data and rules that permit the semi-automatic tools to develop more detailed layouts. The designer could then apply a wide range of changes to a design by selecting a different style (e.g. different survivability levels) and compare the results.

3.3. Developed Approaches to Architecture and Arrangements in Preliminary Ship Design

While the advent of computer aided design systems to naval ship design has led, specifically in US Navy practice, to formalised procedures for General Arrangement Design, the broad principles predate CAD technology in ship design, *Carlson and Fireman (1987)*. The need for the naval architect, at the formative preliminary design stages of a ship design, to have a clear understanding of the issues affecting configuration has become more important, because of the risk that the readily available design tools enable the novice ship designer at his/her personal computer all-too-readily to produce what appear to be worked up ship design solutions.

When considering layout evolution *Brown (1987)* discussed various numerical techniques under two categories, namely those intended to quantify the need for the layout feature and those used to analyse the performance of a stated function. Another approach proposed for looking at layout design is that of expert systems. These have been applied to layout design by *Helvacioğlu and Insel (2003)*, who

outline a container ship design tool where the ship is described at three levels of detail, with different rule bases and expert system engines applied to each level of decomposition. Current research at the University of Michigan, UCL, and TU Delft represent three of the novel approaches to architecture and arrangements in preliminary design. These three layout generation methods will be used in the integrated approach for style definition and represent just a few of the developed methods that can be integrated in the approach.

3.4. University of Michigan – Intelligent Ship Arrangements

The “Intelligent Ship Arrangement” (ISA), *Nick et al. (2006), Nick and Parsons (2007), Nick (2008), Parsons et al. (2008), Daniels and Parsons (2008), Daniels et al. (2009)*, focuses on arranging spaces into pre-defined structural zones. ISA was developed in the context of the U.S. Navy’s design process, which has influenced the scope, direction, and intended use of the method. ISA solves only the space arrangement part of the total ship design problem, taking as key inputs: 1) a ship hull including structural subdivisions, 2) a list of spaces to be arranged, and 3) a collection of relative and absolute space location constraints and space-centric geometric constraints. These inputs can be specified beforehand using automated or manual synthesis tools. As such, ISA focuses on the arrangement design within the fixed envelope of the hull and topside. The ISA method works with a two-step process. The first step allocates the list of spaces to the structural zones, Figs.2 and 3, of the vessel using a Hybrid Genetic Algorithm - Multi Agent System (HGA-MAS) that is driven by fuzzy constraints such as; “close to”, “separated from”, or “more-or-less square”.

Fig. 2: ISA structural zone definition, *Daniels et al. (2010)*

Fig. 3: ISA structural zone arrangement, *Parsons et al. (2008)*

The second step creates multiple geometric arrangement solutions for the allocation of the first step using spaces which have built in geometric constraints that address required area, aspect ratio, minimum dimensions, minimum segment width, and perimeter length. Resulting in a space arrangement of each structural zone according to their assigned topology, this follows the methodology that each space allocation can have multiple geometrical arrangements, while each geometrical arrangement can be traced back to one unique space allocation. Thus, multiple arrangements are needed for each allocation to find the “optimal” allocation/arrangement combination.

3.5. University College London – Design Building Block Approach

The UCL Design Building Block (DBB) developed over time, *Andrews (1981,1986,1987), Andrews and Dicks (1997)*, achieving its first working realisation, produced for the UK Ministry of Defence (MoD) in a classified version, for UK submarine design, *Andrews et al. (1996)*. The DRC has instigated an alliance with Graphics Research Corporation Limited (GRC) to incorporate the Design Building Block approach through the SURFCON facility being incorporated within GRC’s PARAMARINE Preliminary Ship Design System, *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*. PARAMARINE is an object-based naval architectural design package utilising the commercial ParaSolid modeller as its core, Fig.4. The screenshot shows the interactive graphical display of the design configuration: the “graphical pane” on the right, with a hierarchical navigation pane on the left and examples of numerical data and analysis (a resistance estimate in this case).

Fig. 4: Screenshot of PARAMARINE showing information in the Design Building Block objects

Each Design Building Block, as the fundamental component of the SURFCON approach, can be regarded as an object in the design space and as a "placeholder" or "folder" containing all the information relating to a particular function within the functional hierarchy. Design Building Blocks must be placed, or linked to parametric variables, by hand. In this key respect the DBBA differs from the approaches developed by UofM and TU Delft. The approach may be regarded as a CAD human-computer interaction paradigm, which permits a changes and enhancements to the process of preliminary ship design. Instead of a set of numerical steps or a mechanistic approach, where each aspect of the performance of the design is examined separately and sequentially, with any limited graphics being an outcome of the numeric balance, the integrated nature of the SURFCON implementation in PARMARINE allows the physical aspects of the design to be continuously appreciated by the designer from the commencement of the design.

3.6. Delft University of Technology – The Packing Approach

The packing-based ship design approach, *van Oers et al. (2008, 2009, 2010), van Oers (2011)*, is based on the design building block methodology. Systems are represented by building blocks which are placed into a positioning space by a packing-algorithm. Rules govern the packing process and manage the relations between systems, e.g., overlap, relative positions, global positions and connectivity. The sequence and initial positions of blocks can be varied, this creates a parametric ship descriptions which has a high degree of flexibility, e.g., it can handle large changes to the design, Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Example of a parametric model of a frigate with two different arrangements, *van Oers (2011)*

By coupling the packing-based parametric ship description to a search algorithm, and performance measuring tools, a large and diverse set of 3D ship descriptions can be automatically generated. The search algorithm ensures that the resulting designs adhere to a collection of non-negotiable requirements, e.g. float upright, sufficient initial and damage stability, and sufficient power generation capability. Negotiable requirements are dealt with after the design space of basically feasible designs has been created. Based on a set of design criteria the user can select designs, by drawing a selection box, from a scatter plot of the complete design set. By repeating this process, a down-selection is made until a suitable number of designs are left which can be used for further investigation. Fig.6 shows the complete workflow of the current packing-based ship design approach.

The first level comprises the explicit definition of requirements and network analysis of implicit constraints, coupled with the spatial representation of the components to define the input domain for the layout generation. The second level utilizes current well-developed early-stage ship arrangement tools for architectural layout generation. One method is a manually driven Design Building Block approach, *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*, while the other two methods are driven by evolutionary algorithms, *Daniels et al. (2009)*, *van Oers (2011)*. The third level of the design method proposed deals with the exploration and analysis of the generated designs, their associated performance analyses, and their architectural features. At this stage style can be considered among a range of metrics interpreting a larger body of knowledge and group information to elucidate the ship's personality. The concept of style exploration within a design space is captured in this proposed method through the coupled learning within levels and the knowledge gained through the information processed in the feedback loops from each level of the design process. Learning is associated with differences in the solution set to capture style and design changes.

5. Style Elucidation and Input Definition

The first level of the diagram displayed in Fig.7 highlights the style choices and generation of the inputs for the design generation method. Capturing the style is done through the explicit and implicit definition of the parameters that will drive the analysis of performance metrics, and their stylistic or architectural features. Definition of these constraints and requirements is not a trivial process as they are evolutionary throughout the stages of preliminary ship design and through to detail design. Constraints and requirements must be defined explicitly before network analysis or space cast analysis can be performed. Within this level, the relationships between spatial, geometric, and global location preferences are iteratively updated with each completed loop of the integrated approach. The relationships can be studied abstractly through a network analysis, and geometric locations through a space cast analysis. Insights gained during this definition phase must be used to guide the elucidation process towards the novel definition of style intent early in the design process.

Style at this level of the approach can enable the ill-defined knowledge early in ship design and capture the hard to quantify metrics as inputs. The definition of style will be carried through to Level 2 and Level 3 of the design method, coupling the performance metrics to the architectural layout generated for down selection of feasible designs. With proper definition of inputs and associated ship design style, the selected parameters for constraints and requirements will produce designs with higher integrity as the design stages progress.

5.1. Constraint Database Definition

The constraint database represents explicitly defined requirements from the owner, classification societies, and the style identification. This database is representative of design rules and best practices, and so is a direct function of designer experience. Style is driven in this stage of the design phase by how the constraints are defined to couple with resulting performance metrics of the design. Constraints may comprise of ship particulars, system selection, geometric characteristics, compartment adjacency and separation, and global location preferences. The constraint database is held higher than the network and space cast analysis as these variables must be defined before those analyses can be performed. While on the same level of the diagram of Fig.7, the constraint database is coupled to the network analysis and space cast analysis for continual learning and style elucidation as the database is updated and the initial metrics are determined for input into the architectural layout generation methods.

5.2. Network Analysis

Existing (semi-)automated early-stage arrangements tools, described in Section 3.3 are capable of generating feasible layouts, but lack the underlying knowledge regarding as to why layouts are configured as they are. Network based methods can be used as they rely on the relationships between shipboard elements and components. A network analysis expands the scope of the constraint database

and elucidates the underlying relationships that drive the designs. These relationships can be shown in a network representation to highlight constraint communities as shown in Fig.8. Network tools will be used to recognize and maintain the underlying relationship structure within early-stage ship design. Identifying these drivers in the design space provides indication of the underlying personality and style of the design. Through various iterations of the network analysis, the constraint database will be updated and the style of the design maintained as it transitions through the other levels of the proposed method and further into detailed design.

Fig. 8: Network representation of component relationships and communities, *Gillespie (2012)*

5.3. Space Cast Analysis

Space cast analysis is the underlying space projection system used in the ISA tool developed at the UofM and recently presented by *Daniels and Singer (2012)*. The algorithm for main spatial optimization follows a three stage pattern per generation; Allocation, Seeding, and Projection. Pairwise comparisons of geometrically allocated and seeded footprints are cycled through the algorithm to split the spaces and remove overlaps between them, resulting in a final iteration where no overlaps remain and a feasible spatial representation of the compartments is found, Fig. 9. This tool will be used in the proposed method to create geometric and spatial projections of the ship's compartment arrangement. To aid in the definition of style, the space cast analysis will present a spatial and geometric representation of constraints which can be used to provide inputs for level two of Fig.8. The generated spatial constraints will be constantly updated through the feedback of knowledge gained in the interpretation of style in the further stages of the design process.

Fig. 9: Space split lines (left) and final space projection footprints (right)

6. Design Layout Generation Methods

6.1. Arrangement Generation

The overall method shown in Fig.7 includes at Level 2 the generation of design layouts. The method contains two concepts of ship arrangements analysis; that carried out in Level 1, which examines the

arrangements at an abstracted level of definition that does not include a spatial model; and that in Level 3, which utilises a spatial model of the vessel and its internal arrangements to carry out further analysis. Level 2 is the process that connects these two by translating the abstracted definition of the arrangement and the design requirements into a spatial definition of the design and the internal arrangements.

The three project partners have each developed a method for generating design layouts; intelligent ship arrangements, the design building block approach and the packing approach. These have been outlined in Section 3.3. The overall method is intended to be flexible and to permit the use of different tools to address different design problems. There is also the possibility of combining these approaches to permit the capture and elucidation of different types of knowledge about the ship design under consideration.

6.2. Comparison of Existing Methods

Table 1 summarizes the main features of the three arrangement generation methods developed by the project partners. It is important to note that these features are a combination of those fundamental parts of each methodology, and of features that have evolved purely due to the current implementations in specific software form.

Table 1: Comparison of salient features of the three arrangements generation methods

Item	ISA	DBBA	Packing
Layout generation	Hybrid Genetic Algorithm - Multi Agent System	Manual	Packing algorithm and genetic algorithm
Optimisation	Fuzzy optimisation	None / manual	None / custom
Exploration of solution space	Low	Medium	High
Incorporation of uncertainty	Mathematical	Procedural	Mathematical
Integration with data libraries	Yes	No	Yes
Hullform and subdivision	Fixed	Flexible	Flexible
Flexibility in geometry	Partially	Yes	Partially
Interactivity	High (Constraints Database)	High	Medium
Number of variants	Low	Low	High
Design selection	Integral	Integral	Post processing

7. Design Exploration and Feedback of Knowledge

The third level of Fig.7 deals with the exploration and analysis of the generated designs, their performance metrics, and their stylistic or architectural features. However, the proper analysis of a large set of semi-automatically generated designs is not trivial. The relations between requirements and the generated design solutions are likely to become apparent only during design evolution where consequences of design decisions can be studied. The insights gained during this exploratory phase must be used to guide the elucidation process towards solutions of interest. This requires a novel and interactive approach to design exploration, including feedback of knowledge. Current research at TU Delft focuses on developing this interactive design exploration approach.

Colwell (1988), Nixon (2006), van Oers et al. (2008), Vasudevan (2008), McDonald (2010), van Oers (2011) include some examples of design exploration approaches intended for the preliminary design stage. However none of these combine a fully architectural synthesis tool with an interactive design

exploration approach which should include feedback of captured insights with respect to the relations between requirement and design solutions. For configuration driven designs, e.g. a naval combatant, where the stylistic architectural design decisions greatly influence a design's performance, this lack of architectural synthesis within design exploration is currently a gap.

Within the proposed approach a designer can interactively explore the design space to gain insight in the relationship between requirements and the design. These insights are then used to steer the process described in Fig.7, preferably towards promising high performance solutions. This interactive approach to design exploration would reduce the "black-box" nature of many preliminary optimisation-based ship design tools.

7.1. Gaining Insights

We believe that reducing the "black-box" nature of tools during early stage design is essential if the manner in which the design and its requirements emerge and interact is to be understood. This insight, which is gained during design exploration itself, is necessary to make informed decisions in the early stage design process. In order to gain this insight for proper requirements elucidation, *Andrews (2012b)*, a few necessary aspects are required:

1. Linking requirements to design solutions, i.e. given a set of requirements what do my solutions look like, and vice-versa;
2. Identify which requirements might conflict and when, i.e. illustrate the degree with which conflicts between requirements can be avoided, and if this proves impossible, to provide early feedback to stakeholders about their existence;
3. Identify why requirements conflict, i.e. identify which requirements are bounding the design space for a given set of requirements. This should give valuable information about which requirements are "critical" and thus driving the design.

To achieve these three aspects it is necessary to visualize both the numerical and stylistic architectural characteristics of designs. The architectural characteristics represent design options such as; type of systems, global/relative positions of systems, hull type and arrangement, etc. Numerical characteristics can represent performance metrics or ship characteristics such as; GM, range, displacement, etc.

7.1.1. Visualizing Numerical Characteristics

As a starting point for visualising numerical characteristics, familiar 2D scatter plots can be used. Fig.10 displays such a scatter plot of a large set of designs. Each point in the scatter represents a design solution generated by the architectural synthesis tools from Section 3.3. In this case the resulting design space is bounded by the constraints on length and beam and by a boundary where the main dimensions of the design are too small to include all its systems, e.g. it can no longer be feasibly "arranged".

By using the underlying performance characteristics of each design point, it is possible to identify bounds for specific criteria (or derived requirements), Figs.10 and 11. Beyond these bounds no designs exist which comply to the criteria set by the bound, i.e. the bound represents the extent of the feasible area for that specific criteria or requirement. The area within the bound is referred to as the "possible area of improvement", i.e. designs in this area may improve the criteria or requirement. The bounds are found by identifying which designs comply with a criteria or requirement, and then finding the extent of this "cloud" of designs. As a last step the direction of the bound is plotted using arrows.

By visualizing the requirement boundaries it is possible to identify areas where conflicts between requirements exist, e.g. there is a possible compromise of one or more requirements if designs in this area are preferred. In addition an area may arise where possibly all the requirements are met, Fig. 11. Such an area could represent the area of minimal compromise between the current set of criteria and

requirements, i.e. outside of this area there will always be a compromise with one or more of the current requirements. Studying these boundaries would give insight into possible conflicts between requirements and where they might be avoided. If a design meets all the requirements, but is located close to one or more of the boundaries, those particular requirements will be “driving” the design. To conclude, the insights which may be gained from studying such a design space plot and the criteria/requirement bounds are:

- **Conflicting requirements.** These are visualized by comparing directions of improvement for each required performance aspect. Opposing directions of improvement indicate that, depending on the chosen criteria and design solutions, a trade-off must be made.
- **Compromise areas.** These are the different areas resulting from the requirement boundaries. Depending on the position within the design space, it is possible to identify if a compromise between one or more required performance characteristics is likely.
- **Area of minimal compromise.** Depending on the required performances, there might be an area of minimal compromise. Here possibly all requirements are met and no compromise has to be made. It might even be possible to have a higher performance.
- **Design drivers.** Designs which lie on or near a requirement boundary are driven by that particular performance aspect, i.e., the requirement has become critical for that design. Slight modifications might result in the design not meeting this requirement.

Fig. 10: Multiple requirement bounds including the direction of improvements

Fig. 11: Area of minimal or no compromise between requirements, where preferred designs may be expected

7.1.2. Visualizing Architectural Characteristics

So far the architectural aspects of the set of given designs have been neglected; this section explains how similar 2D scatter plots can help in visualizing architectural features and considerations. The methodology is based on the 2D interactive selection approach developed by *van Oers et al. (2008)*.

Fig. 12: Example of a bridge position preference applied using selection approach, *van Oers (2011)*

In this approach 2D scatter plots are used to plot system positions with respect to a reference point on the hull. A user can apply preferences and criteria by interactively drawing a polygon surrounding the relevant system positions, Fig.12. By repeating these steps a down-selection in a large set of designs can be made based on a set of architectural features of the designs, e.g. the topside arrangement of weapon and communication systems.

7.1.3. Linking Architectural and Numerical Features

The methods described in the above sections allow the naval architect to interactively explore both numerical and architectural features. By linking these two methods mutual interaction between both numerical and architectural features can be explored using the following steps:

1. Define numerical performance requirements;
2. Show system positions of high performance designs;
3. Apply architectural preferences, e.g., topside layout;
4. Re-plot high performance designs which comply with architectural preferences.

Alternatively, the user may start with applying architectural preferences and explore the consequences on performance requirements. Fig.13 shows the results of the above steps for a simple frigate test-case.

Fig.13: Linking architectural preferences (right) to performance requirements (left). The blue designs (left) meet the required performance levels while the highlighted red designs also meet the architectural choices (right).

7.2. Feedback of Gained Insight

To further steer the elucidation process, it is necessary to feedback the insights gained from design exploration to generate new high performance preferred designs. With the information now available to the naval architect the subsequent elucidation process can be steered with the followings steps:

1. Minimal compromise. By focussing on the generation of new designs to the expected high performance area of the design space;
2. Requirements. The introduction of additional requirements while knowing which requirements are or may become critical. Requirements might need to change, shift or broaden the area of interest;
3. Architectural and stylistic features. These can control the search for new designs with respect to architectural preferences, e.g. with system positioning constraints;
4. Interactions. These can highlight further interactions between new performance aspects and architectural stylistic features;
5. Revisit. Earlier design decision must be revisited if consequences are undesirable.

These steps should allow the naval architect to identify and act upon emerging interrelationships and possible conflicts between requirements and design. These conflicts can then be avoided within the interactive approach by exploring alternative design options and/or by altering the performance requirements. If the conflict cannot be avoided, it can be communicated to the stakeholders in an informed discussion, as part of the requirements elucidation process.

8. Implementing the Proposed Approach

The approach is flexible and extensible in that it can be entered at several points, and further tools can be added to incorporate analysis and exploration. This means that there are several ways in which the approach could be implemented in software form. These range from a full integration of the tools into a single software system to a wider methodological study on how the tools and philosophies can be used in tackling design problems with little software integration. A single unified software tool is considered undesirable, as it could complicate future research by the three partners and it is envisioned that it would be difficult to develop a single tool which allowed flexible entry into the process at multiple points, rather than being built around a fixed design process.

The approach that is being adopted is a mix of software development and methodological studies with the aim of producing a suite of software tools with the ability to communicate and transfer data. These will then be used in the exploration and development of the overall method and more detailed procedures. Three areas of software development have been identified so far:

- Design research developments in the core software tools. These are seen to be changes and enhancements to the software to incorporate new methodological concepts;
- Design research developments using new software tools. In some cases, new methodological concepts may be better implemented using new software that interfaces with the existing tools. This is particularly the case for UCL, who use a third-party commercial tool in the form of PARAMARINE and so cannot edit the core software;
- Interface software developments to allow the software to transfer data. This can be accomplished by a combination of changes to the software and the development of external translator applications.

This collaborative project is now in its second year, with a planned duration of five years. The core developments will be undertaken by PhD students over the next three years, with post-doctoral studies intended to incorporate lessons learned and allow some of the questions usually raised in a PhD project to be addressed.

9. Conclusions

We are in the second year of a five year collaborative project to investigate the generation and exploration of general arrangements in preliminary ship design. Although the project is at too early a stage to draw definitive conclusions, some key points have emerged in the discussions so far.

Architecture is an important driver of the ship design: The overall architecture of a vessel can frequently be determined with relatively few features and determines most of the vessel's characteristics, but the architecture is frequently constrained and should be assessed while the design is still fluid. It is insufficient to assume a configuration and perform a purely numerical design synthesis during early stage design.

Style is a type of information relevant to and found at several levels of ship design: Style is proposed to be a grouping of information such that a given decision will primarily be cross-cutting, i.e., have impacts on multiple areas of design characteristics and performance. Style is proposed to be applicable at several levels in the design, from the overall arrangement to lower levels where a

stylistic choice may define the detailed arrangements. The use of design style and an associated ontology and taxonomy of style may allow semi-automated tools to be more closely aligned with the type of decisions made in early stage design.

Manual and automated methods for general arrangements design can be integrated: Several methods and toolsets exist for the development of arrangements in preliminary ship design and an outline approach has been proposed that integrates automated design development with manual exploration and decision making. The proposed approach allows the naval architect to identify and act upon emerging relationships and possible conflicts between requirements and solutions. Unavoidable conflicts and their consequences can be communicated to the stakeholders in an informed discussion. This could move design further towards a process of fuller exploration and better requirements elucidation.

Acknowledgements

Funding for the collaborative study in the Preliminary Ship Design General Arrangements NICOP project was provided by Ms. Kelly Cooper from the US Navy Office of Naval Research and is gratefully acknowledged.

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Streamlining the Steel Design Process by Linking Design and Rule Scantling Tools

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Abstract

Acceptable steel structure scantlings are mandatory during the early design process. For merchant ships the designer has to fulfill the structural constraints posed by the Classification rules. However, the tools provided by the Classification societies are not well adapted to the early design process where frequent changes to all ship design parameters are crucial. For this purpose, we have created a link between the ship design system E4 and the DNV rule scantling tool Nauticus Hull. The link allows for seamless exchange of scantlings information and quick assessment of Class conformity thereby reducing time spent on the steel iterations. The link is demonstrated through the application to a Ro-Pax design. For the scantlings the focus is on rough weight and strength estimation as well as assuring class conformity. A more flexible and comprehensive data exchange is achieved by working directly with the XML storage format of Nauticus Hull.

1. Introduction

1.1. Shipbuilding environment in Europe

The European shipbuilding industry has for several decades been under fierce competition from Asian shipbuilders. Despite substantially higher European labor costs many yards have managed to survive by focusing on innovation and custom-made designs together with their subcontractors.

We see that the building of so-called standard tonnage including Container vessels, tankers and bulkers is overtaken by Asian shipyards. However, the European yards are successful in the building of specialized vessel designs such as RoRo - vessels, cruise vessels and ferries, vessels for the offshore industry or megayachts.

The common denominator for these vessel types is, that normally just one ship or sometimes one or two sister ships are built. Consequently there are few cost saving effects in the engineering process and in the production compared to building the same design several times.

Especially for these custom-made designs, the objective is to know as much as possible about a planned ship project before contracts are signed. This is instrumental for a good prediction of the engineering, material and production costs and to deliver a good product on time and budget. The relation between cost level and time as well as the cost saving effect for series of one ship design is shown in Fig.1 developed by FSG, Krüger (2003).

The diagram was developed based on cost calculations for a series of RoRo vessels. Nearly 70% of the final cost level is fixed within the first 4 weeks while only a small cost is generated in this early stage. From this it follows that technical decisions made very early in the design phase have the greatest influence on the final solution and hence offer a very large potential for savings.

1.2. The early design phase

During this very early design process in modern ship design software such as E4 the hull form is developed and optimized with numerical flow analysis. The tanks, holds and the inner subdivision of a ship are modeled. On this basis the safety and stability rules as well as other class rules are checked. This leads to a first version of the general arrangement plan.

Fig. 1: Cost accounted and fixed over time for one RoRo ship and for a series of 6 sister ships

In steel design, a first idea of a preliminary midship section is developed in parallel. A possible workflow for the described design process is shown in Fig.2 by FSG, *Krüger (2003)*. Often the midship section is based on a similar vessel already built. The first scantlings of the steel plates and stiffeners are determined very roughly using experience from previous designs. Sometimes simple beam static calculations or when there is time, FEM calculations are done in addition. In order to gain confidence that the design will meet the safety and strength standards of the classing regulatory agency, the required rule scantlings need to be determined with the help of a rule scantling tool – such as Nauticus Hull - provided by classification societies. Based on these data and always combined with engineering experience the ship's weight and the material cost as well as production costs can be estimated. At the end of the design phase a media break to detail construction tools is done. The whole process relies on a constant and efficient data exchange between ship design and steel design to achieve a proper and good overall design.

Fig. 2: Ship and steel design process, source: FSG

The needed data exchange is assured automatically by the tool database E4. All the ship design and steel design methods in E4 are utilizing the same database. This assures a consistent design model. The determination of the rule scantlings by using classification software like e.g. Nauticus Hull has to be done separately. As a consequence two steel models, one in E4 and one in Nauticus Hull need to be made. Since the hull form and the inner subdivision of a ship changes quite often in the early design phase, models have to be maintained manually by constantly adapting the scantlings to the status quo. The required manual adaption of the Nauticus Hull model to the E4 design model is time-consuming and prone to errors.

1.3. Motivation for an interface to the classification tools

While the traditional means of conveying the design between designer and class is by paper or digital drawings, it is no doubt that both the design and review process can be significantly reduced if an efficient mechanism exist for sharing the design model. Since the involved organizations rarely use the same tools, some form of data exchange need to take place. Various approaches have been used in the past, *Polini (2011)*. Despite the many efforts the shipbuilding industry has not been able to agree on a common data exchange format resulting in the development of “point-to-point” interfaces to accomplish data exchange needs.

A number of design processes in the early design phase exist where an interface between design and analysis tools would reduce engineering man-hours and shortening the design time. These cover a broad spectrum ranging from hull form development and fairing, hydrostatics, computational fluid dynamics, finite element meshing and analysis, hydrostatics, intact and damaged stability and longitudinal strength.

Fig.3: E4 to Nauticus Hull Interface in the steel design process

Without an efficient interface with a two-way communication between E4 and Nauticus Hull, the designer has to manually transfer the information between the two tools. This is error prone and time consuming. With an automatic data exchange between the two systems, it is possible to transfer and check more versions of a set of cross-section scantlings in the same time frame. The steel design model stays up-to-date and is closer to the ship design. The result is a better optimized midship section in steel weight, longitudinal strength questions, number of structural members or the height of deck girders etc.

This is the motivation for developing an interface between E4 and Nauticus Hull. Fig. 3 shows where the interface can be used within the steel design process.

2. The E4 Steel Methods

In addition to the ship design calculation methods, the methods concerning steel design in E4 give the designer a variety of useful tools.

2.1. Steel sections

The complete hull steel structure of the ship, including all plates, stiffeners and girders can be modeled. This works for all longitudinal members as well as for all transversal members of the steel structure. The location and extension of the weld seams on the shell plating can be exactly described.

The structure model is based on 2D cross-sections but can describe the vessel fully in 3D by using the “forward / aft view” concept. In Fig. 4 this is illustrated with a 3D view of a RoRo section with hidden shell plating. On Frame 130 a deck opening begins. In a frame-based 2D way of thinking it is not possible to describe this frame clearly. Two frame definitions are needed to avoid inconsistencies.

One definition has to be made for the forward view and one for the aft view. In E4 each structural member “knows” if it is valid at a frame and if it is starting, ending or going through at this frame. By this, the modeling of e.g. a shaped hull form, deck openings or cambered bulkheads is easily possible. This behavior is one of the main differences between E4 steel and Nauticus Hull since the steel description in the rule scantling tool is not fully in 3D. Structural members valid on other frames can be spread fast and easily to the whole ship. Therefore the generation of a global ship model based on the midship section is fast and efficient.

Fig. 4: Forward/Aft concept

2.2. Available exchange possibilities

The global steel model can be exported to the FEM program ANSYS to perform global strength and vibration analysis. Several local and global static and dynamic loads can be applied on the structure. Thereby amongst others the influence on the structure caused by the ships weight and loading, the hydrostatic pressure and the hydrodynamic added masses as well as the main oscillators, the main engine and the propeller can be considered.

2.3. Link to E4 Design

As mentioned before one of the important information flows during the early design phase is a reliable and distinctive link between the steel design and the ship design. This link is completely implemented in E4. The shell plating is linked to the actual ship's hull form used in the design. The plating of the inner decks and the longitudinal and transversal bulkheads on the other hand is linked to the inner compartmentation of the hull. Since the stiffeners on their part are linked to the plates, all relevant members of the steel structure follow automatically if the hull form or the compartments change during the ship design.

If e.g. the height of the double bottom changes in the ship design, the steel members of the double bottom will also change by following the new room definition. In this example the double bottom plating with stiffeners will change its z - coordinate and the longitudinal girders in the double bottom will change their height in a way that they keep their link to the double bottom. The same applies to the shell plating, which also will change when the hull form is modified in the ship design.

2.4. Summary of E4 Steel methods

In summary the E4 steel methods contain a lot of features which are essential for the early design process.

- Complete 2D based 3D modeling of the steel structure
- Easy and fast generation of a mid-ship section or even a global ship model
- Pre- and Post processing functionalities for global vibration analysis in FEM
- Strong link to E4 design to adapt ship design changes easy and fast

But until now the required steel scantlings had to be verified separately in the classification tools.

3. Data handling

The first step of the interface programming is to consider the data handling. Mainly which data has to be transferred between the design method database E4 and the rule scantling tool Nauticus Hull. From a technical point of view the question was, in which format the information is transferred.

3.1. Objectives for interface

The first task to be addressed is:

- Transfer cross-section data from E4 to Nauticus Hull and determine rule conform scantlings

Unfortunately the modeling and scantling determining possibilities for transversal steel members in Nauticus Hull are limited. Only some basic transverse steel members can be modeled and their minimum scantlings calculated based on the rule formula. The treating of more complicated steel members such as transverse bulkheads, floor plates or the massive transverse girders of a RoRo deck is not possible. Therefore only longitudinal members of the steel structure can be transferred between the two programs.

Besides the information about all longitudinal steel members of a cross-section, the scantling determination functionality in Nauticus hull needs a complete dataset of all important main dimensions and the frame table. This data is available in E4 and the following tasks are added to the tasks already named.

- Transfer relevant main dimensions from E4 to Nauticus Hull
- Transfer the frame table from E4 to Nauticus Hull

With this information given the steel scantlings can be determined in accordance to the classification rules from DNV. The results are saved in the original Nauticus Hull dataset. Subsequently the data from Nauticus Hull have to be transferred back to E4 in a practical way. Then E4 is able to check which dimensions are changed and to adapt these changes. Therefore another task is:

- Transfer the determined rule scantlings from Nauticus Hull back to E4

Finally the primary intention of the interface is to support the work of a steel designer in E4 and on that account to perform most of the designing tasks in E4. Hence the last task is:

- Minimize the modeling work as well as the setting of rule and calculation parameters in Nauticus Hull

3.2. Choice of interface format

A common way of transferring data between software applications is through a common interface file format usually written in ASCII. The format is defined from one party or in the best case from all parties using the interface. Nauticus Hull provides for this purpose the exchange file format 2dl. The exact structure of this file is fixed and well documented. The 2dl file written by Nauticus Hull contains a mix of the ships main dimensions, program parameters and the cross-section information. While reading the 2dl file Nauticus Hull only utilizes the cross-section information. The reading of e.g. main dimension data or the frame table from the 2dl file is not possible. Therefore data exchange exclusively based on the 2dl format is not adequate for the given tasks named above.

One of the advantages of Nauticus Hull is its storage format. All ship data, steel data and the settings made while using the program are stored into a readable and editable XML format. Therefore it suggests itself to use this format directly for the interface which is done finally.

The following problems arise after this decision:

- The XML format of Nauticus Hull is not documented.
- Not all of the necessary XML files are fixed format from DNV side.
- The possibility to search, read, store, change and write efficiently the files without destroying the XML structure is not implemented in E4.

3.3. The xml handling

The following part describes the XML handling in E4. Files are first read completely into the memory. Each character of the file is stored into a large one-dimensional character array of dynamic size, Fig.5. Then the content is analyzed to build the XML structure of the file. It is stored in a one dimensional integer array of dynamic size, called the structure array. For each tag or attribute the following information is stored in the array:

- Level of tag below the first parent
- Position in character array of the leftmost character of the tag name
- Position in character array of the rightmost character of the tag name
- Position in character array of the leftmost character of the tag content
- Position in character array of the rightmost character of the tag content

For example the tag <Name>Frl Mayer</Name> has the “address” (4 98 101 103 111) in the structure array, Fig.6.

With this “address” available for each tag after reading and building, the character array can be searched and modified fast and efficiently without looking up each character every time.

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<shiplist>
  <Entry Shiptype="Container">
    <Name>Frl Mayer</Name>
    <Length>100</Length>
    <Breadth>12</Breadth>
    <Drawing />
    <IMO_Numb>1234567</IMO_Numb>
    <Status>
      <Flag>Germany</Flag>
      <Homeport>Hamburg</Homeport>
    </Status>
  </Entry>
</shiplist>

```



```

character_array = (<,?,x,m,l, ,v,e,r,s,i,o,n,= . . . l,i,s,t,>)

```

Fig.5: Example: Store XML file in character array

Example	=	<Name>Frl Mayer</Name>
level	=	4
character_array	=	(. . . <N,a,m,e,>F,r,l, ,M,a,y,e,r,</N,a,m,e,>. . .)
Stored Position numbers	=	98 101 103 111


```

structure_array = (... ,4,98,101,103,111,...)

```

Fig.6: Example: store XML structure in integer array

Based on this functionality a lot of smaller subroutines have been programmed which read, change or delete the tag values of a tag as well as subroutines which read, create and delete complete new tags with values and attributes in a XML file. The programmed algorithms assure that a valid file is read in and control that a correct XML structure is written back.

4. E4 to Nauticus Hull Interface

In order to establish an efficient data transfer between E4 and Nauticus Hull, the intended interface is developed with the help of the aforementioned data handling concepts.

4.1 Problems solved during development

Since the XML storage format of Nauticus Hull was never intended to be an exchange format, it is not documented at all. To compensate the missing documentation and identify which information is stored where and when, two file versions are compared before and afterwards each relevant program step in Nauticus Hull.

In addition a lot of information about GUI settings, internal program settings and not identifiable switches is stored also in the files. This data is obviously not of interest for the interface. Because it is not feasible to provide all this unwanted information in the interface, it is decided to create a new XML data file not from scratch but based on a default file body provided by Nauticus Hull.

Finally the chosen XML based interface emerges as not practicable for the cross-section data, since the actual XML format for a CrossSection.xml file is not yet fixed. In contrast the 2dl format contains all this data. To avoid the multiple re-programming of the structure written out, it is decided to use the 2dl format temporarily for transferring the cross-section data. As soon as the format will be fixed the data can be written directly into the XML file.

4.2. What is transferred between E4 and Nauticus Hull

Since one objective is to minimize the work of a designer in Nauticus Hull, as much as possible modeling work is done in E4 and the interface provides Nauticus Hull with almost all necessary information to perform a scantling determination. The whole modeling work for a new cross-section is done previously in E4. When the cross-section data changes at a frame or a new frame is modeled the interface can be used to check the scantlings according to the rules.

Based on the ship design and steel design information available in E4, the following information can be exported to Nauticus Hull at this time:

- The hull form as a 3D *.dxf file. This file is read in manually from Nauticus Hull. Since the hull form is only needed when modeling directly in Nauticus Hull, this possibility is not treated further in this paper
- General Hull Information such as the rule version in effect, the freeboard type, identification data and other options which must be set in Nauticus Hull before the rule scantling determination.
- All relevant ship data such as the main dimensions, deadweight etc.
- The ship's frame table
- The cross-section steel data at selected frames including all longitudinal members of the ship's steel structure. This means longitudinal plates, longitudinal stiffeners and girders. For each steel member the dimensions, the material and also the necessary rule information (position ID & girder ID) are exported.

After this data is imported in Nauticus Hull by the interface files, just a minimum of work remains in Nauticus Hull before the rule scantlings can be determined.

4.3. Interface workflow

The intended technical workflow for the interface is shown in Fig.7. While starting the interface a check for an existing Nauticus Hull dataset is performed. Dataset means, all relevant XML files to perform a rule check. Namely the files are the Hulljob.xml, the Frametable.xml and the Shipdata.xml file. If one of the 3 files is found new data is stored in the existing XML file. If no file is found a new XML file is created from the default files.

The resulting dataset is a fully functioning Nauticus Hull ship dataset. It contains all main dimensions, the frame table and other parameters needed to determine the steel scantlings later on.

Subsequent the missing cross-section data can be exported. Amongst all frames with steel information in E4, the user has to select the cross-sections he wants to export. The steel data of each selected cross-section is written into one 2dl file respectively. The filename contains the frame number of the original frame and its respective view direction to identify the effective steel members. (See chapter 2.1.)

Fig.7: Workflow of the E4 to Nauticus Hull interface

The cross-section data has to be imported manually in Nauticus Hull by reading the CrossSection.2dl files. The result is a cross-section with steel scantlings in a chosen longitudinal extension, which is stored in a CrossSection.xml file.

Now only the following manual steps in Nauticus Hull remain before the calculation is possible. At first the compartments and local loads in the tanks have to be defined. Then the global hull girder loads have to be limited by defining the maximum values for shear force and bending moment in still water and wave condition. As a default, rule based standard values can be chosen to quickly form a first steel concept in early design.

Then the properties and dimensions of the plates and stiffeners can be changed manually or by using the functionalities in Nauticus Hull which determine the scantlings automatically according to the classification rules. The changed dimensions and properties are stored in the XML format by the program.

Going back to E4 the new scantlings can be read in now directly from the Nauticus Hull dataset. The plate and stiffener data is read in from the CrossSection.xml file, is compared with the actual values in E4 steel and is changed there if necessary.

5. Conclusion and outlook

A fast and accurate early design process is of crucial importance to build competitive ships in a difficult international environment. Besides the hull form, the general arrangement or other common ship design activities, precise cost estimation is based also on a first weight determination and a basic midship section. This implies the necessity of a strong and reliable link between the early steel design and the early ship design. Since most of the design software systems are not able to determine the steel scantlings according to the classification tools automatically, this is normally done separately by hand in the respective tools.

The developed interface automates the time-consuming and error-prone manual steel data exchange and transfers all relevant steel members between the classification tool Nauticus Hull and the ship design method database E4. Therefore it has the potential to substantially streamline the early design process. It uses a mixture of the 2dl interface file format and a direct writing into the XML database of Nauticus Hull and minimizes the work of the designer in the classification software, since only a few settings concerning loads and compartments have to be made in the class software.

In the future, the Nauticus Hull interface will continue to evolve and be extended. Possible extensions are: Replacing the text based 2dl format by a XML Schema and transferring also the loads and compartments from the design tool.

On the long run it is desirable to avoid the media break between the two programs. A necessary batch mode functionality of Nauticus Hull is basically possible. The result could be a design tool where defined steel scantlings are automatically sized according to the rules.

The lack of commercial support for industry standard interfaces has created the need for establishing “ad-hoc” solutions to solve data exchange needs. It is the hope of the authors that the industry can agree on a neutral exchange format, because this will reduce the need for costly point-to-point integrations.

In the future we may see that a common and widely accepted industry format for data exchange in the early design phase could lead to a completely electronic verification process without the need to rely on paper drawings.

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Handling Human Models in Virtual Reality Applications with MS Kinect

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Abstract

To successfully compete on the market, the shipbuilding industry has to provide good quality of the products. Another aspect is also a good ergonomic handling of the ship. Virtual human models are used to ensure this already in the early design phase. The handling of these models is not intuitive and even simple analyses can become time consuming. Due to the size of the products, it is not possible to cover the complete ship. This paper shows a concept of how to handle virtual human models intuitively and thereby reduce the effort of ergonomic analyses.

1. Introduction

The complexity of ships and the increasing international competition within the industry request high quality products with competitive manufacturing and operating costs. One potential hereby is a good ergonomic handling during the manufacturing and the use of the product. Already in early phases of ship construction Virtual Reality (VR) technology can be used to avoid mistakes and to assure good ergonomics over the complete product life cycle.

However handling of virtual human models is often complicated and even simple analyses can become time consuming. Currently available VR-solutions normally consist of two different ways to control the human model: manual control and tracking the user (body tracking). Both methods are difficult to use and need funded knowledge. Due to size and complexity it is not economic to verify the ergonomics of a complete ship. Instead concepts for the selection of the investigated parts and for an efficient usage are required.

Furthermore the immersion during the ergonomic analysis is not fully exploited, because the VR-user is decoupled from the ergonomic model. An intuitive handling of the virtual human model is needed. A new concept for an easy interaction had to be developed to reduce the effort of ergonomic analyses and to increase the acceptance by the users.

This paper presents an approach on how to interact with the virtual human model intuitively with the use of the MS Kinect sensor. Virtual tools are developed to support the user: A concept for the use from a first person perspective is shown to increase interaction and the degree of immersion of the VR-user. The paper shows how the effort for ergonomic analyses can be reduced and will allow a more efficient application in the shipbuilding industry.

First, some basics about virtual human models are explained. The potentials for using them in the maritime industry are derived and different scenarios are shown. Afterwards, the problems of the existing solutions are discussed in respect to the requirements of shipbuilders and a potential technology to solve these is introduced. A concept is presented next, how to use the technology to handle virtual human models. The concept then is extended with virtual tools to adapt it to the needs of shipbuilders. To cover the complete variety of ergonomic investigations different perspectives under consideration of the used technology are discussed in the end.

2. Virtual human models

2.1 Basics

Virtual Reality applications help to assure high quality products. The user can visualize the product and interact with it already in an early stage of the development. Virtual human models for ergonomic

analyses are provided by several merchantable software tools. This allows the VR-user to assure the later use of the product. Stereoscopic view and a high immersion support the user during the investigation.

In the past the development of virtual human models was pushed by the automotive industry. The available tools to perform ergonomic analyses are adapted to the needs of this industry, *Rodriguez-Flick (2010, Spanner-Ulmer and Muehlstedt (2010))*. They include e.g. reachability and visibility analyses and the adjustment of the human model to different populations.

Ergonomic analyses can be performed in several levels of detail. The spectrum reaches from space allocation over the reachability analysis of different person up to complex investigations with complete movements and actions of the virtual human model, Fig. 1. The basis for all these analyses is the handling of the ergonomic model. Two ways to control the manikin are common: manual adjustment and body tracking.

Fig. 1: Spectrum of ergonomic investigation

The manual handling allows the user to manipulate each joint of the ergonomic model. The manikin is a coherent chain and its movements are limited to the natural ones. This proceeding is very exact, so accurate positions are possible. However this method is not easy to use, because every joint has to be moved separately and even small changes can become time consuming.

The second way to interact with the virtual human model is the body tracking. The actual movements of the VR-user are tracked by cameras and applied to the ergonomic model in real time. This method allows natural postures of the model and an interaction with the complete body at a time. There are several technologies on the market (e.g. optical target tracking, CUELA) which provide a high precision of the recorded movements. However, the user has to wear markers or even bigger targets, e.g. full body suits) and is thereby affected in his movements. Furthermore, a detailed calibration of the tracking system for each user is needed before every new investigation to track the markers accurately. Due to this, the available methods are not suitable for a rapid analysis.

2.2 Ergonomics in the shipbuilding industry

The importance of good ergonomics over the complete product life cycle is increasing. Research projects, e.g. USE-VR, POWER-VR, *Nedess et al. (2009), Friedewald et al. (2012)*, showed possible scenarios for the use of virtual human models in the shipbuilding industry. These scenarios embrace the early design phase, over the manufacturing and operating up to the recovery of a ship, Fig. 2. The identified scenarios cover the full range of the shown spectrum. The requirements to the human model vary hereby from the depicted scenario.

Fig. 2: Ergonomic scenarios in the product life cycle of a ship

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In the early design phase the virtual human model is often used to validate the correct measurements of systems. This is especially important for specialized areas like a machinery repair shop. The use of a human model helps validating the dimensions and the arrangement of the proposed tools. The validation of the correct labeling of emergency exits can also be supported with ergonomic models. Visibility analyses in VR let the user identify potential design mistakes. It is also possible to extend such investigations by adding bad visibility by e.g. gas or fire.

During manufacturing the assembly sequence can change due to rescheduling or redesign either. Big parts normally cause a change of sequence for several surrounding parts. The previously planned assembly steps need to be verified. Virtual human models help to check critical spots of the new assembly sequence. Similar to the investigations during the design phase, ergonomic analyses have their biggest potentials in specialized and safety relevant areas.

Fig. 3: Identification of components for ergonomic investigation

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Another field of operation for ergonomics is the staff training. Virtual human models are used to visualize procedures on a ship. These can range from showing instructions for everyday operations up to security procedures where staff has to interact with the environment.

The presented scenarios cover a big range of components on a ship. Theoretically it is possible to investigate all of them. However, this is not economic and would increase the costs for a ship significantly. Such investigations can only be performed at selected parts. To identify the critical components a logic should support the user, Fig. 3. Every part is rated in two categories with the scale from 1 (low) to 10 (high): safety relevance, effort of usage. The second aspect contains the frequency of usage and the required force for this action. Both are equally weighted. The rating can be done once and be adopted if needed. Based on the rating, the parts can be classified in the logic and it can be seen if the particular component needs an ergonomic investigation. It is not possible to draw a strict line between the decision for or against an investigation. A zone for individual decisions is recommended and should be adopted to each company.

3. Ergonomic analyses with the use of MS Kinect

3.1 Problem

Ergonomic investigations are claimed by the maritime industry as shown. However, the use of virtual human models in VR is yet not adapted to the requirements of the shipbuilding industry. To support the shipbuilders the effort for such investigations has to be reduced to a minimum. One big part of every analysis is the handling of the human model. As mentioned above, the handling is not intuitive and even small changes can become time consuming. In the shipbuilding industry design and manufacturing often process in parallel. The time span between engineering and assembly is short and is thereby an important factor for the desired analyses.

Nedess et al. (2009) present a standard process for a Virtual Reality meeting. Ergonomic investigations follow the same approach. However, the focus hereby lies on the preparation of the session, the performance of the session and the documentation. The Virtual Production (ViP) Toolset contains virtual tools to increase the performance of these three steps and fulfil the requirements of the maritime industry, *Loedding et al. (2012)*. The handling of the virtual human model is supported with tailored tools on a tablet-computer and a concept to move and position the manikin in three steps. This approach allows the VR-user to prepare the scene with just a few clicks. The limit of this procedure is the movement of the virtual worker. Every motion has to be adjusted manually by the user. The desired analyses can then be done in defined postures. The actual movement of the virtual worker is not considered.

As shown in chapter 2.2, the applications in the shipbuilding industry contain scenarios where motion of the human model is needed to allow dynamic investigations. Furthermore, new concepts are required to ease the use and increase the degree of immersion for the VR-user. In USE-VR so-called motion procllets were introduced to fulfil worker movements. Different operations can be constructed by sequencing several movement elements, which is sufficient for basic moves. For complex movements, body tracking can be used, however this isn't commonly used by the shipyards yet. In the following an approach is provided which goes beyond the motion procllets and allows intuitive and natural movements of the virtual human model by an innovative body tracking. Before, the used technology is introduced.

3.2 MS Kinect

The Kinect sensor is a motion capturing device and was introduced by Microsoft in the year 2010 for the gaming industry, Fig. 4. The sensor contains one RGB-camera for coloured images, one infrared emitter, one infrared camera and a microphone array. The Kinect provides a coloured and a depth image of the recorded space. The technology behind it was patented by *Zalovsky et al. (2005)*.

Fig. 4: Skeleton-tracking with the Kinect sensor

The Kinect was developed as a motion sensing input device for the Microsoft Xbox. The player gets the opportunity to steer the environment without holding a controller. This is done by the provided skeletal tracking which is based on the depth image. The sensor recognizes the user, identifies the joints and follows the actions. Through gestures the user can interact with the game. The Kinect can be coupled with the PC via the Software Development Kit (SDK) which is provided by Microsoft, *Microsoft (2013)*. Through this, it is possible to access of the functionalities of the sensor.

3.3 Movement control of virtual human models

As discussed earlier, handling of virtual human models by body tracking is not commonly used in the shipbuilding industry. For this reason, an alternative method was developed in cooperation with several shipbuilders in the context of the POWER-VR research project.

The MS Kinect provides potentials for the control of ergonomic models as shown. The inbuilt skeletal-tracking exports the positions (relative xyz-coordinates) of up to 20 joints in real time. This information is transferred to the Virtual Reality environment and assigned to the ergonomic model. The accuracy of tracking is limited to the amount of available joints. High precision work, e.g. inserting a screw in a hole, cannot be covered. However, the precision is sufficient for the depicted scenarios, Fig. 2.

The use of a marker-free tracking system allows the VR-user to act without limitations in his movements. This leads to intuitive and natural workflows and a better acceptance of the technology. The assigned movements can be coupled with the virtual human model in two ways, *Titov and Friedewald (2013)*: adopting the manikin to the user or scale the user movements to the manikin. To exploit the advantages of the marker-free tracking the user is scaled to the virtual human. In this case only the directions of the joints are transferred. This method allows a usage without a calibration of the VR-user. By changing between different populations the same user gets the ability to control various types of human models.

During the investigation the Virtual Production Toolset provides the access to several analyses tools. The user can control these over a tablet-computer or immersive menus. Through the body tracking in real time the user gains the ability for direct validation, e.g. reachability, visibility. To secure the results or change the user it is possible to toggle the tracking.

The described motion control of the virtual human model is an intuitive way of handling the manikin. It can be used efficiently in several scenarios in the shipbuilding industry for positioning or executing operations. In combination with the developed VR tools, *Friedewald et al. (2012)*, the depicted scenarios can be covered. Compared to common optical tracking, this technology is easy to use due to non-existing limitations of movement and no need of calibration, Fig. 5. The accuracy thereby does fulfil the requirements for the majority of the scenarios. One limitation of both systems is the field of motion which is given through the surroundings. In the following chapter tools are introduced to solve this problem and allow the movement of the virtual human model through the complete ship to the components selected for an investigation.

Fig. 5: Body tracking technologies

3.4 Extended motion

Virtual Reality environments are normally designed for sessions with a couple of users. The available space in front of the projection is limited to several square meters. Having a look at the size of a ship, it is obvious that the provided space of motion for the user is not sufficient to reach every part of the entire ship. Movement in the virtual environment is normally realized with a controller, e.g. a flystick. Analyses however are normally executed via a tablet computer. Often it is not possible to split these to aspect and they have to be done simultaneously. For the actual user it is not handy to use the flystick next to a tablet computer. Preferably the user can move and steer the virtual human model through the ship without holding any controlling device.

A further limitation of motion during ergonomic investigations is the maximum recorded space by the Kinect sensor. This is limited up to a distance of 3.5m from the Kinect. After coupling the movements of the user to the virtual human model, the area of motion is also transferred. To assure ergonomic analyses over the complete ship in one session without moving the human model manually a new control method was implemented. Hereby the tracked area is moved in the virtual environment through the ship, Fig. 6. To ease the handling the motion is split in horizontal and vertical movements.

Fig. 6: Movement of the ergonomic model in VR

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Horizontal movements of the investigation area are attached to the decks of the ship. Via a commercially available balance board the VR-user gets the ability to move in the level without holding additional controls in his hand. This method transfers the examined area through the ship during the session. To adopt the vertical movement to the given boundary conditions it is limited to the elevation between separate decks. This can be performed in two ways: by choosing a deck on the schematic plan on a tablet computer or by speech recognition provided by the Kinect sensor. At the moment there are several research works in the field of speech recognitions. However, this technology is depended on the user and can be error-prone. Due to this only the tablet controls were considered in this work. In combination with the marker-free body tracking shipbuilders gain the ability to naturally move through the ship.

4. First person view for higher immersion

In the previous chapters it was shown how to control the virtual human model intuitively. Beyond the handling of the ergonomic model the desired analyses are in point of interest. The introduced handling methods already include some functions and reduce the need of tools for further investigation. Especially reachability of parts can be verified directly by the user. Additional tools for desired investigation, such as force analyses or the influence of different population, are brought to the user via a tablet computer for an easy and direct use. Normally, the analyses are performed from a view point outside the human model (Fig. 7a). In this case the VR-user can navigate around the scene to find an optimal position for the evaluation.

The immersion can be increased by linking the perspective of the virtual human model to the view point of the user. Thereby the user doesn't just control the manikin, but gains the ability to interact with the virtual environment from a first person view, Fig. 7b. Turning the head of the user actually turns the view point. Therefore the permanent linkage in real time between the user and the human model is important to assure a dynamic investigation. This is realized by a marker-free head tracking tool using the face recognition from the Kinect SDK. The rotations of the head are calculated and applied to the virtual human model.

Fig. 7: Ergonomic investigation from different view points

The view from the first person perspective has several advantages. It provides better understanding by giving the VR-user the option to see the virtual environment through the workers eyes. The result is a natural behaviour of both, the user and the ergonomic model. Obviously some important information, e.g. comfort zones of the joints, cannot be seen from this perspective. To solve this, three options are provided to the user. It is possible to record the motions of the virtual human model and follow them a second time from another view point. A second option is to toggle the tracking and switch view points during the investigation. The third possibility is to visualize the results of selected joints directly within the field of view of the user.

The ability to toggle the view point to objects allows the user to set viewpoints relative to the human model. The different viewpoints are important for efficient ergonomic investigations. Due to this the VR-user gains an overview of the situation and a better understanding of the working circumstances.

5. Conclusion

Handling of virtual human models can be done in different ways: manually or via body tracking. Body tracking provides several advantages for the use in the shipbuilding industry. However, common merchantable products do not cover all requirements. Especially the investment costs and time effort for e.g. calibration are often a barrier to use this technology.

In this paper an approach for an intuitive handling of the virtual human model is shown. The VR-user is tracked by the Kinect sensor which was originally developed for the gaming industry. Through this, the sensor is a low-cost hardware product with a sufficient accuracy for shipbuilding applications. The tracking is based on a depth image of the surrounding and provides the positions of up to 20 joints of the actual user in real time. These positions can be transferred and applied to the virtual human model.

To extend the range of investigations and cover the size of a complete ship the tracking was improved with additional tools. The user can move in the horizontal plane (over a deck) with a balance board. This method is intuitive and easy to use. The vertical movement between decks is controlled via a tablet computer. In the end, this paper shows an extension (first person view) to the body tracking. This increases the immersion and allows the user to dynamically interact from the perspective of the virtual human model.

The presented work was done in cooperation with shipbuilding companies during the research project POWER-VR, funded by the German Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Technologie - BMWi / Projektträger Jülich PTJ) due to a decision of the German Bundestag. All existing scenarios for ergonomic investigations claim a suitable handling of the virtual human model. This was derived and presented in this paper.

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Modeling the Impact of Significant Wave Height and Wave Vector using an On-board Attitude Sensor Network

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Abstract

High-frequency data from a low-cost attitude sensor network together with weather data is applied to predict and measure the impact of various sea conditions on vessel motion. The machine learning approach relies on fusion of sensor network data fusion weather data. The models can be used as part of the process to predict future motions according to the significant wave height fields and wave vectors forecasts.

1. Introduction

Approximately 90% of all global trade is transported by seas. International shipping enables affordable transportation of food, goods and energy. Rising environmental pressure and fuel prices are compelling ship owners to build fleets of intelligent vessels capable of executing safe and optimized voyages, a transformation which began decades ago in airline industry is now sweeping across the shipping industry. In this context one key aspect is finding the safest and most economical routes in various sea conditions. Today direct quantifiable measurement of sea conditions on-board, especially wave height and direction require expensive specialized radar technology. Finding a low-cost solution would allow safer and more economical routing to be accessible for all vessels operating around the world, *Aas-Hansen (2010)*.

Knowledge about wave induced motions and loads of ships is important in determining operational efficiency, *Bertram (2000)*, *Padhy (2008)*, *Hennessy et al. (2009)*. Large floating structures (such as cruise vessels or tankers) undergo translatory and angular motion (roll, pitch and yaw), carry large momentum and can experience large bending moments. There are different approaches to modelling the dynamics of oceangoing ships under the influence of external forces such as waves, *Drennan et al. (1994)*, *Jensen et al. (2004)*, *Spanos et al. (2008)*. Both parametric and non-parametric modelling can be used, *Tannuri et al. (2003)*, *Nielsen (2006)*, *Caires (2011)*. It is a pre-requisite to know the sea condition and the behaviour of the ship in waves; in the simplest case by representing it by loss of speed due to the wave-field, *Padhy (2007)*. More advanced methods on Bayesian modelling are covered by *Iseki (2000)*, *Hauser et al. (2003)*, *Nielsen (2006)*.

The objective of this study is to obtain a simple, yet realistic, empirical model of a ship in an open ocean under the action of periodic incoming waves. This work is motivated by the need to improve wave modelling for decision support tools for optimum speed and route, *Montes (2005)*, *Ilus and Heikkinen (2012)*.

2. Data

Data used in this study is collected from a container vessel operating between Europe, South-America and Asia. Fig.1 shows the vessel route for the duration of the study. To execute the study, Eniram data was supplemented with historical wave information from National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), more specifically their WAVEWATCH-III v. 2.22 hindcast analysis data was used as an estimate of outside sea state, *Tolman (2002)*, *Chawla et al (2011)*. Table I includes the variables used in the study.

Fig. 1: Route of the vessel used in the study

Table I: Variables used to model vessel response in waves characterized by regular wave parameters

Variable	Abbreviation	Unit	Source
Trim	t	m	Eniram
Draft	d	m	Eniram
Longitudinal Motion Fore Sensor	P_{lf}	deg	Eniram
Transverse Motion Fore Sensor	P_{tf}	deg	Eniram
Longitudinal Motion Aft Sensor	P_{la}	deg	Eniram
Transverse Motion Aft Sensor	P_{ta}	deg	Eniram
Longitudinal true wind relative to vessel	W_l	kn	Eniram
Transverse true wind relative to vessel	W_t	kn	Eniram
Speed Over Ground	V	kn	Eniram
NOAA Significant wave height	H	m	WAVEWATCH-III
NOAA peak wave period	T	s	WAVEWATCH-III
NOAA significant wave direction	D	deg	WAVEWATCH-III

2.1 On-board data

The Eniram system collects in real-time data from various sources like weather stations, GPSs, doppler logs, automation systems, integrated-bridge systems etc. Furthermore Eniram installs high-frequency sensors on-board to capture vessel trim and motions very accurately. Sensors operate between 16 Hz and 25 Hz depending on model, the vessel in question is equipped with multiple inclinometers with frequency of 16 Hz and accuracy of 0.01 degree root mean square, RMS. Sensors measure both transverse and longitudinal motions. Figure 2 describes the basic sensor fusion process where raw vibrational data is recorded and transformed via spectral analysis into power variables. The other Eniram signals listed in Table I are collected from various sources such as GPS and weather station.

Fig. 2: Method of extracting data from two sensors onboard. Raw data is processed using spectrum analysis (FFT) and wave bandwidth is selected. RMS of bandwidth is used in modelling wave impact

Fig. 3: Example of NOAA ocean wave modelling

2.2 Ocean wave model

WAVEWATCH-III™ model is spectral wave model used by NOAA to forecast global ocean wave and sea state, *Tolman (2002)*. NOAA offers hindcast re-analysis database from AUG 1999 until present. This data is used for the study to give an estimate of outside sea-state. WAVEWATCH-III is a model and therefore only approximates actual conditions. Accuracy of the model depends both on actual conditions, location and time, *Sølvsteen and Hansen (2006)*. Fig.4 shows the root mean square error (RMSE) of the model's significant wave height over time. The RMSE varies between 0.25-0.75 m depending on the season.

Fig.4: NOAA WAVEWATCH III 3 year wave height global RMSE

2.3 Data fusion and basic inference

WAVEWATCH-III data is available in 3 h period, thus Eniram continuous data is sampled every 3 h to match forecast grid. Simple spherical interpolation is employed to extract from the vessel's GPS location information on the corresponding wave parameters.

Fig. 5: Polar charts show the impact of wave height (distance from origin), wave direction relative to bow and Eniram transverse fore motion power (left). Wave height H against Eniram transverse aft motion power, color: NOAA wave direction D (right)

Fig.5 shows the basic relationships between Eniram motion data and NOAA forecasts. The polar chart on the left depicts that the biggest transverse motions are observed when forecast data indicates the height of the waves is high and advancing towards the sides of the vessel. The picture on the right shows the correlation between aft transverse power measurement and the wave height. This is shown by the different colour that the surfaces areas change to. Waves originating from front or aft induce a less transversal power motion which is expected. From this we can conclude that it is possible to use both NOAA and Eniram datasets for mutual inference and modelling. For wave direction estimation we use symmetrical scale and roll the measurement between $0^\circ - 180^\circ$.

3. Modelling method

Ship behaviour in waves encompasses several factors including: added resistance and loss of speed, wave loads and slamming, safety and comforts, and establishing operational limits, *Padhy (2007)*. The responses $r(t)$ of the vessel in regular waves can be presented as

$$r(t) = R \cos(\omega' t + \epsilon),$$

where ϵ is the phase angle between encountered wave with frequency

$$\omega' = \omega \left(1 - \frac{\omega V}{g} \cos \beta\right),$$

which depends on ships speed V and relative heading β . For incident regular wave

$$u = W \cos(kx - \omega t)$$

the transfer function Q , generally termed response amplitude operator (RAO), is represented as

$$Q(\omega, V, \theta) = R(\omega, \beta, V)/W$$

The response R depends on wave frequency ω , relative heading β and ship speed V . For details see *Padhy (2007)*, *McCue and Campbell (2007)*, *van den Boom et al. (2008)*.

The increased fuel consumption of ship and speed penalty can be described using the approximated formulas for contact angle between the wave and the ship together with wave amplitude and numerical values for responses, *Jalkanen et al. (2009)*. While simple environmental models, e.g. *Hellstrom (2002)*, are appropriate for certain applications, we seek to inspect multivariate inference using modern regression methods.

As an estimator of the relationships between WAVEWATCH-III parameters and on-board measurements two different state-of-the-art machine learning methods are employed. The first method is called multivariate adaptive regression splines (MARS), *Friedman (1991)*, *Milborrow (2012)*, *Ihaka and Gentleman (2012)*. It is a non-parametric method which is described as non-parametric regression algorithm which employs automatic splitting of the data into hinges to handle non-linearity. The second method is known as random forest which is an ensemble classifier which uses a combination of tree predictors to find an optimum estimator, *Breiman (2001)*.

The experiment has a two phased approach: first we try to estimate the WAVEWATCH-III parameters using measurements done onboard and then we try to estimate motions experienced inside the vessel measured by the inclinometers and using NOAA parameters. The goal is to predict added resistance due to wave field and solve the inverse problem between the vessel and the sea state. Data is split randomly between training and test data for validation.

4. Results

Models prepared with training data and tested with the randomly selected test set. Classical model selection criteria, e.g. *Aranda et al. (2005)*, Akaike information criterion, measuring the relative goodness of fit, was used to select optimal model formulas. Figs. 6-8 show examples of modelling accuracy for three significant variables

- Wave height
- Wave angle
- Attitude sensor power spectrum

Variables listed in Table I including measured wind was used as suggested by *WMO (1998)* and *Etemadshahidi et al. (2009)*. Estimates on error distribution and prediction versus the test data for each variable are provided.

Fig. 6: Distribution of wave height model error (left) and wave height prediction (right) compared with NOAA model

Results are quantified in Table II by using root mean square error RMSE, model bias, Pearson correlation factor r and scatter index SI.

Predicting WAVEWATCH-III wave direction using measured motion variables proved to be the most challenging task of the research and showed the RMSE of the estimate to be 33° , Fig.7 and Table II. The results for other NOAA wave parameters have smaller bias and errors margins. For significant wave height RMSE is 0.5 m, Fig. 6.

Table II: Accuracy of WAVEWATCH-III wave parameters for model relying onboard measurements only

NOAA parameter	Bias	RMSE	r	SI
Significant wave height, m	0.00	0.5	0.83	0.22
Significant wave period, s	-0.02	2.0	0.64	0.19
Significant wave direction, deg	-0.15	33	0.69	0.54

Fig. 7: Wave direction estimate error (left) and wave direction prediction validated against NOAA model (right)

Fig. 8: Distribution of transverse motion model error (left) and model prediction compared to onboard attitude measurements (right)

For practical applications, we are interested how accurately wave-field parameters can be measured with onboard attitude sensors. Table III summarizes the sensor response model accuracy. For longitudinal coordinate the RMSE is 0.02 degrees and for transverse direction <0.3 degrees, Fig. 8.

Table III: Accuracy of sensor spectral powers components for model using WAVEWATCH-III parameters

Sensor spectral power	Bias	RMSE	r	SI
Longitudinal fore, deg	0.0001	0.019	0.79	0.33
Longitudinal aft	0.0007	0.020	0.77	0.36
Transverse fore	0.0058	0.28	0.74	0.37
Transverse aft	0.0066	0.26	0.77	0.36

5. Conclusions

A method to associate wave forecast data into vessel motions has been outlined. An approach using multivariate adaptive regression splines and randomized classification trees have been used to demonstrate how wave load can be measured onboard and how these measurements can be fused with model data with predictive capability. High frequency measurements from attitude sensors located on the vessel forward and aft have been used and the power spectrum analysed. This was done in conjunction with the investigation of a temporal phase that has been used in the reconstruction of directional wave model.

This study shows the variables that correlate significantly with the wave data and a method using weather forecasts to model motions differences to match absolute wave height, direction and length is presented. Model prediction accuracy for significant wave height was at 0.5 m RMSE level, which corresponds to the modelling input parameter accuracy of the WAVEWATCH-III data. The accuracy achieved for wave model parameters and for corresponding attitude sensor response, <0.3°, indicates that we can create a useful vessel specific wave load model.

Future work includes extending the research to add parameters to the wave models. One example is to add direct wave measurements using radar. A more detailed hull bending model including best available time resolution data will be created in order to improve accuracy. When combined wave load with a propulsion power prediction model, the results can be applied to improving how optimal speed profiles are determined. When installed onboard a ship, completed models can be used in building decision support tools for route optimization and for improving operational efficiency.

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Robust Characterization of Ship Power Plant Fuel Efficiency

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Abstract

Fuel oil consumption constitutes the largest portion of the ship operating costs. Regardless of noisy signals and scattered data, reliable estimation of fuel consumption is important. With data based methods, fuel consumption of the ship power plant can be evaluated and modeled in the actual operating conditions. In this paper, robust estimates are derived that also take into consideration additional data available such as bunker delivery notes and fuel oil laboratory tests.

1. Introduction

Fuel oil consumption constitutes the largest portion of the ship operating costs. Regardless of noisy signals and scattered data, reliable estimation of fuel consumption is important. Instantaneous specific fuel consumption of a single engine is affected by various factors, including:

- Change in operating point (power), e.g. due to changing weather and environmental conditions
- Fuel properties such as the amount of energy stored in the fuel (calorific content), *Wärtsilä (2007)*, *Wild (2005)*
- Ambient conditions such as engine intake air temperature, pressure and humidity, *Wärtsilä (2007)*, *Hatlevold (2010)*
- Engine driven auxiliaries such as pumps, *Wärtsilä (2007)*

In practice, fuel consumption measurement is often unavailable or it is challenging to measure. Even the revised NO_x technical code allows the use of test bed measurements as a fuel consumption estimate, *IMO (2008a)*. On some vessels, a fuel flow meter is installed, and therefore an estimate of fuel oil volume flow rate is available. In these cases, multiple engines can share the same measurement instrument, which makes it more challenging to see the fuel consumed by an individual engine. Volumetric flow rate measurements can be converted to mass flow rates based on fuel density information.

For more accurate data-driven efficiency analysis, a rich combination of additional data should be used. BDN must contain at least the following details related to fuel oil properties, *IMO (2008b)*:

- Product name
- Density at reference temperature, kg/m³
- Sulfur content, %
- Quantity in metric tons

Fuel oil laboratory test data contain additional information such as:

- Lower calorific value (LCV) or calorific content
- Density measurement
- Viscosity
- Water content
- Elemental composition

Examples of calorific content and density laboratory measurements of fuel oil samples are presented in Fig.1. With Residual fuel oil variance in density and calorific content can be seen, even though most of the residual oil samples are of the same type (RMG-380). The variance is due to varying

quality of the heavy fuel oil, as indicated by the sulfur content. With sulfur content fixed, density and lower calorific value are linearly correlated. With both fuel types, energy content of the fuel can be predicted by just using sulfur and density information. Both of these are available in the bunker delivery note.

The more sulfur there is in the fuel, the lower LCV can be expected. The connection between sulfur content and lower calorific value can be explained through the changing carbon-hydrogen ratio, *ABS (1984)*.

These relationships with calorific content, density and sulfur concentration can be used to determine the unknown variable when dealing with incomplete fuel oil data. For example, if the sulfur concentration of the fuel oil is known to be 3%, the lower calorific value of 40.2 MJ/kg can be expected. Alternative ways of estimating LCV are presented in *ISO (2010)* and *Wild (2005)*.

Fig. 1: Residual fuel oil calorific content is largely dependant on fuel oil density and sulfur content. Based on data from fuel oil laboratory sample results.

The effect of ambient conditions on the specific fuel consumption and power of the engine are documented in *ISO-3046-1*, *ISO (2002a)*, *ISO (2002b)*. The standard quantifies the effect of ambient air temperature, humidity, pressure and charge air coolant temperature to power and SFC. Simulations by *Hatlevold (2010)* show that ambient air temperature alone might have an effect of roughly one percent on SFC, which means that the ambient factors in total might have an effect of several percents on SFC.

This paper uses three types of data to improve the accuracy of engine efficiency estimates. These are i) bunker delivery note (BDN) data, ii) fuel oil laboratory test data, and iii) the position of the vessel. More precisely, a calibration method for volumetric fuel flow rate measurement is presented that enables more accurate and in-depth engine efficiency modeling. The resulting specific fuel consumption curves are useful e.g. in speed profile optimization and engine analysis, *Bruns et al. (2011)*, *Ilus and Heikkinen (2012)*, *Salonen et al. (2012)*.

2. Energy Conversion Efficiency

When considering how much power is produced with a kilogram of fuel oil, it is important to consider how much energy is stored in the fuel. A commonly used quantity to express this is the lower heating value (LHV), or lower calorific value (LCV). Lower calorific value gives the heating value of the fuel, assuming all water content is vapor, *Hatlevold (2010)*. Unlike with higher heating value (HHV), the latent heat of water vapor is not included, *Woodyard (2004)*. In theory, low LCV means that more fuel must be burned for the same power output, compared to fuel with a high heating value. Typically the quantity is expressed as joules per kilogram of fuel oil. According to *Hatlevold*

(2010), LCV is virtually determined by the carbon-hydrogen ratio, which is almost uniquely fixed by the density. The author also points out that with heavy fuel oil, additional losses are expected, and typically engines designed to be running with heavy fuel might be de-rated by up to 10%. Similarly, Cooper (2002) proposes the addition of 10 g/kWh to SFC with heavy fuel oil.

The overall engine efficiency η_E represents the ratio between the engine output power P and the rate of energy inputted in the form of fuel Q_f , Shi et al. (2010):

$$\eta_E = P / Q_f = P / (m_{rf} * LHV) \quad (1)$$

Essentially, the formula calibrates the specific fuel consumption (SFC), i.e. fuel mass flow rate divided by the output power,

$$b = m_{rf} / P, \quad (2)$$

with the lower calorific value of the fuel. Related concept is so called heat rate (HR), which is the ratio of heat energy needed to produce unit of output power:

$$HR = 1 / \eta_E = b * LHV. \quad (3)$$

Assuming that the overall efficiency stays the same, the heat rate will be constant for different fuels. Similarly to SFC, heat rate is power-dependent. Next it is assumed that two different specific fuel consumption values are available, b_1 and b_2 , and these are specified in terms of different heating values, LHV_1 and LHV_2 . The conversion formula between these can be derived from the fact that the heat rates will be equal:

$$b_2 = b_1 * LHV_1 / LHV_2. \quad (4)$$

According to Eq. (4) specific fuel consumption will increase roughly by 7% if it is defined in terms of fuel oil LHV of 40 MJ/kg instead of the higher value of 42.7 MJ/kg, Wild (2005), Rattenbury (2008). This is roughly consistent with the estimates presented in Hatlevold (2010), Cooper (2002). In practice however, the equation should only be used after confirming that the overall efficiency is in fact the same with different fuels.

The above modeling approach is applicable for steady state conditions, Shi et al. (2010). For modeling engine as a dynamic system, refer to Schulten (2005).

3. Robust Data Processing

In this paper, a rich combination of additional data sources is integrated with high frequency time series data to improve data-based fuel consumption and efficiency estimates. Fuel oil properties alone can have an effect of several percents to the fuel consumption which is quite significant when conducting in-depth energy analysis, or when temporal variations in fuel consumption and efficiency are of interest.

For the purposes of this work, it is assumed that fuel oil laboratory sample results, including the BDN data are available. Fig.2 illustrates typical density discrepancy found with laboratory tests and BDN notes with fuel oil density. In practice the difference is negligible, and can be considered to stem from measurement noise.

Even though the fuel oil laboratory tests are conducted for every bunker delivery, there is often no digital indication available onboard to show which fuel is being used at any given time. This is a challenge for offline fuel efficiency analysis since the parameters of the fuel oil can be quite different depending on the fuel type used. For example, density alone can vary over 10% between residual and distillate fuel oils.

Fig. 2: Histogram of fuel density discrepancy of laboratory tests and bunker delivery note data of residual fuel oil samples. The histogram area is normalized to 1. Based on data from fuel oil laboratory sample results.

Determination of fuel type used can take advantage of global emissions regulations. For example, in some ports and emission control areas (ECA) special requirements are set for the fuel. In this research, this kind of approach is used to identify the fuel used. Emission control areas used in the algorithm are presented in Fig.3. The type of fuel oil can be linked to these geographical areas based on sulfur content information provided by the BDN.

Fig. 3: Three ECAs in effect from August 2012: Baltic Sea, North Sea and North America

4. Case Results

As an application of the presented methods, a cruise vessel entering the North Sea is taken as an example. The analysis is based on high frequency time series data including position and speed of the vessel. Furthermore, power and fuel consumption measurements of the diesel engine-generator set (genset) are available. The fuel flow meter measures the volume flow rate, which has to be converted to mass for meaningful efficiency analysis.

In addition to the time series data, data from the BDN and the laboratory tests are available. For this particular case vessel and time period, the distillate fuel oil LCV was not available, and therefore typical value of 42.7 MJ/kg is assumed. Alternative ways of estimating fuel oil LCV are presented in *ISO (2010)*, *Wild (2005)*.

Fig. 4 shows the route of the vessel. Using a combination of several techniques, the used fuel oil (distillate vs. residual) is determined automatically. Fig 5 presents the decimated time series of speed over ground, DG power and fuel flow measurements.

Fig. 4: Vessel route on a map. The fuel oil type used is determined automatically based on several criteria. Red and blue colors refer to residual fuel oil and distillate fuel oil, respectively.

Fig. 5: Speed over ground (SOG), diesel generator (DG) power and fuel consumption from the time interval corresponding to Fig.4.

Fig.5 highlights that the fuel consumption is higher with the distillate fuel oil (blue color) when compared to residual fuel oil (red) with the same power. This observation is investigated in more detail in Fig.6 which shows the results of volumetric specific fuel consumption (Vol-SFC) calculations in a narrow power region around the most typical operating point. The situation is exactly the opposite when fuel oil density is used to determine SFC. With the residual fuel oil, the specific fuel consumption is roughly 7% larger (see Table I), which agrees well with the heat rate balance of Eq.(4) with typical calorific values, *Wild (2005), Rattenbury (2008)*.

Using the heat rate balance equation, Eq.(4), the SFCs of different fuels are matched to a LCV of 42.7 MJ/kg. Fig.6 illustrates that the calibration makes the SFC values much closer to each other. This indicates that the energy conversion efficiency of the engine η_E remains roughly the same even though the fuel changes. The LCV-calibrated SFC is within the typical range quoted in *Wild (2005)*.

Fig. 6: Volumetric specific fuel consumption (left) is significantly higher with distillate fuel oil. The situation is reversed when density is taken into account (center). Final calibration to a common LCV matches the SFC measurements (right). The box and whisker plot is calculated only for data around the typical operating point. Whiskers denote the 1.5 inter-quartile-range, while the box extends from lower to upper quartile.

Table I: Change in median of different engine efficiency figures around the typical operating point when the vessel changes from residual to distillate fuel oil.

	Unit	Change in median [%]
Vol-SFC	L/MWh	+5.0
SFC	kg/MWh	-6.8
SFC @ 42.7MJ/kg	kg/MWh	-1.0
HR	MJ/MWh	-1.0

Fig. 7: Offset between residual fuel oil (red) and distillate fuel oil (blue) SFC figures is removed by using the calibration techniques presented.

The change is visible quite clear in power-SFC scatter and time series visualization, Fig.7. Effectively, the calibration procedure reduced the noise and bias associated with changing fuel oil parameters.

4. Summary

In this research paper, robust techniques for calibrating volume-based fuel consumption measurement in the presence of missing data are presented. The methods are based on rich combination of fuel oil laboratory tests results, bunker delivery note information and time series data.

As a case example, the techniques were applied to a six day time series data, in which the fuel was changed from residual fuel oil to distillate fuel oil. The point of change was determined applying known emission control areas and other factors. Using the calibration procedure, the efficiency difference of 5% (uncalibrated volumetric SFC) between different fuels was reduced to 1% (calibrated SFC). Furthermore, the difference between uncalibrated mass specific emissions was agreement with literature values, confirming the precision of volume flow meter.

Future research will consider additional improvements to the calibration procedure by:

- Improving the automatic detection of the fuel oil used, e.g. by using uncalibrated specific fuel consumptions
- Adding layer of calibration using ambient conditions
- Using the presented method in engine aging and other temporal analyses

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Multiple Simulation Assessments from a Single Ship Product Model

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Abstract

With a focus on naval ships, a technology platform and approach is explored that will allow a varied range of iterative simulations, including strength, hydrostatics, hydrodynamics, fatigue, explosion and radar signatures via the integration of a single product data model with disparate simulation assessment tools. Opportunities and examples that the platform can provide are highlighted; namely the justification for creating a detailed structural model earlier in the design cycle to allow comprehensive assessment of design alternatives in a short timescale.

1. Introduction

This paper describes typical situations and combinations of tools found in the design process and the challenge and strategies when linking these together in a semi-automated software framework to provide naval architects with practical insight into the ship structure and response in a timely fashion. A framework has been constructed using technologies from Lloyd's Register, Martec and the DRDC. The focus is primarily concerned with early ship design and iteration of variations in those designs. The resulting framework is also suitable to be enhanced to start taking account of in-service condition data and form part of an engineering Lifecycle Management (LCM) solution.

The range of disciplines to be investigated in the early design of a ship is large, even more so in the case of naval ships which look to significantly increase the operational envelope in specific areas with each design. To meet the specific needs of analyses such as strength, hydrodynamics, signatures, shock and blast resistance, fatigue, etc., specific software packages have been created and a large number of these tools and associated models build up in specialist design offices.

Fig.1: Design assessment showing common situation of many ship models required for assessments

Often the same ship information is entered multiple times by multiple people into multiple tools. This problem is exacerbated in the situation where multiple designs or design variations are under consideration and yet require the full spectrum of iterative analysis – the timescales and duplicated effort contribute to an already long delivery duration. Variations for design in the early stage can arrive from a number of sources, e.g. a mix of drawings, CAD models, and other simulation results data. Often each analysis software has its own ship modeller, though there may be instances where some of the tools take the same input, e.g. a lines plan or similar.

This process is outlined in Fig.1, showing how 3 design variations and 4 analysis tools can lead to the creation of 9-12 models dependant on whether any of the analysis tools can share an input model.

Lloyd’s Register has experience interfacing software to assess class requirements with those tools used in shipyards to design ships. A systems integration initiative culminated in the development of the ‘interface toolkit’ including the DIME (Data Interface Management Engine) application provided by Lloyd’s Register. The creation of this tool enabled software engineers and naval architects to begin a dialogue around how to transfer data from design into assessment systems. The opportunity to work alongside DRDC provides focus on specific analyses, particularly those involving FEM. Previous projects initiated by DRDC have also undertaken to link commercial ship CAD tools to their in-house analysis tools; joining the shared experiences from DRDC and Lloyd’s Register/Martec will give the resulting framework a balance of bespoke interfaces for specific rule checking and thorough geometry exchange suitable for FEM.

2. Required Naval Ship Analyses

The design and analysis of a new ship goes through many stages of increasing complexity. Earlier identification of design challenges in a design is beneficial and reduces the consequent more costly re-work later.

Fig.2: Design spiral for naval ships (highlighted assessments are the focus of integration and analysis)

The role of Class and of those procuring a design (such as a Navy), is to evaluate and accept the design at various stages of the process. The efficient management of the ship scantling data greatly facilitates both the designer’s and the acceptance authority’s ability to arrive at a complete solution. For naval ship design (and increasingly for commercial design as well), the considerable effort in developing models and undertaking analysis for the complex topics of signatures and survivability are often left until the design is near completion, with mainly a rule-based scantling design defining the vessel for much of the design process. As such it is difficult to incorporate the more complex requirements into an efficient and optimized design. Other modelling requirements such as those to support advanced computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and manoeuvring simulations to arrive at an

efficient and effective hull form, could also potentially be done earlier in the design process if they could be facilitated in a cost and time efficient manner.

Once the initial midship scantling design is achieved via rules calculations, an expanded 3D ship product model (likely created by a commercial CAD package) could be created and used to undertake a number of analysis scenarios summarised in Figs.2 and 3, and briefly described here:

- Creation of full ship coarse mesh finite element model, to verify stress levels, undertake fatigue analysis, or provide initial results for non-traditional structure
- Ultimate Strength Assessment at chosen locations (USA-2D cross-section models)
- Creation of detailed FEMs to further refine fatigue design
- Hydrodynamic models to assess sea keeping, manoeuvrability and hull form efficiency
- Specific models to address operations such as helicopter landing (airwake)
- Simulation models to assess efficient layout for operations (weapons loading, cargo and boat handling)
- Signature models to assess radar cross section, infrared, and acoustic signatures
- Models (which may be FEA models) to assess resistance to underwater shock, blast, fragmentation weapons loads
- Models to assess a cathodic protection design
- Residual strength models to assess the effects of specific damage scenarios

Fig.3: Selection of analyses of concern to naval vessels

3. Master Ship Product Model

A 3D ship model capable of supporting the analysis in scope is required (hopefully also additional analysis as required). This model we will call the Ship Product Model (SPM). The SPM is a detailed model of the ship suitable for design and build and increasingly through-life purposes. The SPM will be produced using a commercial ship CAD system used and validated through extensive use by industry. These systems contain robust logic for managing the hierarchical/topological connections between structural data with the most sophisticated systems having evolved to support production including machinery, piping and other systems linked via the structural coordinates.

From an analysis point of view there is a risk that as the design evolves the models can become too complex and it is difficult to transfer data containing only the required information, i.e. at the correct ‘granularity’ for the analysis in question. The ability to create export models for additional specific analysis was not the primary intention of many tools, although this is starting to be considered by some vendors. As such, some additional effort is usually required to ‘massage’/manipulate or extend the geometry data to be suitable for translation to other uses.

Fig.4: SmartMarine 3D ship product data model

4. Model Analyses to be obtained from the SPM

4.1. Various FEM from the Global Finite Element Model

This type of model has to be able to be derived successfully from the SPM. In this solution the meshing routines are performed by in-house meshers. The Global FEM model is well known and is used to establish global (or field) stress levels at a higher order of accuracy than rules calculations. It usually consists of finite element mesh sizes on the order of frame and stiffener spacing dimensions, or larger. It is often used to look for potential problem areas in terms of high stress, and to define boundary conditions for more detailed models of smaller areas (top-down FEA). The global FE model is also used for hull vibration analysis which requires a mass distribution in addition to structural information. The vibration (or dynamic) global FE model can also be used for shock and blast analysis and some signatures models such as structurally radiated acoustic signature. Depending on the type of dynamic analysis, the added fluid mass from the surrounding water must also be included. Some finite element packages have the ability to auto-generate a fluid mesh, which in some cases is similar to the hydrodynamic mesh described below. The global FE model is probably the most versatile model in the ship designer's toolkit, as it can be used for a broad range of analysis types. Fig.5 shows a typical global finite element mesh. This model was translated through the Data Interface Management Engine (DIME) system described in this paper from the SmartMarine 3D SPM data to the Lloyd's Register Martec TRIDENT finite element model shown here.

Fig.5: Typical global finite element model produced in the "Trident" package

4.2. Detailed Finite Element Model

Localised fine mesh finite element models are used mainly to investigate fatigue crack initiation at the design stage. They may also be derived from SPM and possibly specialized mesh refinement tools.

Fig.6: Typical detail finite element model used for fatigue crack initiation analysis

The model shown in Fig.6 is typical of a 'graded' mesh used to develop stress information at a hot spot which is then used in a Miner's sum approach to determine fatigue life. The forcing function to create the stress value comes from forces or displacements applied to the model boundaries. These are assumed to cycle through a range of amplitudes derived from the expected sea states and ship's operational profile. Development and analysis of the detail FE model analysis are usually undertaken within the finite element program used for the global analysis. Additional information on the detail and material fatigue properties are required which have to be supplied from external sources, or could be stored in the single ship database for common structural details and materials.

4.3. Ultimate Strength Model

Ultimate strength is defined as the maximum hull girder bending moment that the ship can withstand including the effects of plasticity and buckling collapse of stiffened panels. There are several packages which require two dimensional cross section data for input (plate thicknesses, longitudinal bulkheads and longitudinal stiffener data) as shown in Fig.7. Analysis proceeds by determining the elasto-plastic collapse behaviour (load-shortening curves) of individual longitudinally stiffened panels and then integrating the resulting cross section forces to determine the hull girder bending moment. The load-shortening curves are often developed in pre-determined databases for the scantlings of interest, or can be developed through nonlinear FEA of the stiffened panels. The ultimate strength analysis itself is not a FEA and hence is run very rapidly. The cross-sectional data could be easily derived from SPM data or can be derived from a FE model of the hull as shown in Fig.7. This type of analysis lends itself to assessing the residual strength of the hull girder after damage, as structure can easily be removed for analysis. The limitation of this analysis is it assumes failure to occur between frames so does not take into account global stiffened grillage response.

Fig.7: Two-dimensional cross section data for ultimate strength analysis

4.4. Hydrodynamic Model

Hydrodynamic models require only the part of the ship which interfaces with the sea, and thus are fairly simple compared to finite element models. A full ship mass distribution is also required. The coarseness of the panels depends on the ship type and hydrodynamic analysis being undertaken but for typical naval vessels can be at least as coarse as the global finite element mesh or coarser. The models can be derived from the global FE model by extracting the 'wetted surface' elements, or can be meshed from scratch using hull lines of form. The hydrodynamic model, Fig.8, is used to assess ship motions and dynamic pressure loads.

Fig.8: Typical hydrodynamic panel mesh

4.5. Shock and blast models

The design of naval vessels, and in some cases certain commercial vessels, requires an assessment of their ability to withstand weapons loads, or accidental explosions. The models required for this vary from geometric descriptions of compartments for analytical equation based assessment, to 3D FE models, often the global FE model including mass description. The modelling of mass distribution often has to be more refined and include shock isolation mounts for major weight components such as engines. For more complex response to shock and blast loads, coupling to specialized loading codes is often done to model the shock or air blast pressure and interaction with the structure. Underwater shock loads also produce a whipping response from the cyclic collapse of the gas bubble. Computational fluid dynamics is used for very specialized modelling of the shock wave.

4.6. Signature models

Signatures models are of two basic types; those requiring only a coarse description of the outer surfaces of the vessel for radar cross section and infrared signatures, or those requiring a complete description of the structure for transmission of structurally radiated acoustic noise. The latter is often satisfied by the global FE model and mass distribution, in addition to specialized acoustic fluid elements to analyze the extent of the radiated acoustic pressure from the vessel. The former could be easily generated from the SPM geometric data, as they are not FE models. These models will require additional data to model the signature properties and excitation sources (heat, vibration, etc).

4.7. Simulation/Operation Models

Extensive computing power and visualization capabilities are bringing simulation technologies (often real time) to the ship designer's toolkit. These can be used to model such things as the effects of layout on the ability to optimize the moving of cargo or conduct other operations on the vessel, to studying the effects of ship motions on such operations as replenishment at sea, boat launch and recovery, helicopter landing, etc. The model requirements are dependent on the simulation but are usually fairly coarse geometric models of the visible structure and components. For ship motions these would be tied to the hydrodynamic models. Ultimately these simulation capabilities would allow designers to 'plug and play' different component modules to evaluate various design options

4.8. Cathodic Protection Models

As an example of another specialized analysis model, Fig.9 shows the results of a cathodic protection analysis, where, again, all structure in contact with sea water is modelled in a geometric sense including, the propellers, shafting and rudders. The aim is to design an effective layout of sacrificial anodes.

Fig.9: Potential contours on an example hull (all 12 hull anodes and 12 rudder anodes)

5. Multiple Simulation Assessment Approach

The objective of the project described here was to design a framework that facilitates the production and management of all types of input models required for naval and commercial vessel design analysis, in particular, allowing some of the more complex analyses to be undertaken more easily and earlier in the design process. The optimal solution would be required to:

- 1) Import models from a range of commercially available ship CAD packages
- 2) Facilitate inclusion of multiple analysis tools of varying degrees of complexity and sophistication, and
- 3) Clearly show users where additional data is required and be able to append that data to the core model.

The framework which is being developed is described by the following basic steps, Fig.10:

- a) Variations for design in the early stage can arrive from a number of different sources and organisations. The submission may be a mix of drawings (paper plans), some CAD geometry and simulation models.
- b) A single ship modelling tool is used to create the master model for the ship under analysis - the Ship Product Model (SPM). The ship modelling tool is a software package that has the power and functionality to model complex ship structures efficiently. The ability to take ship models from a selection of vendors would be seen as advantageous to the solution.
- c) The geometry is translated to a neutral format that serves as the in-house backbone to all assessment applications. An orchestration layer should be provided that manipulates/translates the data to the downstream analysis applications.

- d) Any further information required by the analysis application is made transparent to the user at this stage depending on the analysis that is desired. This component as well as being responsible for managing a single geometry representation that is acceptable to the various analysis tools has to orchestrate data amongst the supported analysis tools and be responsible for ensuring required datasets are present. The ship geometry alone is not sufficient to undertake analysis and additional parameters are required.
- e) Many analyses such as FEA will require the model geometry be discretized before being passed downstream. The mesher and boundary conditions tool facilitates generating a mesh for the model geometry as well as application of boundary conditions and general loads (some specialized loading may be performed further downstream). This tool ensures physical traits (such as material properties, thicknesses, stiffener scantlings, etc.) are maintained in the discretized representation and passed to the analysis.
- f) The requirement of the framework is that it be designed with sufficient flexibility to cope with changes at the analysis tools layer, including adding new tools. Where the analysis tools are created in house, they can be modified to ensure maximum compatibility; third party tools would be selected on the basis of their API's to allow data to be transferred.

Fig. 10: Early design assessment – overview of steps required in optimised process

5.1. Data Exchange and Re-Use

There are three aspects to exchange:

- 1) Structural geometry – the representation of the physical structures.
- 2) Additional attributes to support the individual applications.
- 3) Processing and manipulation of data to meet the individual analysis tools.

A framework that has a chance of success has to be designed with flexibility in mind from the outset and with the ability to be extensible; the system must be modular and changes in the requirements of one system must not affect another. Another important requirement is that the assessment process be repeatable; given the same starting data, one should be able to generate the same analysis models.

5.1.1. Structural geometry

Experience showed that the optimal solution will use a variety of techniques to get the required geometry. In addition to parameter based geometry often required by classification rules; for FEM based analysis, the solution will be more powerful if it adopts best practice in the industry e.g. IGES / STEP / SAT formats. The solution however needs to be able to accurately place these surface formats at the correct 3D locations and logic is required for this. Challenges with geometry exchange are highlighted in the “Approach in Practice Section”.

5.1.2 Data Models

In software concerning data exchange, the data model and the allowable components/structure that can feed off this are key. The Lloyd’s Register DIME/Interface Toolkit (Data Interface Management Engine) was designed to assist interfacing to disparate components, it exposes a single data model which can be extended as new functionality / new data types are required. Data elements have been consolidated across the applications resulting in a single common data model. This allows a single instance of third party data the potential to be passed to numerous Lloyd's Register applications and in this project extended to meet the needs of DRDC applications.

Fig. 11: Patrol vessel as shown in the neutral geometry format of the DIME

5.1.3 DIME – Data Interface Management Engine (The Orchestration Layer)

DIME has a number of possible methods of operation. The ideal state is to run in the background, providing relevant progress information as data passes between applications but alerting the user if there is missing/incorrect data. If the user chooses to enter the data in DIME at this time, the data will be stored and the user will not be prompted on subsequent data transfers. The DIME, Fig.11, keeps a comprehensive transaction log with timestamp, source application, location and target application information.

5.1.4. Fidelity and Idealisation

One of the biggest challenges to realising seamless re-use of a single model across a diverse assortment of analyses is the variation in model fidelity required by each. For instance, a high fidelity model (including minute details such as small penetrations, end cuts, brackets, etc.) would be undesirable for global FEA as it would make the analysis model much larger (i.e. slower to process) than necessary as well as likely yield too many local effects to capture global response. Conversely, a low fidelity model (including only major plates and perhaps a simplified representation of stiffeners) may not include enough detail to calculate the local stress fields required to accurately predict fatigue crack initiation.

In most cases, ship product modelling systems are capable of creating very high-fidelity models. If no effort is made by the vendor to simplify the fidelity then considerable effort must be put into the DIME layer to simplify the detail for analysis. Perhaps counter-intuitively, this is still by no means an easy task, particularly if the expectation is that it be done automatically. Various geometry-centric heuristics can be employed, such as removal of detail below a threshold scale, but the most robust approaches leverage object geometry, semantics and context. Knowing a particular object represents a stiffener in a given location (e.g. a vertical bulkhead stiffener between two decks) allows one to apply more suitable simplification algorithms to it than if it was simply considered “a collection of relatively long and narrow geometric faces.”

Some SPM products already leverage the wealth of model knowledge they hold natively to support querying objects at a desired level of fidelity. This introduces the possibility to handle model fidelity customisation upstream of the DIME application itself. Others do not, however, necessitating that the DIME provide at least some capability in this area. Fortunately, data typically comes to DIME including some semantic information, which can be combined with its geometry processing capabilities to achieve a solution. If no semantic information is available to DIME, it will have to present the user tools to intervene in the process and guide the outcome.

Even with the capability to customise the model fidelity level to suit a given analysis, one must still know what that level should be. It is here that in-depth knowledge of all analysis types is necessary in order to prescribe a target fidelity level for each. That knowledge has to then be turned into algorithms that can be integrated into the final solution. Once this is done, the system can automatically determine and apply the appropriate algorithm to prepare input based on the user’s choice of analysis type.

5.1.5. SPM Model Augmentation

While SPMs include a great deal of model detail, they focus mainly on what is necessary to design and manufacture the vessel. Data pertinent to specific niche analyses, particularly of naval concern, may therefore not be considered by the SPMs themselves. Examples include the advanced material properties required for various types of signatures analysis, including permittivity, conductivity, permeability, magnetic properties, etc., Fig.12. As this data lies outside the typical area of concern for the SPM products, it seems unlikely that they will ever become part of their native data schema, and as such an alternative mechanism to deal with them is required. One such mechanism is here forth termed SPM model augmentation. It basically involves introducing a virtual layer between the SPM model itself and the orchestration module wherein data queries can be intercepted and augmented

with additional data. From the orchestration module, it should appear as if the augmented SPM data is served by the SPM itself, whereas in reality the intermediate layer is intercepting the orchestrator's queries and augmenting the return values with further data.

In order for this mechanism to work, various requirements must be met:

- 1) The augmentation layer must provide a means to persist the additional data, likely using its own database, Fig.12.
- 2) The layer must have a way to associate the additional data with SPM entities such that the association itself is persistent. This could take the form of associating the additional data to SPM entities by unique ID, provided the entities have such IDs. If the entities lack unique IDs, or the IDs are subject to change for whatever reason, alternative ways to make the association would be necessary. The challenge will be to ensure the augmented data is properly managed in the face of changes to the SPM model (e.g. changing entities, deleting entities, etc.).

Fig. 12: Extensions made to the DIME Data model

Once the augmentation layer is in place, it must be populated with data. This would perhaps most naturally be done from the orchestration module by, for example, introducing tools into DIME to expose these data elements. An alternative approach, however, would be to attempt to “push” data from the analysis level upstream to be persisted at the augmentation layer. The benefit to this approach would be that the analysis tools already contain interfaces for collecting and manipulating these specialized data. However, since it would likely be undesirable to introduce logic in the analysis packages themselves to push the data upstream, the logic would likely reside, again, at the orchestration level in the form of routines that “pull” the data upwards.

5.1.6. Automated Mesh Generation

Automatic mesh generation has been studied heavily for the past two decades, but still presents challenges (in this context, mesh generation is considered to refer to surface meshes, not volumetric meshes – i.e. tri/quadrangles, not tetra/hexahedrals). While the process of generating a mesh given well-behaved atomic geometric regions (closed loops, actually) is mostly well in hand, decomposing an overall vessel model into well-behaved regions remains difficult. The requisite step to generating a well-connected structural FE model is connecting the disparate geometric entities through a process called imprinting. During imprinting, entity faces and edges are split and merged based on the spatial connections and intersections of the entities with their neighbours. The process is computationally

intensive, and its success often depends on various factors. Firstly, the robustness of the geometry kernel performing the imprinting operations plays a large role; the better the kernel, the more likely it will obtain solutions for the more difficult outlier-cases. Secondly, the quality of the geometry to which the process is being applied makes a difference; poorly-formed geometry can often confound the kernel to the point that it produces undesirable results or no results at all. Finally, the two are actually related – a kernel will usually deal better with its own geometry than with geometry originating in another kernel, as it is intimately aware of its own tolerances, peculiarities and limitations.

Since many types of analyses are fundamentally mesh-based, the integrated system must indeed surpass these difficulties and provide a robust mesh generation capability. One can strive to eliminate the difficulties but soon realize it is a futile pursuit. An alternative approach is to introduce an intrinsic tolerance into the imprinting process, hereafter termed ‘fuzzy imprinting’. Fuzzy imprinting considers all model faces and edges to have an associated tolerance, which itself can be relatively large in comparison to typical geometry kernel tolerances (i.e. a few mm vs. a fraction of a mm). Once fuzzy imprinting is applied to yield a fully connected model, within tolerance, the mesh is generated and actual discrepancies are removed by local mesh adjustments. This approach is found to be very robust and able to deliver the critical capability to the system.

Fig.13: Project solution

Fig 14: Meshed model shown in Trident Modeller with hull removed

Fig 15: Meshed model shown in Trident Modeller with hull ready for analysis

Fig.16: Transverse section of the model taken from DIME into a LR rules checking program

Fig.17: Acoustic signature calculations from within Trident AVAST module; SPM derived model

6. Results

A multiple assessment system comprising the components shown in Fig.13 has been constructed and been used to validate the approach. To date the analysis system created by Lloyd's Register / Martec / DRDC as shown in Fig.13 has been used to convert a SmartMarine3D and Aveva Marine CAD model of a Patrol Vessel to a 3D finite element model using the Martec TRIDENT FEA package, Figs.14 and 15, and to the LR Rules Calculation software, Fig.16. Subsequently the model was passed to the Trident modules for acoustic signatures and cathodic protection as shown in Figs.17 and 18. Work continues to further automate the connection and storing of individual parameters for each of the detailed assessments within the DIME format as described in section 5.1.5.

Fig.18: Cathodic Protection Analysis within Trident CPBEM package

7. Conclusions

We have described the multitude of complex ship analyses that are required to be undertaken on naval ships and details of a framework for facilitating the creation of several different ship design analysis models from a common single database. The goals are to make this as flexible as possible by accepting data from several different sources initially (different commercial CAD ship design packages) and to make as wide a variety of analyses options available earlier in the design process.

The DIME (Data Integration Management Engine) under development by Lloyd's Register and DRDC has been illustrated and demonstrated by translating two commercial Ship CAD models to rule checking class software and to the Trident suite for assessment by means of creating a global finite element model, signatures model and cathodic model. It is planned that after actively identifying the required data needed for the breadth of assessments, discussions will continue with the ship CAD vendors where appropriate to ascertain whether the ship CAD tools could provide additional data at source.

The framework detailed has been shown to support multiple analyses of a highly specialised nature, all of which were derived from a Single Product Model. The results from these assessment tools are more rapidly available and will therefore enable engineers to more effectively iterate the SPM to the optimal design in the least possible time.

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Democratization of Virtual Reality in Shipbuilding

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Abstract

In theory, 3D Virtual Reality (VR) models provide numerous benefits to shipbuilders. Many authors have highlighted potential use cases including design review, customer review, supply chain collaboration, project scheduling and shop floor 3D. However, in practice the technology, including generation of the virtual models from existing CAD tools, is too costly, complex, and rigid to be implemented across all segments of the industry. Fortunately, a method now exists to dramatically simplify the creation of VR models, making it practical for more people to utilize VR. This democratization of the technology has made VR's theoretical benefits a reality.

1. VR benefits often unattainable

When a shipyard implements a new technology, accessibility and transparency is often limited. Therefore, the technology does not get utilized by all levels and roles within an organization which lessens the potential power of the solution. Such is the case with Virtual Reality (VR) and related 3D visualization tools. The potential benefits are seldom realized due to a number of factors and unless these factors are addressed, VR is unlikely to be widely adopted within all areas of a company. On the other hand, if the technology is made cost effective, the chances of it being purchased are increased. If it is easy to implement, it is more likely to be widely deployed and if it is simple to use and is powerful and practical, the chance of it being adopted go up.

Indeed, if these key components are present, experience has shown that the demand for VR usage can cascade throughout an enterprise. In fact, percolating upwards is sometimes a better analogy because if the right factors are in place, in certain scenarios, the drive to implement VR has come from line workers rather than top down management. Executives have sometimes found that workers are using VR tools to facilitate production, training, marketing and other aspects of shipbuilding in innovative ways that were not even conceived of by upper management. Executives have found that if they allow workers to have access to intuitive, powerful and flexible tools that are interoperable with other programs being utilized, then the workers will find ways to use them. But if the technology solution has a variety of weaknesses, the tools will sit unused or dramatically underutilized; the promised advantages of Virtual Reality will remain virtual for the majority of those who would otherwise benefit.

2. Definition of Virtual Reality in a Shipbuilding Context

Before going further, it is important to clarify a key term. For the purposes of this paper, what is meant by Virtual Reality is a computer simulated, highly immersive 3D environment. In a shipbuilding context, it refers to the ability to “fly-through” a semi-realistic 3D model of a ship, navigating up, down and around from side to side, zooming in and out from different angles as if one was playing a video game. And just like with a video game, there should be a level of interaction between this virtual world and the viewer that goes beyond the simple 3D representation of the environment. In a shipbuilding context, one would want to be able to easily stop, query, and determine a wealth of attributes about the various objects being viewed.

As noted in *Góngora (2011)*, options included in VR tools are, among others:

- Interactive navigation through the 3D model with different navigation modes
- Handling of very large 3D models

- Selection of objects or group of objects (according to build strategy) and display of technological and graphical attributes
- Marking-up of objects and addition of commentaries for further navigations or modifications in the 3D model
- Calculation of ship coordinates, distances, angles, clearances between objects
- Illumination of 3D model according to actual luminance on board
- Assignment of textures, colors and transparencies to objects
- Collisions checking
- Deletion and invisibility of objects or group of objects
- Movement of objects and groups of objects (linear and rotations)
- Handling of human models and checking of ergonomics
- Simulations or escape routes and dismantling routes of equipment
- Simulation of fire and smoke conditions
- Creation, storing and reproduction of trajectories
- Generation of Video files

3. Benefits of Virtual Reality

As is perhaps obvious from the previous list, there are multiple use cases for Virtual Reality in a shipbuilding context. All of these uses are derivative of the fact that VR has an unparalleled ability to be used as a communication tool since everything is clearer in three dimensions. While much detail can be shared via 2D drawings, interpreting these drawings requires knowledge of marine-specific symbology and the ability to translate in one's mind two dimensions into three. This is an acquired skill that takes extensive training to develop.

As is noted in *Pal (2011)*, "...2D drawings in many cases (like complex outfitting assembly drawings, and block assembly drawings for complex steel structures) require extended time for workers to understand the assembly situation, and inherit the probability of misinterpretations."

On the other hand, flying through a VR environment enables a less experienced individual to see a high level of detail and intuitively understand what things look like. Virtual Reality, as its name suggests, is simply far closer to reality.

This makes it a useful tool during contract design, engineering, design review, customer review, supply chain collaboration, project scheduling (including assembly sequencing), training and simulations. Several of these advantages have been highlighted in a plethora of academic papers in the past. For example, at ICCAS 2011 alone, there were multiple papers extolling use cases for 3D Virtual Reality. *Góngora (2011)* mentioned VR's usage in the efficient design of outfitting and machinery spaces. *Baguio (2011)* extolled the quality improvement in hull and outfitting designs that came about from using 3D model review. *Lödding et al.(2011)* talked about assembly planning simulation using VR while *Tozzi and Zini (2011)* described how Virtual Reality could be used to assess naval operations through HLA (High Level Architecture) based simulation.

Other authors have noted how VR is an effective tool for supply chain collaboration amongst disparate organizations using a variety of CAD systems. Additionally, to cite a previous COMPIT paper from the authors of this essay, VR can also be used in shop floor 3D applications whereby workers spontaneously check VR models at terminals on the floor so as to gain more information which helps them understand assembly requirements and other production scenarios, *Morais et al. (2011)*. A number of these advantages will be further highlighted in case studies later in this paper.

4. Challenges of using VR

Unfortunately though, despite all of the potential benefits, there are several challenges preventing the adoption of Virtual Reality throughout the shipyard. These challenges can be classified into two areas,

corresponding with two types of VR programs. The first class of VR software is composed of tools that are developed by an existing vendor of shipbuilding specific CAD software. The second class of VR software is made up of those tools that have been developed for a broad range of industries by a major CAD vendor that does not provide a shipbuilding specific CAD solution. Difficulties with both of these software types will be highlighted separately below.

4.1. Shipbuilding specific VR tools

Let us start with shipbuilding specific VR tools. Many of the shipbuilding specific CAD vendors offer proprietary VR tools that are tightly coupled with their own CAD programs. Typically these tools are targeted, in terms of usability and capability, at the engineering staff within the shipyard. They offer a set of tools demanded specifically by the shipbuilding industry, and when implemented successfully can effectively solve a certain set of challenges within the shipyard.

4.1.1. Complexity of Implementation

A common use of this class of VR tools is in the development of a static, formal design review environment. These environments involve the use of high end 3D projection equipment and technology that allows for simultaneous multi-user interaction. In a paper regarding the application of VR to shipbuilding *Alonso (2012)* cited a dedicated VR room as one of the most common applications of VR technology, and the place in which “Most parts of the applications of the VR to shipbuilding can be carried out.” This type of implementation is undoubtedly valuable in the ways mentioned in the paper but the accessibility to the individual in the shipyard and application to their particular challenges is questionable. Additionally, implementations of this complexity and cost are achievable only by larger shipyards or those involved in high dollar naval vessels. While the application of this class of VR tool to this type of high-end implementation does not preclude the possibility of much lighter weight implementations, it does show the prevailing mind-set around typical applications of the technologies.

4.1.2. Complexity of Use

In addition to the complexity of many of the implementations of this class of VR technology, the products are often difficult for those without engineering backgrounds to use effectively. They often have an engineering pedigree which benefits the engineering department but causes challenges with regard to the “democratization” or widespread usage of the technology as advocated by us.

In order to capitalize on the widespread adoption of VR by all areas of the shipyard, those who have first-hand knowledge of the challenges in their area must have the ability to apply VR technology to those challenges without the involvement of an intermediary from IT or engineering. This is particularly important if the desire is to promote innovative applications of VR in all phases of the shipbuilding process, rather than just those approaches that have been pre-determined by a smaller number of individuals with the required knowledge. Ease of use has to be a paramount consideration in order for a variety of departments within a shipyard to realize the benefits of VR.

4.1.3. Limited Set of Capabilities

Additionally, innovation in this area requires a certain flexibility and level of capabilities to exist in VR tools. Many of the examples in this class have the minimum set of capabilities required to solve a known set of challenges for the shipbuilding industry but it can be argued that, unlike those VR tools developed for a wider audience, these tools lack the depth of capability to be routinely applied in innovative and unintended ways. This should not be surprising. While shipbuilding is a global industry and is of significant size, it is not by any means unlimited in scope. This is especially true when compared to the size of the general manufacturing, or AEC (architecture, engineering and construction) industries. This means that software developed for other larger industries will often be more likely to develop new features than software developed specifically for shipbuilding.

4.1.4. Limited Variation of Platforms

The industry specific nature of the VR tools in this class also introduces another challenge. As related technologies including mobile and cloud computing become part of our everyday lives, the expectations of potential users of VR tools encompasses these technologies. The limited size of the market for shipbuilding specific VR tools, compounded by the comparatively large number of vendors in the industry, make introduction of these capabilities in existing tools challenging, at least in a way that is affordable to all segments of the industry. Unfortunately the ideas and approaches considered for the application of VR tools outside of, and even within, engineering will more and more often involve these technologies and will go unimplemented if they remain unavailable.

4.1.5. Cost Effectiveness

This leads to the next challenge: cost effectiveness. The combination of the challenges in the preceding sections, particularly: the scope and complexity of target implementations and the industry specific nature of this class of VR tools, leads to implementations that are of a significant cost and yet do not realize benefit across the entire organization. For some organizations, namely very large shipyards and naval shipbuilders, this cost may not be prohibitive and the value obtained may justify that cost regardless. For example Virtualis, www.virtalis.com, has a case study of BAE Systems workers using shop floor 3D cabins with dedicated personnel to help build submarines. However, due to the costs involved, implementation is less likely on lower dollar value projects or in many shipyards that are not in that exclusive first tier.

4.1.6. Lack of Integration with other systems

Then there is the problem of interoperability. Any form of communication presupposes at least two parties exchanging information using some sort of shared medium. The problem in a shipbuilding context is that there are so many different software tools utilized. This issue is troublesome enough within a single organization but is compounded when more than one company is involved. A good description of this challenge is shown in *Pal (2011)*.

“Besides CAD/CAM, many other software tools are used by shipyards for activities like production planning, project management, and ERP. As a ship enters service, yet more software tools are used for applications like operational performance, configuration management, etc. Each CAD system has its own data format optimized for its own functions. As a result, there are many kinds of data structures and data representation schemes. CAD geometric models are represented by different schemes like 3D graphic entities, 3D wireframe, 3D surface models, or solid models....”

“The shipbuilding industry also has the involvement of a huge supply chain which includes design agents, marine equipment manufacturers, weapons manufacturers, other shipyards, block fabricators, system integrators, etc. Each of these organizations would be using their own design (CAD/CAM/CAE) systems which in many instances are different from the systems used by the shipyard...”

In order to communicate then, a VR system capable of accepting information from a variety of different applications is therefore required. Unfortunately however, many VR systems used in the shipbuilding industry lack the ability to easily import data from other systems. *Pal (2011)* therefore recommends the use of a VR system with a neutral format containing the following characteristics:

- a.) Disclosure of format specification
- b.) Wide-spread use of the format
- c.) File size (small)
- d.) Data security (high)
- e.) Application in other future engineering activities
- f.) Long term data archival capabilities

This approach solves a number of problems but brings challenges as addressed in the next sections.

4.2. Neutral Vendor VR Tools

The other class of VR tools that has been commonly adopted in the industry is from non-shipbuilding specific vendors. These solutions are typically of a lower cost (though not necessarily more cost effective), are scalable in terms of size and scope of implementation, have a high degree of capability and are accessible on a large number of platforms. These VR tools can read a wide range of generic 3D formats, and even attribute information in some cases. However, these tools are not without their challenges, some of which can only be overcome by the application of additional cost and effort.

4.2.1. Lack of Shipbuilding Specific Capabilities

While the VR tools in this class can often read enough general purpose 3D formats to facilitate the visualization of the 3D model, the rich attributes and intelligence required to satisfy the definition of “VR for shipbuilding” are not generally available out of the box. Without this information, many of the activities for which VR is used in shipbuilding, including interrogating attributes of the model during a design review, simulating the assembly sequence for the project, and validating collisions in the 3D model, simply cannot be accomplished.

Due to the flexibility and depth of capability inherent in these general VR tools, it is often possible to incorporate the required level of intelligence into the 3D model and apply the tools in the required ways. However, it should be noted that this is usually only accomplished by the liberal application of software development and IT which unfortunately results in a system with significantly increased complexity, scope and cost.

Lödning et al. (2011) elaborate on this complexity including the various steps involved in the process such as defining required data size and data quality, conversion of 3D CAD into the VR software format, testing model data and checking for errors, reduction of data for larger models in VR software, preparing model data, structuring in groups, and adjusting materials. They further go on to show how specialized software (ViP Composer) can be implemented that loads metadata into the VR software and connects the metadata to the required geometry. Obviously this takes time.

4.2.2. Disconnected Workflows

The time and complexity of creating comprehensive VR models using this class of VR tools leads to another problem. The delays, combined with the rapid pace of shipbuilding projects today, lead to the information in the resulting VR model often being out of date before it is viewed. Therefore, to be truly effective, and to ensure trust in and subsequent use of the technology, this class of VR tools actually needs to be tightly coupled with the shipbuilding specific CAD software that is being used. While this is possible and has been accomplished in specific cases where the cost and complexity of doing so was outweighed by the benefits, it is by no means a common occurrence.

5. Overcoming the Challenges

Keeping in mind all of the previous difficulties with both types of VR programs, it would seem then that an answer to these challenges would be a shipbuilding specific CAD/CAM solution developed by one of the major CAD vendors who also produce a class leading general purpose VR toolset. This would combine the best of both worlds.

5.1. Overview of ShipConstructor

An argument can be made that ShipConstructor is one of the only, if not the only, shipbuilding solutions that overcomes all of the challenges mentioned above. In order to delve further into how it does so, an understanding of what ShipConstructor truly is will be required.

In simple terms ShipConstructor is a solution engineered specifically for shipbuilding and built on AutoCAD technology from Autodesk, with a database backend that stores the complete 3D product model including all geometry, intelligence, shipbuilding standards and attributes. This simple explanation however can be misleading. A common misperception is that ShipConstructor is simply a set of tools that run inside the AutoCAD environment and allow individual shipbuilding operations to be performed against an AutoCAD drawing. The reality however is much deeper. ShipConstructor is as enmeshed into the fabric of AutoCAD as any other Autodesk product that is based on AutoCAD. Examples of these other applications include AutoCAD Plant, AutoCAD P&ID, AutoCAD Electrical, and AutoCAD Mechanical.

This depth of integration has tremendous implications for implementations of shipbuilding solutions based on ShipConstructor. Specifically, every Autodesk product which is available and has some connection into the world of AutoCAD treats ShipConstructor, and the intelligent ship model behind it, as if it were an Autodesk product. This includes virtually all of the products Autodesk offers for 3D visualization, simulation and VR. These products not only allow for the visualization of the ShipConstructor 3D model in real-time, they also allow for the interrogation of part, stock and standard level information from the model in question.

This combination makes ShipConstructor (despite utilizing technology from various vendors) essentially a shipbuilding specific solution from a major CAD vendor with a class leading VR and 3D visualization toolset, and thus satisfies the requirements of a solution as proposed earlier in the paper.

5.2. Overview of the VR Capabilities of a ShipConstructor-based Solution

To further validate an Autodesk based industry specific solution like ShipConstructor as one that overcomes these challenges, one must look into the depth of the 3D visualization and VR capabilities offered. While Autodesk has a number of visualization and VR technologies that work with ShipConstructor models including Autodesk Design Review, Design Review Mobile, Autodesk Showcase, Autodesk Inventor Publisher, and Inventor Publisher Mobile, this paper will focus on Autodesk Navisworks as the primary VR tool used with ShipConstructor.

5.2.1. Autodesk Navisworks

Autodesk Navisworks is the flagship product in Autodesk's range of visualization and VR products. Navisworks allows users to walk through a real-time view of the ShipConstructor product model, along with a multitude of other model formats. It also offers an extensive range of capabilities to interact with the environment.

5.2.2. Large Data Sets

One of the key requirements of any VR tool used for shipbuilding is the ability to handle very large datasets in real time. The visualization of a complete ship model is beyond the typical requirements of virtually any other industry with the possible exception of the building industry. Navisworks has been used extensively in the AEC (architecture, engineering, and construction) industry as well as for the visualization of major navy shipbuilding programs, Fig.1.

5.2.3. Ease of Use

Earlier in the paper it was argued that a prime requirement to promote the democratization of virtual reality in the shipbuilding industry was the availability of tools that were intuitive. Navisworks was originally developed for a wide cross section of industries and has been built with simplicity as a key requirement. Additionally, the ShipConstructor model can be viewed directly in Navisworks so there is little to no knowledge of ShipConstructor or other technical knowledge required to create the virtual reality model. Any user can begin interrogating the virtual reality model in little to no time.

Fig. 1: A complete ShipConstructor model of a jackup rig in Autodesk Navisworks

5.2.4. Ease of Implementation

While Navisworks can be implemented into dedicated VR rooms complete with stereoscopic 3D viewing of the ship model, the most common scenario involves the Navisworks technology in some form being available on every device within the shipyard environment. In any case, the software is installed via a consumer grade software installation process and requires absolutely no configuration by the end user in order to begin exploring ShipConstructor models. This enables access to Navisworks capability wherever it is needed to solve particular challenges.

5.2.5. Mobile Platforms

Navisworks is used in a variety of industries and by a very deep and broad user base. This combines with the changing expectations of the average user around accessibility to information on mobile platforms to provide Autodesk with both the resources and demonstrated need to make Navisworks technology available on mobile devices. What this means is that ShipConstructor models can be viewed on commonly available tablet devices with the same fidelity as they can in the engineering office. In addition to navigating the model this includes the availability of all properties from ShipConstructor and the ability to measure and control visibility of various portions of the model.

The ability to access these tools in ways that fit the way users interact in their daily lives bridges the gap between accessibility to the technology and availability to the benefits that it brings.

5.2.6. Interoperability

In an industry where collaboration with the supply chain, and the myriad of CAD tools they use, is common place, a key consideration for the adoption of a VR tool is the ability to consume CAD information from virtually any source. Navisworks can read CAD data, and point cloud data, in many formats including: DWG, DXF, MicroStation (SE, J, V8 & XM), 3D Studio, ACIS SAT, CIS/2, DWF/DWFX, FBX, IFC, IGES, Pro/ENGINEER, Inventor, Informatix MicroGDS, JT Open, PDS Design Review, Parasolids, RVM, SketchUp, STEP AP214, AP203E2, STL, VRML, Siemens NX, Dassault Systèmes CATIA®, Dassault Systemes Solidworks®, Graphisoft® ArchiCAD® 14, 15, ASCII Laser File, Faro, Leica, Riegler, Trimble, Z+F.

Additionally, VR tools can also play a critical role in determining the producibility of a given assembly sequence, or the impact of specific schedule changes to the manufacturing process. However to use it in this way requires access within the VR tool to the CAD model, the assembly sequence and the production schedule. Even where dedicated shipbuilding CAD tools are used, these are often in a variety of products. With Navisworks, the ShipConstructor geometry and build sequence are available. Additionally as Navisworks is COTS (commercial-off-the-shelf) technology, it has been designed to work with other similar software and can therefore tie various project planning and scheduling tools into an existing Navisworks model. These tools include:

- Asta Powerproject 9 to 10
- Microsoft Project 2003 to 2007
- Oracle Primavera
- Microsoft Project Exchange Format
- CSV

Of course, this allows project planning and scheduling information to be used to simulate the production sequence for a ShipConstructor project with little effort. More importantly, this is an example of how the wide range of capabilities and accessibility within Navisworks (and therefore within a ShipConstructor solution) allow users to adopt and implement VR as required to solve challenges as they arise.

5.2.7. Cost Effectiveness

Another factor that was mentioned earlier as being critical to drive adoption at all levels was cost effectiveness. Fortunately, Navisworks as a general purpose solution is very cost effective, especially compared with those solutions that are targeted only at the shipbuilding industry and its comparatively small user base. This is especially evident due to the fact that Navisworks can also be implemented on an unlimited number of devices for viewing-only at no cost. This promotes the availability of the technology on every device in the organization.

6. Case studies

The success of the ShipConstructor/Autodesk solution in regards to democratizing Virtual Reality can be illustrated by highlighting several case studies of this solution in action.

6.1. Shop Floor 3D-Royal Huisman

The first case study highlights an aspect of VR that has been mentioned several times so far in this essay which is shop floor 3D. To cite our previous COMPIT Paper, *Morais et al. (2011)*: “The idea behind shop floor 3D is to allow the manufacturing team to better understand their jobs.”

It was noted that in shipbuilding, a 3D model is typically transformed into 2D drawings which must be interpreted by workers in the yard. Engineers who create the production documentation determine the amount of detail they think is required and detail the drawings accordingly but the use of 3D data would be a more effective method of communication and a more powerful tool for production workers. The paper further went on to show how workers at prestigious yacht builder Royal Huisman view screens containing Navisworks Virtual Reality models to answer questions as they arise regarding assemblies. The ShipConstructor CAD model with attribute data is viewed directly in Navisworks with all of the associated attribute information for each part.

As was noted earlier in this paper, in this case, the demand for the usage of VR came about from the workers themselves who realized that the capabilities existed. The technology was there and thus it was utilized. This is an example of the democratization of Virtual Reality driving adoption.

6.2. Supply Chain Collaboration-Chetzemoka

A more familiar example of VR usage is for supply chain collaboration, specifically regarding subcontractors. To cite our previous paper again, a good case study regarding the use of Virtual Reality in this context is the design review and client review during the construction of the recent Washington State Ferries, the first of which, the “Chetzemoka”, launched in 2010, *Morais et al.* (2011). In an industry where multiple entities commonly work on a single job, this project had an even higher than average degree of collaboration required.

Washington State Ferries was actively involved in the design and construction process which involved multiple different companies including Guido Perla & Associates, Todd Pacific Shipyard (now Vigor Industrial), Jesse Engineering, Nichols Brothers Boat Builders and Everett Shipyard. The 3D CAD model for the 273 foot long vessel was created in the ShipConstructor AutoCAD based application from which a Navisworks VR model was derived. All the different parties involved had regular meetings to view the Navisworks model and this viewing of the Navisworks model significantly aided the multiple organizations to work together to complete the project.

The fact that Navisworks is an easily accessible, COTS technology was important in deciding to use this VR solution for supply chain collaboration.

6.3. Laser Scanning—Gibbs & Cox.

Another interesting example of using VR involves incorporating point cloud models from laser scans (high definition surveying). High definition surveying is a non-intrusive means of rapidly collecting detailed and accurate as-built data. This technique uses a narrow laser beam to sweep across a target object so that hundreds of thousands of closely spaced measurements can be taken in a matter of minutes. When these scanned measurements are displayed on a computer, a dense representation of the target results (a point cloud) can be viewed. This can be viewed and navigated much like a 3D model. CAD objects can be modeled around this background or the point cloud can be used to generate a CAD model. In a shipbuilding context, key applications for this technology are to aid assembly, validate manufacturing and to assist repair and refit activities, *Morais et al.* (2011).

One customer making use of both VR and laser scanning is Gibbs & Cox, the renowned Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering firm. In an article in the March 2012 issue of Maritime Reporter Magazine, Ben Capuco, Vice President Platform Solutions Group for Gibbs & Cox tells how in a number of situations, before completing a repair job, it is useful to create a 3D Virtual model that is shared with a client at the shipyard.

He gives the example of a complex repair job using a cofferdam where a 3D model of the damaged portion of the ship’s bow was developed which allowed them to check proper fit of the cofferdam. He uses this example to extol the benefit coming from the ability to visualize work ahead of time because he notes that visualization during 3D fly-throughs can significantly enhance collaboration between engineering and production and is particularly useful in developing repair processes and procedures. He goes on to say, “Questions of producibility such as “Can a welder fit in the space to make the weld” are difficult to answer in 2D but can easily be checked in a 3D (virtual) model. 3D models are often used as a tool in studies for special projects such as repowering, hull plugs and mission changes. It allows everyone to clearly visualize the final configuration and prevent issues such as interferences, auxiliary equipment issues and tear out and replacement accessibility while ensuring that the client’s objective is still met.” *Capuco* (2012)

He then goes on to talk about how, “...advances such as digital (laser) scanning, aid in the rapid development of 3D models of existing spaces. These advances can allow rapid development of tailored 3D CAD repair models, even during transit of the ship to the shipyard, allowing design and planning to proceed in advance of ship arrival, facilitating future repairs on schedule, within budget and technically correct.”

The approach that Capuco outlines is anticipated to be used more and more in the future and as can be imagined, pricing is a driving factor in the cost sensitive repair business. The cost for laser scanners has come down dramatically (\$30,000 USD) in recent years, making it more cost effective for usage. This will further help spread the democratization of VR.

6.4. Estaleiro Atlantico Sul – Petrobras P-55 Semi-submersible Platform

As mentioned earlier, a key requirement for widespread use of VR tools is the ability to be implemented regardless of the various CAD tools and formats used by the many engineering offices and shipbuilders involved in a single project. It was also noted previously that this is one of the key strengths of a ShipConstructor-based Navisworks implementation.

As an example, the hull of the Petrobras P-55 platform in Brazil was to be built by Estaleiro Atlantico Sul (EAS). Just prior to the award of this contract, Petrobras had removed a long standing requirement mandating the use of Intergraph PDS on all platforms. However the restriction, which was later removed entirely, remained in place for the topside of the platforms. EAS had selected ShipConstructor for both the P-55 hull and an award of several Suezmax tankers. The engineering of the topside for the P-55 was performed by a Brazilian engineering firm using PDS.

This resulted in a requirement to find neutral ground on which to perform consolidated design reviews and clash detections between the models produced by the two engineering locations in their respective software packages. As Navisworks natively reads the ShipConstructor product model, and can import the Intergraph PDS model, it was an obvious choice. The engineering staff at EAS, using the free Navisworks viewer, had access to a virtual reality model containing both the up to date ShipConstructor model and the latest Intergraph PDS model for continued engineering work.

Fig.2: Intergraph PDS data added to the ShipConstructor product model in Autodesk Navisworks

The implementation of Navisworks on the P-55 project was so successful; it was subsequently implemented directly by Petrobras for work on future projects.

7. Conclusion

Shipbuilding is an extraordinarily competitive industry with narrowing margins and ever more aggressive project schedules. New technology, even where it can bring significant advantage, is slower to be adopted. And even when it is embraced, it isn't adopted across the entire shipyard. This is due to many factors including an aversion to the disruptive nature of costly and complex implementations, difficulty with using new technologies outside of engineering, and challenges involving integration between the various CAD vendors in use in a comparatively small industry.

A prime example of a technology that has not been implemented in as many places within the shipyard as it should be is Virtual Reality (VR). However, this paper has shown the benefits and capabilities of a solution developed exclusively for the shipbuilding industry that is based on the technology of one of the world's largest CAD vendors and provides a lightweight, cost-effective, industry neutral, multi-format VR toolset. This approach, which has also been extended into other areas including analysis, reality capture, data management and analysis, allows for the democratization of the VR tools across the industry and in every aspect of the shipbuilding process.

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Decision Support for the Crew Scheduling Problem in Ship Management

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Abstract

For decades decision support systems are an integral part of business information management systems and a wide range of Operations Research (OR) methods are applied. Many OR methods for solving the airline crew scheduling problem (ACSP) were developed in the last decades. In the maritime sector, the development and use of OR methods for the crew scheduling problem is less common than in the airline sector. The aim of this paper is to provide an insight into this important area in ship management and to formulate a mathematical model – the vessel crew scheduling problem (VCSP).

1. Introduction

Ship management has to face volatile business conditions, escalating volumes of information, increasing complexity of company processes and larger fleet sizes. This leads to increased requirements for the planning processes, so that the shipping business places greater demands on decision support. Especially crewing, as one main task of ship management with significant fixed operating costs, *Drewry (2011)*, has to deal with increasing demands imposed by new regulations and legislation as well as crew welfare aspects.

Today, one key challenge of decision support in crewing is a reliable middle and long term personnel planning under different objectives in order to manage the crew effectively. The vessel crew scheduling problem (VCSP) deals with the allocation and rotation of crews on operating ships under various constraints and different objectives.

In the last decades several OR methods for solving the crew scheduling problem were developed. Most applications are prevalent in the airline industry. Today, the airline crew scheduling problem (ACSP) and its solution methods are widely published in literature. There are also existing applications for other areas, for example train and bus transportation.

Contrary to the airline industry the use of OR methods is not common in the existing decision support systems for crewing in the maritime sector. Corresponding to this the engagement of the research community in this area is very low and just at the beginning comparing to the airline sector. No suitable approach for long term personnel planning could be identified.

The aim of this paper is to formulate the VCSP and to show the possible benefits of a mathematical optimization. This will include a precise look on the actual decision problem of crew scheduling in medium-sized and large shipping companies. Possible extensions of the VCSP are illustrated. In addition a comparison of the VCSP with the problem structure in the airline sector is conducted. Together with a conclusion, an outlook on future research needs to implement the VCSP model for decision support is given.

2. Crew scheduling in ship management

In general, ship management distinguishes between two main tasks: commercial management and technical management. Technical management deals with the operative tasks on a vessel which can be grouped into repair and maintenance, crewing, regulations and purchasing/procurement.

Ship managers expect that in the mid-term-future crewing has to face the biggest challenges. As reasons, besides the dominant issue of cost pressure, especially the large number of new regulations and compliance requirements are to be named. Integrated crewing software packages including crew planning and scheduling, in the meaning of automatically matching manning requirements with available crew resource are the key to meet future challenges, *Büssow et al. (2013)*.

In the crew scheduling problem a set of given ships have to be filled with available seafarers. This problem can be considered both in short and long term, whereas in this paper the focus lies on the long term planning with a time frame of one year.

2.1. Involved actors and workflow in crew scheduling

Various actors influence the crew scheduling process. Important actors represent the customer of the ship manager which receives the crewing service and flag states. Both determine fundamental requirements and regulations which set the framework of crew planning. The ship manager also defines requirements to guarantee a quality standard to customers.

The operative planning is done primarily by superintendents. Every superintendent is responsible for a distinctive group of vessels which have to be filled with seafarers. Permanently employed seafarers communicate directly with the ship manager. The seafarers who are not permanently employed do this through the manning agencies which are working closely together with the superintendents. These agencies conduct the administration (e.g. certification and travel management) with the seafarers in their home country.

2.2. Challenges of crew scheduling

One key challenge of crewing consists in the existence of several requirements which have to be considered. These requirements affect many different aspects of crewing for instance minimum experience times or the number of crew changes for a ship.

Another challenge is the problem size of crewing. Large sized ship management companies can operate hundreds of ships and have to assign thousands of seafarers. To cope with the problem size the planning problem is divided into several subproblems which are assigned to the superintendents. This makes it difficult to generate a schedule which is optimal for the whole fleet.

In many cases crewing is done only for short or medium time frame. This leads to short term requests for seafarers which in turn reduce the possibility to find an available seafarer. If there is no seafarer available a rescheduling of an already assigned seafarer to this empty position is necessary. In the end a low reliability of the generated schedule can lead to low reliability of the seafarers and vice versa.

3. The vessel crew scheduling problem (VCSP)

In order to solve the crew scheduling problem a mathematical model – the VCSP – has to be constructed. It is formulated as an integer linear programming problem (ILP), more precisely, as a 0-1 binary linear programming problem. The VCSP deals with the assignment of seafarers to different contract periods for each position on various ships. In the next two passages the general framework of the crewing problem is described.

It is common that contract periods have a defined length for each rank on a ship. These periods usually range between two and nine months and tend to be lower for higher ranks. A contract period includes the on board period and the required travel time. If a position change is made an overlap time is necessary. In this time the seafarer is giving information about the position to his detachment. The overlap time lies between one and several days depending on the experience times of the detaching seafarer.

The port for a position change is not restricted to the home country of the seafarer. If necessary the seafarers are travelling via plane to/from the start/end port of the contract. The ship schedule defines the port arrival and departure times which are not available for long term. Usually the availability in advance reaches from one day in tramp shipping to a few months in liner shipping. Furthermore there are often delays of ships so that the inclusion of the ship schedule is not appropriate in long term planning. An adjustment of the origin contract periods is often necessary in short term planning (rescheduling problem) when arrival and departure times are available.

3.1. Construction of the contract periods

It would be possible to integrate the start and end dates of the contract periods as decision variables into the VCSP. However, in this paper a sequential approach is pursued. First it is necessary to determine the start and end dates of the contract periods. Then these values are used as input parameters for the VCSP which is formulated in section 3.2. Since the focus in this paper is on the VCSP the problem of determining the start and end dates is described shortly in this subsection.

The end dates of the actual contract periods are important for initialization. They determine the start date of the first contract period in the planning horizon. Under consideration of the contract period length it is then possible to determine all contract periods in the planning horizon. In the design phase of the contract periods some constraints have to be considered which prevent in most cases a simple extrapolation of the same contract length over the whole planning horizon:

- The number of crew changes for one ship has to be less than a maximum value. A crew change for a ship occurs when at least one position change in a port is made. Reducing the number of crew changes should lead to e.g. reduced travel fix costs.
- The number of position changes in the same port has to be less than a maximum value. This should avoid that too many seafarers are leaving the ship at the same time.
- A minimum time span between position changes of two defined positions has to be considered (for instance 10 days between position change of master and first officer).

The implementation of these constraints differs from one ship manager to another.

3.2. Formulation of the VCSP

In this subsection the formulation of the VCSP including the definition of sets, parameters and decision variables is given.

Sets

I	set of all seafarers	
I^{leave}	set of all seafarers which are on leave at the moment of planning ($I^{\text{leave}} \subseteq I$)	
I_{kc}	set of all seafarers which could be assigned to position c on ship k ($I_{kc} \subseteq I$)	$\forall k \in K, \forall c \in C_k$
K	set of all ships	
K_i	set of all possible ships of seafarer i ($K_i \subseteq K$)	$\forall i \in I$
C_k	set of all positions on ship k	$\forall k \in K$
C_{ik}	set of all positions on ship k of seafarer i	$\forall i \in I, \forall k \in K_i$

T_{kc}	set of all contracts for position c on ship k	$\forall k \in K, \forall c \in C_k$
Q_i	set of all possible contracts of seafarer i	$\forall i \in I$
T_{iqkc}	set of all contracts for position c on ship k that could be assigned to contract q of seafarer i ($T_{iqkc} \subseteq T_{ikc}$)	$\forall i \in I, \forall q \in Q_i,$ $\forall k \in K_i, \forall c \in C_{ik}$
Q_{ikct}	set of all possible contracts of seafarer i that could be assigned to contract t for position c on ship k ($Q_{ikct} \subseteq Q_i$)	$\forall k \in K, \forall c \in C_k,$ $\forall t \in T_{kc}, \forall i \in I_{kc}$

Subset I_{kc} restricts the possible seafarers for a specific position on a ship. These restrictions arise from rank and ship type (bulker, container etc.). Other restrictions could originate from the required nationality group respectively wage scale for this position. Contrary to this, the subset K_i restricts the possible ships for a specific seafarer. Set T_{kc} contains all contracts for a specific position on a ship which have to be assigned to seafarers in the planning horizon. Analogous set Q_i defines the maximum possible contracts of seafarer i . The sets have the form $T_{kc} = \{1, 2, \dots, \rho_{kc}\}$ and $Q_i = \{1, 2, \dots, \eta_i\}$. Contract 1 is passed before contract 2 which again is passed before contract 3 and so on. The construction of set Q_i (which is equivalent to determine η_i) could be done under consideration of the end date of the actual or last contract, the minimum and maximum leave times and the contract period length of the seafarer. Subsets T_{iqkc} and Q_{ikct} exist to keep the number of decision variables Z_{iqkct} as low as possible. This could be done because a specific contract for a position cannot fit with all possible contracts of a seafarer and vice versa because of lacking intersection.

Parameters

v^{big}	sufficiently large number	
$Z_{i0kc0} = \begin{cases} 1 \\ 0 \end{cases}$	if the actual contract of seafarer i is equal with the actual contract for position c on ship k otherwise	$\forall k \in K, \forall c \in C_k,$ $\forall i \in I_{kc}$
$\zeta_i = \begin{cases} 1 \\ 0 \end{cases}$	if seafarer i is under contract at the moment of planning otherwise	$\forall i \in I$
ω_i	end date of last contract of seafarer i before the moment of planning	$\forall i \in I^{leave}$
η_i	number of possible contracts of seafarer i in the planning horizon	$\forall i \in I$
ρ_{kc}	number of contracts for position c on ship k	$\forall k \in K, \forall c \in C_k$
α_{kct}^{on}	start date of contract t for position c on ship k	$\forall k \in K, \forall c \in C_k,$ $\forall t \in T_{kc}$
α_{kct}^{off}	end date of contract t for position c on ship k	$\forall k \in K, \forall c \in C_k,$ $t=0, \dots, \rho_{kc}$
γ_i^{\min}	minimum leave time of seafarer i	$\forall i \in I$
γ_i^{\max}	maximum leave time of seafarer i	$\forall i \in I$

It is assumed that there are actual assignments of seafarers at the moment of planning which have to be considered. So the parameters Z_{i0kc0} , ζ_i and ω_i are important to initialize the planning problem. The actual assigned contract has the number $q=0$ from the perspective of a seafarer respectively $t=0$ from the perspective of a position. Parameter η_i defines the number of possible contracts of a seafarer. The word possible indicates that this parameter is an upper bound for the number of contracts. The process of determining ρ_{kc} , α_{kct}^{on} and α_{kct}^{off} is described in Section 3.1.

Decision variables

There are two binary decision variables:

$$Z_{iqkct} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if contract } q \text{ of seafarer } i \text{ is equal with contract } t \text{ for} \\ & \text{position } c \text{ on ship } k \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall i \in I, \forall q \in Q_i \\ \forall k \in K_i, \forall c \in C_{ik}, \\ \forall t \in T_{iqkc} \end{array}$$

$$G_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if seafarer } i \text{ is assigned to at least one contract} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall i \in I$$

ILP model

$$\text{Min } \sum_{i \in I} G_i \quad (1)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{q \in Q_i} \sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{iqkc}} Z_{iqkct} \leq G_i v^{big} \quad \forall i \in I \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} \sum_{q \in Q_{ikc}} Z_{iqkct} = 1 \quad \forall k \in K, \forall c \in C_k, \forall t \in T_{kc} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{iqkc}} Z_{iqkct} \leq 1 \quad \forall i \in I, \forall q \in Q_i \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{iqkc}} Z_{iqkct} - \sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{i,q-1,kc}} Z_{i,q-1,kct} \leq 0 \quad \forall i \in I, q=2, \dots, \eta_i \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{i1kc}} (\alpha_{kct}^{on} - v^{big}) Z_{i1kct} - \omega_i + v^{big} \geq \gamma_i^{\min} \quad \forall i \in I^{leave} \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{i1kc}} (\alpha_{kct}^{on} + v^{big}) Z_{i1kct} - \omega_i - v^{big} \leq \gamma_i^{\max} \quad \forall i \in I^{leave} \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{iqkc}} ((\alpha_{kct}^{on} - v^{big}) Z_{iqkct} - \sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{i,q-1,kc}} \alpha_{kct}^{off} Z_{i,q-1,kct} + v^{big}) \geq \gamma_i^{\min} \quad \forall i \in I, q=2-\zeta_i, \dots, \eta_i \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{iqkc}} \alpha_{kct}^{on} Z_{iqkct} - \sum_{k \in K_i} \sum_{c \in C_{ik}} \sum_{t \in T_{i,q-1,kc}} \alpha_{kct}^{off} Z_{i,q-1,kct} \leq \gamma_i^{\max} \quad \forall i \in I, q=2-\zeta_i, \dots, \eta_i \quad (9)$$

$$Z_{iqkct} \in \{0,1\} \quad \forall i \in I, \forall q \in Q_i, \forall k \in K_i, \forall c \in C_{ik}, \forall t \in T_{iqkc} \quad (10)$$

$$G_i \in \{0,1\} \quad \forall i \in I \quad (11)$$

The objective function (1) minimizes the number of seafarers which are necessary to operate all ships. Possible extensions of this basic objective function are part of Section 3.3. Constraint (2) ensures that $G_i = 1$ when at least one contract is assigned to seafarer i , (3) enforces that every contract for a position is assigned to exactly one seafarer. Constraint (4) allows the assignment of at most one contract for a position to a specific contract for a seafarer. If constraint (4) is equal to zero, then this contract is called a dummy contract. These dummy contracts exist because the set Q_i contains all possible contracts which cannot be assigned for all seafarers completely. Constraints (5) are of

technical nature. They guarantee for every seafarer that the dummy contracts are following after the “real” contracts. Constraints (6) to (9) ensure that the minimum and maximum leave times are considered. Constraints (6) and (7) enforce this for the first contract which starts in the planning horizon when the seafarer is in leave at the moment of planning. Constraints (8) and (9) enforce this for the remaining contracts. The decision variables are required to be binary in (10) and (11).

In this problem formulation the total amount of operated ships and related positions are considered together. However there exist some potential to split up this model in several smaller submodels without losing optimization performance. The first possibility to reduce the problem size is to build submodels for different ship types. This could be done when there exist closed pools of seafarers for every ship type. A further opportunity for a reduction of the main model is to consider each position (or a group of positions) individually. This is possible if there are no constraints which are important for more than this position (or a group of positions).

3.3. Possible extensions of the VCSP

Several extensions of the VCSP could be relevant for practical crewing problems. The objective function could contain following extensions:

- distribution of seafarer experience times among the ships (which should be as equal as possible)
- deviation of real leave times from “optimal” leave times (which should be low)
- travel costs (which should be low)

Following further constraints could be added additionally:

- compliance of common seafarer experience times for combinations of positions (e.g. the common experience time on tankers of master and first engineer should be in sum more than a required minimum value)
- earliest contract start dates of the seafarer which have to be considered
- preferred assignment of permanently employed seafarers
- some critical combinations of seafarers which are experienced in past should be avoided

3.4. Comparison of the VCSP to the airline crew scheduling problem (ACSP)

Barnhart et al. (2003) and *Gopalakrishnan and Johnson (2005)* present the state of the art in airline crew scheduling. The problem is typically divided into two subproblems. In the first step, the crew pairing problem is solved. A pairing represents a sequence of flight legs. The departure city of the first flight leg and the arrival city of the last flight in the pairing must coincide with a crew base. Furthermore the arrival city of a specific flight leg must be equal with the departure city of the following flight leg. The crew pairing problem deals with selecting a subset of all possible pairings so that each flight leg is covered by exactly one pairing. The obtained solution is then used as an input for solving the crew assignment problem. In this problem the selected pairings are combined to create individual work schedules for each crew member. Beside many similarities of the VCSP and the ACSP there exist some differences. Three of them are pointed out here:

1. The lengths of time of the smallest elements in crewing differ considerably. A contract period on a vessel has usually a length between two and nine months whereas a flight leg lies in quite smaller range (hours).
2. The flight legs including the arrival and departure times are always assumed to be fixed in airline crew scheduling. This is necessarily not the case in the maritime context (see section 3.1.). So there are two main options to handle this. One option is to integrate the problem of determining the contract start and end dates into the assignment problem which leads to increased complexity of the model. The other option consists of dividing these two problems and solving them subsequently. This option is chosen in this paper.

3. The restrictions regarding the pairings are not as restrictive in shipping (a pairing in shipping is equivalent to a sequence of contract periods on vessels) than in the airline sector. There are no restrictions in shipping like those described above because the seafarers fly via plane to/from the start/end port of the contract if necessary. This fact makes it interesting to model and solve the pairing and assignment problem for the maritime sector in an integrated approach simultaneously which could lead to a higher optimization benefit. The presented model in this paper pursues this approach.

4. Conclusion and future research

In this paper an insight into the crew scheduling problem in ship management was given and a mathematical model – the VCSP – was presented. The successful use of OR techniques in the context of a decision support system should lead to several benefits. First, an optimization over the whole fleet of ships is supported which is hard to achieve without OR techniques due to the size and complexity of the planning problem. Second, a reliable long term planning should raise the reliability of the seafarers to keep their assured contract periods. Third, the ability to create a long term plan can be used in context of strategic capacity planning. The question could be answered if the existing pool of seafarers is sufficient for an assumed number of ships in future.

There are some next steps which have to be made. A solution method to solve the VCSP has to be developed. This includes analyzing existing solution methods for the ACSP regarding their ability to adapt them for solving the VCSP. Then numerical experiments have to be conducted to assess the performance of the developed solution method.

No mathematical model was presented for the problem of determining the contract start and end dates. The construction of this model and the development of a solution method is an open issue.

The described approach to first determine the contract periods and then assign these contract periods to the seafarers should be compared with a simultaneous approach. Contrary to this, the presented simultaneous approach for the pairing and assignment problem should be compared with a subsequent approach as it is common in the airline sector. Benchmark points for both comparisons should be defined as model complexity, optimization potential and solution time.

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Exploiting Weight Data to Support Engineering and Corporate Decision-Making Processes

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Abstract

Weight control, from early weight estimation through life cycle weight tracking, is often conducted in dangerously inefficient ways or, worse, not conducted at all. Despite a general agreement on the utter importance of weight and centre of gravity calculations, during all phases of ship design, construction and operation, only seldom does weight data receive the attention and appreciation it requires on a corporate-wide scale. This paper will explore the nature of weight data, the tools available for weight control at the various stages through the life cycle of a water-bound vessel, and identify various players who influence the weight of a vessel. Examples of weight data sharing techniques and scope will also be reviewed. Finally, the means of implementing an effective weight policy will be described, and the benefits evoked.

1. Introduction

Weight control, from early weight estimation through in-service weight tracking, is often conducted in dangerously inefficient ways or, worse, not conducted at all. Despite a general agreement on the utter importance of weight and centre of gravity calculations, during all phases of ship design and construction, weight data never seems to receive the attention and appreciation it requires. There are many reasons behind this somewhat conscious disregard, spanning from the cultural to the technical.

Cultural reasons include lack of or limited knowledge of the weight subject itself, lack of statutory requirements (with the notable exception of some Navies), overconfidence in weight related considerations, incorrect appreciation of ships' similarities (or lack thereof), etc. Technical reasons include a limited market offer of dedicated, appropriate engineering tools, limited facilities for interfacing with CAD, limitations in many CAD tools, absence of managed feed-back from production management, difficulties in combining weight data into corporate management processes, etc.

The contradiction between the paramount importance of Weight and CG for a ship and the all too common disregard for these quantities is striking, as if the consequences of underplaying the importance of weight data were not damaging at best, catastrophic at worst. While at least some of the cultural reasons behind a correct and responsible approach to weight and CG calculations can be wiped by the use of appropriate technical tools, the fact remains that today only few technical tools lend themselves to an effective and reliable implementation of a constructive weight policy, able to support both the engineering and corporate decision making processes.

In this paper, for simplicity, we will refer to both weight and centre of gravity as weight, and we will review how the targeted use of state-of-the art IT technology can already today offset virtually all technical obstacles to the encompassing implementation of a corporate-supporting weight policy, as well as the cultural ones.

2. Weight, the skeleton in the closet

Weight is arguably the most common factor behind unachieved design and contractual goals, and generally the most difficult one to work with when it comes to identifying the genesis of error. The weight quantity exists in various forms during the life time of a ship:

- Macroscopic estimation at the very early stages based on a general mission statement and ship type selection.

- Estimation coupled with the development of feasibility study and conceptual design.
- Estimation evolved in parallel with pre- and contract reviews.
- Integration of CAD data during design.
- Integration of as-built data during production.
- Integration of in-service weight data to improve realism and quality of historical data

3. Weight groups and weight items

It is important to distinguish between weight groups and weight items, a distinction which is often overlooked, and to their complementarities.

Weight groups represent a range of unspecified but certainly present weight items. Weight items are collected within weight groups, at the various levels in the weight model hierarchy. The weight value of a weight group can be estimated using macroscopic ship parameters such as type, mission profile, etc. For example, within a specific ship type, the weight of the engine room can be accurately estimated from ship size, service profile, etc. On the contrary, despite mostly containing the same equipment and machinery by nature, the engine room of a tanker will be identifiably different from the engine room of a tug or of an Offshore Supply Vessel and therefore one can hardly estimate the weight of the tanker's engine room from the known weight of an OSV's engine room.

More immediately identifiable to the layman, weight items are just that, individual components of the ship. While there are tools and ways to add up almost all the components of a ship, a complete list of all the items making a ship is simply not available until the ship's construction is truly completed, therefore an item list becomes a reliable approach to weight control only at later stages of the vessel's genesis.

The importance and usefulness of weight groups is therefore evident, from the very first stages of the ship design process. It also follows that weight groups and weight items are complementary, and that both are required to carry out a constructive weight control strategy.

Furthermore, it is important to factor in the too often disregarded yet very real role of non-engineers in the weight determination process. For example, consider the specification of heavy equipment, often dictated by price rather than absolute technical specifications or performance measurement, or by availability, and which may not be defined until a later stage in the design process.

Then, perhaps surprisingly to some, it becomes clear that weight is influenced by many different players within the corporate panorama, and that communication between them can only be beneficial to the success of a corporate weight strategy.

4. Weight data organization

In the more rational approaches, weight groups and weight items are organized in hierarchical data structures generally referred to as Weight Breakdown Systems (WBSs). Various WBSs have been developed ever since ship design became a formalized discipline, but they can be exploited most efficiently only since the invention of relational databases. On the other hand, the eternal, ubiquitous spread-sheets do not lend themselves well to the use of WBSs, because the macroscopic aspects of discriminating weight calculations made possible by the use of WBSs are very difficult to implement therein.

In WBSs, weight groups are organized in hierarchical fashion: for example, let us refer to the NATO WBS, used by many Navies and, until recently, more generally across the ships industry.

A brief history of Ship WBS

- since the 30th century BC: imaginative intuition, gut feeling, luck
- since the 19th century : weighted, proportional extrapolation, simple statistical analysis
- sometime in the 20th century - Ship Work Breakdown Structure (SWBS)
- 1970s onwards - pre-spreadsheet, in-house development of computerized weight tracking
- mid-1980s - advent of the spreadsheet
- 1988 - Expanded Ship Work Breakdown Structure (ESWBS) - the functional configuration definition of the ship is improved and expanded to serve logistics support, to become an integrating, common reference point from design through operation, allowing life cycle data to become an intrinsic contributor to the ship design process
- early 1990s - Commercial Ship WBS developed by BAS Engineering, Norway - departure from the US Navy-originated and NATO adopted SWBS, and from the ESWBS, to accommodate the different product model nature of and predictive algorithms required by commercial ships of different types.

Fig.1: Brief history of the ship WBS

Easy to guess, weight items are collected within weight groups. But, perhaps less easy to guess, not all weight groups are made to collect weight items. The reason for this is that higher level weight groups lend themselves well to predictive regression analysis, and at this rather macroscopic level individual weight items are not relevant. Of course, advanced software tools do allow the adding of the odd weight item even at the higher levels of a WBS.

Over time, several industry-standard WBSs have been developed from the one or two primitive WBSs of old, and they are loosely referred to in most weight estimation and weight tracking work. However, while it is always tempting to develop one's "special" WBS in the quest of perfecting the weight prediction exercise into a most accurate result, one must be careful to maintain sufficient homogeneity in the general WBS structures being used to allow the identification of similarities not only between ships of the same general type, but also, very importantly, between ships of different types.

In fact, ignored by many, it is this very ability to identify similarities within and across ship types that constitutes the basis of the most powerful and accurate weight estimations, and which can contribute the most to the overall corporate ship design and ship building process from the earlier stages. To keep to the corporate environment addressed by this paper, let us just remind ourselves of the relationship between weight and quantity (ex. steel plates) and between weight, production planning and financial planning (when will how much steel be required to support the planned production schedule?).

5. Weight Calculation Tools

Various tools of disparate nature are used for weight calculations. Concisely, tools lending themselves to weight data management can be grouped in major categories:

- Design tools
- Production tools
- Corporate tools

Across the categories listed above, the tools most used in weight data management range from the application of simple macro-multipliers, to the ubiquitous but intrinsically limited MS-Excel, to dedi-

cated software applications custom developed by individual companies for in-house use and, finally, to encompassing commercial products like ShipWeight, by BAS Engineering, Norway.

Unfortunately, to date, general CAD and corporate software tools are not commonly considered to be a default integral part of a coordinated, corporate-wide weight policy. To make matters worse, many such tools lack even the simplest connectivity features, making data exchange virtually impossible.

Fig. 2: Later version of the US Navy SWBS was used as the base of most modern SWBSs

5.1 Design tools

Referring to Section 2, design tools will be used until and throughout the integration of CAD data during design work. Design tools can be further grouped by the design phase during which they are used. For example, we could identify:

- Conceptual design tools
- Preliminary design tools
- Contractual design tools
- Detailed Design tools

There are of course tools which span the realm of the above, and they will be addressed separately.

The aim at the conceptual stage of design is to identify the overall weight of the ship, and to validate the estimated weight by analysing second and perhaps third level weight groups for congruency and consistency as a function of the mathematical methods employed. Conceptual design tools span the range from simplistic macro-multipliers to top-WBS level prediction methods. For example, if a relational database is available, one can regress a weighted and qualified interpolation through a historical database data set, using appropriate coefficients and drawing from a heterogeneous library.

Preliminary design tools are used to validate and converge the conceptual weight estimation. If a hier-

archical WBS is used, third level weight groups are scrutinized very closely, and the first, heaviest weight items are included in the weight calculation, collected under the appropriate, lower level, respective weight groups. With simpler tools, the weight calculation remains ineffective at this stage, because too few of the weight items can be identified and located accurately in the ship to make for a realistic weight model. In both cases, some 3D CAD tools can assist to quite an extent, *Danese (2009,2010), Aasen (2010), Aasen et al. (2010,2011,2012,2013)*, e.g. ShipConstructor, which offers extensive interactive and associative weight calculation facilities.

Fig. 3: Use Rhinoceros3D[®] to check locations and spatial extents of ShipWeight weight groups and weight items

Contractual design tools reach into the CAD, 3D CAD for the modern, rational designer, realm. The role of 3D CAD becomes very important at this stage, particularly if the environment lends itself to analysis thanks to a relational database structure.

Corporate tools also begin to play a significant role at this stage, in that the establishment of a contract requires the identification and specification of most major components, equipment and machinery, where cost check may be influenced not just by type or nature of an item, but also by its quantity - all directly related to weight. Conversely, if cost were to be too different from the budget developed to this point, adjustments may also influence weight, even to significant extents. For example, drawing from real life, the author has witnessed occasions on which fluctuations in the raw material market forced the switching of the basic building material from aluminium to steel, or allowed the opposite. In both cases, an inaccurate weight estimation would have had severe consequences on the overall project and, in the former case, could have even spawned the bankruptcy of the yard.

Design tools begin to play a vital role once the design has advanced enough towards Classification that the weight estimation is replaced by weight tracking. At this point, fully managed 3D CAD models, interfacing to and interacting with corporate processes become essential. In addition to the purchasing office and its selection of major, heavy equipment and machinery, the production planning and human resource offices are now wholly involved. Weight will determine how big an assembly can be built, where in the shipyard it will be built, which crane and transport machinery will be needed to move it, how much pre-outfitting can take place at which moment during the production process, how many people will be needed where, at which exact moment in time and for how long.

In the case of shipyards building more than one vessel simultaneously, the importance of the above increases by orders of magnitude.

At this point, itemization of the weight model has begun in earnest, and multi-disciplinary, integrated CAD tools shine in supporting the maintenance of the weight model and the overall weight calculation.

5.2 Production tools

Perhaps also because design seems to be a never ending process, production inevitably starts before design is finished or, often times, even approved by Class. Moreover, to varying extents, some modern 3D CAD tools allow bridging the gap between design and production, and can be used seamlessly through both phases of the ship's genesis. These are, of course, 3D, realistic, CAD tools hinged on relational databases. More specifically, tools allowing multiple product hierarchies, one of which will mimic the weight software WBS, are perfectly suited to be an integrated part of the weight tracking and control process.

ID & Description	WgtGrp	ItemNo	Description	RegUser	RegDate
114	00	0	SHELL APPENDAGE	Administrator	11/02/2013 04:00

Qt 1 [-]	Qt Y [-]	Qt A [-]	Qt E [-]	UnitWeight [lb]	Weight [lb]	VCG [ft]	LCG [ft]	TCG [ft]	VCG_min [ft]	VCG_max [ft]
1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.000

Codes	RefInd	Station	RepNo	Margin	Change Order	Class	Package	Block
#85 digits	00 01	A	0		B12	E	W4	U

WgtGrp	ItemNo	Description	16672	Qt 1 [-]	Qt Y [-]	Qt A [-]	Qt E [-]	Unitweight [lb]	weight [lb]
114	00	0	SHELL APPENDAGES	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.00
114	00	1	BASED ON YFRT RUDDER /	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.00
114	00	2	APPENDAGE DWG DTD 4 JULY 85	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.00
114	00	3	SCANTLING DWG DTD 4 JULY 85	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.00
114	01	0	BILGE KEEL	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.00
114	01	107	KEEL PLATE STA 8-15 P/S	272.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	17.850	4855.20
114	01	207	2 INCH STD PIPE STA 8-15 P/S	140.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	3.650	511.00
114	01	305	KEEL SUPPORTS 10.2 # PLT P/S	21.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	10.200	214.20
114	02	0	SKEG	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.00
114	02	104	BOTTOM PLATE	48.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	20.400	979.20
114	02	204	SIDE PLATE	144.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	20.400	2937.60
114	02	304	WEBS & STIFFS	60.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	15.300	918.00

Total weight & CoG										
Weight [lb]	Weight [lb]	VCG [ft]	LCG [ft]	TCG [ft]	VCG_min [ft]	VCG_max [ft]	LCG_min [ft]	LCG_max [ft]	TCG_min [ft]	TCG_max [ft]
10415.20	4.65	3.02	140.74	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Fig. 4: Weight item inside a weight group

While production engineering should not engender remarkable changes to the model and its weight, it is the crucial moment when the design comes together and flaws may be exposed. Because in some vessels even small changes to the weight and/or its distribution can have noticeable, undesired effects, keeping a running check of weight is very important.

When production engineering begins, weight itemization fully replaces weight estimation. Continuing the verification process started during the later design work, it is now possible to accurately judge the accuracy of the estimation by measuring the remainders of each weight group, the remainder being the difference between the estimated weight and the itemized, discretized weight model. It goes without saying that the more complete the ship model is, the more accurately and realistically the remainder can be established, and the more reliable the extrapolation of this evaluation to the ship's scale will be. This is one of the crucial, bare truth moments in the course of the weight control process and, although it is already rather late in the game, only too often major issues appear during production engineering, their influence potentially reaching far beyond simple remedies.

5.3 Corporate tools

In today's 3D CAD and product model world of ship design, it is easy to be lead toward thinking that such modelling tools are sufficient to accomplish all of the ship design tasks. But, weight control, for

one, cannot be achieved by the use of CAD tools only, as it is influenced by other sizeable components of the ship's genesis process, such as corporate-wide planning, purchasing, factors influencing the supply of raw materials, equipment, availability of human resources, etc., all factors that are hard to address with 3D CAD and traditional product models. Therefore, the information available in corporate planning and management software needs to be harvested and processed in parallel with the continually on-going weight calculation. For example, any one of a score of non-engineering reasons could affect the planned outfitting of a ship's section, with repercussions not only on the shipyard's schedule but also on the handling of that section because of a now-challenging weight distribution, CG location, absence of a given item, etc. In other words, corporate reality may very much affect not only the final weight quantities, but also the in-progress weight quantities, at any given stage of design and building, or with respect to any given portion of the vessel.

The industry then faces a double challenge, cultural and technical. The cultural aspect of the challenge is related to the lack of awareness of the importance of non-engineering data in the ship design and production process too often found in corporate management. The technical facet consists of finding the way to convey the data and its meaning to those will be the most immediately confronted with weight deviations and who will be expected to elaborate solutions to the problem.

6. - The ShipWeight environment

ShipWeight is a state of the art weight control tool developed by BAS, Norway, and devised to be used from the earliest stages of design, through production and, uncommonly, throughout the life cycle of the ship. The unique scope of application of ShipWeight is achieved by implementing powerful, modern computer technology in a way that remains totally transparent to the user, on very standard hardware.

The ShipWeight environment can be resumed macroscopically as being composed of:

- a powerful, very flexible and fully customizable weight prediction engine, also allowing partial referencing, relative referencing of both complete and incomplete historical data models, in full or only of portions thereof. The core engine supports and is used for all types of vessel: ships, workboats, yachts, submarines, small craft, Navy vessels, as well as non-marine vessels, such as airplanes, land-bound carrier vehicles, etc.
- a fully customizable WBS structure, which also supports multiple WBSs
- a database centred data storage scheme, unlimited in terms of database size, number of simultaneously addressable databases, number of reference ships, number of weight items, etc.
- a very flexible data import engine, configurable to import virtually any custom data format
- the ability to directly connect to non-ShipWeight databases, files and programs to exchange data both mono- and bi-directionally
- an complete output engine allowing fully customized reports (tables, graphs, etc.)
- an easy to use, graphical, integrated query building system
- an open architecture, simple and fully documented database structure and query library

During the conceptual and preliminary phases of design, a macroscopic approach is privileged, and implemented by using advanced statistical data regression techniques that feed on historical data. The statistical regression tools offered by ShipWeight work by combining correlation coefficients (which can be conceptually compared to weighed scale factors) and parametric methods based on known vessel parameters, to estimate weight and CG of the vessel, or of portions thereof according to the WBS' hierarchical subdivision (the weight groups). Again, it is important to recall that the weight groups may or may not represent a geographical portion of the vessel, or the collection of items of similar nature regardless of their location, or a combination of the two.

Each weight group, in fact down to the very lower level ones, is assigned a method, which is an estimation formula based on appropriate ship parameters. The method is used to compute the weight group's quantity for each of the vessels selected from the historical database for the purpose of estimating the weight group in question. A curve representing the correlation coefficient is then fitted through the data according to a user selected or specified interpolation scheme. Finally, the correlation coefficient for the ship's weight group being evaluated is derived from the curve using one of the several selections and definition options made available by the program. The end result is the assignment of the estimated weight quantity to the weight group.

Once the early design process reaches the contractual stages, some major items will also generally have been included in the ShipWeight model, such as large, heavy or expensive equipment. On the other hand, while their quantity may be relatively well know at this point, at least macroscopically, items like steel will be represented by a lump number, and included in the weight model as such.

Not too far in time from contract signature, general arrangement, structural and distributed systems layouts, major machinery arrangements, etc., will have been advanced enough for a relatively rich, but probably not complete, realistic 3D CAD model to have been developed, and for most, if not all, the items to be sourced to have been defined.

This is another point in the ship design process where high-performance, integrated CAD tools become important in the weight calculation exercise, and yet remain of limited use corporate-wide if the data they generate cannot be integrated with the other IT tools in use and processes underway, the weight control tool and process in particular. In the case of ShipWeight, there are various ways to acquire data from CAD into the weight model, such as direct, managed interfaces (ex. with ShipConstructor) or unmanaged full data replacement interfaces (ex. reading Excel files, neutral dump files from CAD programs, etc.).

Because this is when CAD data should in most cases start constituting a converging, more reliable weight quantity than the macroscopic weight group's weight estimation, the ability to manage the data being acquired is paramount, especially when it comes to tracking the evolution of weight over time *Aasen et al. (2013)*. Once the weight item list becomes complete and accurate enough, quantitatively and quantitatively, the weight figure generated is considered to have superseded the estimated quantity in terms of accuracy and reliability, and becomes the value of record. Perhaps even more so than in previous stages, it then becomes vital to keep the weight-related communications between engineering and corporate players open. Thus, as more and more of the weight groups' values of record come from weight items, the transition from weight estimation to weight tracking occurs. And, as the vessel construction progresses, on-board items can be so tagged in ShipWeight, thereby confirming individual items in a given weight group. Of course, the grouping of on-board items during construction may not match the WBS grouping structure, and ShipWeight offers a powerful facility to reconcile the discrepancy: custom codes.

Custom codes effectively exploit the relational nature of the underlying ShipWeight database. For example, custom codes are used to add properties, attributes and qualifiers to items, without limit on the number of custom codes that can be assigned to a given item. One use of custom codes is to increase the variants in compiling custom reports, in which items can be grouped according to any property, attribute, parameter, ship location, date of handling, and / or other custom code assigned to one or more items. As a simple example, a custom report may group the items present in ShipWeight weight model - regardless of which weight group they are assigned to - in a way that mimics the CAD model's product hierarchy, or the production planning sequence, etc.. This will serve many purposes, one being the ability to compare the item's lists and correct any discrepancies between virtual (CAD, purchasing list, etc.) and real (what went on board the ship). Another use of custom codes is to tag imported items with the name of the weight group the item is destined to, as is done by the interface with ShipConstructor, requiring no further manual action upon import.

Thanks to its powerful and flexible import mechanisms, ShipWeight therefore provides an easy to use environment allowing the exploitation of up-to-date data, regardless of the data's source (CAD, vendor, purchasing, etc.) and format. In fact, much of this process can be semi-automated, or even fully automated, with a surprisingly small programming effort. When exploited, this ability is of great value to the ship genesis process, corporate-wide.

Two other corporate process supporting feature of ShipWeight are:

- revision control
- revision management

Both draw on the focused database aspects of the application, designed to allow moment-in-time freezing and archiving, as well as the historical tracking of data and meta-data, down to the individual item. Therefore, at each project's milestone (entering contract, during design and production, at launch, at delivery, at scheduled maintenance, etc.), a version of the current weight data model is saved. Moreover, because the history of each component of the weight model has been tracked and stored (ShipWeight will record who did what, when and, if the doer provides the information in form of comment, why), as is each action of each user, the revision history of the database and the weight development of the project can be monitored by comparing and analysing changes from one date to another, or from one formal revision to another, during a given period, etc. This ability is very precious in error checking processes.

The scope of application allowed by the use of a very developed database structure extends to areas otherwise very difficult to address, such as:

- weight distribution curves
- radii of gyration
- sanity checks on CG, etc.
- application and management of uncertainty factors
- export of weight curves to stability calculation programs (GHS, NAPA, etc.)

Also very important in a corporate-wide application, ShipWeight offers a possibly unique concurrent multi-user environment, managed by logins and permission controls. Therefore, the project administrator will assign read and/or write privileges (or none) to each user as a function of their role in the ship genesis process, for example:

- the data manager will have full rights, including to the data-validation input environment (the "sandbox" evaluation functionalities)
- weight engineers will have access to their respective input fields
- CAD managers will have access to the data import commands leading to the sandbox, where the data will have to be validated by the weight engineer holding that right before being admitted into the central weight model database
- the purchasing department will have access to some item input fields, to certain export facilities (needed to bring data to their own corporate programs), and to reporting
- the planning department will be able to use all reporting functions, including the creation of new report formats
- company management need not necessarily have access to use of the ShipWeight software itself, but it must have access to all reporting facilities which, in fact, can be fully automated and run without accessing ShipWeight at all

The above further strengthens the notion of data availability, and its importance in the corporate environment. ShipWeight includes a number of formatted reports including tables and graphs of many sorts but, more importantly, its data can be sourced by any program capable of querying an SQL database, such as SAP Crystal Reports. As one may immediately imagine, the power of direct data extrac-

tion from the ShipWeight database by third-part applications is compounded by their ability to also, simultaneously, source data from other sources, for example a CAD database (ex. ShipConstructor), or a purchasing application (ex. SAP, IFS, Trimergo, etc.), etc.

This is where and how ShipWeight data, but not only, crosses the boundaries of the engineering office and becomes directly useful and usable by non-engineering corporate players. For example, as demonstrated by the author on many occasions, top-management could have an icon on their PC's desktop which launches a simple Crystal Reports application comparing:

- estimated steel weight, from ShipWeight
- projected steel requirement as a function of the production calendar, from the planning department
- projected steel purchasing calendar as a function of the expected raw material futures market, from the purchasing department
- steel weight modelled to date by the design department (CAD model), cross referenced to the production calendar
- etc.

Access to data as described above is vital to all informed decision making processes within the corporate environment, and the ability to access, share and exploit data corporate-wide is available today, using off-the-shelf technology as implemented by programs like ShipWeight, ShipConstructor, IFS, and others.

Conversely, non-engineering considerations, requirements, changes to plan and decisions can be conveyed back to others in the corporate network, who may be located elsewhere on the planet, using the same data.

.Fig. 6: ShipWeight Work Flow

7. Implementation of a corporate-wide weight data and management strategy

A good weight control tool is necessary, but not sufficient, to achieve good weight control. The tool must be implemented in the organization alongside the other engineering and corporate tools, but a mutual adaptive evolution of philosophy of use, strategy and goals must also take place. As can easily be deduced from the present discussion so far, the obstacles on the path of achieving a successful corporate-wide weight data strategy are, today, far more cultural than technological: while the author's view may seem futuristic, the underlying problem to be solved was formally reported in detail at least 30 years ago, *Keeley (1988)*, and the technology required to achieve the goal has been readily available off-the-shelf at a lesser cost than a fashionable video game console for some years already.

Some of the principal factors underpinning the implementation of a corporate-wide weight data and management strategy are:

- acknowledge the importance of weight control
- standardize data formats or formally document data equivalencies
- organize the process

7.1 Acknowledge the importance of weight control

The accurate estimation of the ship's weight and centre of gravity may constitute the single most important parameter in the achievement of the design brief and contractual specifications. Deadweight, speed, strength and sea-keeping are only some of the crucial ship parameters that depend directly on weight and centre of gravity. Moreover, not insignificantly, weight is also closely connected to the cost of the vessel. In order to compete within the narrow margins and short turnaround time imposed by today's very competitive market, the highest confidence in preliminary weight estimation and effective weight control during construction of the vessel are a do-or-die requirement, not an optional ornament to the ship genesis process.

While this is readily acknowledged by most, an effective weight strategy must be embraced and put into practice by all connected to and affected by the weight control process. An effective weight control process will involve many people, with jobs and responsibilities spanning the overall corporate horizon, from design, to planning, to purchasing, to production, etc. Moreover, the effective weight strategy will work best, if not only, if all involved are fulfilling their role. If some do not, the damage will be many-fold: it will be difficult to achieve effective weight control, it will be more difficult to realise that the data is bad, and last but not least, it will be even more difficult to unearth the nature of the shortcoming.

Acknowledgement of the true scope of the importance of weight control is, still too often, a major cultural obstacle to overcome but, as mentioned in this paper, the use of off-the-shelf, state-of-the-art technology can provide significant help in bridging the cultural gap.

7.2 Standardize and agree on formats

The establishment of standards and standard equivalencies is the base of data organization. Standards must cater to very different needs (estimation, CAD, purchasing, project specification, etc.) but, to make matters easier, the WBS structure combining weight groups and weight items already provides a friendly basis to start from. Moreover, while there is scope to allow for somewhat differing WBSs (e.g. at the weight group level) being used on very different projects, commercial programs like ShipWeight do, thanks to the use of customs codes, allow for not only the cross-referencing of weight items between differently structured WBSs, but also between various corporate programs. For example, a given weight item will have, as custom codes, attributes like planned date of assembly, manufacturer's item reference number, location of storage and assembly, etc. Many industry standard data formats, such as SAWE, SWBS, SFI, ShipWeight, etc., lend themselves to weight control work and are used by various programs commonly found in the corporate environment.

It is obvious that good weight control implies a lot of data flow, and standardization and equivalency mapping are crucial to the process. Then, deciding on data format will satisfy more than one requirement:

- find the common denominator between CAD, text, databases, spread-sheets, vendors' software, etc.
- from each format extract the data required by ShipWeight
- make the data available to ShipWeight in a way that requires no further manual processing

The same holds for output, and especially the definition of terms. For example, consider how confusing it is to use the ubiquitous word "block", which means different things depending on the context of its use, and sometimes even carries linguistic connotations.

In the case of the Weight, CG and their derivatives, everyone must be sure to have a clear understanding of the nature of what these values refer to. How damaging could it be if the purchasing office bought the wrong amount of steel, or the wrong number of pumps, or ...?

Last but not least, standardization must also encompass checking procedures, search procedures (for items, key words, etc.) and, not to be forgotten, limits and tolerances.

Relational database cored software like ShipWeight offers tabular and graphical tools for searching, grouping, checking, sanity checks, validation of imported candidate data, etc., but these must be matched across the full spectrum of corporate tools to ensure process consistency.

7.3 Get organized

Most will agree that data availability is key to its use, and to the improvement of all processes where that data is applicable. In this paper it is suggested that even data of disparate nature should be available to players in different disciplines, such a manufacturer's ordering reference number to the weight engineer or CAD modelling draftsman. On the other hand, the debate on where the data should be collected or how it should be made available is a never-ending one.

One source of doubt fuelling the debate on which data should be made available, when and how, is the very handling of data itself in the attempt to make it available. Traditionally, handling has been purely manual, a procedure with results in multiple duplications, is very cumbersome and time consuming and is extremely error prone despite the best intentions and efforts, errors which may in truth be more dangerous than the potential benefits of data sharing itself.

Today, the manual process can be easily replaced by off-the-shelf technology, and virtually guarantee the reliable organization and corporate-wide availability of up-to-date data. The key here is not immediate, multiple duplications as it is on-call sourcing. Thanks to flexible interfacing and open data structure architecture, programs like ShipWeight offer both options:

- a more traditional data replication by which data is copied to various pre-determined locations upon its validation (ex. upon saving a file), a procedure which requires the availability of the destination files and involves the thorough control and checking thereof, a non-trivial set of requirements . This can be referred to as data "pushing".
- a more modern source-as-needed approach, which better guarantees that the data is indeed up-to-date. This will require that the data sources are available, which is easy to check and report on. This can be referred to as data "pulling".
- a combination of the two, since some data will lend itself better to pushing and other to pulling

Still considering the use of custom codes to document an item's vendor purchasing reference number example, the weight figure of a given, identified item could be pushed from the purchasing office from the product's electronic specification sheet. Then, if the weight figure were to fail the sanity check carried out by ShipWeight, the weight engineer can report back to purchasing, uniquely identify the item in question and request a check and update of the weight figure, possibly from the manufacturer. In a similar fashion, prior to creating a weight report to match the production schedule; ShipWeight would pull planning data from the planning dataset, search its database by the relevant custom codes, and tabulate the weights and CGs corresponding to the various phases. For the sake of argument, it is a short step to imagine that ShipWeight will identify the item in the planning database by its vendor purchasing reference number, and that the purchasing and planning offices will share data likewise, by pushing and pulling as appropriate.

It is also tempting to then opt for a single database containing all data and being polled by several software applications, or even a single software application capable of handling all tasks. This, how-

ever relatively easy it is from an IT standpoint, remains for the moment both cultural science fiction and unviable business proposition.

On the other hand, the procedures and relatively simple techniques reviewed in this paper lend themselves very well to the simultaneous and combined use of various, disparate software programs and, in fact, is already today immediately applicable in more cases than not, the only requirement being the structured organization of data, its flow and of the procedures governing it.

8. Benefits

In the end, implementing a weight control strategy to support the corporate-wide ship genesis process does require an effort, which can vary greatly depending on many factors. To support the immediate applicability of the subject proposed in this paper, the author's direct experience strongly supports the fact that an introspective and pragmatic corporate process analysis will indicate the sequence of steps and actions appropriate to ensure that the new processes being developed remains in tune with fundamental requirements and evolving corporate characteristics through the development period, and thereafter.

Even after just the first steps of implementation have been accomplished, benefits appear. Well organized historical data, the key to accurate weight estimation in future projects, is one of the first. Time savings, the greater confidence on the side of those making use of the estimation and the ensuing reductions in engineering safety factors and planning and financial provisions follow at once, and while these are difficult to quantify in general, orders of magnitude of savings are not an uncommon measure thereof. The use of company standard report formats and contents save even more time and troubling soul-searching.

One, most desirable direct product of the above is that the now possible close monitoring of weight will ensure that deviations between contract weight and current weight estimation, at any time, are immediately evident to all who share in the responsibility of weight, who will be affected by the discrepancy, and who should play a role in remedying the condition - corporate wide.

Fig. 7: Weight tracking through successive project milestones

9. Conclusion

Weight control is a fundamental factor in the successful achievement of a contract fulfilling ship design and ship building project. The data involved in weight control comes from various, disparate sources within the corporate environment, and is generated, collected and processed by several programs of different nature. While there are cultural obstacles to be reckoned with, modern off-the-shelf

technology can play a significant role in offsetting them. Moreover, the same technology makes the data sharing required for successful weight control readily achievable.

The implementation process leading to the corporate-wide exploitation of weight data is not effortless, but relatively easy and simple to achieve, requiring mostly an earnest and pragmatic corporate-wide process analysis, and a collective, cultural buy-in by all players concerned. And, while data generation and sometimes data input remains the concern of the individual, standard automation techniques can mostly, if not completely, replace manual data sharing procedures.

Very soon upon implementation, the exploitation of weight control produces long sought benefits, not least the ability to continuously compare the estimated weight figure to the evolving, project-specific one, thereby identifying any errors and allowing a remedy effort to take place.

In conclusion, especially when using the readily available appropriate software tools, implementing weight control and exploiting weight data in support of corporate-wide decision making processes is an achievable goal that will produce consequent benefits.

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Port Efficiency Simulations for the Design of Container Ships

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Abstract

Being faster in port allows a ship to transit at lower speeds and to save fuel as well as to reduce emissions. This paper describes a method to consider quantitatively the port efficiency of container ships during conceptual design with the aim to identify better configurations. The method is based on a statistical approach. Port efficiency, i.e., the time needed to move a selected number of containers, is simulated in a multi-stage process: First, a randomly chosen number of containers are distributed over the vessel. Then, from these containers a lower number of containers are randomly selected that are to be unloaded and loaded. This then sets up one of many scenarios for which the fastest time is computed that one, two or more cranes (up to six) would need to move the containers. The simulation is repeated until sufficiently large sets of cases are available for statistical analysis. Several example ships were studied and compared, focusing on the relative merits of individual container ship layouts. The ships investigated were a typical Panmax ship of 4250 TEU as a reference, a smaller ship of 3700 TEU and two variants of a novel design concept with reduced length but increased beam for comparable numbers of container slots. The differences in port efficiency are shown to be tangible.

1. Introduction

Energy efficiency has been the dominating topic in shipping since 2008 and will continue to govern major efforts in both design and operation of cargo ships in the years to come. Numerical flow optimization of ships and components already lead to substantial reductions in energy consumption, in particular for new vessels. For existing vessels important contributions stem from improved operations (e.g. trim optimization), better maintenance (e.g. cleaner wetted surfaces) and retrofitting (e.g. new propellers for altered operating profiles). Slow steaming has become a popular countermeasure since energy consumption typically scales with the third, fourth or even with the fifth power of speed, depending on the ship type and speed range. However, this is usually realized at the price of much longer voyage times (and unfavorable engine rating).

Transport efficiency can be defined techno-economically in terms of design payload W_{PL} , design speed V_S and average annual cost AAC as expressed by the Ship Merit Factor, Benford (1965), $SMF = k \theta W_{PL} \theta V_S / AAC$. Here, k is a service factor that relates the average payload, the average speed and the time at sea to the ideal values specified at design stage. This service factor can be improved by reducing time in port, leading to lower design speeds required and causing substantially lower cost. This is reflected by an old saying between sailors: "The fastest trip is made in port," meaning that any hour lost in port is difficult to recover at sea. In other words, you can lower your speed when spending less time in port and still maintain your overall voyage time. This is particularly advantageous for ships on shorter routes since their share of port time is relatively high. Furthermore, ships that inherently sail at higher speeds such as container ships benefit more notably since any small speed reduction already yields tangible decreases in energy consumption. This makes it worthwhile to study the port efficiency of container ships with focus on short-range transport.

Let us consider a simple example: A container ship travels at 17 kn between two ports. For a distance of 500 nm the vessel would need 29.4 h if it did not need any time for approaches and maneuvering. With just one hour spent close to and in either port at lower speeds, say half the speed at sea, the ship would need 30.4 h in total. If we can speed up loading operations by one hour we could reduce the necessary speed at sea from 17 kn to 16.4 kn (3.4% slower), i.e., we could save roughly half a knot. Assuming conservatively that power requirements scale just with the third power this would bring about energy savings of roughly 10% in ideal conditions, Fig.1.

Fig. 1: Simple example for potential savings on a 500 nm trip by time saved in port

At the design stage of a container ship, however, it is not trivial to predict the actual time used for loading and unloading. Naturally, the time needed depends strongly on the current number of containers to be moved and on their specific distribution. In addition to the particulars of the ship and the loading situation at hand, the land facilities clearly play an important role, most outstandingly the availability and speed of the cranes at the terminal. Consequently, so as to quantify the port efficiency of a container ship at its design stage a statistical approach seems appropriate. A first proposal for such an approach will be discussed in this paper. It was realized within the Computer Aided Engineering software *FRIENDSHIP-Framework*, using the software's programming capabilities that come with its comprehensive feature technology.

Several example ships were studied and compared, focusing on the relative merits of individual container ship layouts. Furthermore, possible advantages by utilizing hydraulic hatches or by adopting an open-top concept with stoppers were taken into account. The ships investigated were a typical Panmax ship of 4250 TEU as a reference, a smaller ship of 3700 TEU and two novel design concepts of decreased length and increased beam but comparable numbers of container slots.

The study focuses on the simulation of port efficiency on the "wet" side of the terminal in order to quantify benefits associated with certain layouts of container ships at the conceptual design stage. This topic appears to have received very little attention so far, at least the authors did not find suitable references. Apparently, most research has covered the "dry" side of port efficiency where terminal operation and logistics are looked into, see *Gadeyne and Verhamme (2011)* for an overview as well *Zeng and Yang (2009)* for references. *Goussiater (2007)* presented a study on improving gross crane rates, i.e., the total number of containers handled divided by the allocated crane time, by means of statistical modeling. Since the gross crane rate directly affects time at berth, its reduction is equivalent to an increase in port efficiency.

2. Overview

Within the newly developed method, port efficiency, defined as the minimum, maximum, mean and significant time needed to move a selected number of containers, is simulated in a multi-stage process:

1. A randomly chosen number of containers are distributed over the vessel.

2. From these containers a lower number of randomly selected containers are identified for loading and unloading.
3. For this specific load case, i.e., the outcome from steps 1 and 2, the respective time is computed that one, two or more cranes (here up to six) would need to move the containers the fastest (determined by the slowest crane).
4. The simulations, i.e., steps 1 to 3, are repeated until sufficiently large sets of load cases are available for statistical analysis.

Due to the randomness in setting up any container distribution even if both the total number of containers to be stored and the number of containers to be moved were the same in two instances, the resulting container distribution would still differ. The virtual time counter for each load case starts when the first container is addressed and stops once the last container has been processed. All port time needed before and afterwards, say for mooring and preparing both the ship and the terminal, are omitted and would need to be added. It should be noted that different ship layouts could possibly also yield different mooring and terminal preparation times.

3. Assumptions and simplifications

Port efficiency depends on many factors. Some of the important contributors are

- Actual distribution of containers onboard
- Container slots scheduled for loading and unloading
- Availability and utilization of cranes
- Speed and equipment of cranes (e.g. spreaders)
- On-shore handling of containers
- Time needed for maneuvering and mooring
- Delays due to wind and waves in port (causing container swaying and ship motion)
- Possible idle times (e.g. waiting for availability of special equipment and personnel)

For each specific port and individual container loading scenario these factors will all determine the actual time needed to come into port with certain containers and to leave again with different containers. Many of the original containers will have been taken off, new containers will have been loaded and some containers will have been relocated. In any case there will be a new container storage plan and the time spent is critical to know for the operators of both the vessel and the terminal.

However, for the designers of a container ship no single scenario seems particularly meaningful since too many factors lie outside their control. Rather, many scenarios need to be considered and suitably averaged in order to understand the implications design alternatives may bring about, calling for a statistical approach. This will not allow distinguishing any merits or drawbacks that a chosen design may have in a particular situation (for instance, unloading of 911 TEU and loading of 1432 FEU in Singapore on the 16th of April 2013). Instead, the statistics can only serve to show that there are indeed differences if a large number of cases are relevant. For instance, let us consider an Asian trade with 13 ports that takes four weeks for the round trip. Within 10 years of service a ship will have had more than 1500 calls in port as would all its competitors. On average one of the contending ship concepts would be inherently faster even though any other can outperform this design on single occasions.

Several assumptions were made for a first implementation of simulating port efficiency. The most important assumption is that any change on the side of the port will equally benefit all vessels under consideration and any delay that may occur will slow down all vessels by the same amount of time. For instance, if spreaders are available to handle several containers in one move this should speed up all competing designs more or less equally. The assumptions and simplifications are summarized in Table I.

Table I: Assumptions and simplifications

	Assumptions	Details and comments
1	Any change on the side of the port will equally benefit all vessels under consideration and any delay that may occur will slow down all vessels by the same amount of time.	Different cranes do not favor any particular design. Handling of more than one container at a time is equally positive for every design.
2	On-shore handling is ideal.	There are no delays of containers at the pier when picked up or delivered.
3	Operators' know-how and experience influence different designs similarly.	There is no advantage of any single design due to special treatment either by terminal or ship operators.
	Simplifications	
1	Loading and unloading of a vessel can be treated equally.	According to measurements the time needed for either loading and unloading differ only marginally.
2	Time needed for container movement depends only on its relative position to the pier.	Crane speed is independent of a container's weight.
3	Simulations can be undertaken for TEU and then abstracted towards reasonable TEU to FEU ratios.	Only TEU are distributed. Since any mix of TEU to FEU can occur in real life the speed up effect should not differ between layouts.
4	Disturbances, if any, are the same for all vessels.	Hence, they are neglected. (Alternatively, they could be considered by offsets in time.)
5	Ships stay in their initial position at the pier.	Sinkage and trim, if taking place while loading/unloading, do not make a difference in port time.
6	Ships do not move while being un/loading.	There are no delays due weather conditions such as unfavorable waves in port.
7	Containers do not sway.	There are neither strong nor gusty winds that increase the time for container handling.
8	Ships are presented equally well to port on average.	No special preconditioning of container distribution is made, e.g. containers are confined to a particularly low number of bays.
9	Physical and regulatory constraints can be neglected.	Each load case is feasible with regard to hydrostatics, strengths, regulations and economics.
10	All containers are equal.	And none are more equal than others; high cubes and non-standard sizes are ignored.

4. Load and move cases

4.1. Container grid

From an operational point of view a container ship can be interpreted as a three dimensional grid of potential container slots, Fig.2, as proposed e.g. by *Papanikolaou et al. (1990)*. The grid consists of several bays (longitudinal axis), rows (transversal axis) and tiers (vertical axis). When mapping the available slots to a regular grid with i, j and k as counters quite a few slots lie outside the hull form, are occupied by the deck house and machinery room, would obstruct the line of sight or are taken by the hatch covers, Fig.2B. Obviously, these slots are not available for container transport and need to be "grayed out" in the port efficiency simulation.

Fig.2: Setting up of container grid for port efficiency simulation

Each slot in the grid corresponds to one TEU (Twenty-foot Equivalent Unit). In longitudinal direction of each bay two neighboring slots could be occupied by one FEU (Forty-foot Equivalent Unit). Fig.2A depicts a generic container ship with 13 (nominal) bays and 16 tiers in the grid. The carrier may feature 13 rows as shown in Fig.3. In the example the container ship has seven tiers in the holds and eight tiers on deck while one tier is blocked by hatch covers, Fig.2B.

Fig.3: Side view of container grid with terminal crane

Fig.2C illustrates the formal grid of available slots, the picture corresponding to an empty ship. For port efficiency simulations this grid needs to be provided for each ship as an input. Fig.2D exemplifies one particular load case. All container slots that are being occupied are marked orange. Fig.2E presents those containers that shall be moved marked green. For simplicity no containers are taken into account that should be moved but are stacked below any containers that shall actually be left on board. Nevertheless, some containers may have to be taken off and loaded on again since they stand on top of a hatch which needs to be removed in order to access containers in the hold. These containers are marked blue. Within each simulation a state identifier f_{ijk} is assigned for all combinations of i, j and k , Table II. Note that in Fig.2 just one slice through the ship is displayed. Obviously, other rows would show different loading patterns.

Fig.2F depicts the time needed for each bay to be processed. In the picture the fourth bay to the left, i.e., the fifth bay from the stern when taken into account the bay blocked by the deck house, would need the longest processing time. Meanwhile the fourth bay to the right, i.e., close to the bow, would need the shortest time. Fig.4 gives a visualization from the simulation within the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework* within which the entire simulation process was realized. Here, the container ship contains 13 (nominal) bays in the grid, the third one being blocked as this is where the deck house and engine room are placed.

Table II: State identifier for each slot in container grid

Identifier	Processing of container slot	Color of slot
$f_{ijk} = -1$	Not available for container storage	Gray
$f_{ijk} = 0$	Empty slot at given point in time	White
$f_{ijk} = 1$	Container to be left untouched (not handled)	Orange
$f_{ijk} = 2$	Container to be moved	Green
$f_{ijk} = 3$	Container to be moved off and on due to hatch	Blue

Fig.4: Visualization of a load case within the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework*

4.2. Distribution of containers

For every ship of interest its individual container grid including the "gray spaces" needs to be set up first. While building the grid within the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework* the number of slots available for container storage is computed to be used later for determining load case estimations and for checking simulation input, such as the total amount of containers to be loaded which obviously must not exceed the number of slots available. Further pieces of information associated with each column in the grid (identified via i and j) are the vertical position of the lowest "white" slot (see Table II), the overall number of utilizable slots and the tier (identified by k) at which the hatch is located.

On the basis of the container grid different load cases are realized as shown in Fig.5. A random number r_{ij} between 0 and 1 is computed for each column. According to its value the column is filled with containers, see orange slots in Fig.5A. Partially filled slots will either be filled completely or left empty in dependence of their filling level, borrowing this idea from a volume-of-fluid approach in two-phase fluid dynamics. As soon as all columns are processed the total number of containers that have been stored this way can be summed up. In all likelihood this number of containers will not match the required number of containers that should be on board for the load case at hand. It might either be too many or too few. Therefore, the entire level will have to be slightly lifted (if too few containers were stored initially) or lowered (in case of too many containers). For the adjustment a single factor, a in Fig.5A, is introduced by which to scale the random numbers of all columns. This factor is iteratively changed via a dedicated bi-sectional search until the desired number of containers has been reached. This then constitutes one random "load case" (out of many).

On the basis of any given load case all those containers need to be marked which are to be moved. If we considered the idealized situation in which containers would only be unloaded, the ship would come into port with containers according to the load case and all those containers would be identified that have to be taken off. This so-called "move case" is set up much in the same way as the preceding load case, see illustration in Fig.5B. Random numbers are again generated for every column. Starting from the highest container in the stack the selection now goes top down and is subsequently adjusted to the level that gives the prescribed number of containers to be moved. Naturally, only those containers that are present in the load case can be selected in the move case and, hence, the characteristics of the former determines various properties of the latter.

Fig.5: Container distribution at two consecutive bays for a certain layer j :
 (A) "load case" in which containers are distributed into available slots and
 (B) "move case" in which containers are marked that are to be handled

In addition, whenever a container needs to be moved from below a hatch, the hatch must necessarily be removed first. Unfortunately, it may happen that there are containers on top of this hatch that should actually remain onboard but would need to be lifted off and on again (blue containers in Fig.5B) even though load planners are trying to avoid this scenario. Hatches span entire container bays longitudinally with several hatches in transverse direction. Frequently they are all removed for better visibility during crane operations. In the simulation, therefore, if only one container below deck has to be moved all containers on deck for that bay need to be handled, too. According to *Goussiater* (2007) processing a standard hatch requires about eight minutes while some operators suggest shorter time spans. Since often one bay will be covered by three hatches transversally, an additional 15 minutes per bay are added during the simulation if one or more containers happen to be below deck that require treatment.

As a final result of both the load case and the move case each slot in the container grid has a value assigned according to Table II. Taking into account these state identifiers along with the actual position in space and the relative position towards the quay, the time associated with processing every container in the grid can be calculated. To do so typical move times, see Table III following a report by *Goussiater*, were taken as input for speed calculations. The move times are then summed up bay by bay, resulting in the specific processing time for every bay for the given random loading scenario. It has to be noted that in real life any combination of FEU and TEU might occur. In 2011, worldwide about 45% of all containers were TEU while about 55% were FEU. Consequently, a simple speed up of processing time was applied for all container moves per bay according to this ratio, supposing the differences between moving containers of various sizes are negligible.

5. Optimization of crane allocation

Within the simulation one to six cranes were considered, six being the practical upper number of cranes allocated by many terminals. Three to four cranes are very typical scenarios. Nevertheless, also the time needed for one crane and for two cranes were determined for completeness. If there is only one crane the solution becomes trivial, namely the sum of time for processing each bay plus the time required to move the crane from one bay to the next. In all other situations there are many more possible combinations of allocating cranes. Two major constraints need to be observed, i.e., (i) two neighboring cranes need to have a minimum of one bay in between them to avoid collision and (ii) no crane can evidently overtake any other as they utilize the same rails. Consequently, there is a large yet limited number of perturbations for x cranes operating y bays.

The strategy adopted for solving this task is an exhaustive nested loop structure that investigates all possible solutions for two to six cranes. Operating time is determined for each solution as the maximum time required by the slowest crane. Finally, all potential crane distributions are compared and the fastest is chosen. The computational burden is rather low. It should be kept in mind, however, that for vessels with many bays and if quite a few cranes are involved the effort increases rapidly.

Table III: Times used for speed calculations

Unloading containers from hold	Ideal time in sec	Realistic time in sec	Loading containers into hold	Ideal time in sec	Realistic time in sec
start cycle					
engage	2	4	engage	2	4
hoist in hold	10	10	hoist	8	10
hoist	11	11	travel outward	17	20
travel inward	17	20	lower	10	12
lower	8	10	spot and enter cell guides	11	15
spot	5	10	lower	10	12
disengage	2	4	disengage	2	4
start to get next container on board			start to get next container from terminal		
hoist	8	8	hoist in hold	10	10
travel outward	17	20	hoist	11	12
lower	10	12	travel inward	17	20
spot and enter cell guides	11	15	lower	8	10
lower	10	12	spot	5	5
spot	5	10			
total cycle time	116	146	total cycle time	111	134
moves/hour	31	25	moves/hour	32	27
Unloading containers from deck	Ideal time in sec	Realistic time in sec	Loading containers onto deck	Ideal time in sec	Realistic time in sec
start cycle					
engage	2	4	engage	2	4
hoist	11	15	hoist	5	5
travel inward	17	20	engage twistlocks	15	20
lower	8	10	hoist	10	15
spot	5	10	travel outward	17	20
remove twistlocks	15	20	spot	5	10
hoist, travel, lower, spot	15	20	lower	10	12
disengage	2	4	disengage	2	4
start to get next container on board			start to get next container from terminal		
hoist	8	10	hoist	11	15
travel outward	17	20	travel inward	17	20
spot	5	10	lower	8	10
lower	8	10	spot	2	5
total cycle time	113	153	total cycle time	104	140
moves/hour	32	24	moves/hour	35	26
longitudinal move of crane from one bay to the next					120

6. Performing port efficiency simulations

One port time evaluation for a vessel of about 4000 TEU took approximately 1.5 minutes on a 3 GHz processor. For statistical reasons a large number of load cases were needed, say 2000 as elaborated above, for which the calculation time would have been roughly 50 h in sequential execution. A distributed computing solution was therefore set up, using the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework's* remote computing capabilities. Here, one *Framework* project acted as the administrator that controlled the process as a whole. This "mother" project called several other "child" projects in parallel that were run in batch mode as external computations.

Within the administrator project a standard Design-of-Experiment, namely a Sobol distribution, was conducted whose main variables were (i) the number of containers to be moved and (ii) the total number of containers to be loaded. A few additional variables were taken into account that addressed the spread of the loading pattern, giving denser or sparser container distributions. For an even spread of solution points as needed for a statistical analysis with sufficient instances in each group the design space was mapped to avoid infeasible scenarios in which more containers would have to be moved than were actually loaded in the first place. For each loading scenario the administrator project exported the free variables as arguments to the external computations. Once these external computations had finished the results were passed back to the administrator project.

7. Container ships studied

Several container ships were studied that would potentially compete with each other in an Asian trade as described above. One ship is a standard Panmax vessel of 4250 TEU cascaded down from other routes, being disposed there by newer and larger carriers. One ship is a smaller design of 3700 TEU with its deck house at the stern. The vessel is called TKMS 3700 as it was designed by TKMS in Emden. For some of its features see *Hinrichsen et al. (2007)*. The two other ships are novel concepts developed jointly by Germanischer Lloyd and FutureShip. They are called CV 3700 12x15 and CV 3700 13x14, indicating the effective number of bays available for container stowage by the number of rows. (Note that the number of nominal bays used in the container grid during the port efficiency simulation is one bay higher so as to capture the region blocked by deck house and engine room.) Finally, for additional comparison a new open top design with about 4100 TEU is considered (but not elaborated here).

The principle particulars of the ships are summarized in Table IV. Fig.6 presents the general arrangements of three selected vessels. Fig.7 shows the longitudinal distribution of container slots per bay (similar to a sectional area curve). The bays with zero container slots give the position of deck house and engine room.

Table IV: Principle particulars of container ships studied

	Panmax 4250	TKMS 3700	CV 3700 12x15	CV 3700 13x14
Length b.p.	247.1 m	232 m	211.9 m	226.9 m
Breadth	32.2 m	32.2 m	37.3 m	35.20 m
Design draft	12.8 m	10.5 m	11.0 m	11.0 m
Depth	19.3 m	18.6 m	19.9 m	19.9 m
Number of nominal bays used in container grid	18	15	13	14
Number of bays available for container stowage	17	14	12	13
Number of rows	13	13	15	14
Descriptor [bay] x [row]	17x13	14x13	12x15	13x14

Fig.6: General arrangements of (A) Panmax 4250, (B) TKMS 3700 and (C) CV 3700 12x15

Fig.7: Number of container slots per bay (bay 1 is at the stern, deck house and engine room are counted as one bay)

It can be seen in Fig.7 that Panmax 4250 is long and rather slender with many bays and relatively low numbers of container slots per bay while CV 3700 12x15 has the lowest number of bays and the highest number of container slots for any single bay. TKMS 3700 features a rather even distribution of container slots longitudinally and, prominently, the deck house and engine room are located right at the stern.

Fig.8: Scatter plots for port time vs. containers moved for different number of cranes

8. Selected results

Simulation results are presented with focus on Panmax 4250, CV 3700 12x15 and TKMS 3700. Fig.8 shows port time for three vessels over a range of TEU to be moved from 400 to 3600. The graphs are scatter diagrams as they results from the simulation without further processing. It can be readily appreciated that the more cranes are utilized the faster the operation which is, of course, expected. It

can also be observed that on average some ships perform better than others. However, the ranking partly depends on the number of cranes involved and the number of TEU to be handled. It is apparent that the spread between faster and slower loading scenarios is higher for lower number of containers to be moved. This is quite reasonable since fewer containers can be either stored close to each other (yielding favorable loading scenarios) or put far from each other (leading to unfavorable distributions). (Since loading experts carefully avoid the latter and work towards the former more importance could be assigned towards the faster simulations. One way to account for this is to consider significant values, i.e., the mean of the 1/3 fastest port times.)

Fig.9: Statistically evaluated port efficiency

Fig.9 compares the Panmax 4250 and the novel CV 3700 12x15 statistically. The figure shows mean (light bar), standard deviation (colored rectangles below and above the mean) as well as minimum and maximum occurrences (black lines) within the sets of grouped data. Groups comprise containers to be moved in 400 TEU intervals. Within each of these groups 200 loading scenarios are present,

lending a sufficient base for analyses. The data clearly suggest an advantage of the CV 3700 12x15 when compared to the Panmax 4250 with its 17 bays and 13 rows in almost all groups.

It should be kept in mind, naturally, that the port times resulting from the simulations stem from ideal container handling, see assumptions and simplifications above. Waiting times and breaks for personnel as well as possible delays are not explicitly accounted for and would need to be added, at least partially. As a consequence, emphasis should be put on the potential for time savings rather than on the actual times spent in port. The latter depend too much on the port specifics as can be seen in Table V. When averaging the performance over loading cases from 400 to 2000 TEU and over two to five cranes for a representative trade in Asian ports CV 3700 12x15 needs 12.7 hours while Panmax 4250 spends 13.7 hours. This is an advantage of one hour in port efficiency that originates directly from the ship's layout.

The following ship layout features were considered to have a prominent effect on container movement times and, hence, on port efficiency:

- More containers on deck are favorable since less hatches need to be moved, see Fig.10A; CV 3700 12x15 has the highest ratio in the group of reference vessels.
- Less bays are advantages as cranes need not be moved longitudinally so often, see Fig.10B; here again CV 3700 12x15 has an advantage, namely the lowest number of bays. (Note that this becomes a drawback if a very high number of cranes is allocated since they would then not be able to operate concurrently any more.)
- Low variability of container slots on deck is better to give cranes an even work load, see Fig.10C; for this measure TKMS 3700 is the best in the group.

Fig.10: Analysis of ship layout features

A first simplified formula was created on the basis of these three factors; see Fig.10D for a comparison between simulation and approximation. Any approximating formula will aim at getting a first guess of expected container movement rate without need for sophisticated simulations. The

ranking is captured well while the absolute accuracy is still acceptable. It seems premature to publish the formula due to the low number of vessels investigated. Nevertheless, it serves to underline that the effects mentioned are important contributors to port efficiency.

9. Verification and validation

Verifications and validations were undertaken to ensure the viability of the port time simulations. However, it has to be noted that due to a lack of outside references this is a delicate task.

The optimization of crane allocation was first realized within Excel before being implemented as a feature within the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework*. Systematic comparisons between the two implementations showed full agreement, giving confidence that the tool at least computes the right data for the proposed model. Two academic test cases were studied to see if the port time simulations would yield results that could be (a) anticipated a priori and (b) interpreted easily. The two academic container vessels were a pure open-top rectangular box and a box whose bottom was linearly raised from the maximum section in the middle towards both the stem and the bow. The simulation results were consistent with the expectations. For instance, with one crane only the port time increases linearly with the number of containers to be moved. Furthermore, both the pure box and the box with the raised bottom led to the same statistical results. This was also the case for two crane scenario which is reasonable as the cranes will not interfere. Finally, higher number of cranes gave the speed up expected, for instance half the time if two cranes are employed instead of just one.

Systematic plausibility checks were made for all data. The most important benchmark is the TEU rate computed vs. the typical number of container moves reported. *Goussiattiner (2007)* states that gross crane rate for conventional cranes is about 30 containers per hour in single lift mode, see also Table III, which is in line with reported terminal productivity as given in *New Zealand (2011)*, see Table IV. *Goussiattiner (2007)* further elaborates that the sustainable gross rate should be at least 35 containers per hour while the technical productivity rate for conventional cranes is even greater, namely about 45 containers per hour, even if this is not yet realized by many terminals in the world. The data produced within the simulation yield results in the mid thirties, see Fig.10D. This seems an acceptable outcome, considering the idealizations within the simulation model.

Table V: Typical number of containers moved per crane in Asian ports

Port	Containers moves	Port	Containers moves
Ningbo	31/h	Quindao	26/h
Hong-Kong	31/h	Dalian	26/h
Kaohsiung	29/h	Shanghai	25/h

10. Conclusions

The paper discussed a statistical approach to port efficiency simulations for container ships. Tangible differences could be identified for the time spent in moving given numbers of containers depending on ship layout. In the simulation a shorter and beamer design showed higher port efficiency than a longer and more slender ship of Panmax size. One reason could be the higher number of container slots on deck for the shorter and beamer ship which results in fewer hatches to be moved in the statistical mean. Another reason may be found in the fewer numbers of bays to operate. Particularly if only a few cranes are available less crane time is lost by transferring from bay to bay. The container ship with its deck house at the stern performed very well. There is, however, a certain limit to this particular arrangement as the line of sight restricts the number of layers on deck.

The benefits when comparing one design to another depend on the most likely operational profile. For instance, one hour of average port time could be saved for moving 800 to 2000 TEU when comparing a standard Panmax 4250 with 17 bays and 13 rows to a compacter ship of 3700 TEU with 12 bays and 15 rows. The time saved in port can be used to decrease the speed required to cover the distance

between two ports within a fixed schedule. On average this leads to lower fuel consumption and a reduction of green house gas emissions. In addition to this advantage for the ship operator, the terminal operator gets the benefit of improved gross crane rates. Hence, reduced port time not only leads to lower vessel speeds at sea but, ideally, also to more ships that can be processed by the terminal with the available hardware.

11. Outlook

In the work presented statistical modeling was utilized in order to see if there are differences between design options that really show potential beyond the noise of the underlying simulation. It is believed that a speed up in port efficiency of one hour should be larger than the uncertainty caused by the assumptions and simplifications. In order to increase the quality of the simulations, quite a few additions would be needed: Inevitable delays and downtimes, possible use of double cycling instead of pure single-lift operation, spreader utilization (which is known to significantly speed up operations) and further concentration of containers in certain bays are just a few important issues. It remains to be studied if higher fidelity can still be captured statistically or if a discrete event simulation would be needed to properly account for all states on both the "wet" and "dry" side. Complementing considerations during ship design there are, naturally, quite a few measures that the terminal operator can pursue, too, in order to push port efficiency. Examples are further training of personnel, introduction of automatic mooring systems, advanced twistlock handling, crane control systems to avoid wrong container moves etc. It seems a fair supposition that all measures will help to decrease port time, even if they may not simply add up, and will contribute to higher energy efficiency in ship operations if utilized for lower speeds.

Acknowledgement

The short and beamy container ship was jointly developed by Germanischer Lloyd SE and FutureShip GmbH - A GL Company. We thank our colleague Fridtjof Rohde for the general arrangements and his design expertise. The layout of the ship by TKMS was supplied by Gregor Schellenberger, professor at the University of Applied Sciences in Bremen. Furthermore, thank Henning Dichter from Hamburger Hafen und Logistik AG (HHLA) for the tour over the container terminal Burchardkai, allowing to validate some of the assumptions made for the simulations.

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The Digital Handover – Shipyards as Producers of Life-Cycle Maintenance Models

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Abstract

The value of intelligent 3D models of the as-built asset, combined with advanced information management technologies, is being increasingly recognized in the marine industry. A complete digital counterpart of the physical ship is compiled during its design and construction and may subsequently be used to support every aspect of its operation. This paper provides a comprehensive overview of challenges, solutions and best practice in the handover from shipbuilder to operator of a complete digital information asset.

1. Introduction

As vessels are large and spatially complex, the parties responsible for in-service integrity management and safety at sea have recognized the benefit of access to up-to-date 3D models in the support of many critical processes. Having access to accurate 3D geometry greatly enhances the efficiency of critical processes such as; damage assessment, risk based inspection, upgrade design and model preparation for safety related training and simulation. The vision of many vessel operators is to have the ability to maintain an as-operated 3D model that is the basis of all 3D based in-service activities.

Fig.1: The vision of an oil and gas super major, a graphical database to support operational activities

2. The Background

To understand the drivers for this industry vision it is necessary to take a look at the existing practices in the industry.

2.1 Multiple models supporting the engineering and design work

3D models are a common basis for many of today's modern engineering processes; however these 3D models differ in the detail of their content and are highly optimised to suit the process they are used to support. E.g. a 3D model to support hydrodynamic analysis need to have an accurate representation of the geometry of spaces but not much else, and in order that the hydrodynamic analysis software operated efficiently the 3D model contains no more than is needed. On the other hand a model to support training and simulation must have textures and colours that closely resemble the real operational environment, but exact geometry is not a must.

Fig 2: Various CAD models, 2D or 3D, are created to support engineering and design work in yard

2.2 Drawing based handover to owner/operator and Class

Current industry practices do not require the handover of 3D models to the owner or class, partially because historically there has been no need for this and because the shipyards do not wish to handover the model which represents significant Intellectual Property in terms of the man-hours invested to design the vessel and any design or production techniques that have been developed by the shipyard. The design office must however deliver the mandatory drawings to Class and the owner, and accurate lists of machinery and equipment as well as supplier documentation. The preparation of the handover documents is essentially an overhead for the yard as there is currently no incentive for them to invest in preparing higher quality data for handover.

Fig.3: Paper drawings from a shipyard ready to be delivered to the owner

2.3 Re-modelling from drawings

When a 3D model needed by the ship owner or class society it is common practice today to re-create the 3D model from the drawings provided by the yard. This practice not only requires more work to define in 3D what was already modelled by the yard, but also introduces the opportunity for human error and increases the complexity in terms of managing an up-to-date model data. In addition this practice poses a major risk in terms of IPR protection.

Most technical data leakages stem from ship owners and classification societies, resulting from everyday shipping activity:

- Because ships are sold with their drawings, drawings are passed from the selling to the buying ship owner at ship's sale;
- Similarly, when ships change classification society, drawings are passed from the losing class to the gaining class;
- The superintendents give copies of the necessary structural drawings to the thickness measurement companies when steel thickness measurements are required;
- The superintendents give copies of the necessary structural drawings, annotated to specify the elements to be renewed, to repair shipyards.
- Finite element models for the calculation of the points with the highest stress concentration, or stability models for emergency response services, are routinely made from the drawings.
- In recent times, owners have started to create their own geometrical 3D models out of the main ships drawings, for use in the life cycle tools supplied by the class. This is also true for oil operators who are starting to have 3D models for their FPSOs.

It is clear that this practice reflects the easiest way to do things and is thus the de facto standard. The advent of electronic documents only made this practice easier. However standards such as PDF that do allow some kind of security are a good basis for adding a layer of IPR protection.

3. Trends that are driving the move to 3D model handover

The use of 3D models in operations is increasing gradually due to a number of factors. One major influencer is the offshore industry where the handover of a more detailed as built package has been mandated for many years. While on the other hand there is a general industry trend to move away from ships as a commodity and see ships in the same light as aircraft i.e. valuable revenue earning assets. This in turn is driving a more lifecycle focused approach to ship building and operation where the digital asset plays an ever more important role.

3.1. Management of an evergreen engineering model in offshore

In the offshore industry early adopters are already managing and maintaining as operated engineering models. Which means they ensure that every physical modification to the plant is made reflected in the digital plant that supports it. Aside from greater investment in the IT systems that support operations one of the reasons this way of working has been possible is that the consortium of companies involved in the design construction and operation is all under the ultimate control of the Operator. I.e. those operators who contract out the initial engineering work also manage the engineering contractors who make changes for refit or upgrade projects. Thus a single engineering & design system can be mandated for the new build and also used to capture any subsequent changes without requiring any remodelling or data conversion.

Fig.4: Global work sharing in a typical offshore project

They achieve this result through a combination of laser scanning, which is then used to reverse engineer 3D models for older assets, and a global concurrent engineering platform that allows subcontractors to work locally on their modification projects and replicate the changes directly to a master database at the corporate headquarters.

Fig.5: Reverse engineering a laser point cloud to create a production ready CAD model

3.2 Focus on Hull Integrity Management in Floating Offshore Installations

The current trend towards deep water oil and gas is seeing a continued growth in the construction and operation of FPSO type installations. Their prolonged operational cycles and lack of dry dock time has resulted in the current focus on Hull integrity management, which is becoming a critical safety factor. Hull integrity is a process that can greatly benefit from an integrated approach to its management, in particular the use of a master model to capture the as operated status of the structures is seen as a particularly important deliverable.

Fig.6: Hull Condition monitoring is a labour and risk intensive task on FOIs

3.3 Hull Integrity management by Class societies

Although Asset management software is widely used in the offshore industry it is often primarily focused on the plant or processing functions due to their direct relationship to the earning capabilities of the asset, in this space generic asset management software is often used such as Maximo or SAP. In the structural integrity asset management area more specialised software from the Class societies is used. As there was significant potential for efficiency gains Class societies have been pushing for a 3D model based structural integrity management process.

The monitoring of ships during their whole operational life requires hull Life cycle monitoring “LCM” software systems, which increasingly consist of an integrated suite of tools, where the 3D models play a major role, typically: a structural geometrical 3D viewer, a survey tool for steel thickness measurements and observation input and reporting (coating, cracking, defects, pitting and buckling), an integrity tool for advanced processing (e.g. prediction of structural condition), modules for risk-based inspection, finite element analysis, stability and hydrodynamic calculations.

Fig. 7: BV's Veristar Hull LCM software interface

3.4. New business models for Ship Owners

Ship owners are continuously seeking new ways to keep their fleet as profitable as possible, sometimes this focuses on extending the life of vessels in which case good management of structural integrity is a must. In other cases it focuses on finding the right time and price to charter vessels, something that is often affected by the life expectancy of the overall structure. 3D models

significantly improve a ship operators ability to have an overview of the condition of their vessel hull structures. There are also cases of ship operators who use 3D model to facilitate rapid crew training, training them with simulations on shore before the ship has even changed hands from the Shipyard or current owner.

3.5. New business models for Shipyards

The shipbuilding industry has for many years aspired to adopt the business models of the aerospace and automotive industries, where products are more standardised, and higher profit margins can be achieved with less manpower. However the economics of ship operations has never favoured this approach, meaning shipyards are often chosen simply for their ability to deliver by a certain time at a certain price, preferably as low as possible.

During shipbuilding downturns when there is less demand for simple transportation vessels shipbuilders are taking the opportunity to specialise in more complex, higher value vessel types. In fact in high labour cost countries this has become the only way to survive, as seen by the waves of shipyard consolidation into larger groups that specialize in either Naval, Offshore, Cruise or other specialised ship types.

Specialisation also results in new business opportunities particularly in the through life support of vessels. This approach has long been the case for naval vessels where the design and construction contract often came with a contract for in service support. This model is very applicable to highly specialised vessel types such as dredgers, where many of the major equipment items are engineered and built by the shipyard group but we are also seeing the first shipyards who are replicating this model for passenger vessels and offshore support vessels. The management of a 3D model could be a key deliverable that supports these new business models.

4. Benefits of handing over a 3D model to operations

The use of 3D models in operations benefits many parties in the shipping industry below is a summary of the envisioned benefits upon reaching this vision.

4.1. For Owner Operators

Owner Operators are clearly the major benefactors of the realisation of this handover vision, not only having an accurate basis for their as operated master model but being able to use this data for many lifecycle processes. For example;

- Ship owners want to plan steel renewal for the next dry-docking of the ship
- To reduce down time for emergency repairs,
- To adjust the condition of their vessel to foster favorable chartering conditions,
- To take various decisions involving the structural condition
- To conveniently store inspection data.
- To rapidly create a model for simulation and training purposes

4.2. For Shipyards

Handover of shipyard model data is often seen today as a zero benefit work package, in that the shipyard have additional work to do and have little return on investment. However, arguably the investment of man-hours to create a 3D model is mostly done to benefit the shipyard that uses the 3D model to product production instructions. Only the preparation of this model data for use in operations is an overhead. Shipyards can benefit from the use of 3D model in operations if they take ownership of the process and data.

- Provide a value added service to loyal customers
- Take ownership of their intellectual property as compared to the handover of easily transferable drawings
- Potential to license the use of the model via Digital Right Management.
- Play a greater role in the lifecycle of their products and develop new revenue streams from that.
- Gather feedback on the through life performance of their vessels allowing them to further optimise – steel thickness frame spacing etc.

4.3. For Regulatory bodies (class)

The classification societies want to increase the safety of navigation, avoiding ships structural failures, checking that the structure is properly maintained and in good condition, thus avoiding hazardous structural failure at sea, all this requiring a certain level of technical information. Class societies and other regulatory bodies can greatly benefit from the use of 3D model in operations primarily as they are highly focused on the hull structural integrity.

- Support of 3D based hull integrity programs
- Support for Structural analysis
- A basis for Digital classification.

5. Requirements

Clearly progress is being made in term of the handover and use of 3D model in operations however in order to achieve the vision of an evergreen as-operated 3D model several changes are needed in the way the industry works.

5.1 Shipyards handover or sharing of the as-built digital asset

To realise this vision shipyards would be expected to handover or share an accurate as-built version of the 3D model or better still the complete digital asset to operators and regulatory bodies. This as-built model would serve as a baseline for the as-operated models. The as built digital asset would be more than just the 3D model used for detailed design and construction it would also contain reference to any other documentation associated with the product such as supplier documentation, original specifications and requirements and even disposal instructions.

Aside from the obvious IPR issues shipyards do not actually model the exact as-built status of what they build as their 3D modelling is focused on delivering work instructions to production. This often means last minute changes made in the dock or shop floors are not reflected in the 3D model. For shipyard to deliver a true as-built model 3 challenges would need to be addressed:

- A suitable business model found to motivate shipyards to do this additional work.
- A new process of capturing last minute changes would be needed
- A method to protect shipyard IPR

5.2. Operators and Class need a mechanism to facilitate the updating of a master model from multiple model formats from multiple parties.

Assuming an accurate unified as-built model can be obtained from shipbuilders the maintenance of it would require ship operators, repair yards and class societies to work to a closed loop process to ensure that any changes to the physical asset are reflected in the digital asset.

Fig.8: Ideal exchange of lifecycle information if owner and class society are in steady state

If there was only one 3D model that could be used for all the in service processes, and if the owner and class society remained constant throughout the lifecycle of a vessel this process would be relatively easy to achieve, however this is not the case.

As mentioned in the background section there is a variety of different 3D models that will be useful in the operational life of a vessel. These models not only refer to different sets of information but they are also likely to be compatible with a variety of different software vendor's platforms and in turn versions of those platforms.

Add to this the fact that a vessel will change ownership and associated class society several times in its operational life and it becomes clear there is a need for a mechanism that would separate the useful information from the issues of file format, model type and ownership.

This requires a common conceptual model to be created that will allow transfer of geometry and metadata over a variety of file formats to generate a variety of model types for the different business processes to be supported.

Fig. 9: Common conceptual model or framework that supports multiple owners and file formats

This conceptual frame work would facilitate the exchange of model data which would then need to be managed in a system that could record and propagate changes in the data.

5.3 Suitable IPR protection system that has safety in mind

As we have highlighted in the section relating to shipyards and IPR mechanism will be required to make this vision reality. However it is critical that this IPR system take into account emergency situations on board i.e. the models must remain readily available for ship emergencies. Licenses expiry dates must be continuously checked, ideally by some piece of software, so that models cannot be blocked due to any IPR issue.

5.4 Longevity of electronic data

Vessels stay in operation for around 20- 30 years depending on role therefore the vision of maintaining 3D models throughout their lifecycle requires a form of electronic data that will be readable and usable for the duration of this time frame.

6. Recommended actions

The benefits of handing over 3D models to operations is so great that the shipping industry is focused on solving these challenges, the following section takes a look at the recommended activities that would need to be undertaken to realize this vision..

6.2. Enabling the shipyards to be producers and custodians of Lifecycle maintenance models

Shipyards may think today that giving access to 3D models is a sheer matter of convenience for the Owners, but they need to get prepared to an increased demand from Owners willing to get models at ship delivery time. Shipyards have indeed the same problem of access to their suppliers' models: they need the external shape and connections of equipment and have sometimes difficulties getting them.

This issue of life cycle models could even be a first step towards the extension of today's shipyards beyond the traditional role of shipbuilder, leading to "one stop companies for ships", providing all the necessary services to the ship-owner. Shipyards may value that "life cycle services" are less dependent of the economic environment.

A "one stop company for ships" could include any of the following activities, in addition to shipbuilding: management of technical data databases, engineering calculations, preparation and implementation of dry-docks and repairs, retrofitting and training in the use of equipment and vessels. Operators and Class and software vendors need to work closely with shipyards to ensure that a suitable business model can be found and that the software components needed to make this work are available.

6.3. A centralised shipyard owned models database

In order to improve safety at sea through better access to up-to-date documentation the European ships and maritime equipment association "SEA Europe" and the Shipbuilders' association of Japan "SAJ" intend to issue a Ship Construction File "SCF" detailed industry standard on July 2016. This SCF will focus on providing access to the documents that the shipyards deliver with their ships. The SCF database will be split between "not very sensitive" documents, which can be kept on board, and "sensitive" documents, which will be kept in an ashore archive center.

The logical extension of this concept is to provide a repository for models related to each vessel. Therefore industry proposes that, in parallel to the SCF, the shipyards will have a database dedicated to ships' models, that we tentatively call here the Model Repository File "MRF". We imagine that the MRF will consist of a database of models supplied by the shipyard and access management software.

Fig. 10: Proposed use of a Shipyard Model Repository File (MRF)

Due to the volatility of shipyards ownership and exposure to the economy, it is likely to be the case that the MRF data would need to be placed into the custody of the relevant Classification societies, who have a higher likelihood of remaining under the same ownership. Even then strict legal agreements would need to be made regarding actual ownership of the models.

6.4. Form a Joint Industry Project to define a common conceptual frame work to facilitate the exchange of models and data

As model data is likely to come from a variety of shipbuilding modelling systems, and is likely to be utilised in a variety of Asset /lifecycle management systems by the operators a common conceptual frame work is essential to enable consistent application of the handover vision. Only when the key stake holders work together with shipyards will a solution be found that benefits all parties in a satisfactory way. Together software providers, class societies, shipyards and operators can identify the information that needs to be shared, and from that develop a framework of information exchange for models and the appropriate IPR protection.

6.5. Mechanisms to protect IPR of shipyards

Shipyards are very vigilant about protecting their know-how, especially structural design. Shipyards are afraid that a competitor builds sister ships of their ships, but also of leakage of valuable design information. In order for this whole vision to become a reality there is an underlying need to support this concept with suitable IPR protection. The various levels and techniques that can be used to protect IPR are discussed in the following sections.

6.5.1. Simplified model

Certain models required in operational activities can be simplified a lot without compromising safety, for example models for hull condition monitoring only require enough geometry to be able to recognize the structural elements when inspected. This makes it difficult for another shipyard to build a sister ship:

- The only requirement is to be able to recognize the structural element which is inspected;
- The shape of the element can be approximate, as long as it is possible to identify it;
- The specific hull form can be replaced by any standard form, in case the hull form cannot be supplied;
- CAD model coordinates or frame shapes could be slightly altered through an automatic mechanism.
- The CAD editor provides an Export module which can filter out all types of details (cutouts, small brackets, etc) and even complete parts of the CAD model, if the shipyard wishes so;
- It can filter all elements only required during the construction phase of the ship;
- Small cut-outs or brackets can be removed.

This capability is already standard in the most used design tools such as AVEVA Marine where the fully topological model allows the production hull form to be replaced with a modified version before export of the structural elements, and the need to simplify geometry before exporting FEM models has resulted in new idealization capabilities that can be applied to any AVEVA Marine hull model.

Fig. 11: AVEVA Marine hull model before (left) and after idealisation

AVEVA Marine in this case provides a variety of filtering mechanisms to allow the Shipyard to tune the output for the best results depending on the further use of the model. This idealization process also significantly reduces the file size when exporting the 3D data to a single file as is the case with OpenHCM.

6.5.2. Delay after delivery

A simple option to protect sensitive IPR is to agree to give delayed access to the models, for example 10 years after delivery when the models become of historical interest and less sensitive. On the owner's side, it is after 10 years that it is especially worth paying attention to the structural condition. The use of the OpenHCM standard as storage format will help to be able to read the models after so long a delay.

6.5.3. IPR protection by DRM

Some lifecycle models will, still contain information that shipyards deem as confidential, such as:

- major cut-outs,
- reinforcing of major cut-outs,

- plate thicknesses allowing the calculation of the total weight and therefore the price
- midship sections showing major technical choices.

Therefore the use of Digital rights management “DRM” is a potential solution for additional protection for shipyards’ IPR. DRM is used today by companies distributing media content or software in view to avoiding piracy. Some specialized companies provide “ready-made” DRM solutions, but basically they all check that the users are doing what they have the right to do, typically in terms of downloading and copying rights.

This technology has generated legal disputes since its introduction, users complaining about abusive limitation of their rights and sometimes deploring intrusion into the privacy sphere. If we consider the use of DRM with a MRF database of models we can imagine the following scenario: Typically, the user connects himself to the MRF website and activates the encrypted model. The system requires the user to sign, preferably electronically, an NDA or verifies that there is an existing NDA that covers the use of the model by that user. The NDA requires the authorization of the designer (e.g. the shipyard) and the model editor (e.g. the classification society) for disclosure to a third party. After this activation, the user can handle the model through its LCM system. Thus, the shipyards keep full traceability of the models, NDAs and accesses (e.g. of class, owners, TMCOs and repair yards).

Fig. 12: Entry of Non Disclosure Agreement “NDA”

The accessibility of the models should be in line with the duration of the commercial contract: normally, owner and class should have unlimited access as long as the vessel remains in their ownership /jurisdiction, and a thickness measurement company should get about three months access, which would be good enough for performing the required measurements.

In addition, the models will need to be re-activated, say, every six months, in order to keep continuous track of their status.

Fig. 13: Activation of ship model

6.5.4. Legal framework required

Aside from the various digital means of protecting IPR a good legal model is required. The most basic form of this is the inclusion of a solid non-disclosure agreement in the contract, which agrees that any digital data handed over is protected and may not be disclosed to any third party with perhaps the exception of the Class societies. However this situation becomes more complex when we consider the reality of remodeling during the lifecycle of a vessel.

The basic legal principle is that the ship design belongs to the ship's designer and the modeling work belongs to the model editor, i.e. the entity who makes the model, whether the model is created by the shipyard or outside the shipyard. As we cannot split those two aspects, the IPR belongs jointly to the designer and to the model editor. Therefore communication to a third party cannot be done without agreement from both the ship's designer and the model editor.

Today the editor of the ship's model is legally in a fuzzy situation, somewhere between the general indifference regarding the whereabouts of the model and the risk of being sued by the construction shipyard. This should be clarified by the implementation of an IPR system, the status of non-registered models becoming "pirate copy", with the risk of some technical limitation in the future or of being sued by shipyards.

The above IPR system schema could be expanded in the future as follows:

- Models made outside shipyards carry as much shipyard confidential information as models exported from shipyards. The editor of the models may also wish to avoid legal problems with the shipyards and to benefit from a DRM mechanism. He could voluntarily register and deposit his model into the shipyard's MRF. Afterwards, the use of the model would be the same as for models created by the shipyard. The IPR mechanism could apply to all models, shipyard-made or not.
- As MRF models will be updated by the users, a versioning will take care of the successive versions of the model.
- In the future, MRF could become the repository of other types of digital models needed by life-cycles systems, such as finite element or stability models.

Shipyards would thus benefit from the database of all existing models for their ships. Once stored in the shipyard repository, there is a market for those models: shipyards can grant an access license to third parties, typically: new ship owners (after sale of the ship) or new class (after change of class). This would definitively solve the problem of availability of ships models, by defining a simple location where all existing models can be retrieved.

7. Progress to date

The benefit of using 3D models in operations has been highlighted at several international conferences by some of the major Classification societies, and is therefore beginning to attract the attention of operators. As a result many of the component parts of this vision are in place today.

7.1. The Open Hull Condition Monitoring standard

A consortium of Class societies, software providers and thickness measurement companies have developed the OpenHCM standard, openhcm.spruz.com, which provides a standard for 3D models that support thickness measurement and thus the structural integrity management process. At the time of writing, two major CAD vendors are able to export lightweight models which can directly be used in the Class Societies software for hull integrity management.

Fig.14: Hull model in AVEVA Marine

Fig.15: Same model transferred to BV Veristar using OpenHCM

It specifically deals with 3D modeling of the ship structure and related measurements. Models here are XML files, organized according to an XML Schema Definition (XSD file), which is documented in the standard. The size of OpenHCM ship models is in the order of 50 MB.

7.2. 3D design systems becoming more open

3D design systems are becoming more open in general as the need to share data with competing systems grows. What was once a risk is now seen as an opportunity.

Fig. 16: AVEVA MARINE supports a variety of import and export formats that enable collaboration and global working with partners

7.3 .Lifecycle Management Systems

There are several software re products on the market that aim to provide management of lifecycle data. These are mainly focused on the management of structured text and product structures but not 3D models coming from a variety of sources over a long time period. These systems have the potential to provide the basis for the evergreen digital asset vision. AVEVA NET is one such system that has been developed with the concept of a digital asset in mind. It features a highly configurable data model that can captures all product data related to a vessel, be that original requirements, supplier documentation, 2D and 3D CAD models and product structures and it is provided with a web

based interface that allows users in globally distributed locations to access the data in a consistent way. More significantly, however, AVEVA NET has a set of gateways available which are focused on the transformation of industry standard CAD formats to a neutral data format. These gateways can already take Hull data from several leading design systems and extract the full 3D geometry and metadata to a neutral format and a web viewable 3D model.

Fig. 17: AVEVA offers gateways for many software systems and 3D design tools, which enable the extraction and visualisation of intelligent documents and datasets in AVEVA NET

It may not come as a surprise that AVEVA NET has been used to build solutions for lifecycle maintenance activities on the oil and gas industry. Here operators are regularly faced with the challenge of managing handover of data from several CAD systems, a variety of document formats and thousands of unclassified hard copies of drawings. The ISO 15926 standard is used extensively in this industry to facilitate the common framework for data exchange between multiple parties.

Fig. 18: AVEVA NET is used extensively in operational plant projects to facilitate handover of CAD data

7.4. Proposal for a Joint Industry Project

Oil and gas majors, class societies and software vendors have already held initial meetings to form a Joint Industry Project, with the vision of using shipyard models in operations. The proposed project has the following scope.

Phase 1 will focus on understanding and solving the issues in the current business model and will use the already developed OpenHCM standard as a basis of this work.

ID	Description
Work pack 1	Workshops with Shipyards/EPCs and Operators to identify the value of the digital handover assuming the whole production model will be handed over in an as built condition. Or identifying what parts of the model are acceptable to handover.
Work pack 2	Identify and test mechanisms to protect IPR on OpenHCM models, including standardizing the levels of detail required to generate useful models.
Work pack 3	Test the use of Open HCM model in through-life environment, i.e. feeding back the actual thickness of structural elements as recorded in the OpenHCM models to a master 3D model, and then using this to derive updated FEM models and strength analysis results. Modifying the structural arrangement in the master 3D model and deriving an up-to-date FEM and OpenHCM model for strength analysis and condition monitoring.
Work pack 4	Document finding and best practices from the above processes regarding levels of detail required, model ownership and rights etc.

Phase 2 will focus on the other models that can be handed over, developing the exchange of models for Hydrostatic analysis, structural analysis and possibly systems (outfitting) based on the finding of the Phase 1 work packages.

ID	Description
Work pack 1	Establish the ground rules for further exchange standards for compartmentation, hull forms and FEA models. Including identifying levels of detail
Work pack 2	Develop initial versions of these standards
Work pack 3	Develop interfaces from CAD tools and into Class / asset management tools
Work pack 4	Investigate the interoperability of these standards with the aim to maintain a single models or master model for operations.
Work pack 5	Test the use of the interoperable models in through life environment, i.e. making updates, refit, model ownership and rights, etc.
Work pack 6	Document finding and best practices

7.5. Pilot operations

The use of 3D modeling is ultimately of benefit to the wide maritime community. Today, the use by shipyards of 3D models and electronic drawings to perform classification and maintenance tasks has been limited to pilot schemes. The aim must be to extend the initiative, so that it becomes common practice throughout the industry. We can guess that it could take a long time before the IPR system, as described in this paper, is standardized and generalized. Whence the idea of gathering a team of industrial partners, e.g. organized as a Joint industry project (JIP), to build, in the short future, a core version of this system. Once developed, this core version, which will include at least a central database and a DRM distribution mechanism, will be immediately available to support the export of shipyards' models during the industrial partners' commercial activities. Afterwards, this IPR system can progressively be generalized, through either a wider commercialization of this core version or active promotion by the shipyards' associations.

Fig. 18: Shipyard model used in pilot operation

8. Conclusion

The handover of as built 3D models to operations has always shown potential but there has never been the compelling reason for shipyards to do this. As 3D based condition monitoring, simulation and structural analysis gain popularity and acceptance in the ship operations field the pressure is increasing for shipyard to handover models.

However, to realize the benefits of model reuse and lifecycle management the industry must act as a whole, ensuring shipyards have a viable business model and motivation to produce accurate as built models with suitable IPR protection, and ensuring operators can read and exchange model data in various formats throughout the lifecycle of their assets.

The technology has long existed to enable this vision; it is now up to the operators, shipyards and class societies to develop the mechanisms that will ensure acceptance of this new way of working.

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Distributed Cooperative Algorithms for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles in Marine Search Missions

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Abstract

Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) have found their application in exploration and surveillance. This paper describes the development of AUVs with capabilities for multi agent exploration and proposes a cooperative distributed search algorithm based on a minimum entropy approach. The work is motivated by the project “Thesaurus”, whose ultimate goal is to survey marine areas of archaeological interest in the Tuscan Archipelago. The cooperative algorithm prescribes that each vehicle moves on the exploration area taking into account communication constraints and an a priori prediction probability map, which is updated on line as the mission proceeds. The prior probability map over the exploration area is built through Gaussian kernel approximation, on the basis of previous findings and historical archival data.

1. Introduction

The project “Thesaurus”, funded by Tuscany Region, aims to develop techniques for systematic exploration of marine areas of archaeological interest through team of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs). The project has several different specific objectives:

- development of AUVs capable to carry side-scan sonar and optical payloads at depth of 300 m, with 12 hours of autonomy at 2.5 knots cruising speed;
- definition of a prediction probability map of marine areas in the Tuscan Archipelago;
- implementation of acoustic communication modalities and procedure for a network of at least three vehicles;
- definition of a cooperative search strategy, to be implemented through distributed algorithms.

The final purpose is to explore marine areas through a team of AUVs. Current state-of-the-art does not offer many examples of cooperative explorations with at least three AUVs. The ambition of the project is to represent a step further towards future developments of multi-agent systems for marine survey. In addition to the “Centro Piaggio” of the University of Pisa, which is the coordinating partner, “Thesaurus” sees the involvement of the University of Florence, the Institute of Information Science and Technology of the National Research Council (CNR) in Pisa, and the Scuola Normale Superiore, Pisa. Detailed information on the project is available at the site <http://thesaurus.isti.cnr.it>.

Cooperation may be intended in several ways, from simply having more vehicles pursuing different pre-planned missions in different areas, to interaction among the vehicles during the mission (as in our case), to strict formation control, the strongest form of cooperation. There are a number of advantages in considering a team of small AUVs for specific operations instead of a single, large, more powerful AUV:

- the team will not be affected as a whole by the malfunctioning of a single vehicle, or at least the system performance will degrade gently;
- scale economies may be gained in vehicle production;
- launch and recovery issues are less relevant for small vehicles;
- overall mission time may be minimized, with consequent cost savings.

There are also specific missions that can only be pursued by a team, for instance synoptic sampling of the ocean (i.e., synchronous sampling in time distributed over a spatial domain). The drawback of the team mission is that functionalities have to be designed and implemented at group level: a system design approach has to be pursued.

The last five-six years have seen a rise in both theoretical and experimental work on the subject, with a clear domain of application in area mapping, environmental monitoring/surveying, and underwater surveillance system. The Monterey Bay series of experiments, *Bellingham (2009)*, have examples of all three cooperation modalities, as well as heterogeneous components (propelled AUVs, gliders, surface platforms, fixed assets as oceanographic buoys or benthic stations, satellite interaction), with various degrees of integration, realizing the AOSN framework envisaged in *Curtin et al. (1993)*. Cooperative adaptive oceanographic sampling and missions are investigated also by *Eickstedt et al. (2006)*, *Alvarez et al. (2007)*, *Munafò et al. (2011)*. In this paper the focus is on cooperative search missions, in which prior knowledge is available over the area to be searched in terms of a probability map. The available vehicles choose their course (through a suitable definition of way-points) in order to maximize the expected information gain. At the same time, the vehicles have to maintain communication connectivity. At algorithmic level, the search objectives are achieved through the use of Equitable Power Diagrams, *Pavone et al. (2009)*, *Pavone et al. (2011)*, to divide the search area among the vehicles while preserving connectivity, and by minimization of the Renyi's entropy, *Renyi (1960)*, in order to maximize the expected information gain.

2. The Thesaurus project vehicle: *Tifone*

The functional specification of the Thesaurus AUVs requires the capability of performing navigation, exploration and surveillance of underwater archaeological sites at maximum depth of 300 m, *Allotta et al. (2011)*. Mechanical and electrical design of the AUVs was performed by the University of Florence team. The University of Florence has also designed the low-level guidance, navigation and control loop, while the University of Pisa has taken care of the mission planner, mission supervisor, inter-vehicle communication and cooperative navigation, and distributed search strategy. Each vehicle can carry as payload a side-scan sonar, for acoustical seafloor imaging, a pair of cameras for stereo vision at close ranges, a green laser, acoustic modems for underwater communications. The concept of the AUV team is to perform wide area mapping in cooperation using the side-scan sonar as payload. Anomalies in the side-scan records are then explored at closer range with the cameras and the green laser payload. In the following of the paper, where we refer only to the wide area search task, we assume the availability of three vehicles all of them equipped with a side-scan sonar.

Fig. 1: (a): the design sketch of the *Tifone* AUV developed within the Thesaurus project; (b) the vehicle before deployment at the Roffia lake, near the Arno river.

The design of the vehicle, named “Tifone” (Italian for typhoon), is sketched in Fig.1(a). The first of the three vehicle is shown in Fig. 1(b), taken at the Roffia Lake, appropriately mid-way between Florence and Pisa, on the occasion of the first wet test of the vehicle, in early February this year.

Tifone has a length of 3.70 m and a dry weight of 170 kg., while it is slightly buoyant positive in water. The test at sea of the three vehicles is scheduled for the summer 2013.

3. Probability Map

A multi agent system to explore any marine area requires a prediction probability map to choose agents waypoints and some rules to move each vehicle team along the surveyed environment. In the following, we describe one method to obtain the probability map in accordance to historical records of finding or events, as applied in our case to the Tuscan Archipelago.

The prediction probability map is the (estimated) probability density function (pdf) of finding a relict of archaeological interest over a given marine area. The pdf is estimated using Parzen windows theory, *Parzen (1962)*, with Gaussian kernels. We start from historical archival data of relicts and events as found in the Tuscan Archipelago. These data come from the archive of the National Authority (Superintendence of Tuscany for Cultural Heritage). To each archival data, probability and reliability are associated. Reliability is associated to the geographical position, while probability is associated to the information source. Note that the archival data include actual findings on the seabed verified by the Superintendence, which have both probability and reliability of 1, as well as other kinds of indications or warnings. For instance, an amphora caught in a fishing net is highly probable, but the reliability of the position is low; the unconfirmed indication of an amateur diver maybe associated to both low probability and reliability. Historical data (diaries, paintings, etc.) have also been included in the data base considered. The subjective evaluation of probability and reliability has been carried out with the help of a group of experts including historians and marine archaeologists.

Eventually, we consider a set of N_{data} points with three attributes:

$$X_i (\text{position}, \text{probability}, \text{reliability}), \quad i = 1, \dots, N_{data} \quad (1)$$

Fig.2 shows the position of (a subset of) the points considered in the northern part of the Tuscan Archipelago. Red dots represent the position of the historical harbours and ports in the area.

Fig. 2: Plot of the historical archival data position in the Tuscan Archipelago

To each data point is associated a Gaussian random variable having as mean the spatial position and as variance the information reliability. Therefore, we have as many Gaussian variables as historical archival data points.

$$T_i \sim \mathcal{N}(x_i, \sigma_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, N_{\text{data}} \quad (2)$$

We now extract a new set of M total data point over the geographical area as samples from each Gaussian variable. The m_i , number of samples extracted from each variable, is a function of the probability information: K points are extracted when the probability is 1:

$$m_i = [K \cdot X_i(\text{probability})] \quad (3)$$

Fig.3 plots a portion of the study area with the new data sampled in accordance to the probability and reliability (variance of the samples) historical archival data.

Fig. 3: (a) Zoom of the historical data plot. (b) Zoom of the same area shown in (a) with sampled data. Closely clustered data indicate that the point that originated them is highly reliable, hence the position has small variance. The number of generated samples from any individual point in (a) is proportional to the probability of the original point.

At this time the prediction probability map can be estimated by multivariable kernel density estimation as product of Gaussian kernel over M -samples:

$$P_{KDE}(x) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M (G(x, x^{(i), h_1, \dots, h_D})) \quad (4)$$

$G(x, x^{(i), h_1, \dots, h_D}) = (1/(h_1 \dots h_D)) \prod_{(d=1)}^D K((x_d - x_d^{(i)})/h_d)$, K a standard Gaussian pdf, M the total number of samples, D the dimension of the space of x , h^2 the variance of Gaussian kernel often called Bandwidth in the literature. In our case, with $D=2$, we obtain:

$$P_{KDE}(x) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{1}{h_1} \frac{1}{h_2} K\left(\frac{x_1 - x_1^i}{h_1}\right) K\left(\frac{x_2 - x_2^i}{h_2}\right) \quad (5)$$

The problem of choosing the bandwidth is crucial in density estimation because with large h the estimated density will over-smooth and mask the structure of the data while with small h the estimated density will be spiky and very hard to interpret. The statistical approach of *Sheather (2004)* has been employed, leading to the following bandwidth choice:

$$h^* = 0.9 \cdot \min\left(\sigma, \frac{IQR}{1.34}\right) \cdot M^{-0.2} \quad (6)$$

IQR is the difference between the 75th percentile ($Q3$) and the 25th percentile ($Q1$): $IQR=Q3-Q1$, of the generated data sample. Eventually, with the available historical data, the probability map of Fig.4 was generated.

Fig.4: (a) Historical findings of archaeological interest in the northern Tuscan Archipelago. (b) The estimated probability prediction map. Hot colours indicate high probability of finding a relict, cold colours indicate low probability.

4. The cooperative search algorithm

Once the prior map has been built, as described in the previous section, the overall objective is to search systematically with the AUV team for undiscovered relicts over the study area, giving priority to high probability sub-areas. The search is intended to be cooperative, and the cooperative search algorithm is divided in two parts: motion rules to which each vehicle must comply, and determination of waypoints during the explorative mission. In particular, our strategy is to deploy the team so that each vehicle negotiates with the others which subarea to search; once the vehicles have agreed on area subdivision, each vehicle independently from the others select its waypoints within the given area. that will be dedicated to In the first part of this section we introduce briefly a review on equitable Power diagram, a particular instance of Voronoi diagrams, *Imai et al. (1985)*, *Aurenhammer (1987)*, *Okabe et al. (2000)*, which is the mathematical tool for dynamic deployment of the AUV team, and we define the motion rules of the vehicles. In the second part we describe a minimum entropy algorithm to choose the waypoints.

4.1. Area partition among the vehicles: equitable power diagrams

The rules to move the vehicles can be defined using the potential function theory and a particular modification of Voronoi diagrams, the so-called Equitable Power diagram, *Pavone et al. (2009,2011)*. Assume there are n AUVs over the survey area Q ; assume that $G = (g_1; \dots ; g_n)$ is the ordered set of positions of the AUVs. The Voronoi diagram V generated by the points G is defined as:

$$V(G_i) = \{x \in Q \mid \|x - g_i\| \leq \|x - g_j\|\} \quad (7)$$

We can define the bisector between g_i and g_j as

$$b(g_i, g_j) = \{x \in Q \mid \|x - g_i\| = \|x - g_j\|\} \quad (8)$$

The face $b(g_i; g_j)$ bisects the line segment joining g_i and g_j , and this line segment is orthogonal to the face. Assume now that each point g_i has assigned a scalar weight w_i ; we define the power distance as:

$$d_p(x, g_i; w_i) = \|x - g_i\|^2 - w_i \quad (9)$$

Consider now the new ordered set of distinct points $GW = ((g_1; w_1); \dots; (g_N; w_N))$; we define the power diagram as:

$$V(G_i) = \left\{ x \in Q \mid \|x - g_i\|^2 - w_i \leq \|x - g_j\|^2 - w_j \right\} \quad (10)$$

There are several differences between power diagram and Voronoi diagram. First, the power diagram might have some empty cell. Second, some agent might not be in its own power cell, Fig.5. Moreover notice that, when all weights are set equal, the power diagram coincides with the Voronoi diagram. Finally, the bisector of (g_i, w_i) and (g_j, w_j) , $i \neq j$, is defined by

$$b((g_i, w_i), (g_j, w_j)) = \left\{ x \in Q \mid (g_j - g_i)^T x = \frac{1}{2} (\|g_j\|^2 - \|g_i\|^2 + w_i - w_j) \right\} \quad (11)$$

Hence, b is a face orthogonal to the line segment $g_i g_j$ and passing through the point g_{ij}^* given by

$$g_{ij}^* = \frac{\|g_j\|^2 - \|g_i\|^2 + w_i - w_j}{2\|g_j - g_i\|^2} (g_j - g_i) \quad (12)$$

It is possible to arbitrarily move the bisector by changing the values of the weight. This property is used to obtain the equitable diagram algorithm.

Fig. 5: Examples of Voronoi diagrams and power diagrams. (a) Voronoi diagram. (b) Power diagram, from *Martinez et al.(2006)*. The weights w_i are all positive. The power generator (g_2, w_2) has an empty cell. The power generator (g_5, w_5) is outside its region of dominance.

The probability prediction map, assigned over the environmental of survey, is a probability function so it is the drive to ensure an even workload for each vehicle. The workload sharing can be achieved by modifying the weight of the power diagram in accordance to the probability function. This is allowed because an equitable power diagram always exists for any function of measure $p(x)$. A partition that guarantees equitable workload sharing, is a partition where each integral of the function $p(x)$ on the n sub-regions Q_i of the environmental Q , is the same for all agents. In our specific implementation, the algorithm computes the right weights of the power diagram in accordance to the prior probability map generated through the algorithm of Section 3.

The algorithmic generation of the correct set of weights is obtained by defining an energy function with the proprieties that:

- 1) it depends on the weights of the vehicles;
- 2) all its critical points correspond to vectors of weights yielding an equitable power diagram

Then, the weights associated to each agent are updated according to a spatially distributed gradient-descent law until a critical point of the energy function is reached.

4.2 Way-point generation within partitions: a minimum entropy approach

Once the equitable power diagram has been built, to each vehicle in the team is assigned a search area, all areas having the same integral of the relict prediction pdf. Roughly speaking, each area has the same workload. Within each assigned area, any vehicle has now to independently generate its own search waypoints in order to give priority first to the routes with higher prediction probability. This is accomplished by finding the maximum probability path among the possible straight-line paths of pre-assigned length (or time duration) departing from the vehicle current position; once the first way-point is reached, a second one is generated according to the same algorithm, and including, if available, any new information coming from the vehicle own search and from the other agents search.

We assume $p(x)$, Eqs.(4-5), as probability density function (omitting the subscript for ease of notation); the associated Renyi's quadratic entropy, *Renyi (1960)*, is given by:

$$H_R(x) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \ln \int p^\alpha(x) dx \quad \alpha > 0; \quad \alpha \neq 1 \quad (13)$$

Taking $\alpha = 2$, we obtain

$$H_R(x) = -\ln \int p^2(x) dx \quad (14)$$

The integral in (14) can be analytically evaluated, *Gokay and Principe (2002)*:

$$H_R(x) = -\ln \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p^2(x) dx = -\ln \frac{1}{M^2 (2h_1 h_2)} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^M K\left(\frac{x_1^i - x_1^j}{\sqrt{2}h_1}\right) K\left(\frac{x_2^i - x_2^j}{\sqrt{2}h_2}\right) \quad (15)$$

K is the Gaussian kernel centred on x^j , with variance $2h^2$, evaluated at x^i .

As the classical Shannon entropy, also Renyi's quadratic entropy is a measure of information, and in particular, as referred to our case, the higher the prediction probability, the lower the Renyi's entropy (see Fig. 5). This property, as well as the possibility of analytical computation offered by (15), justifies the choice to use Renyi's entropy for the waypoints computation problem. In particular, considering as Q_i , the region assigned to the i -th vehicle by the equitable the power diagram procedure, and let the maximum path length from current vehicle position be R_{max} . Assuming that from the current point to the next way point the vehicle will move along a straight path, the next way point is determined among as the one that minimizes the Renyi's entropy integral along the path, among all the possible straight paths of length not exceeding R_{max} and still belonging to Q_i . Formally:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_x H_R(x) = -\ln \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p^2(x) dx \\ x \leq R_{max} \\ x \in Q_i \end{array} \right. \quad (16)$$

Thus, the entropy minima are achieved in correspondence of the maxima of the prediction probability, Fig. 6.

Fig.6: (a) Prediction probability map in the Tuscan Archipelago. (b) Renyi's Entropy calculated over the prediction probability map (a) – hot colours correspond to higher entropy, cold colours to lower entropy.

Once the next way-point has been established, navigation to the way-point is determined using behaviours implemented through potential functions, as discussed in detail in *Munafò et al. (2011)*. Two potential functions have been defined: attraction and obstacle avoidance. The first guarantees that each vehicle move itself toward its own waypoints, while the second one forces a repulsive potential in correspondence of the other vehicles and/or fixed obstacles. In summary, we start with the initialization of the vehicles' position and we calculate the equitable power diagram into sub region of the environmental, guaranteeing the communication constraint. Then, each vehicle estimates its waypoint and moves itself by the rules of Attraction and Obstacle avoidance potential function. The minimum entropy algorithm estimates the waypoints.

5. Simulation

The algorithm testing in simulative scenarios is now reported. The code is written in MATLAB and makes use of the C++ Computational Geometry Algorithms Library CGAL (<http://www.cgal.org/>). The cooperative algorithm is applied to the three vehicles case; initial positions are within the bounds of the environment Q and the weights are initialized to zero. Time is discretized and vehicles' speed is bounded by 1.5 m/s (three knots). We consider the prediction probability map $p_{KDE}(x)$, Fig.3 (b), as measure over the environment Q to calculate the equitable power diagram. Then, we initialize the vehicles' position and we start the simulation along a sub region of the Tuscan Archipelago, Fig.6.

Fig.7: (a) Initial position and power diagram. (b) The black rectangle indicates the portion of marine

area to be searched.

After the initial computation of the equitable power diagrams, each vehicle moves toward the waypoint at minimum entropy within its own partition, surveying the route with their side-scan sonars. While on the route, they communicate to the other team members their position and the findings, if any, along the route. This allows updating dynamically the equitable power diagram as the mission is in progress. If no finding is encountered along the route, the detection probability of the surveyed area is decreased toward zero along the path; in our simulations we have assumed a range of 100 m along the sway and a resolution of 10 m along the surge axes of the vehicles. Fig.8 show the result of one simulation, starting from the initial conditions of Fig.7, in which the updated diagrams are visible, and also the updated probability map, in which lower probability has now been assigned to the surveyed regions. Note that the final waypoints are at the points within the diagrams with maximum expected discovery probability.

Fig.8: Simulative application of the algorithm over a portion of the marine area: the white lines indicate the vehicles trajectories; the straight blue lines indicate the current power diagram partitions; the blue strips around the vehicles trajectories indicate the updated probability of detection as obtained by the survey, on the assumption that no new findings has been encountered along the routes.

5. Conclusions

We have presented a cooperation algorithm to explore an environmental. The proposed approach allows a team of autonomous underwater vehicles to search an area where the workload sharing is equal for each vehicle, while preserving communication among the team. Waypoints are established through a minimum entropy approach that is equivalent to search first along the routes at higher expected discovery probability. While our approach, as well as examples and simulations, have been focused on the marine archaeology case, the proposed algorithms are indeed general, and can be transferred with minor modifications to other search applications (e.g., airplane black-box search) that may include different sensor payloads with respect to those installed in the “Thesaurus” vehicles.

Acknowledgment

This work has been supported in part by the Tuscany Region, project “Thesaurus”, initiative “PAR FAS REGIONE TOSCANA Linea di Azione 1.1.a.3. Scienze e tecnologie per la salvaguardia e la valorizzazione dei beni culturali”. The work of Vincenzo Calabrò has been carried out while the Author was at Centro Piaggio, University of Pisa.

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Efficient Use of CAE Pre- and Post-Processing in Offshore Structures Design

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Abstract

Safety and efficiency are key factors for offshore structures. Such structures operate under hazardous environmental conditions and have to withstand extreme weather phenomena. Moreover, as they are usually located close to delicate environments, even the slightest possibility of an accident is not acceptable. During the design process of such structures, the extensive use of CAE simulations is often required in addition to the standard assessment. In most cases, the large scale of the offshore structures makes a full model physical test impossible. This in turn, makes the simulation process imperative. The use of such tools helps to ensure the product's performance characteristics and minimizes failure risk throughout its lifetime. Furthermore, CAE simulation is a valuable tool for the design of innovative structures and the usage of exotic materials. The numerical simulation process is always time consuming, since many load cases and disciplines need to be set up for the accurate investigation of model behavior. The use of high efficient pre- and post- processing software is essential for the reduction of engineer work hours in such analyses. This paper presents how ANSA CAE pre-processor and μ ETA CAE post-processor fulfill this requirement for the Offshore Structures Industry by offering advanced simulation techniques and automation capabilities. Three case studies of CFD and structural analyses for offshore structures are used in this investigation.

1. Introduction

Safety and efficiency are key factors for offshore structures. Such structures operate under harsh environmental conditions and thus have to withstand extreme weather phenomena. Moreover, as they are usually located close to delicate environments, any possibility of failure or accident should be eliminated.

During the design process of such structures, the extensive use of CAE simulations is often needed in addition to the standard assessment calculations. In most cases offshore and energy production structures are complex and large-scale, thus full model physical tests are not possible. This in turn, makes the simulation process imperative. The use of simulation helps to ensure the upfront achievement of the product's performance characteristics and minimizes the failure risk throughout its lifetime. Furthermore, CAE simulation is an imperative tool for the design of innovative structures and for the use of exotic materials. The numerical simulation process may prove to be time consuming, since many load cases and disciplines need to be employed to ensure the accurate investigation of the model's behavior.

The use of high efficient pre- and post- processing software is essential for the time reduction of engineering analyses. This paper presents how ANSA CAE pre-processor and μ ETA CAE post-processor fulfill this requirement for the Offshore Structures Industry by offering advanced modeling and results assessment features, enhanced with advanced automation capabilities. Three case studies of structural and CFD analyses for offshore structures are used in this investigation.

2. Structural analysis of a semi-submersible platform

In the first case study a semi-submersible platform is analyzed, Fig.1. The simulation consists of a static analysis in hogging condition. A 10 m height wave affects the structure while its length is identical to the platform's length. In this load case the platform is fully loaded, so masses are distributed in the hull, deck and tanks in order to simulate the additional weight of the ballast, production and storage tanks. Mooring and riser lines' forces were applied at the hull at certain

positions. Gravity acceleration was also applied. Finally, buoyancy was applied as hydrostatic pressure on the elements below waterline and varied linearly with water depth. Special tools of ANSA are used to facilitate the definition of the FE model such as the wave definition tool, the mass balance and the buoyancy application. The ANSA Task Manager provides great assistance in the organization and automation of the above process.

Fig. 1: Static analysis of a semi-submersible platform

2.1. Process management

The definition of the platform FE model can be facilitated and automated through the Task Manager tool provided by the ANSA pre-processor, Fig.2. In this tool, all actions needed to complete an FE model are defined in a stepwise manner. Actions such as geometry handling, meshing and boundary conditions are defined as a Task Item. Then, the Task Manager runs and realizes every Task Item and thus sets up the FE model automatically.

Fig. 2: Task Manager model set-up sequence

The first step of the FE model set-up process is the gathering of all CAD data of all sub-assemblies in one geometrical model. The sub- assemblies are connected together according to defined connectivity

specifications. Meshing is applied at the model at the next step of the Task Manager sequence. Meshing parameters and quality criteria are defined for different areas, parts or assemblies of the model. Then, meshing is applied automatically by the ANSA Batch Meshing tool, which is controlled by the Task Manager. During the batch meshing, geometrical simplifications such as holes' filling and representation of reinforcements with beams are also performed. At the next steps of the Task Manager, mass and loads - which are described below in detail - are applied. After the definition of all steps, the Task Manager runs and performs one by one every action on the model.

2.2. Model simplification

Prior to the application of the mesh, an important step for the model set-up is the simplification of the geometry. This action excludes unnecessary details from the model that do not affect its behavior but still tend to reduce meshing quality. In this case holes with diameter less than a specified value are identified and filled automatically. The model is automatically re-meshed at the filled areas. The hole filling improves the mesh quality and reduces the number of elements and thus the simulation time needed for this analysis, Fig.3. The parameters for the holes' filling are prescribed at the Batch Meshing action applied to the model by the Task Manager.

Fig. 3: Holes filling at transverse section

Another simplification action is the replacement of longitudinal stiffeners by beam elements. This action significantly reduces the number of small elements that represent the stiffeners. The beams applied have the same characteristics and behavior with the replaced stiffeners. Beams replacement is an automatic process in ANSA that is able to replace the whole model's stiffeners with minimum interaction. Beams are offset and oriented to fit the stiffener position and also connected to the shells of the model, Fig.4.

Fig. 4: Stiffeners replacement by beams

2.3. Batch meshing

The meshing of the model is applied automatically through the ANSA Batch Meshing tool. Meshing parameters and quality criteria are defined for each sub- assembly. The whole meshing process is controlled by the Task Manager. Local refinement can also be applied on critical areas where accurate results should be extracted. A special meshing scenario can be defined for these areas as shown at Fig.5. The meshing information and quality criteria used for the platform are shown in Table I.

Table I: Meshing parameters and quality criteria

Global element length	0.28 m
Local element length	0.04 m
Number of shell elements	~1.4 millions
Number of beam elements	155544
Quality Criteria	
Skewness (Nastran)	30
Aspect ratio (Nastran)	3

Fig. 5: Refinement areas

2.4. Loading condition

In this step of the model set-up, boundary conditions, loads and all auxiliary FE entities, such as additional mass, are applied. The non-structural mass applied represents the machinery on deck and hulls. This mass does not contribute to the model strength, so it is added as lumped masses distributed on the FE nodes. Another portion of mass will also be added in order to simulate the water ballast. The amount of water ballast is calculated to equalize the weight of fluids in storage tanks, and also the risers and mooring forces. The calculation tries to achieve a horizontal position for the platform.

Fig.6: Non structural mass distribution

The ANSA Mass Balance tool is used for the calculation and distribution of the mass in order to achieve a prescribed mass value and COG position. The calculation process is controlled by the Task Manager sequence and runs automatically. The result is the application of different amounts of mass in every tank, distributed on their nodes, Fig.6. The weight from mooring and raisers lines is applied as nodal forces on the deck. In order to avoid high stresses on single nodes, rigid elements distribute the forces on a wider FE area of the deck.

At the final step of the analysis definition, the platform is positioned on a 10 m height trochoidal wave. A special tool is used to balance the model on the wave by iteratively adjusting the draught and trim until the resultant net force and moment of the platform is ideally zero. The buoyancy force is calculated and applied on the model as PLOAD4 on the hull elements below waterline with a linear variation with water depth, Fig.7. Using the balancing technique the model is able to run in NASTRAN solver without the need of displacement constraints (SPCs), which would lead to high local stresses. A NASTRAN keyword for inertia relief (INREL) is added for this solution.

Fig.7: Cargo loads and buoyancy

2.5. Analysis results

For this static analysis the NASTRAN solver has been used. The results of the analysis are presented and examined in μ ETA post-processor. Critical areas with high stress can be identified and further analysis can be done for every case. Some results are presented in Fig.8.

Fig.8: Von Mises stresses in μ ETA

3. CFD analysis of a wind turbine rotor

A CFD analysis of a wind turbine's three bladed rotor is performed in the second case study, Fig.9. Since the model is axisymmetrical, the computational domain of this simulation consists of only one blade, the rotor hub, and the volume around the blade. Periodic boundary conditions are used to model the other two blades to the calculation.

Fig.9: Wind turbine CFD model

The blade geometry has been meshed with a variable size triangular surface mesh. In the fluid domain, additional refinement is applied on areas of interest with the aim of ANSA's SIZE BOXES tool. The boundary layer, generated on the blade, consists of ten layers of prisms, generated in aspect mode with a growth factor of 1.2 and first height of 2 mm. A tetra mesh has been generated on fluid domains with a total size of nearly 24 million tetras and pentas. The whole meshing process of the blade and fluid domain is elaborated through the ANSA Batch Meshing Tool, Fig.10.

Fig.10: Refinement areas and layers

For this analysis the ANSYS FLUENT v14.0 software has been used. Converge was achieved after about 200 iterations and 2.5 calculation hours on a 12 CPUs machine. The results of the analysis are presented in μ ETA post-processor, which supports results from numerous CFD solvers. Some results, such as velocity and vorticity in contour plot, streamlines, and path lines of the flow, are shown in Figs.11 to 14.

Fig. 11: Velocity contour plot

Fig. 12: Vorticity contour plot

Fig. 13: Streamlines

Fig. 14: Path lines

4. Structural analysis of a riser's flexible joint

In the last case study, a flexible joint of a riser line is analyzed, Fig.15. This device connects a riser line to the platform. Since the riser and platform are continuously in motion, the flexible joint should be able to absorb relative movement between the connecting parts and avoid damage on the riser. To allow this movement, the flexible joint has two moving parts.

Fig. 15: Contact analysis on a riser's flex-joint

The target of this example is to ensure that the moving parts will remain in contact, in any loading condition, avoiding any fluid leakage. A static analysis is performed using the ABAQUS solver for two different loading conditions of the riser line. The model consists of two bodies (first and second body), a tube where the riser is welded and an elastomeric element. The semi spherical surfaces of the first body and tube allow for the rotation of the tube in order to absorb the riser's motion. The elastomeric element applies pressure between the first body and the tube and keeps these parts in contact.

4.1. Model set-up

The flexible joint is meshed with full hexa mesh of approximately 200 thousands hexas. Each part of the model is meshed separately using different meshing parameters. In order to apply the 100% hexa meshing, a special tool of ANSA is used, the HEXA BLOCK tool. This is a semi- automatic process where hexahedral domains are defined and fit on the model's shape. Then, hexa meshing is applied on these domains, which correspond to the mesh of the model. All parts that are meshed are axi-symmetric so, only a few domains are defined and copied by rotation to cover the whole model. The mesh and HEXA BLOCK domains of the first body are shown in Fig.16. The elastomeric part is also meshed with hexa elements. Steel plates inside the elastomeric matrix reinforce the part, Fig.17. The elastomeric and steel plates are connected by pasted nodes.

Fig. 16: The HEXA BLOCKs and the full hexa meshing

Fig.17: Elastomeric part and steel plate reinforcements

The next step of the model set-up is the definition of contacts between the parts of the assembly. Contact entities could be of “sliding” type, such as the contact between the first body and tube where sliding is allowed. In this case a friction model is applied with friction coefficient of 0.2. The rest of the contacts are of “tied” type, such as the contact between the elastomeric part and the tube due to the fact that the two parts are considered glued and no movement is allowed between them. Totally,

four contact pairs are identified. The use of a special ANSA tool for this purpose facilitates the identification of the mating surfaces and the definition of the contacts. The user just needs to confirm the mating surfaces and select the type of the contact. All contacts are shown in Fig.18.

Fig.18: Contact pairs on the flex joint

The first and second bodies are connected together using bolts. At the FE model, bolts are represented by a combination of beams and rigid bodies. The definition of the bolts FE representation is an automatic process in ANSA, which consists of two steps. Firstly, the bolt positions are identified by the bolts' holes and the connecting parts, and ANSA Bolt Entities are applied at these positions. Then, at each Bolt Entity an FE representation is created according to the user specifications. In this analysis the bolt FE representation consists of BEAMS for the bolt body and rigid elements for the bolt head and thread, Fig.19. A pre-tension model is also applied on the bolts to simulate the tightening force.

Fig.19: Bolt FE representation

The elastomeric part should apply pressure to the tube part by a pre-tension. In this case, squeezing the elastomeric part during the assembly process performs the pre-tension. The elastomeric part in its initial dimensions causes a small gap between the first and second part. During the simulation the bolts' pre-tension closes the gap and squeezes the elastomeric part and so, the pressure on the semi-spherical surfaces is applied, Fig.20.

Fig.20: Pre-tension on elastomeric part

The first load case arises when the riser is welded on the flex joint and the latter is transferred from a crane, Fig.21. The crane hook is mounted on the upper flange of the flex joint. The flex joint should withstand the load of the riser while the semi-spherical surfaces should not be separated. Two opposite loads are applied which are connected to the assembly by rigid body elements. The second load case is when the flex joint is situated on the supporting frame of the platform and the riser applies load at a certain angle. In this case, SPCs are applied at the bottom and the sides of the second body to simulate the supporting frame constraint, Fig.22.

Fig.21: 1st load case

Fig.22: 2nd load case

4.2. Analysis results

The model is solved with the ABAQUS solver and the run lasted about 1 hour and 30 minutes in a four CPUs machine. The results are presented in μ ETA post-processor. At the first load case, the maximum Von Mises stresses appear on the first body on the edges of the semi-spherical surface. Significant stresses also develop on the connecting bolts since they carry both the riser and the pre-tension loads. In the second load case, the tube is subjected to high stress even if the tube is allowed to rotate on the semi-spherical surface. Results from μ ETA are shown in Figs.23 and 24.

Fig.23: Von Misses stress for the 1st load case

Fig.24: Von Misses stress for the 2nd load case

In order to investigate the contact pressure between the moving parts, a special μ ETA tool is used. This tool is able to create a shell element representation for the contact surfaces to facilitate the visualization of the pressure distribution. The contact pressure for the pre-tension first and second load case are shown in Figs.25 to 27, respectively. There is no separation of the surfaces for all load cases. The uneven distribution of the pressure shown as a “radial stripes pattern” is dependent on the element length of the surface. Finer mesh at this area results in smoother pressure distribution and minimization of the “radial stripes pattern” effect.

Fig.25: Contact pressure at pre-tension

Fig.26: Contact pressure at 1st load case

Fig.27: Contact pressure at 2nd load case

5. Conclusions

ANSA pre-processor was successfully and efficiently used for the definition of several CAE analyses scenarios for structural and CFD disciplines. Process organization and standardization is possible using the Task Manager tool. The needs of CAE set-up for the offshore structures design are covered by special tools. Applications like wave creation, mass balance, vessel balance on waves, and buoyancy calculation can be automated using the above-mentioned tools. μ ETA post-processor is a versatile post-processor which provides sophisticated tools for results reporting and evaluating and it can cover the needs of the offshore industry with success.

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Bridging the Gap between Steady-State and Transient Simulation for Torsional Vibrations under Ice Impact

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Abstract

The transient simulation of ice impact scenarios by now became an integral part of classification requirements. This development is forcing OEM and suppliers into simulation technologies which are significantly different from the classical steady-state analysis commonly applied in the past. This paper introduces modeling and simulation methods, which permit transient and steady-state analysis to operate on the same model base. We also present recent developments in propeller modeling which incorporate the established methods for both worlds and are in the process to be certified by Germanischer Lloyd for compliance with the classification rules.

1. Introduction

The modeling and simulation of torsional vibration systems has been treating steady-state analysis and transient simulation independently of each other very often or has been focusing on just one of the aspects. Nowadays, both sides form essential parts of certification requirements, see e.g. *GL (2012)*, *FSA (2010)*, *IACS (2011)*. However, their mutual independence significantly increases modeling as well as model management efforts.

Finding solutions, which allow combining the steady-state and transient simulation approaches into one tool and permitting to execute both on the same model base, has the potential to streamline the modeling and simulation process. Following such an approach introduces a number of challenges and requirements:

- Nonlinear behavior: Generally, the classical steady-state approaches are based on linear integral transformations such as Laplace or Fourier transform to relate time domain representations of systems and signals into corresponding frequency domain representations. Due to the linearity of the transformations only linear systems are easily transferable in such an approach. In classical steady-state analysis for torsional vibrations the response of nonlinear system components has been approximated in the frequency domain directly (e.g. through frequency-dependent stiffness or damping characteristics), resulting in models, which are not transferable back into the time domain.
- Modeling and result continuity: New methodologies for combining steady-state and transient simulation have to take into account that established approaches have merge smoothly into them. In particular it is necessary to preserve established ways of parameterization so that existing data can be continued to be used for modeling. Also, new methods applied to steady-state simulation in particular should be capable to reproduce results computed previously using classical approaches (including nonlinearity modeling).
- Going beyond mechanical modeling: The restriction to the modeling of the mechanical subsystem is usually acceptable for steady-state computations. But generally, the dynamic behavior may be significantly affected by other system components too. Thinking e.g. of transient ice impact analysis it becomes apparent that the dynamic response of the engine control may considerably alter the overall driveline behavior and vibration response. So it is desirable to include further modeling domains in a simulation framework.

Within the software SimulationX ITI has implemented a broad range of component libraries dedicated to torsional vibration analysis (TVA). This includes the propeller modeling which is also discussed in

detail in this paper, as well as solutions for engines, shafts, couplings and gears, which are tailored to torsional vibration analysis requirements for ship propulsion systems. All models are implemented in the Modelica modeling language, which can also be applied by the end user for customized modeling. Within the software was realized a solution, where steady-state analysis and transient simulation can be executed on one and the same models, making modeling and simulation significantly more effective.

Coping with the limitations of the strictly linear relationship between time and frequency domain we show how a combined application of time and frequency domain methods based on harmonic balance can help to bring both worlds closer together.

A current driver for creating a closer relationship between transient and steady-state analysis is the requirement for performing transient simulations for ice class certifications in addition to the classical frequency domain TVA. The core aspect of considering ice impact in transient as well as potentially in steady-state simulation is the modeling of the propeller and the propeller load generated in ice impact situations. The modeling of propellers for transient and steady-state analysis in compliance with the various standards thus forms the second major topic of this paper.

2. Joint Modeling for Time and Frequency Domain Simulation

2.1. Unified Framework

The simulation and analysis of models in time and frequency domain requires the selection of an appropriate model description approach. Since torsional vibration analysis very often is based on describing systems as intermeshed networks of lumped parameter elements, formulations as systems of ordinary differential equations or differential algebraic equations (ODE or DAE) are an appropriate way to describe the dynamics of a drive system as well as any other lumped-parameter system. In a general form such equations look as follows:

$$0 = f(\underline{x}(t), \dot{\underline{x}}(t), \underline{p}) \quad (1)$$

With \underline{x} denoting the vector of states in the model, \underline{p} the parameters and t the time. There are a large number of tools available which are capable to solve such systems in transient analysis. If a model is linear (such as in classical torsional analysis), Eq.(1) becomes a linear differential matrix equation in $\underline{x}(t)$ and $\dot{\underline{x}}(t)$.

The transition of the signals for a steady-state analysis into frequency domain takes place by using the correspondences for harmonic signals

$$\underline{x}(t) \leftrightarrow (\hat{\underline{x}})(\omega) \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{\underline{x}}(t) \leftrightarrow j\omega(\hat{\underline{x}})(\omega) \quad (2)$$

Where $\hat{\underline{x}}$ is a vector of complex numbers representing amplitude and phase of the respective signal at frequency ω . For a linear system these correspondences transfer Eq.(1) into a system of algebraic matrix equations, which can be solved independently for any frequency ω . The reduction to algebraic equations is the strength of the classical frequency domain methods.

If the equation system is non-linear, there is no possibility to transfer the complete model into frequency domain in such a straightforward way. But, there is still the possibility to transfer from a system of differential equations into a system of algebraic equations, which also allow the computation of steady state results. The starting point for this transformation is the assumption of an existing harmonic steady-state solution, which allows expressing \underline{x} as a Fourier series

$$\underline{x}(t) = \underline{x}_p \frac{t}{T} + \underline{\hat{x}}[0] + \text{Re} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^N \underline{\hat{x}}[k] \cdot \exp(j\omega_0 k t) \right\} \quad (3)$$

In accordance with Eq.(2) the vectors $\underline{\hat{x}}[k]$ represent amplitudes and phases in $(\underline{\hat{x}})(\omega)$ for $\omega=\omega_0k$. \underline{x}_p describes the periodicity of the signals, i.e. the advance over one fundamental vibration period of the system (such as the advance of rotation angles by 4π per cycle in a four-stroke combustion engine). Inserting Eq.(3) in Eq.(1) allows to create an algebraic equation system in $\underline{\hat{x}}[k]$. The solution approach for such a system is known as harmonic balance (balancing amplitudes and phases of the different orders k up to N in order to solve the equation system for $\underline{\hat{x}}[k]$).

Without going further into details and referring to *Abel and Nahrung (2008)*, we would like to point out that using harmonic balance it is possible to compute spectral results for steady-state operation also for nonlinear systems and without a complete transformation of the system into the frequency domain. This solution approach can use an equation system which is closely related to the original transient differential equation system as seen in Eq.(1). Such approach has been realized in the simulation software SimulationX by ITI, originating from a transient simulation tool and growing into a combined time- and frequency-domain simulation environment in recent years.

2.2. Network Modeling Approach for Torsional Vibration Analysis

Network modeling methods are well established in modeling of physical systems, since they are suitable for describing lumped-parameter physical systems in different domains (mechanical, fluid, thermal, electrical, etc.). The modeling approach is based on fundamental balancing laws for across quantities (such as angle or speed difference) and through quantities (such as torques), which exist in a similar fashion in the different physical domains.

Fig. 1: Network model of a vessel driveline

In a network model the elements interact in a non-causal way, i.e. there is no prescribed direction of propagation for particular physical quantities in the overall system model. As a consequence, model

components based on this approach are freely inter-connectable, reaching a high flexibility in the modeling process. Also, this allows the creation of universal component libraries for assembling any type of vibratory system with almost no modeling constraints. For classical TVA applications such libraries may consist of engine components (crank mechanics, excitation models), driveline parts (gears, couplings, dampers) as well as specific load models, in particular those with vibratory characteristics (pumps, propellers – this modeling is introduced in more detail within this paper). Within SimulationX, the modeling is based on the Modelica modeling language, www.modelica.org, which provides a flexible and user-expandable modeling environment and permits to place a graphical modeling frontend on top. Fig.1 shows a modeling example of a ship driveline, which can be used for transient and steady-state analysis.

2.3. Simulation in Time and Frequency Domain

Models as seen in Fig.1 and formulated in the Modelica language can be simulated in both, time and frequency domain. The simulation is moved from one mode to the other by toggling a switch and setting appropriate simulation parameters. In transient simulations these are naturally start and stop time. In a frequency-domain simulation the analysis range is defined through a start and stop value for a selected reference quantity, such as rotational speed. Since a network model allows combining components in arbitrary ways, the solver will not be able to identify automatically a reference point for which the speed reference should be valid. In SimulationX it is therefore possible select any point in the system as reference point. This has the additional benefit that results can be generated with respect to various locations in a system, such as engine, propeller or other elements like pumps or generators.

Since the harmonic balance methods generally address nonlinear models, they also have to take into account that different orders are not superimposed independently from each other as it would appear in a linear system. Instead, different frequency components modulate each other. With increasing degree of nonlinearity the modulation effects increase. For this reason the number of considered orders can be specified and an internal amount of additional orders is considered for improved accuracy.

The modeling in such an approach can use techniques which are common and well established for transient modeling of torsional vibrations in combustion engines drivelines. Namely the excitation forces are feedback coupled to the dynamics of the system, such as for example:

- **Mass forces:** The piston mass excitation will respond to the crankshaft dynamics at any time instant. The effect of the piston mass will vary depending on the instantaneous crank position. Consequently, also the effective mass on the torsional system will vary over crank rotation. When a (nonlinear) network model is created, this relationship is naturally incorporated when relating rotary model parts (crank) and translatory parts (piston, pressure excitation) through the crank equation.
- **Pressure/torque excitation:** In SimulationX, excitation models are given as functions of crank angle and speed by sensing the respective quantities and computing the excitation from the respective instantaneous values. This has the consequence that the excitation is responding to variations of these quantities too, which arise e.g. from the torsional vibrations in the driveline. In the real system such an effect is present also – it is the spring behavior of the gas inside the piston.

Both effects are nonlinear. When computing steady-state behavior using harmonic balance, this type of nonlinear relationships for mass and pressure/torque excitations is preserved in the analysis and is visible in the results. This is a fundamental difference to classical steady-state analysis, where all excitations are treated as if they would be externally generated excitation signals. Although the harmonic balance results can be expected to be closer to the behavior of the real physical system, these results may be significantly different from the results computed through a classical TVA approach.

Fig. 2: Transient and steady-state results from the same simulation model

We addressed this problem by providing dedicated model elements which allow to modify the model such that it becomes equivalent to a classical steady-state analysis model by filtering signals in the frequency domain. The linear time-invariant (LTI) filters allow altering spectral properties of their input signals.

- **LTI Order Filter:** These filters are capable of filtering particular orders (including mean value) from their input at the currently analyzed steady-state speed. By default they pass the mean value and the signal portion growing linearly over one cycle (which are the first two summands in the Fourier representation in Eq.(3)). If such a filter is applied to a speed or angle signal derived from the drive train, it only passes the mean-value parts and thus the excitation signal derived from it will not contain any oscillatory components. This is equivalent to using an external excitation signal and thus allows matching the excitation to classical TVA.

There are further useful applications of the LTI Order Filters. One is the handling of absolute damping. In classical TVA the mean values (operating point) of the system is often not taken into account in the analysis. Parameters such as absolute damping are examined only according to their contribution to individual vibration orders. Quite often this leads to parameter sets, where the absolute damping would create non-realistic load torque if applied to the mean-value speed. In order to reproduce such results of classical TVA the order filter can remove mean value components from a speed signal so that only vibration orders are considered in damping torque computation.

- **General LTI Filter:** In classical TVA the specification of frequency-dependent parameters such as stiffness or damping is a common approach and is achieved through prescribing the parameter as a function of frequency and selectively applying appropriate values to the different orders of an angle or speed. This methodology has been developed from frequency domain consideration only and usually has no equivalent model in the time domain. In order

to match such modeling in the harmonic balance approach, the general LTI filter can be applied to a signal, acting directly in frequency domain on the spectrum of the input signals and providing an easy way to implement frequency-dependent parameters in steady-state analysis.

Due to usual non-transformability of frequency-dependent parameters to time domain alternative models have to be found for the time domain modeling. This is a particular challenge for consistent modeling in both worlds and often a task not easy to solve. Orienting the analysis more strongly onto time domain and network modeling allows exploring methods such as harmonic balance, which will produce consistent results for transient and steady-state analysis.

3. Propeller Modeling

Having created a simulation framework for combining transient and steady-state analysis the incorporation of propeller modeling into the software was a natural next step. Ice class requirements for propeller excitations are described primarily in time domain due to the fact that ice impact is a very non-stationary process and the resulting critical load scenarios are transient. At the same time the regular propeller blade excitation and propeller loads are equivalently describable in time and frequency domain. On the other hand, some propeller damping models do only exist in frequency domain and respective modeling capabilities have to be created in time domain. The inclusion of frequency-domain specific models allows keeping results in agreement with the still widespread classical frequency domain simulation tools.

The presented propeller model computes the driveline loads due to ice impact according to various classification rules and covers the ice classes:

- E1, E2, E3, E4, *GL (2012)*,
- IC, IB, IA, IA super, *FSA (2010)* and
- PC1, PC2, PC3, PC4, PC5, PC6, PC7, *IACS (2011)*.

It also permits a free customization of the ice class definitions within the framework of the used computational background. The dependency on nominal and geometric parameters, propeller and water inertia and damping is considered.

3.1. Ice Impact

Ice impact creates a pulsing load on the driveline with pulses whenever a propeller blade hits ice. In order to define a unified framework for simulating such a process, major classification societies defined a model assumption to be obligatory used in transient ice impact simulation.

This model requires the impact sequence to be modeled as a succession of half sine pulses. The duration (in terms of angle) of the pulses depends on the amount of ice (small block, large block, two blocks – termed Case 1 to 3 in the rules), whereas the amplitude of the pulses is defined through a set of coefficients for the amount of ice (case 1 to 3 above), propeller type (ducted or open), propeller and hub diameter, ice thickness, propeller pitch and pitch variability, drive type (engine, turbine, electric motor), as well as propeller speed. For a complete ice impact sequence the pulses for the single blades are to be superimposed according to the number of blades on the propeller, whereby single pulses may mutually overlap. Fig.3 shows sample scenarios as they are listed in the various classification requirements.

The implementation for transient simulation in SimulationX specifies the properties as stated above through the parameter dialog of the element. This permits to handle the various possible configurations in a straightforward and comprehensible way, Fig.4.

Fig. 3: Ice impact torque profile according to *GL (2012)*, *FSA (2010)*, *IACS (2011)*

Fig. 4: Propeller parameterization for transient ice impact simulation

In addition the parameterization provides the possibility the override the standard configuration options by user-defined torque profile parameters. In the simulation the propeller response will not be replayed like an external signal defined for a particular reference speed, but the generated torque profile will dynamically respond to the condition of the simulated driveline by adjusting amplitudes and angle growth rate to the current rotation speed of the propeller and thus reflect the effect of drive speed reduction due to the load increase caused by the ice impact.

Ice Class E4 - Case 1, 2, 3 - Qmax exact

Fig. 5: Model from the certification test set and tests results

In order to allow a certification of the models a test set has been generated, where each model in the set reproduces a particular behavioral aspect of the propeller as well as specific parameter combinations, excluding any dynamic interaction with a driveline model, which potentially modifies the results such, that a clear verification becomes impossible. This test set and the documented

reference results allow the quick verifying of the correct behavior of the models after model modifications or the appearance of new software releases. Fig.5 shows a test set example model, generating and displaying torque load results for a particular ice class and varying ice amounts.

When connected to a driveline model the propeller excitation will vary with the dynamic state of the driveline and the transient response of the overall system will depend on various system parameters such as the mass-elastic properties, but also for instance the reaction of the engine speed control. Fig.6 shows such a model with a simple mean-value engine model, so that the observed driveline oscillations are exclusively attributed to the propeller excitation. The propeller excitation itself is composed of a propeller load model, regular propeller blade excitations (visible through slight torque and speed fluctuations in stationary operation before the ice impact) and the shown ice impact torque. As response to the ice impact the engine speed drops and is later re-adjusted by the speed controller.

Fig. 6: Transient response model for a four-bladed propeller

For simulation in steady state the ice impact specification is kept with the only exception that the torque load is considered as an infinite sequence of ice hits.

3.2. Propeller Load Modeling

For modeling of propeller loads in frequency domain there exists a number of approaches, see e.g. Ker Wilson (1956). These are composed of descriptions for the mean value load (not affected by oscillatory components) such as propeller or combinator curves and models for the damping of oscillatory components in the propeller vibrations. Typical damping assumptions are classical damping models of Archer, Schwanecke or Frahm, but also standard damping assumptions such as Lehr's damping. The damping models usually depend on the mean values of torque and speed, as well as the vibration orders.

In frequency-domain modeling and stationary operation the separation between mean value and vibratory behavior is straightforwardly described and used in computations. In contrary, in time-domain transient simulation mean values are not clearly defined for non-stationary signals and also the estimation of mean values from stationary signals requires the observation of the signal over at least one cycle of an oscillation. For low-frequency portions in non-stationary signals this can mean that the "mean" value may change transiently in shorter time intervals than the low frequency portions themselves. In this case it becomes impossible to distinguish between the two aspects.

Considering this it becomes questionable whether the classical steady state damping models are transferable at all into a non-stationary time-domain analysis. This question is not yet clearly answered. For the modeling of propellers applicable to transient and steady-state analysis in SimulationX we eventually made the decision to not apply the steady-state damping models to the time domain. So, only the propeller load curves are commonly used for both analyses and in transient simulation use short-time filters for mean value estimation. Damping for the propeller models in transient simulation is described by a viscous damping coefficient, applied to the deviation between mean value speed and current speed of the propeller. How well such an approach correlates with the results computed in a steady-state analysis and with the classical propeller damping models is subject to further research. The same applies to the establishment of guidelines for a consistent parameterization of transient and steady-state modeling in order to achieve at least similar results.

Fig.7 shows the parameterization of the propeller model for different propeller load and damping scenarios. In Fig.8 the certification test setup for applying and measuring the propeller damping according to Schwanecke is displayed. In this analysis the propeller is set to a mean value speed and a specific first-order oscillation. The chart shows the resulting damping torque.

4. Model Certification

The analysis of non-stationary torsional vibrations in particular under ice impact is a fairly recent extension of the various class rules. The computational implementation of these rules for software vendors is a step into new territory and the respective solutions have to be proven to be compliant with the class rules. At the same time transient simulation is characterized by a multitude of dynamic interactions between the different elements in a complete model, which might obscure the actual behavioral aspects of the model properties to be verified.

Fig. 7: Propeller load parameterization

Fig. 8: Test setup and test result for steady-state propeller damping according to Schwanecke

For this reason Germanischer Lloyd as one of the drivers and certifying agent in the development of the new ice rules and ITI as provider of a simulation tool for transient and steady-state vibration analysis have decided to establish a well-defined procedure for:

- Measuring and evaluating individual behavioral aspects of simulation model objects (namely propeller models) in transient and steady-state simulation
- Defining how the behavior is validated against the class rules
- Establishing a procedure how the model compliance can be checked continuously and in particular after release changes in models and/or simulation environment

Whereas ITI as software developer is executing the verification sequence and result generation, Germanischer Lloyd verifies and testifies the compliance with the class rules. Eventually the compliance will be confirmed by issuing a certification by Germanischer Lloyd that the modeling approach and simulation results obtained in SimulationX are in accordance with the class rules.

4.1. Certification test report

The main task for the model certification was to find appropriate test scenarios, whose simulation results can be recomputed manually or by other computation software. By this, the test scenarios are for testing only one feature (e.g. only mean load or only ice impact load). Every test scenario has been described in an separate chapter of the certification test report. Fig.9 shows a sample page of this report for testing the propeller blade excitation with 1st and 2nd harmonic:

Fig. 9: Sample page of the certification test report

4.2. Automatically testing the certified model for new software releases

The certified simulation results from the certification test report are frozen to the test models. ITI's in-house test engine runs all models and compares the current simulation results with the stored reference results. All newly computed results must accord to the reference results within the limits of numerical accuracy. Only after this the test has been passed. This procedure becomes part of the standard SimulationX software tests and only after full compliance a new release will be published. In addition the permanent testing approach allows an easy re-initiation of the certification process and a renewal the compliance certificate issued by Germanischer Lloyd if this should become necessary.

5. Conclusions

Bridging the gap between steady state simulation in the frequency domain and transient simulation in the time domain for non-linear models poses considerable challenges to simulation engineers and tool providers. This is primarily caused by the linear nature of the model transformations between time and frequency domain. As a consequence both worlds have been quite strongly separated in the past when it came to the description of the behavior of non-linear phenomena, which has led to non-transferable solutions on both sides.

In this paper we have demonstrated, that it is generally possible to implement modeling methods, which allow executing transient as well as steady-state simulations on the very same model and are consistently applicable to linear as well as non-linear models. This opens new possibilities in torsional vibration analysis as well as other fields.

A dedicated propeller model was created in collaboration with the Germanischer Lloyd, which works in time and frequency domain and computes the driveline loads due to ice impact according to various classification rules.

It has to be noted nevertheless, that this process is still under way and some of the established methodology especially in steady-state analysis does not (yet?) fit very well into the presented framework. Such topics remain subject to further research and maybe open a perspective into rethinking the way how such kind of analyses should be performed in the future.

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The Spectral Method Re-Engineered: High-Performance Finite-Element-Based Fatigue Assessment Processes for Ship Structures

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Abstract

Fatigue assessment with spectral methods is described in the literature for some time. But applying such methods to whole ships is expensive to carry out in practice and has not become a standard tool. Current spectral fatigue assessment processes and related software tool chains were analyzed and considerable optimization potential was identified. The optimization techniques were applied to a tool chain based on the GL ShipLoad software. The resulting software tool demonstrated that fatigue assessments with spectral methods can be performed economically for whole ships structures, requiring similar user effort and computation time as classical (design load) methods.

1. Introduction

First-principle fatigue assessment methods for ship structures, based on long term statistics of stress spectra obtained by means of finite element analysis, are described in the literature for at least two decades now. Guidelines for applying spectral fatigue assessments are published by several classification societies, *ABS (2004)*, *DNV (2012)* and *GL (2004)*. Thus, they are considered state-of-the-art. Nevertheless, such methods are hardly applied in practice.

1.1. Spectral fatigue assessment in practice – the problems

One reason for being hardly applied is the complexity of the required software tool chain. Even for a very basic spectral fatigue assessment, several rather different processing steps need to be performed. This includes calculating hydrodynamic loads, transferring those loads to a finite element model, applying consistent internal inertia loads, performing finite element analyses for a very large number of wave load cases, extracting response amplitude operators from the finite element results, calculating a stress spectrum, and finally assessing the fatigue damage caused by the stress spectrum. Standard software tools are available for performing all above process steps. But most of those standard tools have not been designed for interworking and are controlled by incompatible interfaces. Thus, some glue code is typically implemented, controlling the execution and converting between the interfaces of a particular set of standard tools. Further, the different tools relate to different areas (e.g. hydrodynamics, finite element simulation, fatigue assessment) of analysis that are traditionally carried out by different experts. In practice, using such a tool chain requires a large amount of expert knowledge and requires a considerable amount of working time. The risk of errors is increased by the complexity of the tool chain. Tracking down problems can be difficult and time-consuming.

Managing the above principal basic spectral fatigue assessment process is not enough. To reflect practical ship operation patterns, the analyses need to be performed and combined for several different sea states, loading conditions and forward speeds. In addition, this has to be done for many different stress evaluation points. This will further increase required computer resources (storage as well as CPU time) and human efforts (e.g. modelling time).

All in all, performing spectral fatigue analyses for ship structures by means of standard tool chains is rather expensive. The related costs are currently prohibitive for standard fatigue assessments. Thus, carrying out large scale FEM-based spectral fatigue analyses is justified for a very limited number of special projects only.

Principal tasks for spectral fatigue analysis are:

- Selecting loading conditions and modelling associated finite element mass loads (e.g., container stacks, tank contents, bulk cargo).
- Specifying a set of regular waves and performing a related see-keeping analysis, resulting in external pressure loads and ship motions.
- Combining pressure and motion results (from the see-keeping analysis) with inertia loads (from mass modelling) and generating associated finite element load cases.
- Solving the finite element equations and computing the associated stress results for a large number of load cases and elements.
- Spectral/statistic post-processing of the raw finite element stresses, yielding stress spectra and fatigue results related to a large number of different sea states, ship speeds and loading conditions.
- Combining all (short term) statistic results into single (long term) statistic results.

1.2. Acceptance requirements

Would spectral fatigue assessment be accepted as a standard method if all above technical problems were fixed? Not necessarily! It is more important that the additional effort will pay off. Acceptance would be more likely if the added value delivered by the spectral method over-compensated for the additional effort. Even the considerable effort related to current spectral fatigue assessment tools is already accepted for niche projects. But it is not accepted for standard projects where the added value is too small.

The current standard FEM fatigue assessment process is based on design loads where certain design load cases are applied to the FE-model. The FE-system is solved and the stresses are evaluated. Reference stress ranges are determined from the maximum and minimum stress values among all design load cases. Fatigue is finally assessed based on those reference stress ranges. The design loads are either defined explicitly by rules (e.g. Common Structural Rules for Bulk Carriers) or indirectly by hydrodynamic loads related to prescribed design waves.

Thus, focussing on the technical problems in an isolated manner is not sufficient. The additional effort with respect to the current design load approach should be as low as possible. This includes many different aspects, e.g.:

- modelling additional loading conditions
- additional FE modelling
- additional (spectral method specific) configuration
- additional stress evaluation configuration
- additional computation time and storage requirements
- additional time for controlling, supervising and troubleshooting the computation process
- additional time for co-ordinating contributions of experts working in different departments
- additional training
- restricted flexibility (e.g. replacing current analysis tool components by newer and better ones)
- increased software maintenance requirements

Any improvement strategy needs to address this from the very beginning.

1.3 Improvement potential

Spectral fatigue assessment is a complex process in principle. Therefore, the potential for reducing the complexity of the tool chain is limited. But it should be possible to hide the complexity of current tool chains from the user. This would require investing considerable development effort into the management code that controls the software components and glues them together. The management code

needs to be very robust, anticipate all possible error conditions and handle them appropriately without user intervention. The related development effort is difficult to anticipate and likely larger than expected.

While this could significantly reduce the user effort to manage a spectral fatigue assessment process, it won't reduce problems inherent to the tool chain components. For example, classification societies typically have developed in-house statistic programmes that read transfer functions and a wave scatter diagram, perform a long term statistic calculation and output the results as a human-readable file or as a plot file. If such programme is used inside a spectral fatigue tool chain, the control code might need to read stress results from the finite-element result database, wave parameters from the seakeeping programme's configuration file and generate a transfer function input file from those data. After that, the control code needs to execute the statistic programme and convert the result file to a format as required by the next tool in the chain.

When re-engineering some of the tools, such interface-conversion overhead can be eliminated (e.g., the new tool could read transfer functions directly from the FEM result database). Frequently, the historical tools are affected by design decisions or restrictions that are no longer necessary. A re-design, exploiting current hardware features, might significantly improve performance.

1.4. Remark

The situation is different in the offshore industry. Here, the costs (downtime, docking, repair) related to possible fatigue failures are significantly larger. Thus, the costs of performing spectral fatigue assessments are more easily justified. Some vendors, who provide integrated hydrodynamic load and FEM analysis software for offshore structures, have addressed this by supporting spectral fatigue assessment.

Spectral fatigue analysis for ships and offshore structures (in particular FPSOs) might share some concepts. But there are also different or additional technical requirements, e.g:

- Supporting different forward speeds, loading conditions and sea areas is essential for ships.
- The design and approval processes are different.
- Offshore analysis software does not support ship-type-specific modelling, such as container loads.

Thus, the availability of offshore fatigue assessment software does not solve all problems.

2. Spectral fatigue assessment

2.1. Spectral fatigue assessment in theory – brief introduction

Let Δs be a stress range or $s = \Delta s / 2$ the corresponding stress amplitude. The value of the SN-curve $n(\Delta s)$ or $n(s)$ is the number of corresponding stress cycles endured. The linear damage accumulation hypothesis is applied. If $p(s)$ is a probability density for the stress amplitudes and N_0 is the total number of stress cycles, the total damage is given by the damage integral

$$D = \int_0^{\infty} N_0 p(s) / n(s) ds \quad (1)$$

The SN-curve occurring in fatigue assessment rules is usually composed of pieces

$$n(s) = n_0 \left(\frac{s}{s_0} \right)^k \quad (2)$$

or in logarithmic scale

$$\log(n) = \log(n_0) - k(\log(s) - \log(s_0)) \quad (3)$$

k is the slope of the SN curve, s_0 a reference stress level where n_0 stress cycles are endured.

The principle idea of spectral fatigue assessment assumes that the stress history is generated by a Gaussian process with power spectrum $S(\omega)$. I.e. the stress process in time domain $\sigma(t)$ has a Fourier transform $\hat{\sigma}$ such that

$$\sigma(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\sigma}(\omega) e^{i\omega t} dt \quad \text{and} \quad S(\omega) = |\hat{\sigma}(\omega)|^2 \quad (4)$$

ω is the circular frequency.

The stress collective $N_0 p(s)$ in the damage integral (1) is approximated by a simple function that only depends on a few spectral moments of the power spectrum. A spectral moment of order ν is defined as

$$m_\nu = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \omega^\nu S(\omega) d\omega \quad (5)$$

Spectral moments from 0 to fourth order are typically used.

The integral in Eq.(4) is computed numerically. The numerical integration requires evaluating the power spectrum $S(\omega_i)$ for many encountering frequencies ω_i . That power spectrum value is computed indirectly from a wave power spectrum $W(\omega)$ and a complex transfer function $Y(\omega)$. The wave spectrum is usually given parametrically, e.g. as a Bretschneider spectrum defined by significant wave height, wave period and direction. It can be evaluated for arbitrary ω_i . A particular transfer function value is evaluated by selecting a wave corresponding to the frequency ω_i . Two 90° phase shifted harmonic wave loads at unit wave amplitude are computed by a seakeeping analysis program. The pressure loads are transferred to a finite element model of the ship. The finite element system is solved and the finite element stress results at a particular point are extracted. The two stress results related to the two 90° phase shifted load cases form the real and imaginary part of the transfer function value $Y(\omega_i)$. The stress power spectrum value finally computes as

$$S(\omega_i) = W(\omega_i) |Y(\omega_i)|^2 \quad (6)$$

Once the stress power spectrum is evaluated, the spectral moments (5) are computed by numerical integration. The stress collective $N_0 p(s)$ as parameterised by those spectral moments is determined and the damage integral (1) is evaluated by means of numerical or analytical integration.

The simplest stress collective formula commonly applied is based on a Rayleigh distribution of stress amplitudes

$$p(s) = \frac{s}{m_0} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2}{2m_0}\right)^2 \quad (7)$$

with the total number of cycles during a time period T

$$N_0 = \frac{T}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{m_2}{m_0}} \quad (8)$$

This formula will reproduce rainflow-counted stress cycles exactly for narrow-banded processes. But it is even frequently applied when the narrow band assumption is violated. Some more complicated

formulas that aim at approximating rainflow-counted stress cycles for non-narrow-banded process better, are in common use to. Those formulas depend on more spectral moments (typically up to 4) and involve more analytical functions terms. See, e.g., *Benasciutti (2012)* for details.

Computation of spectral moments is further complicated because encountering frequencies ω_e depend on ship speed and wave angle. For ships with non-zero forward speed u , computation of spectral moments is usually done by a nested integration

$$m_v = \iint \omega_e(\omega, \theta, u)^v S(\omega, \theta) d\omega d\theta \quad (9)$$

$$S(\omega, \theta) = W(H_s, T_z, \mu; \omega, \theta) |Y(\omega, \theta)|^2 \quad (10)$$

The wave spectrum is typically a product of a one-dimensional spectrum $W(H_s, T_z; \omega)$ and a spreading function

$$\cos^2(\theta - \mu) \frac{2}{\pi} \quad \text{for} \quad -\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \theta - \mu \leq \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad 0 \text{ otherwise} \quad (11)$$

The computation of damage or other statistic results related to a particular combination of significant wave height, period, direction and ship speed is commonly called short-term statistics, because the ship will be operated in such conditions for a rather limited time.

A ship will be operated with lots of different parameter combinations, each of them expected with a certain probability. The short term damages need to be computed for a large representative set of parameter combinations. The sum of all short term damages weighted by the probability of occurrence will model the expected total damage. Combining the weighted results of all short term statistics is commonly called long-term statistics.

2.2. Spectral and design load fatigue assessment process compared

A global finite element model of the ship structure is needed. It is assumed that the same model can be used for a design load analysis as well as for spectral analysis. Thus, no additional finite element modelling work is expected.

In addition to the structure, mass loads related to specific loading conditions must be modelled. For a design load analysis, some extreme loading conditions, such as representing maximum still water hogging or sagging condition, are typically used. For a first trial, the same loading conditions can be used for a spectral fatigue analysis and no additional mass modelling work is required. However, taking full advantage of spectral method analysis might require to model additional (e.g. most likely) loading conditions. A good pre-processor for load modelling can re-use the modelling work already done for the extreme loading conditions. Thus, the additional mass modelling work can be kept low.

Next, the FEM loads need to be computed. Wave loads are computed by a seakeeping analysis programme, the resulting pressure loads are transferred to the finite element model and combined with the mass-induced loads. This task is considerably more complex than computing design loads prescribed by explicit rules. But the same complex tasks needs to be processed when design loads are derived from hydrodynamically computed design waves. Thus, compared to design-wave based loads, computation of spectral FEM load cases does neither require additional software nor does it involve additional modelling. There are just some differences in detail:

- The wave parameters applied will be different. But as selecting appropriate wave parameters is typically taken care of by the software, the user is not affected by this.
- Determining design waves might involve complex algorithms. In contrast, appropriate wave parameters for spectral loads can be fixed a-priori.

- Taking full advantage of spectral analysis will typically involve more operating conditions, where an operating condition is determined by a loading condition and the vessels forward speed. Using design waves, a single speed (prescribed by the rules) is typically applied. Advanced spectral analyses may compute wave loads related to several different speeds for each loading condition. However, the user is hardly affected by this. The only additional modelling work consists of configuring the speeds for each loading condition.
- The number of spectral FEM load cases is much larger than the number of design load cases. This does not affect modelling effort, but significantly increases storage requirements.

After FEM loads are computed, the FE analysis, i.e. solving the finite element equations, needs to be performed. The very same task occurs for a design load analysis. The only difference is the huge number of FEM load cases. Unfortunately, some finite element programmes fail when too many load cases are present. Thus, the choice of FEM codes is more restricted. The larger number of load cases also affects computation time. But the increase is usually moderate because most of the computation time is consumed for factorising the FEM matrix. Additional load cases are typically cheap.

With design loads, the final fatigue assessment is a computationally rather simple post-processing step. A programme needs to read the FEM result database, determine the maximum and minimum FEM stress and compute the difference.

In principle, a spectral short term statistics requires similar computational effort per load case. But as there are many more load cases, computational effort for one short term statistic is already larger. The total computational effort is even larger because computing one long term statistic requires computing a lot of short term statistic results.

The design load assessment simply needs access to the FEM stress results. The spectral method additionally needs access to the wave parameters. But for a finite element analysis, only the FE-loads themselves are relevant. As the original wave parameters are transparent to the FE-analysis, the FE result database usually does not contain the wave data. Thus, spectral fatigue assessment usually cannot be organized as a simple finite element post-processing step. Additional organisational effort is necessary for accessing the wave parameters from earlier processing steps. In practice, this can lead to additional sources of errors (such as FE results inconsistent with wave data) and reduce flexibility (e.g., a particular combination of hydrodynamic and finite element tool might be required).

When performing numerical simulations, the most significant costs are frequently caused by modelling and configuring. Fatigue assessment of FEM stresses requires selecting the stress results (e.g. by specifying a particular finite element) and assigning some fatigue-related configuration data (e.g. SN-curve parameters) to it. Configuration effort can be significantly reduced by assessing all finite elements of the model by means of several SN-curves simultaneously. This trades computation time (by computer, which is cheap) for modelling time (by human, which is expensive). In principle, this approach applied to design load as well as spectral fatigue assessment. But in practice, the related increase in computation time might only be acceptable for the (faster) design load approach.

Fatigue assessments are frequently carried out for assisting final detail design. The designer will vary parameters and study the related effect on fatigue. Thus, re-assessment of fatigue with changed parameters shall perform well. With the design load approach, it is generally acceptable to repeat the whole fatigue post-processing step with changed parameters. This cannot be expected with the computationally more demanding spectral method.

In contrast to a design load approach, spectral fatigue assessment allows for respecting individual ship operation patterns. Obviously, this requires additional configuration data. A round trip may be partitioned into several pieces (partial voyages from one particular harbour to another). Each partial voyage will relate to a typical loading condition and (possibly different) operating speeds. The sea states expected are usually defined by scatter diagrams (auxiliary software is available to calculate

scatter diagrams related to a specific route). Under the linear damage accumulation hypothesis, the damages related to a particular round trip can be computed by accumulating the damages related to the partial voyages. A user needs to model partial voyages by a pairs of operating condition and scatter diagram (triples of loading condition, speed, and scatter diagram). Then voyage scenarios can be specified by assigning contribution factors to the partial voyages. Several different voyage scenarios should be configurable and processed in parallel.

2.3. Use case

As a reference use case, a global finite element model containing 50000 plain stress or shell elements is assumed. Evaluating one stress result per element, a design-load fatigue analysis can be performed easily with current soft- and hardware.

Spectral fatigue assessment shall be based on the same FE-model. Elementary waves for 12 directions times 25 wave lengths are assumed, representing a currently typical set of spectral wave loads. This multiplies to 300 transfer functions per operating condition. With one real and imaginary part, there are 600 FEM load cases per operating condition.

The spectral use case might apply three loading conditions combined with 3 different speeds each. Thus, we can multiply the number of load cases and numerical effort related to a single operating condition by a factor of 9. A few thousand fem load cases are expected in real world spectral analysis models.

In spectral statistics, the stresses caused by elementary (unit) waves are combined with a sea states. The sea states are typically parameterized by a significant wave height H_s , a zero upcrossing period T_z and a direction μ .

For long-term statistics, a typical scatter diagram with 16 different significant wave heights and periods is assumed. A few combinations occur with probability zero. Thus, only 240 (H_s, T_z) combinations are assumed, each of them occurring in combination with one out of 12 different main sea directions μ . Thus, there are 2880 different contributing short-term sea states parameterized by the triples (H_s, T_z, μ).

3. Optimisation analysis

For an internal project, the GL ShipLoad software has been used within a classical fatigue assessment tool chain as described in the introduction. The question arose whether the practical difficulties were caused by principle problems or just by a lack of appropriate software tools. GL ShipLoad is a software tool to compute FEM loads based on design waves, *Eisen and Cabos (2007)*. Thus, as outlined in section 2.2, the initial part of a spectral fatigue assessment process (up to the FEM analysis) is already supported well. The related additional user effort for configuring and modelling is small. Thus, the algorithms and design of the statistic modules were reviewed.

Some typical common features of the statistics programmes usable in the spectral tool chain were identified:

- The programmes read the transfer functions and other configuration data from a text-formatted input file. The syntax of those files is tuned for direct human input. Some traditional conventions are used that ease direct input, but are not necessary for technical reasons.
- The tools aim at supporting several advanced statistic methods in a flexible manner. This design goal conflicts with optimising for performance.
- The originally intended use is studying just one (or very few) details. When using the tools for performing a lot of similar related computations, identical intermediate processing steps are unnecessarily repeated.

- Changing configuration parameters (e.g. SN curve) that only affect the final computation steps, requires to re-run the computation from the very beginning.

This indicated that a specially designed spectral fatigue post-processor was necessary to address the difficulties.

3.1. FEM result databases as transfer function source

As already mentioned, fatigue assessment by means of design loads is managed easily because it is just a simple finite element post-processing step that only needs access to the FEM stress result data. For managing spectral fatigue assessment equally easily, the spectral fatigue post-processor should also read all stress data directly from the finite element stress result database.

In addition to the stress results, spectral analysis needs to know about the related wave parameters. The wave parameters are metadata associated with the FE load cases. They do not affect the FE-analysis but are used when post-processing the FE results. Therefore, the finite element load data model was enhanced. In particular, the following metadata attributes were assigned to the FE load cases:

- the wave vector (equivalent to wave length and direction),
- the wave phase,
- the forward speed,
- a tag for identifying different loading conditions.

The GL ShipLoad software was enhanced accordingly. In addition to the finite element wave load data, the software also wrote the associated load case attributes into the FE load data file.

The spectral fatigue post-processor only relied on the presence of the load attributes. No further conventions, such as special ordering of load cases, were required. Upon start up, the fatigue post-processor first extracted all load case metadata from the FE result database. Load cases related to the same operating conditions were identified by the forward speed and loading condition attributes. For each referenced operating condition the related wave load cases were identified. The stress results related to those load cases were read and transformed to the real and imaginary part of the transfer function values.

The concept of storing the wave parameters together with the fem stress results also made the spectral fatigue post-processing independent of other modules in the tool chain. E.g., it was possible to compute the wave loads by different hydrodynamic methods.

Many different finite element codes are in common use. All finite element codes can compute stresses. Thus, spectral fatigue post-processing is not restricted to a particular finite element programme. But reading stresses directly from the FEM result database restricts the post-processor to supported database formats. To limit the impact of this restriction, the spectral fatigue postprocessor accessed the fem result database through a driver interface. This reduced the implementation effort for supporting additional stress result databases.

When new FEM database formats shall be supported, the wave load attributes need to be stored inside the FEM database. Some FEM databases might already support storing of transparent load case attributes. Other database formats will not explicitly support this. But it might still be possible to store the load attribute data by means of some conventions and tricks. If not, an auxiliary file for the load case attributes is always an option (but the user will be responsible to ensure consistency of result and attribute files).

3.2. From transfer functions to spectral moments

Spectral moments of stress spectra are usually computed by numerically integrating [6]. This is an integral about a two-dimensional space. Spectral statistic programmes typically do this by nesting two one-dimensional integrations. This typically imposes some restrictions on the choice of wave directions and length:

- Wave loads need to be evaluated for small number of different equidistant wave directions θ
- For all directions, the wave loads need to be evaluated at the same wave frequencies ω
- Separation of spectrum variables assuming a spreading function (11) is frequently hard-coded.

These restrictions are artificial. The wave spectrum can be transformed to a two-dimensional vector coordinate, say wave vector k and the moments can be computed as

$$m_\nu = \iint \omega_e(k)^\nu \overline{W}(H_s, T_z, \mu; k) |Y(k)|^2 dk \quad (12)$$

A numerical integration formula consists of selecting a set of evaluation points k_i and associated quadrature formula weights w_i such that Eq.(12) is approximately evaluated as

$$m_\nu = \sum_i w_i \omega_e(k_i)^\nu \overline{W}(H_s, T_z, \mu; k_i) |Y(k_i)|^2 \quad (13)$$

All factors left of $|Y(k_i)|^2$ depend on the short term wave spectrum, ω_e^ν and the quadrature formula, but not on the transfer function. They can be pre-computed once and re-used to compute the spectral moment for any transfer function. If the moments related to all short term sea spectra are collected in a vector m and the squared transfer function values are collected in a vector y , those moments can be computed by a matrix-vector-multiplication

$$m = My \quad (14)$$

For the use case, this would require $2880 \cdot 300 = 864000$ floating point operations per stress evaluation point. Computing moments of 4 different orders at 50000 stress points would require 172 800 000 000 operations. This can be interpreted as a matrix-matrix-multiplication. Practically, this can be performed almost exploiting the full floating point processing power of current hardware. Assuming 5 GFlops, all spectral moments could be computed within 35 s.

3.3. From spectral moments to long term statistics

The statistic results related to all short term sea states need to be combined to the final results. Assuming a ship will be operated in several sea states parameterized by significant wave height, zero up-crossing period and direction $(H_s, T_z, \mu)_{j=1, \dots, J}$. Let P_j be the probability of sea state (H_s, T_z, μ) and r_j a related static result. The long-term statistics result is defined by

$$r = \sum_j P_j r_j. \quad (15)$$

If we are mainly interested in damages, the damage integral (1) can be computed related to every short term sea spectrum. Assuming the linear damage accumulation hypothesis, the long term statistic damage is simply the weighted sum of the short term damages. This is conceptually simple and storage requirements are small (one damage value). A disadvantage is that all parameters affecting damage computations (SN curve, stress concentration factors) need to be known in advance. After modifying such parameters, the damage calculation must be repeated from the very beginning. Another disadvantage is that the long term statistics results are provided for damages only. It is not possible to compute long term statistic results related to other vales (e.g. zero up-crossing counts).

Alternatively, stress collectives $N_0 p(s)$ can be computed for every short-term sea spectrum. The short-term collectives can be finally combined to a long term stress collective. Only one damage integral (1) is computed from the finally combined stress collective. The finally combined long term stress collective can be stored. Damage calculation or other statistic post-processing can be based on the stored long term collective.

But this approach is more difficult to carry out. In principal, the stress collectives could be accumulated linearly. But the collectives resulting from short term statistic spectral moments are given in parametric form. The sum of two parametric collectives is no longer parameterized by a similar formula. Therefore, it is necessary to represent the short term collectives in a different form that can be accumulated numerically.

The most obvious representation is obtained by evaluating the short term collectives at some stress levels s_i . For each short term sea state, the number of exceedances related to a particular stress level s_i is accumulated. This finally results in a numerical representation of the long term stress collective at stress nodes s_i . When a sufficiently dense set of stress levels is used, the representation directly allows for computing the damage integral (1) numerically.

The approach requires that all short term stress collectives are evaluated at the same stress levels s_i . Spectral fatigue analysis requires combining results for several loading conditions, speeds, and scatter diagrams. Therefore, a common set of stress level s_i must be chosen a-priori and used with all short-term sea states.

The computational effort for evaluating the short term stress collectives is significant. After the optimisation potential for computing the spectral moments had been exploited (see previous subsection), numerical experience indicated that the largest amount of computation time was spent for evaluating the short-term statistics stress collectives.

The exact computation time is difficult to estimate. For each stress level, an analytical function needs to be evaluated. Even the most simple function (narrow band assumption with Rayleigh spectrum, see subsection 2.1) contains one square root and one exponential function. Other formulas will contain even more function terms. The numeric evaluation of one analytical function term already involves several floating point operations. Such evaluations cannot exploit the computational power of modern hardware as efficiently as a matrix-matrix-multiplication. Thus, numerically evaluating the stress collective for a single stress level and a single short term sea state consumes a lot of CPU time. That computation time may be equal to or even larger than the time for computing the related spectral moments from $300 |Y(k_i)|^2$ values.

3.4. Representing a stress collective by a generalized gamma distribution

As most of the computation time is consumed for evaluating the short term stress collectives at the stress levels s_i , the number of stress levels should be as small as possible. Unfortunately, evaluating the damage integral (1) by means of simple numerical integration schemes (e.g. trapezoidal rule) will require several (e.g. 20 or 40) stress levels.

On the other hand, long term stress collectives caused by wave-induced loads are frequently modeled by means of a simple exponential distribution. That collective depends on two parameters only. In principle, the collective is uniquely determined by evaluating it at two different stress levels. This can be exploited in a spectral hybrid algorithm:

- Short term stress collectives are evaluated at two fixed stress levels only.
- Long term stress collectives are accumulated.
- The long term stress collective is interpolated by an exponential function.

- Further statistic post-processing (such as computing the damage integral) is based on the parametrically represented exponential function.

The interpolation is only done for the finally accumulated long term stress collectives. Thus, the additional impact on total computation time is negligible. As the number of stress levels is significantly reduced, the computation time decreases proportionally. The storage size for representing the stress collectives is reduced by the same factor.

Frequently, three-parameter stress collectives based on the Weibull distribution are used in current rules (e.g. IACS Common Structural Rules for Tankers). Such distributions can also be used with the hybrid approach after evaluating the stress collectives at three different stress levels (instead of only two as for the simple exponential function).

The hybrid approach offers some additional benefits. As the long term stress collective is represented by a parametric formula, it can be evaluated at arbitrary stress levels later. The same holds for its inverse function. For piecewise linear SN curves, the damage integral can be computed analytically by means of incomplete Gamma functions

$$\gamma(\alpha; x) = \int_0^x t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt, \quad \Gamma(\alpha; x) = \int_x^{\infty} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt \quad (16)$$

The incomplete Gamma functions are also useful to define a four-parameter representation of stress collectives:

$$P(\alpha, x) = \gamma(\alpha; x) / \Gamma(\alpha; 0) \quad (17)$$

is a cumulative probability distribution function, defining the so-called Gamma distribution. Thus,

$$P(\alpha, (bs)^\beta) \quad (18)$$

is also a cumulative probability distribution function, defining the so-called generalized Gamma distribution that is parameterized by α , b , and β .

Fig.1: Generalized Gamma distribution

Note that different parameterizations are used in the literature. With $\alpha = 1$ this reduces to the Weibull distribution.

It was observed that numerically computed stress collectives frequently show different asymptotic behavior for large and small stress levels. This cannot be modeled by means of a Weibull distribution. But the additional parameter of the generalized Gamma distribution allows for fitting the asymptotic behavior at either ends independently. Together with the N_0 -parameter, this forms a four-parameter stress collective representation. For piecewise linear SN curves it is still possible to compute the damage integral analytically, *Yang and Moan (2011)*.

Therefore, the hybrid approach based on the generalized Gamma stress collective was used. This required evaluating the short term stress collectives at four different stress levels. Interpolation by a generalized Gamma collective turned out to be more difficult. The parameters of a Weibull collective that interpolates three values can be computed analytically. The generalized Gamma interpolating functions needed to be calculated iteratively. This increased the related numerical effort. But as the interpolation is only computed for the final long term static collectives, this is still negligible in context of the whole process.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of current spectral fatigue analysis tool chains revealed sufficient optimisation potential. A theoretical analysis suggested that by exploiting that optimisation potential, practical problems in managing the tool chain could be eliminated. Computational efficiency could be enhanced such that performing spectral fatigue analysis for a very large number of FEM stress results (e.g., all elements of a global finite element model) was practicable.

The identified optimisation techniques were applied to a tool chain based on the GL ShipLoad software. As GL ShipLoad already supported the computation of section loads from hydrodynamic loads, spectral analysis was also applied to the section load values. Spectrally analysing all section load values was as fast as determining critical design loads.

The storage requirements for the spectral method were significantly higher than for design loads. Further, the optimisation techniques made use of trading computation time for space. However, the additional storage was easily provided by modern hardware and operating systems.

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Application of Cross-Impact Analysis to Evaluate Innovations in the Cruise Industry

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Abstract

Ship owners of cruise lines have the problem to evaluate technical (or business) innovations concerning their cruise ships. The question is whether the investment will pay back or not or whether the investment is really necessary for not losing track compared with competitors. Often, the pay back of investment costs cannot be calculated directly because they are influenced by indirect or long-term effects (uncertainties) which are difficult to monetize. The causal cross-impact analysis method allows to define beside the hard variables (like the costs) also soft variables (like the image of a cruise line) and the inter-relationships between such variables. This paper describes a cross-impact model developed for the support of investment decisions including such soft factors and uncertainties. The model was implemented with the simulation software JCrimp developed at BIBA.

1. Introduction

The building of a cruise ship is long-term investment as cruise ships often have a 30+ years life cycle. Therefore, all decisions concerning technological and other details of the cruise ship to build can be considered strategic as they may influence the profitability of the ship in the long-term. Decisions have to be taken with uncertainty concerning future developments (e.g. regulations concerning CO² output). Also soft factors like the image of the ship owner or of the ship itself (e.g. the image concerning environmental friendliness or safety) have a significant impact the profitability. As a consequence ship owners are often reluctant when implementing innovations because the pay-off is hard to estimate especially in times of turbulent markets but with but with qualms about the correctness of decisions. One approach to anticipate the unknown future is the application of scenario techniques.

Scenario technique, *Götze (1993)*, or scenario planning, *Walton (2008)*, is a widely used tool for strategic planning, risk and sensitivity analysis and organisational learning. When dealing with hard (quantitative) approaches of forecasting, the result is often just one single scenario connected with a specific probability of occurrence. But, to anticipate the full range of possible future states, other approaches (like narrative storytelling, simulations with varying parameters) should be applied. The natural time frame for scenario techniques is mid-term to long-range. Concerning the planning of building a cruise ship two aspects are important: First, the long-range trends in the cruise industry market and its environment, and second the ship owner itself with focus on its economic development.

Scenario techniques are based on two principles, *Gausemeier et al. (1996)*:

- System thinking: Organisations – in this case the cruise ship owner – must perceive their environment as a complex network of inter-related (external as well as internal) factors.
- Multiple futures: Organisations should not reduce their strategic thinking to exactly one prognosticated future. Instead, alternative future scenarios should be created and considered during strategic planning.

The scenario generation approach adopted by BIBA is based on causal cross-impact analysis, *Krauth et al. (1998)*, which has first been developed by *Helmer (1977,1981)*. Up to now, BIBA included several enhancements to the causal cross-impact analysis method according to requirements identified during various research projects: delayed impacting, threshold impacting, expression variables and a

technique for structuring and managing scenarios in a tree. BIBA implemented a cross-impact modelling and simulation software package called JCrimp, which allows the interactive set-up, simulation and evaluation of causal cross-impact models, *Duin (2007a,b)*.

The basic idea of cross-impact analysis is to get a systemic picture of the rough structure of a complex system supporting long-term planning and assessment tasks. In difference to other simulation approaches like system dynamics, causal cross-impact analysis is not used to generate prognostic data, but to analyse effects over and above a business-as-usual scenario anticipated by the user.

2. Research Approach

In the following the formal elements of a causal cross-impact-model are introduced. For a better understanding of the attributes of the model elements, screen shots of JCrimp are shown.

2.1 Theory of Causal Cross-Impact-Analysis (CIA)

In difference to other approaches the Cross-Impact-Analysis (CIA) is based on a discrete time model. Therefore, the time period under investigation is divided into single time steps called scenes. Each scene represents a time span, e.g. a year, a quarter or a month. The end of the total time period under consideration is called the time horizon.

The basic elements of a cross-impact model are time dependent trend variables representing the core elements of the system under consideration. For each trend variable the user is asked to provide a time series describing the estimated future development of the trend variable. This time series represents the business-as-usual case and is called the a-priori time series. Together with the a-priori time series the user defines the range of possible values for the trend. To express uncertainty in the estimation of the a-priori time series the user defines an interval around these values, called the volatility. The volatility describes that the estimated a-priori value is with 50% probability within this interval. Examples for trend variables may be the operative costs of cruise ship, the global oil price or the buying power of potential customers. Fig. 1 shows the trend editor of JCrimp with the trend definition of a variable called “OperativeCosts”.

Fig. 1: Trend-editor in JCrimp

Trend variables are interconnected by so-called cross-impacts. A cross-impact describes the direction and the strength of an influence between a source and a target trend. When the source trend deviates during simulation from its a-priori values the impact will cause a deviation in the target trend. The caused deviation in the target trend depends on the strength of the cross-impact and the volatilities of both the source and the target trend. Defining impacts between trend variables results in a network of inter-connected trend variables describing the structure of the system. This network can be visualized as a graph or as a matrix.

Further model elements are event variables. Events are not under the control of any player involved in the system but have strong impacts on other variables. With each event the user defines an occurrence probability for each scene of the model. Between event and trend variables cross-impacts can be defined. Therefore, the occurrence (or absence) of an event during simulation can cause a deviation in the target trend. A trend can also impact an event variable, i.e. the occurrence probability of the event. An example of an event may be a global oil crisis with strong impact on prices.

Action variables are model elements representing the strategic manoeuvring space of actors. To describe the interactions between action and trend variables also cross-impacts can be defined. An actor can set an action by spending money on it. The money is subtracted from the budget of the actor and represents the costs of the action. Depending of the amount of money spent and its type the action develops an intensity with which it influences other variables (trends or events) via the cross-impacts. The JCrimp editor for action variables is shown in Fig.2. The trend, event and action variables with the defined cross-impacts between them span the cross-impact matrix, the heart of each model. The matrix is an alternative format for visualising the network of interconnected variables, Fig.3.

Fig. 2: Action-editor in JCrimp

Fig. 3: Network of trend, action and event variables visualized as graph and as matrix

Additional elements of each model are so-called expression variables. Such variables do not have any influence on other model elements but can be used to define indicators by performing calculations including the values of other variables.

Such a cross-impact model has static and dynamic properties and an analysis of the static properties allows estimating dynamic behaviour. Each variable has an active and a passive sum which are the additions of all impacts per row and column respectively. Variables with a high active sum tend to drive the system in certain directions while variables with a high passive sum tend to act as buffers. Variables with high active and high passive sum are considered critical because they tend to reinforce deviations they once received. Also important are the feedback loops where a deviation sent out by a variable comes back over some steps (e.g. trend A impacts trend B, trend B impacts trend C, and trend C impacts trend A again). If the sum of cross-impacts in such a feedback loop is greater one, the feedback loop has reinforcing effects.

Detailed dynamic behaviour of the cross-impact model can only be observed by applying simulation to it. The simulation algorithm is designed in such a way that if no event is explicitly set to occur and no action is set to develop intensity the simulated values of trends should be near by the a-priori values of those trends (i.e. at least within the volatility interval of the trend). A cross-impact model which shows this behaviour is said to be valid.

2.2. Approach Taken for this Research

For the model development, we built a team of three subject matter experts and one experienced cross-impact modelling expert. This group met regularly over a time span of several months to first identify the objective for the cross-impact model and then developing the model itself. After the objective of supporting investment decisions in innovations has been clarified a "standard cruise ship" has been defined to support the definition of realistic trend variables. Also, two event variables have been identified, but focus was more on defining a good set of trend variables.

Because of investment decisions are measured by monetary indicators, most important indicators have been included like costs, turnover, surplus, and return on sales as expression variables.

The most time consuming task was to estimate the cross-impacts between trends. Each member of the group filled out the cross-impact matrix in a qualitative way with the coding of 0 is no impact, 0.5 is a weak impact, 1 is a medium impact and 2 is a strong impact. The sign (plus or minus) gives the direction of the impact. After combining these four matrices into one matrix it became clear that the members of the group had slightly different understanding of the system because about 30% of estimated cross-impacts differed strongly among members. This made it necessary to discuss the variables again and to perform a second round of individual cross-impact estimation. After the second round, only around 10% of impacts had strong deviations among team members and have been discussed and agreed in the group.

Within the next step, real data was used to define the a-priori time series of trend variables. Simulation runs for model validation were quite promising using qualitative estimations of cross-impacts. However, after modelling some fictitious innovations as action variables it became clear that some of the impacts are far too strong. This made it necessary to re-assess all cross-impacts again with a quantitative approach, i.e. defining what deviation in the source trend will result in what deviation in the target trend (e.g. increasing the prestige of the company by one point will result in \$50 increase in the turnover of a lower berth day). New validation simulations were positive and finally action variables representing the innovation options were defined to round up the cross-impact model.

3. Results

This chapter provides details of the cross-impact model developed to support decision making in investment situations. Because of we were not directly involved in such an investment situation during the time the model was developed, a virtual "standard cruise ship" was defined allowing to endow it with realistic numbers which are publicly available. The definition of such a "standard cruise ship" was done for two reasons. First, this allows using some real numbers which are public available to prove the general structure of the model, and second, such a model can easily be adapted to real investment decision situations.

The "standard cruise ship" contains 1,046 cabins with a lower berth of 2,092. This results in available lower berth days of 747,320. Acquisition costs for the ship is \$ 352,000,000. The ship is running with an occupancy rate slightly above 100% (between 103 and 111%) with an average availability of 95% of time during a year (5% are assumed for obligatory maintenance and repairs). The total number of crew is 607. The operational model foresees that the ship is during operation 60% of the time in harbour and 40% of the time at sea. The average fuel consumption is 140t HFO (Heavy Fuel Oil) per 24 hours with 85% MCR (Maximum Continuous Rating). Financial data for the "standard cruise ship" was generated by averaging public available data from Annual Reports of the Carnival Corporation, Table 1, as obtained from <http://phx.corporate-ir.net/phoenix.zhtml?c=140690&p=irol-reportsoter2>. The time model starts in 2013 having 20 scenes of a length of a quarter (three months), thus covering a time period up to the end of 2017.

Table 1: Averaged Carnival data from years 2006 – 2011

Measure	Value
Available Lower Berth Days (ALBD)	60,273,827
Passenger ticket revenues (in \$)	10,572,500,000
Onboard revenues (in \$)	2,958,333,333
Tours and Others (in \$)	342,500,000
Operational days	347.76
Turnover per LBD (in \$)	175.88
Onboard Spending per LBD (in \$)	54.44
Total Revenues per LBD (in \$)	230.32
Operation Costs (in \$)	93.38
Sales, Marketing and administration per ALBD (in \$)	25.16
Personnel (in \$)	24.29
Fuel per ALBD (in \$)	23.90
Financing per ALBD (in \$)	5.58
Depreciation (2.83% of acquisition costs in \$)	21.47

3.1 Cross-Impact Variables

Based on the assumptions for the "standard cruise ship" the trend variables shown in Table 2 were defined for the cross-impact model. Table 3 and Table 4 show the event and expression variables of the resulting model. For modelling an investment concerning an innovation just one action variable has been defined called Innovate. This variable needs to be adapted and/or replaced by other action variable(s) for the specific innovation under consideration.

Table 2: Trend variables of the cross-impact model, LBD = lower berth day

Trend	Unit	Description
Prestige	Scale [-10,10]	Prestige represents the image of the ship and is a composition of social, safety, brand and environmental image as seen by the general public.
TurnoverByPassenger	\$/LBD	Sum of average ticket price and onboard spending including tours per lower berth day. It is assumed to be constantly 230\$ with a volatility of 10%.
ShipUtilization	%	Occupancy Rate. The lower berth capacity represents 100%. The occupancy rate has a value between 0 and 2. A typical utilization is a value > 1

		(e.g. 1.1).
YearlyUtilisation	%	The yearly utilization represents the average percentage the ship is in operation per year. (e.g. 347.8 of 365 days is around 95%.)
Capacity	#	The capacity of the cruiser in terms of number of passengers. The lower berth capacity is assumed to be 2092 passengers.
Personnel	#	The total number of crew members is assumed to be 607.
OperativeCosts	\$/LBD	The average operative costs per lower berth day. It is assumed to be constantly 93\$ with a volatility of 10%.
AdministrativeCosts	\$/LBD	The average administrative costs per lower berth day. It is assumed to be constantly 25\$ with a volatility of 10%.
CustomerPotential	Ratio	Pax day demand by available lower berth.
BuyingPower	\$/Person/Year	Buying power depends on the par capita income which is roughly estimated to be 26800 \$ per year and person.
HarbourBySea	%	The relation of harbor days to sea days; measured in percent of time the cruiser is on sea.
GlobalFuelPrice	\$/t	Price for HFO or IFO380; see bunkerworld.com. It is assumed that the price is growing from 650\$ in 2013 to 1,300\$ by the end of 2017.
GlobalWages	\$/Person/Quarter	The average wage for crew which is constantly 7,477\$ with a volatility of 10%.
AverageFuelConsumption	t/Day	Average fuel consumption at 85% MCR for 24 h (140t).

Table 3: Event variables of cross-impact model

Event	Unit	Description
FuelPriceChanges	%	Due to an oil crisis the fuel prices are increasing much stronger than anticipated in the business-as-usual case.
WagesPriceChanges	%	Staff is earning more money than anticipated in the business-as-usual case.

Table 4: Expressions of the cross-impact model

Expression	Unit	Description / Formula
FinanceAndDeprication	\$/ Quarter	Constant: $0.0283 * 505120000 / 4 = 3,573,724$
FuelConsumption	t / Quarter	Formula: $(1/3 * (1-HarbourBySea) * AverageFuelConsumption * 365.25/4 + 2/3 * HarbourBySea * AverageFuelConsumption * 365.25/4) * YearlyUtilisation$
FuelCosts	\$/ Quarter	Formula: $FuelConsumption * GlobalFuelPrice$
WagesCosts	\$/ Quarter	Formula: $Personnel * GlobalWages$
OperationalCosts	\$/ Quarter	Formula: $OperativeCosts * Capacity * 347.8/4$
AdminCosts	\$/ Quarter	Formula: $AdministrativeCosts * Capacity * 347.8/4$

TotalCosts	\$ / Quarter	Formula: OperationalCosts + WagesCosts + FuelCosts + AdminCosts + FinanceAndDeprication
Turnover	\$ / Quarter	Formula: YearlyUtilisation * ShipUtilisation * TurnoverByPassenger * Capacity * 365.25/4
Surplus	\$ / Quarter	Formula: Turnover - TotalCosts
ReturnOnSales	Ratio	Formula: Surplus / Turnover

3.2 Cross-Impact Matrix

The variables introduced in the previous chapter are inter-connected through cross-impacts as shown in Fig.4. The direction of an arrow in the cross-impact matrix represents the direction of the effect, i.e. an upward arrow represents a positive impact, and a downward arrow depicts a negative impact. The size of the arrow indicates its strength. The cross-impacts on the main diagonal of the matrix require special attention. These impacts describe direct self-reinforcements of variables. Trends and events can have self-impacts while actions can not. Most of the cross-impacts are constants describing a coefficient of how much of a deviation in terms of volatility in the target variable will cause a deviation of one volatility unit in the source variable.

Fig. 4: Cross-impact matrix of the model

3.3 Driving Structures of the Model

The driving forces in the model can be analyzed by mapping the active and passive sums of variables into a two-dimensional diagram. This is supported by JCrimp as shown in Fig.5. The analysis of the variables reveals that BuyingPower and GlobalFuelPrice have high active sums (of 5.77 and 4.03, respectively) and therefore should have a strong influence on other variables. Variables TurnoverByPassenger and OperativeCosts have high passive sums (8.25 and 5.09) meaning that they may be strongly influenced by others. The critical variables are Prestige and CustomerPotential with having relatively high active and passive sums. That means that these variables are the driving forces of the model and strategic actions should address them to gain changes in the 'right' direction.

Fig. 2: Analysis of active and passive sums with JCrimp

Fig. 6: Analysis of feedback loops with JCrimp

Other driving structures are the feedback loops of the model which can also be analysed with JCrimp, Fig.6. In total this model contains 26 feedback loops including direct self-impacting loops. Examples for feedback loops are:

- CustomerPotential \Rightarrow TurnoverByPassenger \Rightarrow Prestige \Rightarrow CustomerPotential
All of the cross-impacts in this loop are positive resulting in a reinforcing loop. The strength of the reinforcement is not very high because of the weak impact of TurnoverByPassenger on Prestige. Multiplying all cross-impacts in this loop results in a value of 0.66.
- ShipUtilization \Rightarrow Personnel \Rightarrow TurnoverByPassenger \Rightarrow ShipUtilization
Not all of the cross-impacts in this loop are positive resulting in a reinforcing loop with alternating amplitudes. The strength of the reinforcement is again not high because of the weak impacts of Personnel on TurnoverByPassenger and TurnoverByPassenger on ShipUtilization. Multiplying all cross-impacts in this loop results in a value of -0.15.

3.4 Simulation Results

During the simulation values of trends are determined by using a random number generator drawing numbers which are following a normal distribution and with a probability of 0.5 the value is in the range of the volatility of the trend variables. Doing so, one scenario might look very much different to another one depending on the initialization of the random number generator. To support the analysis of such scattered values the JCrump software performs many (the user decides on the number) simulation runs and calculates statistical data such as average, standard deviation, median, etc. The numbers shown in the result chart of Fig.7 are average values of 100,000 simulation runs. The time needed to perform this amount of simulation runs was about 9 minutes on a standard laptop computer.

Fig. 7: Simulated results of expressions Turnover, TotalCosts, and Surplus

The first simulation runs are used to validate the model. A model is considered to be valid when the average of all simulated values of trend variables is within the interval defined by its volatility. This is the case for the presented model. The next check is whether the financial numbers generated by the model correspond to the financial numbers which could be generated from aggregated Carnival data. Table 5 shows the differences with less than 1% in turnover and costs and less than 2% in surplus and return on sales (the numbers taken from the JCrump simulation are taken from the first scene).

Table 5: Comparison of aggregated Carnival data and simulated values

	Revenues	Total Costs	Surplus	Return on Sales
Averaged Carnival Data	43,565,942	33,898,969	9,666,973	22.19
JCrimp Simulated Data	43,365,431	33,918,259	9,508,843	21.89
Difference (in %)	0.46	0.06	1.64	1.18

Fig. 8: Effect of a simulated oil crisis on the global fuel price

Fig.7 shows that the surplus expected to gain from operating the "standard cruise ship" will decrease from around 10m \$ to 6m \$. The main reason for that is the increase in the total costs which are driven by increasing fuel prices. The waves in turnover (and thus in surplus) are a result of assuming different ship utilization rates (between 103% and 111%) depending on the quarter, i.e. seasonal fluctuations).

Next, two scenarios were created to show the effects of an event (oil crisis) and an action (introduction of multipurpose room). First, we set the event FuelPriceChange explicitly to occur from the 11th scene up to the end. This has a direct impact on the variable GlobalFuelPrice from its 12th scene on, Fig.8. The variable GlobalFuelPrice passes this impact along to other variables, i.e. Turnover-ByPassenger (ship owner have to increase prices), ShipUtilization (ship owners try to maximize operative time), OperativeCosts, BuyingPower (people have less to spend on cruises), HarbourBySea (ship owners try to reduce ship movement), and AverageFuelConsumption (ship owners try to reduce fuel consumption).

The second scenario concerns the introduction of a multipurpose room. This is an idea developed from the Meyer Werft GmbH in Papenburg, Germany in the context of the European funded large scale integrating project BESST (Breakthrough in European Ship and Shipbuilding Technologies, www.besst.it). The innovative introduction of a multipurpose room has investment costs of about 2.3m \$ and various impacts on other variables: the lower berth capacity can be enhanced by 42 cabins with 2 beds each, operative costs (energy consumption and maintenance) can be reduced, and crew needs to be increased slightly.

Fig.9 shows how the surplus is developing within the business-as-usual scenario, the scenario with the assumed oil crisis and the scenario with investments in a multipurpose room.

Fig. 9: Development of surplus in business-as-usual, oil crisis and multipurpose room scenarios

4. Discussion

This analysis has shown that the sudden occurrence of an oil crisis can turn the surplus into a negative number. The model shows that there are some inherent mechanisms that catch the free fall of the surplus and brings it back into the positive zone. These mechanisms are most probably some feedback loops which need further investigation to validate their correctness.

The introduction of a multipurpose room has some positive benefits. The number of available lower berth days is increased, operative costs are reduced and the development of the surplus shows that the additional costs in personnel and is easily compensated. Analyzing the values of Fig.9 shows that the surplus with the investment into the multipurpose room is in average 132.5% of the surplus of the business-as-usual situation. Aggregating the numbers reveals that during the time span under consideration the surplus could be enhanced from 183.6m \$ to 239.9m \$, i.e. by 30.7%.

5. Conclusions and Outlook

This paper introduced the causal cross-impact analysis as a decision support tool to assess long-lasting investments in the cruise ship building industry. A model has been developed including not only monetary variables, but also soft factors like the image of the ship owner or of the ship itself. It has been shown how the structures of such a model can be analyzed and the dynamics can be simulated.

The data used to get most realistic simulation values has been based on public available data from Carnival Corporation. The results as been discussed in the previous chapter are quite promising, but they still lack validation with real cases. Also, the quantitative data needs to be compared with data from other decision support tools to get a better understanding of differences and similarities. Therefore, we can conclude that the presented approach with the preliminary model is still in evaluation and needs further investigation and refinement which best is done by applying the whole method in the context of a real investment decision case.

Acknowledgements

This work has been partly funded by the European Commission through European Project ThroughLife: Improved through-life asset management through application of advanced production, retrofit and dismantling processes (EU FP7 Project 265831; www.throughlife.eu) of the 7th Framework Research Programme. We also thank Meyer Werft GmbH for providing the idea of a multipurpose room as an innovation in cruise ship business. This idea has been developed in the context of the European Project BESST: Breakthrough in European Ship and Shipbuilding Technologies (EU FP7 Project 233980; www.besst.it) of the 7th Framework Research Programme.

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Design Evaluation of Energy-Saving Devices for Full Form Ship Propulsion

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Abstract

This study further applied the CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics)-based propeller energy-loss analysis approach developed previously for performance evaluation of a selected ESD (Energy-Saving Devices) design adopted on a full form ship (Capesize bulk carrier). Comprehensive flow information obtained from CFD simulation and detailed ESD working mechanics from the energy-loss analysis are presented. In addition, to confirm propeller cavitation and propeller-induced hull pressure are well controlled with no propeller-induced hull vibration risk, blade cavity and cavitating induced hull pressure analyses are performed in this study.

1. Introduction

Stern appurtenances, also known as energy-saving devices (ESD), have been used to improve propulsive efficiency for more than 100 years. ESD utilization began to draw attention during the oil crisis in early 1980s, and in recent years it is becoming more popular because of the high demand of fuel saving for ship propulsion. In the past, ESD design optimization mainly relies on model testing. One disadvantage of using model testing for design is that only limited flow data around the propeller and ESD is provided in model test measurement because detailed flow field measurement is usually very expensive. However, this information is important for understanding how the ESD is interacting with the propeller thereby guiding the ESD optimal design. To date, model testing in combination with CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) is commonly accepted as the most effective way for ESD design assessment and enhancement.

This paper further extended the authors' previous study of propeller energy-loss reutilization for a full form ship, *Lee et al. (2012)*. In the previous study, a CFD model was validated using the model testing data. With the confidence of CFD simulation accuracy, a CFD-based control volume energy-loss analysis was performed to evaluate the performance of a four-blade propeller in the behind-ship condition based on the information of energy-loss components, including kinetic energy of axial jet, rotational cross-flow and friction loss. In the present paper, this CFD-based approach was applied to study the energy-saving performance of a selected ESD design, i.e., pre-swirl stators with four asymmetric fins installed on the ship stern in front of the propeller. CFD simulations with and without the ESD were performed under the model scale condition. Each energy-loss component for both cases was calculated for a quantitative comparison. To confirm propeller cavitation and propeller-induced hull pressure are well-controlled with no propeller-induced hull vibration risk, propeller cavitation and cavitation-induced hull pressure which may trigger vibrations were investigated. And the results were compared between the cases with and without ESD.

2. Methodology

2.1. CFD numerical method

The CFD simulations were performed using the level-set Finite-Analytic Navier-Stokes (FANS) numerical method of *Chen and Yu (2009)*. The FANS method solves the continuity and Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations for incompressible flow in a curvilinear body-fitted coordinate system. The governing equations are discretized using the finite-analytic method, *Chen and Chen (1998)*, *Chen et al. (1990)*, on a non-staggered grid and solved by the hybrid PISO/SIMPLER algorithm, *Chen and Korpus (1993)*. Turbulence was modelled all the way to the sub-layer

region near the solid wall boundary by employing the two-layer turbulent model of *Chen and Patel (1988)*, which solves the one-equation k - ϵ model in the near-wall region and standard k - ϵ model outside of the near-wall region.

The level-set FANS method employs the overset grid approach, *Chen (2009)*. In this approach, the entire computational domain is composed of separate structural overlapping grid blocks. The overset grid approach can easily generate good quality grids for complex configurations such as the ship hull and propeller and facilitate large body motion simulation such as a rotating propeller in this study.

2.2. Energy-loss analysis

Propeller energy-loss analysis in this study is based on the first law of thermodynamics, i.e., the change in energy of the system (dE) is the sum of the work done and heat exchange in the system, *White (2005)*,

$$dE = dW + dQ_h \quad (1)$$

dW is the work done on the system; dQ_h the heat exchange. For a moving system, e.g., flowing fluids, system energy E includes the internal energy, kinetic energy, and potential energy (i.e., $E = e + 1/2V^2 - \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{r}$). Mechanical work W includes the work done on the boundaries due to normal and shear stresses and any shaft work added to the system ($W = W_{normal\ stress} + W_{shear\ stress} + W_{shaft}$). Eq.(1) can be rewritten using the Reynolds transport theorem as follows:

$$\frac{dW}{dt} + \frac{dQ_h}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \int_{CV} (e + 1/2\mathbf{v}^2 - \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{r}) dV + \int_{CS} \rho (e + 1/2\mathbf{v}^2 - \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{v} \cdot d\mathbf{A} \quad (2)$$

For the present study, a control volume (system) for the analysis was defined by a fixed cylinder as shown in Fig.1. The system was assumed adiabatic and isothermal, i.e., $dQ_h/dt=0$ and $e=0$. The work of shear stress on the control surfaces, $W_{shear\ stress}$, can be reasonably neglected when the inlet and outlet flows are approximately uniform and parallel. The net potential energy was negligible in the study case. Therefore, a quasi-steady (i.e., flow is assumed steady during a discrete time period so d/dt term vanishes) energy balance equation can be written as,

$$\frac{dW_{shaft}}{dt} = \int_{CS} \rho \left(-\frac{p}{\rho} + 1/2\mathbf{v}^2 \right) \cdot \mathbf{v} \cdot d\mathbf{A} \quad (3)$$

p is the pressure. From the x -momentum conservation of the control volume, the pressure force acting on the inlet and outlet can be expressed as,

$$\int_{CS} p d\mathbf{A} = -T + \int_{CS} \rho(\mathbf{v}) \cdot \mathbf{v} \cdot d\mathbf{A} \quad (4)$$

T is the propeller thrust. Combining Eqs.(3) and (4), the energy balance equation used in the analysis can be obtained,

$$Q\omega = TV_a - \int_{CS} (1/2 \rho \mathbf{v}^2) \cdot \mathbf{v} \cdot d\mathbf{A} - \dot{W}_{ns,lateral} - \Delta \dot{E}_{frictional} \quad (5)$$

Q is the propeller torque, ω the propeller rotating speed, and V_a the advance velocity. The left-hand-side term of Eq. (5) is the shaft power; on the right hand side, the first and second terms are the rate of usable energy to propel the ship and the net flow rate of kinetic energy across control surfaces,

respectively. The third term, $\dot{W}_{ns,lateral}$, is the rate of work done by the normal stress on the lateral control surface of the control volume. The last term, $\dot{E}_{frictional}$, denotes the rate of frictional energy loss on propeller blades and surrounding fluids.

Fig. 1: Sketch of the control volume for the energy-loss analysis

3. Full form ship case study

3.1. Simulation scenarios

The full form ship in this study is a Capesize bulk carrier with 287.4 m L_{pp} (length between perpendiculars) equipped with a four-blade propeller. The propeller diameter is 8.4 m. This bulk carrier has a design speed of 15.2 knots and propeller rotating speed of 83.1 rpm. Under this operating condition, the draught and waterline breadth are 16.5 m and 45 m, respectively.

This paper continues the study by *Lee et al. (2012)*. In *Lee et al. (2012)*, three important validation cases including the bare hull resistance, open water propeller, and propeller/hull interaction cases were presented. In the present study, we focused on the comparison of propeller performance between the conditions with and without ESD.

Two simulation scenarios were conducted in the model scale condition (1:39.45). The first scenario is the propeller/hull interaction case (hereafter abbreviated to as “without ESD case”). The self-propulsion point was modelled under the ship speed of 1.245 m/s with a propeller rotating speed (n) of 8.06 rps. To overcome the difference in ship friction resistance coefficient between model scale and full scale, a towing force of 19.67 N was added to the model ship. For the second scenario, an energy-saving device (ESD) was added to simulate the propeller/hull/ESD interaction (hereafter abbreviated to as “with ESD case”). The ESD selected in this study was pre-swirl stators (PSS), which are four fins installed in front of the propeller. The self-propulsion point for the second scenario at the design ship speed was also simulated. The added towing force was the same as the first scenario because the increase in surface area from PSS is negligibly small, i.e., 0.07% of the total ship wetted surface area. For both scenarios, bare hull resistance was also modelled without the operating propeller. The numerical time increment of $1/(60n)$ was used for all simulations.

The simulated results at the model scale were further extrapolated to full scale for the evaluation of propeller performance for the cases with and without ESD.

3.2. CFD grid system and boundary conditions

The CFD mesh for the hull was generated based on the IGES geometry data. The propeller geometry was assumed as the Wageningen B-screw propeller geometry as the actual propeller geometry information is not available. More details of the propeller geometry determination were discussed in *Lee et al. (2012)*.

The computational domain was set with a length of 2.5 ship length (L), a width of 12 ship width (B) and a height of 10 ship draught (T), Fig.2(a). Along the longitudinal direction of ship length, the distance from the bow to the upstream inlet boundary is $0.5L$ and from the stern to the outflow boundary is L . In this study, free surface was not included; the top boundary of the domain was set at the still waterline plane. Fine cylindrical grids were used around the propeller in order to capture the detailed flows generated by the propeller, Fig.2(b). The computational domain was decomposed into separate structural grid blocks. For the case without ESD, there were 36 grid blocks with 10,169,403 grid cells. For the case with ESD, there were 52 grid blocks with 11,203,691 grid cells. Fig.3 displays the mesh around propeller for the case with ESD. Meshes for the bare hull cases were obtained simply by taking out the grid blocks of propeller from the meshes with the propeller.

There are five boundary conditions applied. On the top boundary, the still water surface was treated as a symmetric plane. No-slip boundary condition was applied on the hull and propeller blade surface. On the bottom and side boundaries, a slip boundary condition was used. At the upstream inlet, a uniform flow (U_0) with the model ship speed 1.245 m/s in negative x-direction was employed. The downstream outlet was the outflow boundary condition.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2: Meshes for the CFD simulations, (a) Computational domain, (b) detailed mesh in the stern region and around the propeller

Fig. 3: Mesh for the propeller/hull/ESD interaction simulation, (a) side view, and (b) aft view

3.3. CFD simulation results

3.3.1. Hull pressure and resistance

Table I summarizes the measured and simulated resistance and resistance coefficients at model scale condition. Model test data are available for the case without ESD. For the case without ESD, the total resistance coefficient, C_T , based on the simulation results is 3.755×10^{-3} which agrees well with the C_T obtained from the model test, i.e., 3.814×10^{-3} . The discrepancy between the measured and simulated C_T is about -1.5% . The under-prediction of C_T can be due to the omission of the free surface effects in the simulation. Fig.4 displays the distribution of hydrodynamic pressure coefficient, C_p , i.e., $p/(0.5\rho U_0^2)$, on the hull surface from the simulation without ESD. From the fore view, the maximum C_p of 0.972 is identified around the stagnation point at the bow along with the local low pressures at the bottom of the bow. In the middle of ship body, the pressure gradient was small. In the stern region, the pressure recovery was about 20% of the pressure at the bow.

As shown in Table I, for the case with ESD, the simulated bare hull resistance was 38.86 N, which increased by 4% compared to the case without ESD. The ESD itself creates resistance, contributing about 1.5% (out of 4%) of the resistance increase, Fig.5(a). The results show that the resistance on the hull surface (excluding the resistance on the wetted surface of the ESD) also increased by about 2.5% (out of 4%), suggesting the hull/ESD interaction reduced the hull efficiency. Fig.5(b) shows the axial velocity distribution around the ESD fins. Local faster (slower) velocity appeared at the upper (lower) side of the fins. With a rotating propeller behind the ship, the simulated hull resistance was 42.95 N, which increased by 2% compared to the case without ESD. There was no significant difference in the hull pressure distribution between the cases with and without ESD. The total resistance coefficient for the case with ESD is 3.938×10^{-3} . Note that when the ESD was included for the propeller/hull interaction simulation, the propeller rotating speed had to be adjusted to reach the self-propulsion point, i.e., 7.90 rps.

In Table I, the frictional resistance coefficients were calculated based on the 1957 ITTC-Line,

$$C_F = \frac{0.075}{(\log Rn - 2)^2} \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

Rn is the Reynolds number. The residuary resistance coefficient is obtained by subtracting C_F from C_T .

Table I: Summary of resistance from model tests and CFD simulations (Model scale)

	RT,m [N]	n [1/s]	R,m [N]	CT,m	CF,m [*1000]	CR,m
Model test ¹	37.64	8.06	42.74	3.814	3.056	0.728
without ESD	37.25	8.06	42.04	3.775	3.056	0.719
with ESD	38.86	7.90	42.95	3.938	3.056	0.882

RT,m: bare-hull resistance

n: propeller rotating speed

R,m: total resistance

¹ In the model test, the ESD was not included

CT,m: total resistance coefficient

CF,m: frictional resistance coefficient

CR,m: residuary resistance coefficient

Fig. 4: Hydrodynamic pressure coefficient C_p on hull from case without ESD, (a) fore view, (b) aft view. Contour is labeled by the dynamic pressure coefficient. Dotted contour lines are for negative C_p values.

Fig. 5: (a) Normalized hydrodynamic pressure on ESD, (b) normalized axial velocity around ESD

3.3.1. Propeller loading and efficiencies

Fig.6 displays the pressure distribution on the propeller blades behind the ship without and with ESD. As shown, the pressure distribution is not identical on each blade owing to the non-uniform ship wake in front of the propeller. It is noted that the blade load is higher when the blade rotates to the starboard

side for both cases. The higher load on the starboard side is the result of the larger angle of attack, *Lee et al. (2012)*. Besides, by comparing the suction pressure on Blade #4 (on the port side) between the cases with and without ESD, the suction pressure in the case with ESD is clearly lower, resulting in a higher propeller load on the port side. This suggests that the ESD (i.e., three pre-swirl stator fins) installed on the port side in front of the propeller improved the propeller inflow. Fig.7 shows the velocity distributions of propeller inflow without and with ESD. The tangential component of the cross flow on the port side was reduced in the case with ESD. As discussed in *Lee et al. (2012)*, the reduced cross flow on the port side provides a greater angle of attack, and thus the propeller load increases. Based on the CFD results, the propeller load from the case with ESD is more balanced between the starboard and port side compared to the case without ESD.

Fig.6: Pressure distributions on propeller blades from the simulations without and with ESD. The numbers denote the blades.

Table II summarizes propeller loading, resistance coefficients and efficiencies from the model test and CFD simulation results. For the case without ESD, the discrepancy in propeller loading between model test and CFD can be due to the use of the equivalent propeller geometry (not the actual propeller tested in the model test). However, the comparison between the CFD cases with and without ESD is important because the main objective of this study is to investigate the effects of ESD on the propulsion performance. The full-scale resistance coefficients were determined based on the model-scale resistance coefficients under the assumptions of the Froude Method. The residuary resistance coefficients are the same between the model scale and full scale because the Froude number is kept the same between the two scales, and the full-scale frictional resistance coefficient was determined by

using Eq.(6). Three efficiencies at full scale were calculated as listed in Table II. With ESD installed, the hull efficiency slightly decreased, and the behind efficiency increased by 1.84%. Overall, the propulsive efficiency ($=\eta_H \times \eta_B$) increased by 1.34%.

Fig.7: Axial velocity contour and cross-flow vector field on the plane of $0.15D$ in front of the propeller. D is the propeller diameter.

Table II: Summary of the propeller loading, resistance coefficients, and efficiencies based on the model test and CFD simulation results.

	Model scale						Full scale				
	n	T,m	Q,m	CR	CF	CT	RT	T	η_H	η_B	η_D
	[1/s]	[N]	[mN]		[*1.0E3]		[kN]	[kN]			
Model test ¹	8.06	23.07	0.6062	0.728	1.414	1.790	1130	1476	1.228	0.583	0.716
without ESD	8.06	21.34	0.6947	0.719	1.414	1.781	1098	1346	1.096	0.563	0.616
with ESD	7.90	24.46	0.7635	0.882	1.414	1.944	1198	1543	1.090	0.573	0.625

n: propeller rotating speed

T,m: propeller thrust at model scale

Q,m: propeller torque at model scale

CR: residuary resistance coefficient

CF: frictional resistance coefficient

CT: total resistance coefficient

¹ In the model test, the ESD was not included

RT: total resistance

T: propeller thrust

η_H : hull efficiency

η_B : behind efficiency

η_D : propulsive efficiency

4. Propeller energy-loss analysis

The propeller energy-loss analysis was based on the simulated flow solutions. The control volume for the analysis was constructed by an inlet located at $0.15D$ in front of the propeller plane, an outlet located at $0.16D$ behind the propeller plane, and a lateral control surface (where D is the propeller diameter). In energy-loss analysis, Eq.(5) was used. Each term in Eq.(5) was calculated every 6 degrees for two revolutions. In Eq.(5), the kinetic energy $1/2\rho v^2$ was further decomposed into the axial kinetic energy $1/2\rho u^2$ and rotational kinetic energy $1/2\rho(u_i^2 + u_n^2)$ components in the calculation as follows:

$$\frac{1}{2} \rho \mathbf{v}^2 = \frac{1}{2} \rho (u^2 + u_t^2 + u_n^2) \quad (7)$$

u is the velocity in the axial direction; u_t and u_n are the velocity components of the cross-flow in the tangential and radial directions with respect to the propeller rotating center. With the knowledge of the shaft power, usable power and the change rate of kinetic energy, the change rate of frictional loss can be determined using the energy conservation, i.e., Eq.(5).

Fig.8 shows the spatial distributions of the axial and rotational kinetic energy at $x=-0.15D$ (i.e., inlet of the control volume) and $x=0.16D$ (i.e., outlet of the control volume). In the case without ESD as shown in Fig.8 (a), the distribution of the axial kinetic energy at $x=-0.15D$ is quite symmetric to the central plane. There was only a limited part of the blade rotating over the upper boundary layer at 12 o'clock. The rotational kinetic energy at $x=-0.15D$ has a much smaller magnitude than the axial kinetic energy, and its distribution is also quite symmetric. At $x=0.16D$, the axial kinetic energy behind the propeller was more concentrated on the starboard side which agrees with the higher propeller load on the starboard side, Fig.6. On the other hand, the rotational kinetic energy behind the propeller was more concentrated on the port side except for the top region where the flow was affected by the rudder behind. For the case with ESD as shown in Fig.8 (b), the distributions of both axial and rotational kinetic energy in front of the propeller (at $x=-0.15D$) were affected by the ESD, especially on the port side where there were three pre-swirl stators installed.

(a) Without ESD

(b) With ESD

Fig. 8: Axial kinetic energy from simulations without and with ESD at $x=-0.15D$ (inlet of control volume), and $x=0.16D$ (outlet of control volume), where D denotes the propeller diameter. Note that there are two different color maps for the axial and rotational kinetic energy and numbers denote the blades.

Fig.9 shows the change rate of each energy component relative to the shaft power ($Q\omega$) for the time period of two rotations. Each energy component oscillates at the first blade rate frequency of the four-bladed propeller, i.e., four times over one rotation. Higher blade rate frequency components are also observed in the time series of the usable power and frictional energy loss, Fig.8 (a) and (d).

Fig. 9: Time series of the (a) usable energy, and the propeller energy loss due to the (b) axial kinetic energy, (c) rotational kinetic energy, and (d) frictional loss. Note that the values are the percentage compared to the shaft power, i.e., $Q\omega$, the thin blue line is the case without ESD and the thick pick line is the case with ESD.

Table III summarizes the mean change rate of each energy component relative to the shaft power. For the case without ESD, the mean usable energy for propulsion from propeller is 56.24%. The primary propeller energy loss is due to the axial kinetic energy gain (19.41%) and friction (17.18%) in the surrounding fluid from the propeller action. The tangential kinetic energy loss is 6.94%, and the radial kinetic energy loss is small (0.23%), resulting in the total rotational loss of 7.17%. With ESD, the axial energy loss decreased by 1.32%; the rotational kinetic energy loss decreased by 2.92%; and the usable energy increased by 1.08%. From the analysis, the studied ESD design has more pronounced effect on the tangential kinetic energy loss reduction.

Table III: Mean change rate of each energy component in the control volume.

Note that values are percentages of each energy components relative to shaft power $Q\omega$

	Usable	Axial KE	Rotational KE			Frictional
			Radial	Tangential	Total	
Without ESD	56.24%	19.41%	0.23%	6.94%	7.17%	17.18%
With ESD	57.32%	18.09%	-0.62%	4.87%	4.25%	20.39%
Difference	1.08%	-1.32%	-0.85%	-2.07%	-2.92%	3.21%

5. Propeller cavitation and strength analysis

5.1. Cavitation analysis

Propeller cavitation analysis was performed using the MPUF-3A and GBFLOW programs. MPUF3A was originally developed based on the vortex-lattice method (VLM) at Massachusetts Institute of Technology, *Kerwin and Lee (1978)*, *Greeley and Kerwin (1982)*, and further developed at the University of Texas, *Lee and Kinnas (2001)*. MPUF3A calculates the propeller load and cavity patterns. GBFLOW is an Euler solver for propeller/wake interaction (effective wake) prediction based

on a finite volume method, *He and Kinnas (2010)*. Fig.10 shows the algorithm for the analysis. The preWKProc and WKProc are for converting the CFD simulated nominal wake to the input format for MPUF3A calculations. MPUF3A and GBFLOW run iteratively until convergence is reached.

Fig.11 shows the cavity pattern on the suction side of the blade for the cases without ESD and with ESD. Without ESD, the cavitation appeared in a limited area and was slightly wider on the starboard side. For the case with ESD, the cavitation enhanced and clearly shifted toward the port side where there were three ESD fins installed. The enhanced cavitation is because of the greater propeller load resulting from the greater angle of attack of propeller inflow when the ESD fins were present. Overall, the cavitation was not significant for both cases.

Fig.10: Flow chart of propeller cavitation analysis

Fig.11: Cavity pattern on the suction side for the cases (a) without ESD, and (2) with ESD

5.2. Cavitation-induced hull pressure

The cavitation-induced hull pressure was computed using the HULL Field Point Potential (HULL-FPP) program, *Chang and Kinnas (2010)*. The cavity calculated by MPUF3A was used as the input excitation sources in HULLFPP calculations. For the present study, there were 2072 panels used to describe the hull geometry (stern part only). Fig. 12 demonstrates the contours of the first blade rate cavitation-induced hull pressure for the cases without and with ESD. For both cases, the pressure distributions were consistent with the cavity patterns. Without ESD, the predicted pressure is slightly greater on the starboard side and the maximum hull pressure amplitude is 0.98 kPa. With ESD, the predicted pressure is clearly higher on the port side with the maximum amplitude of 1.23 kPa. The results suggest that the propeller-induced hull pressure was not significant and the risk for propeller-induced vibration was low.

Fig.12: Cavitation-induced hull pressure (1st harmonic) for the cases without and with ESD

6. Closing remarks

The shipping industry is eagerly looking for more efficient energy-saving propulsion to save costs and reduce pollution. Energy-saving devices have been recognized as an effective measure. In this paper, a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD)-based energy-loss analysis methodology was applied to evaluate a selected ESD design, i.e., pre-swirl stators, installed on a Capesize bulk carrier.

Based on the CFD results, the studied ESD improved the propeller inflow on the port side where three stators were located. Those stators adjusted the cross-flow and increased the angle of the attack, resulting in an increased propeller load on the port side compared to the case without ESD. In addition, the propeller load was more balanced with the ESD installed. The ESD reduced the axial and rotational kinetic energy loss by 1.32% and 2.92%, respectively. The studied ESD design has a more pronounced effect on the reduction of tangential kinetic energy loss. Overall, the propulsive efficiency was improved by 1.34% with the ESD installed.

The propeller cavitation analysis shows that the cavitation enhanced when the ESD fins were present. However, for both cases (with and without ESD), the cavitation and propeller-induced hull pressure was not significant and the risk for propeller-induced vibration was low.

The CFD-based energy-loss analysis approach provides detailed information of velocity and energy flow around the propeller and ESDs in both the temporal and spatial domain, which is usually very difficult and expensive to measure in the model tests. The detailed information from CFD simulation also allows a better understanding of the working mechanics of ESDs. This paper has demonstrated

the ability of the CFD-based energy-loss analysis approach in evaluating the performance of energy-saving devices and the potential for ESD design.

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CFD Virtual Model Basin Development for Offshore Applications

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Abstract

A CFD Virtual Model Basin has been developed and is capable of analyzing complex offshore hydrodynamic problems. This virtual basin brings about a collection of state-of-the-art CFD techniques to provide a platform that is practical for advanced offshore engineering problems. Currently this CFD Virtual Model Basin has been applied in many offshore applications in ABS. This paper presents some selected applications of the Virtual Model Basin.

1. Background and motivation

Driven by declining continental shelf reserves and increasing oil demand, offshore exploration and production has been progressing to deep water and ultra-deep water. In deep water and ultra-deep water locations, harsh environments with high waves and strong currents normally are prevalent. One of the major challenges faced when designing floating systems for ultra-deep water is predicting the environmental loads and the induced global response for the combined system of the floater, risers and moorings. In current practices, the process of optimization, parametric studies, etc. to evaluate design options, remains in the domain of numerical simulation. Physical model tests in a model basin serve more as a final verification. While a host of analytical tools has been developed over the last three decades to serve the offshore engineering community, these tools are based largely on potential flow theory for simplicity and manageability. Tools based on this theory ignore or approximate real-life fluid-flow phenomena such as violent free surface phenomenon, viscous effects and turbulence. It is well recognized that such approaches increase the margin of error.

The primary objective of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Virtual Model Basin is to develop a CFD-based numerical simulation facility for solving complex offshore engineering problems using first principle analytical methods. In this virtual model basin, the techniques being introduced include the following: level-set module for violent free surface simulation, overset grid numerical technique for offshore floater large amplitude motion, fully nonlinear wave generator for rough sea situations and six-degree-of-freedom large motion capability.

When used together, these techniques provide a practical analysis tool to handle real world engineering applications. This paper presents some applications of the virtual model basin capabilities. They include studies on jack-up leg hydrodynamic loads due to currents and waves, deep draft semi-submersible Vortex Induced Motion (VIM) and wave impact load prediction on a semisubmersible under highly nonlinear waves, and green water loads on offshore platforms due to short-crested random waves under extreme hurricane conditions. Through these simulation cases, the current technical capabilities of the CFD Virtual Model Basin are demonstrated for complex offshore problems. While CFD can boast many successful applications, it is still a developing technology. Selected experimental data remains necessary to validate CFD results for these new applications if they are to gain a following.

2. CFD methodology in Virtual Model Basin

In essence, CFD is based on a mathematical model known as Navier-Stokes (NS) equations, by which the physics related to fluid viscosity can be represented. The CFD Virtual Model Basin introduces specific techniques and software to provide capability to simulate and analyze complex offshore

problems. The techniques being introduced include numerical methods based on Finite Analytic Navier-Stokes (FANS) method, viscous-inviscid coupling technique, overset grid technique, level set technique and wave generator. Each of these techniques is further described as follows:

As the solver of the CFD Virtual Model Basin, FANS uses finite analytic method for solving the Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations for turbulent flows. In FANS, in each discretized element, the finite analytic method is used to solve the local governing RANS equations. The solution thus satisfies the physics of the local flow conditions, and it holds true regardless of aspect ratio or distortion in element shape. Further, finite analytic method is capable of automatically adjusting discretized solution based on flow conditions. As a result, FANS formulation is very robust and can handle a very high Reynolds number with a very large element aspect ratio, *Pontaza et al. (2005)*.

Since a turbulence model is introduced into the governing equations, it is critical to choose an appropriate turbulence model for certain applications. RANS equations are used along with turbulent models such as $k-\epsilon$, $k-\omega$, or Reynolds stress models to simulate turbulent flow. RANS equations are a time-averaged form of NS equations after Reynolds Averaging Process. Moreover, the Large Eddy Simulation (LES) module has also been developed in the CFD Virtual Model Basin.

Typically, numerical wave tanks apply either pure potential flow model or pure RANS model. Usually, RANS simulations take much more CPU time than potential flow simulations. In a very large domain containing a marine structure, the use of RANS simulations alone would be too time-consuming, while the use of potential flow simulation alone would not be representative of the actual flow near the marine structure. A hybrid method employing viscous-inviscid coupling method can take account of both viscous flow near the marine structure and nonlinear wave effects in the far field. In this approach, the potential flow calculation takes care of the wave propagation from the far field while the RANS method calculates turbulent boundary and wake flows around marine structure. The viscous-inviscid interaction between the potential flow and RANS region is taken care of through a direct matching of the velocity and pressure fields in an overlapped RANS and potential flow computational region, *Chen and Lee (1996)*. This methodology improves largely the calculation efficiency and cuts down the computational time.

An overset grid module, *Chen (2009)*, has been developed as a grid generation software tool using overlapping, embedding and matching grid blocks to facilitate the simulation of flow around any complex configuration of disparate bodies. Each grid block can move freely in the fluid domain. The overset grid system is used to account for relative motions among various moving bodies, for example, solving propeller/hull interaction problems under seaway wave conditions, *Lee et al. (2010)*. The use of this module also can alleviate the difficulty of structural grid generation for complex geometrical configuration.

An interface capturing module using the Level Set method has been developed for simulating violent free surface such as wave breaking, spray, two-phase flow, etc., *Chen and Yu (2006,2009)*. In addition to interface-capturing between two different fluids, this module is also the basis for wave generation module. Benchmark testing has been done for the sloshing phenomenon in LNG tanks of LNG ships, *Chen (2011a)*. The CFD simulation captures the impact pressures in very good agreement with experimental data.

Both regular and irregular wave modules have been developed in this Virtual Model Basin. In regular waves simulation both linear wave generator based on linear wave theory and the fully nonlinear wave generator based on Finite Amplitude Wave Theory (FAWT) applicable for deep and shallow water are available. For irregular wave generation, a directional wave simulation (DWS) module is developed for simulating the extreme waves especially under the harsh environment, such as hurricane. Besides the capabilities of the surface waves generation mentioned above, a module for generating the internal solitary wave (ISW) has been developed, in which the nonlinear internal solitary wave can be generated with specified properties.

In the Virtual Model Basin package, the FANS solver is designed to have the flexibility to plug in any CFD module that may be developed in the future. And for each of the CFD modules, the stand-alone feature is maintained to allow them to link with other CFD solvers. Currently, the CFD Virtual Model Basin has been in service for offshore and marine applications. In the following some selected offshore applications using the CFD Virtual Model Basin are reported.

3.1. Jack-up leg hydrodynamic load prediction

In jack-up structure and foundation designs, the accurate prediction of drag and wave forces is important but difficult. Historically, hydrodynamic loads on jack-up legs have been estimated based on wind tunnel measurements. Wind tunnel tests can account for steady current situations but experience more difficulty for other complex flow situations (such as oscillatory waves). However, by using the CFD Virtual Basin that has been developed, it has become possible, at a relative modest cost, to predict the hydrodynamic loads on jack-up legs due to current, ocean surface waves and internal waves.

3.1.1. Hydrodynamic load due to current and waves

In jack-up leg hydrodynamic application, a truss-type jack-up leg is selected which is composed of repeated bay units in the vertical direction. As shown in Fig. 1, in each bay unit the structure consists of three chords and 12 tubular components, i.e., nine bracings and three span breakers. For the three chords, each of them is composed of repeated chord units in vertical direction (25 chord units for a single chord in a bay unit). To validate the accuracy of the Virtual Model Basin, a CFD study of a single chord unit was done in the past, *Lee et al. (2010)*. In this paper, only the CFD simulation for a bay unit under pure current and current plus wave cases will be reported. In order to reduce the computational cost, when calculating the loadings of the bracings, including 12 tubular members, on the bay unit, the Morison equation method is applied. CFD-based hydrodynamic load calculation is performed only to the three chords. For implementing the methodology described above, a house-hold tool is developed for the calculation of the total force on the cylindrical components in the flow field. The total force includes drag force, inertia force and friction force.

Fig. 1: A bay unit for a jack-up leg: configuration (left); the definition of incident flow angle (right)

A uniform flow passing a jack-up bay unit with different incident angles, Fig.1, was simulated and compared with wind tunnel measurement data. An overset grid system is adopted, Fig.2, for the current study. The system consists of three O-type blocks to enclose the three chords and three Cartesian small blocks to be located in the near field of the chords, and one large Cartesian block to cover the far field of the computational domain. Totally, there are seven grid blocks with grid points around 9.6 million. In CFD simulations, the seven grid blocks are distributed individually in seven CPU processors for paralleling computation.

For the total hydrodynamic force acting on the individual chord, simulation results shown in Fig. 3 display the time histories of the total forces under various incident flow angles on the three chords of the bay unit. The time history for the case of 30° is special since the force is oscillating with larger amplitude value compared to other incident angle cases although its mean force value is smaller compared to others. In fact, the small mean force for 30° case can be explained according to the

blocking effect. As noted, for 30° incident flow condition the downstream chord is in the wake of the upstream chord, Fig.4 (right). For the large oscillation amplitude it is a special phenomenon caused by the resonance of shedding vortex frequency between the upstream chord and the downstream chord. To have a general idea of the flow field is important as the flow field around the chord is substantial and critical for the hydrodynamic force exerted on the jack-up leg. Fig. 4 plots the U-contours of the flow field under two typical conditions (incident flow angles are 0° and 30°). The flow is fully-developed turbulent flow with strong vortex shedding.

Fig. 2: Grid system for bay unit

Fig. 3: The time histories of the total forces under various incident flow angles

Fig. 4: The flow field (U contour) under 2 typical incident flow angles: 0 (left) and 30 degree (right)

In sea operating condition, the jack-up legs are subjected to wave and current forces simultaneously. The loadings of the oscillating forces due to waves are of central concern to the designer. In this CFD study, a simplified uniform oscillating flow is used to approximate the small amplitude wave effect. For the incident flow angles 30°, the flow field and dynamic pressure distributions are displayed in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. Due to the existence of the current, the maximum magnitudes of the water particle velocities are not the same in two opposite directions. It can be observed that the evolution of

the flow field and pressure distribution is not symmetric in one wave cycle, and the shedding effects are also not developed in the same level.

Fig. 5: Velocity U contours for a bay unit (incident flow angle = 30°)

Fig. 6: Dynamic pressure distribution for a bay unit (incident flow angle = 30°)

The asymmetric feature is also shown in the time histories of loadings. Fig.7 demonstrates the loadings on three chords obtained from CFD simulations. Due to the existence of the current, the time histories exhibit an asymmetric pattern. In Fig.7, the total loadings on the leg which include the loadings in the bracing members are also calculated using CFD combined Morison equation method as mentioned earlier. In comparison with the method of SNAME 5-5A, the loadings on bracings, chords and total loading are also shown in Fig.7. It can be observed that the asymmetric properties of the loadings in a wave period exist, and the loadings calculated using the CFD combined Morison equation method agree with the SNAME results reasonably.

Fig. 7: Loadings on bracings and chords and total loadings on bay unit compared with results obtained using SNAME: (a) Incident flow angle = 0° , and (b) Incident flow angle = 30°

3.1.2. Internal wave effect on jack-up legs

It has been reported many times that due to the activities of the internal waves in certain sea areas, the offshore exploration and drilling operations were disrupted. With the jack-up leg configuration selected as before, the investigation of the internal wave loading on jack-up legs has been performed using the Virtual Model Basin developed. Systematic parametric studies were carried out to find out the dependence between the hydrodynamic load and internal wave amplitude under different incident wave directions, *Lee and Yan (2012)*. In the CFD study, an overset grid system with nine grid blocks is adopted, Fig.8. The system consists of three blocks to enclose the three chords and six other blocks to cover the far field for background flow. The background domain is long enough compared with the solitary wave length scale so the solitary wave can thoroughly pass through the jack-up leg structure. The total number of the grid points used is about 4.62 million. For efficient computation, the nine blocks are distributed in eight CPU processors for parallel computations.

Fig. 8: Section of the overset grid system for CFD computation (left: top view) and the background grid blocks only showing the edges (right: perspective view)

For the simulation of the internal solitary wave, a two-layer ocean model is adopted and the KdV theory is used for describing the solitary wave passing through the jack-up leg, *Osborne and Burch (1980)*. Numerically, the internal solitary wave will be generated by inserting the analytical solution into a two-layer CFD domain as the initial condition. For the top and bottom boundaries, the boundary conditions can be treated using the rigid-lid approximation approach i.e., using slip boundary condition ($w=0$). The rigid-lid approximation is an appropriate treatment for interfacial waves in an ocean, *Sutherland (2010)*.

In this CFD based internal wave load study, three internal wave conditions are considered namely small amplitude (10 m), medium amplitude (20 m) and large amplitude (30 m). For modeling the two-layer ocean, we set the upper layer thickness $h_1 = 25$ m, and the lower layer thickness $h_2 = 75$ m. The

densities in the upper and lower layers are 1000kg/m^3 (for fresh water) and 1025kg/m^3 (for sea water). CFD simulations are performed for two wave incident angles, 0 and 30° , in this study. When an internal solitary wave is passing through a jack-up leg, the interfacial free surface will be disturbed by the structure around the jack-up chords. Fig. 9 displays the solitary wave interfaces for the cases with various wave amplitudes (10 m, 20 m and 30 m) for the 0° wave incident angle case at the instance when the solitary wave trough reaches the jack-up leg.

Fig. 9: Internal solitary wave interfacial free surfaces around the jack-up leg for various solitary wave amplitudes ((a) 10 m, (b) 20 m, and (c) 30 m under incident flow angle = 0°)

In a typical solitary wave system, the horizontal velocities in the lower layer are opposite in direction to those in the upper layer. Meanwhile, the vertical velocity magnitudes are much smaller in comparison with the horizontal ones. Hence horizontal velocity (U component) contour plot is representative to demonstrate the velocity fields under various internal solitary wave scenarios. For the incident flow angle 30° , Fig.10 shows the side view and top view of the U component contours. To have a clear vision of the flow field around the jack-up chords due to blockage effect, the side view plane is selected for the location passing through the centers of the upstream and downstream chords. The vortex shedding behind the downstream chord is stronger due to the resonance effect between the upstream wake and the downstream wake. For the lower layer, due to the small magnitudes of the velocities, no vortex shedding occurs even for the large amplitude scenarios.

Fig. 10: U contour for solitary wave amplitude = 30m, left: side view; right: top view ($\theta=30^\circ$)

Fig. 11: Perspective view of solitary wave profile (the transparent surface) and U component contour for solitary wave amplitude = 30m (left: $\theta=0^\circ$; right: $\theta=30^\circ$)

Fig.11 shows the flow field at different horizontal planes and the profiles of the internal solitary waves (the transparent surfaces). As seen, the vortex shedding is fully developed in the upper layers, while no shedding occurs in the lower layers.

3.2. Deep draft semi Vortex Induced Motion

Offshore structures such as columns, risers, and pipelines may experience vortex induced motion (VIM) under current and wave conditions, especially when the vortex shedding frequency is close to natural frequency of the structure. As it is well known, VIM is an important source of fatigue damage accumulation. Generally, model tests are a practical method to observe this phenomenon. The VIM of Spar or mono-column is always an important study when dealing with fatigue life analysis, *van Dijk et al. (2003)*. Due to the efficiency improvements of software and hardware, the researches of VIM investigation have been shifted from mono-column to multi-column recently, *Waals et al. (2007)*, *Rijken and Leverette (2008)*, *Kim et al. (2011)*. Using the Virtual Model Basin that has been developed, CFD simulations are performed to study the VIM phenomenon.

In this study, the Semi configuration is based on the paper from *Waals et al. (2007)*. Because all towing tests were done in stable current conditions without the presence of waves, the free surface effect was ignored in the simulation. Only surge, sway and yaw motions were considered and natural periods for the corresponding motions were 12 s, 12 s and 7 s, respectively. The results of VIM response are analyzed by Eq.(1), where σ = standard deviation of $Y(t)$:

$$\text{nominal response : } \left(\frac{A}{D} \right)_{\text{nominal}} = \frac{\sqrt{2} \times \sigma(Y(t))}{D} \tag{1}$$

A lock-in condition example for $U_r = 7$ in 45° is demonstrated in Fig.12. The shedding period is about 12 s, which is close to the natural period. On the other hand, a post lock-in condition can be observed in Fig.13. The motion amplitude decreases and becomes random with the period shorter than 12 s. These results indicate that VIM phenomena can be captured well by the CFD Virtual Model Basin. Fig.14 presents a typical vorticity pattern behind the semi columns. As seen, the flow separates near the corners of columns and the flow pattern of the far right column is affected by the heading column.

Fig. 12: Y-Response for 45° , $U_r=7$

Fig. 13: Y-Response for 45° , $U_r=14$

Fig. 14: z-vorticity for 45° , $U_r=7$

Fig. 15: Nominal Y-response

Fig.15 presents the averaged motion amplitude, and the results are in good agreement with the model test results. For the 45° incidence, the lock-in condition occurs around $A/D \approx 0.3$ for $6 \leq U_r \leq 12$, and the post lock-in condition can be seen after $U_r > 12$. For the 0° incidence, A/D meets the maximum value for $U_r = 10$. This trend is similar to the experimental data. For yaw response, the vortex induced yaw motion (VIY) occurs when the shedding frequency close to the natural frequency of yaw, i.e. the higher current speed region in Fig.16. According to this, the reduced velocities are recalculated based on the natural frequency of yaw and plot again in Fig.17. As seen, for the 0° incidence, a typical VIY phenomenon can be observed around $6 \leq U_r \leq 8$. The VIY at 45° seems to be shifted due to the resonant behavior with transverse motion.

Fig. 16: Nominal yaw-response

Fig. 17: Nominal yaw-response ($U_r=U_{r,yaw}/D$)

3.3. Wave run-up and impact load on semi under highly nonlinear waves

In the real sea environment, safe and economic design of offshore structures will significantly depend on accurate prediction of representative wave loads. For semisubmersibles, the deck underside and the columns are often subjected to wave impact and slamming. Several experimental studies indicate that forces of wave impact could be two times higher than that of non-impact waves of comparable amplitudes. The corresponding impact pressure can be ten times higher than non-impact pressure. Therefore, a proper estimation of the wave run-up must go beyond the linear wave theory.

To validate the accuracy of the developed Virtual Model Basin for a wave/structure interaction problem, CFD simulations of the wave run-up along legs of a semisubmersible platform are performed and compared with experimental data and CFD results from *Iwanowski et al. (2009)*. The numerical sensors are monitored at the same locations as the experimental ones in Figs.18 and 19. The wave height is 20 m and wave period is 13 s, respectively. Numerical results for wave elevation of incoming wave, run-up on the 1st column and run-up of the 2nd column are plotted in Figs.20 to 22. The CFD results for the elevations are in reasonable agreement with the experimental measurements.

Fig. 18: Location of wave elevation probes

Fig. 19: Location of impact pressure sensors

Fig. 20: Incoming wave elevation comparison

Fig. 21: Wave elevation comparison, run-up on the 1st column

Fig. 22: Wave elevation comparison, run-up on the 2nd column

Fig. 23: Dynamic pressures comparison, bottom of the 1st column

The prediction of fluid dynamic pressure is quite important in the structure design stage. Figs. 23 to 25 show the simulation results of the impact pressure time histories at top, bottom and under-deck on the 1st column. The impact time decreases from bottom to under-deck during the period of wave run-up, and this trend is same as the experimental results. As shown in Fig. 23, the results agree very well with the measurements, except the pressure impact occurring around 20 s. This happens because the wave is still not fully developed at this moment. In general, all the impact pressures predicted by CFD Virtual Model Basin are in reasonable agreement with experimental measurements.

Fig. 24: Dynamic pressures comparison, top of the 1st column

Fig. 25: Dynamic pressures comparison, under-deck of the 1st column

3.4 Green water load on jack-up under hurricane wave

Simulations using the CFD Virtual Model Basin were performed for a simplified jack-up structure, Fig.26. In this typical jack-up unit, the structure consists of a buoyant triangular platform (hull) resting on three independent truss-work legs. Each jack-up leg component is usually designed with three cylindrical-shaped chords connected through bracing members, *Lee et al. (2009)*. Here, each jack-up leg is represented by three cylindrical piles, and the bracing trusses were not included in the simulations. The height of the jack-up hull is 8.5 m; the upper deck surface of the jack-up is 20 m above the calm-water surface. The primary objective of this study is to estimate the wave impact loads on the jack-up hull and topside structures under extreme storm wave conditions. For simplicity, five rectangular blocks were strategically placed on the platform deck to estimate the maximum impact loads resulting from hurricane waves. The dimensions of S1 is 18 m × 2 m × 5 m; blocks S2 and S3 are 23 m × 2 m × 5 m; block S4 is 41 m × 2 m × 5 m and the biggest block S5 is 20 m × 16 m × 10 m. These five rectangular structures provide a simple and effective way to estimate the wave impact pressure and horizontal forces for topside equipment at various locations on the jack-up deck. The size of the computational domain is 240 m × 240 m × 150 m, Fig.27, and the water depth is 100 m.

Fig. 26: Geometry of generic offshore platform

Fig. 27: Computational domain

Fig.28 shows the detailed overset grid system on the jack-up deck surface. Each cylindrical shaped chord of the jack-up leg is surrounded by a cylindrical grid block with self-overlap in the circumferential direction. The topside structures (S1, S2, S3 and S4) are covered by two overlapping grids with a self-overlapped O-type grid wrapping around each block and a rectangular grid covering the top surface. The biggest structure (S5) is covered by two C-type grids in the circumferential direction and two rectangular grids on the top and bottom surfaces. The horizontal grid spacing varies from 0.05 m around the jack-up legs to 1.5 m in the far field, while the vertical grid spacing varies from 0.5 m near the jack-up hull to 10 m adjacent to the ocean floor.

Fig. 28: Overset grids around jack-up structure

The present grid is slightly finer than those used earlier in Chen (2010, 2011b) for a fixed platform in a 121.92-m (400-ft) water depth. The overall grid consists of 43 computational blocks and a total of 5.93 million grid points.

In studies by *Chen (2010,2011b)*, numerical simulations were performed for a fixed offshore platform under monochromatic waves, and 2D long-crested waves as well as 3D short-crested waves. The simulation results demonstrated that the directional short-crested waves are capable of producing significantly higher impact pressure and wave loads than those generated by 2D long-crested waves with identical frequency spectrum and total energy. In the present study, one of the extreme wave events from a random 3D wave spectrum was chosen for random waves/structure interaction problem.

Fig.29 shows the directional wave spectra of Hurricane Katrina which is used in the present simulation of extreme wave impact loads on the jack-up structures. The spectral variance of the directional wave energy is expressed in terms of 23 wave frequencies and 17 wave directions. The directional wave simulation (DWS) program of *Huang and Zhang (2009)* is employed to compute the time history of the irregular waves analytically based on the linear wave theory. DWS provides the time histories of water surface elevation, the horizontal and vertical velocities and the dynamic pressure at any given location in the entire solution domain. The significant wave height of $H_s = 24$ m was considered in the present simulation.

Due to the large number of wave frequencies and wave directions, it is very time-consuming to perform full-domain DWS calculations over a sufficiently long duration. Fig. 30 shows the time history of free surface elevation at the center of jack-up structure. Therefore, the single-point DWS calculation allows us to quickly identify the extreme wave event at the center of jack-up structure. In the present study, Navier-Stokes simulations of wave impact loads on the jack-up structures have been performed for the extreme wave which has the maximum crest height 26.7 m. After identifying the exact time of occurrence of the maximum wave crest elevation for the extreme wave event at the jack-up center, full-domain DWS and FANS simulations were then performed over a narrow window to capture these big waves at the precise moments.

Fig. 29: Directional wave spectra of Hurricane Katrina

Fig. 30: Free-surface elevations at the center of jack-up structure

Fig.31 shows the directional nonlinear wave field obtained by the Virtual Model Basin CFD simulations for the selected extreme wave event using the starting time $t_s = 14,935$ s and a time increment of $0.01T_c$ (the characteristic time) which is 0.00319 s. This provides accurate temporal resolution of the highest frequency short waves in the Katrina wave spectra. It can be observed that the wave crests are considerably narrower than the overall size of the jack-up for the wave condition considered here. Due to the short crest feature of the storm waves in comparison with the jack-up size, the overtopping wave patterns and their impact locations vary greatly in different time instances.

4. Closing remarks

With years of developing efforts, the CFD Virtual Model Basin now includes versatile capabilities as the following:

- Finite Analytic Navier-Stokes (FANS) solver, which is a unique and stable numerical method for handling high-Re full-scale simulation;
- Viscous-inviscid coupling technique for enhancing computational efficiency;
- An overset grid technique for alleviating grid generation difficulty and handling flow interactions or relative large motions between floating structures;
- Level set technique for simulating interfacial free surface;
- Various wave generating modules: linear/fully-nonlinear, regular/irregular wave generators, and nonlinear internal wave generator.

The development of CFD Virtual Model Basin is still on-going, and more advanced capabilities will be included in the future. With the state-of-the-art numerical simulation techniques, the CFD Virtual Model Basin has the capability for real world offshore/marine applications. Since the CFD method has proven to be a practical and cost-effective tool to predict hydrodynamic loadings and responses, the CFD Virtual Model Basin will be of great benefit to the offshore structure designs in industry.

Fig. 31: Impact of directional short-crested waves on jack-up: wave elevation contours (left), pressure contours on structure (right)

Through investigating several real offshore problems in this paper, the simulation capabilities of the CFD virtual model basin are demonstrated. However, it should be pointed out that although the CFD Virtual Model Basin is a promising tool for complex offshore problems, it is suggested that traditional approaches such as model tests and industrial empirical methods should be used simultaneously whenever they are available. In this way, the data from using CFD Virtual Model Basin can be validated, and further the insightful findings will be clearly discovered in comparison with the traditional tools.

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Utilizing a Robust Fatigue Screening Process for Initial Design and Throughout the Ship Life-Cycle

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Abstract

The paper presents methodologies, procedures, and results from conducting an analysis using a simplified fatigue assessment rooted in beam theory as well as a spectral-based fatigue analysis procedure implemented in MAESTRO to globally screen for fatigue damage. The paper presents how the MAESTRO software open framework and the MAESTRO Spectral Fatigue Analysis implementation serve as key enabling technologies to the vision of implementing a fully functional life-cycle framework for maintenance, monitoring, and reliability of ship structures. It will discuss how a completely implemented and functional life-cycle framework can mitigate, among other things, extensive fatigue damage in the hull girder.

1. Introduction

It is well documented that a primary limiting component for a ship's service life is the hull structure. The fatigue life (or damage due to fatigue) is one of the major design issues naval architects and owners must contend with. Structural fatigue life is assessed during early stage design and often revisited through its operating life in order to mitigate further damage and keep ships operational throughout the intended service life or beyond. Over the years there have been many methods used to conduct fatigue damage assessment ranging from simplified methods to spectral-based methods. Like most complex analysis problems, each method has pros and cons as well as varying levels of uncertainties. These uncertainties are introduced from both the analysis methodologies themselves, as well as from the engineers executing the methods. It is well established that the costs associated with in-service fatigue damage are significant. This reality continues to drive industry to find more accurate and robust methods to predict these structural inadequacies. Therefore, it is an important objective for designers and owners to exercise an accurate process that can perform global fatigue screening of details in the primary hull structure early in the design process and throughout the ship's service life. This process should begin at preliminary design and can result in great insight for the designer regarding the fatigue distribution of the structural hull system. This knowledge, learned early in the design process, reduces some burden of the detail design phase with respect to structural fatigue. In this respect, the insight and knowledge serves as an excellent jumping-off point for downstream detailed design and the associated detailed fatigue analysis.

2. Process Overview

The following two sections describe the process for performing fatigue assessment using a spectral-based global screening approach and a simplified approach respectively. Each section will present the approach by addressing the main steps in the process. The objective of both approaches is to compute the fatigue demand on a structural entity and compare it to the predicted fatigue strength of that entity, *ABS (2003)*. The main steps can be identified as: Initialization of Structural Arrangements/Scantlings, Generation of Structural Analysis Model, Determination of Loads, Computation of Stress Range, and Computation of Fatigue Damage/Life. This procedure is shown in Fig.1. The following sections will describe steps 2 through 5 for both approaches. Step 1, Initialization of Structural Arrangements/Scantlings, is presented in Fig.1 to illustrate that the designer should begin the process of fatigue assessment by understanding what details are used (or envisioned to be used) for the ship structural system. At the very least, an awareness of the structural details is important because proper detailing and proven details are an effective way of extending the fatigue life of a structural connection, *Glen et al. (1999)*.

Fig. 1: Fatigue design and assessment procedure

The following section describes how the software suite MAESTRO, <http://www.maestromarine.com>, has implemented a spectral-based fatigue assessment approach. MAESTRO (Method for Analysis, Evaluation, and STRuctural Optimization) is a structural design tool specifically tailored to suit naval architects and their finite element analysis and limit-state (failure mode) evaluation needs. MAESTRO has seamlessly integrated all the necessary analysis methodologies to execute a *spectral*-based global fatigue screening procedure through a single Windows-based GUI. This MAESTRO-based procedure seamlessly integrates the structural modeling (preprocessing), the ship-based loading (including seakeeping loads), the finite element analysis, stress range computation, fatigue damage computations, and the post-processing. A key enabling aspect of this MAESTRO-based method is its efficiency which permits this high fidelity fatigue screening approach to be used as an intrinsic aspect of the early-stage (e.g., preliminary design) structural design process.

2.1 MAESTRO Spectral-based Global Fatigue Screening

2.1.1 Generation of the Structural Analysis Model

The generation of a global three dimensional (3-D) finite element model (FEM) that represents the entire hull structure is the first major step in the fatigue assessment process. The global model must sufficiently capture the stiffness and inertial properties of the entire structure. Further, the model must be generated in such a way to accurately compute (through FEA) the nominal stress or provide sufficient boundary conditions for fine-mesh models that may be generated as the design matures. This can be accomplished through coarse-mesh finite element modelling and the representation of stiffened panels through orthotropic shell elements (i.e., smeared stiffener approach). For a global screening process that makes use of the nominal stress it is unnecessary to generate a very fine mesh model to determine the required local nominal stress, *ABS (2003)*. Fig.2 shows a MAESTRO global model that illustrates the above approach for coarse-mesh modelling.

This theory is implemented as a plug-in component called MAESTRO-Wave. Because MAESTRO-Wave is a plug-in component, the MAESTRO model's wetted panel definition, evaluation patch definition, tank definition and weight distribution, are used to generate regular unit wave responses in the form of a database (i.e., exists as a separate *.smn file), which includes ship motions, accelerations and dynamic pressure acting on the hull for each speed, heading and wave frequency. For the computation using 3-D potential theory, the user has the ability to make use of three different wetted panel discretization methods: the original finite element mesh, the evaluation patch mesh, and the section based re-panelization mesh, for the linear seakeeping analysis. After MAESTRO-Wave generates the unit wave hydrodynamic load database, the hull girder load response RAOs, such as vertical bending moment, shear force and torsional moment, as well as the element stress RAOs, can be obtained. The hull girder load response RAOs form the basis for conducting extreme load analysis while the element stress RAOs form the basis for conducting spectral fatigue analysis. This is computed in step 4 of Fig.1 and will be discussed in the next section. Fig.4 shows the real and imaginary components of the complex hydrodynamic loads transferred onto the MAESTRO structural model.

2.1.3 Computation of Stress Range

After the database of complex pressures are computed (as described in the previous section), the next step for the designer is to compute the stress range distributions for each hydrodynamic case. However, prior to computing the stress range, it is necessary to find the stress transfer function (i.e., stress RAOs) for the entire global model as well as any fine-mesh models that may be included in the MAESTRO FEM. MAESTRO accomplishes this by decomposing the complex load vector into two vectors: the real component and the imaginary component, followed by conducting a finite element analysis for each component. This will establish the relationship between the stress in each element within the FEM and the wave frequency, heading, and speed for each base loading condition defined in step 2 of Fig.1. Depending on the number of base loading conditions and wave frequencies, headings, and speeds, the database that holds this information can become quite large. MAESTRO stores this information in a binary file called the *.sfa file.

Fig. 5: Stress transfer function FEA response

Once the stress transfer function is established, the next step is to incorporate wave data to generate the stress-range spectra. The wave data comes in the form of wave distributions as a wave scatter diagram as well as wave spectra. MAESTRO provides the option of choosing from five standard wave spectra: JONSWAP, Bretschneider, Pierson-Moskowitz, Ochi 6 Parameter, and North Atlantic 2 Parameter. Wave scatter diagrams can be chosen from a library incorporated into MAESTRO or the user can define a custom wave scatter diagram.

Fig. 6: MAESTRO wave data dialogs (Wave spectra and wave scatter diagram)

With this information defined by the user, MAESTRO can then perform direct integration of the stress range for each cell of the wave scatter diagram. Summed together, this produces a long-term stress range distribution for the global structure.

2.1.4 Computation of Fatigue Damage/Life

The final step in the procedure, step 5 of Fig.1, requires the user to define the operational profile, the exposure time, the particular structure to be screened, its associated S-N curves, and finally the stress concentration factor (SCF). The operational profile consists of the probabilities of speeds and headings at each wave height, Fig.7. The exposure time and the probabilities of speeds and headings together will provide the number of stress range cycles for a given cell in the wave scatter diagram. This information is defined in the MAESTRO Spectral Fatigue Analysis dialog, Fig.8.

Fig. 7: MAESTRO operational profile dialog

Fig. 8: MAESTRO spectral fatigue analysis dialog

Next, the user will select which portions of the FEM fatigue damage should be computed for. Here the user can select the entire global FEM, all fine-mesh FEM, or portions of the FEM. This is done by creating MAESTRO general groups of structure of interest. Once the user has defined these groups of structure, they can be collected in MAESTRO's Spectral Fatigue Analysis dialog where the user can associate the appropriate S-N curves and SCFs, Fig.9. The S-N curves will define the fatigue strength of the structural component defined in the MAESTRO general group. In practice, the designer would typically begin with a single large area of structure to screen as opposed to the entire FEM all at once. For example, the designer may choose to first screen the main deck (or strength deck) within the 0.4L

of mid-body. This step would inform the designer of the fatigue damage distribution throughout this portion of the hull structure. If the designer continues to add large portions of remaining structure in this manner, a true global fatigue damage screening model will emerge.

Fig 9: Associating structure groups with S-N Curves and SCFs

In the final step in the spectral-based global fatigue screening, MAESTRO uses the Palmgren-Miner's rule to compute damage. The Palmgren-Miner's cumulative fatigue damage rule assumes that the cumulative fatigue damage D inflicted by a group of variable amplitude stress cycles is the sum of the damage inflicted by each stress range d_i , independent of the sequence in which the stress cycles occur, *ABS (2007)*. Mathematically, this is expressed by Eq.(1):

$$D = \frac{T}{A} (2\sqrt{2})^m \Gamma(m/2 + 1) \sum_{i=1}^M \lambda(m, \varepsilon_i) \mu_i f_{0i} p_i (\sigma_i)^m \quad (1)$$

where:

- $T =$ design life [s]
- $m, A =$ physical parameters describing the S-N curve
- $\Gamma =$ complete gamma function with the argument $(m/2+1)$
- $\lambda =$ rainflow factor of Wirsching
- $\varepsilon_i =$ spectral bandwidth
- $\mu_i =$ endurance factor (between 0 and 1), measuring contribution of lower branch of damage
- $f_{0i} =$ zero-up-crossing frequency of the stress response (Hz)
- $p_i =$ joint probability of H_s and T_z
- $\sigma_i = \sqrt{m_0}$ for the i -th considered sea state

For damage ratio $D > 1$, the fatigue capability of the structure in question is not acceptable. MAESTRO provides the user with the ability to plot the damage ratio D or the Fatigue Life, which is expressed as:

$$\text{Fatigue Life} = \frac{\text{Design Life}}{D} \quad (2)$$

These results would be produced from this MAESTRO-based spectral fatigue screening method for typically hundreds (or thousands) of structural intersections depending on the elements included in the fatigue assessment group. The value to the designer comes in the form of the relatively short amount of time required to begin understanding the fatigue damage distribution via this global screening process. A timeline for this activity would entail generating the global FEM with base loading conditions (2-2.5 man-weeks) followed by performing linear frequency domain 3D panel hydrodynamic load computations (3 man-days). At this juncture, the engineer will begin to establish global fatigue screening groups and in effect begin the global fatigue screening process. In this amount of time, the designer will begin to benefit from a global view of the fatigue damage distribution.

2.2 Simplified Approach

As an alternative to a more extensive spectral-based fatigue assessment, many classification societies provide detailed guidance for performing simplified fatigue assessment, which serves to assess standard structural details as opposed to novel structural configurations or unusual wave environ-

ments. Further, this approach is used prior to detail design and provides the designer with insight regarding the structural system's measure against fatigue damage. The following section will describe a simplified approach as defined by the Common Structural Rules (CSR) for Oil Tankers that was developed by a group of International Association of Classification Societies (IACS) members, *IACS (2010)*. This fatigue assessment uses a nominal stress approach based on beam theory.

2.2.1 Generation of the Structural Analysis Model

The CSR simplified approach is based on beam theory; therefore, the analysis model can be thought of as simply the hull girder cross section. For this CSR procedure, the fatigue calculation is performed in two steps: (1) a simplified check of the hull girder section modulus compared to a required fatigue section modulus and (2) a fatigue life assessment of standard structural details.

The hull girder fatigue section modulus required is Z_{v-fat} [m^3] and is given in CSR Section 8.1.5:

$$Z_{v-fat} = \frac{M_{wv-hog} - M_{wv-sag}}{1000 \cdot R_{al}} \quad [m^3] \quad (3)$$

where:

M_{wv-hog} = hogging vertical wave bending moment for fatigue [kNm]

M_{wv-sag} = sagging vertical wave bending moment for fatigue [kNm]

R_{al} = allowable stress range [N/mm^2]

$$R_{al} = 0.17 \cdot L + 86 \text{ for class F-details} \quad (4)$$

The hogging and sagging vertical wave bending moments used for fatigue strength assessment are multiplied by a factor of 0.5, which accounts for the probability level of wave bending moments. This is described in CSR Section 7.3.1.2 and Section 7.3.4.1.3.

2.2.2 Determination of the Loads

As is the case with other industry-accepted simplified fatigue assessment approaches, the CSRs use parametric equations to determine the loads for use in fatigue assessment. These well-recognized parametric equations have no explicit relationship to the ship operations or the wave data that the ship will operate in. The hogging and sagging vertical wave bending moments for fatigue are M_{wv-hog} and M_{wv-sag} respectively as given in CSR section 7.3.4.1.3. However, the vertical bending moments calculated in CSR section 7.3.4.1.3 are for the life-time extreme and have an exceedance probability value of 10^{-8} , but for fatigue assessment purposes CSR uses a higher exceedance probability value (10^{-4}). This is accounted for using the parameter f_{prob} and is described in CSR section 7.3.4.1.3.

$$M_{wv-hog} = f_{prob} \cdot 0.19 \cdot f_{wv-v} \cdot C_{wv} \cdot L^2 \cdot B \cdot C_b \quad [kNm] \quad (5)$$

$$M_{wv-sag} = -f_{prob} \cdot 0.11 \cdot f_{wv-v} \cdot C_{wv} \cdot L^2 \cdot B \cdot (C_b + 0.7) \quad [kNm] \quad (6)$$

where:

f_{prob} = probability of exceedance factor (equal to 0.5 for fatigue analysis)
 f_{wv-v} = distribution factor for vertical wave bending moment along vessel length
 L = vessel length
 B = vessel moulded breadth
 C_b = block coefficient

2.2.3 Computation of Stress Range

The calculation of the hull girder stresses are attained through the use of simple beam theory. The application of simple beam theory is an expedient way of getting reasonable approximations of stress levels in the longitudinal hull girder. The hull girder stresses from simple beam theory have the following assumptions, *Glen et al. (1999)*:

- plane cross-sections remain plane;
- stresses remain in the elastic range and thus allow superposition;
- the beam is essentially prismatic (no openings or discontinuities; and
- there is no interaction between bending and other response modes (e.g., transverse and longitudinal deflections or shear and torsional distortions).

With the above simple beam theory assumptions, the nominal stress range can be calculated:

$$S_{Ri} = \frac{M_{wv-hog} - M_{wv-sag}}{Z_{v-net75}} \quad [\text{N/mm}^2] \quad (7)$$

where:

M_{wv-hog} = defined in Eq.(5)

M_{wv-sag} = defined in Eq.(6)

$Z_{v-net75}$ = Net vertical hull girder section modulus of hull cross-section about transverse neutral axis. This is calculated based on gross thickness, minus the corrosion addition $0.25 t_{corr}$ of all effective structural elements.

The calculated stress range is assumed to have a long-term distribution that fits a two-parameter Weibull probability distribution. This assumption enables the use of a closed form equation to compute the fatigue life, *IACS (2010)*.

2.2.4 Computation of Fatigue Damage/Life

Assuming the stress range has a long-term distribution that fits a two-parameter Weibull probability distribution allows the fatigue damage ratio DM_i for the applicable base loading condition to be defined as, *IACS (2010)*:

$$DM_i = \frac{\alpha_i N_L}{K_2} \cdot \frac{S_{Ri}^m}{(\ln N_R)^{m/\xi}} \mu_i \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{m}{\xi} \right) \quad (8)$$

where:

α_i = proportion of the ship's life

N_L = number of cycles for the expected design life

K_2 = S-N curve parameter as defined in CSR section C.1.4.5.5

S_{Ri} = stress range at the representative probability level of 10^{-4} [N/mm²]

m = S-N curve parameter as defined in CSR section C.1.4.5.5

N_R = 10,000, number of cycles corresponding to the probability level of 10^{-4}

ξ = Weibull probability distribution parameter, defined in CSR section C.1.4.1.6

μ_i = coefficient taking into account the change in slope of the S-N curve, defined in CSR section C.1.4.1.4

Γ = Gamma function

Finally, the resultant cumulative damage is to be taken as:

$$DM = \sum_{i=1}^2 DM_i \quad (9)$$

Where $i = 1$ for full load condition and $i = 2$ for normal ballast condition

3. Procedure Example

3.1 Vessel Description

The vessel analysed in this paper is an articulated tank barge (ATB), Table I. The deck, side shell, and bottom areas of the vessel are made of ABS Grade A steel, while the shear strake areas of the vessel's mid-body are made of ABS Grade D steel. The deck has a series of hatch openings outboard (both port and starboard) that are distributed through the length of the vessel.

Table I: Main characteristics of ATB

Length between perpendiculars L_{pp}	175.00 m
Moulded breadth B	22.50 m
Moulded depth D	12.20 m
Scantling draught T	8.90 m

3.2 MAESTRO Spectral-based Global Fatigue Screening

A global MAESTRO FEM was generated to properly represent the vessel's entire hull girder structure and main supporting members as well as the appropriate base loading conditions. In creating the global FEM, care was taken to choose nodes and elements to represent the stiffness and inertia properties of the hull structure, while keeping the size of the file to a manageable level (i.e., small data file), *ABS (2006)*. The FEM for this exercise is shown in Fig.2. Generally, a full MAESTRO model such as the one shown in Fig.2, with base loading conditions, can be generated by an experienced user in one to two weeks after the necessary input data (e.g., drawings, load distributions, etc.) is collected.

The next step was to generate a frequency loads database using MAESTRO-Wave's 3D potential theory approach (i.e., 3D panel code). As described in the previous section, the FEM wetted panels served as the MAESTRO-Wave hydrodynamic model and is shown in Fig.10. The matrix of hydrodynamic runs executed is shown in Table II and input via the MAESTRO-Wave setup dialog.

Fig. 10: MAESTRO-Wave panel model for hydrodynamic analysis

Table II: Matrix of hydrodynamic cases

Load Condition	Speeds (knots)	Headings (degrees)	Wave Frequencies (radians/second)
Full Load	0	0,30,...,330	0.2,0.3,...,1.8

Next, the process involved the establishment of the stress transfer functions for the database of frequency loads (both real and imaginary). Once this was established the computation of fatigue damage was initiated by defining the following: Wave Scatter Diagram (IACS North Atlantic), Wave Energy Spectra (Bretschneider), and Operating Profile (equal probabilities of wave headings and speeds). Per IACS guidance, the operating profile accounted for 85% of the life at sea. Finally, the procedure moved to deciding what portion of the structure was to be selected for fatigue damage screening (i.e., fatigue screening group) and the application of S-N data and exposure time. The parameters used for this exercise are captured in Table III. Table IV and Table V capture the fatigue screening group parameters and results respectively.

Table III: Spectral Fatigue Analysis Setup

Base Load	Environment	Wave Spectra	Operating Profile	Exposure Time
Full Load	IACS North Atlantic	Bretschneider	Equal Probabilities	21.25
Full Load	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Non-sailing	3.75

Table IV: Global Fatigue Screening Group

Screening Group	S-N Curve	SCF
	1.0	

Table V: Global Fatigue Life Screening Results

Full Model Plot (< 25 years)	Fatigue Screening Group Plot (< 10 years)

3.3 Simplified Approach

Following the procedure discussed in the previous sections, the hull girder cross-sectional properties were calculated for a section of interest with the appropriate corrosion deduction $Z_{v-net75}$ and compared to the required fatigue section modulus Z_{v-fat} . Table VI and Table VII provide the input and results for Eq.(3).

Table VI: Input parameter to Z_{v-fat} calculation

M_{wv-hog}	546,158 [kNm]
$M_{wv-saog}$	-555,969 [kNm]
R_{al}	115.58 [N/mm ²]

Table VII: Comparison of Z_{v-fat} and Z_{actual}

Z_{v-fat}	9.45 [m ³]
$Z_{v-net75}$	11.24 [m ³]

Table VIII: Fatigue damage calculation input and results

α_i	N_L	K_2	S_{Ri}	N_R	ζ	μ_i	DM_i	DM	Fatigue Life
0.5	$7.48 \cdot 10^7$	$6.30 \cdot 10^{11}$	97 N/mm ²	10,000	1.014	0.742	0.323	0.645	39 years

Note: S-N curve data, in-air for a Class F detail was used (see CSR Table C.1.6)

The stress range, which is computed using Eq.(7) and the input parameters from Table VI and Table VII resulted in 97 N/mm². Finally, using Eq.(8), the fatigue damage ratio can be computed. Table VIII provides the input parameters and results of this calculation.

4. Contrast between Screening and Simplified

The following two sections summarize the MAESTRO spectral-based global fatigue screening and the simplified approach in an attempt to provide a context to view each of these levels of fatigue assessment. Obviously, a spectral-based approach is more robust due to the direct hydrodynamic loads computations and the consideration of operating profiles and wave environment data; however, it may be less obvious how accessible this procedure becomes in MAESTRO, making this approach very manageable and appealing to the designer. Overall, the results between the two approaches described in this example were comparable. As shown in Table VIII, the fatigue life for the simplified approach was 39 years. To compare these results to MAESTRO spectral-based fatigue analysis results, a fatigue screening group that collected elements within a single deck transverse strip was defined and fatigue life results computed. These results are shown in Table IX and the fatigue life ranges from 20.96 years to 60.75 years. The range in fatigue life (in each element) is due to the asymmetric nature of the internal structure that was modeled and follows the stress distribution of a previously run static Full Load condition. On average, the fatigue life across this deck strip is 41 years. This fatigue distribution is something you can easily attain through global screening.

Table IX: Deck Strip Fatigue Screen (< 25 years)

4.1 Global Screening Approach

Global screening for fatigue provides the designer with a high-level assessment of fatigue damage and the distribution of fatigue damage in the hull structure. In this manner, the designer does not have to depend purely on the experience or guidance from classification society to determine on which particular areas to perform fatigue assessment. The designer would certainly review these areas, but the full global screening process described in previous sections provides the opportunity to find other areas that may be problematic. Further, after the hydrodynamic analysis step and the stress range computation step, this database is readily available for on demand fatigue analysis. This provides a practical and cost-effective way to bring spectral-based fatigue analysis into the early design stage of structural assessment. Although the determination of hydrodynamic loads, per step 3, can be computationally expensive, the increasingly large computing power of typical engineering PCs makes this a practical step to execute. Further, the analysis time required doesn't necessarily consume the engineers time as the processors are performing the computation. One can conclude that the major

time expended for global screening is post-processing results and perhaps performing sensitivity studies and general effort with respect to the application of S-N curves, SCFs (if used), and other general parameters used for the analysis procedure. However, the time spent performing a global screening process should highlight potential problematic areas and provide an opportunity for the engineer to gain an improved understanding of the design's adequacy with respect to fatigue strength. The results also enable a mature starting point from which more detailed fatigue analysis of specific structural details can be conducted during design or during the ship's service life.

4.2 Simplified Approach

Many of the commonly used simplified ship fatigue analysis procedures are based on the same knowledge base and can be traced back to other non-marine or offshore standards. This knowledge base and existing standards have been applied with varying degrees of customization, detail, and interpretation, *Glen et al. (1999)*, by classification societies such as ABS, DNV, GL and LR. This approach makes use of simple beam theory for computing nominal stress in the hull girder and can be done so very easily very early in the design process. This procedure can be leveraged as part of the design evolution of the hull girder cross-sectional properties without much effort. The simplified approach has its merits in this regard and should be undertaken as a first data point for the designer.

5. Conceptual Integrated Life-Cycle System

Although fatigue analysis methods exist and have been utilized for many years, it is difficult to find them embedded in a comprehensive structural life-cycle framework system. This is not to suggest that such life-cycle systems do not exist; however, within the marine industry they largely reside only in the research and development community. For example, the U.S. Office of Naval Research is currently supporting a project at Lehigh University focused on the concept of an integrated life-cycle framework for ship reliability assessment, redundancy estimation, damage detection, and optimum inspection planning, *Frangopol et al. (2012)*. The notion of bringing together a full range of life-cycle analysis and management techniques into a set of linked technologies is nothing new. Ship Structure Committee (SSC) report SSC-427, illustrates how a complete set of analysis techniques can be linked to provide ship owners and operators with quantitative tools for design, construction, acquisition, repair, maintenance, and removal from service, *Dinovitzer (2003)*. However, these comprehensive tools are not prevalent today. Even a key component to a life-cycle framework such as structural reliability still largely remains in the research community and not in practical ship design and assessment tools. These methodologies must find their way into practical tools that can be utilized by practicing naval architects even if all the necessary attributes are not readily available.

For this, it is proposed that the MAESTRO software suite, which contains the necessary underpinnings for a structural life-cycle framework, can be used as a tool box from which to realize this vision of a user-friendly, practical, life-cycle assessment capability. By leveraging a tool that can contribute to the design process as well as the life-cycle assessment process, a single data model can be initiated and then populated and updated as the ship ages. Such an integration of external or third-party technology is a concept that has been embraced by the MAESTRO software system from its inception and continues today. The core capability of MAESTRO is part of a larger open product model framework as shown in Fig.11. This open framework allows the interfacing (i.e., data input and data output) of MAESTRO with a variety of ship structural design and life-cycle assessment technologies for several technical domains including, but not limited to: structural life-cycle assessment, underwater shock assessment, fatigue analysis and assessment, hydrodynamic loads analysis, ultimate hull girder strength assessment, and ship salvage assessment. The implementation of a life-cycle system would represent an additional interface (or set of interfaces) with the MAESTRO open product model framework shown in Fig.11.

Fig. 11: MAESTRO Open Modeling/Analysis Framework

6. Conclusions

A primary limiting component for a ship's service life is the hull structure. In particular, a ship's fatigue life remains one of the major design issues naval architects are faced with in terms of how a design is initially assessed during early stage design, and what mitigating steps can be taken to control fatigue damage throughout the structural system's service life. To address this complicated subject, industry has implemented and exercised various long-standing approaches; however, many of these approaches are exercised during later stages in the design process, or after construction or even while a vessel is in service. Remediation of any issues that are found can be problematic and costly. Further these established approaches typically do not directly function within a larger structural life-cycle framework system as such systems still remain to a large extent only within the research and development community. Therefore, establishing an efficient and robust process that allows the naval architect to perform global fatigue screening of acceptable details in the primary hull structure early in the design process and throughout the service life is invaluable. Today, this can be accomplished by both designers and ship service-life manager who use the MAESTRO Spectral Fatigue Analysis technology.

In this respect, the benefits of performing global structural fatigue screening early in the design process should not be assumed to be small relative to the perceived complexity and required time for performing such a task. Dedicating three man-weeks of effort to establish an accurate initial understanding of how a ship structural system performs under fatigue demand is a small investment compared to the costs associated with discovering this during detail design or during the ship's in-service life. The lack of initial insight in this respect has the potential to also add to other costs such as repair and life extension activities.

Acknowledgements – Legal disclaimer

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Utilizing CAD/CAM Models for Ongoing Weight Estimation and Control

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Abstract

Controlling the weight of a vessel over the design and engineering lifecycle is critical but is an ongoing challenge for shipbuilders. Excellent tools exist for both weight estimation and control and design and engineering; however the area where these two meet is often filled with Microsoft Excel spreadsheets or databases developed in house by individual shipyards. These approaches leave much to be desired. This paper will explore the implementation and benefits gained by integrating existing design and engineering tools with existing weight control applications.

1. Introduction

1.1. Weight Control

Good weight control should start when the very first weight and center of gravity (CG) estimates in the tender phase of a project are carried out, and carry on all through basic design, detailed design, and construction until the vessel is completed. Through these phases, weight data is available in different formats and at a different level of accuracy and quality. At early stages of the tender and basic design, when detailed information of the vessel is not available, weights and center of gravity come from experience, whether it is from the designer's own experience, or from a more structured approach using systematic regression of weight data from historical vessels. As the project progresses, more detailed information becomes available. Information can come in the form of weights for equipment from the vendor, it can be modeled or calculated weights from a CAD system's model, or come from the actual recorded weighting of items at the shipyards. At any point in time during the design and construction of a vessel one should have available and be utilizing the most accurate and most up-to-date weight and center of gravity information to allow purposeful monitoring and control of the evolution of weight and CG.

1.2. 3D CAD Tools

Since their introduction in the 1990's, 3D CAD tools have become a potentially powerful source of information about the vessel. Over time, these tools have been developed to become more of a product model than a geometry model. When the vessel's geometry is modeled in the 3D tool, properties for densities can be assigned to the materials of the model and thus weights and center of gravity can be calculated from the 3D model. Naturally, the ship engineer will be very interested in exploiting this weight and center of gravity calculation derived from the model. At first glance it may seem like a very straightforward thing to do: assign material density and be done with it. However, it is unfortunately not as trivial as one may first think. This paper will discuss some of the issues involved with utilizing CAD models for weight calculation and weight control and offer some guidance on how to best deal with them.

1.3. Benefits

The benefits of utilizing a 3D CAD model for weights are obviously numerous, if one is able to do it the right way. It can provide a rather accurate weight and center of gravity in a timely way and with a small amount of effort. Having this information readily available can provide earlier detection of negative trends in mass properties and provide more complete and accurate as-built weight databases.

2. Weight Data in 3D Models

A valid question from the reader would be why the 3D CAD model is not the weight tool of reference, since it seems so well suited for calculating weight and CG. Why use anything else for weight control during the engineering design process? There are several reasons for this:

- First of all, a 3D CAD model is not available in the early stages of a ship design.
- A CAD model is rarely complete enough, and generally will include only most of the structure, major pipes and HVAC ducting, some if any at all of the electrical and at best only some of the equipment.
- Almost without exception the 3D model is only available after the design contract has been entered into, and weight control needs to be set in motion before this part of the design cycle occurs.
- Further, the 3D CAD model tool often offers no place to store as-built data when this weight information becomes available and therefore should be used as the most accurate recording of the weight at that time instead of 3D weight data that is calculated.

There is a period during the engineering process where the 3D CAD model plays a major role in containing the most accurate and up-to-date weight data within a vessel design, but this period is of limited duration. Finally, a 3D CAD tool has no or limited capabilities for required functions for data collection and revision involving weight estimation, monitoring, tracking, and the corresponding reporting.

2.1. Limitation with respect to Weight Data in 3D Models

Even within the period of time where 3D CAD models do contain good and valuable information for weight control, there are limitations one needs to be aware of. Two important questions to ask are:

- What weight data is available in the 3D model?
- What is the quality of the data in the 3D model?

The answers to these questions are not necessarily as straightforward as they seem. For example, the weight data that is available is determined by what has been modeled and given a material density property. If there is no material density assigned to the modeled object, no weight can be calculated. It is important to remember that for good weight control, knowing what is not present is equally important as knowing what is present.

Equally knowing what has been modeled and has assigned density properties does not answer yet another question, which is the quality of the data available. In order to determine the quality of the data one needs to know the level of maturity of the modeled parts. In addition to knowing the maturity of the parts, there can be modeling errors that have little impact on the geometry of the model, but can give significant errors in the calculated weight. This is often a result of the CAD modeler not having weight calculation in mind during modeling.

The typical example could be explained by a cable tray that is modeled as a rectangular solid rather than as a U-shaped hollow figure. In most cases such errors do not create any geometrical problems, but for calculating the weight of the cable tray the error will be several hundred percent. Missing or incorrectly assigned density properties are another source of errors in the 3D CAD model. So, it is very important to know the quality of the data that will be received from the 3D CAD model, and to strive for the best data as possible. A lot can be accomplished through educating the 3D CAD modeler in the importance of weight control, but in addition, checks should be made to minimize the effect of errors in the model.

3. Harvesting Weight Data from 3D models

When a good and reliable 3D CAD model is available, it makes sense to use this data in weight control. In other words, the data should be extracted from the 3D CAD model and imported into the weight control tool.

Assuming the 3D CAD model does offer weight data, this can be extracted in several ways for use by the weight tool. There are normally 4 ways of extracting data from a 3D CAD model in order to get it into weight control software:

- Normal export/import through an intermediate file using any of a number of techniques
- Direct access to the CAD file, for example using the facilities provided by the software's native language like (AutoCAD®'s LISP)
- Direct access to the database (if one exists) of the 3D CAD model from the weight control software
- for the more capable systems, access the 3D CAD model's database through the API and/or stored procedures of the 3D CAD model's environment

3.1. Export/Import through an Intermediate File

The export/import through an intermediate file is the most common way of exchanging data between a CAD tool and a weight control tool, usually in the form of a text file or Excel® file. The advantage of this method is that most CAD systems are natively able or can be programmed to export weight information in formats like these. This method can work well, but the disadvantage is that it requires the weight control engineer to be very familiar with the contents of the file at hand, and to be able to very accurately manage modifications, deletions, additions, and replacement of items. The procedure is very “manual”, it is time consuming and error-prone, it must be enacted at the correct moment in time to capture the evolution of the CAD model, and may in some cases require formatting of the files to be imported.

3.2. Direct access to the CAD file

This technique is not dissimilar from the export/import strategy, but it does carry the advantage of programmatic direct interrogation. Direct access to the CAD file is acquired in memory space as opposed to in an intermediate file which, by definition, structures the data being read. The step to formatting the data appropriately for the direct consumption of the weight tool is small, and required intrinsically for the process to complete.

3.3. Direct Access through a Database

Direct access to the 3D model's database requires the 3D tools to store the information in a database that is accessible externally from other programs. Having this type of access is not always the case as some tools use proprietary, pseudo-databases or store the data in files that are not accessible by other software. The disadvantage of this method includes requiring good knowledge of the database table structure, the data to be accessed, and the custom programming for the extraction of the data which becomes obsolete when the database structure or nature of the data formatting changes. Moreover, the weight engineer must have the appropriate level of permissions to access the 3D model's database, which in some IT environments can be problematic. Finally, this strategy is also vulnerable to database changes resulting from design iterations and scenarios stored in the database, and design changes that will occur in the design cycle within the 3D tool; this may invalidate the method of data extraction. On the other hand, the advantage is that this constitutes a managed and faster way of importing, data both in regards to the actual import, but also in terms of the greatly reduced manual handling of the data to be imported.

3.4. Access through API or Stored Procedures

For those cases where a database exists and access to it is made available, it tends to be one of the industry standard ones, such as Microsoft SQL Server®, Oracle®, etc. In this case, the best way of importing is through the use of an API (Application Programming Interface) or stored procedures made available from the 3D tool vendor. This will also require custom programming, but lacks several of the disadvantages of directly accessing the database. The significant advantage is that changes to the database structure, or the data formatting, and even to the nature of the data will not corrupt the interface. The API and stored procedures are always maintained (and generally used by) the software manufacturer as their own software programming will utilize the same API.

3.5. What to get from the 3D CAD Model

Establishing the best possible method is a good start, but there are more issues to be considered prior to the harvest of the weight data. For example, what do we want to get from the 3D model?

- The complete model or only portions?
- What level of data detail is to be acquired into the weight database?
- Do we want additional data information beyond weight and CG?

The nature of the first point is practical, and has to do with the size of the 3D model. A 3D model can contain several hundred thousand weight items, and to import all of these every time a change to the model would warrant an update of the weight database can be a very inefficient way of working, simply because of the time a large update will require. Therefore it makes more sense to restrict the import to only the model modifications and to only carry the data that is required to provide a given update. On the other hand, not updating often enough or artificially limiting the scope of the update can create different problems, as discussed in the next section on “Deleted Items”.

The second issue, the level of detail, is also relevant from a practical standpoint, as this will directly impact the duration of the updating procedure. Very large databases make for a slowdown in data handling and require more hardware power and network capacity.

In addition there is one more thing to consider: it is good practice, as far as possible, to import only those items that make sense to the weight control engineer. Effective weight control involves checking and reasoning based on the items present in the weight model database. It is much easier, for example, to ascertain the validity of the weight and CG of a ladder assembly as a single item rather than that of all its composing rungs, columns and rails individually.

Finally, weight control is more than just collecting items to be summarized for a total weight and center of gravity. It should also include:

- checking the validity of the data,
- measuring maturity
- reporting data for operations like lifting and launching
- making sure that the weight database can be utilized as an historical reference for future estimations.

In order to accomplish collection of the items noted above, the associated weight data needs to be tagged with additional information that allows for grouping and summarizing according to the arbitrary criteria. A 3D CAD model will most often contain data valuable for this purpose, such as block, module, or unit information, and the modeled object’s discipline, for example.

4. Special challenges

Some special challenges to be kept in mind when importing data from a 3D CAD model include:

- Deleted items
- Temporary items
- Work breakdown structure.

4.1. Deleted Items

It may be easy to overlook the fact that when a weight database is updated from a CAD model deleted items are just as important to account for as added and changed items. A list containing the latest and most up-to-date information on modeled parts of the vessel is likely to not include items that have been deleted, which should then be removed from the weight database as part of the update process. Generally there are two ways of handling this.

The first is to always import and update a complete “package”, a “package” being a structured list of items, for example; a block, a system, etc.; in essence, anything that is easy to group and to identify as a “package”. In this case, items are unambiguously either a part of the “package” or not. Updates should always address complete packages, and the packages should be replaced completely. This means that updating the “steel” of a particular block assembly means deleting this block assembly entirely from the weight model before importing its latest version. The following process ensures that a deleted item from the CAD model will also disappear from the weight database.

A second way to treat items deleted from the CAD model when updating the weight database is to retrieve the information of the deleted items from the CAD model and make sure these items are also deleted from the weight database. This technique obviously requires a much finer process in granularity and the ability to individually address any item.

Either approach would be acceptable in handling deleted items within a CAD model. Serious weight data collection, monitoring, and tracking problems would occur if the deleted items were not managed in the updating of data items from the CAD model.

4.2. Temporary Items

It seems to be quite common amongst 3D CAD modelers to draw “temporary” objects outside the “visible” drawing space. Unfortunately, often these objects are just left there as they don’t interfere with the drawing or the model. If these objects are left in the 3D CAD model, they become an unintentional part of the weight model and can be hard to find and remove, thereby constituting a dangerous error, and unknown in its existence with impossible to manage scenarios.

4.3. Lack of Work Breakdown Structure

A Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) should be used in every weight control exercise. There are several reasons why this is important. When an early weight and CG estimate is conducted, the vessel has to be divided into a set of weight groups in the form of a WBS. This is important because trying to estimate the whole vessel as a unique, all encompassing object seldom gives good results, as does the attempt to represent the vessel by a developed itemized list. The vessel must be broken down into groups that can be estimated individually, and then the summary of these groups makes up the whole vessel estimate. Further, during weight tracking and monitoring, weights are collected according to the weight model’s hierarchical organization as laid out by the weight groups. These weight groups support direct comparison against the values originally estimated for the same groups. Deviation of weight and CG is then checked at the weight group level. Incidentally, many navies require weight reports to be prepared during the construction of the vessel according to a specific WBS.

One common challenge lies within the fact that in most cases the items in the 3D CAD model are not tagged with WBS information, and most of the time this information cannot easily be derived from CAD model itself. Exporting thousands of items with weight and center of gravity information, but without any WBS information, to the weight tool does create a data management puzzle.

Depending on the type of WBS and meta-data attached to the items in the CAD model, it may be possible to define a logic that allows for some automatic or semi-automatic assignment of WBS information, but in many cases the only way of getting good WBS information is to have the CAD modeler directly assign this information during the design. This is easier said than done and requires the modeler to both have competence about the WBS and also knowledge about weight control to gather and tag the modeled items with the WBS information. Alternatively, the weight engineer can make the WBS assignment to each item when it is transferred into the weight control software. Then when the data is updated, each part “remembers” its WBS, while updating any other information. Alternatively, once the WBS has been assigned in the weight control software, that data could be exported back to the 3D CAD model, if a suitable interface is created. In either case, the idea is to only have to assign the WBS to a part one time in its life, whether that’s done by the CAD modeler or the weight engineer.

4.4. 3D Model versus As-built

Great looking 3D CAD models of the vessel with a lot of detail often lead to the conclusion that the weight calculated from the model must be accurate. This can make people put their guards down in terms of executing the proper checking and verification of the results from the CAD model. But even without any mistakes from the 3D CAD modeler it is important that the weight engineer considers the as-built steel weight additions which are not necessarily a part of the model, such as mill tolerance and welding. These typically add up to about 2% of the steel weight. There are some CAD tools that can add these weights automatically, but it is important to know if they do or not. Even with the welding and mill tolerance accounted for, it is important that the weight engineer is aware of the fact that sometimes real construction does not always comply with the model. As an example, if the drawing specifies a plate of thickness 8 mm and only 10 mm plates are in stock, often a 10 mm plate will be used. This is not a problem with the strength of the vessel, but for the weight it represents an increase of more than 20% for the plate, and obviously has an effect on the CG of vessel. Also, even the most detailed of 3D CAD models may not be completely detailed designed with all components that go into the construction of the ship. Some shipyards may subcontract out entire systems that are not contained within the 3D CAD model and therefore as-built configurations with weight and CG data must be considered in the overall weight control.

5. Getting 3D data from ShipConstructor to ShipWeight

The following part of this paper describes work done in the National Shipbuilding Research Program (NSRP) project “Leveraging Detail Design Data in Weight Engineering”. The purpose of the project is to focus on the efficient use of detail design data as an input to weight engineering. During this project, current and desired business process work flows and improved use cases were documented through an activity based process modeling technique in cooperation within two large shipyards, VT Halter Marine and Marinette Marine Corporation. An interface strategy, beginning with a data alignment and exchange map, was developed based on the process information identified by the shipyards. The map documented allowed for software developers to improve the transfer of data from a detail design system to a weight engineering program based on the captured “To-Be” business process state. The project approach was not to be specific to improving or developing any particular detail design or weight engineering software. However, since software must be used for the proof of concept for this type of data exchange and development, it was decided that the implementation strategy for this project would be to transfer data from ShipConstructor to ShipWeight. The main reason why these software programs were chosen was that both companies participating in the NSRP project were already using these programs. Incidentally, these two programs are the most commonly used detail

design and weight engineering tools in the US shipbuilding industry, including the majority of all the shipyard participants in the NSRP R&D program.

5.1. ShipWeight at a Glance

ShipWeight is a state of the art weight control tool that can handle early stage design weight and center of gravity estimations, as well as weight tracking and monitoring from basic design throughout detailed design and construction.

In early design, weight and center of gravity are estimated based upon regression of historical data with the purpose of finding good correlations (scaling factors) between the weight and CG of a vessel and known parameters of the design (parametric estimation). The vessel is divided into a hierarchy of weight groups, and each group is assigned an estimation formula containing ship parameters and a scaling coefficient used to calculate the weight and CG for that particular weight group. When the design progresses and more detailed and specific item weight data becomes available, this information is collected in the appropriate weight groups. As the item weight data matures and becomes more accurate and certain than the estimated value, this value is carried on as the preferred one for the remainder of the project.

As more and more weight groups become itemized and more accurate weight data is available, the weight control exercise migrates from estimation to tracking mode. ShipWeight provides the environment and tools needed to continually harvest the most accurate data available from whatever source, whether this is from a CAD model, a vendor, an estimate, or as-built data from weighing.

For it to express all its power, ShipWeight should always be current with the most up-to-date information from all weight groups. At each milestone of the project, for instance entering contract, or at regular intervals throughout the project, a version of the current weight data is saved and stored as a separate revision of the weight model database. The weight development of the project can then be monitored by comparing and analyzing development from one revision to another. Also, a comparison supported by the data checking tools is needed to establish the validity of the Weight and CG figures, in detail.

5.2. ShipConstructor at a Glance

ShipConstructor is an AutoCAD[®]-based shipbuilding CAD/CAM software suite that provides fully integrated, multi-disciplinary detailed design and modeling tools for production engineering of marine structures. ShipConstructor captures all information relevant to the 3D design, manufacturing, maintenance, repair and refit of complex marine projects inside a Marine Information Model (MIM). At the heart of the model is a single relational database residing on a Microsoft SQL Server that can be integrated with related business processes and applications. ShipConstructor's unique software architecture and AutoCAD foundation provide significant competitive advantages.

ShipConstructor's AutoCAD foundation leads to a decrease in required training time. ShipConstructor is built on top of AutoCAD, where this foundation provides a population of skilled workers already familiar with the basic tools and general look and feel of the software. Additionally, ShipConstructor is a suite of products targeted specifically at the shipbuilding and offshore industries. The basic philosophy behind the technology allows clients to directly interact with the 3D product model of a ship or offshore project in a manner that is natural for their business. Users with a solid foundation of AutoCAD skills and a decent understanding of the industry can quickly become proficient with the software.

ShipConstructor facilitates the ability to shorten the detailed design process by allowing the ability to utilize a single Marine Information Model to create the associated production output. This means that all of the various design disciplines can work within the same model concurrently, and provides a means to respond to changes from other disciplines in real time. Production drawings are dynamically

linked to the model so that when the model changes they are automatically updated without any loss of custom detailing. Consequently the engineering team can start production drawings much earlier than in other basic CAD systems.

The native format of ShipConstructor is DWG which is one of the most common standards for data exchange. ShipConstructor can also consume and create virtually any format required for communication with associated service providers in the shipbuilding industry including Autodesk DWG, DXF, DWF, SAT, STEP, IGES, and 3DM. This level of interoperability makes it far easier to import information from suppliers, manufacturers and subcontractors into a ShipConstructor project.

ShipConstructor has created an open architecture and a best of breed approach in efforts to meet and exceed the requirements of the shipbuilding and offshore industries. Integration and interoperability are supported by an open, accessible relational Microsoft SQL database with numerous APIs (Application Programming Interfaces). This platform enables ShipConstructor to work with a variety of software packages.

6. Architectural Overview of the Weight Data Transfer

6.1. Fulcrum Application - Middleware

The solution selected to accomplish the weight data transfer from CAD to the weight tool has been to develop a middleware software component, called Fulcrum. The Fulcrum application acts as the facilitator of the data exchange by extracting the data from ShipConstructor and preparing it for consumption by ShipWeight.

6.2. Fulcrum Application – Functional Requirements

The following list defines the functional requirements for the Fulcrum middleware application:

1. Open and retrieve weight data from an existing ShipConstructor database.
2. Extract specified weight data from a ShipConstructor database. Allow filtering by project, block/module, discipline, Ship Work Breakdown Structure (SWBS) group, drawing, planar group, and revision number.
3. Serialize weight data to a neutral file format that can be imported into ShipWeight.
4. Identify additions, deletions, and revisions made within a ShipConstructor database and transfer update information to a neutral file format that can be imported into ShipWeight.

6.3. Principal Use Cases

All of the use cases involve an actor defined as an engineer or naval architect who is the application end-user. The following list defines the principal use cases for the application:

1. Collect by Project: Retrieve all weight data for a specific project from a ShipConstructor database. All hull blocks/modules and all engineering disciplines would be included.
2. Collect by Project and Block: Retrieve weight data for a specific block in a specific project from a ShipConstructor database. Allow filtering by a single discipline or multiple disciplines.
3. Collect by Project and Discipline: Retrieve weight data for a specific discipline in a specific project from a ShipConstructor database. Allow filtering by one or more drawing numbers, block, or planar group.
4. Collect by Project and SWBS: Retrieve weight data for a specific SWBS group in a specific project from a ShipConstructor database. Allow filtering by one or more drawing numbers or by block.
5. Collect by Project and Drawing #: Retrieve weight data for a specific drawing number in a specific project from a ShipConstructor database. Allow filtering by revision number.

6.4. Workflow Description

The principal workflows for the prototype application are shown in Fig.1. Each starts with the user opening a project in an existing ShipConstructor database that has been fully or partially populated with parts. Opening the project allows the prototype application to retrieve the current parts list and to identify and cache lists of valid values for various part properties (e.g., the list of valid block numbers or SWBS groups). The next step is for the user to select the data that is to be extracted from the database. This is done by creating the data extraction filters that define the block(s), discipline(s), SWBS group(s), drawing(s), planar group(s), and drawing revision(s) for the data to be extracted. A collection of these filters can be saved as a named filter set for future use. If any named filter sets have been previously saved, the user can choose a saved filter set and apply it directly or modify it. After the data extraction filters have been defined, the filtered weight data can be extracted from the parts list and then exported to a neutral file format by the user. The neutral file, which will contain sufficient information to define not only the part/weight data but also the lineage of this data, can then be imported into ShipWeight. During the ShipWeight import, items that already exist in the ShipWeight database are updated as appropriate, and any items that were deleted from the ShipConstructor model but had been previously imported into ShipWeight are deleted. Because the neutral file contains information about the weight data lineage (such as the definition of the filters that were applied), it can be used in an alternative workflow in which the user just extracts added, deleted, or modified part information from the ShipConstructor database relative to a prior data extraction. The architecture of the prototype software intended to facilitate these workflows is described in the following section.

Fig. 1: Workflow for prototype application

7. Key Issues

To execute the data transfer as described above, the following functionality has been put in place:

- For ShipConstructor, functionality needs to be in place to allow tagging of WBS information and other filter parameters to the items in the 3D model and also make stored procedure and/or API available to Fulcrum to access the data.

Fig. 2: Fulcrum showing data from ShipConstructor

- Fulcrum must process the data retrieved from ShipConstructor and produce a neutral XML file containing the relevant information from ShipConstructor.

Fig. 3: Sample XML neutral file

- For ShipWeight, the software must be able to interpret and consume the information in the neutral file produced by Fulcrum and execute additions, changes and deletions.

Fig. 4: ShipWeight XML import

8. Conclusion

While 3D CAD import may not be trivial, it offers significant benefits making it definitely worth harvesting weight data from CAD models to support the weight control process. One must consider the challenges and strive to find the best and most efficient way of doing it, which may involve not only software tools, but also a cultural and technical evolution of the corporate business process.

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An Optimisation Methodology for Ship Structural Design using CAD/FEM Integration

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Abstract

In ship structural design, scantling optimisation using mathematical algorithms is not yet largely implemented in industry. Optimisation with mathematical algorithms can be very helpful to find the best solution (minimum weight, minimum cost, maximum inertia, etc.). Typically, finite element analysis (FEA) tools are used in ship structural assessment. But, to build a FEM model from a CAD one is not easy. It needs a big amount of manual work. In the present work, an innovative optimisation workflow was developed. The following steps are carried automatically without any manual intervention. First, from the 3D CAD model, an idealized CAD model is created by the idealization module to take into account the FEM needs. Then, the idealized CAD model is transferred to the FEM tool. After that, the FEM model is meshed and loaded. After FEM solving, the results (stress, displacement, volume etc.) are transferred to the optimiser. The optimiser evaluates the values of the objective function and the constraints previously defined and modify the design variables (plate thickness and the stiffener scantling) to create a new structural model. After several iterations, the optimum solution is evaluated.

1. Introduction

The optimisation process developed on the present work is presented on the following steps, Fig.1. The 3D CAD model is transferred from the CAD software to the idealization module. The idealization module will generate a simplified geometry which belongs to the FEM needs and then the idealized CAD model is transferred to the FEM tool to create a meshed and loaded structural model. After solving, the results (stress, displacement, volume etc.) are transferred to the optimiser.

Fig. 1: Optimisation workflow

The optimiser evaluates the values of the objective function and the constraints previously defined and modify the design variables (plate thickness and the stiffener scantling) to create a new structural model. After FEM solving, the results (stress, displacement, volume etc) are transferred again to the optimiser.

AVEVA Marine, Bohm (2010), Doig et al. (2009), Doig and Bohm (2010), and FORAN are used as CAD software. An idealized geometry is created and transferred to ANSYS (FEA tool) to build the FEM model. For the optimisation process, modeFRONTIER is used. This platform has a full library of algorithms for both single and multi-objective optimisation and allows easy coupling to ANSYS. As a case study, the scantling optimisation is performed for a typical deck structure for local optimisation. Structural and geometrical requirements are imposed.

2. Description of the case study: Deck structure

The model studied is a deck structure shown in Fig.2. The structure is constituted by deck plate, longitudinal girders, transversal frames, longitudinal stiffeners and two longitudinal walls connected to the deck structure. The boundary conditions are presented in Fig.2. A lateral pressure of 0.2 MPa is applied on the deck. The initial scantlings are defined in Table I. The Young's modulus $E = 2.060 \cdot 10^5$ MPa and the Poisson ratio is 0.33.

Table I: Initial geometry

Element	[mm]	Element	[mm]
Longitudinal girders: flange width	300	Transversal frames: flange thickness	10
Longitudinal girders: web height	600	Transversal frames: web thickness	5
Longitudinal girders: flange thickness	10	Deck thickness	10
Longitudinal girders: web thickness	5	Longitudinal wall thickness	10
Transversal frames: flange width	180	Deck stiffener	Hp160x9
Transversal frames: web height	300	Longitudinal wall stiffener	Hp180x8

Fig. 1: Deck structure (boundary conditions)

Fig.3 shows the meshed structure. Plate, girders and frames are modelled with shell elements. The longitudinal stiffeners are modelled with beam elements.

Fig. 2: Mesh

The following design variables are considered:

- Plate thickness
- Longitudinal girders: web height and thickness, flange breath and thickness
- Transversal frames: web height and thickness, flange breath and thickness
- Longitudinal stiffeners profile: web height and thickness, flange breath and thickness
- Number of stiffeners between girders

Maximum and minimum dimensions allowed are presented in Table II. The values of plate thicknesses and stiffeners profiles are taken from catalogues.

Table II: Design variable limits

	Min (mm)	Max (mm)
Longitudinal girders: flange width	50	500
Longitudinal girders: web height	200	1000
Longitudinal girders: flange thickness	5	40
Longitudinal girders: web thickness	5	40
Transversal frames: flange width	50	500
Transversal frames: web height	200	1000
Transversal frames: flange thickness	5	40
Transversal frames: web thickness	5	40
Deck thickness	5	40
Longitudinal wall thickness	5	40
Number Deck stiffener between girders	5	15
Deck stiffener	Hp60x4	Hp430x17
Longitudinal wall stiffener	Hp60x4	Hp430x17

The volume of the structure is defined as the objective function to minimize. As a constraint, the maximum stress is imposed to be less than 235 MPa. Some geometrical constraints are imposed:

- Web thickness of frames less than the double of the plate thickness
- Web thickness of stiffeners less than the double of the plate thickness
- the plate thickness less than the double of web thickness of stiffeners
- Web height of the frames greater than the web height of stiffeners

Optimisation results are presented in Figs. 4 and 5. We can see the variation of the objective function and maximum Von Mises stress. The optimum is reached on the 210th iteration. The minimum value of the weight is 83661.9 kg. The Von Mises stress at this iteration is 220.4 MPa.

Fig. 3: Total weight variation

Fig. 4: Maximum stress variation

For a comparison, additional to the initial design, the results of other iterations are plotted. On the iteration 279, we have the minimum value of the weight 79589.2 kg. This value is lower than optimum solution but even if the level of the maximum stress here is lower than the limit (226.2MPa) but one geometrical constraint (Web thickness of stiffeners less than the double of the plate thickness) is not respected, see Fig.6. So, this solution is not feasible.

On iteration 16, the weight becomes maximum. The plate thickness (39 mm), the number (14) and dimensions (hp430x20) of deck longitudinal stiffeners are maximum compared to the other iterations, Figs.7 and 8. Iterations 23 and 179 give the designs with the minimum and maximum level of stress. Table III, in addition to the initial design, gives the values of the design variables on iterations 16, 23, 176, 179 and the optimum 210.

Fig. 5: Web thickness of stiffeners minus the double of the plate thickness

Table III: Optimisation results

	Init. Geom.	16	23	176	179	210
Deck stiffener web height	180.0	430.0	320.0	80.0	80.0	80.0
Deck stiffener web thickness	11.5	20.0	13.0	7.0	6.0	6.0
Deck plate thickness	22.0	39.0	19.0	9.0	7.0	9.0
number of Deck stiffeners between girders	5.0	14.0	9.0	11.0	13.0	11.0
Frame web height	345.0	275.0	305.0	390.0	325.0	335.0
Frame web thickness	17.0	18.0	36.0	18.0	17.0	17.0
Frame flange width	375.0	165.0	275.0	225.0	210.0	225.0
Frame flange thickness	11.0	33.0	27.0	31.0	33.0	30.0
Girder web height	440.0	205.0	760.0	945.0	860.0	855.0
Girder web thickness	34.0	34.0	26.0	11.0	10.0	11.0
Girder flange width	255.0	125.0	445.0	495.0	500.0	480.0
Girder flange thickness	14.0	8.0	25.0	18.0	20.0	19.0
long bulkhead stiffeners web height	280.0	180.0	320.0	200.0	180.0	200.0
long bulkhead stiffeners web thickness	10.5	11.5	11.5	12.0	11.5	11.0
long bulkhead plate thickness	14.0	15.0	27.0	10.0	12.0	8.0
Constraint: TW -2*TP =	-27.0	-60.0	-2.0	0.0	3.0	-1.0
Constraint: MaxStress	430.1	231.4	140.0	555.2	226.2	220.4
TotalWeight	148808.3	359144.5	205599.6	88160.5	79589.2	83661.9

Fig. 6: Number of stiffeners between girders

Fig. 7: Deck plate thickness variation

3. Conclusions

In the present work, the challenge was to develop an innovative structural optimisation workflow. From a 3D CAD model, a FEM model can be created automatically and the FEM results can be used by an optimisation algorithm to evaluate an optimum solution. Much effort was spent on performing a correct connection between the different modules included on the developed optimisation workflow. The case study presented is simple. The goal was to test the optimisation workflow. A remaining work is to improve the optimisation process by adding more structural constraints (fatigue, buckling, vibration...) and considering other or additional objective functions (minimum cost, maximum inertia, ...) to get a realistic and feasible optimum solution.

Acknowledgements

The present work has been done in the framework of the European Project BESST "Breakthrough in European Ship and Shipbuilding Technologies". The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement n° 233980.

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